

Monolix

Product Documentation

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1 Introduction to Monolix

Monolix is a **cutting-edge, user-friendly** solution for **non-linear mixed effects modeling (NLME)** in pharmacometrics. Powered by the SAEM algorithm, it ensures robust and reliable convergence, even for complex PK/PD models with dense or sparse, continuous or non-continuous data. Widely adopted across academia, the pharmaceutical industry, and regulatory agencies, Monolix supports modeling needs from preclinical research to clinical development and systems pharmacology.

The Monolix streamlines the entire modeling process, from exploratory analysis to regulatory submission. Analyses performed with Monolix are accepted by agencies such as the EMA and FDA, which hold licenses for the software. As detailed in the documentation it ensures quality control, reproducibility and consistency of the analysis.

warfarinPK_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

Tasks

POPULATION P... EBES CONDITIONAL ... STANDARD E... LIKELIHOOD PLOTS RUN

Use linearization method

Observation model $f(x)$

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

Individual model $f(x)$

Add covariate: CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	age	sex	wt
		Select: All None	#1			
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

This documentation is for Monolix starting from 2018 version. For documentation of previous versions, please check Legacy Documentation.

1.1 Why should you use Monolix?

1.1.1 What does Monolix offer?

1.1.1.1 User-friendly interface

Designed for ease of use with a modern, user-friendly graphical interface. Simple and intuitive workflow means less programming for you and more focus on exploring models and pharmacology.

1.1.1.2 Advanced statistical methodologies

Lixoft, in collaboration with Inria, pioneered the implementation of the SAEM algorithm. Reliable convergence for all types of data and innovative automatic model building tools are a centerpiece in population modeling provided by Monolix.

1.1.1.3 Interactive diagnostic plots

Automatic generation of a full set of diagnostic plots gives immediate feedback, while the interactive features assure to make the most of the analysis. In only a few clicks you create the VPC, split it by any patient subgroup, adjust axis settings, and export it to a report.

1.1.1.4 R API to automate your workflows

Applications of MonolixSuite can be controlled with an API: the R package *lixoftConnectors*. This package offers functions that allow users to script all the actions that can be performed via the graphical user interface.

1.1.1.5 Increased productivity and quality

Efficient C++ solver package, standardized model language Mlxtran, built-in model libraries, integrated automatic tools and interoperability across other applications in the Suite all contribute to better productivity and quality of the results.

1.1.1.6 Integration with NCA and simulations

Monolix is part of the MonolixSuite. Fully interoperable applications give you a complete modeling and simulation workflow from data visualization and non-compartmental analysis to population modeling and simulations. Intuitive, effective, and offering the most advanced calculation capabilities.

1.1.2 Why should I use it?

1.1.2.1 Less time on programming, more time for the science

Spend less time on programming and more time to explore models and results thanks to a user-friendly environment with a modern graphical interface design, intuitive workflow, clear display of settings and results, and interactive data visualization.

1.1.2.2 Develop and optimize your models faster

Use built-in libraries with more than 30 thousand editable models, automatic algorithms for initialization, advanced model building tools, and a full set of interactive diagnostic tools.

1.1.2.3 Get a reliable convergence

Reliable convergence for all types of data, sparse data sets, and complex models thanks to the innovative implementation of the SAEM algorithm.

1.1.3 Who is the team behind Monolix

Monolix is a product of Simulations Plus and it is developed by the Clinical Pharmacology and Pharamcometrics software team. We are doctors, scientists and developers eager to deliver the most advanced methods and models to fasten the drug development process. Check our news to meet us at the next webinar, training or conference 😊 .

1.2 The Monolix Workflow

1.2.1 The modeling and estimation workflow

1. **Set the data**

2. Explore the data with interactive plots
3. **Set the model**
 - a. Setting the structural model
 - b. Setting the initial values
 - c. Setting the statistical model
4. **Run estimation tasks** (population and individual parameters, conditional distribution, standard errors and likelihood)

In the following steps, compare models and **track runs** in Sycomore

5. **Optimize the structural model** with diagnostic plots, and the obtained standard errors and likelihood
6. **Optimize the statistical model**
 - manually with diagnostic plots and statistical tests
 - or with model building automated tools
7. **Generate a report**

and potentially

- Extend the study to a new dataset using a joint model (for example PD observation)
- Use the best model to perform simulations in Simulx

2 Data

On the following pages you can find information about loading and manipulating a data set in Monolix:

2.1 Data overview

To load a dataset in Monolix, follow these steps:

1. Create a new project and [load the data set file](#)
 - a. **Dataset that needs formatting:** If needed, [format your data](#) first by selecting 'Browse' under '**Format data**' to use the data formatting module which allows you to:
 - to handle several header lines
 - merge several observation columns into one
 - add censoring information based on tags in the observation column
 - add treatment information manually or from external files
 - add more columns such as covariates from an external file
 - b. **Already formatted dataset:** If the data is already in the right format, load it directly by selecting 'Browse' under '**Data file**'

 If the dataset does not follow a formatting rule, the dataset will not be accepted, but errors will guide you to find what is missing and could be added by data formatting.

2. [Column tagging](#) : tag the columns not recognized automatically to indicate their type and click on ACCEPT.
3. [Specifying observation types](#): specify if the observation is of type continuous, count/categorical or event.
4. [Filters](#): If needed, filter your dataset to use only part of it in the Filters tab
5. [Explore](#): The interpreted dataset is displayed in Data, and Plots and covariate statistics are generated.

To use a dataset from a PKanalix project, or to use simulations from a Simulx project, you can directly import or export the PKanalix/Simulx project which will automatically define the dataset in the Data tab.

2.2 Loading a data set

2.2.1 Providing a data set

To start a new project, after clicking on the “New project” option, you need to provide a data set by loading a file in the Data tab.

 Supported file types include .txt, .csv, and .tsv files. Starting with version 2024, Excel and SAS files (.xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat, and .xpt files) are supported as well.

There are two options available:

The option “Data file” (in purple) can be used if the data set follows the standard MonolixSuite format. This format is the same across all of the MonolixSuite applications. Briefly:

- Each line corresponds to one individual and one time point.
- Each line can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount, or both a measurement and a dose amount. Multiple types of observations are all specified in the same column and identified by a separate occasion or observation id column.
- Dosing information should be indicated for each individual, even if it is identical for all individuals.

If your data set is not already in this format, you can use the “Format data” (in green) option to transform it. The data formatting module allows adding information on dose amounts, limits of quantification, or removing excess header lines, for example.

More information about the two options can be found on these pages:

2.2.2 Data set load times

Starting with the 2024 version, project load times can be improved, especially for projects with large data sets, by saving the data as a binary file. This option is available in Settings>Preferences and will save a copy of the data file in binary format in the results folder. When reloading a project, the data set will be read from the binary file, which is faster. If the original dataset file has been modified (compared to the binary), a warning message appears, the binary dataset is not used and the original dataset file will be loaded instead.

2.2.3 Data format

In Monolix, a dataset should be loaded in the Data tab to create a project. To be accepted in the Data tab, the dataset should be in a specific format described below. If your dataset is not in the right format, in most cases, it is possible to format it in a few steps in the data formatting tab, to incorporate the missing information. Once the dataset is accepted and once a model is loaded, it is possible to filter the dataset to remove outliers or focus on a particular group. The data set format used in Monolix is the same as for the entire MonolixSuite, to allow smooth transitions between applications. In this format:

- Each line corresponds to one individual and one time point.

- Each line can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount (or both a measurement and a dose amount).
- Dosing information should be indicated for each individual in a specific column, even if it is the same treatment for all individuals.
- Headers are free but there can be only one header line.
- Different types of information (dose, observation, covariate, etc) are recorded in different columns, which must be tagged with a column type (see below).

The column types are very similar and compatible with the structure used by the *NONMEM* software (the differences are listed [here](#)). This is specified when the user defines each column type in the data set as in the following picture.

Data file

...21R2/demos/1.creating_and_using_models/1.1.libraries_of_models/data/theophylline_data.txt

Data information

CONC

Add. covariates

	ID	AMOUNT	TIME	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
LINE NUMBER	ID	AMT	TIME	CONC	WEIGHT	SEX
1	1				79.6	M
2	1	4.02	0		79.6	M
3	1		0.25	2.84	79.6	M
4	1		0.57	6.57	79.6	M
5	1		1.12	10.5	79.6	M
6	1		2.02	9.66	79.6	M
7	1		3.82	8.58	79.6	M
8	1		5.1	8.36	79.6	M

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 132
 << Page 1 of 3 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 132 entries - 12 individuals

Notice that Monolix often provides an initial guess of the type of the column depending on the name.

2.2.3.1 Description of all possible column types

Column-types used for all types of lines:

- **ID (mandatory)**: identifier of the individual

- **OCCASION (formerly OCC)**: identifier (index) of the occasion
- **TIME (mandatory)**: time of the dose or observation record
- **NOMINAL TIME** (from 2024 version): time at which doses and observations were expected to occur
- **DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3**: date of the dose or observation record, to be used in combination with the TIME column
- **EVENT ID (formerly EVID)**: identifier to indicate if the line is a dose-line or a response-line
- **IGNORED OBSERVATION (formerly MDV)**: identifier to ignore the OBSERVATION information of that line
- **IGNORED LINE** (from 2019 version): identifier to ignore all the informations of that line
- **CONTINUOUS COVARIATE (formerly COV)**: continuous covariates (which can take values on a continuous scale)
- **CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (formerly CAT)**: categorical covariate (which can only take a finite number of values)
- **REGRESSOR (formerly X)**: defines a regression variable, i.e a variable that can be used in the structural model (used e.g for time-varying covariates)
- **IGNORE**: ignores the information of that column for all lines

Column-types used for response-lines:

- **OBSERVATION (mandatory, formerly Y)**: records the measurement/observation for continuous, count, categorical or time-to-event data
- **OBSERVATION ID (formerly YTYPE)**: identifier for the observation type (to distinguish different types of observations, e.g PK and PD)
- **CENSORING (formerly CENS)**: marks censored data, below the lower limit or above the upper limit of quantification
- **LIMIT**: upper or lower boundary for the censoring interval in case of CENSORING column

Column-types used for dose-lines:

- **AMOUNT (mandatory, formerly AMT)**: dose amount (with version 2024 only mandatory if dataset contains STEADY STATE, ADDITIONAL DOSES, INFUSIONRATE or INFUSION DURATION columns)
- **ADMINISTRATION ID (formerly ADM)**: identifier for the type of dose (given via different routes for instance)
- **INFUSION RATE (formerly RATE)**: rate of the dose administration (used in particular for infusions)
- **INFUSION DURATION (formerly TINF)**: duration of the dose administration (used in particular for infusions)
- **ADDITIONAL DOSES (formerly ADDL)**: number of doses to add in addition to the defined dose, at intervals INTERDOSE INTERVAL
- **INTERDOSE INTERVAL (formerly II)**: interdose interval for doses added using ADDITIONAL DOSES or STEADY-STATE column types
- **STEADY STATE (formerly SS)**: marks that steady-state has been achieved, and will add a predefined number of doses before the actual dose, at interval INTERDOSE INTERVAL, in order to achieve steady-state

2.2.3.2 Order of events

There are prioritization rules in place in case of various event types occurring at the same time. The order of row numbers in the data set is not important, and same is true for the order of administration and empty/reset macros in model files. The sequence of events will always be the following:

1. regressors are updated,
2. reset done by EVID=3 or EVID=4 is performed,
3. dose is administered,
4. empty/reset done by macros is performed,
5. observation is made.

2.2.3.3 Columns used to identify subject-occasions

2.2.3.3.1 ID: subject identifier

The column is used to identify the different subjects and is mandatory. Its content is totally free (integers, double, strings...), but we recommend to use integers for better readability. The IDs will be sorted by order of appearance in the data set.

2.2.3.3.1.1 Examples

- **Example with strings:** the string '.' will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line. As a consequence a data set of the form

```
ID * *  
John * *  
John * *  
Mike * *  
. * *
```

contains 3 different subjects : 'John', 'Mike' and '.'.

- **Example with mixed IDs:** the lines corresponding to the same subject do not need to be next to each other. Thus, the following file contains 2 subjects with IDs "1" and "2".

```
ID * *  
1 * *  
1 * *  
2 * *
```

```
2 * *  
1 * *
```

2.2.3.3.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall contain one and only one column ID.
- The ID must be defined for all lines.
- The string '.' will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line

2.2.3.3.2 OCCASION (formerly OCC): occasion identifiers

<https://youtu.be/ejBb9yxzwwY>

Occasions define different periods of time within individuals. **Occasions may be (but don't have to) used to define inter-occasion (intra-patient) variability.** The MonolixSuite allows the definition of several columns with the column-type OCCASION, which can be used to define several levels of inter-occasion variability. The OCCASION columns can contain only integers (neither necessarily starting at one, nor necessarily consecutive), which represent occasion identifiers. All times points belonging to one occasion must be in one block (i.e not interrupted by time points of another occasion). When switching from one occasion to the next one, time can restart at the initial value or continue. If different occasions contain time points that overlap, a washout will automatically be added.

2.2.3.3.2.1 Examples and typical situations

- **Cross over study:** In that case, data are collected for each patient during two independent treatment periods of time, there is an overlap on the time definition of the periods (e.g both periods start at 0). A column-type OCCASION can be used used to identify the periods. See here for an example.
- **Occasions with washout (due to EVENT ID = 4):** In that case, there are no overlap between the periods. The time is increasing but the dynamical system (i.e. the compartments) is reset when the second period starts. In particular, `EVENT ID = 4` indicates that the system is reset (washout) for example, when a new dose is administrated. See here for an example.
- **Occasions with washout (due to overlapping times):** In that case, the time is increasing and the overlap between two time points of two different occasions creates a washout. If the washout is not desired, one of the two times can be offset by a small value to avoid the overlap.
- **Occasions without washout:** In that case, there are no overlap between the periods. The time is increasing and we want to differentiate periods in terms of occasions without any reset of the dynamical system. On the example defined here, multiple doses are administrated to each patient and each period of time between successive doses is defined as a different occasion via the column-type OCCASION.

Crossover with overlapping time periods <table border="1" style="font-size: small;"> <thead> <tr><th>ID</th><th>TIME</th><th>OCC</th><th>AMT</th><th>Y</th></tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>10.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>8.9</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>6.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>2</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>15.2</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>10.6</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>5.5</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	1	0	1	10	.	1	1	1	.	10.5	1	2	1	.	8.9	1	3	1	.	6.5	1	0	2	10	.	1	1	2	.	15.2	1	2	2	.	10.6	1	3	2	.	5.5	Occasions with increasing time and no washout <table border="1" style="font-size: small;"> <thead> <tr><th>ID</th><th>TIME</th><th>OCC</th><th>AMT</th><th>Y</th></tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>10.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>8.9</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>6.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>4</td><td>2</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>5</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>15.2</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>6</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>10.6</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>7</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>5.5</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	1	0	1	10	.	1	1	1	.	10.5	1	2	1	.	8.9	1	3	1	.	6.5	1	4	2	10	.	1	5	2	.	15.2	1	6	2	.	10.6	1	7	2	.	5.5	Occasions with increasing time and EVID=4 washout <table border="1" style="font-size: small;"> <thead> <tr><th>ID</th><th>TIME</th><th>OCC</th><th>AMT</th><th>Y</th><th>EVID</th></tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>10</td><td>.</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>10.5</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>8.9</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>6.5</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>4</td><td>2</td><td>10</td><td>.</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>5</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>15.2</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>6</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>10.6</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>7</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>5.5</td><td>0</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	EVID	1	0	1	10	.	1	1	1	1	.	10.5	0	1	2	1	.	8.9	0	1	3	1	.	6.5	0	1	4	2	10	.	4	1	5	2	.	15.2	0	1	6	2	.	10.6	0	1	7	2	.	5.5	0	Occasions with increasing time and washout due to time overlap <table border="1" style="font-size: small;"> <thead> <tr><th>ID</th><th>TIME</th><th>OCC</th><th>AMT</th><th>Y</th></tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>1</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>10.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>2</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>8.9</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>1</td><td>.</td><td>6.5</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>3</td><td>2</td><td>10</td><td>.</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>4</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>15.2</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>5</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>10.6</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>6</td><td>2</td><td>.</td><td>5.5</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	1	0	1	10	.	1	1	1	.	10.5	1	2	1	.	8.9	1	3	1	.	6.5	1	3	2	10	.	1	4	2	.	15.2	1	5	2	.	10.6	1	6	2	.	5.5
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1	0	1	10	.	1																																																																																																																																																																																											
1	1	1	.	10.5	0																																																																																																																																																																																											
1	2	1	.	8.9	0																																																																																																																																																																																											
1	3	1	.	6.5	0																																																																																																																																																																																											
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1	6	2	.	5.5																																																																																																																																																																																												

However, the following situation, which would aim at defining the same occasion index to all morning doses, is not allowed:

Not allowed

ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	
1	0	1	10	.	<i>morning dose</i>
1	1	1	.	10.5	
1	2	1	.	8.9	
1	12	2	20	.	<i>evening dose</i>
1	13	2	.	15.2	
1	14	2	.	10.6	
1	24	1	10	.	<i>morning dose</i>
1	23	1	.	9.5	
1	25	1	.	7.8	

2.2.3.3.2.2 How can occasions appear while no OCCASION column is defined?

Occasions are automatically created if there is an **EVENT ID** column with a value 4, which is not the first record of the individual. Within an individual, each EVENT ID = 4 will create a new occasion. The automatically created occasion column is called **OCCEvid** and will be visible in the **Statistical model & Tasks** tab in Monolix interface. The data set file itself is not modified (the OCCEvid column is internal in Monolix). The OCCEvid column is not created if an identical OCCASION column is already present. Inter-occasion variability can be considered for the automatically created OCCEvid occasions but doesn't has to.

The following data on the right has an EVID column (tagged as **EVENT ID** column-type) with a value of 4. This will automatically create an occasion column called OCCEvid. The data set on the left is thus equivalent to the data set on the right:

ID	TIME	Y	EVID
1	0	0	0
1	1	2	0
1	2	2	0
1	0	0	4
1	4	1	0
1	5	2	0

ID	TIME	Y	OCCevid
1	0	0	1
1	1	2	1
1	2	2	1
1	0	0	2
1	4	1	2
1	5	2	2

2.2.3.3.2.3 FAQ on occasions in the data set

- **Do all the individual need to share the same sequence of occasion?**
No, the number of occasions and the times defining the occasions can differ from one individual to another.
- **Do the occasion indices need to start at one for each individual?** No.
- **Do the occasion indices need to be consecutive for each individual?** No.
- **Is there any limit in terms of number of occasions?** No.
- **Is it possible to have several levels of occasions?**
Yes, it is possible to have several level of occasions (multiple occasion columns).

2.2.3.3.2.4 Format restrictions

- The OCCASION columns should contain only integers.
- If the OCCASION column-type is used, the OCCASION must be defined for all lines.

2.2.3.4 Columns used to define time

2.2.3.4.1 TIME: data time stamp

The TIME columns define the time at which dose and observation events occurred. When no DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, the time represents the time elapsed. When a DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, it represents the time of the day. **The time can be defined using a double, or a clock format hh:mm or hh:mm:ss. Negative time values are allowed.** When the double format is used, and no DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, the time has no predefined units. In all other cases, the time units are hours.

When a subject has time under the clock format, all times are converted into relative hours, as on the following example:

TIME	Reconstructed time
10:00	10
10:30	10.5
14:00	14
08:59	8.983333

When there is no column-type TIME, the column-type NOMINAL TIME is used as time, and if neither TIME nor NOMINAL TIME column-types are present, the column-type DATE is ignored, and the first column-type REGRESSOR is used as time. If no columns are tagged as REGRESSOR, time will be equal to the index of row number containing observations / amounts for each subject-occasion.

2.2.3.4.1.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with the column-type TIME.
- If the TIME column-type is used, the TIME must be defined for all lines.
- String “.” will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line and is non-compliant with formats listed here-above.

2.2.3.4.2 **NOMINAL TIME: data nominal time stamp**

The NOMINAL TIME column defines the time at which doses and observations were expected to occur. The column format is the same as the format of the TIME column and the same restrictions apply, with the exception that lines with missing values are not automatically ignored, but taken from TIME column, if it exists in the data set.

If defined, the NOMINAL TIME column:

- can be used instead of TIME column on x-axis of Observed data (Monolix/PKanalix) and Visual predictive check (Monolix) plots,
- can be used instead of TIME column in the NCA Concentrations table (PKanalix),
- is used in NCA sparse data calculations (PKanalix),
- is used in all other calculations, if TIME column is not defined (Monolix/PKanalix).

2.2.3.4.3 **DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3: date information**

The DATE column-type can be used to indicate the date of the dose or observation event. It is usually used in combination with the TIME column-type, which in that case indicates the time of the day. To accommodate the different date formats, several column types are possible:

	Format and associated date column name

	DATE	DAT1	DAT2	DAT3
Day, month and year	mm/dd/yy or mm/dd/yyyy mm-dd-yy or mm-dd-yyyy	dd/mm/yy or dd/mm/yyyy dd-mm-yy or dd-mm-yyyy	yy/mm/dd or yyyy/mm/dd yy-mm-dd or yyyy-mm-dd	yy/dd/mm or yyyy/dd/mm yy-dd-mm or yyyy-dd-mm

By default, when the year is coded with two digits, it is interpreted as 20xx.

2.2.3.4.3.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column-type DATE / DAT1 / DAT2 / DAT3.
- Year, day, and month shall be integers.
- The separator must be "/" or "-"
- Character "." will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line and is not compliant with the DATE formats.
- All the lines should be filled correctly within the same delimiter, according to the specified date format: i.e., no empty year, no empty month, no empty day, no mix of delimiters.

2.2.3.4.4 Timestamp summary

There are several ways to define the timestamp of the data set depending if there is a TIME column or not and if there is a DATE column or not.

	(NOMINAL) TIME column present	(NOMINAL) TIME column not present
DATE column present	DATE column is considered to represent the day and the TIME column the hour within this day	Date column ignored (regressor or index used)
DATE column not present	TIME column is considered to represent the time (no specific units)	First regression-column will be used to timestamp data

2.2.3.4.5 FAQ

- **My data is not "over time", what should I do?** You can arbitrarily set the time of each observation to 0.
- **What happens if neither TIME nor DATE is defined?** We strongly encourage the user to explicitly define the TIME column-type. However, if there is neither TIME nor DATE column-types, the first regression-column (i.e. first column with column-type REGRESSION) will be used to timestamp data. Moreover, if there is no TIME, no DATE and no REGRESSION column-type, time is equal to row indexes of each subject-occasion.

2.2.3.5 Columns used to define observations

2.2.3.5.1 OBSERVATION: response

The OBSERVATION column-type can be used to record continuous (PKanalix and Monolix), categorical (Monolix), count (Monolix) or time-to-event (Monolix) data. For dose lines, the content is free and will not be used. For response lines, the requirements depend on the type of data and are summarized below.

2.2.3.5.1.1 Continuous data

The value represents what has been measured (e.g concentrations) and can be any double value.

Examples

- **Basic example:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	50	.
1	0.5	.	1.1
1	1	.	9.2
1	1.5	.	8.5
1	2	.	6.3
1	2.5	.	5.5

- **Full data set for continuous data:** [theophylline data set](#), the [warfarin data set](#), and the [HIV data set](#) among others can be found [here](#).

2.2.3.5.1.2 Categorical data

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZG7LhmApb_s

In case of categorical data, the observations at each time point can only take values in a fixed and finite set of nominal categories. In the data set, the **output categories must be coded as consecutive integers**.

Examples

- **Basic example:**

ID	TIME	Y
----	------	---

```

1 0.5 3
1 1 0
1 1.5 2
1 2 2
1 2.5 3
  
```

- **Full data set for joint continuous and categorical data:** One can see the [respiratory status data set](#) and the [warfarin data set](#) for example for more practical examples on a categorical and a joint continuous and categorical data set respectively.

2.2.3.5.1.3 Count data

Count data can take only non-negative integer values that come from counting something, e.g., the number of trials required for completing a given task. The task can for instance be repeated several times and the individuals performance followed.

Count data can also represent the number of events happening in regularly spaced intervals, e.g the number of seizures every week. If the time intervals are not regular, the data may be considered as repeated time-to-event interval censored, or the interval length can be given as [regressor](#) to be used to define the probability distribution in the model.

Examples

- **Basic example:** in the data set below, 10 trials are necessary the first day (t=0), 6 the second day (t=24), etc.

```

ID TIME  Y
1  0    10
1  24    6
1  48    5
1  72    2
  
```

One can see the [epilepsy attacks data set](#) for a more practical example.

2.2.3.5.1.4 (Repeated) time-to-event data

In this case, the observations are the “**times at which events occur**”. An event may be one-off (e.g., death) or repeated (e.g., epileptic seizures, mechanical incidents, strikes). In addition, an event can be exactly observed, interval censored or right censored.

For the formatting of time-to-event data, the column TIME should contain:

- the time of an event,
- the time at which the observation period starts (required by the MonolixSuite, contrary to other tools for survival analysis. This allows to define the data set using absolute times, in addition to

durations (if the start time is zero, the records represent durations between the start time and the event).

- the end of the observation period or time intervals for interval-censoring.

The column OBSERVATION contains an integer that indicates how to interpret the associated time. The different values for each type of event and observation are summarized in the table below:

TIME	OBSERVATION (EVENT)	Exactly observed		Interval-censored	
		Single	Repeated	Single	Repeated
Start time of the observation period	0	✓	✓	✓	✓
Time of event	1	✓	✓		
Start of an interval where one or several event have occurred	0			✓	✓
End of an interval where an event has occurred	1			✓	
End of an interval where N events have occurred	N				✓
End of the observation period, with a possible event later on (right-censoring)	0	✓	✓	✓	✓

The figure below summarizes the different situations with examples:

Single events exactly observed data

One must indicate the start time of the observation period with $Y=0$, and the time of event ($Y=1$) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred ($Y=0$).

Examples

- **Basic example:** in the following dataset, the observation period lasts from starting time $t=0$ to the final time $t=80$. For individual 1, the event is observed at $t=34$, and for individual 2, no event is observed during the period. Thus it is noticed that at the final time ($t=80$), no event occurred.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	34	1
2	0	0
2	80	0

Using absolute times instead of duration, we could equivalently write:

ID	TIME	Y
1	20	0
1	54	1
2	33	0
2	113	0

The duration between start time and event (or end of the observation period) are the same as before, but this time we record the day at which the patients enter the study and the days at which they have events or leave the study. Different patients may enter the study at different times.

- **Full data sets for time-to-event data:** [PBC data set](#) and [Oropharynx data set](#)

Repeated events exactly observed data

One must indicate the start time of the observation period ($Y=0$), the end time ($Y=0$) and the time of each event ($Y=1$).

Examples

- **Basic example:** below the observation period lasts from starting time $t=0$ to the final time $t=80$. For individual 1, two events are observed at $t=34$ and $t=76$, and for individual 2, no event is observed during the period.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	34	1
1	76	1
1	80	0
2	0	0
2	80	0

Single events interval censored data

When the exact time of the event is not known, but only an interval can be given, the start time of this interval is given with $Y=0$, and the end time with $Y=1$. As before, the start time of the observation period must be given with $Y=0$.

Examples

- **Basic example:** we only know that the event has happened between $t=32$ and $t=35$.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	32	0
1	35	1

Repeated events interval censored data

In this case, we do not know the exact event times, but only the number of events that occurred for each individual in each interval of time. The column-type Y can now take integer values greater than 1, if several events occurred during an interval.

Examples

- **Basic example:** No event occurred between $t=0$ and $t=32$, 1 event occurred between $t=32$ and $t=35$, 1 between $t=35$ and $t=50$, none between $t=50$ and $t=56$, 2 between $t=56$ and $t=78$ and finally 1 between $t=78$ and $t=80$.

ID	TIME	Y
1	0	0
1	32	0
1	35	1
1	50	1
1	56	0
1	78	2

1 80 1

2.2.3.5.1.5 Warnings

- If a subject or a subject-occasion has no observations, a warning message arises telling which subjects or subjects-occasions have no measurements and will be ignored.

2.2.3.5.1.6 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type OBSERVATION. Multiple observation types need to be distinguished with the OBSERVATION ID column.
- If **EVENT ID** = 1, 3 or 4, the content of the OBSERVATION column is free and ignored.
- If **EVENT ID** = 0, and **IGNORED OBSERVATION** = 1 or 2, the content of the OBSERVATION column is free and ignored.
- If **EVENT ID** = 0 and **IGNORED OBSERVATION** = 0, the content of the OBSERVATION column has to be a double (dots '.' are not allowed).
- If the **EVENT ID** column is absent (and whatever the **IGNORED OBSERVATION** column is), the content is free. Values that are not doubles (for instance dots '.' or strings) are ignored.

2.2.3.5.2 OBSERVATION ID: response identifier

The OBSERVATION ID column permits to distinguish several types of observations (several concentrations, effects, etc). The OBSERVATION ID column assigns an identifier to each observation of the OBSERVATION column. Those identifiers are used to map the observations of the data set to the outputs of the model (in the OUTPUT block of the model file). The dot "." is not considered as a repetition of the previous line but as a different identifier.

There can be more OBSERVATION ID values than there are outputs in the model file. In that case only the observations corresponding to the first identifiers(s) in alphabetical order will be used (example below).

For continuous data, in the Monolix graphical user interface, the data viewer and the plots, the observations will be called yX with X corresponding to the identifier given in the OBSERVATION ID column (for instance y1 and y2 if identifiers 1 and 2 were used in the OBSERVATION ID column).

2.2.3.5.2.1 Examples

- **Basic example with integers:** with the following data set

TIME	AMT	OBS	YTYPE
0	.	12	1
5	.	6	2
10	.	4	1

```
15 . 3 2
```

and the following output block

```
OUTPUT:  
output = {Cc, R}
```

the observations "12" and "4" which have identifier "1" will be matched to the output "Cc", while observations "6" and "3" with identifier "2" will be matched to "R".

- **Basic example with strings** (not recommended): with the following data set

```
TIME AMT OBS YTYPE  
0 . 12 PK  
5 . 6 PK  
10 . 4 PD  
15 . 3 PD
```

and the following OUTPUT block in the Mlxtran model file:

```
OUTPUT:  
output = {Cc, R}
```

the observations tagged with "PD" will be mapped to the first output "Cc" (which is probably not what is desired), and those tagged with "PK" will be mapped to the second output "R", because in alphabetical order "PD" comes before "PK".

- **Basic example with more OBSERVATION ID values than model outputs:** with the following data set

```
TIME AMT OBS YTYPE  
0 . 12 1  
5 . 6 2  
10 . 4 1  
15 . 3 2
```

and the following output block

```
OUTPUT:  
output = {Cc}
```

the observations tagged with identifier “1” will be mapped to the model output “Cc” and the observations tagged with “2” will be ignored. If the user wants to use only the data tagged with “2”, he can add an **IGNORED OBSERVATION** column which ignores all observations with identifier “1” (see below).

- **Basic example with more OBSERVATION ID values than model outputs and an IGNORED OBSERVATION column:** with the following data set

TIME	AMT	OBS	YTYPE	MDV
0	.	12	1	1
5	.	6	2	0
10	.	4	1	1
15	.	3	2	0

and the following output block

```
OUTPUT:  
output = {Cc}
```

the observations tagged with identifier “1” will all be ignored (due to the MDV column tagged as **IGNORED OBSERVATION**) and the observations with identifier “2” will be mapped to the model output “Cc”.

- **Full data set example:** [warfarin](#) PKPD data set, [PSA and survival](#) data set

2.2.3.5.2.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- The content of the OBSERVATION ID column can be strings or integers.
- The dot “.” is not considered as a repetition of the previous line but as a different identifier.

2.2.3.5.3 CENSORING: censored observation

The CENSORING column permits to mark censored data. When an observation is marked as censored, the (upper or lower) limit of quantification is given in the OBSERVATION column (not in a separate column).

- CENSORING = 1 means that the value in OBSERVATION column is a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ). The true observation y verifies $y < \text{LLOQ}$.
- CENSORING = 0 means the value in response-column corresponds to a valid observation (no interval associated).
- CENSORING = -1 means that the value in OBSERVATION column is an upper limit of quantification (ULOQ). The true observation y verifies $y > \text{ULOQ}$.

The mathematical handling of censored data is described here.

2.2.3.5.3.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type CENSORING.
- For dose lines, the content is free and will be ignored.
- For response lines, there are only four possible values : -1, 0, 1 and '.' (interpreted as 0).

2.2.3.5.4 LIMIT: limit for censored values

When the column LIMIT contains a numeric value and CENSORING is different from 0, the value in the LIMIT column is interpreted as the second bound of the interval. Writing jobs the value in the OBSERVATION column and ylimit the value in the LIMIT column, the true observation y verifies $y \in [y_{\text{limit}}, y_{\text{obs}}]$. When LIMIT = '.', the value is interpreted as -infinity or +infinity depending on the value of CENSORING (1 or -1 respectively) as if the LIMIT column would not be present.

2.2.3.5.4.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type LIMIT.
- A data set shall not contain any column with column-type LIMIT if no column with column-type CENSORING is present.
- Allowed values are doubles and dot '.', and strings are not allowed (even when CENSORING = 0).

2.2.3.5.4.2 Example with CENSORING and LIMIT

It is possible to have both censoring type on the same individual, i.e. both upper or lower limit of quantification. It is possible to have measurements with and without bounds. The example below gives an overview of the possible combinations:

ID	TIME	Y	CENS	LIMIT	
1	0	3.3	0	.	$y = 3.3$ (and value in LIMIT not read)
1	1	0.1	1	0	$0 < y < 0.1$
1	2	0	1	0.1	$0 < y < 0.1$ + warning because opposite order given
1	3	0.1	1	.	$-\text{inf} < y < 0.1$
1	4	100	-1	1000	$100 < y < 1000$
1	5	1000	-1	100	$100 < y < 1000$ + warning because opposite order given
1	6	100	-1	.	$100 < y < +\text{inf}$

2.2.3.6 Columns used to define doses

2.2.3.6.1 AMOUNT: dose amount

The AMOUNT column records the amount of the administrated doses. For dose-lines, the value must be a double. For response-lines, the content is free.

2.2.3.6.1.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** the individual 1 receives a dose of 10 at time 0

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	10	.
1	1	.	6
1	2	.	4

- **Example with a single dose split into two routes of absorption:** a single dose may be absorbed at different sites, leading to several absorption route. This can be taken into account by splitting the dose into several fractions, directed to several absorption macros. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	10	.
1	1	.	6
1	2	.	4

and the following PK block in the model file:

```
PK:  
oral(ka=ka1, p=F)  
oral(ka=ka2, Tlag, p=1-F)
```

a fraction F of the dose is absorbed via a first-order process with rate constant ka_1 , and a fraction $1-F$ is absorbed with a absorption constant ka_2 after a lag time $Tlag$.

2.2.3.6.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column-type AMOUNT.
- For dose-lines with EVENT ID = 1, 3 or 4, the value must be a double.
- For lines without EVENT ID, the value must be a double or a dot '.'

2.2.3.6.2 ADMINISTRATION ID: administration identifier

The ADMINISTRATION ID column permits to distinguish different types of administrations, for instance oral administrations and intravenous administrations. The content of the ADMINISTRATION ID column is used for dose-line only and must be a positive integer. This integer works like a flag, which can be used in the model file to link the dose information of the data set to a specific administration route in the model.

2.2.3.6.2.1 Examples

- **Example with oral and iv administrations:** For instance, with the following data set:

```
ID  TIME  AMT  ADM  Y
John 0    10   1    .
Eric 0    20   2    .
Jean 0    10   3    .
```

and the following **PK block** in the Mlxtran model file:

```
PK:
iv(adm=1)
oral(adm=2, ka)
```

the subject John will receive a dose of 10 via a bolus iv, while subject Eric will receive a dose of 20 orally with first-order rate constant ka. The identifier in the ADMINISTRATION ID column should match the "adm=" field of the **administration macros**. A same subject can receive some doses via one route and other doses via another route. The administration type with id '3' is not used in the model, thus all doses with this id will not be applied.

The default value for administration types is 1. This means that if there is no column ADMINISTRATION ID in the dataset, all doses will be associated to the administration id 1. If the dataset contains a column ADMINISTRATION ID but the structural model does not include arguments *adm* to indicate how to apply the different types of doses, only the doses with administration id '1' in the data set will be used.

2.2.3.6.2.2 Format restrictions

- For dose-lines, the column shall contain only positive integers. For response-lines, dots '.' or integers are allowed.
- A data set shall not contain more than one ADMINISTRATION ID column-type.

2.2.3.6.3 INFUSION RATE and INFUSION DURATION: rate and duration of infusion

These columns enable to define the rate (INFUSION RATE column-type) or duration (INFUSION DURATION column-type) of doses administered as infusions. The column content is meaningful only for dose-lines. The rate and duration information is transferred to the model via the use of the **iv macro**, **depot macro** or **pkmodel macro**. If a RATE is defined, the duration of the infusion will be AMOUNT/RATE. If a DURATION is defined, the rate will be AMOUNT/DURATION. The units must be coherent with the units of the AMOUNT and TIME columns. A dose-lines, if a negative value, or dot '.' or 0 is used, the infusion will be replaced by a bolus.

We strongly recommend to have small duration values (less than 10). Indeed, if the duration is too long, the calculation of the analytical solution of the model may produce NaN. Two workarounds are possible:

- Either rescale the time units to have smaller duration values.
- Use ODEs instead of analytical solutions. ODEs can be enforced with `useAnalyticalSolution = no` in the model file.

2.2.3.6.3.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** with the following data set, assuming the TIME units are minutes and AMOUNT units mg, an amount of 10 mg will be applied via an infusion over 5 minutes starting at time 0. This is equivalent to a RATE of 2 mg/minute. The 20 mg doses at time 2, 3, and 4 minutes are applied via a bolus.

ID	TIME	AMT	TINF	Y
1	0	10	5	.
1	1	.	.	6
1	2	20	0	.
1	3	20	-2	.
1	4	20	.	.

2.2.3.6.3.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION.
- A negative value, "." or 0 means a bolus dose, without any infusion rate or time.
- For dose-lines, the value must be a double, or a dot '.'.
- For response lines, the content is free.

2.2.3.6.4 STEADY STATE and INTERDOSE INTERVAL: steady-state and inter-dose interval

Steady-state is used to specify that any transitory effect is over and that the system response is now a periodic function of doses. In practice, a fixed number of doses (by default 5) is added before the dose entered with the STEADY STATE flag (so 6 doses in total, by default). The period between doses is set to the INTERDOSE INTERVAL. The number of doses to add can be changed when loading the data and will be saved in the project file. The number of added doses may be reduced compared to the specified value if the doses to add would interfere with another dose or observation: any steady-state dose that would be added before (i.e. earlier in time) a dose or response line is not added, even if the line information is ignored (for instance with EVENT ID = 2 or IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1).

The allowed values are the following:

- STEADY-STATE = 0 or '': no steady-state, the dose is a normal dose.
- STEADY-STATE = 1 : the system has achieved steady-state. A washout (i.e reset to the initial values of the model) is applied before the first added dose.
- STEADY-STATE = 2 or 3 : the system has achieved steady-state. Unlike STEADY-STATE = 1, no washout is added.

STEADY-STATE and EVENT ID: when STEADY-STATE = 1 is used on the same line as EVENT ID = 3 or 4, a washout is applied just before the first dose added for steady-state (because of STEADY-STATE = 1) and also just before the dose defined on that line (because of EVENT ID = 3 or 4). When STEADY-STATE = 2 or 3 is used on the same line as EVENT ID = 3 or 4, a washout is added just before the dose defined on that line.

2.2.3.6.4.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** On the following example:

ID	TIME	AMT	SS	II	Y
1	0	10	1	2	.

5 doses are applied, at times -10, -8, -6, -4, -2 in addition to the dose at time = 0. The above data set is thus equivalent to:

ID	TIME	AMT	SS	II	Y
1	-10	10	0	0	.
1	-8	10	0	0	.
1	-6	10	0	0	.
1	-4	10	0	0	.
1	-2	10	0	0	.
1	0	10	0	0	.

The first added dose will have a wash-out.

- **Example with informations colliding with doses to add:** The following data set, with a normal dose at $t=0$ and a steady-state dose at $t=10$ with an interdose-interval of 3.5 will lead to the following situation:

Even if 5 additional doses are specified in the GUI when loading the data, there will be only 2 additional doses as otherwise the previous measurements would be interfered with. In addition, there is a washout (highlighted in purple) just before the first added dose. If we would replace SS=1 by SS=2 on line 5, we would again have only 2 doses added but no wash out as can be seen in the following figure:

- **Typical example with pre-dose PK measurement, dose at site and post-dose PK measurements:** the subject takes regularly doses at home. During a hospital visit, he gets a pre-dose PK measurement, a dose at site, and one or several post-dose PK measurements. The STEADY-STATE statement cannot be applied on the dose administered at site, as the doses to add would interfere with the pre-dose PK measurement. We thus need to write:

1	0	10	1	24	.	; steady-state statement
1	23.9	.	.	.	5.5	; pre-dose measurement
1	24	10	.	.	.	; dose at site
1	25	.	.	.	9.9	; post-dose measurement

2.2.3.6.4.2 FAQ

- **Can I define two different STEADY-STATE lines for morning and evening doses?** No, as the doses to add would collide with each other. You will have to use an ADDITIONAL DOSES column instead.

2.2.3.6.4.3 Format restrictions (STEADY STATE)

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type STEADY STATE.
- If there is a column-type STEADY STATE, there should be a column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- Accepted values (for all lines, including response-lines): 0, 1, 2, 3 or dot '.'

2.2.3.6.4.4 Format restrictions (INTERDOSE-INTERVAL)

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- If there is a column-type STEADY STATE, there should be a column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- Accepted values:
 - on response-line: 0 or '.' (non-zero double value will generate a warning)
 - on normal dose-line (no STEADY-STATE or ADDITIONAL DOSE): 0 or '.' (non-zero double value will generate a warning)
 - on STEADY-STATE or ADDITIONAL DOSE line: non-zero double value
- Clock format is not accepted

2.2.3.6.5 ADDITIONAL DOSES: additional dose line

The ADDITIONAL DOSES column is a useful shortcut to specify dose regimens with repetitive treatments. The value in ADDITIONAL DOSES is the number of times the dose shall be repeated (in addition to the dose defined on that line) and column INTERDOSE INTERVAL contains the dose repetition interval. Doses that would be added after the last measurement are useless and will thus not be added.

2.2.3.6.5.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** For instance to specify a dose of 10 every 12 hours during 3 days it is possible to write:

```
ID TIME AMT
Tom  0  10
Tom 12  10
Tom 24  10
Tom 36  10
Tom 48  10
Tom 60  10
```

```
Tom 72 10
```

but ADDITIONAL DOSES (ADDL) and INTERDOSE INTERVAL (II) can also be used to specify the same information in a single line

```
ID TIME AMT ADDL II
Tom 0 10 6 12
```

2.2.3.6.5.2 Format restrictions

- When there is an ADDL column there must be an INTERDOSE INTERVAL (interdose interval) column to indicate the inter dose timing.
- For dose-lines with ADDL strictly positive, the INTERDOSE INTERVAL value must be strictly positive.
- Accepted values:
 - on normal dose lines: 0 or ''
 - on response lines: 0 or ''
 - on lines where ADDITIONAL DOSES is needed: positive integer

2.2.3.7 Columns used to define covariates

2.2.3.7.1 CONTINUOUS COVARIATE: continuous covariate

The column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE is used to tag continuous covariates, i.e covariates which can take values on a continuous scale (such as weight or age). Covariates tagged in the data set can (but don't have to) be used as covariates in the model. The covariate value must be constant within subjects (or within occasions if occasions are present). If the value is not constant, the first value of each subject in time ordering will be used for all times (and a warning is generated). To define time varying covariate, use REGRESSORS.

The allowed values are doubles or dot '.'. There must be at least one non-dot value per subject (or per occasion if occasions are defined).

2.2.3.7.1.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** in the following data set, individual 1 has weight WT = 78, individual 2 has WT = 80 for all times points (first value in time ordering) and individual 3 has WT = 90.

```
ID TIME Y WT
1 0 5.7 78
```

1	1	5.6	78
2	0	6.7	80
2	1	6.5	82
3	0	7.8	.
3	1	8.9	90

2.2.3.7.1.2 Format restrictions

- Continuous covariate columns shall contain either a double or “.”.
- The covariate must be defined at least once per subject-occasion.
- The covariate must remain the same for all the lines within the same subject-occasion.

2.2.3.7.2 CATEGORICAL COVARIATE: categorical covariate

The column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE is used to tag categorical covariates, i.e covariates which can only take a finite number of values (such as sex or a genotype). Covariates tagged in the data set can (but don't have to) be used as covariates in the model. The covariate value must be constant within subjects (or within occasions if occasions are present). If the value is not constant, the first value of each subject in time ordering will be used for all times (and a warning is generated). To define time varying covariate, use REGRESSORS.

The allowed values are strings, doubles or dot ‘.’. There must be at least one non-dot value per subject (or per occasion if occasions are defined), otherwise the category is considered to be ‘NA’.

2.2.3.7.2.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** in the following data set, the covariate SEX has two categories ‘F’ and ‘M’ and the individual 3 has value ‘F’. The covariate GENO has three categories ‘1’, ‘2’ and ‘NA’ (coming from the individual 3 which has no valid value). The covariate RACE has only one category ‘1’. Individual 1 has RACE = 1, as this is the value defined first in time. RACE will not appear in the graphical user interface because it is not possible to use a covariate with only one category in a model.

ID	TIME	Y	SEX	GENO	RACE
1	0	5.7	F	1	1
1	1	5.6	F	1	2
2	0	6.7	M	2	1
2	1	6.5	M	2	1
3	0	7.8	.	.	1
3	1	8.9	F	.	1

2.2.3.7.2.2 Format restrictions

- The covariate must be defined at least once per subject-occasion.
- The categorical covariate must be the same for all the lines with the same subject-occasion.

2.2.3.8 Columns used to define regressors

2.2.3.8.1 REGRESSOR: regression value

REGRESSOR columns define variables (possibly time-varying) that will be available for calculations in the structural model after regressor definition. Regressors can for instance be used to take into account time-varying covariates (example here), or tag the columns corresponding to individual PK parameters in a sequential PKPD modeling approach. Regressors can also be used, instead of time, on x-axis of the Observed data and VPC plots.

Allowed values in the REGRESSOR column are doubles and dot '.' (to indicate missing values). For the first record (observation or dose line) of each subject (or subject-occasion if occasions are present), the regressor value cannot be missing (no dot '.' allowed). For the following missing values, the interpolation will be done using the setting chosen in the GUI, which can be "**Last Carried Forward**" or "**linear interpolation**". Regressor values on observation or dose lines are used the same way, as well as regressor values on lines with no observation and no dose.

- **last carried forward:** if we have defined in the dataset two times for each individual with (reg_A) at time (t_A) and (reg_B) at time (t_B)
 - for (t ≤ t_A), (reg(t)=reg_A) [first defined value is used]
 - for (t_A ≤ t < t_B), (reg(t)=reg_A) [previous value is used]
 - for (t ≥ t_B), (reg(t)=reg_B) [previous value is used]
- **linear interpolation:** the interpolation is:
 - for (t ≤ t_A), (reg(t)=reg_A) [first defined value is used]
 - for (t_A ≤ t < t_B), (reg(t)=reg_A+(t-t_A)frac{(reg_B-reg_A)}{(t_B-t_A)}) [linear interpolation is used]
 - for (t ≥ t_B), (reg(t)=reg_B) [previous value is used]

LINE NUMBER	SUBJ	TIME	DV	WT	SEX	AGE	REGRESSOR
2	1	0	98	66.7	1	50	
3	1	24	49	66.7	1	50	9
4	1	36	32	66.7	1	50	7
5	1	48	26	66.7	1	50	6
6	1	72	22	66.7	1	50	4

Several columns can be tagged as REGRESSOR. In that case, **the mapping with the regressors defined in the model is done by name if possible, otherwise by order**: the first column tagged as REGRESSOR in the data set is mapped to the first element in the model input list defined as regressor.

If within a subject (or subject-occasion if occasions are present) two events are defined at the same time on two different lines, the regressor value must be the same on both lines. The regressor value is used even if the dose or observation is ignored (for instance using the [EVENT ID](#) and [IGNORED OBSERVATION](#) columns).

Lines added due to a [STEADY-STATE](#) column get the same regressor value as the line with the STEADY-STATE statement. Lines added due to an [ADDITIONAL DOSES](#) column get a dot '.' and are then interpolated based on the previous values.

2.2.3.8.1.1 Examples

- **Example with one regressor**: the regressor corresponds to the drug concentration, which will be used in a direct effect PD model. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	Y	REG
1	0	3.3	6.2
1	1	5.6	4.1
1	2	6.8	.
1	3	7.0	2.9

and the following model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {E0, IC50 , Cc}
Cc = { use = regressor }

EQUATION:
E = E0 * (1 - Cc/(Cc+IC50))

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
```

The regressor variable Cc in the model will take the values defined in the REG column and be used to calculate the effect E. For time points not defined in the data set, interpolation will be done depending on the chosen Regressor Setting. **If “Last Observation Carried Forward” is selected:** during the time interval [0, 1[, the regressor value is that defined on time 0. Note that the column header and the model regressor variable name can differ.

Regressor Cc

Output E

- **Example with two regressors:** the regressors correspond to the individual PK parameters used to calculate the drug concentration, itself impacting the effect E. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	V_mode	k_mode
1	0	10	.	6.2	1.2
1	0	.	3.3	6.2	1.2
1	1	.	5.6	6.2	1.2
1	2	.	6.8	6.2	1.2
1	3	.	7.0	6.2	1.2

and the following model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```

input = {E0, EC50 , V, k}
V = { use = regressor }
k = { use = regressor }

```

EQUATION:

$$C_c = \text{pkmodel}(V, k)$$

$$E = E_0 * (1 - C_c / (C_c + EC50))$$

OUTPUT:

```
output = {E}
```

The first column tagged as REGRESSOR (V_mode) is mapped to the first regressor in the `input` list (V), and the REGRESSOR column of the data set (k_mode) is mapped to the second regressor of the model (k).

Regressors V and k

Variable Cc

Output E

• **Example with STEADY-STATE and ADDITIONAL DOSES:**

ID	TIME	AMT	SS	ADDL	II	Y	REG
1	0	5.5	1
1	8	10	1	.	1	.	2
1	9	4.2	3
1	10	3.3	4
1	12	5	.	2	2	.	5
1	13	6.7	6
1	15	5.4	7
1	17	4.5	8

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	REG
1	0	.	5.5	1
1	3	10	.	2
1	4	10	.	2
1	5	10	.	2
1	6	10	.	2
1	7	10	.	2
1	8	10	.	2
1	9	.	4.2	3
1	10	.	3.3	4
1	12	5	.	5
1	13	.	6.7	6
1	14	5	.	6
1	15	.	5.4	7
1	16	5	.	7
1	17	.	4.5	8

lines added by SS=1 have the same regressor value as on the SS=1 line

lines added by ADDL are interpolated based on the previous time

2.2.3.8.1.2 Format restrictions

- The regression-columns (i.e. columns with column-type REGRESSOR) shall contain either doubles or "." (which will be interpolated).
- The first record for each subject (or subject-occasion) cannot be dot '.'.

- When there are several lines with the same time, same id and same occasion, the value of the regressor column must be the same.

2.2.3.9 Columns used to define controls and events

2.2.3.9.1 **EVENT ID: event identification data item.**

The EVENT ID column permits to assign lines to be dose or response-lines, and to define washouts/ resets. The column is not mandatory, as dose and response lines can be recognized based on the content. The EVENT ID column can take 5 different values:

- **EVENT ID = 0:** observation event, the line is a response-line. The dose-related informations (AMOUNT column, etc) are ignored.
- **EVENT ID = 1:** dose event, the line is a dose-line. The response-related informations (OBSERVATION column, etc) are ignored.
- **EVENT ID = 2:** other event. Both the dose information and the observation are ignored. Note that no prediction will be outputted for that time in the output files.
- **EVENT ID = 3:** reset + dose event. The system is reset to the initial values and the dose is applied immediately after. To do a reset without applying a new dose, the dose amount can be set to zero. Unlike EVENT ID = 4, no occasions are created. The line is a dose-line (i.e the response-related informations are ignored).
- **EVENT ID = 4:** reset + dose event. The system is reset to the initial values and the dose is applied immediately after. If at least one EVENT ID = 4 appear at a position which is not the first record of an individual, a OCCASION column-type called OCCEvid will be created. It may (but doesn't have to) be used to define inter-occasion variability. To do a reset without applying a new dose, the dose amount can be set to zero. The line is a dose-line (i.e the response-related informations are ignored).

All combinations of EVENT ID and IGNORED OBSERVATION values are possible and EVENT ID has priority over IGNORED OBSERVATION (for instance if EVENT ID = 1 and IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, the line is a dose-line). For all EVENT ID values, the REGRESSOR values are taken into account.

2.2.3.9.1.1 Examples

- **Example with EVENT ID = 0, 1, 2 and 3:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	EVID
1	0	10	.	1
1	1	.	9.8	0
1	2	.	6.7	0
1	3	10	.	2
1	4	.	4.3	0
1	5	.	2.3	0
1	6	0	.	3
1	7	.	0	0
1	8	.	0	0
1	9	10	.	1
1	10	10	.	3
1	11	.	7.6	0

dose-line

dose ignored

reset + dose=0

dose-line

reset + dose

- **Example with EVENT ID = 4:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	EVID
1	0	10	.	1
1	1	.	9.8	0
1	2	.	6.7	0
1	3	10	.	4
1	4	.	4.3	0
1	5	.	2.3	0

dose

reset + new occ + dose

2.2.3.9.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type EVENT ID.
- EVENT ID shall contain an integer in {0, 1, 2, 3, 4}.
- When a line is tagged EVENT ID = 0, and IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, the value contained in column OBSERVATION shall be a double.
- When a line is tagged EVENT ID = 1, 3 or 4, the value in the AMOUNT column shall be a double.

2.2.3.9.2 IGNORED OBSERVATION: ignores the observations (missing dependent variable)

The IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type enables to tag lines for which the information in the OBSERVATION column-type should be ignored (because they are outliers, or because one wants to ignore all PK measurements for instance). The column is not mandatory. Several IGNORED OBSERVATION columns are possible (see below) and 3 values are possible:

- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0**: the value in the OBSERVATION column is not ignored. If in addition EVENT ID = 0, the value in the OBSERVATION column has to be a double.
- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1**: the value in the OBSERVATION column is ignored.
- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 2**: identical to IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1. Note that no prediction will be made at that time point in the output files.

If there are both an IGNORED OBSERVATION and an EVENT ID column, the EVENT ID column has priority to define dose and response-lines. It is not necessary to set IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1 when EVENT ID = 1.

For all IGNORED OBSERVATION values, the REGRESSOR values are taken into account.

It is possible to have multiple IGNORED OBSERVATION columns in order to ignore observations for different reasons (for instance an “outliers” column to ignore outliers and a “placebo” column to ignore individuals which received only placebo, both tagged as IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type). When there are multiple IGNORED OBSERVATION columns, a synthetic value is computed as:

- if IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0 in all columns, then resulting synthetic IGNORED OBSERVATION equals 0.
- if IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1 or 2 in at least one column, then the resulting synthetic IGNORED OBSERVATION equals 1.

2.2.3.9.2.1 Examples

- **Example with IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, 1 or 2:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	MDV
1	0	10	.	1
1	1	.	10.1	0
1	2	.	8.3	2
1	3	.	6.9	0
1	4	.	5.7	0
1	5	.	4.8	1
1	6	.	3.6	0

observation ignored

observation ignored

2.2.3.9.2.2 Format restrictions

- IGNORED OBSERVATION shall contain only integers in {0, 1, 2}.
- If IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0 and EVENT ID = 0, the value in the OBSERVATION column has to be a double.

2.2.3.9.3 IGNORED LINE: ignores all the element of the line

Starting from the 2019 version, the IGNORED LINE column-type enables to tag lines for which all the information should be ignored (because they are outliers, or because one wants to ignore all PK measurements for instance). Contrary to the IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type that only ignores the observation value, the IGNORED LINE column-type allows to ignore doses and regressor values in addition to the observation values.

The column is not mandatory.

Starting from the 2021 version, there can be several columns IGNORED LINE, while in previous versions there can be only one such column.

Starting from the 2024 version, IGNORED LINE column can contain integers larger than 1, while previously the values were restricted to 0 and 1.

2.2.3.9.3.1 Format restrictions

- IGNORED LINE shall contain only non-negative integers.

2.2.3.10 NONMEM/MonolixSuite differences

The required format for the data set in NONMEM and in the Monolix Suite is very similar. Usually only few changes (if any) are required to go from one format to the other one.

2.2.3.10.1 General formatting

- **Column names:** in the Monolix Suite column names are not restricted in length, and not restricted to uppercase format. Special characters such as spaces " ", stars "*", parentheses or brackets "(", dashes "-", slashes "/" are supported but are replaced by "_" in the interface and results.
- **Header line:** no need to start the header line with the "#" character in the Monolix Suite, the column headers line will be recognized automatically.
- **Number of columns:** there is no limitation of the number of columns in the Monolix Suite

2.2.3.10.2 Dose column-types

- **STEADY STATE column:** When a data set contains a column with column-type STEADY STATE (formerly SS), there must be a column with column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL (formerly I). If STEADY STATE>0, then the value in the INTERDOSE INTERVAL column must be strictly positive. In case of steady-state, steady-state formulas are not used. Instead, [additional doses](#) (5 by default) are added before the STEADY STATE dose to reach steady-state.
- **INFUSION RATE and INFUSION DURATION:** in case of an infusion, in the Monolix Suite, it is possible to define either the rate (INFUSION RATE column-type, formerly RATE) or the duration (INFUSION DURATION column-type, formerly TINF). The rate and the duration are related to each

other via the amount: $TINF=RATE/AMT$. Negative values in the RATE column-type result in a bolus, when used in combination with the [iv macro](#) (and models from the library with iv). When used in combination with the [oral macro](#) (and models from the library with oral0 or oral1), the RATE column is ignored if the value is negative and an error is triggered if the value is positive. If infusion duration is defined in the model (parameter or fixed value), the RATE column is not necessary (in opposition to NONMEM, where RATE=-1 and RATE=-2 are used).

- **CMT column:** in NONMEM, for observation-lines, CMT specifies the compartment from which the predicted value of the observation is obtained. For dose-lines, CMT specifies the compartment into which the dose is introduced. In the MonolixSuite, the matching between the data (dose and observation lines) and the model (administrations and predictions) is done using identifiers, not based on compartment numbers. To assign a dose to a specific administration of the model ([oral](#) or [iv macros](#) for classical PK models, [depot macro](#) for more complex ODEs), the column [ADMINISTRATION ID](#) (formerly ADM) is used. The identifier in the ADMINISTRATION ID column should match the "adm=" field of the macro. To assign an observation to a prediction, the column [OBSERVATION ID](#) (formerly YTYPE) is used. Observation lines with OBSERVATION ID=1 will be assigned to the first output (output = {...} statement in the model file), lines with OBSERVATION ID=2 to the second output, etc. Note that the default values for the administration id in administration macros or in the pkmodel macro is adm=1. Similarly, in case of a single output, OBSERVATION ID=1 by default (while in NONMEM, the central compartment may have number 1 or 2). In the ADMINISTRATION ID column-type, negative values are not allowed. Turning off compartments should instead be defined in the model file.

NONMEM
MonolixSuite
Data set formatting:

ID	TIME	AMT	DV	CMT
1	0	10	.	1
1	1	.	3.5	2
1	1.05	.	50.1	3
1	5	.	2.1	2
1	5.04	.	60.3	3

ID	TIME	AMT	ADM	Y	YTYPE
1	0	10	1	.	.
1	1	.	.	3.5	1
1	1.05	.	.	50.1	2
1	5	.	.	2.1	1
1	5.04	.	.	60.3	2

Model scheme:

Control stream/model file:

```

$PROB 1st-order abs., linear elim., peripheral comp.
$INPUT ID TIME AMT DV CMT
$DATA datafile.csv
$SUBROUTINE ADVAN4 TRANS1 TOL=5

```

```

$PK
V = THETA(1) * EXP(ETA(1))
K = THETA(2) * EXP(ETA(2))
K23 = THETA(3)
K32 = THETA(4)
KA = THETA(5)
S3 = THETA(6)
S2 = V

```

```

$THETA
(10); THETA_V
(0.01); THETA_K
(0.01); THETA_K23
(0.01); THETA_K32
(0.1); THETA_KA
(5); THETA_S2
$OMEGA 0.5; ETA_V
$OMEGA 1; ETA_K
$SIGMA 1

```

```

$error
Y = F + ERR(1)

```

```

$EST METHOD=SAEM NBURN=2000 NITER=1000

```

```

DESCRIPTION: first-order absorption, linear elimination model,
peripheral compartment

```

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input={KA, Vc, K, K23, K32, Vp}

```

```

PK:
compartment(cmt=2, volume=Vc, concentration=Cc)
peripheral(k23=K23, k32=K32, volume=Vp, concentration=Cp)
elimination(cmt=2, k=K)
oral(ADM=1, cmt=2, ka=KA)

```

Lines with ADM=1 correspond to administration macros with adm=1

```

OUTPUT:
output={Cc, Cp}

```

Lines with YTYPE=1 correspond to the first output (here Cc)

+ parameter distributions, error model, initial values and correlations defined in the GUI

2.2.3.10.3 Control and event columns-types

- **EVID column-type:** in the Monolix Suite, the **EVENT ID** (formerly EVID) column is not mandatory, since dose-events (EVENT ID=1) and response-events (EVENT ID=0) are automatically recognized. The Monolix Suite also recognizes EVENT ID=2 (“Other event”), EVID=3 (“Reset event”), and EVID=4 (which corresponds to a reset to initial values immediately followed by a dose). EVID=4 creates a new occasion for the individual. In NONMEM, EVID=2 is sometimes used to define a time point at which one would like to predict a concentration, without having an observation. In the Monolix Suite, no prediction will be outputted for that time in the output files.
- **MDV column-type:** the **IGNORED OBSERVATION** (MDV) column is not mandatory in the Monolix Suite. Dose-lines and observation-lines will be recognized automatically based on their contents. Yet the IGNORED OBSERVATION column can be useful to force a response-line to be ignored (IGNORED OBSERVATION=1). Several IGNORED OBSERVATION columns are allowed, in this case a synthetic IGNORED OBSERVATION value is computed. In the Monolix Suite, IGNORED OBSERVATION can in addition take the value IGNORED OBSERVATION=2, which is identical to IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1. Note that no prediction will be made at that time point in the output files. Simulx can be used to obtain predictions from a model at different time points.

2.2.3.10.4 Response column-types

- **Censored data:** in the Monolix Suite, censored data should be tagged in the data set using additional columns with **CENSORING** (formerly CENS) to mark censored observation, and if necessary **LIMIT** (give other interval boundary) column-types. The LOQ value is indicated in the **OBSERVATION** column. Censored data are then automatically taken into account in the likelihood in a rigorous statistical way. If only the **CENSORING** column is used, the method in the Monolix Suite is equivalent to the so-called M3 method. When both **CENSORING** and **LIMIT** are used, the method is equivalent to M4.

2.2.3.10.5 Subject identification columns-types

- **ID column-type:** in NONMEM all lines related to a single individual must be in one block, which is not the case in the Monolix Suite. If the ID column contains the following IDs: [1,1,1,2,2,1,1], NONMEM will consider that the dataset comprise three individuals with IDs 1 (with 3 observations), 2 (with 2 observations) and 1_1 (with 2 observations). In the Monolix Suite, two individuals are considered, with IDs 1 (with 5 observations) and 2 (with 2 observations).

2.2.3.10.6 Time column-types

- **TIME column-type:** values in the time column can be negative in the Monolix Suite.

2.2.3.10.7 Covariates and regression column-types

- **Covariates:** in the Monolix Suite, columns corresponding to continuous covariates must be set to the **CONTINUOUS COVARIATE** (formerly COV) column-type, and categorical covariates to the **CATEGORICAL COVARIATE** (formerly CAT) column-type.
- **Regression variables:** in the Monolix Suite, regression variables must be set to the **REGRESSOR** (formerly X) column-type. If several regression variables are used, their order must be the same in the dataset and in the “input” field of the model file. Interpolation between two regressor values is done using “last observation carried forward” in Monolix, while it is “next observation carried backward” in Nonmem. When converting a Nonmem dataset to Monolix format, the time-varying regressor columns must be shifted one cell up for each individual.

2.2.3.10.8 Unsupported column-types

- The PCMT, CONT, CALL, MRG_, RAW_, RPT_, L1, and L2 column-types are not supported in the MonolixSuite.

2.2.3.11 Allowed characters

We recommend to use only alphanumeric characters and the underscore “_” character in the strings of your data set.

Unfortunately, special characters such as spaces “ ”, stars “*”, parentheses “()”, brackets “[”], dashes “-”, dots “.” and slashes “/” are not supported in:

- the headers,
- the strings in categorical covariate columns.

Please be careful that if your data set includes unsupported characters, the error will only be detected and displayed when loading a saved project (and not when creating and saving the project).

2.2.3.11.1 On the use of “.”

The “.” can be used in almost all the lines of the data set but has several meaning depending on the context. The following table summarizes the use of it.

Type of column	Not allowed	Considered as a regular string	Considered as	Not considered
ID		X		
OCCASION (OCC)	X			
TIME	X			
DATE/DAT1/DAT2/ DAT3	X			
OBSERVATION (Y)	On a response line			On a dose line
OBSERVATION ID (YTYPE)		On a response line		On a dose line (not read)
CENSORED (CENS)			0	
LIMIT			-Inf if CENS =1 , +Inf if CENS = -1	
AMOUNT (AMT)	On a dose line			On a response line (not read)
ADMINISTRATION ID (ADM)	On a dose line			On a response line (not read)
STEADY STATE (SS)			0	
ADDITIONAL DOSE (ADDL)			0	
INTERDOSE INTERVAL (II)			0	
CONTINUOUS COVARIATE (COV)			Previously defined value of the COV (in the ID/OCC)	

Type of column	Not allowed	Considered as a regular string	Considered as	Not considered
CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (CAT)		X		
REGRESSOR			Interpolation	
EVENT ID (EVID)	X			
IGNORED OBSERVATION (MDV)	X			

2.2.4 Data formatting

The same dataset format is used in all applications of MonolixSuite, to allow for smooth transitions between applications. In this format, some rules have to be fulfilled, for example:

- Each line corresponds to one individual and one time point.
- Each line can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount (or both a measurement and a dose amount).
- Dose amount should be indicated for each individual dose in a column AMOUNT, even if it is identical for all.
- Headers are free but there can be only one header line.

If your dataset is not in this format, in most cases, it is possible to format it in a few steps in the **data formatting** tab, to incorporate the missing information.

In this case, the original dataset should be loaded in the “Format data” box, or directly in the “Data Formatting” tab, instead of the “Data” tab. In the data formatting module, you will be guided to build a dataset in the MonolixSuite format, starting from the loaded csv file. The resulting formatted dataset is then loaded in the Data tab as if you loaded an already-formatted dataset in “Data” directly. Then as for defining any dataset, you can tag columns, accept the dataset, and once accepted, units can be specified in the Data tab (only in PKanalix) and the Filters tab can be used to select only parts of this dataset for analysis. Note that units and filters are neither information to be included in the data file, nor part of the data formatting process.

From the version 2024R1, it is possible to save and reapply data formatting steps on multiple projects, using data formatting presets (in both Monolix and PKanalix).

The original datafile is NOT modified by PKanalix and Monolix. Formatting operations are saved in the projects and applied to the data when the project is loaded. The formatted dataset is not saved by default, but it can be exported by the user as a CSV file.

2.2.4.1 Data formatting workflow

When opening a new project, two Browse buttons appear. The first one, under “Data file”, can be used to load a dataset already in a MonolixSuite-standard format, while the second one, under “Format data”, allows to load a dataset to format in the Data formatting module.

After loading a dataset to format, data formatting operations can be specified in several subtabs: Initialization, Observations, Treatments and Additional columns.

- Initialization is mandatory and must be filled before using the other subtabs.
- Observations is required to enable the Treatments tab.

After Initialization has been validated by clicking on “Next”, a button “Preview” is available from any subtab to view in the Data tab the formatted dataset based on the formatting operations currently specified.

2.2.4.2 Dataset initialization

The first tab in Data formatting is named Initialization. This is where the user can select header lines or lines to exclude (in the blue area on the screenshot below) or tag columns (in the yellow area).

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	CONC_mg_L	SORT	AGE	WT	SEQ
1	Description: crossover study with two formulations						
2	ID	TIME	CONC		AGE	WT	SEQ
3		h	mg/L				
4	1	0	BLQ	ref	25	66	RT
5	1	1	NA	ref	25	66	RT

2.2.4.2.1 Selecting header lines or lines to exclude

These settings should contain line numbers for lines that should be either handled as column headers or that should be excluded.

- **Header lines:** one or several lines containing column header information. By default, the first line of the dataset is selected as header. If several lines are selected, they are merged by data formatting into a single line, concatenating the cells in each column.
- **Lines to exclude (optional):** lines that should be excluded from the formatted dataset by data formatting.

2.2.4.2.2 Tagging mandatory columns

Only the columns corresponding to the following tabs must be tagged in Initialization, while all the other columns should keep the default UNDEFINED tag:

- **ID (mandatory):** subject identifiers
- **TIME (mandatory):** the single time column
- **SORT (optional):** one or several columns containing SORT variables can be tagged as SORT. Occasions based on these columns will be created in the formatted dataset as described in Section "Creating occasions from a SORT column".
- **START, END and VOLUME (mandatory in case of urine data):** these column tags replace the TIME tag in case of urine data, if the urine collection time intervals are encoded in the dataset with two time columns for the start and end times of the intervals. In that case there should also be a column with the urine volume in each interval. See Section "Handling urine data" for more details.

2.2.4.2.3 Initialization example

- demo **CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting initialization and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo the first line of the dataset is excluded because it contains a description of the study. The second line contains column headers while the third line contains column units. Since the MonolixSuite-standard format allows only a single header line, lines 2 and 3 are merged together in the formatted dataset.

The screenshot illustrates the 'Data formatting' process in Monolix. The top panel shows the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings' (Header lines: 2, Lines to exclude: 1). The middle panel shows a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, FORM, AGE, WT, SEQ. A green arrow points to the first row, labeled 'EXCLUDED LINE'. An orange bracket groups the first two rows, labeled 'CONCATENATED HEADERS'. A blue 'PREVIEW' button is shown below. The bottom panel shows the 'Data information' and 'Units' settings (Urine selected, TIME: hour, CONC: milligram/liter, AMT: milligram/liter). The bottom table has columns: TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, FORM, AGE, WT, SEQ, FORM_OCC, AMT, ADMID, CENS. An orange arrow points to the 'FORM_OCC' column.

2.2.4.3 Creating occasions from a SORT column

A SORT variable can be used to distinguish different sets of measurements (usually concentrations) within each subject, that should be analyzed separately by PKanalix or Monolix (for example: different formulations given to each individual at different periods of time, or multiple doses where concentration profiles are available to be analyzed following several doses).

These different sets of measurements must be distinguished as OCCASIONS (or periods of time), via the OCCASION column-type. However, a column tagged as OCCASION can only contain integers with occasion indexes. Thus, if a column with a SORT variable contains strings, its format must be adapted by Data formatting, in the following way:

- the user must tag the column as SORT in the Initialization subtab of Data formatting,
- the user validates the Initialization with “Next”, then clicks on “Preview” (after optionally defining other data formatting operations),
- the formatted data is shown in Data: the column tagged as SORT is automatically duplicated. The original column is automatically tagged as CATEGORICAL COVARIATE in Data, while the duplicated column, which has the same name appended with “_OCC”, is tagged as OCCASION. This column contains occasion indexes instead of strings.

Example:

- demo **CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of occasions and excludes other elements present in the demo):

The image below shows lines 25 to 29 from the dataset from the CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx demo, where covariate columns have been removed to simplify the example. This dataset contains two sets of concentration measurements for each individual, corresponding to two different drug formulations administered on different periods. The sets of concentrations are distinguished with the FORM column, which contains “ref” and “test” categories (reference/test formulations). The column is tagged as SORT in Data formatting Initialization. After clicking on “Preview”, we can see in the Data tab that a new column named FORM_OCC has been created with occasion indexes for each individual: for subject 1, FORM_OCC=1 corresponds to the reference formulation because it appears first in the dataset, and FORM_OCC=2 corresponds to the test formulation because it appears in second in the dataset.

The left screenshot shows the 'Initialization' tab. The 'Lines settings' section includes 'Header lines' (1-3) and 'Lines to exclude' (1-3). Below is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, UNDEFINED, SORT, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED. The 'SORT' column is highlighted with a red box. A blue arrow points from the 'PREVIEW' button to the right screenshot.

The right screenshot shows the 'Observations' tab. The 'Data information' section includes 'Units' (None, Plasma) and 'Time' (column 1), 'Conc' (column 1), and 'AMT' (column 1). Below is a table with columns: TIME, OBSERVATION, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, CONTINUOUS COVARIATE, CONTINUOUS COVARIATE, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, OCCASION, AMOUNT. The 'OBSERVATION' column is highlighted with a red box.

2.2.4.4 Selecting an observation type

The second subtab in Data formatting allows to select one or several observation types. An observation type corresponds to a column of the dataset, that contains a type of measurements (usually drug concentrations, but it can also be PD measurements for example). Only columns that have not been tagged as ID, TIME or SORT are available as observation type.

The screenshot shows the 'Observations' tab. A dropdown menu is open, showing options: CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, SEQ.

The screenshot shows the 'Observations' tab. The 'Observation type based on CONC_mg_L' is selected. The 'Censoring tags' section is visible, with a checkbox for 'Use all automatically detected tags' (recommended for creating presets in case of dataset dependent censoring tags) and a list of tags: BLQ, NA.

This action is optional and can have several purposes:

- If doses must be added by Data formatting (see Section "Adding doses in the data set"), specifying the column containing observations is mandatory, to avoid duplicating observations on new dose lines.
- If several observation types exist in different columns (for example: concentrations for different analytes, or measurements for PK and PD), they must be specified in Data formatting to be merged into a single observation column (see Section "Merging observations from several columns").
- In the MonolixSuite-standard format, the column containing observations can only contain numbers, and no string except "." for a missing observation. Thus if this column contains strings in the original dataset, it must be adapted by Data formatting, with two different cases:
 - if the strings are tags for censored observations (usually BLQ: below the limit of quantification), they can be specified in Data formatting to adapt the encoding of the censored observations (see Section "Specifying censoring from censoring tags"),
 - any other string in the column is automatically replaced by "." by Data formatting.

2.2.4.5 Merging observations from several columns

The MonolixSuite-standard format allows a single column containing all observations (such as concentrations or PD measurements). Thus if a dataset contains several observation types in different columns (for example: concentrations for different analytes, or measurements for PK and PD), they must be specified in Data formatting to be merged into a single observation column.

In that case, different settings can be chosen in the area marked in orange in the screenshot below:

- The user must choose between distinguishing observation types with observation ids or occasions.
- The user can unselect the option “Duplicate information from undefined columns”.

2.2.4.5.1 As observation ids

After selecting the “Distinguish observation types with: observation ids” option and clicking “Preview,” the columns for different observation types are combined into a single column called “OBS.” Each row of the dataset is duplicated for each observation type, with one value per observation type. Additionally, an “OBSID” column is created, with the name of the observation type corresponding to the measurement on each row.

This option is recommended for joint modeling of observation types, such as CA in PKanalix or population modeling in Monolix. It is important to note that NCA cannot be performed on two different observation ids simultaneously, so it is necessary to choose one observation id for the analysis.

Example:

- demo **merge_obsID_ParentMetabolite.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of observations and excludes other elements present in the demo):

This demo involves two columns that contain drug parent and metabolite concentrations. When merging both observation types with observation ids, a new column called OBSID is generated with categories labeled as “PARENT” and “METABOLITE.”

The screenshot shows the Monolix Data Formatting interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. The main area is divided into 'Data file' and 'Lines settings'.

Lines settings: Header lines: 1, Lines to exclude: (empty).

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	DOSE	SEX
1	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	1000	M
2	1	2	24.7161	2.66854	1000	M
3	1	4	34.6926	9.95048	1000	M
4	1	6	38.251	17.8245	1000	M
5	1	8	32.0533	20.99	1000	M

Data information: METABOLITE: Urine (selected), Plasma; PARENT: Urine (selected), Plasma.

Units: TIME: hour, CONC: milligram / milliliter, AMT: milligram.

Settings dialog: Distinguish observation types with: observation ids, occasions. Duplicate information from undefined columns: .

Data table (after preview):

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	DOSE	SEX	AMT	OBS	OBSID
2	1	0	1000	M	1000	.	.
3	1	1	1000	M	.	13.4806	PARENT
4	1	1	1000	M	.	1.00136	METABOLITE
5	1	2	1000	M	.	24.7161	PARENT
6	1	2	1000	M	.	2.66854	METABOLITE
7	1	4	1000	M	.	34.6926	PARENT

2.2.4.5.2 As occasions

After selecting the “Distinguish observation types with: occasions” option and clicking “Preview,” the columns for different observation types are combined into a single column called “OBS.” Each row of the dataset is duplicated for each observation type, with one value per observation type. Additionally, two columns are created: an “OBSID_OCC” column with the index of the observation type corresponding to the measurement on each row, and an “OBSID_COV” with the name of the observation type.

This option is recommended for NCA, which can be run on different occasions for each individual. However, joint modeling of the observation types with CA or population modeling with Monolix cannot be performed with this option.

Example:

- demo **merge_occ_ParentMetabolite.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix):

This demo involves two columns that contain drug parent and metabolite concentrations. When merging both observation types with occasions, two new columns called OBSID_OCC and OBSID_COV are generated with OBSID_OCC=1 corresponding to OBSID_COV="PARENT" catand OBSID_OCC=2 corresponding to OBSID_COV="METABOLITE."

The image displays two screenshots of the Monolix software interface, illustrating the process of merging observation types with occasions.

Top Screenshot: Data Formatting - Observations

The interface shows the 'Data file' section with a file path and a 'Lines settings' section with 'Header lines' set to 1. The main table displays data for 6 rows. The columns are: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, PARENT, METABOLITE, DOSE, and SEX. The 'PARENT' and 'METABOLITE' columns are highlighted with a red box.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	DOSE	SEX
1	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	1000	M
2	1	2	24.7161	2.66854	1000	M
3	1	4	34.6926	9.95048	1000	M
4	1	6	38.251	17.8245	1000	M
5	1	8	32.0533	20.99	1000	M

Bottom Screenshot: Data Formatting - Additional columns

The interface shows the 'Data information' section with 'Urine' selected and 'Plasma' selected. The 'Units' section shows 'TIME' in 'hour', 'CONC' in 'milligram / milliliter', and 'AMT' in 'milligram'. The main table displays data for 6 rows. The columns are: ID, TIME, DOSE, SEX, AMT, OBS, OBSID_OCC, and OBSID_COV. The 'OBS', 'OBSID_OCC', and 'OBSID_COV' columns are highlighted with a red box.

ID	TIME	DOSE	SEX	AMT	OBS	OBSID_OCC	OBSID_COV
1	0	1000	M	1000	.	1	PARENT
1	0	1000	M	1000	.	2	METABOLITE
1	1	1000	M	.	13.4806	1	PARENT
1	1	1000	M	.	1.00136	2	METABOLITE
1	2	1000	M	.	24.7161	1	PARENT
1	2	1000	M	.	2.66854	2	METABOLITE

Settings Dialog:

The settings dialog is open, showing options for distinguishing observation types with observation IDs (recommended for joint CA and population modeling) and occasions (recommended for NCA). The 'Duplicate information from undefined columns' option is checked.

2.2.4.5.3 Duplicate information from undefined columns

When merging two observation columns into a single column, all other columns will see their lines duplicated. The data formatting will know how to treat columns which have been tagged in the Initialization tab, but not the other columns (header "UNDEFINED") which are not used for data formatting. A checkbox enables to decide if the information from these columns should be duplicated on the new lines, or if "." should be used instead. The default option is to duplicate information, because in general, the undefined columns correspond to covariates with one value per individual, so this value is the same for the two lines that correspond to the same id.

The screenshot illustrates the process of duplicating information from undefined columns. It is divided into two parts:

Top Panel: Initial State

- Data file:** C:\Users\FrancoMhaJevic\Software\jkanalix\jkanalix2024R1\demo\0\data_formatting\fd...
- Lines settings:** Header lines: 1, Lines to exclude: (empty)
- Table:** Columns include ID, TIME, UNDEFINED (PARENT, METABOLITE), and UNDEFINED (DOSE, SEX). The DOSE and SEX columns are highlighted with an orange box.
- Text:** **DOSE AND SEX UNDEFINED**

Bottom Panel: Final State

- Data information:** Urine (selected), Plasma (unselected)
- Units:** TIME: column x 1, hour; CONC: column x 1, milligram / milliliter; AMT: column x 1, milligram
- Settings:** Duplicate information from undefined columns
- Table:** Columns include ID, TIME, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (DOSE, SEX), AMOUNT (AMT), OBSERVATION (OBS), and OBSERVATION ID (OBSID). The DOSE and SEX columns are highlighted with an orange box.
- Text:** **DOSE AND SEX VALUES DUPLICATED**

Blue arrows indicate the flow from the initial state to the settings and then to the final state.

It is rare that you need to uncheck this box. An example where you should not duplicate the information is if you already have a column Amount in the MonolixSuite format, so with a dose amount only at the dosing time, and "." everywhere else. If you do not want to specify amount again in data formatting, and simply want to merge observation columns as observation ids, you should not duplicate the lines of the Amount column which is undefined. Indeed, the dose amounts have been administered only once.

The screenshot shows the 'Data formatting' interface in MonolixSuite. The 'Data file' is 'C:\Users\FrancoMihaljevic\Documents\Documentation\Screenshots\formattedData.csv'. The 'Lines settings' show 'Header lines: 1' and 'Lines to exclude:'. The table below has columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, PARENT, METABOLITE, and AMT. The 'AMT' column is highlighted with an orange box and labeled 'AMT UNDEFINED'. A 'Settings' dialog box is open on the right, with the 'Duplicate information from undefined columns' checkbox checked. A 'PREVIEW' button is visible below the dialog.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	AMT
1	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	AMT
2	1	0	13.4806	.	1000
3	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	.
4	1	2	24.7161	2.66854	.
5	1	4	34.6926	9.95048	.
6	1	6	38.251	17.8245	.

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 761
Page 1 of 16
Showing 1 to 50 of 761 entries

Settings:

- Distinguish observation types with:
 - observation ids (recommended for joint PK and disposition modeling)
 - OCCASIONS (recommended for NCA)
- Duplicate information from undefined columns

PREVIEW

AMT UNDEFINED

2.2.4.6 Specifying censoring from censoring tags

In the MonolixSuite-standard format, censored observations are encoded with a 1 or -1 flag in a column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, while exact observations have a 0 flag in that column. In

addition, on rows for censored observations, the LOQ is indicated in the observation column: it is the LLOQ (lower limit of quantification) if CENSORING=1 or the ULOQ (upper limit of quantification) if CENSORING=-1. Finally, to specify a censoring interval, an additional column tagged as LIMIT in the Data tab must exist in the dataset, with the other censoring bound.

The Data Formatting module can take as input a dataset with censoring tags directly in the observation column, and adapt the dataset format as described above. After selecting one or several observation types in the Observations subtab (see Section "Selecting an observation type"), all strings found in the corresponding columns are displayed in the "Censoring tags" on the right of the observation types. If at least one string is found, the user can then define some censoring associated with an observation type and with one or several censoring tags with the button "Add censoring". Additionally, option "Use all automatically detected tags" exist and can be used when all censoring tags correspond to the same censoring type (this option is recommended for the usage with data formatting presets, if censoring tags vary between data sets in which the preset will be used). 3 types of censoring can be defined:

- **LLOQ**: this corresponds to left-censoring, where the censored observation is below a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), that must be specified by the user. In that case Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the LLOQ, and creates a new CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with 1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows.
- **ULOQ**: this corresponds to right-censoring, where the censored observation is above an upper limit of quantification (ULOQ), that must be specified by the user. Here Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the ULOQ, and creates a new CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with -1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows.
- **Interval**: this is for interval-censoring, where the user must specify two bounds of a censoring interval, to which the censored observation belongs. Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the upper bound of the interval, and creates two new columns: a CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with 1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows, and a LIMIT column with the lower bound of the censoring interval on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and "." on other rows.

For each type of censoring, available options to define the limits are:

- **“Manual”**: limits are defined manually, by entering the limit values for all censored observations.
- **“By category”**: limits are defined manually for different categories read from the dataset.
- **“From data”**: limits are directly read from the dataset.

The options “by category” and “from data” are described in detail in Section “Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the data set”.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_manual.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_manual.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of censored observations and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are two censoring tags in the CONC column: BLQ1 (from Study 1) and BLQ2 (from Study 2), that correspond to different LLOQs. An interval censoring is defined for each censoring tag, with manual limits, where LLOQ=0.06 for BLQ1 and LLOQ=0.1 for BLQ2, and the lower limit of the censoring interval being 0 in both cases.

The screenshot illustrates the 'Data Formatting' module in Monolix Suite. It shows the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings' tabs, the 'Data information' and 'Units' tabs, and the 'Data' table. The 'Data' table has columns for ID, TIME, CONC, AGE, WT, and STUDY. The 'PREVIEW' button is visible. Two 'Interval censoring' dialog boxes are shown on the right, one with an orange border and one with a purple border, both showing 'Upper limit' and 'Lower limit' settings.

2.2.4.7 Adding doses in the dataset

Datasets in MonolixSuite-standard format should contain all information on doses, as dose lines. An AMOUNT column records the amount of the administered doses on dose-lines, with "." on response-lines. In case of infusion, an INFUSION DURATION or INFUSION RATE column records the infusion duration or rate. If there are several types of administration, an ADMINISTRATION ID column can distinguish the different types of doses with integers.

If doses are missing from a dataset, the Data Formatting module can be used to add dose lines and dose-related columns: after initializing the dataset, the user can specify one or several treatments in the Treatments subtab. The following operations are then performed by Data Formatting:

- a new dose line is inserted in the dataset for each defined dose, with the dataset sorted by subject and times. On such a dose line, the values from the next line are duplicated for all columns, except for the observation column in which "." is used for the dose line.
- A new column AMT is created with "." on all lines except on dose lines, on which dose amounts are used. The AMT column is automatically tagged as AMOUNT in the Data tab.
- If administration ids have been defined in the treatment, an ADMID column is created, with "." on all lines except on dose lines, on which administration ids are used. The ADMID column is automatically tagged as ADMINISTRATION ID in the Data tab.
- If an infusion duration or rate has been defined, a new INFDUR (for infusion duration) or INFRATE (for infusion rate) is created, with "." on all lines except on dose lines. The INFDUR column is automatically tagged as INFUSION DURATION in the Data tab, and the INFRATE column is automatically tagged as INFUSION RATE.

Initialization
Observations
Treatments
Additional columns
RESTORE DATA
PREVIEW

+ ADD TREATMENT

Treatment 1
🗑️

REGULAR
MANUAL
EXTERNAL

Apply to all ids

Start time	Interdose interval	Number of doses
0	24	4

Repeat cycle

Amount MANUAL FROM DATA 100

By category No category

Infusion MANUAL FROM DATA 2

By category No category

Administration id MANUAL FROM DATA 1

By category No category

Common settings

Dose intervals as occasions

Duplicate observations at dose time into each occasion

Infusion type

duration rate

For each treatment, the dosing schedule can be defined as:

- **regular**: for regularly spaced dosing times, defined with the start time, inter-dose interval, and number of doses. A “repeat cycle” option allows to repeat the regular dosing schedule to generate a more complex regimen.
- **manual**: a vector of one or several dosing times, each defined manually. A “repeat cycle” option allows to repeat the manual dosing schedule to generate a more complex regimen.
- **external**: an external text file with columns id (optional), occasions (optional), time (mandatory), amount (mandatory), admid (administration id, optional), tinf or rate (optional), that allows to define individual doses.

Starting from the 2024R1 version, different dosing schedules can be defined for different individuals, based on information from other columns, which can be useful in cases when different cohorts received different dosing regimens, or when working with data pooled from multiple studies. To define a treatment just for a specific cohort or study, the dropdown on the top of the treatment section can be used:

▼ Treatment 1

REGULAR MANUAL EXTERNAL

Apply to ids with STUDY equals to 1

Start time	Interdose interval	Number of doses
0	24	4

While dose amounts, administration ids and infusion durations or rates are defined in the external file for external treatments, available options to define them for treatments of type “manual” or “regular” are:

- **“Manual”**: this applies the same amount (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) to all doses.
- **“By category”**: dose amounts (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) are defined manually for different categories read from the dataset.
- **“From data”**: dose amounts (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) are directly read from the dataset.

The options “by category” and “from data” are described in detail in Section “Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the dataset”.

There is a “common settings” panel on the right:

- **dose intervals as occasions:** this creates a column to distinguish the dose intervals as different occasions (see Section "Creating occasions from dosing intervals").
- **infusion type:** If several treatments correspond to infusion administration, they need to share the same type of encoding for infusion information: as infusion duration or as infusion rate.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_manual.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_manual.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo, doses are initially not included in the dataset to format. A single dose at time 0 with an amount of 600 is added for each individual by Data Formatting. This creates a new AMT column in the formatted dataset, tagged as AMOUNT.

The screenshot shows the 'Data Formatting' interface in Monolix. The top panel displays the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings'. The main table shows the initial dataset with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, and STUDY. The 'AMT' column is initially empty.

The 'Treatment 1' panel on the right shows the configuration for adding a dose. The 'Amount' is set to 600, and the 'Time' is set to 0. The 'Repeat cycle' checkbox is unchecked. The 'By category' dropdown is set to 'No category'. The 'Administration id' checkbox is unchecked.

The bottom panel shows the 'Data information' and 'Units' sections. The 'AMT' column is highlighted in orange, and the 'Amount' is set to 600. The 'Preview' button is highlighted in blue.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	CONC_mg_L	AGE	WT	STUDY	AMT
1	1	0	-	25	66	1	-
2	1	1	0.34	25	66	1	-
3	1	2	0.34	25	66	1	-
4	1	3	0.34	25	66	1	-
5	1	4	1.44	25	66	1	-

2.2.4.8 Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the dataset

When defining censoring limits for observations (see Section "Specifying censoring from censoring tags") or dose amounts, administration ids, infusion duration or rate for treatments (see Section "Adding doses in the dataset"), two options allow to define different values for different rows, based on information already present in the dataset: "by category" and "from data".

2.2.4.8.1 By category

It is possible to define manually different censoring limits, dose amounts, administration ids, infusion durations, or rates for different categories within a dataset's column. After selecting this column in the "By category" drop-down menu, the different modalities in the column are displayed and a value must be manually assigned each modality.

The image shows two screenshots of the Monolix software interface. The left screenshot shows the configuration for 'Interval censoring' for the column 'CONC_mg_L'. The 'Upper limit' is set to 'MANUAL' and 'FROM DATA'. A table is displayed with the following data:

By category	Modalities	Upper limit
STUDY	SD_400mg	0.01
	SD_500mg	0.1
	SD_600mg	0.1

The right screenshot shows the configuration for 'Treatment 1'. The 'Amount' is set to 'MANUAL' and 'FROM DATA'. A table is displayed with the following data:

By category	Modalities	AMOUNT
STUDY	SD_400mg	400
	SD_500mg	500
	SD_600mg	600

- For censoring limits, the censoring limit used to replace each censoring tag depends on the modality on the same row.
- For doses, the value chosen for the newly created column (AMT for amount, ADMID for administration id, INFDUR for infusion duration, INFRATE for infusion rate) on each new dose line depends on the modality on the first row found in the dataset for the same individual and the same time as the dose, or the next time if there is no line in the initial dataset at that time, or the previous time if no time is found after the dose.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.pkx/DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are three studies distinguished in the STUDY column with the categories "SD_400mg", "SD_500mg" and "SD_600mg". In Data Formatting, a single dose is manually defined at time 0 for all individuals, with different amounts depending the STUDY category. In addition, censoring interval is defined for the censoring tags BLQ, with an upper limit of the censoring interval (lower limit of quantification) that also depends on the STUDY category. Three new columns – AMT for dose amounts, CENS for censoring tags (0 or 1), and LIMIT for the lower limit of the censoring intervals – are created by Data Formatting. A new dose line is then inserted at time 0 for each individual.

The image illustrates the process of importing data from a dataset into Monolix. It shows three main stages:

- Data Import:** The 'Data file' is loaded, and 'Lines settings' are configured. The resulting table shows columns for ID, TIME, CONC, AGE, WT, STUDY, and LLOQ. Some values are highlighted with orange and purple boxes.
- Data Information:** The 'Data information' panel shows units and display options. The resulting table shows columns for ID, TIME, OBSERVATION, CONTINUOUS COVARIATE, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, IGNORE, AMOUNT, and CENSORING. Some values are highlighted with orange and purple boxes.
- Configuration:** The 'Interval censoring' and 'Treatment 1' panels show configuration options. The 'Interval censoring' panel shows 'Upper limit' and 'Lower limit' settings. The 'Treatment 1' panel shows 'Amount' and 'Modality' settings. A blue arrow points from the 'PREVIEW' button in the 'Treatment 1' panel to the 'PREVIEW' button in the 'Data information' panel.

2.2.4.8.2 From data

The option "From data" is used to directly read censoring limits, dose amounts, administration ids, infusion durations, or rates from a dataset's column. The column must contain either numbers or numbers inside strings. In that case, the first number found in the string is extracted (including decimals with .).

- For censoring limits, the censoring limit used to replace each censoring tag is read from the selected column on the same row.
- For doses, the value chosen for the newly created column (AMT for amount, ADMID for administration id, INF DUR for infusion duration, INFRATE for infusion rate) on each new dose line is read from the selected column on the first row found in the dataset for the same individual and the same time as the dose, or the next time if there is no line in the initial dataset at that time, or the previous time if no time is found after the dose.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_fromData.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_fromData.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and censoring and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are three studies distinguished in the STUDY column with the categories "SD_400mg", "SD_500mg" and "SD_600mg". In Data Formatting, a single dose is manually defined at time 0 for all individuals, with the amount read the STUDY column. In addition, censoring interval is defined for the censoring tags BLQ, with an upper limit of the censoring interval (lower limit of quantification) read from the LLOQ_mg_L column. Three new columns – AMT for dose amounts, CENS for censoring tags (0 or 1), and LIMIT for the lower limit of the censoring intervals – are created by Data Formatting. A new dose line is then inserted at time 0 for each individual, with amount 400, 500 or 600 for studies SD_400mg, SD_500mg and SD_600mg respectively.

The screenshot illustrates the 'Data Formatting' process in Monolix. It is divided into two main parts: the initial data view and the formatted data view, with a 'PREVIEW' button connecting them.

Initial Data View (Top): Shows a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, STUDY, and LLOQ_mg_L. The 'STUDY' column contains values like 'SD_400mg' and 'SD_500mg'. The 'CONC_mg_L' column contains values like 'BLQ' and '0.0348967'. A 'Lines settings' panel is visible at the top right.

Formatted Data View (Bottom): Shows the same data after processing. New columns 'AMT' and 'CENS' have been added. The 'AMT' column contains values like '400' and '500', and the 'CENS' column contains '1' and '0'. The 'CONC_mg_L' column now contains numerical values like '0.01' and '0.1' instead of 'BLQ'. A 'Data information' panel is visible at the top right.

Configuration Panels:

- Interval censoring:** Shows settings for 'Upper limit' (MANUAL, FROM DATA, LLOQ_mg_L, BLQ) and 'Lower limit' (MANUAL, FROM DATA, 0).
- Treatment 1:** Shows settings for 'Amount' (MANUAL, FROM DATA, STUDY) and 'Censoring' (BLQ).

Blue arrows indicate the flow from the initial data view to the formatted data view, and from the configuration panels to the formatted data view.

2.2.4.9 Creating occasions from dosing intervals

The option “Dose intervals as occasions” in the Treatments subtab of Data Formatting allows to create an occasion column to distinguish dose intervals. This is useful if the sets of measurements following different doses should be analyzed independently for a same individual. From the 2024 version on, an additional option “Duplicate observations at dose times into each occasion” is available. This option allows to duplicate the observations which are at exactly the same time as dose, such that they appear both as last point of the previous occasion and first point of the next occasion.

Example:

- demo **doseIntervals_as_Occ.mlxtran** (Monolix demo, can be imported into PKanalix):

This demo has an initial dataset in Monolix-standard format, with multiple doses encoded as dose lines with dose amounts in the AMT column. When using this dataset directly into Monolix or PKanalix, a single analysis is done on each individual concentration profile considering all doses, which means that NCA would be done on the concentrations after the last dose only, and modeling (CA in PKanalix or population modeling in Monolix) would be estimated with a single set of parameter values for each individual. If instead we want to run separate analyses on the sets of concentrations following each dose, we need to distinguish them as occasions with a new column added with the Data Formatting module. To this end, we define the same treatment as in the initial dataset with Data Formatting (here as regular multiple doses) with the option “Dose intervals as occasions” selected. After clicking Preview, Data Formatting adds two new columns: an AMT1 column with the new doses, to be tagged as AMOUNT instead of the AMT column that will now be ignored, and a DOSE_OCC column to be tagged as OCCASION.

The image illustrates the process of formatting data in Monolix. It shows two screenshots of the software interface and two corresponding concentration-time plots.

Initial Data Set (NO OCCASIONS): The top-left screenshot shows the 'Data file' section with a table of data points. The top-right plot shows concentration (CONC) vs. time (time) with multiple lines representing different individuals, but no explicit occasion markers.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	CONC	AMT
10	1	12	-	40
11	1	23	3.54146	-
12	1	24	-	40
13	1	35	4.33902	-
14	1	36	-	40
15	1	47	4.9619	-
16	1	48	-	40

Formatted Data Set (WITH OCCASIONS): The bottom-left screenshot shows the 'Data information' section with a table where each dose is now associated with an occasion number (DOSE_OCC). The bottom-right plot shows the same data with vertical dashed lines indicating the occasions at which doses were administered.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	CONC	AMT	DOSE_OCC	AMT1
11	1	12	-	40	2	40
12	1	12	-	40	2	40
13	1	23	3.54146	-	2	-
14	1	24	-	40	3	40
15	1	24	-	40	3	40

Arrows indicate the flow from the initial data set to the formatted data set, and from both to their respective plots. A 'PREVIEW' button is visible in the bottom-left screenshot.

Example:

- demo **CreateOcc_duplicateObs.pkx** (can be imported into Monolix):

Data file | Data information | Units

Urine Plasma

TIME column × 1 = hour
 CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter
 AMT column × 1 = milligram /

LINE NUMBER	Animal	Dose_mg_kg	Time_h	Concentration_ng_mL	DOSE_OCC	AMT
7	1001	2	4	29	1	
	1001#2	2				
8	1001	2	8		2	2
9	1001	2	8	5.35	2	
10	1001	2	8.5	94.1	2	
11	1001	2	9	75.1	2	
12	1001	2	10	43.7	2	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 364
 << Page 1 of 8 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 364 entries - 28 Individuals

Duplicate observations at dose time into each occasion

Data file | Data information | Units

Urine Plasma

TIME column × 1 = hour
 CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter
 AMT column × 1 = milligram /

LINE NUMBER	Animal	Dose_mg_kg	Time_h	Concentration_ng_mL	DOSE_OCC	AMT
7	1001	2	4	29	1	
8	1001	2	8	5.35	1	
	1001#2	2				
9	1001	2	8		2	2
10	1001	2	8	5.35	2	
11	1001	2	8.5	94.1	2	
12	1001	2	9	75.1	2	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 392
 << Page 1 of 8 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 392 entries - 28 Individuals

2.2.4.10 Handling urine data

In PKanalix-standard format, the start and end times of urine collection intervals must be recorded in a single column, tagged as TIME column-type, where the end time of an interval automatically acts as start time for the next interval. If a dataset contains start and end times in two different columns, they can be merged into a single column by Data Formatting. This is done automatically by tagging these two columns as START and END in the Initialization subtab of Data Formatting (see Section "Data set initialization"). In addition the column containing urine collection volume must be tagged as VOLUME.

Example:

- demo **Urine_LOQinObs.pkx** (can be imported into Monolix):

Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting Initialization Observations Treatments Additional columns
RESTORE DATA

Data file

C:/Users/FrancoMihaljevic/ixorb/pskanalix/pskanalix2024R1/demos/0_data_format...

BROWSE...

Lines settings

Header lines:

Lines to exclude:

LINE NUMBER	ID	START	END	VOLUME	UNDEFINED
LINE NUMBER	ID	START_TIME	END_TIME	VOLUME	CONC
1	ID	START TIME	END TIME	VOLUME	CONC
2	1	0	4	410	112
3	1	4	8	280	92
4	1	8	12	390	41
5	1	12	18	450	29
6	1	18	24	415	12
7	1	24	48	1730	2.6

Records per page: 10 25 29
Showing 1 to 29 of 29 entries

NEXT

Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting Data Filters

Data file

BROWSE...

From data formatting

Data information

Urine Plasma

Regressor for urine volume

VOLUME

Units

TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = milligram

AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	REGRESSOR	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	INFUSION DURATION	CENSORING
LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	VOLUME	CONC	AMT	INF DUR	CENS
1	1						
2	1	0	0		146	2	
3	1	0	0				
4	1	4	410	112			notCensored
5	1	8	280	92			notCensored
6	1	12	390	41			notCensored
7	1	18	450	29			notCensored

Records per page: 10 25 36
Showing 1 to 36 of 36 entries - 4 individuals

2.2.4.11 Adding new columns from an external file

The last subtab is used to insert additional columns in the dataset from a separate file. The external file must contain a table with a column named ID or id with the same subject identifiers as in the dataset to format, and other columns with a header name and individual values (numbers or strings). There can be only one value per individual, which means that the additional columns inserted in the formatted dataset can contain only a constant value within each individual, and not time-varying values.

Examples of additional columns that can be added with this option are:

- individual parameters estimated in a previous analysis, to be read as regressors to avoid estimating them. **Time-varying regressors are not handled.**
- new covariates.

If occasions are defined in the formatted dataset, it is possible to have an occasion column in the external file and values defined per subject-occasion.

Example:

- demo **warfarin_PKPDseq_project.mlxtran** (can be imported into PKanalix):

This demo has an initial PKPD dataset in Monolix-standard format. The option “Additional columns” is used to add the PK parameters estimated on the PK part of the data in another Monolix project.

The image shows two screenshots from the Monolix software interface. The top screenshot shows the 'Data formatting' tab with the 'Additional columns' sub-tab selected. A file named 'warfarinPK_regressors.txt' is loaded, and a preview table is displayed:

id	Tlag_mode	ka_mode	V_mode	Cl_mode
1	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
2	0.739306	0.906915	8.35584	0.128526
3	0.909005	0.955194	8.46397	0.112645
4	0.893931	1.42947	5.08504	0.072557
5	0.851363	1.36498	11.5598	0.176061

A blue arrow points from the 'PREVIEW' button in the top screenshot to the bottom screenshot. The bottom screenshot shows the 'Data file' tab with various settings for units and regressors. A table of the formatted data is shown, with the regressor columns highlighted in an orange box:

LINE NUMBER	id	time	amt	dv	dvid	wt	sex	age	Tlag_mode	ka_mode	V_mode	Cl_mode
1	1	0	100			66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
2	1	0		98	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
3	1	24		9.2	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
4	1	24		49	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
5	1	36		8.5	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
6	1	36		32	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
7	1	48		6.4	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825

2.2.4.12 Exporting the formatted dataset

Once data formatting is done and the new dataset is accepted, the project can be saved and it is possible to export the formatted dataset as a csv file from the main menu **Export > Export formatted data**.

Note that if you did some data formatting directly in Monolix (instead of PKanalix), the possibility to save the project and export the formatted data is enabled only after loading a model in the structural model tab.

2.2.4.13 Data formatting presets

Starting from the 2024R1 version, if users need to perform the same or similar data formatting steps with each new project, a data formatting preset can be created and applied for new projects.

A typical workflow for using data formatting presets is as follows:

1. Data formatting steps are performed on a specific project.
2. Steps are saved in a data formatting preset.
3. Preset is reapplied on multiple new projects (manually or automatically).

2.2.4.13.1 Creating a data formatting preset

After data formatting steps are done on a project, a preset can be created by clicking on the New button in the bottom left corner of the interface, while in the Data formatting tab:

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. At the top, there are tabs for 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. Under 'Data', there are sub-tabs: 'Data formatting', 'Initialization', 'Observations', 'Treatments', and 'Additional columns'. The 'Data formatting' sub-tab is active, showing a 'Data file' section with a file path and a 'BROWSE...' button. To the right, there are 'Lines settings' with 'Header lines' (1 x 2 x) and 'Lines to exclude' (empty) fields. Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, STUDY, and LLOQ_mg_L. The table contains 8 rows of data. At the bottom left, there is a 'NEW +' button highlighted with a red box, and an 'APPLY' button below it. The bottom of the interface shows pagination information: 'Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 512 866', 'Page 1 of 18', and 'Showing 1 to 50 of 866 entries'.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	CONC_mg_L	AGE	WT	STUDY	LLOQ_mg_L
1	ID	TIME	CONC	AGE	WT	STUDY	LLOQ
2		h	mg/L				mg/L
3	1	0	BLQ	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
4	1	1	BLQ	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
5	1	2	0.0638908	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
6	1	3	0.213188	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
7	1	4	0.35487	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
8	1	5	0.46173	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01

Clicking on this button will open a pop-up window with a form that contains four parts:

New custom preset from current data formatting

Name:

INITIALIZATION
 OBSERVATIONS
 TREATMENTS

Description:
Add description

Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps

CANCEL

CREATE

1. **Name:** contains a name of the preset, this information will be used to distinguish between presets when applying them.
2. **Configuration:** contains three checkboxes (initialization, observations, treatments). Users can choose which steps of data formatting will be saved in the preset. If option “External” was used in creating treatments, the external file paths will not be saved in the preset.
3. **Description:** a custom description can be added.
4. **Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps:** if ticked, the preset will be automatically applied every time a data set is loaded for data formatting in PKanalix and Monolix.

After saving the preset by clicking on Create, the description will be updated with the summary of all the steps performed in data formatting.

Important to note is that if a user wants to save censoring information in the data formatting preset, and the censored tags change between projects (e.g., censoring tag <LOQ=0.1> with varying numbers is used in different projects), the option “Use all automatically detected tags” should be used in the Observations tab. This way, no specific censoring tags will be saved in the preset, but they will be automatically detected and applied each time a preset is applied.

Censoring tags
↻

Use all automatically detected tags
(recommended for creating presets in case of dataset dependent censoring tags)

BLQ ×

×

2.2.4.13.2 Applying a preset

A preset can be applied manually using the Apply button in the bottom left corner of the data formatting tab. Clicking on the Apply button will open a dropdown selection of all saved presets and the desired preset can be chosen.

The Apply button is enabled only after the initialization step is performed (ID and TIME columns are selected and the button Next was clicked). This allows PKanalix/Monolix to fall back to the initialized state, if the initialization step from a preset fails (e.g., if ID and TIME column header saved in the presets do not exist in the new data set).

After applying a preset, all data formatting steps saved in the preset will try to be applied. If it is not possible to apply certain steps (e.g., some censoring tags or column headers saved in a preset do not exist), the error message will appear.

Manage data formatting presets
×

Presets list

Custom presets

- DF_preset
- Plasma
- Plasma_infusion
- Urine

+ NEW
DELETED
IMPORT
EXPORT

Preset information

DF_preset ✎

Data formatting: OBSERVATIONS TREATMENTS

Description:

Here is a sample user-defined description.

OBSERVATIONS:

tags = BLQ

CONC_mg_L

interval = (tags = BLQ, loq = (fromData = LLOQ_mg_L, limit = (value = 0)))

TREATMENT:

Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps

CLOSE

2.2.4.13.3 Managing presets

Presets can be created, deleted, edited, imported and exported by clicking on Settings > Manage Presets > Data Formatting.

The pop-window allows users to:

1. **Create presets:** clicking on the button New has the same behavior as clicking on the button New in the Data formatting tab (described in the section “Creating a data formatting preset”).
2. **Delete presets:** clicking on the button Delete will permanently delete a preset. Clicking on this button will not ask for confirmation.
3. **Edit presets:** by clicking on a preset in the left panel, the preset information will appear in the right panel. Name and preset description of the presets can then be updated, and a preset can be selected to automatically format data in PKanalix and Monolix.
4. **Export presets:** a selected preset can be exported as a lixpst file which can be shared between users and imported using the Import button.
5. **Import presets:** a user can import a preset from a lixpst file exported from another computer.

Additionally, an option to pin presets (always show them on top) can be used by clicking on the icon to facilitate the usage of presets when a user has a lot of them.

2.3 Tagging a data set

2.3.1 Column tagging

After loading a formatted data set directly, or previewing a data set that has gone through data formatting, users need to assign meaning to different columns of the formatted data set.

This is done in the Data tab by clicking on the dropdown menus above each of the column headers:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	IGNORE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
	ID	TIME	AMT	CONC	BLQ	STUDY
2	1	0	50	.	.	101
3	1	0.5	.	3.05	0	101
4	1	2	.	5.92	0	101
5	1	4	.	4.7	0	101
6	1	6	.	4.14	0	101
7	1	8	.	4.65	0	101
8	1	12	.	2.64	0	101
9	1	18	.	2	0	101
10	1	24	.	1.8	1	101
11	1	30	.	1.8	1	101
12	2	0	50	.	.	101
13	2	0.5	.	6.24	0	101
14	2	2	.	7.08	0	101

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 1000
 << < Page 1 of 20 > >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 1,000 entries - 100 individuals

CANCEL **ACCEPT**

After tagging the columns and accepting the data set, the interpreted data set is shown. The interpreted data set may be different from original data set, as it shows a data set after data formatting and filtering steps were applied. It also includes doses added through the ADDL column and steady state settings, additional covariates, interpolated values of regressors, censoring information as strings, ...

The information about the meaning of each of the dropdown option can be found on these pages:

- [Columns used to define controls and events](#)
- [Columns used to define regressors](#)
- [Columns used to define covariates](#)
- [Columns used to define doses](#)
- [Columns used to define time](#)
- [Columns used to define observations](#)
- [Columns used to identify subject-occasions](#)

2.3.2 Automatic column tagging

MonolixSuite applications automatically suggest column types based on the headers in the data, which can be customized in the preferences. Clicking on Settings>Preferences, displays the following window where mapped headers can be added or removed.

Data

Header types

- ID
- TIME
- OBSERVATION
- AMOUNT
- CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- OCCASION
- EVENT ID
- IGNORED OBSERVATION
- OBSERVATION ID
- CENSORING
- LIMIT
- REGRESSOR

Related headers

- #id
- subj
- id
- nid
- subject
- sdeid

Header name

+ ADD HEADER

In the Data section, you can add or remove preferences for each column.

- To remove a mapping, double-click on the preference you would like to remove. A confirmation window will appear.

- To add a mapping, click on the header type you want to use, add a column name in the 'header name' field and click on "ADD HEADER" as shown here.

Note that the header mapping preferences are shared between Monolix and PKanalix.

Starting with version 2024, the preferences can be updated with the columns tagged in the current project by clicking on the icon in the top left corner of the data table:

LINE NUMBER ↕	ID ↕
2	1
3	1

This will open a window with the option to choose which of the tagged headers to add to preferences:

Send header types to preferences

 Hide up to date aliases

- id** : Already defined in *ID*
- time** : Already defined in *TIME*
- y** : Already defined in *OBSERVATION*
- z** : Add to *REGRESSOR*

CANCEL

OK

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6CTyrut93v8>

2.4 Specifying observation types and regressor settings

During and after the data tagging procedure, the Data information section is available in the Data tab.

Data information

1 CONTINUOUS ▾

2 CONTINUOUS ▾

Regressors settings

Last carried forward Linear interpolation

The Data information section contains:

1. dropdown(s) for definition of observation types,
2. regressor settings (if at least one of the columns was tagged as a regressor column).

2.4.1 Observation types

There are three possible types of observations in Monolix:

- *continuous*: The observation is continuous and can take any value within a range. For example, a concentration is a continuous observation.
- *count/categorical*: The observation values can take values only in a finite categorical space. For example, the observation can be a categorical observation (an effect can be observed as “low”, “medium”, or “high”) or a count observation over a defined time (the number of epileptic crisis in a week).
- *event*: The observation is an event, for example the time of death.

For each OBSERVATION ID, the type of observations must be specified by the user in the interface. Depending on the choice, the data will be displayed in the Observed Data plot in different ways (e.g spaghetti plot for continuous data and Kaplan-Meier plot for event data). The mapping of model outputs and observations from the dataset will also take into account the data type (e.g a model output of type “event” can only be mapped to an observation that is also an “event”). Once a model has been selected, the choice of the data types are locked (because they are enforced by the model output type).

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. The 'Data' tab is active, and the 'Data information' section is highlighted with a green box. It shows two rows of data type selection: Row 1 is set to 'CONTINUOUS' and Row 2 is set to 'EVENT'. Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, AMT, Y, and YTYPE. The table shows data for 5 rows, with the first row having ID 1, TIME 0, AMT 0.25, and YTYPE 2. The interface also shows a 'Data file' path and 'BROWSE...' and 'FORMAT' buttons.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMT	Y	YTYPE
1	1				
2	1	0	0.25		
3	1	0		0	2
4	1	0.5		0.0112	1
5	1	4		0.0307	1

2.4.2 Regressor settings

If columns have been tagged as **REGRESSORS**, the interpolation method for the regressors can be chosen.

Regressors are defined over time for a finite number of time points. In between those time points, the regressor value can be interpolated in two different ways:

- **last value carried forward**: if we have defined reg_A at time t_A and reg_B at time t_B
 - for $t < t_A$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [first defined value is used]

- for $t_A \leq t < t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [previous value is used]
- for $t \geq t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_B$ [previous value is used]
- **linear interpolation:**
 - for $t < t_A$, $reg(t) = reg_A$ [first defined value is used]
 - for $t_A \leq t < t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_A + (t - t_A) \frac{reg_B - reg_A}{t_B - t_A}$ [linear interpolation is used]
 - for $t \geq t_B$, $reg(t) = reg_B$ [previous value is used]

The interpolation is used to obtain the regressor value at times not defined in the dataset. This is necessary to integrate ODE-based models (which are using an internal adaptative time step), or obtain prediction on a fine grid for the plots (e.g in the Individuals fits) for instance.

When some dataset lines have a missing regressor value (dot "."), the same interpolation method is used.

LINE NUMBER	SUBJ	TIME	DV	WT	SEX	AGE	Cc
1	1			66.7	1	50	
2	1	0	98	66.7	1	50	0
3	1	24	49	66.7	1	50	9.36576
4	1	36	32	66.7	1	50	7.87517
5	1	48	26	66.7	1	50	6.62182

2.5 Filtering a data set

Due to technical reasons, the filtering option in Monolix is only available after loading a model. So, the workflow is as follows: load the data set, load a dummy model, filter the data set, change the structural model.

Starting on the 2020 version, filtering a data set to only take a subpart into account in your modelization is possible. It allows to make filters on some specific IDs, times, measurement values,... It is also possible to define complementary filters and also filters of filters. It is accessible through the filters item on the data tab.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	DV	AMT	SEX	WEIGHT
1	1				F	70.6466
2	1	0		100	F	70.6466
3	1	1	16.6314		F	70.6466
4	1	1.5	21.5208		F	70.6466
5	1	2	11.746		F	70.6466
6	1	2.5	20.0199		F	70.6466
7	1	3	11.9624		F	70.6466
8	1	4	10.7658		F	70.6466
9	1	5	13.9579		F	70.6466
10	1	6	8.71148		F	70.6466
11	1	8	17.574		F	70.6466
12	1	10	8.24835		F	70.6466
13	1	12	5.81872		F	70.6466
14	1	18	4.55314		F	70.6466

2.5.1 Creation of a filter

To create a filter, you need to click on the data set name. You can then create a “child”. It corresponds to a subpart of the data set where you will define your filtering actions.

You can see on the top (in the green rectangle) the action that you will complete and you can CANCEL, ACCEPT, or ACCEPT & APPLY with the bottoms on the bottom.

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. The main window displays a data flow from 'data_covariates.csv' to 'data_covariates_filtered'. A dialog box titled 'data_covariates_filtered' is open, showing a table for defining filtering actions. The table has the following structure:

action	header	operator	value
select ids	ID	=	1

At the bottom of the dialog, there are three buttons: 'CANCEL', 'ACCEPT', and 'ACCEPT & APPLY'.

2.5.2 Filtering a data set: actions

In all the filtering actions, you need to define

- An **action**: it corresponds to one of the following possibilities: select ids, remove ids, select lines, remove lines.
- A **header**: it corresponds to the column of the data set you wish to have an action on. Notice that it corresponds to a column of the data set that was tagged with a header.
- An **operator**: it corresponds to the operator of choice ($=$, \neq , $<$, \leq , $>$, or \geq).
- A **value**. When the header contains numerical values, the user can define it. When the header contains strings, a list is proposed.

For example, you can

- Remove the ID 1 from your study:

action	header	operator	value
remove ids ▾	ID ▾	= ▾	1

In that case, all the IDs except ID = 1 will be used for the study.

- Select all the lines where the time is less or equal 24:

action	header	operator	value
select lines ▾	TIME ▾	≤ ▾	24

In that case, all lines with time strictly greater than 24 will be removed. If a subject has no measurement anymore, it will be removed from the study.

- Select all the ids where SEX equals F:

action	header	operator	value
select lines ▾	SEX ▾	= ▾	F ▾

In that case, all the male subjects will be removed from the study.

- Remove all Ids where WEIGHT less or equal 65:

action	header	operator	value
remove ids ▾	WEIGHT ▾	≤ ▾	65

In that case, only the subjects with a weight over 65 will be kept for the study.

In any case, the interpreted filter data set will be displayed in the data tab.

2.5.3 Filters with several actions

In the previous examples, we only did one action. It is also possible to do several actions to define a filter. We have the possibility to define UNION and/or INTERSECTION of actions.

2.5.3.1 Intersection

By clicking by the + and – button on the right, you can define an intersection of actions. For example, by clicking on the +, you can define a filter corresponding to intersection of

- The IDs that are different to 1.
- The lines with the time values less than 24.

	action	header	operator	value	
	select ids ▾	ID ▾	≠ ▾	1	-
INTERSECTION	select lines ▾	TIME ▾	≤ ▾	24	- +

Thus in that case, all the lines with a time less than 24 and corresponding to an ID different than 1 will be used in the study. If we look at the following data set as an example

2.5.3.2 Union

By clicking by the + and - button on the bottom, you can define an union of actions. For example, in a data set with a multi dose, I can focus on the first and the last dose. Thus, by clicking on the +, you can define a filter corresponding to union of

- The lines where the time is strictly less than 12.
- The lines where the time is greater than 72.

select lines ▾
TIME ▾
< ▾
12
▾

UNION

select lines ▾
ID ▾
= ▾
12
▾

UNION

select lines ▾
AMT ▾
= ▾
100
▾

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	3.365
1	0.5		2.4718
1	1		2.5617
1	3		1.8819
1	5		2.1349
1	7		1.6741
1	9		2.0317
1	11		4.219
1	12	40	3.3258
1	12.5		3.4157
1	13		2.7359
1	15		2.9889
1	17		2.5281
1	19		2.8857
1	21		...
1	23		...
1	24	40	...
1	72	40	...
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

select lines with
time < 12

➔

select lines with time > 72

➔

select lines
with amt = 40

➔

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	3.365
1	0.5		2.4718
1	1		2.5617
1	3		1.8819
1	5		2.1349
1	7		1.6741
1	9		2.0317
1	11		4.219
1	12	40	3.3258
1	12.5		3.4157
1	13		2.7359
1	15		2.9889
1	17		2.5281
1	19		2.8857
1	21		...
1	23		...
1	24	40	...
1	72	40	...
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	3.365
1	0.5		2.4718
1	1		2.5617
1	3		1.8819
1	5		2.1349
1	7		1.6741
1	9		2.0317
1	11		4.219
1	12	40	3.3258
1	12.5		3.4157
1	13		2.7359
1	15		2.9889
1	17		2.5281
1	19		2.8857
1	21		...
1	23		...
1	24	40	...
1	72	40	...
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

Union of all three

Notice that, if just define the first two actions, all the dose lines at a time in]12, 72[will also be removed. Thus, to keep having all the doses, we need to add the condition of selecting the lines where the dose is defined.

In addition, it is possible to do any combination of INTERSECTION and UNION.

2.5.3.3 Other filters: filter of filter and complementary filters

Filtering a data set can be nested. Based on the definition of a filter, by clicking on the filter, it is possible to create:

- A **child**: it corresponds to a new filter with the initial filter as the source data set.
- A **complement**: corresponds to the complement of the filter. For example, if you defined a filter with only the IDs where the SEX is F, then the complement corresponds to the IDs where the SEX is not F.

2.6 Data exploration

2.6.1 Data exploration

Once the dataset has been tagged and accepted:

- **Plots** are automatically generated based on the interpreted dataset to help you explore the data before running any of the tasks.

- The **interpreted dataset** appears in Data tab, which shows the final dataset after formatting, setting units, and filtering.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	ADMINISTRATION ID	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
1	1	0		100	1	IV
2	1	0.083	3826.27			IV
3	1	0.25	3101.72			IV
4	1	0.5	3955.83			IV
5	1	1	3024.63			IV
6	1	2	3441.82			IV
7	1	8	3869.37			IV
8	1	12	3127.52			IV
9	1	24	2259.83			IV

- **Covariate Statistics** appear in a section of the data tab.

2.7 How Monolix handles censored data

Objectives: learn how to handle easily and properly censored data, i.e. data below (resp. above) a lower (resp.upper) limit of quantification (LOQ) or below a limit of detection (LOD).

Projects: censoring1log_project, censoring1_project, censoring2_project, censoring3_project, censoring4_project

2.7.1 Introduction

Censoring occurs when the value of a measurement or observation is only partially known. For continuous data measurements in the longitudinal context, censoring refers to the values of the measurements, not the times at which they were taken. For example, the lower limit of detection (LLOD) is the lowest quantity of a substance that can be distinguished from its absence. Therefore, any time the quantity is below the LLOD, the “observation” is not a measurement but the information that the measured quantity is less than the LLOD. Similarly, in longitudinal studies of viral kinetics, measurements of the viral load below a certain limit, referred to as the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), are so low that their reliability is considered suspect. A measuring device can also have an upper limit of quantification (ULOQ) such that any value above this limit cannot be measured and reported.

As hinted above, censored values are not typically reported as a number, but their existence is known, as well as the type of censoring. Thus, the observation $y_{ij}^{(r)}$ (i.e., what is reported) is the measurement y_{ij} if not censored, and the type of censoring otherwise. We usually distinguish between three types of censoring: left, right and interval. In each case, the SAEM algorithm implemented in Monolix properly computes the maximum likelihood estimate of the population parameters, combining all the information provided by censored and non censored data.

2.7.2 Theory

In the presence of censored data, the conditional density function needs to be computed carefully. To cover all three types of censoring (left, right, interval), let I_{ij} be the (finite or infinite) censoring interval existing for individual i at time t_{ij} . Then,

$$p(\mathbf{y}^{(r)} | \boldsymbol{\psi}) = \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{j=1}^{n_i} p(y_{ij} | \psi_i)^{\mathbf{1}_{y_{ij} \notin I_{ij}}} \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \in I_{ij} | \psi_i)^{\mathbf{1}_{y_{ij} \in I_{ij}}}$$

where

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \in I_{ij} | \psi_i) = \int_{I_{ij}} p_{y_{ij} | \psi_i}(u | \psi_i) du$$

We see that if y_{ij} is not censored (i.e. $\mathbf{1}_{y_{ij} \notin I_{ij}} = 1$), its contribution to the likelihood is the usual $p(y_{ij} | \psi_i)$, whereas if it is censored, the contribution is $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \in I_{ij} | \psi_i)$.

For the calculation of the likelihood, this is equivalent to the M3 method in NONMEM when only the CENSORING column is given, and to the M4 method when both a CENSORING column and a LIMIT column are given.

2.7.3 Censoring definition in a data set

In the dataset format used by Monolix and PKanalix, censored information is included in this way:

- The censored measurement should be in the **OBSERVATION** column.
- In an additional **CENSORING** column, put 0 if the observation is not censored, and 1 or - 1 depending if the measurement given in the observation column is a lower or an upper limit.
- Optionally, include a **LIMIT** column to set the other limit.

To quickly include censoring information to your dataset by using BLQ tags in the observation column, you can use data formatting.

Examples are provided below and [here](#).

2.7.4 PK data below a lower limit of quantification

2.7.4.1 Left censored data

- **censoring1log_project** (data = 'censored1log_data.txt', model = 'pklog_model.txt')

PK data are log-concentration in this example. The limit of quantification of 1.8 mg/l for concentrations becomes $\log(1.8)=0.588$ for log-concentrations. The column of observations (Y) contains either the LLOQ for data below the limit of quantification (BLQ data) or the measured log-concentrations for non BLQ data. Furthermore, Monolix uses an additional column **CENSORING** to indicate if an observation is left censored (CENS=1) or not (CENS=0). In this example, subject 1 has two BLQ data at times 24h and 30h (the measured log-concentrations were below 0.588 at these times):

ID	TIME	AMT	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS	CENS
1	0	50	.	.
1	0.5	.	1.115	0
1	2	.	1.778	0
1	4	.	1.548	0
1	6	.	1.421	0
1	8	.	1.537	0
1	12	.	0.971	0
1	18	.	0.693	0
1	24	.	0.588	1
1	30	.	0.588	1

The plot of individual fits displays BLQ (red band) and non BLQ data (blue dots) together with the predicted log-concentrations (purple line) on the whole time interval:

Notice that the band goes from .8 to -Infinity as no bound has been specified (no [LIMIT](#) column was proposed).

For diagnosis plots such as VPC, residuals of observations versus predictions, Monolix samples the BLQ data from the conditional distribution

$$p(y^{BLQ} | y^{nonBLQ}, \hat{\psi}, \hat{\theta})$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\psi}$ are the estimated population and individual parameters. This is done by adding a residual error on top of the prediction, using a truncated normal distribution to make sure that the simulated BLQ remains within the censored interval. This is the most efficient way to take into account the complete information provided by the data and the model for diagnosis plots such as VPCs:

A strong bias appears if LLOQ is used instead for the BLQ data (if you choose LOQ instead of simulated in the display frame of the settings):

Notice that ignoring the BLQ data entails a loss of information as can be seen below (if you choose no in the "Use BLQ" toggle):

As can be seen below, imputed BLQ data is also used for residuals (IWRES on the left) and for observations versus predictions (on the right).

2.7.4.2 More on these diagnosis plots

2.7.4.2.1 Impact of the BLQ in residuals and observations versus predictions plots

A strong bias appears if LLOQ is used instead for the BLQ data for these two diagnosis plots:

while ignoring the BLQ data entails a loss of information:

2.7.4.2.2 BLQ predictive checks

The BLQ predictive check is a diagnosis plot that displays the fraction of cumulative BLQ data (blue line) with a 90% prediction interval (blue area).

2.7.4.3 Interval censored data

- **censoring1_project** (data = 'censored1_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVk.txt')

We use the original concentrations in this project. Then, BLQ data should be treated as interval censored data since a concentration is known to be positive. In other words, a data reported as BLQ data means that the (non reported) measured concentration is between 0 and 1.8mg/l. The value in the observation column 1.8 indicates the value, the value in the **CENSORING** column indicates that the value in the observation column is the upper bound. An additional column **LIMIT** reports the lower limit of the censored interval (0 in this example):

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS	LIMIT	CENSORING
ID	TIME	AMT	Y	LIMIT	CENS
1	0	50	.	.	.
1	0.5	.	3.05	.	0
1	2	.	5.92	.	0
1	4	.	4.7	.	0
1	6	.	4.14	.	0
1	8	.	4.65	.	0
1	12	.	2.64	.	0
1	18	.	2	.	0
1	24	.	1.8	0	1
1	30	.	1.8	0	1

2.7.4.3.1 Remarks

- if this column is missing, then BLQ data is assumed to be left-censored data that can take any positive and negative value below LLOQ.
- the value of the limit can vary between observations of the same subject.

Monolix will use this additional information to estimate the model parameters properly and to impute the BLQ data for the diagnosis plots.

Plot of individual fits now displays LLOD at 1.8 with a red band when a PK data is censored. We see that the band lower limit is at 0 as defined in the limit column.

2.7.5 PK data below a lower limit of quantification or below a limit of detection

- **censoring2_project** (data = 'censored2_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVk.txt')

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	LIMIT	CENSORING
ID	TIME	AMT	Y	LIMIT	CENS
1	0	50	.	.	.
1	0.5	.	3.72	.	0
1	2	.	5.17	.	0
1	4	.	5.3	.	0
1	6	.	3.58	.	0
1	8	.	4.03	.	0
1	12	.	3.02	.	0
1	18	.	2.17	.	0
1	24	.	1.8	1.2	1
1	30	.	1.2	0	1

Plot of individual fits now displays LLOQ or LLOD with a red band when a PK data is censored. We see that the band lower limits depend on the observation.

2.7.6 PK data below a lower limit of quantification and PD data above an upper limit of quantification

- **censoring3_project** (data = 'censored3_data.txt', model = 'pkpd_model.txt')

We work with PK and PD data in this project and assume that the PD data may be right censored and that the upper limit of quantification is $ULOQ=90$. We use `CENS=-1` to indicate that an observation is right censored. In such case, the PD data can take any value above the upper limit reported in column `Y` (here the `YTYPE` column of type `OBSERVATION ID` defines the type of observation, `YTYPE=1` and `YTYPE=2` are used respectively for PK and PD data):

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	OBSERVATION ID	LIMIT	CENSORING
ID	TIME	AMT	Y	YTYPE	LIMIT	CENS
1	0	50
1	0	.	55.7	2	.	0
1	0.5	.	4.52	1	.	0
1	2	.	5.43	1	.	0
1	4	.	3.86	1	.	0
1	4	.	90	2	.	-1
1	6	.	2.45	1	.	0
1	8	.	3.86	1	.	0
1	8	.	90	2	.	-1
1	12	.	2.22	1	.	0

Plot of individual fits for the PD data now displays ULOQ and the predicted PD profile:

We can display the cumulative fraction of censored data both for the PK and the PD data (on the left and right respectively):

2.7.7 Combination of interval censored PK and PD data

- **censoring4_project** (data = 'censored4_data.txt', model = 'pkpd_model.txt')

We assume in this example

- 2 different censoring intervals (0,1) and (1.2, 1.8) for the PK,
- a censoring interval (80,90) and right censoring (>90) for the PD.

Combining columns **CENS**, **LIMIT** and **Y** allow us to combine efficiently these different censoring processes:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS	OBSERVATION ID	LIMIT	CENSORING
ID	TIME	AMT	OBS ID 1	YTYPE	LIMIT	CENS	
1	0	50	-	-	-	-	-
1	0	-	64.1	2	-	-	0
1	0.5	-	1.8	1	1.2	1	1
1	2	-	4.1	1	-	-	0
1	4	-	4.58	1	-	-	0
1	4	-	90	2	-	-	-1
1	6	-	5.39	1	-	-	0
1	8	-	2.81	1	-	-	0
1	8	-	90	2	-	-	-1
1	12	-	3.57	1	-	-	0
1	12	-	90	2	80	1	1
1	16	-	90	2	80	1	1
1	18	-	2.48	1	-	-	0
1	20	-	90	2	80	1	1
1	24	-	1.8	1	1.2	1	1
1	24	-	77.8	2	-	-	0
1	28	-	71.6	2	-	-	0
1	30	-	1	1	0	1	1
1	32	-	70.3	2	-	-	0

This coding of the data means that, for subject 1,

- PK data is between 0 and 1 at time 30h (second blue frame),
- PK data is between 1.2 and 1.8 at times 0.5h and 24h (first blue frame for time .5h),
- PD data is between 80 and 90 at times 12h and 16h (second green frame for time 12h),
- PD data is above 90 at times 4h and 8h (first green frame for time 4h).

Plot of individual fits for the PK and the PD data displays the different limits of these censoring intervals (PK on the left and PD on the right):

Other diagnosis plots, such as the plot of observations versus predictions, adequately use imputed censored PK and PD data:

2.7.8 Case studies

- **8.case_studies/hiv_project** (data = 'hiv_data.txt', model = 'hivLatent_model.txt')
- **8.case_studies/hcv_project** (data = 'hcv_data.txt', model = 'hcvNeumann98_model_latent.txt')

2.8 Import a PKanalix project

2.8.1 Importing a project from Datxplore or PKanalix

It is possible to import a project from Datxplore or PKanalix. For that, go to Project>Import from>Datxplore/PKanalix (as in the green box of the following figure). In that case, a new project will be created and all the DATA tab will already be filled by the information from the Datxplore or PKanalix project (including data formatting and data filtering).

2.9 Data set examples

Here you can download examples of MonolixSuite formatted data sets and see their references, descriptions and explanations of columns:

2.9.1 Continuous data

2.9.1.1 Warfarin data set

Download data set: warfarin_data.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

O'Reilly (1968). Studies on coumarin anticoagulant drugs. Initiation of warfarin therapy without a loading dose. Circulation 1968, 38:169-177.

Warfarin is an anticoagulant normally used in the prevention of thrombosis and thromboembolism, the formation of blood clots in the blood vessels and their migration elsewhere in the body, respectively. The data set provides set of plasma warfarin concentrations and Prothrombin Complex Response in thirty normal subjects after a single loading dose. A single large loading dose of warfarin sodium, 1.5 mg/kg of body weight, was administered orally to all subjects. Measurements were made each 12 or

24h.

On the two following figure, one could see the concentration and the effect with respect to time for all subjects.

The data set for subject one can be defined as follows

id	time	amt	dv	dvid	wt	age	sex
1	0	100	.	1	66.7	50	1
1	0	.	100	2	66.7	50	1
1	24	.	9.2	1	66.7	50	1
1	24	.	49	2	66.7	50	1

1	36	.	8.5	1	66.7	50	1
1	36	.	32	2	66.7	50	1
1	48	.	6.4	1	66.7	50	1
1	48	.	26	2	66.7	50	1
1	72	.	4.8	1	66.7	50	1
1	72	.	22	2	66.7	50	1
1	96	.	3.1	1	66.7	50	1
1	96	.	28	2	66.7	50	1
1	120	.	2.5	1	66.7	50	1
1	120	.	33	2	66.7	50	1

2.9.1.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- id: the subject ID, column-type ID
- time: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- amt: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT.
- dv: the measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.
- dvid: the type of measurement. In this study, one has two measurement, the concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the Prothrombin Complex Response (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- wt: Weight of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- age: Age of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- sex: Sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. The first line corresponds to a dose, while the other ones are measurements. This explains the dot in the CONC column for the first line and the dots in the AMT column for the other ones.
2. The covariates columns (the continuous wt and the categorical covariates age and sex) are filled with the same values. Even though it is not necessary, we encourage the user to fill the columns for readability and usage reasons.
3. In the presented case, both PK and PD measurements are at the same time, this is not required for data exploration using Datxplora, nor parameter estimation using Monolix.
4. Finally, notice that no initial washout is needed at the beginning as by default, the null initial condition is used for parameter estimation.

Interestingly, one can display the Effect with respect to the Concentration in order to have an idea on how to model the interaction between the PD and the PK part.

Then, the response does not seem to be direct. **Notice that, as the observation times are not the same between the PK and the PD, interpolation is made to propose this kind of plot.** One can also focus on one individual in particular as on the following figure

Notice that we also propose a red arrow to describe the evolution of time.

2.9.1.2 Theophylline data set

Download data set: [theophylline_data.txt](#)

The data considered here are courtesy of Dr. Robert A. Upton of the University of California, San Francisco. Theophylline is a methylxanthine drug used in therapy for respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma under a variety of brand names. Theophylline was administered orally to 12 subjects whose serum concentrations were measured at 11 times over the next 25 hours. This is an example of a laboratory pharmacokinetic study characterized by many observations on a moderate number of individuals. A representation of the concentration over time for each subject is presented on the following figure.

The purpose of this page is to see the construction, the definition and the use of such a data set in Datxplore and Monolix. For sake of simplicity, we look only on one subject (corresponding to ID 1).

2.9.1.2.1 Simplified data set

The data set for subject one writes as follows

ID	AMT	TIME	CONC	WEIGHT	SEX
1	4.02	0	.	79.6	M
1	.	0.25	2.84	79.6	M
1	.	0.57	6.57	79.6	M
1	.	1.12	10.5	79.6	M
1	.	2.02	9.66	79.6	M
1	.	3.82	8.58	79.6	M
1	.	5.1	8.36	79.6	M
1	.	7.03	7.47	79.6	M
1	.	9.05	6.89	79.6	M
1	.	12.12	5.94	79.6	M
1	.	24.37	3.28	79.6	M

2.9.1.2.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- AMT: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT.
- TIME: the time of the event, column-type TIME.
- CONC: the measured concentration, column-type OBSERVATION.
- WEIGHT: Weight of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- SEX: Sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. The first line corresponds to a dose, while the other ones are measurements. This explains the dot in the CONC column for the first line and the dots in the AMT column for the other ones.
2. The covariates columns (the continuous WEIGHT and the categorical SEX) are constant over the individual. Even though it is not necessary, we encourage the user to fill the columns for readability and usage reasons.
3. Finally, notice that no initial washout is needed at the beginning as by default, the null initial condition is used for parameter estimation.

2.9.1.3 Tobramycin data set

Download data set: tobramycin.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

Aarons, L., Vozeh, S., Wenk, M., Weiss, P. H., & Follath, F. (1989). Population pharmacokinetics of tobramycin. British journal of clinical pharmacology, 28(3), 305-314.

Tobramycin is an antimicrobial agent of the aminoglycosides family, which is among others used against severe gram-negative infections. Because tobramycin does not pass the gastro-intestinal tract, it is usually administrated intravenously as intermittent bolus doses or short infusions. Tobramycin is a

drug with a narrow therapeutic index.

Tobramycin bolus doses ranging from 20 to 140mg were administrated every 8 hours in 97 patients (45 females, 52 male) during 1 to 21 days (for most patients, during ~6 days). Age, weight (kg), sex and creatinine clearance (mL/min) were available as covariates. The tobramycin concentration (mg/L) was measured 1 to 9 times per patients (322 measures in total), most of the time between 2 and 6h post-dose. This sparse data set is presented on the figure below

Below is an extract of the data set:

ID	TIME	CP	EVID	DOSE	WT	AGE	SEX	CLCR
2	0	0	1	100	69.5	72	0	39
2	8	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	16	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	24	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	26	7.12	0	0	69.5	72	0	39
2	30	2.98	0	0	69.5	72	0	39

The columns have the following meaning:

- ID: the subject's ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the record (administration or measurement) in hours, column-type TIME.

- CP: the measured drug's concentration in mg/L, column-type OBSERVATION.
- EVID: event identifier, 1 for doses and 0 for response lines (measurements), column-type EVENT ID.
- DOSE: the amount of drug administrated to this subject in mg, column-type AMOUNT.
- WT: weight of the subject in kg, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- SEX: sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- CLCR: creatinine clearance of the subject in mL/min, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed:

1. The four first lines correspond to doses, while the other ones are measurements, as indicated by the EVID column. The MDV column is not necessary. The zeros of the DOSE and CP columns could have been replaced by dots '.'.
2. The covariates columns (WT, SEX and CLCR) are filled with the same value for each individual. Covariates must be constant within subjects (or subject-occasions when occasions are defined).

2.9.1.4 HIV data set

Download data set: hiv_data.txt

In the COPHAR II-ANRS 134 trial, an open prospective non-randomized interventional study, 115 HIV-infected patients adults started an antiviral therapy. 48 patients were treated with indinavir (and ritonavir as a booster) (treatment A), 38 with lopinavir (and ritonavir as a booster) (treatment B), and 35 with nelfinavir (Treatment C). patients were followed one year after treatment initialization.

Viral load and CD4 cell count were measured at screenin, at inclusion and at weeks 2 (or 4), 8, 16, 24, 36, and 48. Plasma HIV-1-RNA were measured by Roche monitored with a limit of quantification of 50 copies/ml. The results of this trial are reported in Duval and al. (2009).

On the two following figures, one could see the two outputs with respect to time for all subjects split by treatments. The red circle corresponds to censored data.

2.9.1.4.1 Simplified HIV data set

The data set for subject 2 can be defined as follows

ID	TIME	Y_NCENS	Y	CENS	YTYPE	TREATMENT
2	-2.43	4.9443	4.9443	0	1	A
2	-2.43	249	249	0	2	A
2	0	4.5245	4.5245	0	1	A

2	2	2.3546	2.3546	0	1	A
2	2	266	266	0	2	A
2	4.29	268	268	0	2	A
2	8	2.5585	2.5585	0	1	A
2	8	34	34	0	2	A
2	16	352	352	0	2	A
2	24	1.7981	2	1	1	A
2	24	385	385	0	2	A
2	32	348	348	0	2	A
2	43	415	415	0	2	A

2.9.1.4.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the measurement, column-type TIME.
- Y_NCENS: Non censored measurement. Ignored in the representation.
- Y: Considered measurement taking the censoring constraints into account, column-type OBSERVATION.
- CENS: Explicit if the data is censored or not, and the associated type of censoring, column-type CENSORING.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. In this study, one has two measurements, column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- TREATMENT: Type of treatment, considered as a categorical covariate in our case, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. There are no dose in the data set.
2. There is only a categorical covariate defining the treatment.
3. In the presented case, one does not necessary have both measurements at the same time. Indeed, this is not required for data export using Datxplore, nor parameter estimation using Monolix. Moreover, measurements for negative time is possible.

2.9.1.5 Remifentanil data set

Download data set: pkpdRemifentanil.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Influence of age and gender on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of remifentanil. I. Model development. Anesthesiology, Minto, et al. (1997)

Remifentanil is an opioid analgesic drug with a rapid onset and rapid recovery time. It is used for sedation as well as combined with other medications for use in general anesthesia. It is given in adults via continuous IV infusion.

65 healthy adults have received remifentanil IV infusion at a constant diffusion rate between 1 and 8 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 4 to 20 minutes. The data set contains remifentanil admission characteristics (time and rate of infusion), dense measurements of remifentanil blood concentration during infusion and after (PK data), as well as dense electroencephalogram measurements (PD data) recording the depth of anesthesia. In addition, a list of covariates is available: age, gender, and lean body mass (LBM). Moreover, a variable TINFCAT classifies the patients in several categories with similar infusion time.

One can see on the following figure the remifentanil concentrations over time split in two groups (female and male). On each figure, the subjects with age lower than 50 are in blue while the ones with an age over 50 are in green.

On the following figure, one can see the electroencephalogram measurements with respect to time for all subjects.

Below is an extract of the data set file:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	RATE	OBSERVATION YTYPE: 1 CONTINUOUS	YTYPE	MDV	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	TIME	AMT	RATE	DV	YTYPE	MDV	AGE	SEX	LBM	TINFCAT
1	0	.	.	18.85	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0	1439.8	71.99	.	.	1	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0.5	.	.	19.91	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1	.	.	19.51	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	18.67	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	9.51	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	11.5	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	19.08	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.5	.	.	16.04	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.52	.	.	14.1	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20

The columns have the following meaning:

- ID: the subject's ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the record (administration or measurement) in minutes, column-type TIME.
- AMT: the amount of drug, column-type AMOUNT.
- RATE: the rate of drug delivery, column-type INFUSION RATE.
- DV: remifentanil concentration measurement or electroencephalogram measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. There are two measurement types in this data set: the remifentanil concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the electroencephalogram measurement (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.

- MDV: Missing Data Variable, column-type MDV.
- AGE: Age of the subject in year, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- SEX: sex of the subject (F for female and M for male), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- LBM: lean body mass, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- TINFCAT: Categories of infusion time, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

2.9.1.6 Veralipride data set

Download data set: PK_veralipride.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Plusquellec, Y, Campistron, G, Staveris, S, Barre, J, Jung, L, Tillement, JP, Houin, G (1987). A double-peak phenomenon in the pharmacokinetics of veralipride after oral administration: a double-site model for drug absorption. J Pharmacokinet Biopharm, 15, 3:225-39.

Veralipride is a benzamide neuroleptic medicine indicated in the treatment of vasomotor symptoms associated with the menopause.

In this dataset, 100 mg doses of veralipride were given to 12 healthy volunteers by oral solution. Individual plasma concentrations of veralipride (ng/ml) were observed at 16 time points during 24h (time is measured in h) after the administration. Doses were given in the morning after an overnight fast, and subjects fasted up to 4 hr after drug administration in each case.

This data set is displayed on the figure below. For some individuals, as the one highlighted on the figure, a double peak in plasma concentrations was observed after oral administration of the solution.

This double peak phenomenon is not systematically noticeable, as can be seen on the next figure.

Below is an extract of the data set file:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
1	0	100	.	.
1	0.17	.	571.7	.
1	0.33	.	780	.
1	0.5	.	629.3	.
1	0.75	.	551.7	.

The columns are:

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- AMT: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT
- Y: the measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.

2.9.2 Categorical data

2.9.2.1 Respiratory status data set

Download data set: respiratory.csv

In this data set, 111 patients have been administrated a placebo or an active treatment. At randomization and at four visits during the treatment, their respiratory status was determined as being “poor” or “good”, which constitutes the categorical output. Covariates such as center, sex and age were also recorded. The goal was to evaluate the effect of the treatment on the respiratory status.

This data set has been originally published in:

Davis, C. S. (1991). Semi-parametric and non-parametric methods for the analysis of repeated measurements with applications to clinical trials. Statistics in Medicine, 10(12), 1959–80

Below we show a snapshot of the data set:

subject	month	statusInteger	status	treatment	sex	age	centre
1	0	0	poor	placebo	female	46	1
1	1	0	poor	placebo	female	46	1
1	2	0	poor	placebo	female	46	1
1	3	0	poor	placebo	female	46	1
1	4	0	poor	placebo	female	46	1
12	0	0	poor	treatment	female	14	1
12	1	1	good	treatment	female	14	1
12	2	1	good	treatment	female	14	1
12	3	1	good	treatment	female	14	1
12	4	0	poor	treatment	female	14	1

In MonolixSuite, the **output categories must be coded as integers**. Thus, we have created the column statusInteger where the respiratory status is coded as 0 for “poor” and 1 for “good”. For individual 1 on placebo, the respiratory status is poor at randomization and remains so during the 4 months. For individual 12 on treatment, the respiratory status is poor at randomization and improves to good during the first three months before deteriorating again to poor at month 4.

The definition of the columns is the following:

- **subject:** patient identifier, column-type ID.
- **month:** month after treatment start, column-type TIME
- **statusInteger:** respiratory status coded as integer, 0 for “poor” and 1 for “good”, column-type OBSERVATION.
- **status:** respiratory status coded as strings “poor” and “good”, column to be ignored
- **treatment:** type of treatment, active or placebo, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- **sex:** sex of the patient, female or name, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- **age:** age of the patient (in years), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.

- **centre**: index of the study center, 1 or 2, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

The representation of statusInteger with respect to time is proposed on the following figure

Several points can be noticed:

1. The categories must be coded as integers.
2. There are respiratory status measures for each individual, the month column allows to define at which time the measures were done.
3. ID and TIME column are mandatory. Thus, even when there is only one measurement per individual, an additional column with TIME should be added (full of 0 for example).
4. Covariates must be constant within subjects (or subject-occasions when occasions are defined).
5. In this example, two categories are present ("good" and "poor"), but any number of categories is possible.

When loading this data set into Datxplorer, one can easily visualize the number of individuals with "poor" (coded as 0, in dark blue) or "good" (coded as 1, in light blue) respiratory status over time in the case of placebo (left) or active treatment (right):

Based on this figure, it seems that the treatment is efficient a priori. We can additionally look at the other covariates and the impact on the output. One can split by sex as can be seen on the following figure.

In that case, the sex covariate seems not to influence a lot the output.

2.9.2.2 Zylkene data set

Download data set: zylkeneCat.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

C. Beata, J. Cordel, N. Marlois (2007). Effect of alpha-casozepine (Zylkene) on Anxiety in Cats, Journal of Veterinary Behavior: Clinical Applications in Research, Vol. 2., Issue 2, pp. 40-46.

The putative effects of a tryptic bovine α 1-casein hydrolysate on anxious disorders in cats was investigated. This product is known as alpha-casozepine and patented under the name of Zylkene (Ingredia, Arras, France). Within veterinary practices, 34 cats were recruited by certified behaviorist surgeons. This 56-day trial against placebo showed the statistically positive effect of this product in the management of anxious disorders such as social phobias in cats. Global score, as well as different items (fear of strangers, contact with familiars, general fears, fear-related aggressions, autonomic disorders), were all significantly improved by the use of this natural decapeptide.

Below we show a snapshot of the data set:

ID	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	TIME	OBSERVATION	DISCRETE
ID	WT_KG	AGE_M	Gender	TRT	TIME	SCORE	
1	4	15	NeuteredF	Zylkene	1	8	
1	4	15	NeuteredF	Zylkene	2	9	
1	4	15	NeuteredF	Zylkene	3	8	
1	4	15	NeuteredF	Zylkene	4	9	
1	4	15	NeuteredF	Zylkene	5	9	
2	4	67	NeuteredF	Placebo	1	9	
2	4	67	NeuteredF	Placebo	2	9	
2	4	67	NeuteredF	Placebo	3	9	
2	4	67	NeuteredF	Placebo	4	9	
2	4	67	NeuteredF	Placebo	5	9	

Note that in the MonolixSuite the **output categories must be coded as integers**. In that cases, observation is a score between 1 and 25. The definition of the columns is the following:

- **ID:** cat identifier, column-type ID.
- **WT_KG:** weight of the cat (in kg), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- **AGE_M:** age of the cat (in month), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- **Gender:** gender of the cat, Neutered F, Neutered M, or F, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- **TRT:** type of treatment, Zylkene or placebo, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- **TIME:** time of the score evaluation, column-type TIME.
- **SCORE:** global score of emotional state, column-type OBSERVATION.

We can see on the following figure the evolution of all SCORE with respect to time. We see that, when the time increases, the number of cats with a higher score increases too.

To see the impact of the treatment, we can split by the covariate TRT and see what is the difference between the two groups as on the following figure (placebo on the left and treatment on the right). We see that the treatment seems efficient as the SCORE is better with the treatment

We can do the same with the GENDER categorical covariate, we can create two groups the female (associating F and NeuteredF) and the male (NeutredM). On the contrary to the treatment, the GENDER does not seem to impact the SCORE.

2.9.2.3 Inpatient multidimensional psychiatric data set

Download data set: schizoSeverity.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

Hedeker D. and Gibbons R.D. (1996) A computer program for mixed-effects ordinal regression analysis. Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine **49**, 157-176.

These data are from the National Institute of Mental Health Schizophrenia Collaborative Study and are available here. Patients were randomized to receive one of four medications, either placebo or one of three different anti-psychotic drugs. The protocol indicated subjects were to then be evaluated at weeks 0, 1, 3, 6 to assess severity of illness; additionally some measurements were made at weeks 2, 4, and 5. The primary outcome is item 79 on the Inpatient Multidimensional Psychiatric.

Scale which indicates severity of illness. We will analyze `imps79o` which is an ordinaly scaled version of the original variable `imps79` which has the following interpretation

IMPS	IMPSo
1 and 2	1 (not ill or borderline)
3 and 4	2 (not ill or borderline)

IMPS	IMPSo
5	3 (markedly)
6 and 7	4 (severely or most extremely ill)

Predictor variables of interest are TxDrug a dummy coded variable indicating treatment with drug or placebo. Below is an extract of the data set:

The columns have the following meaning:

ID	IMPS	IMPSo	TxDrug	Week
1103	5.500	4	drug	0
1103	3.000	2	drug	1
1103	2.500	2	drug	3
1103	4.000	2	drug	6
1104	6.000	4	drug	0
1104	3.000	2	drug	1
1104	1.500	1	drug	3
1104	2.500	2	drug	6
1105	4.000	2	drug	0
1105	3.000	2	drug	1

- *ID*: patient identification number, column-type ID
- *IMPS*: original variable imps79. This column is ignored as we use an ordinally scaled version of this variable.
- *IMPSo*: ordinally version of imps79, column-type OBSERVATION.
- TxDrug indicates if there is a treatment or the placebo, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- *Week*: measurement period, column-type TIME.

One can see on the following figure the evolution of the IMPSo with respect to time on both treated patients and patients with placebo.

2.9.3 Count data

2.9.3.1 Epilepsy attacks data set

Download data set: epilepsy.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Leppik, I.E. et al. (1985) A double-blind crossover evaluation of progabide in partial seizures. Neurology 35, 285.

The data arose from a clinical trial of 59 epileptics who were randomized to receive either the anti-epileptic drug progabide or a placebo, as an adjuvant to standard chemotherapy. The hope was that progabide would help to reduce the number of seizures experienced by patients. Patients attended four successive post-randomisation clinic visits, where the number of seizures that occurred over the previous 2 weeks was reported. At baseline, information on the age of the patient and the 8-week pre-randomisation seizure count was recorded.

Below is an extract of the data set:

The columns have the following meaning:

CATEGORICAL COVARIATE ▾	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE ▾	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE ▾	OBSERVATION ▾	DISCRETE ▾	TIME ▾	ID ▾
treatment	base	age	seizure_rate	period	subject	
placebo	11	31	5	1	1	
placebo	11	31	3	2	1	
placebo	11	31	3	3	1	
placebo	11	31	3	4	1	
placebo	11	30	3	1	2	
placebo	11	30	5	2	2	
placebo	11	30	3	3	2	
placebo	11	30	3	4	2	
placebo	6	25	2	1	3	
placebo	6	25	4	2	3	

- *treatment*: factor with levels placebo progabide indicating whether the anti-epilepsy drug Progabide has been applied or not, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- *base*: number of epileptic attacks recorded during 8 week period prior to randomization, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- *age*: age of the patients, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- *seizure_rate*: number of epilepsy attacks patients have during the follow-up period, column-type OBSERVATION.
- *period*: measurement period, column-type TIME.
- *subject*: patient identification number, column-type ID.

Several points can be noticed:

1. There are several seizure counts for each individual, thus the time allows to define to which period it is related.
2. ID and TIME column are mandatory. Thus, if there is only one count measurement by individual, an additional column with TIME should be added (full of 0 for example).
3. The covariates columns (treatment, base and age) are filled with the same value for each individual. Covariates must be constant within subjects (or subject-occasions when occasions are defined).

Moreover, we can split by the covariate treatment and thus see the impact of the treatment

It seems the the subjects with the treatment have lower seizure rate. We can also display it grouped and not in a spaghetti display as in the following

Using that, we have a better understanding of the seizure_rate, and it seems that the treatment is effective.

2.9.3.2 Crohn's Disease Adverse Events data set

Download data set: crohnAdverseEvent.csv

Data set issued from a study of the adverse events of a drug on 117 patients affected by Crohn's disease (a chronic inflammatory disease of the intestines). In addition to the response variable AE (number of adverse events), 7 explanatory variables were recorded for each patient: BMI (body mass index), HEIGHT, COUNTRY (one of the two countries where the patient lives), SEX, AGE, WEIGHT, and TREAT (the drug taken by the patient in factor form: placebo, d1, d2).

Below is an extract of the data set:

ID	TIME	OBSERVATL. DISCRETE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	TIME	nrAdvE	BMI	height	country	sex	age	weight	treat
19908	0	4	25.22	163	c1	F	47	67	placebo
19909	0	4	23.8	164	c1	F	53	64	d1
19910	0	1	23.05	164	c1	F	58	62	placebo
20908	0	1	25.71	165	c1	F	48	70	d2
20909	0	2	25.95	170	c1	F	67	75	placebo
20910	0	2	28.7	168	c1	F	54	81	d1
21908	0	3	26.62	161	c1	F	53	69	d1
21909	0	0	26.22	168	c1	F	53	74	placebo
21910	0	1	32.05	154	c1	F	47	76	d2
21911	0	0	33.27	157	c1	F	58	82	placebo

The definition of the columns is the following:

- **ID**: subject identifier, column-type ID
- **TIME**: constant to 0, column-type TIME. This column is mandatory. Thus all the values are fixed to 0 as there is only one evaluation.
- **nrAdvE**: the number of adverse events during the period, column-type OBSERVATION.
- **BMI**: body mass index, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **height**: height of the subject in cm, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **country**: country of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **sex**: sex of the subject (M or F), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **age**: age of the subject (in year), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **weight**: weight of the subject in kg, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **treat**: type of treatment, placebo, d1, or d2, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE

We can see on the following figure the number of adverse events on that period providing a global evaluation of the number of adverse events over the population.

One can split by the categorical covariate treat and see if this covariate has an impact on the number of adverse events. As we can see on the following figure, the drugs seem efficient as we notice that the number of adverse events decrease when drug is used.

One can also stratify by the other covariate to have a first idea of the dependencies before the statistical population analysis using Monolix.

2.9.4 Time-to-event data

2.9.4.1 NCCTG lung cancer data set

Download data set: lung_cancer.csv

The North Central Cancer Treatment Group (NCCTG) data set records the survival of patients with advanced lung cancer, together with assessments of the patients performance status measured either by the physician and by the patients themselves. The goal of the study was to determine whether patients self-assessment could provide prognostic information complementary to the physician's assessment. The data set contains 228 patients, including 63 patients that are right censored (patients that left the study before their death).

This data set has been originally presented and analyzed in Loprinzi et al. (1994). Prospective evaluation of prognostic variables from patient-completed questionnaires. North Central Cancer Treatment Group. *Journal of Clinical Oncology : Official Journal of the American Society of Clinical Oncology*, 12(3), 601–607.

A snapshot of the data set is displayed below:

ID	TIME	Y	age	sex	ecogPH	karnoPH	karnoPAT
1	0	0	74	M	1	90	100
1	306	1	74	M	1	90	100
2	0	0	68	M	0	90	90
2	455	1	68	M	0	90	90
3	0	0	56	M	0	90	90
3	1010	0	56	M	0	90	90

The observation period for individual 1 start at 0 and the death event is observed at time 306. On the opposite, individual 3 left the study at time 1010, before his death.

The meaning of the columns is the following:

- **ID**: ID of the patient, column-type ID
- **TIME**: time of start of the observation period (if Y=0, first occurrence), death (if Y=1) or censoring (if Y=0, second occurrence), column-type TIME.
- **Y**: 0 to indicate the start of the observation period or censoring and 1 to indicate death, column-type OBSERVATION.
- **age**: age of the patient (years), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **sex**: sex of the patient (F for female, M for male), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **ecogPH**: ECOG (Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group) performance status assessed by the physician, on a scale from 0 (fully active) to 5 (dead). For information on the scale, [click here](#), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **karnoPH**: Karnofsky performance status, assessed by the physician, on a scale from 0 (dead) to 100 (completely healthy). More details about the scale can be found [here](#), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- **karnoPAT**: Karnofsky performance status, assessed by the patient, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE

Using Monolix, one can visualize the Kaplan-Meier curve. The censored data are indicated by red points.

2.9.4.2 Veterans' Administration Lung Cancer data set

Download data set: `veteran.csv`

In a study conducted by the US Veterans Administration, male patients with advanced inoperable lung cancer were given either a standard therapy or a test chemotherapy. Time to death was recorded for 137 patients, while 9 left the study before death. Various covariates were also documented for each patient.

The primary goal of the study was to assess if the test chemotherapy is beneficial. Secondary goals included the analysis of covariates as prognostic variables.

This data set has been published in D Kalbfleisch and RL Prentice (1980), *The Statistical Analysis of Failure Time Data*. Wiley, New York.

A snapshot of the data set is shown below:

ID	TIME	Y	trt	celltype	karno	diagtime	age	priortherapy
1	0	0	standard	squamous	60	7	69	no
1	72	1	standard	squamous	60	7	69	no
10	0	0	standard	squamous	70	6	70	no
10	100	0	standard	squamous	70	6	70	no
95	0	0	test	smallcell	40	36	44	yes
95	2	1	test	smallcell	40	36	44	yes
114	0	0	test	adeno	60	3	43	no
114	52	1	test	adeno	60	3	43	no

The TIME and Y columns are interpreted in the following way: the observation period for individual 1 start at time 0 and the event occurs at time 72 (i.e 72 days after the enrollment). For individual 10, the start time is also 0 and by the end of the observation period for this individual at time 100, no event has yet occurred.

The structure of the data file is the following:

- **ID**: ID of the patient, column-type ID
- **TIME**: time of start of the observation period (if Y=0, first occurrence), death (if Y=1) or censoring (if Y=0, second occurrence), column-type TIME.
- **Y**: 0 to indicate the start of the observation period or censoring and 1 to indicate death, column-type OBSERVATION.
- **trt**: treatment type, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **celltype**: histological type of the tumor, categorical covariate, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **karno**: Karnofsky performance score that describes the overall patients status at the beginning of the study, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **diagtime**: Time between diagnosis and start of the study (in month), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **age**: age of the patient (in years), column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
- **priortherapy**: indicates if the patient has received another therapy before the current one, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE

Using Monolix, one can visualize the Kaplan-Meier curve. The censored data are indicated by red points.

2.9.4.3 Primary Biliary Cirrhosis data set

Download data set: primaryBiliaryCirrhosis.csv

Primary Biliary Cirrhosis is a rare but fatal chronic liver disease of unknown cause, with a prevalence of about 50-cases-per-million population. The primary pathologic event appears to be the destruction of interlobular bile ducts, which may be mediated by immunologic mechanisms.

Between January, 1974 and May, 1984, the Mayo Clinic conducted a double-blinded randomized trial in primary biliary cirrhosis of the liver (PBC), comparing the drug D-penicillamine (DPCA) with a placebo. There were 424 patients who met the eligibility criteria seen at the Clinic while the trial was open for patient registration. Both the treating physician and the patient agreed to participate in the randomized trial in 312 of the 424 cases. The date of randomization and a large number of clinical, biochemical, serologic, and histologic parameters were recorded for each of the 312 clinical trial patients. The data from the trial were analyzed in 1986 for presentation in the clinical literature. For that analysis, disease and survival status as of July, 1986, were recorded for as many patients as possible. By that date, 125 of the 312 patients had died, with only 11 not attributable to PBC. Eight patients had been lost to follow up, and 19 had undergone liver transplantation.

The considered data set comes from *Counting Processes and Survival Analysis* by T. Fleming & D. Harrington, (1991), published by John Wiley & Sons. On the following figure, one could see the survival curve and the mean number of events with respect to time.

In this data set, there are a lot of available covariates


```

id      = case number
fuptime = number of days between registration and the earlier of death,
         transplation, or study analysis time in July, 1986
status  = 0=alive, 1=liver transplant, 2=dead
drug    = 1= D-penicillamine, 2=placebo
age     = age in days
sex     = 0=male, 1=female
ascites = presence of ascites: 0=no 1=yes
hepato  = presence of hepatomegaly 0=no 1=yes
spiders = presence of spiders 0=no 1=yes
edema   = presence of edema 0=no edema and no diuretic therapy for edema;
         .5 = edema present without diuretics, or edema resolved by diuretics;
         1 = edema despite diuretic therapy
bili    = serum bilirubin in mg/dl
chol    = serum cholesterol in mg/dl
albumin = albumin in gm/dl
copper  = urine copper in ug/day
alk_phos = alkaline phosphatase in U/liter
sgot    = SGOT in U/ml
trig    = triglicerides in mg/dl
platelet = platelets per cubic ml/1000
protime = prothrombin time in seconds
  
```

stage = histologic stage of disease

On the two following figure, one could see the survival curve with respect to the treatment.

2.9.4.3.1 Simplified data set

The data set for subjects 1 and 2 can be defined as follows

```
ID;TIME;Y;TRT;AGE;SEX;
1;0;0;1;58.7652;1;
1;400;1;1;58.7652;1;
2;0;0;1;56.4463;1;
2;4500;0;1;56.4463;1;
```

One must indicated the start time of the observation period with Y=0 (at line 1 and 3 for subject 1 and 2 respectively), and the time of event (Y=1) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred (Y=0). In this simplified data set, subject one had an event at time 400 leading to a line in

the data set where Y=1. On the contrary, no event occurred for subject 2. Thus, at the end of the observation (TIME=4500), Y is set to 0.

2.9.4.4 Cardiovascular data set

Download data set: azCardiovascular.csv

Data come from the 1991 Arizona cardiovascular patient files. A subset of the fields was selected to model the differential length of stay for patients entering the hospital to receive one of two standard cardiovascular procedures: CABG and PTCA. CABG is the standard acronym for Coronary Artery Bypass Graft, where the flow of blood in a diseased or blocked coronary artery or vein has been grafted to bypass the diseased sections. PTCA, or Percutaneous Transluminal Coronary Angioplasty, is a method of placing a balloon in a blocked coronary artery to open it to blood flow. It is a much less severe method of treatment for those having coronary blockage, with a corresponding reduction in risk.

Below we show a snapshot of the data set:

ID	TIME	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	OBSERVATION	EVENT				
ID	los	procedure	sex	admit	age75	hospital	Y	
1	0	1	0	1	0	3.60000014305115	0	
1	67	1	0	1	0	3.60000014305115	1	
2	0	0	0	1	0	6.70000028610229	0	
2	53	0	0	1	0	6.70000028610229	1	
3	0	1	0	0	0	2.5	0	
3	51	1	0	0	0	2.5	1	
4	0	0	0	1	0	6.5	0	
4	30	0	0	1	0	6.5	1	
5	0	1	0	0	0	3.70000004768372	0	
5	43	1	0	0	0	3.70000004768372	1	

The definition of the columns is the following:

- **ID:** patient identifier, column-type ID
- **los:** time in days when the patient goes out of the hospital, column-type TIME
- **procedure:** procedure used, 1 or 0 (1 for CABG and 0 for PTCA), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **sex:** sex of the patient, 1 or 0 (1 for Male and 0 for female), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **admit:** type of admission, 1 or 0 (1 for Urgent/Emergency and 0 for elective), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **age75:** is the subject's age over 75 years, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **hospital:** string describing the hospital, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
- **Y:** event type (0 to enter in the hospital, 1 when the event 'The subject leaves the hospital' happens), column-type OBSERVATION

The representation of the Kaplan-Meier curve with respect to time is presenter below.

2.9.4.5 Oropharynx data set

Download data set: `pharynx_filt.csv`

The following data set provides the data for a part of a large clinical trial carried out by the Radiation Therapy Oncology Group in the United States. The full study included patients with squamous carcinoma of 15 sites in the mouth and throat, with 16 participating institutions, though only data on three sites in the oropharynx reported by the six largest institutions are considered here. Patients entering the study were randomly assigned to one of two treatment groups, radiation therapy alone or radiation therapy together with a chemotherapeutic agent. One objective of the study was to compare the two treatment policies with respect to patient survival. Approximately 30% of the survival times are censored owing primarily to patients surviving to the time of analysis. Some patients were lost to follow-up because the patient moved or transferred to an institution not participating in the study, though these cases were relatively rare.

The considered data set comes from *The Statistical Analysis of Failure Time Data*, by JD Kalbfleisch & RL Prentice, (1980), Published by John Wiley & Sons.

On the following figure, one could see the survival curve and the mean number of events with respect to time.

This study included measurements of many covariates which would be expected to relate to survival experience. Six such variables are given in the data (sex, T staging, N staging, age, general condition, and grade). The site of the primary tumor and possible differences between participating institutions require consideration as well.

CASE	Case Number
INST	Participating Institution
SEX	1=male, 2=female
TX	Treatment: 1=standard, 2=test
GRADE	1=well differentiated, 2=moderately differentiated, 3=poorly differentiated, 9=missing
AGE	In years at time of diagnosis
COND	Condition: 1=no disability, 2=restricted work, 3=requires assistance with self care, 4=bed confined, 9=missing
SITE	1=facial arch, 2=tonsillar fossa, 3=posterior pillar, 4=pharyngeal tongue, 5=posterior wall
T_STAGE	1=primary tumor measuring 2 cm or less in largest diameter, 2=primary tumor measuring 2 cm to 4 cm in largest diameter with minimal infiltration in depth, 3=primary tumor measuring more than 4 cm, 4=massive invasive tumor
N_STAGE	0=no clinical evidence of node metastases, 1=single positive node 3 cm or less in diameter, not fixed, 2=single positive node more than 3 cm in diameter, not fixed, 3=multiple positive nodes or fixed positive nodes
ENTRY_DT	Date of study entry: Day of year and year, dddy
STATUS	0=censored, 1=dead
TIME	Survival time in days from day of diagnosis

On the two following figure, one could see the survival curve and the mean number of events with respect to time for two groups, the first groups concerns the subjects younger than 55 years and the other group concerns the other one.

2.9.4.5.1 Simplified Oropharynx data set

The data set for subjects 47 and 48 can be defined as follows

```
ID;INST;SEX;TRT;GRADE;AGE;COND;SITE;T_STAGE;N_STAGE;ENTRY_DT;Y;Time
47;4;1;2;2;49;3;1;4;3;5669;0;0
47;4;1;2;2;49;3;1;4;3;5669;1;74
48;3;1;1;1;44;1;1;3;1;2769;0;0
48;3;1;1;1;44;1;1;3;1;2769;0;1609
```

One must indicated the start time of the observation period with Y=0 (at line 1 and 3 for subject 47 and 48 respectively), and the time of event (Y=1) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred (Y=0). In this simplified data set, subject 47 had an event at time 74 leading to a line in the data set where Y=1. On the contrary, no event occurred for subject 48. Thus, at the end of the observation (TIME=1609), Y is set to 0.

2.9.5 Joint data

2.9.5.1 PSA and survival data set

Download data set: PSA_survival_dataset.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Desmée, S, Mentré, F, Veyrat-Follet, C, Sébastien, B, Guedj, J (2017). Using the SAEM algorithm for mechanistic joint models characterizing the relationship between nonlinear PSA kinetics and survival in prostate cancer patients. Biometrics, 73, 1:305-312.

It contains PSA kinetics and survival data for 400 men with metastatic Castration-Resistant Prostate Cancer (mCRPC) treated with docetaxel and prednisone, the first-line reference chemotherapy, which constituted the control arm of a phase 3 clinical trial. In this context of advanced disease, the incidence of death is high and the PSA kinetics is closely monitored after treatment initiation to rapidly detect a breakthrough in PSA and propose rescue strategies. In more details:

- PSA kinetics: 6627 PSA measurements were collected, among which roughly 20% were pretreatment, 60% on treatment, and 20% posttreatment. 2.5% are below the limit of quantification (LoQ), set at 0.1 ng.ml^{-1} .
- survival: 286 patients deceased (71.5%), leading to a median survival of 656 days.

PSA measurements are displayed on the figure below. Since the data density is too high to see clearly, the next figure is a selection of six individuals, that allows to identify the shape of PSA measurements followed by most individuals: a decrease of PSA concentration after the treatment initiation at time zero, followed by an increase some time later due to resistance.

The following figure shows the Kaplan-Meier curves for the survival data split in two groups by the median time of end of treatment

Below is an extract of the data set file:

TIME ▾		ID ▾		OBSERVATION ▾		CENSORED ▾		YTYPE ▾		CONTINUOUS COVARIATE ▾	
				YTYPE: 2 ▾	EVENT ▾						
TIME	↕	ID	↕	Y		CENS	↕	YTYPE	↕	TIME_ENDtr	↕
-626		2008		3.1904763503465		0		1		620	
-248		2054		1.25276296849537		0		1		168	
-245		2072		2.79116510781272		0		1		189	
-225		2042		3.89182029811063		0		1		188	
-223		2011		3.86702563949741		0		1		190	
-217		2008		4.2916915584923		0		1		620	
-212		2068		1.52388002407245		0		1		340	
-205		2076		0.936093359170335		0		1		272	
-185		2053		2.32238772029023		0		1		252	
-176		2050		1.09861228866811		0		1		189	

The columns are:

- TIME: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- Y: measurements of PSA concentration in ng.ml^{-1} , or death events, column-type OBSERVATION.
- CENS: CENS=1 indicates values below the limit of quantification (LoQ), column-type CENSORING.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. There are two measurement types in this data set: the PSA concentration measurement (corresponding to the PD), and death events, column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- TIME_ENDtr: day of end of treatment, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.

2.9.5.2 Warfarin joint data set

Download data set: warfarin_data.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

O'Reilly (1968). Studies on coumarin anticoagulant drugs. Initiation of warfarin therapy without a loading dose. Circulation 1968, 38:169-177.

Warfarin is an anticoagulant normally used in the prevention of thrombosis and thromboembolism, the formation of blood clots in the blood vessels and their migration elsewhere in the body, respectively. The data set provides set of plasma warfarin concentrations and Prothrombin Complex Response in thirty normal subjects after a single loading dose. A single large loading dose of warfarin sodium, 1.5 mg/kg of body weight, was administered orally to all subjects. Measurements were made each 12 or 24h.

On the two following figure, one could see the concentration and the effect with respect to time for all subjects.

The data set for subject one can be defined as follows

id	time	amt	dv	dvid	wt	age	sex
1	0	100	.	1	66.7	50	1
1	0	.	100	2	66.7	50	1
1	24	.	9.2	1	66.7	50	1
1	24	.	49	2	66.7	50	1
1	36	.	8.5	1	66.7	50	1
1	36	.	32	2	66.7	50	1
1	48	.	6.4	1	66.7	50	1
1	48	.	26	2	66.7	50	1
1	72	.	4.8	1	66.7	50	1

1	72	.	22	2	66.7	50	1
1	96	.	3.1	1	66.7	50	1
1	96	.	28	2	66.7	50	1
1	120	.	2.5	1	66.7	50	1
1	120	.	33	2	66.7	50	1

2.9.5.2.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- id: the subject ID, column-type ID
- time: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- amt: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT.
- dv: the measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.
- dvid: the type of measurement. In this study, one has two measurement, the concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the Prothrombin Complex Response (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- wt: Weight of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- age: Age of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- sex: Sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. The first line corresponds to a dose, while the other ones are measurements. This explains the dot in the CONC column for the first line and the dots in the AMT column for the other ones.
2. The covariates columns (the continuous wt and the categorical covariates age and sex) are filled with the same values. Even though it is not necessary, we encourage the user to fill the columns for readability and usage reasons.
3. In the presented case, both PK and PD measurements are at the same time, this is not required for data exploration using Datxploré, nor parameter estimation using Monolix.
4. Finally, notice that no initial washout is needed at the beginning as by default, the null initial condition is used for parameter estimation.

Interestingly, one can display the Effect with respect to the Concentration in order to have an idea on how to model the interaction between the PD and the PK part.

Then, the response does not seem to be direct. **Notice that, as the observation times are no the same between the PK and the PD, interpolation is made to propose this kind of plot.** One can also focus on one individual in particular as on the following figure

Notice that we also propose a red arrow to describe the evolution of time.

2.9.5.3 Remifentanil joint data set

Download data set: [pkpdRemifentanil.csv](#)

This data set has been originally published in:

Influence of age and gender on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of remifentanyl. I. Model development. Anesthesiology, Minto, et al. (1997)

Remifentanyl is an opioid analgesic drug with a rapid onset and rapid recovery time. It is used for sedation as well as combined with other medications for use in general anesthesia. It is given in adults via continuous IV infusion.

65 healthy adults have received remifentanyl IV infusion at a constant diffusion rate between 1 and 8 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 4 to 20 minutes. The data set contains remifentanyl admission characteristics (time and rate of infusion), dense measurements of remifentanyl blood concentration during infusion and after (PK data), as well as dense electroencephalogram measurements (PD data) recording the depth of anesthesia. In addition, a list of covariates is available: age, gender, and lean body mass (LBM). Moreover, a variable TINFCAT classifies the patients in several categories with similar infusion time.

One can see on the following figure the remifentanyl concentrations over time split in two groups (female and male). On each figure, the subjects with age lower than 50 are in blue while the ones with an age over 50 are in green.

On the following figure, one can see the electroencephalogram measurements with respect to time for all subjects.

Below is an extract of the data set file:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	RATE	OBSERVATION	YTYPE	MDV	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	TIME	AMT	RATE	DV	YTYPE	MDV	AGE	SEX	LBM	TINFCAT
1	0	.	.	18.85	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0	1439.8	71.99	.	.	1	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0.5	.	.	19.91	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1	.	.	19.51	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	18.67	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	9.51	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	11.5	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	19.08	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.5	.	.	16.04	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.52	.	.	14.1	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20

The columns have the following meaning:

- ID: the subject's ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the record (administration or measurement) in minutes, column-type TIME.
- AMT: the amount of drug, column-type AMOUNT.
- RATE: the rate of drug delivery, column-type INFUSION RATE.
- DV: remifentanil concentration measurement or electroencephalogram measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. There are two measurement types in this data set: the remifentanil concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the electroencephalogram measurement (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.

- MDV: Missing Data Variable, column-type MDV.
- AGE: Age of the subject in year, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- SEX: sex of the subject (F for female and M for male), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- LBM: lean body mass, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- TINFCAT: Categories of infusion time, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

3 Structural model

Here is the list of pages that describe how to use structural models in Monolix:

3.1 Setting the structural model

After creating a new project and loading a dataset, a structural model should be loaded and its output variables mapped to the measurement types from the data.

3.1.1 Loading or creating a model

In Monolix, structural models are provided as external .txt files, whose path is saved into the Monolix project.

There are three options to load a structural model:

1. Use the option **“Browse”** to load an existing file containing a structural model.
2. Use **“Load from library”** to select a model from the available [model libraries](#). Models from the libraries are not saved as external files but are generated on-the-fly. Once loaded, it is possible to open the content of a library model, edit it and save it as an external file.
3. Use **“New model”** to open the built-in editor, [write your own model](#) using the Mlxtran language, and save it as an external file.

3.1.2 Format of the structural model

The content of the structural model file should follow the Mlxtran syntax, with two main rules:

- The file has to start with **[LONGITUDINAL]**, which is the section containing the structural model. In Monolix, the statistical part of the model (covariate effects, parameter distributions and error model) is defined through the graphical user interface. When saving a Monolix project, the statistical part of the model is automatically written directly in the .mlxtran project file using mlxtran language as additional sections **[INDIVIDUAL]** and **[COVARIATE]**.
- The rest of the content should be divided into different blocks to define different types of variables:
 - **DESCRIPTION:** (optional) to describe the content of the model
 - **PK:** (optional) to use PK macros
 - **EQUATION:** (optional) to define equations
 - **DEFINITION:** (optional) to define non-continuous variables
 - **OUTPUT:** (mandatory) to define the output variables.

When using the option “New model”, the built-in editor opens with an unsaved new file pre-filled with the usual structure:

Details on this syntax and the content of each block are given in [Model syntax: mlxtran language](#)

Models loaded from the libraries also follow the same structure, as on this example:

Untitled* - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data **Structural model** Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Plots

Model file

lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt

i An analytical solution will be used.

BROWSE... **LOAD FROM LIBRARY** **EDIT MODEL**

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption
  (rate constant ka).
3 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear elimination
  (clearance Cl).
4
5 [LONGITUDINAL]
6 input = {ka, V, Cl}
7
8 PK:
9 ; PK model definition
10 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
11
12 OUTPUT:
13 output = {Cc}
14

```

3.1.3 Mapping between the data and the model

After loading a model, its output variables should be mapped to the measurement types from the data.

A default mapping is set by Monolix by order, i.e. the first output listed in the `output=` statement of the model is mapped to the first OBSERVATION ID (ordered alphabetically). The mapping can also be customized by the user.

This page explains in details how to use the mapping: [Mapping between the data and the model](#)

3.2 Using or editing models from the libraries

Nine different libraries are available in Monolix, detailed in [Libraries of models](#)

- **PK** (pharmacokinetics)
- **PD** (pharmacodynamics)
- **PKPD** (joint PKPD)

- **PK double absorption**
- **Parent metabolite**
- **TMDD** (target-mediated drug disposition)
- **TTE** (time to-event)
- **Count** (for non-continuous count data)
- **TGI** (tumor growth and tumor growth inhibition)

3.2.1 Picking a model from a library

To use a model from the libraries, in the Structural model tab, click on “Load from library” and select the desired library. A list of models appears, as well as a menu to filter them. Use the filters and the list of parameters included in the models to select the model you need.

Here is for example how to select a PK model with first-order absorption and linear elimination (parameters k_a , V , Cl):

The model contents correspond to pre-written models in Mlxtran language. In the case of library models, they are not saved as external text files but are generated on-the-fly inside Monolix. Once selected, the model appears in the Monolix GUI. Below we show the content of the (k_a, V, Cl) model:

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface with the 'Structural model' tab selected. The interface is divided into two main panels: 'Model file' and 'Mapping'.

Model file: This panel shows a text editor with the following code:

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption
  (rate constant ka).
3 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear
  elimination (clearance Cl).
4
5 [LONGITUDINAL]
6 input = {ka, V, Cl}
7
8 PK:
9 ; PK model definition
10 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
11
12 OUTPUT:
13 output = {Cc}
14
  
```

Buttons for 'BROWSE...', 'LOAD FROM LIBRARY', and 'EDIT MODEL' are visible above the code editor. A message states: 'An analytical solution will be used.'

Mapping: This panel shows a diagram with a grid background. It has two columns: 'Data (Observation ID)' and 'Model'. A horizontal line connects a blue circle labeled 'CONC' in the 'Data' column to a blue circle labeled 'CONC Cc' in the 'Model' column.

3.2.1.1 Modifying a model from the libraries

Browse existing models from the libraries using the “Load from library” button, then click the “file” icon next to a model name. This opens a pop-up window where the content of the model file is displayed. Click on “Open in editor” to open the model file in the MlxEditor. There you can adapt the model, for instance to add a PD model. Be careful to save the new model under a new name, to avoid overwriting the library files.

The video below shows an example of how a scale factor can be added to a library model:

The video below shows how to combine several library models together:

3.2.2 Step-by-step example with the PK library

We would like to set up a one compartment PK model with first order absorption and linear elimination for the [theophylline data set](#). We start by creating a new Monolix project. Next, in the **Data** tab, click **browse**, and select the theophylline data set. In this example, all columns are already automatically tagged, based on the header names. We click **ACCEPT** and **NEXT** and arrive on the **Structural model** tab, click on **LOAD FROM LIBRARY** to choose a model from the PK library. The menu at the top allow to filter the list of models: after selecting an oral/extravascular administration, no delay, first-order absorption, one compartment, a linear elimination and parametrization with clearance, one model remains in the list, with parameters (ka,V,Cl). Click on the `oral1_1cpt_kaVCl` model to select it.

LINE NUMBER	ID	AMT	TIME	CONC	WEIGHT	SEX
2	1	4.02	0	-	79.6	M
3	1	-	0.25	2.84	79.6	M
4	1	-	0.57	6.57	79.6	M
5	1	-	1.12	10.5	79.6	M
6	1	-	2.02	9.66	79.6	M
7	1	-	3.82	8.58	79.6	M
8	1	-	5.1	8.36	79.6	M
9	1	-	7.03	7.47	79.6	M
10	1	-	9.05	6.89	79.6	M

After this step, the GUI moves to the Initial Estimates tab, but it is possible to go back to the Structural model tab to see the content of the file:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Back to the Initial Estimates tab, the initial values of the population parameters can be adjusted by comparing the model prediction using the chosen population parameters and the individual data. Click on SET AS INITIAL VALUES when you are done.

In the next tab, the Statistical model & Tasks tab, Monolix uses by default:

- a combined error observation model,
- lognormal distributions for all parameters (k_a , V and Cl).

At this stage, the monolix project should be saved. This creates a human-readable text file with extension `.mlxtran`, which contains all the information defined via the GUI. In particular, the name of the model appears in the section `[LONGITUDINAL]` of the saved project file:

```
<MODEL>
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl}

DEFINITION:
ka = {distribution=lognormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=lognormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=lognormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a, b}
```

```
file = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kavCl.txt'
```

DEFINITION:

```
CONC = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=combined1(a,b)}
```

3.3 Writing a model from scratch

If the models present in the libraries do not suit your needs, you can write a model yourself. You can either start completely from scratch or adapt a model existing in the libraries. In both cases, the syntax of the Mlxtran language is detailed in: [Model syntax: mlxtran language](#). You can also copy-paste models from the [pages of model examples](#).

In the “Structural model” tab, you can click on “New model” to open the editor integrated within Monolix, and start writing your own model. The new model contains a convenient template defining the main blocks, input parameters and output variables. When you are done, click on the “Create model” button to save your new model as a .txt file. After saving, the model is automatically loaded in the project.

The figure below shows how to use the editor integrated within the interface of Monolix. The model shown as example corresponds to the model included in the Monolix demo 8.case_studies/hcv_project.mlxtran.

You can even create your own library of models. An example of a basic library which includes several viral kinetics model is available in the demos 8.case_studies/model.

 A button “Check syntax” is available to check that there is no syntax error in the model. In case of an error, informative messages are displayed to help correct the error. The syntax check is also automatically applied before saving the model so that only a model with a valid syntax can be saved.

3.3.1 Understanding the error messages

The error messages generated when syntax errors are present in the model are very informative and quickly help to get the model right. The most common error messages are explained in detail in this video.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HgJ1jBECXPE>

3.3.2 Using the external editor

This video shows how to write a new structural model with the mlxEditor application, that could only be used as a separate application in versions of MonolixSuite prior to 2021R1:

3.4 Mapping between the data and the model

Starting from the 2019 version, it is possible to change the mapping between the data set observations ids and the structural model output. By default and in previous versions, the mapping is done by order, i.e. the first output listed in the `output=` statement of the model is mapped to the first OBSERVATION ID (ordered alphabetically). It is possible with the interface to set exactly which model output is mapped to which data output. Model output or data outputs can be left unused.

3.4.1 Changing the mapping

If you have more output in the data set (i.e. more OBSERVATION IDs) than in the structural model, you can set which data output you will use in the project. In the example below there are two outputs in the data set (managed by the OBSERVATION ID column) and only one output in the structural model, Cc. By default the following mapping is proposed: the data with observation id '1' is mapped to the model prediction 'Cc'. The model observation (with error model) is called 'CONC' (the name of the OBSERVATION column, can be edited):

To set the data output to use to observation id '2', you can either:

- Unlink by clicking on either the dot representing the output '1' of the Data or 'Cc' of the structural model, and then draw the line between '2' and 'Cc' (as can be seen on the figure below on the left)
- Directly draw a line from '2' to 'Cc' (as can be seen on the figure below on the right). This will automatically undo the link between '1' and 'Cc'.

And click on the button ACCEPT on the bottom on the window to apply the changes.

The same possibility is proposed if you have more outputs in the structural model, compared to the number of observation ids. If you have a TMDD model with both the free and the total ligand concentration listed as model output and one type of measurement, you can map either the free or the total ligand as can be seen on the following figure with the same actions as described above.

3.4.2 Several types of outputs

The mapping is only possible between outputs of same nature (continuous / count-categorical / event), i.e. it is only possible to map a continuous output with a continuous output of the structural model. Thus, mapping a continuous output with a discrete or a time-to-event is not possible. If you try to link a forbidden combination, the line connecting line will be displayed in red as in the following figure

The type of output is indicated via the shapes:

- continuous outputs are displayed as circles
- categorical/count outputs are displayed as squares
- event outputs are displayed as triangles

3.4.3 Changing the observation name

In the example below, '1' is the observation id used in the data set to identify the data to use, 'Cc' is the model output (a prediction, without residual error) and 'y1' the observation (with error). 'y1' represents the data with observation id '1' and it appears in the labels/legends of the plots. These elements are related by observation model, which formula can be displayed.

Mapping

Data
(Observation ID)

1 ●

2 ■

Model

y1
Cc

Seizure
Seizure

Observation model ▾ f(x)

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1 ▾	NORMAL ▾
count	2	Seizure			

Observation model ×

$$y1 = Cc + (a + b * Cc) * e$$

For count/categorical and event model outputs, the model observation is defined in the model file directly. The name used in the model file is reused in the mapping interface and cannot be changed.

For continuous outputs, the model file defines the name of the prediction (e.g 'Cc'), while the model observation (e.g 'y1', with error) definition is done in the "Statistical model and tasks" tab of the interface. If there is only one model output, the default observation name is the header of the data set column tagged as OBSERVATION. In case of several model outputs, the observation names are y1, y2, y3, etc. The observation names for continuous outputs can be changed by clicking on the node and "edit observation name":

Model file

C:\Users\FrancoMihaljevic\OneDrive\monolix\monolix2024R1\demos\4_joint_models\4.2_continuous_moncontinuous\model\PKcount_model.txt

An analytical solution will be used.

BROWSE... LOAD FROM LIBRARY EDIT MODEL

```

1 DESCRIPTION: PK model + Count data model
2
3 [LONGITUDINAL]
4 input = (ka, V, Cl, lambda0, IC50)
5
6 EQUATION:
7 Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)
8 lambda = lambda0*(1 - Cc/(IC50+Cc))
9
10 DEFINITION:
11 Seizure = {type = count,
12             log(P(Seizure=k)) = -lambda + k*log(lambda) - factln(k)
13 }
14
15 OUTPUT:
16 output = {Cc, Seizure}
                
```

Mapping

Data
(Observation ID)

1 ●

2 ■

Model

y1
Cc

Seizure
Seizure

Unlink
Edit observation name

3.5 Model syntax: mlxtran language

3.5.1 Introduction: model structure for Monolix

3.5.1.1 Structural model

In Monolix, the model code defined in the “Structural model” tab (external .txt file loaded into Monolix or model selected from a library) contains only the structural part of the model in a single [LONGITUDINAL] section.

The [LONGITUDINAL] section is itself divided into blocks, which allows to define different types of variables in different ways. Here are the possible blocks and variable lists in that section:

- **DESCRIPTION:** (optional): block to put comments on the model
- **input** (mandatory): list of input parameters
- **PK:** (optional): block where macros can be used and combined to define compartments and transfers between them
- **EQUATION:** (optional): block where ODEs and DDES can be defined, as well as mathematical expressions (e.g parameter transformations)
- **DEFINITION:** (optional): block to define random variables (discrete or continuous) which represent observations, via their probability distribution: error model, probability distribution for count/categorical output and hazard for time-to-event output
- **OUTPUT:** (mandatory): block indicating the output of the model
- **output** (mandatory): list of output parameters included in the OUTPUT block.

In all blocks, it is possible to use:

- [if/else statements](#) with [logical operators](#)
- [mathematical functions](#)
- [keywords for the time and dose-related events](#)
- [regressors](#)

[Reserved keywords](#) of the Mlxtran language cannot be used as names for other parameters. Mlxtran is a declarative language, not an imperative language. Therefore equations are mathematical definitions rather than a series of instructions.

3.5.1.1.1 Inputs

In Monolix, the `input = { }` list of the [LONGITUDINAL] section declares the individual parameters and the regressors.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}
```

For regressors, the regressor status must be specified using the following syntax, for instance for two regressors called `regvar1` and `regvar2`. One line per regressor is necessary. As a reminder, in Monolix, the regressors are mapped to the regressor columns of the data set by declaration order (first column tagged as regressor mapped to the first regressor appearing in the input list).

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {..., regvar1, regvar2}
regvar1 = {use=regressor}
regvar2 = {use=regressor}
```

Example:

In this example, `ka`, `V`, `Cl`, `Emax` and `EC50` are individual parameters and `E0` is declared as a regressor and will be read from the first data set column tagged as regressor.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, E0, Emax, EC50}
E0 = {use = regressor}
```

3.5.1.1.2 Outputs

In Monolix, the `OUTPUT:` block declare the variables which will be mapped to the observations in the data set via the `output={}` list, and the additional variables recorded in the output tables via the `table={}` list. The outputs are mapped to the observation ids of the data set via the mapping panel in the Monolix GUI. The variables in the `table={}` statement are outputted in the result folder of Monolix.

Example:

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Conc, Effect}
table = {Ap, T12}
```

3.5.1.1.3 Library of models and examples

The MonolixSuite contains libraries of pre-written structural models which can be directly selected via the GUI in Monolix:

- **PK**: typical pharmacokinetics models with several types of administrations and 1 to 3 compartments
- **PK/PD**: joint PK/PD model with direct effect, effect compartment or turnover
- **PK double absorption**
- **TMDD**: target mediated drug disposition models
- **Parent-Metabolite** models
- **TTE**: time-to-event models
- **Count**: models for count data
- **TGI**: tumor growth and tumor growth inhibition models

Examples of common models which are not (yet) in the libraries are also given here: [Advanced models](#)

3.5.1.2 Statistical model

In Monolix the statistical part of the model (covariate effects, parameter distributions and error model) is [defined through the graphical user interface](#). Then when saving a Monolix project, the statistical part of the model is automatically written in the .mlxtran project file using mlxtran language, divided into three parts:

- **The observation (error) model**: defined inside the DEFINITION: block below the [LONGITUDINAL] section.
- **The individual model**: describes the distributions for the individual parameters, correlation structure and covariate effects, defined inside the [INDIVIDUAL] section.
- **The covariates** defined in the project: described inside the [COVARIATE] section.

3.5.1.2.1 Example

Here is the description of the full model (structural and statistical) corresponding to the Monolix demo 1.1.libraries_of_models/theophylline_project.mlxtran, automatically saved by Monolix inside the <MODEL> part of the theophylline_project.mlxtran file:

```
<MODEL>

[COVARIATE]
input = {WEIGHT, SEX}

SEX = {type=categorical, categories={'F', 'M'}}
```

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl}

DEFINITION:
ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a, b}

file = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt'

DEFINITION:
CONC = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=combined1(a, b)}
```

Note that when exporting the model from Monolix to Simulx, this full model then appears in the interface of Simulx:

Untitled* - Simulx - 2024R1
- □ ×

Project Settings Export Help
▲ 1

🏠 Definition Exploration Simulation
☰

MODEL

 OCCASIONS

 POP.PARAMS

 INDIV.PARAMS

 COVARIATES

 TREATMENTS

 OUTPUTS

 REGRESSORS

Model

Model based on: lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt

🔍 BROWSE...
📖 LOAD FROM LIBRARY
✍️ OPEN IN EDITOR

```

1  [INDIVIDUAL]
2  input = {ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl}
3
4  DEFINITION:
5  ka = {distribution=logNormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
6  V = {distribution=logNormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
7  Cl = {distribution=logNormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
8
9  [LONGITUDINAL]
10 input = {a, b}
11 ;;;; Included file 'oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt'
12 DESCRIPTION:
13 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption (rate constant
   ka).
14 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear elimination (clearance
   Cl).
15
16 input = {ka, V, Cl}
17
18 PK:
19 ; PK model definition
20 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
21
22 OUTPUT:
23 output = {Cc}
24
25 ;;;;
26
27
28 DEFINITION:
29 CONC = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=combined1(a, b)}
```

+ ADD LINES

3.5.2 PK: Using PK macros

On the following pages you can find information about the different types of PK macros:

3.5.2.1 Introduction

Introduction PK macros

A list of PK macros can be used as shortcuts to easily define PK models. All PK macros should be defined in a **PK:** block that must be included into the **[LONGITUDINAL]** section. Macros can be combined with ODE equations defined in an **EQUATION:** block. PK macros cannot be included into an arithmetic expression and cannot be enclosed within a conditional statement

There are three types of macros. We show below as example the same one-compartmental PK model with first-order absorption and linear elimination, using parameters (k_a , V , Cl), defined in three different ways that involve the three types of macros.

You can read more details about each of them here:

Introduction PK macros

The depot macro

This macro is used to provide a link between the administration information in the data set and the model, the rest of the model being defined as equations.

```
PK:
; depot() macro applies doses defined in the dataset to the ODE variable Ad
depot(target = Ac, ka)
EQUATION:
Ac_0 = 0
ddt_Ac = -(Cl/V)*Ac
```

The pkmodel macro

This macro provides a shortcut for standard PK models.

Example:

```
PK:
; pkmodel() macro to define simple PK models in one line
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
```

Piecewise macros

A list of piecewise macros can be combined together to describe PK models. These macros allow the user to have an intuitive and compact representation of the most common PK models used in pharmacometrics.

Example:

```
PK:
; definition of the central compartment, numbered 1, with volume V and
concentration Cc
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
; definition of an oral absorption with first-order rate ka and bioavailability F
for doses with admid=1
; arriving into the central compartment. Note that the depot compartment is
implicit.
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)
; definition of an elimination from the central compartment 1 with clearance Cl
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

3.5.2.2 depot macro

3.5.2.2.1 Description

The macro *depot* is a multipurpose macro that can accommodate different types of administrations. It is used together with ODE systems to define how the administrations from the data set are linked with the model variables. It is the only macro that can be used with ODEs for administration without defining a compartment. With the macro *depot*, a bolus, an infusion (with INFUSION RATE or INFUSION duration defined in the data set), a zero order absorption, or a first order absorption (with or without transit process) can be defined.

As for other macros, *depot* must be used in a block PK; while ODEs must be defined in a block EQUATION:.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hcgI2NIXcFE>

3.5.2.2.2 Arguments

The *depot* macro can be used for bolus doses, infusions (with INFUSION RATE or INFUSION duration defined in the data set), zero-order absorptions, and first-order absorptions. Some arguments are common for the three types of administrations, some are specific.

3.5.2.2.2.1 Arguments common to bolus, zero-order and first-order absorption:

- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to be read by the depot macro. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.
- **target**: Name of the ODE variable on which the doses will be added. *Mandatory*.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Fraction of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.

3.5.2.2.2.2 Specific arguments for bolus doses:

For bolus doses, no additional argument is needed.

The following code defines a bolus for doses of type 1 (e.g ADM=1 in the data set), applied to the ODE variable Ad, with a delay Tlag and a fraction absorbed F :

```
PK:  
depot(type=1, target=Ad, Tlag, p=F)
```

3.5.2.2.2.3 Specific arguments for zero-order absorption:

To define a zero-order absorption, the following argument must be added:

- **Tk0**: Duration of the zero order absorption. *Mandatory to define zero-order absorption*.

The following code defines a zero-order absorption process of duration Tk0, for doses of type adm=2, applied to the ODE variable Ac, without lag time (Tlag=0 when not specified) and with the entire dose being absorbed (p=1 when not defined). Note that the "target" is the variable corresponding to the compartment in which the dose arrives (i.e the central compartment). The depot compartment is implicit and does not need to be defined.

```
PK:  
depot(type=2, target=Ac, Tk0)
```

3.5.2.2.2.4 Specific arguments for first-order absorption:

To define a first-order absorption, the following arguments can be added:

- **ka**: Rate of the first order absorption. *Mandatory to define first-order absorption.*
- **Ktr**: Transit rate.
- **Mtt**: Mean transit compartments time for the absorption.

The following code defines a first-order absorption process with rate ka , for doses of type 1 ($adm=1$ when not specified), applied to the ODE variable Ac , with a lag-time $Tlag$ of 2.1, and only 30% of the dose being absorbed. Note that the “target” is the variable corresponding to the compartment in which the dose arrives (i.e the central compartment). The depot compartment is implicit and does not need to be defined.

```
PK:  
depot(target=Ac, ka, Tlag=2.1, p=0.3)
```

Note: In case of transit compartments and multiple doses, the amounts in the depot, transit and absorption compartments are reset at each new doses. Thus the implementation is valid only if the dose is fully absorbed before the next dose administration. The amount in the central (and possibly other compartments) is not reset and can accumulate.

3.5.2.2.2.5 Rules

- The value after `type=` must be an integer.
- The value after `target=` must be a string representing the ODE variable
- The inputs after `Tlag=`, `p=`, `Tk0=`, `ka=`, `Ktr=`, `Mtt=` can be either a
 - Double
 - Input parameter
 - Variable
 - Calculations are not supported
- The associated treatment or administration can be defined with a rate or an infusion timing from the data set (RATE and TINF column-types in the data set). The rules are the same as for the iv macro.

3.5.2.3 pkmodel macro

3.5.2.3.1 Introduction

The function **pkmodel** permits to define common PK models in a very concise way. The purpose of this macro is to simplify the modeling of classical pharmacokinetics. The PK model is inferred from the provided set of named arguments. Most of the arguments are optional, and the **pkmodel** function

enables several parametrizations, to select different models of absorption, elimination, etc. With the **pkmodel** function, the most common PK models are available. The concentration within the central compartment is the main output of the function. If an effect compartment is defined, its concentration defines the second output. The pkmodel macro only uses doses with `adm=1`. The **pkmodel** function can be used within the block EQUATION: or the block PK:

3.5.2.3.2 Examples

Example 1: One compartment model with intravenous (bolus or infusion) administration

```
Cc = pkmodel(V, Cl)
```

This simple set of named arguments for pkmodel defines a PK model with one central compartment of volume V , with intravenous bolus administration and a linear elimination with clearance Cl . The concentration in the central compartment is the output Cc of the function.

If a column is tagged as infusion duration or as infusion rate in the data, this is recognized by the pkmodel macro and the doses with a non-empty infusion rate or duration are administered as an infusion instead of a bolus.

Example 2: Two-compartment model with first order absorption with lag time

- With elimination rates: parameters Tlag, ka, V, k, k12, k21

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, k, k12, k21)
```

- With clearances: parameters Tlag, ka, V, Cl, Q, V2

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, k=Cl/V, k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

Note that it is not possible to give Q and $V2$ as direct input parameters. Instead, we give the recognized keywords $k12$ and $k21$, and defined them using Q , V and $V2$.

Example 3: Three-compartment model with zero-order absorption

```
Cc = pkmodel(Tk0, V, k, k12, k21, k13, k31)
```

$Tk0$ represents the duration of the zero-order absorption. $k12$ and $k21$ are the rates to and from the first peripheral compartment and $k13$ and $k31$ are the rates to and from the second peripheral compartment.

Example 4: One compartment model with transit compartments

$$C_c = \text{pkmodel}(ka, M_{tt}, K_{tr}, V, Cl)$$

In case of transit compartments, the mean transit time is defined as $M_{tt} = (n+1)/K_{tr}$ with n the number of transit compartments (excluding the depot compartment and the absorption compartment) and K_{tr} the transit rate.

The implementation is the same as described in Savic et al, "Implementation of a transit compartment model for describing drug absorption in pharmacokinetic studies" (2007), except that to approximate the factorial $n!$, we use the gamma function, which is more precise, instead of the Stirling formula.

Note that this model has no analytical solution, so the ODE system is used in the background.

Example 5: One compartment model with effect compartment

$$\{C_c, C_e\} = \text{pkmodel}(ka, V, Cl, ke_0)$$

The one-compartment model is connected to an effect compartment with a bi-directional rate ke_0 . The concentration in the effect compartment is called C_e in this example and can for instance be used to define a PD model.

Example 6: Model using almost all arguments

$$\{C_c, C_e\} = \text{pkmodel}(T_{lag}, ka, p, V, V_m, K_m, k_{12}, k_{21}, k_{13}, k_{31}, ke_0)$$

This more complex set of named arguments for `pkmodel` defines a PK model of a central compartment, with a first order absorption of rate ka , and a Michaelis-Menten elimination of parameters V_m and K_m . The volume of the central compartment is V . The concentration in the central compartment is the first output C_c of the function. An effect compartment is defined with a rate ke_0 and its concentration is the second output C_e . Two peripheral compartments numbered 2 and 3 are linked to the central compartment numbered 1. The respective couples of exchange rates are (k_{12}, k_{21}) and (k_{13}, k_{31}) . The first order absorption has a lag time T_{lag} and the absorbed amount is scaled with a proportion p (bioavailability).

3.5.2.3.3 List of arguments

The complete set of named arguments and output for `pkmodel` follows. They correspond to the central compartment, the absorption process, the elimination process, the exchanges with the peripheral compartments, or an effect compartment. Some arguments are mutually exclusive, or require other ones to be also defined. Most of them are optional, so the mandatory arguments are stated.

3.5.2.3.3.1 Arguments for the central compartment

- **Cc** = `pkmodel(...)`: The first output is the concentration within the central compartment. Another name can be used. *Mandatory*.
- **V**: Volume of the central compartment. *Mandatory*.

3.5.2.3.3.2 Arguments for the absorption process of a standard PK model

- **Tk0**: Defines a zero order absorption of duration $Tk0$. *Excludes ka, Ktr and Mtt*.
- **ka**: Defines a first order absorption of rate ka . *Excludes Tk0*.
- **Ktr**: Along with ka and Mtt , defines an absorption with transit compartments, with transit rate Ktr . *Excludes Tk0*.
- **Mtt**: Along with ka and Ktr , defines an absorption with transit compartments, with mean transit time Mtt . *Excludes Tk0*.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount (bioavailability). Can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration.
- default if no argument supplied for the absorption process: `iv bolus`

3.5.2.3.3.3 Arguments for the elimination process of a standard PK model

- **k**: Defines a linear elimination of rate k . *Excludes Cl, Vm and Km*.
- **Cl**: Along with V , defines a linear elimination of clearance Cl . *Excludes k, Vm and Km*.
- **Vm**: Along with V and Km , defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination of maximum elimination rate Vm . Units of Vm are amount/time. *Excludes k and Cl*.
- **Km**: Along with V and Vm , defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination of Michaelis-Menten constant Km . Units of Km are concentration so amount/volume. *Excludes k and Cl*.

3.5.2.3.3.4 Arguments for the peripheral compartments of a standard PK model

- **k12**: Along with $k21$, defines a peripheral compartment 2 of input rate $k12$.
- **k21**: Along with $k12$, defines a peripheral compartment 2 of output rate $k21$.
- **k13**: Along with $k31$, defines a peripheral compartment 3 of input rate $k13$.
- **k31**: Along with $k13$, defines a peripheral compartment 3 of output rate $k31$.

3.5.2.3.3.5 Arguments for the effect compartment of a standard PK model

- **{Cc, Ce}** = pkmodel(...): The second output is the concentration within the effect compartment. Another name can be used.
- **ke0**: Defines an effect compartment with transfer rate ke0 from the central compartment.

3.5.2.3.3.6 Additional possibilities

Knowing the label of the central compartment (cmt=1) and the administration type supported by the function pkmodel (type=1), one can build up a custom PK model by adding other PK elements to a base standard PK model. Referencing this label and administration type of value 1 allows to connect the additional PK elements.

3.5.2.3.3.7 Overview of arguments

Pkmodel function input	Process	Required parameter	Optional parameter	Excluded parameter
Administration	Bolus		Tlag, p	Tk0, ka, Ktr, Mtt
	Zero order absorption	Tk0	Tlag, p	ka, Ktr, Mtt
	First order absorption	ka	Tlag, p	Tk0
	Absorption with transit compartments of mean transit time Mtt and transit rate Ktr	ka, Ktr, Mtt	Tlag, p	Tk0
	Bioavailability; fraction of the dose absorbed	p	Tlag, Tk0, ka, Ktr, Mtt	
Compartment	Volume	V		
Elimination	Linear, rate	k		Cl, Km, Vm
	Linear, clearance	Cl		k, Km, Vm
	Michaelis Menten	Km, Vm		k, Cl
Transfers	Transfer rates	(k12,k21) (k13, k31)		
	Effect compartment transfer rate constant	ke0		

Output	Concentration in the central compartment	first output name		
	Concentration in the effect compartment	second output name		

3.5.2.3.4 Rules

- Only one type of administration is allowed
- Only one **pkmodel** function is allowed in the Mlxtran file
- Arguments must be from the list of defined arguments for **pkmodel**. Arguments with different names are not recognized.
- **pkmodel** can not be used together with any macros for the administration. The administration is defined exclusively with the arguments supplied to pkmodel()
- A **pkmodel** output can be used with ODEs or with macros.
- **pkmodel** can also be defined in the PK: block or the EQUATION: block.

3.5.2.4 piecewise macros

3.5.2.4.1 Introduction

The mlxtran language provides a set of macros which allow to define a model piecewise, by defining each compartment and the transfer between compartments. The purpose of these macros is to simplify the modeling of classical pharmacokinetics. The PK model is inferred from the ensemble of used macros and the provided set of named arguments. The piecewise macros must be used within the block PK:

An example is shown below:

```
PK:
; definition of the central compartment, numbered 1, with volume V and concentration Cc
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
; definition of an oral absorption with first-order rate ka and bioavailability F for
doses with admid=1
; arriving into the central compartment. Note that the depot compartment is implicit.
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=F)
; definition of an iv administration into central compartment for doses with admid=2
iv(adm=2, cmt=1)
; definition of an elimination from the central compartment 1 with clearance Cl
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

3.5.2.4.2 Compartment macro

Purpose

The macro `compartment` defines a PK model compartment. Compartments can be the target of an administration, can be subject to a clearance process or can be linked with other compartments for exchange processes. The compartment amount, concentration and volume are variables.

Arguments

Arguments for the macro `compartment` are:

- **cmt**: Unique identifier of the compartment. Its default value is 1.
- **amount**: Name of variable defined as the amount within the compartment. Its dynamics are defined by dose absorptions, eliminations, and the transfer rates with other compartments.
- **volume**: Name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment. It enables to define concentration. Its default value is 1.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the compartment.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; To define a compartment with number 1, of volume V, an amount called Ac, and a
concentration called Cc
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
```

If no administration is involved for a compartment, and if the amount and all its dynamics are defined as an ODE component with its derivative, then the compartment macro definition is not needed.

Complete Example

In the following example, a compartment is defined in the PK: bloc and the dynamics of the amount is defined with the iv and elimination macro:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
iv(cmt=1, type=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
```

Assuming the administration of a dose of amount=1 at time=5, we obtain the following for the concentration Cc:

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between concentration, amount, ...
CAUTION: if the volume is not given, it will be assumed to be equal to 1. The volume is in particular needed to calculate k from the clearance when Cl is used as input of the elimination macro.
- The compartment definition has to be done in the first place before additional macros.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after `amount=`, `volume=` and `concentration=` are necessarily strings.

3.5.2.4.3 Peripheral macro

Purpose

The peripheral macro defines a peripheral compartment. It is equivalent to a compartment with two transfers of drug amount towards and from another base compartment. This base compartment must have been previously defined and referenced by the indexes used in the parameter names: `peripheral(k12, k21)` defines a peripheral compartment numbered 2, which will be connected to the already defined compartment 1. If the amount or concentration of the peripheral compartment are not used afterwards, then they do not need to be defined as part of the macro.

Arguments

Arguments for macro peripheral are:

- **kij or ki_j**: Input rate from the compartment of label *i*. It also defines a label *j* for the peripheral compartment. Here, both labels *i* and *j* must be integers. If *i* and/or *j* are larger than 9, the syntax with the underscore is necessary. *Mandatory*.
- **kji or kj_i**: Output rate to the compartment of label *i*. It also defines a label *j* for the peripheral compartment. Here, both labels *i* and *j* must be integers. If *i* and/or *j* are larger than 9, the syntax with the underscore is necessary. *Mandatory*.
- **amount**: Name of variable defined as the amount within the compartment. Its dynamics are defined by dose absorptions, eliminations, and the transfer rates with other compartments.
- **volume**: Name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment. It enables to define concentration. The default value is 1. If the volume is not defined, the concentration cannot be defined.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the peripheral compartment.

Most of the time it is not necessary to name the amount, volume and concentration.

Example

```
PK:
; definition of a peripheral compartment with cmt=2 with rates k12 and k21
peripheral(k12, k21)

; if the concentration in the peripheral compartment is measured
; a volume V2, and a concentration Cp can also be defined
peripheral(k12, k21, volume=V2, concentration=Cp)

; definition of a peripheral compartment with cmt=3, linked to compartment 1,
peripheral(k13, k31)

; using Q and V2 instead
peripheral(k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

```
; with compartments numbers larger than 9
peripheral(k2_13, k13_2)
```

Rules and best practices

- To use inter-compartment clearance *Q* and peripheral volume *V2* as parameters instead of *k12* and *k21*, the syntax is:

```
peripheral(k12=Q/V, k21=Q/V2)
```

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The values after *k* are necessarily an integer (related to predefined compartment id).
 - The value after *kij=* can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter.

- The value after amount= and concentration= are necessarily strings.
- The value after volume= can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter.

3.5.2.4.4 Effect macro

Purpose

The macro effect defines an effect compartment. The effect compartment is usually linked to a central compartment. The drug exchange between the effect compartment and the central compartment does not affect the mass balance of the amount in the central compartment (its impact is considered negligible). The central compartment must be defined before the effect compartment is defined.

Arguments

Arguments for the macro effect are:

- **cmt**: Label of the linked base compartment. Its default value is 1.
- **ke0**: Transfer rate from the linked base compartment. *Mandatory*.
- **concentration**: Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the effect compartment. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; Define an effect compartment linked to the base compartment 1,
; with a transfer rate ke0 to the effect compartment,
; with Ce as concentration's name
effect(cmt=1, ke0, concentration=Ce)
```

Complete Example:

In the following example, a compartment is defined in the PK: bloc. An iv absorption process along with a linear elimination process is added to the main compartment. An effect compartment is added with a transfer rate ke0.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k, ke0}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
iv(cmt=1)
effect(cmt=1, ke0, concentration=Ce)
```

Assuming a single infusion at time=5 for a duration of 2hr, the concentration in the central compartment (orange) and in the effect compartment (blue) are:

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between fields.
- A base compartment must be defined first.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after `ke0=` can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
 - The value after `concentration=` is necessarily a string.

3.5.2.4.5 Transfer macro

Purpose

The macro transfer defines a uni-directional transfer process from a base compartment to a target compartment. The base compartment and the target compartment must be defined first before the transfer can be defined. For the more common bi-directional transfer process it is better to use the macro peripheral instead of the macro transfer, in particular as it allows to use the analytical solution, which is not the case with the macro transfer.

Arguments

Its named arguments are:

- **from**: Label of the source compartment for the transfer. Its default value is 1.
- **to**: Label of the target compartment for the transfer. Its default value is 1.
- **kt**: Rate of the transfer. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

```
PK:
; transfer from compartment 1 to compartment 2 with a rate kt
transfer(from=1, to=2, kt)
```

Complete Example

In the following example, a sigmoid absorption model is shown. Two compartments are defined in the PK block to specify a depot and a central compartment. The oral() macro defines a zero-order absorption into the depot compartment (A transfer from compartment 1 to compartment 2 is added, with a transfer rate kt).

```
<MODEL>
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl}

PK:
; depot compartment
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ad)
; central compartment
compartment(cmt=2, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
; zero-order absorption into the depot compartment 1
oral(cmt=1, Tk0)
; first-order transfer from depot (1) to central (2)
transfer(from=1, to=2, kt=ka)
; elimination from central compartment (2)
elimination(cmt=2, Cl)
```

Best Practices

- We encourage the user to use all the fields in the macro to guarantee non confusion between the fields.
- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after from= and to= are necessarily integers.
 - The value after kt= can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.

3.5.2.4.6 Absorption/oral macro

Purpose

The macro absorption/oral enables to link the administration and the model, for zero-order and first-order absorption processes (for bolus administrations, use the iv macro instead). For Mlxtran the macro names 'absorption' and 'oral' can be used interchangeably. The administration can either be defined in a data set when Monolix is used, or the administration can be defined via an administration

design definition when Simulx is used. In order to handle models with several administrations each administration has a unique identifier called “adm”. This identifier must be defined in the data set or in the administration design definition, and used in the absorption/oral macro.

Arguments common to zero-order and first-order

The absorption/oral macro can be used for zero-order and first-order absorptions. The arguments common to the two absorptions are:

- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to be read by this macro. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.
- **cmt**: Label of the compartment called in by the absorption process. Its default value is 1. The corresponding compartment must be defined before using the absorption/oral macro using a compartment macro.

To define a zero-order or first-order absorption, the additional arguments defined below are needed.

Arguments specific to a zero-order absorption

To define a zero-order absorption, the following argument must be added:

- **Tk0**: Duration of the zero order absorption. *Mandatory to define a zero-order absorption.*

Example:

```
; zero order absorption process for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a  
delay Tlag of 1 and a duration Tk0  
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, Tk0 = 2, p=1)
```

Arguments specific to a first-order absorption

To define a first-order absorption, the following arguments can be added:

- **ka**: Rate of the first order absorption. *Mandatory to define a first-order absorption.*
- **Ktr**: Transit rate.
- **Mtt**: Mean transit time for the absorption.

Example:

```
PK:  
; first order absorption process for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a  
delay Tlag of 1 and a rate ka  
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, ka)
```

Note: in case of transit compartments, the mean transit time is defined as $Mtt = (n+1)/Ktr$ with n the number of transit compartments (excluding the depot compartment and the absorption compartment):

The implementation is the same as described in Savic et al, "Implementation of a transit compartment model for describing drug absorption in pharmacokinetic studies" (2007), except that to approximate the factorial $n!$, we use the gamma function, which is more precise, instead of the Stirling formula.

In case of multiple doses, we assume that the previous dose has been completely absorbed (i.e concentration in the Abs compartment is almost zero) when the next dose is administered. If this is not the case, the remaining concentration in the Abs compartment is erased when the next dose is applied, leading to a loss of dose amount entering the system.

Example with mixed absorptions

Some drugs can exhibit atypical absorption profiles with for instance a zero-order absorption followed by a first-order absorption, or first and zero-order simultaneously.

Sequential absorption, zero-order followed by first-order

In the example below, a fraction $F1$ of the drug is absorbed via a zero-order process for a duration $Tk0$. The remaining fraction $1-F1$ is then absorbed via a first-order process, which starts with a lag-time $Tk0$ (i.e at the end of the zero-order absorption phase).

```
PK:
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tk0, p=F1)
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=1-F1, Tlag=Tk0)
```

Simultaneous first-order and zero-order absorption

In the example below, a fraction $F1$ of the drug is absorbed via a first-order process (with absorption rate ka). Simultaneously the remaining fraction $1-F1$ is absorbed via a zero-order process.

```
PK:
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka, p=F1)
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, Tk0, p=1-F1)
```

A lag time for one or the other process can be added if necessary.

Example with different absorption models

In the presented example, we show the difference between the two absorption processes. In addition, the effect of the K_{tr} and M_{tt} parameters is explored in a third model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Tlag, ka, Tk0, Ktr, Mtt}

PK:
; model 1 with zero-order absorption
compartment(cmt=1, amount=A1, concentration=Cc_zoa, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=1, adm=1, Tk0)
elimination(cmt=1, k=1)

; model 2 with first-order absorption
compartment(cmt=2, amount=A2, concentration=Cc_foa, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=2, adm=1, Tlag, ka)
elimination(cmt=2, k=1)

; model 3 with transit compartments
compartment(cmt=3, amount=A3, concentration=Cc_foaT, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=3, adm=1, Tlag, ka, Ktr, Mtt)
elimination(cmt=3, k=1)
```

The three concentrations are presented in the following figure:

- zero order absorption (blue): the peak concentration is sharp
- first order absorption (orange): the peak concentration is more smooth. In addition, in this example it is delayed before of the T_{lag}
- transit compartments (purple): the start of the absorption is delayed and progressive

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` and `type=` are necessarily integers.
 - The value after `Tlag=`, `p=`, `V=`, `ka=`, `Tk0=`, `Ktr=`, `Mtt=` can be either a double or replace by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
 - The associated treatment or administration can not be defined with a rate nor an infusion timing (`RATE` and `TINF` column-types in the data set). If a rate or an infusion timing is present, the user can use the `iv` macro and/or define a compartment to define the dynamics of the absorption.

3.5.2.4.7 IV macro

Purpose

The macro `iv` enables to link the administration with the model, for intravenous doses (bolus or infusion). Doses defined in the data set without an administration rate or infusion time are instantaneously absorbed within the associated compartment, as an IV bolus. Doses with an administration rate or infusion time are absorbed according to a zero order process, as an IV infusion.

Arguments

Arguments for macro `iv()` are:

- **cmt**: Label of the compartment called in by the absorption process. Its default value is 1. The corresponding compartment must be defined before using the absorption/oral macro using a compartment macro.
- **adm**: Administration identifier of doses to take in. Its default value is 1. Alias: type.
- **Tlag**: Lag time before the absorption. Its default value is 0.
- **p**: Final proportion of the absorbed amount. It can affect the effective rate of the absorption, not its duration. p can take any positive value (including > 1). Its default value is 1.

Basic Example

```
PK; intravenous bolus for the doses of type 1, in compartment 1 with a delay Tlag at 1  
iv(adm=1, cmt=1, Tlag=1, p=1)
```

Complete Example

In the presented example, we show the difference two iv processes with and without a rate in the administration.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]  
input = {V, k}  
  
PK:  
compartment(cmt=1, concentration=Cc, volume=V)  
iv(cmt=1, adm=1)  
elimination(cmt=1, k)
```

The concentration in yellow shows the profile after an iv bolus dose. The concentration in blue shows the profile after an iv infusion of 17 minutes.

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after `cmt=` and `adm=` are necessarily integers.
 - The value after `Tlag=`, `p=` can be either a double or replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.
- With the `iv` macro, it is not possible to give the rate or duration of the infusion as a parameter or fixed value. To do so, use the absorption macro with duration parameter `Tk0` to define a zero-order absorption (i.e infusion).
- When the `iv` macro is used in combination with a data set with a column-type `RATE`:
 - if `RATE >0`: infusion with rate `RATE` and duration `AMT/RATE`
 - if `RATE <=0`: bolus
- When the `iv` macro is used in combination with a data set with a column-type `TINF`:
 - if `TINF >0`: infusion of duration `TINF` at a rate `AMT/TINF`
 - if `TINF <=0`: bolus

3.5.2.4.8 Empty and reset macros

Description

The macro *empty* can be used to set any component of the system, defined in an ODE, to 0 at any given time. Similarly, the macro *reset* is used to reset a variable of the system to its initial value. Empty or reset times are indicated via a type of administration (`adm id`). The actions of these macros are thus selective, contrary to the reset applied with an `EVID` column in the dataset with values 3, which resets all compartments.

Arguments

The arguments are the same for both *empty* and *reset* macros:

- **adm**: Administration identifier used to indicate empty or reset times. Its default value is 1. Alias: type. The empty and reset macros only use the administration times, not the amounts.
- **target**: Name of the ODE variable that is set to 0 or reset to its initial value at the specified times, or target=all to reset all system variables. *Mandatory*.

Basic Example

The following code defines an emptying of the ODE variable Ap on administration times of type 1 (e.g ADM=1 in the data set).

```
PK:  
empty(adm=1, target=Ap)
```

This is equivalent to the following code with the depot macro:

```
PK:  
depot(adm=1, target=Ap, p=-Ap/amtDose)
```

The following code defines a reset based on administration times of type 2 (e.g ADM=2 in the data set), applied to the ODE variable Ac.

```
PK:  
reset(adm=2, target=Ac)
```

It is possible to define several *empty* macros with the same adm identifiers to set several targets to 0 at the same times, and the same for *reset* macros. With the example below, dose events with adm=3 will empty both variables Ac and Ap.

```
PK:  
empty(adm=3, target=Ac)  
empty(adm=3, target=Ap)
```

To reset all variables of the system, "target=all" can also be used:

```
PK:  
reset(adm=3, target=all)
```

Complete example: urine compartment

The following script implements a two compartments model with an additional urine compartment. There is a transfer from the central compartment to the urine compartment. A single dose with $adm=1$ is administered to the central compartment at time 0. A selective reset of the urine compartment corresponding to collecting times is defined with an administration with $adm=2$. Each amount for this administration is defined as 1 but is actually not used in the model.

When using this model with a data set, urine would be collected over consecutive periods of 12 hours and the amount of drug measured in the urine volume collected for each period would be recorded.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Cl, V1, Q, V2, p_urine}

PK:
k_urine = p_urine*Cl/V1
k_non_urine = (1-p_urine)*Cl/V1
k12 = Q/V1
k21 = Q/V2

; Dose administration to central compartment (plasma)
depot(adm=1, target=Ac, ka)

; Reset of urine compartment
reset(adm=2, target=Aurine)

EQUATION:
t_0=0
Ac_0=0
Ap_0=0
Aurine_0=0

ddt_Ac = - k_non_urine*Ac - k12*Ac + k21*Ap - k_urine*Ac
ddt_Ap = k12*Ac-k21*Ap
ddt_Aurine = k_urine*Ac

Cc=Ac/V1

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Aurine}
```

The model gives the following profiles for the drug amount in the urine compartment (blue, left), and the drug concentration in the central compartment (green, right).

Complete example: PD variable

Emptying a compartment or resetting it to its initial state are equivalent actions for compartment which are initially empty. This may be not the case for PD models with non-zero baseline, like in the following example where the PD variable E is reset to its initial value E_0 at time 60 and 108 using a dummy dose with $ADMID=2$.

```

<MODEL>
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, k, E0, IC50, kout}

PK:
depot(target=Ad, type=1)
reset(target=E, type=2)

EQUATION:
E_0 = E0
kin = E0*kout

ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac
ddt_E = kin*(1 - Ac/(Ac+IC50)) - kout*E

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
    
```


Rules

- The value after type= or adm= must be an integer.
- The value after target= must be a string representing the ODE variable.

3.5.2.4.9 Elimination macro

Purpose

The elimination macros permits to define different elimination processes (linear or Michaelis-Menten) for compartments. Several eliminations can be defined for the same compartment.

Arguments

Some arguments are common to the two elimination types, while some are specific to a linear or to a Michaelis-Menten type of elimination.

Arguments common to linear and Michaelis-Menten:

- **cmt**: Label of the compartment emptied by the elimination process. Its default value is 1.

Arguments specific to a linear elimination

The use of one of the following additional arguments defines a linear elimination:

- **k**: Rate of the elimination.
- **Cl**: Clearance of the elimination.

Only one of k or Cl must be defined.

Note, that if no volume has been defined for the compartment, then the default volume $V=1$ is assumed.

Example:

```
PK:
elimination(cmt=1,k)
```

Arguments specific to a Michaelis-Menten elimination

The use of both of the following additional arguments defines a Michaelis-Menten elimination:

- **Vm**: Maximum elimination rate. The unit of Vm is amount/time.
- **Km**: Michaelis-Menten constant. The unit of Km is a concentration.

Both arguments must be defined.

Example:

```
PK:
elimination(cmt=1, Vm, Km)
```

Complete Example

The following model implemented with PK macros includes two compartments, an oral absorption and a dual elimination pathway with parallel linear and Michaelis-Menten eliminations. An equivalent model, implemented with ODEs, is defined in the TMDD model library: it corresponds to the Michaelis-Menten approximation of a TMDD model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Vm, Km, Cl, Q, V2}

PK:
kel = Cl/V
k12 = Q/V
k21 = Q/V2
compartment(cmt=1, concentration=Cc, volume=V)
absorption(cmt=1, ka)
peripheral(k12, k21)
elimination(cmt=1, k=kel)
elimination(cmt=1, Vm, Km)

OUTPUT:
output={Cc}
```

Rules and Best Practices

- *Format restriction (non compliance will raise an exception)*
 - The value after cmt= is necessarily an integer.
 - The value after V=, k=, Cl=, Km=, Vm= can be either a double or be replaced by an input parameter. Calculations are not supported.

3.5.3 EQUATION: Writing model equations

In the EQUATION: block, direct equations, ODEs and DDEs can be defined.

3.5.3.1 Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Introduction

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs) can be implemented in the EQUATION: block of the [LONGITUDINAL] section. The ODEs describe a dynamical system and are defined by a set of equations for the derivative of each variable, the initial conditions, the starting time and the parameters.

Derivatives

The keyword `ddt_` in front of a variable name, as `ddt_x` and `ddt_y`, defines the derivative of the ODE system with respect to time. The variable names denote the components of the solution. These variables are defined at the whole [LONGITUDINAL] section level through their derivatives. The derivatives themselves aren't variables but keywords, and cannot be referenced by other equations nor be defined under a conditional statement (i.e within an if/else block).

Initial conditions

The keyword `t_0` defines the initial time of the differential equation, while the variable names with suffix `_0` define the initial conditions of the system. More precisely, in a differential equation for the variable **x**, **x** is defined at **t = t0** by the initial condition `x_0`, i.e. $x(t_0) = x_0$ and by the differential equation after `t0`.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=e8VGTZdbToY>

Linking administration with ODEs

Mlxtran provides the PK macro `depot()` that can be used to link the administration from a data set with the model.

Details and examples how to use `depot()` for the administration are given [here](#).

Ordinary differential equations (ODEs)

Example

We consider in this example a first order differential equation on **x** defined by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dA_c}{dt} = -k \times A_c \\ A_c(t = 0) = D \end{cases}$$

with *k* the elimination rate and *D* the dose given as a bolus at time 0.

The mlxtran implementation is:

```
DESCRIPTION: Model description with a simple ODE representing a linear
elimination process of a volume
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {k}

EQUATION:
D = 10
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = D
ddt_Ad = -k*Ad
```

Stiff versus non-stiff ODEs

A numerical algorithm providing an efficient and stable way to solve the ODEs and DDEs is used to compute the solution of the dynamical models. Different numerical algorithms can be used to solve the ODE depending on the properties of the ODE system (Adams methods for non stiff ODEs, and Backward Differentiation Formulas methods for stiff ODEs). The right numerical algorithm must be selected in order to get an accurate and stable solution within a reasonable computational time. The stiffness of an ODE systems is one of the main properties that influences the choice of the numerical algorithms. Stiff ODEs can lead to very long computational times if an inappropriate algorithm is used. Stiff ODEs are typical for models that include processes taking place at different time scales. For example models with reaction and diffusion processes are known to be stiff. Reactions can occur at the seconds time scale while diffusion processes can take hours. For such cases a dedicated numerical algorithm for stiff ODEs is available.

A solver for stiff ODEs can be selected in Mlxtran using the keyword `odeType`. There are two possible choices for `odeType`:

```
; ode is considered as stiff
odeType = stiff
; ode is considered as non-stiff (default)
odeType = nonStiff
```

This command has to be defined in the [LONGITUDINAL] section. When `odeType` is not specified then the `nonStiff` ODE solver is used by default.

Note that:

- For the DDEs, the keyword `odeType` is ineffective.
- For many ODEs the stiff solver will provide the best solution.

ODE solver tolerances

The stiff and non-stiff solvers compute the solution of the ODE system up to a certain precision, which is defined through the tolerance. The values by default are the following:

- non-stiff solver: absolute tolerance 1e-6, relative tolerance 1e-3
- stiff solver: absolute tolerance 1e-9, relative tolerance 1e-6

The tolerances can be modified by specifying the desired value in the structural model file using the keywords `odeAbsTol` and `odeRelTol`, for instance:

```
EQUATION:
odeAbsTol = 1e-12
odeRelTol = 1e-9
```

The smaller the tolerance, the closer the computed prediction will be from the true solution. The absolute tolerance indicates how much the absolute difference between the computed prediction y_{solver} and the true solution y_{true} can be, i.e. $|y_{solver} - y_{true}| < \text{odeAbsTol}$. The relative tolerance is related to the number of digits which are correct, i.e. $\frac{|y_{solver} - y_{true}|}{|y_{true}|} < \text{odeRelTol}$.

Note that the right hand side needs to be a number (such as `odeAbsTol=1e-12` or `odeAbsTol=0.000001`) and cannot be an expression (`odeAbsTol=10^(-9)` is not accepted).

Rules and Best Practices

- We encourage the users to define the initial conditions explicitly, although the default initial value is $x_0=0$.
- When no starting time t_0 is defined in the Mlxtran model for Monolix then by default t_0 is selected to be equal to the first dose or the first observation, whatever comes first.
- If t_0 is defined, a differential equation needs to be defined.
- Initial conditions can depend on
 - time
 - an input parameter. Therefore, initial condition values can also be estimated in Monolix.
 - a regressor value. In that case, again, *a differential equation needs to be defined.*
- Only first order differential equation can be used with Mlxtran. If you want to use a differential equation of the form $\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = f(x, \phi)$, you need to transform the higher order differential equation into a first order differential equations by defining n successive differential equations as proposed in the following “Best Practices Ex. 1: Second order differential equation”.
- The derivatives of a ODE system cannot be conditional, i.e. `ddt_` cannot be used within an `if` statement. Instead, conditional intermediate variables for the values of the derivatives should be used as shown in “Best Practices Ex. 2: IF statement”. A conditional statement can be built by combining the keywords `if`, `elseif`, `else` and `end`. Several `elseif` keywords can be chained, and the conditions are exclusive in sequence. A default value can be provided using the keyword `else`, but also as a simple definition preceding the conditional structure. An unspecified conditional value is null. The enclosed variables are not local variables, which means that a variable with remaining conditional definitions is still incomplete and cannot be referenced into another definition, even under the same condition.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H46MeX8kXCs>

Best Practices Ex. 1: Second order differential equation

If you want to use a second order differential equation of the type $\ddot{x} + \dot{x} + x = 0$, with $(x(0), \dot{x}(0)) = (a, b)$, the structural model in Mlxtran writes

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a, b}

EQUATION:
t0 = 0
x_0 = a
dx_0 = b
ddt_x = dx
ddt_dx = -x-dx
```

Best Practices Ex. 2: IF statement

If a parameter value depends on a condition, it can be written with in Mlxtran with the usual if-else-end syntax. For example, if a parameter c should be 1 if $t \leq 10$, 2 if $t < 20$ and 3 otherwise, write

```
if t<=10
  c = 1
elseif t<20
  c = 2
else
  c = 3
end
```

Derivatives cannot be written within an if-else-end structure. Instead, intermediate variables should be used. For example, if a derivative of x over time should be 1 if $t \leq 10$ and 2 otherwise, write

```
if t<=10
  dx = 1
else
  dx = 2
end
ddt_x = dx
```

3.5.3.2 Delay differential equations (DDEs)

3.5.3.2.1 Introduction

Delay differential equations (DDEs) can be implemented in a block EQUATION: of the section [LONGITUDINAL]. For that, the function delay() is proposed. This function allows to delay a dynamical variable by a constant time (which can be estimated). One can also build a model with several delays. Note that delays in the absorption after drug administration represent a different process and must be implemented using the keyword Tlag in the administration macros.

The solver used for delayed differential equations is described in Kuate et al. "A delay differential equation solver for MONOLIX & MLXPLORE".

Since the DDE solver is slower than the ODE solver, we recommend the alternative implementation using ODEs only and presented in the following video, when possible, as it leads to greatly shorter run times.

3.5.3.2.2 Example

We consider in this example a first order delay differential equation on x defined by:

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = k_a \times x(t) - k \times x(t - \tau)$$

This DDE is typically an accumulation process with a delayed linear elimination treatment.

```
DESCRIPTION: Model description with a delay
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {x0, ka, k, tau}

EQUATION:
t0 = 0
x_0 = x0
ddt_x = ka*x-k*delay(x,tau)
```

The simulation of this model using (x0=10, ka=0.5, k=0.25, tau=2) is shown on the following figure. The interesting part in this example is that the delay leads to oscillations.

3.5.3.2.3 Rules

- The delay function can delay a “pure” component in a dynamical equation. There are three main things to point out and we will discuss the three of them:
 - By pure, we mean that the function can not take state calculations into account. In the previous example, if we had used `delay(k*x,tau)` instead of `k*delay(x,tau)`, this would have generated an error.
 - By component, we mean that the delay function can only delay variable with a dynamic behavior (defined by a derivative equation). In the previous example, using the delay function with anything else than `x` would lead to an error.
 - By dynamical equation, we mean that the delay function should be called directly in a `ddt_` equation. For example, if we have in addition a DDE of the form $\dot{y}(t) = x(t - 1) - y(t)$, one could be tempted to implement it in Mlxtran under the following incorrect form:

```
z = delay(x,1)
ddt_y = z-y
```

It should be defined directly as

```
ddt_y = delay(x,1)-y
```

The first implementation would lead to an error.

- The delay must remain constant over the time.

- It is good practice to define the initial conditions of the DDE system (t_0 and initial values for the variables). If the initial condition is not defined, then it is set to the default value 0. Notice that you can have varying initial conditions. Note also that an initialization can be performed if the values can be analytically computed. For example, we can define $x(t) = V(1 + t) \quad \forall t \in [-1, 0]$, and it would be translated in Mlxtran under the form

```
x_0 = V*(1+t)
```

3.5.4 DEFINITION: Defining random variables

The DEFINITION: block is used to define models for random variables which represent observations.

The observations can be:

- **Continuous observations** with a residual error.
- **Non-continuous observations:** count, categorical or time-to-event.

In Monolix, only non-continuous observation models are defined in the structural model file, while the continuous error models are defined in the interface and saved automatically in the Monolix project.

The following pages detail how to model the different types of random observations:

3.5.4.1 Continuous observation model

In Monolix, the residual error model for continuous observations must be defined via the GUI.

3.5.4.2 Time-to-event observation model

Related resources on modeling time-to-event data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of time-to-event data in the MonolixSuite.
- [Time-to-event model library](#): detailed description of the library of time-to-event models integrated within Monolix.
- [Time-to-event data models](#): examples of time-to-event data models from the Monolix demos.

On the current page, we explain the different models for time-to-event data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax.

Time-to-event observation model

Use of time-to-event data

Here, observations are the “times at which events occur”. An event may be one-off (e.g., death, hardware failure) or repeated (e.g., epileptic seizures, mechanical incidents, strikes). Several functions play key roles in time-to-event analysis: the survival, hazard and cumulative hazard functions. We are still working under a population approach here so these functions, detailed below, are thus individual functions, i.e., each subject has its own. As we are using parametric models, this means that these functions depend on individual parameters (ψ_i).

- The **survival function** $S(t, \psi_i)$ gives the probability that the event happens to individual i after time $t > t_{\text{start}}$:

$$S(t, \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(T_i > t; \psi_i)$$

- The **hazard function** $h(t, \psi_i)$ is defined for individual i as the instantaneous rate of the event at time t , given that the event has not already occurred:

$$h(t, \psi_i) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{S(t, \psi_i) - S(t + dt, \psi_i)}{S(t, \psi_i) dt}$$

This is equivalent to

$$h(t, \psi_i) = -\frac{d}{dt}(\log S(t, \psi_i))$$

- Another useful quantity is the **cumulative hazard function** $H(a, b; \psi_i)$, defined for individual i as

$$H(a, b; \psi_i) = \int_a^b h(t, \psi_i) dt$$

Note that $S(t, \psi_i) = e^{-H(t_{\text{start}}, t; \psi_i)}$. Then, the hazard function $h(t, \psi_i)$ characterizes the problem, because knowing it is the same as knowing the survival function $S(t, \psi_i)$. The probability distribution of survival data is therefore completely defined by the hazard function.

Repeated events

Sometimes, an event can potentially happen again and again, e.g., epileptic seizures, heart attacks. For any given hazard function h , the survival function S for individual i now represents the survival since the previous event at $t_{i,j-1}$, given here in terms of the cumulative hazard from $t_{i,j-1}$ to $t_{i,j}$:

$$S(t_{i,j} | t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(T_{i,j} > t_{i,j} | T_{i,j-1} = t_{i,j-1}; \psi_i) = \exp\left(-\int_{t_{i,j-1}}^{t_{i,j}} h(t, \psi_i) dt\right)$$

Observation model syntax

An observation variable for time-to-event or repeated time to event data is defined using the type `event`. Its additional fields are:

- `eventType`: Type of the events. The exact time of the events can be observed, or censored per interval. The respective keywords are `exact` and `intervalCensored`. By default, an exact time is assumed.
- `maxEventNumber`: Maximum number of events (integer). By default the number of simulated events is unlimited. If the event is one-off (as death for instance), it is important to indicate `maxEventNumber=1` to speed up simulations (including simulations for the prediction interval of the TTE plot in Monolix).
- `rightCensoringTime`: Right censoring time of events (number). It is useful for simulation only, and by default it is the actual time of the last record.
- `intervalLength`: Length of censoring intervals (number). It is useful for simulation only, and by default it is the tenth part of the global length.
- `hazard`: Hazard function.

Example

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={gamma, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(V,Cl)
haz = gamma*Cc

DEFINITION:
Seizure = {type = event, eventType = intervalCensored, maxEventNumber = 1,
rightCensoringTime = 120, intervalLength = 10, hazard = haz}
```

TTE model library

A library of typical parametric models is provided in Monolix: [Complete description of the TTE model library](#).

3.5.4.3 Count observation model

Related resources on modeling count data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of count data in the MonolixSuite.
- [Count data model library](#): detailed description of the library of count models integrated within Monolix.
- [Count data models](#): examples of count data models from the Monolix demos.

On the current page, we explain the different models for count data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax.

Count observation model

Use of count data

Longitudinal count data is a special type of longitudinal data that can take only nonnegative integer values $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ that come from counting something, e.g., the number of seizures, hemorrhages or lesions in each given time period. In this context, data from individual i is the sequence $y_i = (y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ where y_{ij} is the number of events observed in the j th time interval I_{ij} .

Count data models can also be used for modeling other types of data such as the number of trials required for completing a given task or the number of successes (or failures) during some exercise. Here, y_{ij} is either the number of trials or successes (or failures) for subject i at time t_{ij} . For any of these data types we will then model $y_i = (y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ as a sequence of random variables that take their values in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. If we assume that they are independent, then the model is completely defined by the *probability mass functions* $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$ for $k \geq 0$ and $1 \leq j \leq n_i$. Here, we will consider only parametric distributions for count data.

Observation model syntax

Considering the observations as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is completely defined by the probability mass functions $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$. An observation variable for count data, with name `Y` for instance, is defined using the following syntax:

DEFINITION:

```
Y = {type=count, P(Y=k) = ...}
```

- `type=count`: indicates the data type
- `P(Y=k)`: probability of a given count value `k`, for the observation named `Y`. The observation name is free but must be the same at the beginning of the line and for the probability definition. `k` is a reserved keyword and represents a positive integer. `k` supersedes in this scope any variable `k` defined previously. The probability must be in $[0,1]$.

A transformed probability can also be provided. The transformation can be log, logit, or probit. For instance with a log-transformation:

```

DEFINITION:
Y = {type=count, log(P(Y=k)) = ...}
    
```

As `k` is only recognized within the probability definition, it is not possible to define the probability using `k` in an EQUATION block above. However, it is possible to use if/else statements within the probability definition:

```

DEFINITION:
Y = {type=count,
  if k==0
  Pk = ...
  else
  Pk = ...
  end
P(Y=k) = Pk}
    
```

Common mathematical functions to define count distributions are `factorial(a)`, `factln(a)` (logarithm of factorial) and `gammaLn(a)` (logarithm of gamma function). They can be used with `a` any positive numerical value (not only integers). Note that factorials grow very rapidly and can be considered as “+infinity” in a computer, even when the probability is defined as a ratio of two factorials which stays with reasonable values on paper. It is thus convenient to work with logarithms of factorials, which grow much slower (see examples).

Examples

Example 1: Poisson distribution with time evolution

In this example, the Poisson distribution is used for defining the distribution of y_j :

$$y_j \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_j) \iff P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda_j^k e^{-\lambda_j}}{k!}$$

where the Poisson intensity λ_j is function of time $\lambda_j = a + bt_j$. This model is implemented as follows

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a,b}

EQUATION:
lambda = a+b*t

DEFINITION:
    
```

```
y = {type=count, P(y=k) = exp(-lambda)*(lambda^k)/factorial(k)}
```

Example 2: Binomial distribution

We consider `n` Bernoulli trials, each having a probability of success `p`. The probability of having `k` successes is:

$$P(Y = k) = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} p^k (1-p)^{n-k}$$

To avoid that `k!` be so large that it will be considered as NaN by a computer, it is good practice to define the log of the probability to convert the ratios of large number into a sum of smaller numbers:

$$\log(P(Y = k)) = \log(n!) - \log(k!) - \log((n-k)!) + k \log(p) + (n-k) \log(1-p)$$

The corresponding Mlxtran model is:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {n, p}

DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count, log(P(CountNumber=k)) = gammaln(n+1) - factln(k) -
gammaln(n-k+1) + k*log(p) + (n-k)*log(1-p)}

OUTPUT:
output = Y
```

Example 3: Poisson distribution with zero inflation

Zero-inflations can be encoded using if/else statements:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda, f}

DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count,
if k==0
Pk = exp(-lambda)*(1-f) + f
else
Pk = exp(k*log(lambda) - lambda - factln(k))*(1-f)
end
P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}

OUTPUT:
output = CountNumber
```

Library of count models

The MonolixSuite library of models includes many pre-written count data models: [Count library](#).

3.5.4.4 Categorical observation model

Related resources on modeling categorical data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of categorical data in the MonolixSuite.
- [Categorical data models](#): examples of categorical data models from the Monolix demos.

On the current page, we show details on the different models for categorical data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax.

3.5.4.4.1 Observation model for categorical ordinal data

3.5.4.4.1.1 Use of categorical data

Assume now that the observed data takes its values in a fixed and finite set of nominal categories $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_K\}$. Considering the observations $(y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ for any individual i as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is completely defined by the probability mass functions $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ and $1 \leq j \leq n_i$. For a given (i, j) , the sum of the K probabilities is 1, so in fact only $K-1$ of them need to be defined. In the most general way possible, any model can be considered so long as it defines a probability distribution, i.e., for each k , $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i) \in [0, 1]$, and $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | \psi_i) = 1$. Ordinal data further assumed that the categories are ordered, i.e., there exists an order \prec such that

$$c_1 \prec c_2, \prec \dots \prec c_K$$

We can think, for instance, of levels of pain (low \prec moderate \prec severe) or scores on a discrete scale, e.g., from 1 to 10. Instead of defining the probabilities of each category, it may be convenient to define the cumulative probabilities $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 1, \dots, K - 1$, or in the other direction: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \succeq c_k | \psi_i)$ for $k = 2, \dots, K$. Any model is possible as long as it defines a probability distribution, i.e., it satisfies

$$0 \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_1 | \psi_i) \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_2 | \psi_i) \leq \dots \leq \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \preceq c_K | \psi_i) = 1$$

It is possible to introduce dependence between observations from the same individual by assuming that $(y_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i)$ forms a Markov chain. For instance, a Markov chain with memory 1 assumes that all that is required from the past to determine the distribution of y_{ij} is the value of the previous observation $y_{i,j-1}$, i.e., for all $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$,

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | y_{i,j-1}, y_{i,j-2}, y_{i,j-3}, \dots, \psi_i) = \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = c_k | y_{i,j-1}, \psi_i)$$

3.5.4.4.1.2 Observation model syntax

Considering the observations as a sequence of conditionally independent random variables, the model is

again completely defined by the probability mass functions $P(y_{ij} = c_k)$ for each category. For a given j , the sum of the K probabilities is 1, so in fact only $K-1$ of them need to be defined. The distribution of ordered categorical data can be defined in the block DEFINITION: of the Section [LONGITUDINAL] using either the probability mass functions. Ordinal data further assume that the categories are ordered: $c_1 \leq c_2 \leq \dots \leq c_K$. Instead of defining the probabilities of each category, it may be convenient to define the cumulative probabilities $P(y_j \leq c_k)$ for k from 1 to $K-1$ or the cumulative logits $\text{logit}(P(y_j \leq c_k))$ for k from 1 to $K-1$. An observation variable for ordered categorical data is defined using the type categorical. Its additional fields are:

- categories: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers.
- P(Y=i): Probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y . A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be log, logit, or probit. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared.

3.5.4.4.1.3 Example

In the proposed example, we use 4 categories and the model is implemented as follows

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {th1, th2, th3}

DEFINITION:
level = {type = categorical, categories = {0, 1, 2, 3},
logit(P(level <=0)) = th1
logit(P(level <=1)) = th1 + th2
logit(P(level <=2)) = th1 + th2 + th3}
```

Using that definition, the distribution associated to the parameters are

- Normal for $th1$. Elsewise, it implies that $\text{logit}(P(\text{level} \leq 0)) > 0$ and thus that $P(\text{level} \leq 0)$.
- Lognormal for $th2$ and $th3$ to make sure that $P(\text{level} \leq 1) > P(\text{level} \leq 0)$ and $P(\text{level} \leq 2) = P(\text{level} \leq 1)$ respectively.

3.5.4.4.2 Observation model for categorical data modeled as a discrete Markov chain

3.5.4.4.2.1 Use of categorical data modeled as a Markov chain

In the previous categorical model, the observations were considered as independent for individual i . It is however possible to introduce dependence between observations from the same individual assuming that $(y_{ij})_{j=1,\dots,n_i}$ forms a Markov chain. If observation times are regularly spaced (constant length of time between successive observations), we can consider the observations $(y_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i)$ to be a discrete-time Markov chain.

3.5.4.4.2.2 Observation model syntax

An observation variable for ordered categorical data modeled as a discrete Markov chain is defined using the type `categorical`, along with the dependence definition `Markov`. Its additional fields are:

- `categories`: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers. It is defined right after type.
- `P(Y_1=i)`: Initial probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y . This probability belongs to the first observed value. A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be `log`, `logit`, or `probit`. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared. The initial probabilities are optional as a whole, and the default initial law is uniform.
- `P(Y=j|Y_p=i)`: Probability of transition to a given category integer j from a previous category i , for the observation named Y . A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be `log`, `logit`, or `probit`. The probabilities are grouped by law of transition for each previous category i . Each law of transition provides the various transition probabilities of reaching j . They can be provided for events where the reached category j is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind for a given law. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a transition probability can be deduced from others within its law, its definition can be spared.

3.5.4.4.2.3 Example

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a1, a2, a11, a12, a21, a22, a31, a32}

DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2,3}, dependence = Markov
```

```

P(State_1=1) = a1
P(State_1=2) = a2
logit(P(State <=1|State_p=1)) = a11
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=1)) = a11+a12
logit(P(State <=1|State_p=2)) = a21
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=2)) = a21+a22
logit(P(State <=1|State_p=3)) = a31
logit(P(State <=2|State_p=3)) = a31+a32}
    
```

Using that definition, the distribution associated to the parameters are

- Logitnormal for a_1 and a_2 to make sure that the initial probability are well defined.
- Normal for a_{11} , a_{21} , and a_{31} to make sure that the probability is in $[0, 1]$.
- Lognormal for a_{12} , a_{22} , and a_{32} to make sure that the cumulative probability is increasing.

3.5.4.4.3 Observation model for a categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain

3.5.4.4.3.1 Use of categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain

The previous situation can be extended to the case where time intervals between observations are irregular by modeling the sequence of states as a *continuous-time Markov process*. The difference is that rather than transitioning to a new (or the same) state at each time step, the system remains in the current state for some random amount of time before transitioning. This process is now characterized by *transition rates* $\rho_{\ell k}(t)$ from the state ℓ to the state k . Given that the system is in state ℓ at time t , the probability to be in state k after a small time h is:

$$\mathbb{P}(y_i(t+h) = k, |, y_i(t) = \ell, \psi_i) = h \times \rho_{\ell k}(t, \psi_i) + o(h), \quad k \neq \ell$$

The probability that no transition happens between t and $t+h$ is

$$\mathbb{P}(y_i(s) = \ell, \forall s \in (t, t+h) | y_i(t) = \ell, \psi_i) = e^{h \times \rho_{\ell \ell}(t, \psi_i)}$$

Furthermore, for any individual i and time t , the transition rates $(\rho_{\ell, k}(t, \psi_i))$ satisfy for any $1 \leq \ell \leq K$,

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \rho_{\ell k}(t, \psi_i) = 0$$

Constructing a model therefore means defining parametric functions of time $\rho_{\ell k}$ that satisfy this condition.

3.5.4.4.3.2 *Observation model syntax*

An observation variable for ordered categorical data modeled as a continuous Markov chain is also defined using the type `categorical`, along with the dependence definition `Markov`. But here transition rates are defined instead of transition probabilities. Its additional fields are:

- `categories`: List of the available ordered categories. They are represented by increasing successive integers. It is defined right after type.
- `P(Y_1=i)`: Initial probability of a given category integer i , for the observation named Y . This probability belongs to the first observed value. A transformed probability can be provided instead of a direct one. The transformation can be `log`, `logit`, or `probit`. The probabilities are defined following the order of their categories. They can be provided for events where the category is a boundary, instead of an exact match. All boundaries must be of the same kind. Such an event is denoted by using a comparison operator. When the value of a probability can be deduced from others, its definition can be spared. The initial probabilities are optional as a whole, and the default initial law is uniform.
- `transitionRate(i,j)`: Transition rate departing from a given category integer i and arriving to a category j . They are grouped by law of transition for each departure category i . One definition of transition rate can be spared by law of transition, as they must sum to zero.

3.5.4.4.3.3 *Example*

An example where we define an observation model for this case is proposed here

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={p1, q12, q21}

DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
P(State_1=1) = p1
transitionRate(1,2) = q12
transitionRate(2,1) = q21}
```

3.5.5 Language reference

3.5.5.1 Reserved keywords

Reserved keywords

Some keywords are used in Mlxtran for dedicated purposes. Thus these keywords are not available for re-definition or overloading.

Time-related keyword

The reserved keyword for the time is `t`. It corresponds to the time defined in the TIME column in Monolix, and the times defined in the treatment, observation and regressor elements in Simulx.

Example:

The keyword time can be used to define a time-varying clearance for instance:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, CLini, CLss, T12}

EQUATION:
Cl = CLss - (CLss-CLini)*exp(-t/T12)
Cc = pkmodel(V,Cl)
```

Administration-related keywords

Information related to the doses defined in the data set or in the Simulx treatment elements are available in the structural model via several keyword. They are piece-wise constant functions which value is updated each time there is a dose. Before the first dose, their value is zero.

The value of the keyword are directly related to the design, they are unaffected by the absorption/depot macros arguments such as Tlag or p. Note that doses are *not* discriminated according to their administration types.

- **tDose:** holds the time of the last administered dose.
- **amtDose:** holds the amount of the last administered dose.
- **inftDose:** holds the infusion duration of the last administered dose.

Example:

The keyword amtDose can be used to define a dose-dependent absorption for instance:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, D50}

EQUATION:
F = D50/(amtDose+D50)
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl, p=F)
```

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9gy1JLfdssl>

Full list of keywords

Reserved keywords

Here is the full list of Mlxtran keywords to use in Monolix, except:

- the keywords used for distribution definition (that are listed [here](#)),
- the keywords used for classical mathematical definition (that are listed [here](#)).

Name	Meaning	where can it be used ?	link
absorption	Macro used for defining the absorption process in a longitudinal model	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
adm	Type of administration (type and adm are equivalent)	In argument of the following macros: absorption, depot, iv and oral	depot macro, other macros
amount	Name of the variable defined as the dose amount within the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment and peripheral	link
amtDose	Amount of the last administered dose. This is a step function and is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	current page
bsmm	Mixture of continuous observations. It is a mixture between subjects model mixtures (BSMM). It assumes no inter individual variabilities for the proportions of each group (i.e. the probabilities to belong to the different groups). It is relevant only for Monolix.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
categorical	Type of observation model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link

categories	List of the available ordered categories for a categorical observation. They are usually represented by increasing successive integers.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is a category	link
cmt	Label of the compartment	In argument of the following macros: absorption, compartment, depot, effect, elimination, iv, oral	link
combined1	Combined error model $y = f + (a + b * f)e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
combined1c	Corresponds to a combined error model $y = f + (a + b * f^c)e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
combined2	Combined error model $y = f + a * e_1 + b * f * e_2$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
combined2c	Combined error model $y = f + a * e_1 + b * f^c * e_2$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
compartment	Macro used for defining a compartment	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
concentration	Name of the variable defined as the concentration within the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment, effect, peripheral	link
constant	Constant error model $y = f + a * e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
continuous	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link
count	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link

delay	It corresponds to delay function to define DDE.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
dependence	It corresponds to the label used to defined that an observation variable for ordered categorical data modelled as a Markov chain.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is categorical	link
depot	It corresponds to an absorption targeting a depot. A component of an ODE system is defined as the target depot for the doses.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
effect	This macro defines an effect compartment. It is linked to a simple compartment and used through the variable for its effect concentration.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
elimination	This macro defines an elimination process.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
else	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statment can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
elseif	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statment can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
end	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statment can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
errorModel	It corresponds to the label to define an error model for a continuous observation model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
event	Type of observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a type=	link

eventType	Label to define the event type for an event observation model. It allows to define if the exact time of the events or censored per interval is observed.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
from	Label of the source compartment for the transfer.	In argument of the following macro: transfer	link
hazard	Hazard function	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
if	It is part of a conditional statement. A conditional statment can be built by combining the keywords if, elseif, else and end.	In a block EQUATION:	link
inftDose	The keyword inftDose defines the infusion time of the last administered dose. This is a step function. The rate of the final absorption can be different from the rate of the administration process. It is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	current page
input	It corresponds to the definition of the inputs in a subsection	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL], [INDIVIDUAL], and [COVARIATE]	link
intervalCensored	Argument of eventType.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
intervalLength	Label to length of censoring intervals in an event observation model. It is useful for simulation only,	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
iv	The macro iv defines an absorption for intravenous doses. Doses without an administration rate or infusion time are instantaneously absorbed within the associated compartment, as an IV bolus.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link

linear	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system as linear	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
Markov	It corresponds to the dependence of a categorical observation model. It allows to define that the observation model is based on a Markov chain	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: after a dependence=	link
maxEventNumber	Maximum number of events in an event observation model. It is useful for simulation only	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
nonStiff	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system is nonStiff and thus yields to an adapted numerical scheme for the resolution	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
odeType	It is the label that allows to define the type of ODE.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
oral	It is a macro used for defining the absorption process in a longitudinal model	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
output	It allows to define the outputs of a structural model	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block OUTPUT:	link
P	The majuscule P corresponds to the definition of a probability	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
p	It corresponds to the bio availability in an absorption process	In argument of the following macro: absorption, depot, iv, and oral	link
peripheral	The macro peripheral defines a peripheral compartment. It is equivalent to a simple compartment with two transfers of amount towards and from another compartment.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link

PK	It defines where the macros are defined	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL]	link
pkmodel	It defines the macro pkmodel	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block PK: or in a block EQUATION:	link
prediction	It corresponds to the name of the base prediction variable	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
proportional	Corresponds to proportional error model $y = f + b * fe$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
proportionalc	Corresponds to proportional error model $y = f + b * f^c e$	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is continuous	link
regressor	It declares the input regression values.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], after the input definition	link
rightCensoringTime	Right censoring time of events. It is useful for simulation only	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION: when the type of observation is an event	link
sd	Standard deviation of the associated normal distribution (standardDeviation and sd are synonymous keywords)	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
stiff	It is an argument of odeType= and allows to define the dynamical system is nonStiff and thus yields to an adapted numerical scheme for the resolution	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link
t	time	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	Current page
t_0	Initialization time for the equations	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link

t0	Initialization time for the equations	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
table	This keywords declares the variables to record in tables.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block OUTPUT:	link
target	Name of the component of an ODE system that is shifted by the absorption.	In argument of the following macro: depot	link
tDose	The keyword tDose defines the time of the last administered dose. This is a step function. Its value is unaffected by any lag time Tlag. Indeed, a lag time targets the dose absorption. It is null before the first dose.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	Current page
to	Label of the target compartment for the transfer	In argument of the following macro: transfer	link
transfer	The macro transfer defines a transfer of amount from a first compartment to a second one.	In subsection [LONGITUDINAL] after PK:	link
transitionRate	Transition rate departing from a given category to another one. It is used in the definition of a categorical observation model.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
type	It allows the type of observation model. It can be continuous, count, categorical, or event.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block DEFINITION:	link
typical	It corresponds to the typical value during a distribution definition	In any distribution definition in a block DEFINITION:	link
use	It allows to define the regressor in the longitudinal subsection. Regressors are defined as inputs at the beginning and thus are specified as regressors using use=	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], after the input definition	link

volume	It corresponds to the name of predefined variable to use as the volume of the compartment	In argument of the following macros: compartment, effect, peripheral	link
wsmm	Mixture of continuous observations. It is a mixture within subjects.	In the longitudinal model, in subsection [LONGITUDINAL], in a block EQUATION:	link

3.5.5.2 If/else statements

If a parameter value depends on a condition, it can be written with in `MLxtran` with the usual if-else-end syntax. For example, if a parameter `c` should be 1 if `t<=10`, 2 if `t<20` and 3 otherwise, write

```

if t<=10
  c = 1
elseif t<20
  c = 2
else
  c = 3
end

```

3.5.5.2.1 Conditional derivatives

Derivatives cannot be written within an if-else-end structure. Instead, intermediate variables should be used. For example, if a derivative of `x` over time should be 1 if `t<=10` and 2 otherwise, write

```

if t<=10
  dx = 1
else
  dx = 2
end
ddt_x = dx

```

3.5.5.2.2 Example: count model

Some models from the Count model library are defined with if/else statements, such as the zero-inflated Poisson model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```

input= {lambda0, nu, f}

EQUATION:
lambda = lambda0*exp(-t/nu)

DEFINITION:
CountNumber= {type=count,
  if k==0
    Pk = exp(-lambda)*(1-f) + f
  else
    Pk = exp(k*log(lambda) -lambda -factln(k))*(1-f)
  end
P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}

OUTPUT:
output= CountNumber

```

3.5.5.3 Mathematical functions

The following usual mathematical functions are available. They perform scalar operations, either on integers or real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation.

Function	Syntax	Remarks
Smallest value	min(a,b)	
Largest value	max(a,b)	
Absolute value	abs(a)	
Square root	sqrt(a)	
Exponential	exp(a)	
Natural logarithm	log(a)	
Common logarithm	log10(a)	
Logistic function	logit(a)	
Inverse of the logistic function	invlogit(a)	
Probit function	probit(a)	Aliases: norminv, qnorm.
Normal CDF	normcdf(a)	Alias: pnorm.

Function	Syntax	Remarks
Sine	$\sin(a)$	
Cosine	$\cos(a)$	
Tangent	$\tan(a)$	
Inverse Sine	$\text{asin}(a)$	
Inverse Cosine	$\text{acos}(a)$	
Inverse Tangent	$\text{atan}(a)$	
Hyperbolic Sine	$\sinh(a)$	
Hyperbolic Cosine	$\cosh(a)$	
Hyperbolic Tangent	$\tanh(a)$	
Four quadrant inverse tangent	$\text{atan2}(a,b)$	
Logarithm of gamma function	$\text{gammaln}(a)$	Alias: lgamma
Downward rounding	$\text{floor}(a)$	
Upward rounding	$\text{ceil}(a)$	
Factorial	$\text{factorial}(a)$	
Logarithm of factorial	$\text{factln}(a)$	
Remainder after division	$\text{rem}(a, b)$	

3.5.5.4 Operators

The following operators are available, under their mathematical acceptance.

3.5.5.4.1 Arithmetic operators

The arithmetic operators perform operations on real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation. The specific operations on integers have a function call syntax, e.g. factorial.

Operator	Syntax	Remarks
Equal	$a=b$	Defines variables
Addition	$a+b$	
Subtraction	$a-b$	
Multiplication	$a*b$	
Division	a/b	
Power	a^b	Right associative
Unitary plus	$+a$	
Unitary minus	$-a$	

3.5.5.4.2 Logical operators

The logical operators perform operations on boolean values. They appear as conditions within conditional statements.

Operator	Syntax	Other possible syntax
Negation	$\sim a$	$!a$
Or	$a b$	$a b$
And	$a\&b$	$a\&\&b$

3.5.5.4.3 Relational operators

The relational operators perform operations on real numbers. These operations are performed using a double precision for their floating-point implementation.

Operator	Syntax	Other possible syntax
Equal to	$a==b$	
Not equal to	$a\sim b$	$a!=b$

Operator	Syntax	Other possible syntax
Greater than	a>b	
Less than	a<b	
Greater or equal to	a>=b	
Less or equal to	a<=b	2

3.5.5.5 Probability distributions

This page summarizes the distributions available in Mlxtran. They can be used to define random variables in the [LONGITUDINAL] section (observations). They are also used by Monolix to automatically define random variables in the [INDIVIDUAL] section (individual parameters) within the .mlxtran Monolix project.

3.5.5.5.1 Normal distribution and the associated transformed

To define the normal distribution and its transformations, Monolix uses the `typical` value of the distribution; as well as the standard deviation `sd` of the associated normal distribution. For the logitnormal distribution, the `min` and `max` can also be specified (optional). Covariates and correlations between random effects are also automatically added in the [INDIVIDUAL] section.

- Normal distribution, used with keyword `normal` : $h(X) = X$

```
y_norm = {distribution=normal, typical=0, sd=1}
y_norm = {distribution=normal, mean=0, sd=1}
```

- Log-normal distribution, used with keyword `lognormal` : $h(X) = \log(X)$

```
y_ln = {distribution=lognormal, typical=1, sd=0.3}
y_ln = {distribution=lognormal, mean=0, sd=0.3}
```

- Logit-normal distribution, used with keyword `logitnormal` : $h(X) = \log\left(\frac{X-a}{b-X}\right)$ with a and b the bounds of the logit-normal distribution indicated in the optional arguments `min` and `max`. By default, $a=0$ and $b=1$.

```
y_lgn = {distribution=logitnormal, typical=0.5, sd=0.6, min=0, max=1}
y_lgn = {distribution=logitnormal, mean=0, sd=0.6, min=0, max=1}
```

- Probit-normal distribution, used with keyword `probitnormal` : $h(X) = \Phi^{-1}(X)$, where Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution

```
y_pbn = {distribution=probitnormal, typical=0.5, sd=0.6}
y_pbn = {distribution=probitnormal, mean=0, sd=0.6}
```

3.6 Libraries of models

On the following pages you can find details about the models contained in each library of Monolix:

3.6.1 PK model library

The PK library is a library of standard PK models. Instead of writing the structural model yourself, you can select among simple PK models already written and verified for you. When you select the PK library, a full list of all available models appear. You can filter a specific model by selecting options for administration, distribution and elimination.

PK	Administration	Delay	Absorption	Distribution	Elimination
PD	bolus	no delay	zero order	1 compartment	linear
PKPD	infusion	lag time	first order	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
PK Double Absorption	oral/extravascular	transit compartments		3 compartments	
	oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion				

TDD: CLEAR FILTERS
 TTE:
 Count:
 TGI:

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 157
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 Showing 1 to 25 of 157 entries

Here we provide general guidelines to select a standard PK model that is the most suited to your dataset.

If you open any of the .txt files in this library, corresponding to the model written in mlxtran-formatted code, you see that the pkmodel macro is always used. This macro enables to define all standard PK models in a compact manner (except for <https://monolixsuite.slp-software.com/monolix/?contextKey=multiple-administration-routes>). It uses the analytical solution of the ODE system to simulate it, if it is available (which is the case for all models with linear elimination and without transit compartments), and otherwise the ODE system itself. A complete list of the analytical solutions for standard PK and PKPD models is available in this document: PKPDlibrary.pdf

If none of the standard PK models seems to fit your needs, consider using a model from our other PK libraries (PK double absorption, TMDD). To define your own custom PK model, jump directly to data and models.

All PK models in the library correspond to a system of equations with the following structure:

- an input rate which depends on the type of administration
- an ODE system based on a number of compartments
- an elimination rate which depends on the type of elimination selected.

The equations express the concentration $C_c(t)$ in the central compartment at a time t after the last drug administration:

- *Single dose*: at time t after dose D given at time t_D
- *Multiples doses*: at time t after n doses D_i for i from 1 to n given at time t_{D_i}
- *Steady state*: at a time t after dose D given at time t_D after repeated administration of dose D given at interval τ (only for linear elimination)

3.6.1.1 Routes of administration

You should know the type of administration to use based on the study that generated the dataset. The route of administration will determine the dynamics of the input rate $In(t)$ for the system described in the Distribution section.

To explore the differences in administration routes, we will see how they impact the input rate of a model with 1 compartment and linear elimination, parametrized with the clearance.

The ODE system for this model is:

$$\frac{dA_C}{dt} = In(t) - \frac{Cl}{V} A_C$$

$$C_C = \frac{A_C}{V}$$

3.6.1.1.1 Intravenous bolus

The intravenous bolus is an injection which quickly raises the concentration of the substance in the blood to an effective level. When bolus is selected, if D is the dose administered at time t_D , we set the amount in the central compartment to $A_C(t_D) = D$. This is equivalent to modeling the input rate as a Dirac delta $In(t) = \delta_{t_D} D$.

The response in the central compartment to a bolus in case of a model with 1 compartment with linear elimination is a decreasing exponential:

Administration	Distribution	Elimination
bolus	1 compartment	linear
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
oral/extravascular	3 compartments	
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion		

3.6.1.2 Infusion

This section focuses on intravenous infusion. For subcutaneous infusions, check the dedicated subsection in the oral/extravascular section.

To have the input modeled as an infusion instead of a bolus, you need to have a column tagged as 'infusion rate' or 'infusion duration' in your dataset in Monolix (the duration will be deduced from the amount and rate columns if rate is specified, and vice versa). In Simulx, you need to create a treatment element that is an infusion.

The intravenous infusion of duration T_{inf} sets the input rate to a constant value during the infusion, and then to zero: $In(t) = \frac{D}{T_{inf}} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D, t_D + T_{inf}]}$.

The response in the central compartment in case of a model with 1 compartment with linear elimination is increasing as soon as the infusion starts, and decreasing as soon as it stops.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination
bolus	1 compartment	linear
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
oral/extravascular	3 compartments	
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion		

Note that bolus and infusion models are encoded exactly the same way with the `pkmodel` macro. It is the `pkmodel` macro that will check if a column tagged as `INFUSION RATE` or `INFUSION DURATION` appears in the dataset, and if this is the case, use the analytical solution of the infusion equations instead of the bolus equations.

3.6.1.2.1 Oral/extravascular administration

In the case of an oral or extravascular administration, you have additional options for delay and for the type of absorption.

Administration	Delay	Absorption	Distribution	Elimination
bolus	no delay	zero order	1 compartment	linear
infusion	lag time	first order	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
oral/extravascular	transit compartments		3 compartments	
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion				

3.6.1.2.1.1 Absorption: 0 or 1st order?

The type of absorption will determine if the peak in the response is sharp or smooth.

A zero-order absorption is modeled with the same input rate as for an infusion, i.e. with a square pulse input, with 2 differences:

- the duration of the input T_{k0} is not known, it is thus part of the parameters to optimize, and it will influence the height and the duration of the response,
- a delay can be added between the dosing time and the start of the pulse, and this delay can also be optimized.

$$In^{0-order-lag}(t) = \frac{D}{T_{k0}} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D+T_{lag}, t_D+T_{lag}+T_{k0}]}$$

A first-order absorption will instead correspond to a sharper input pulse with a slow exponential decay which depends on the absorption rate. Because of this, the response peak is smoother. This input rate is the analytical solution of a system with a depot compartment where the dose would be added at time $t_D + T_{lag}$, and which would be transferred to the central compartment with an absorption rate k_a :

	$In^{1st-order-lag}(t) = Dk_a e^{-k_a(t-t_D-T_{lag})} \mathbf{1}_{[t_D+T_{lag}, \infty[}$
---	---

We compare here zero and 1st order absorption in the case of a lag time, but if there is no lag in the response, the no delay option can be selected and the parameter T_{lag} will disappear.

3.6.1.2.1.2 Delay: lag time or transit compartments?

In the case of a 1st order absorption, it is possible to select between two types of delay: a lag time or transit compartments. The type of delay selected will change the rising phase of the pulse input. A lag time corresponds to an instantaneous increase of the input rate at time $t_D + T_{lag}$ whereas transit compartments will lead to a more gradual increase of the input rate right after t_D . The rationale for transit compartments and alternative phenomenological models for delayed absorption are described here. Transit compartments are sometimes more accurate than a lag time but the models take longer to simulate because there is no analytical solution available.

Instead of adding the dose to a depot compartment which would be also the absorption compartment at $t_D + T_{lag}$, the dose is added at t_D but a number of transit compartments with transit rate k_{tr} between the compartments are added between the depot and the absorption compartment.

The input rate is the solution of the following system:

$$A_n = D \frac{(k_{tr}t)^n e^{-k_{tr}t}}{n!}$$

$$\frac{dA_a}{dt} = k_{tr}A_n - k_a A_a$$

$$In = k_a A_a$$

This absorption model gives more flexibility to fit the absorption phase with the 3 following parameters: transit rate k_{tr} , the absorption rate k_a and the mean transit time $M_{tt} = \frac{n+1}{k_{tr}}$.

3.6.1.2.1.3 Subcutaneous infusion

To have the input modeled as a subcutaneous infusion, you need to

- select a model with an oral/extravascular administration
- have a column tagged as 'infusion rate' or 'infusion duration' in your dataset in Monolix (the duration will be deduced from the amount and rate columns if rate is specified, and vice versa), or create a treatment element that is an infusion in Simulx.

Only 1st-order absorption is available in this case, and the input rate in case of Tlag (or no delay, i.e. Tlag = 0) is the solution of the following subsystem, combining the equations described above for infusion and for first-order absorption:

$$A_d(0) = 0$$

$$\frac{dA_d}{dt} = \frac{D}{T_{inf}} - k_a A_d$$

$$In(t) = k_a A_d(t - T_{lag})$$

3.6.1.2.2 Multiple administration routes

It is possible to use a combination of an oral or extravascular administration, and a bolus or an infusion. For this, a column should be tagged as administration ID in the dataset with 1 for all doses administered intravenously and 2 for orally or extravascularly administered doses. In this case, the input rate is the sum of:

- an infusion rate if columns tagged as INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION appear in the data, or a bolus rate otherwise,
- a rate for oral administration defined above.

In practice, most of the time the two administrations are not simultaneous and the rate takes in turn the value of a rate for an infusion/bolus and for an oral administration, according to the dosing times in the data set.

For each of the combined models, there is a possibility to incorporate the bioavailability by selecting the model with parameter F . This will multiply the oral/extravascular administration input rate by the number F . We give this possibility only in case of multiple administration routes because in a single route setting, F and V would only appear in the ratio V/F which makes them non-identifiable.

3.6.1.3 Distribution

The input rate defined by the administration route impacts the amount of drug in the central compartment. You can select to have additional peripheral compartments leading to a system with 1, 2 or 3 compartments in total:

Distribution

1 compartment

2 compartments

3 compartments

The ODE system for standard PK models involves one species per compartment. The amount of drug in the central compartment is called A_c , and for the 2nd and 3rd compartment it is called A_2 and A_3 . The output of the model is the concentration in the central compartment C_c .

The ODE system for each case is given here, parametrized by the volumes in each compartment V_1, V_2, V_3 and the inter-compartmental clearance Q .

Instead of using the inter-compartmental clearance Q_i between the central compartment and a peripheral compartment i , and a volume V_i for each compartment, it is also possible to use the volume V in the central compartment only and transfer rates for each peripheral compartmental compartment i :

$$i: k_{1i} = \frac{Q_i}{V_1}, k_{i1} = \frac{Q_i}{V_i}.$$

In and El rates are defined by the selected administration route and the elimination rate.

To show the impact of the number of compartments, we will see how they impact the response of a model with a bolus and linear elimination, parametrized with the clearance.

3.6.1.3.1 Impact of parameters in the case of 1 compartment

In the case of 1 compartment, the ODE system for a bolus with linear elimination parametrized with the clearance for $t \geq t_D$ is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_C(t_D) &= D \\
 \frac{dA_C}{dt} &= -\frac{Cl}{V} A_C \\
 C_C &= \frac{A_C}{V}
 \end{aligned}$$

The response is given by a decreasing exponential $\log(C_C) = \log\left(\frac{D}{V}\right) - \frac{Cl}{V}(t - t_D)$. If the elimination rate Cl/V is kept constant (to focus on the effect of the distribution parameters), increasing the volume V will translate the whole response down:

3.6.1.3.2 Impact of parameters in the case of 2 compartments

In the case of 2 compartments, the ODE system for a bolus with linear elimination leads to a response involving a sum of decreasing exponentials such that $\text{log}(C_c)$ shows 2 different slopes. Increasing V_1 makes the response start lower, increasing V_2 decreases the value at which the slope changes, and increasing Q moves this point earlier, making the slope change also sharper.

3.6.1.3.3 Impact of parameters in the case of 3 compartments

The case of 3 compartments is similar to the case of 2 compartments. $\log(Cc)$ shows 3 different slopes. V_1 , V_2 and Q_2 influence the early dynamics by playing on the initial value, and on the time and height of the first point of slope change. Q_3 and V_3 influence the later dynamics by playing on the second point of slope change.

3.6.1.4 Elimination

The elimination rate denoted in the previous section as El can be either a linear rate involving the clearance Cl , or a Michaelis Menten rate involving the constants Km and Vm . Another possible parametrization for the linear rate is using the elimination rate $k=Cl/V$. To visualize the difference in the response, we show below the response of a 1-compartment model to a bolus in the two cases.

3.6.2 PK/PD model library

The PK/PD model library is combining our library of standard pharmacokinetic models described on the PK model library page, with a library of standard pharmacodynamic models.

Most PD models included in the PK/PD library can also be used alone (without a PK model) in the PD library, and some models from the PD library are only available alone.

Here we provide general guidelines to guide you towards the standard PD model that is the most suited to your dataset. The guidelines are also summarized in this guidelines pdf: [summary_pkpd_library_v2.pdf](#)

The complete list and full equations for PD models in the PD library is available in this document: [PKPDlibrary.pdf](#) Here we focus on the PD models of the PK/PD library because they are the most widely used.

PD models can be categorized by:

- the type of response linking the concentration of the drug in the central compartment C_c to the effect E or to the response R . The effect can be either direct, or with an effect compartment, or an action on a turnover rate;
- the type of drug action on the response or on the rate. It can be a stimulation or an inhibition;
- the presence or absence of sigmoidicity in this drug action.

3.6.2.1 Type of response

The response links the drug concentration C_c to the effect E or the response R via a function A modeling the action of the drug. The type of response specifies whether this action impacts directly the effect, or via an effect compartment or turnover rates. The content of the action function will be specified in the next section: type of drug action. To explore the differences in the types of response, we will see how they impact the PD output for a 1 compartment PK linear infusion model, with a stimulation action of the drug and without sigmoidicity.

3.6.2.1.1 Direct

In case of a direct response, the effect E directly relates to the concentration in the central compartment C_C via

$$E = A(C_C)$$

Therefore the dynamics of the effect follow the dynamics of C_C without any delay, meaning that as soon as C_C starts decreasing, E decreases as well, and the trajectory in the phase plane C_C vs E is a single line because it follows the same route during the increase and the decrease of the signals. Below is an example simulation of a direct model with a stimulation action of the drug on the PD.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	Emax	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	Imax	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.6.2.1.2 Effect compartment

The site of action of the drug is often not be the same as the central compartment, and therefore a delay often appears between the PK and the PD measurements. To account for this delay it may be enough to add a single theoretical effect compartment with a drug concentration C_e equal to the concentration at the site of action. This theoretical compartment is assumed not to impact the

concentration in the central compartment CC , therefore we write the transfer arrows between the central compartment and the effect compartment with dashed lines. A single transfer rate ke_0 is used and the effect now directly relates to C_e :

$$\frac{dC_e}{dt} = k_{e0} C_C - k_{e0} C_e$$

$$E = A(C_e)$$

Below is an example simulation of a model with an effect compartment and with a stimulation action of the drug on the PD. The higher the transfer parameter ke_0 , the higher the response and shorter the delay in the response.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	E_{max}	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	I_{max}	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.6.2.1.3 Turnover

To model a PD response showing delay compared to the PK, it is also possible to consider that the PK concentration has an impact on the production or the degradation rate of a response variable R , as described by Sharma et al (1998). The response is then modeled with the following ODE:

- if action on the production rate: $\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} A(C_C) - k_{out} R$
- if action on the degradation rate: $\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} - k_{out} A(C_C) R$

In both cases, the model can be parametrized with the initial value of R R_0 and the parameter k_{out} , and k_{in} is derived as $k_{in} = R_0 k_{out}$.

We compare below the response in the case of production stimulation and degradation inhibition. k_{out} plays a similar role as ke_0 in the case of an effect compartment: the higher k_{out} , the shorter the delay.

The difference between a turnover effect on the production or on the degradation is not obvious when checking the response to a single dose amount. A clear difference can be seen if two different dose amounts are given to the same individual. In the case of a turnover on production, the responses will show exactly the same delay, whereas in the case of a turnover on degradation, the delay in the response will be different for different dose amounts.

3.6.2.2 Type of drug action

The type of drug action will determine the function A relating the PK concentration to the PD effect. It can be a stimulation or an inhibition, and it is written differently depending on the type of response.

3.6.2.2.1 Stimulation

- In the case of a **direct model** or an **effect compartment**, the action of stimulation is parametrized with E_{max} , EC_{50} , γ if sigmoidicity is selected (otherwise $\gamma=1$), and E_0 if baseline is selected (otherwise $E_0=0$). The equation for A in the most general case is:

$$A(C) = E_0 + \frac{E_{max} C^\gamma}{C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma}$$

where C is the concentration in the central compartment C_C if the model is direct, and the concentration in the effect compartment C_E if the model includes an effect compartment.

- In the case of a **turnover model**, the action of stimulation can happen on the production or on the degradation rate. In any case, it is parametrized with E_{max} , EC_{50} , and γ if sigmoidicity is selected, and the function always takes as an input the concentration in the central compartment CC . E_0 does not appear because turnover models already include a parameter R_0 to model the initial value of the response R .

$$A(C_C) = 1 + \frac{E_{max} C_C^\gamma}{C_C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma}$$

Below is the example response of a direct model with a stimulation action (called E_{max} in the drug action section of the library) and without sigmoidicity ($\gamma=1$). We show the influence of increasing E_0 , E_{max} , or the EC_{50} . The influence of the sigmoidicity parameter γ is shown in the next section.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	E_{max}	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment	I_{max}	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity
turnover			

3.6.2.2.2 Inhibition

- In the case of a **direct model** or an **effect compartment**, the action of inhibition is parametrized with E_0 , IC_{50} , I_{max} if partial inhibition is selected (otherwise $I_{max}=1$), γ if sigmoidicity is selected (otherwise $\gamma=1$). The equation for A in the most general case is:

$$A(C) = E_0 \left(1 - \frac{I_{max} C^\gamma}{C^\gamma + EC_{50}^\gamma} \right)$$

where C is the concentration in the central compartment C_C if the model is direct, and the concentration in the effect compartment C_E if the model includes an effect compartment.

- In the case of a **turnover model**, the action of inhibition can happen on the production or on the degradation rate. In any case, it is parametrized with IC_{50} , I_{max} if partial inhibition is selected (otherwise $I_{max}=1$), and γ if sigmoidicity is selected, and the function always takes as an input the concentration in the central compartment CC . E_0 does not appear because turnover models already include a parameter R_0 to model the initial value of the response R.

$$A(C_C) = 1 - \frac{I_{max} C_C^\gamma}{C_C^\gamma + IC_{50}^\gamma}$$

Below is the example response of a direct model with an inhibition type of action (called I_{max} in the drug action section of the library) and without sigmoidicity ($\gamma=1$). We show the influence of increasing I_{max} , or the IC_{50} . The influence of the sigmoidicity parameter γ is shown in the next section.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Inhibition	Sigmoidicity
direct	E_{max}	full inhibition	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment turnover	I_{max}	partial inhibition	with sigmoidicity

3.6.2.3 Sigmoidicity

Whether it is a stimulation or an inhibition type of action, the drug action function can always involve an exponent parameter γ . If this parameter is higher than 1, the response curve in the phase plane (C_c vs E) looks more like a sigmoid. Sigmoidicity can impact the dynamics in the PD response, making the response more switch-like due to threshold effects. If sigmoidicity is selected, the parameter γ will be estimated.

Below is the example response of a direct model with a stimulation type of action, and with sigmoidicity. The higher the gamma, the steeper the dose response, and the more square-like the time response.

Administration	Distribution	Elimination	
bolus	1 compartment	linear	
infusion	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	
oral/extravascular	3 compartments		
oral/extravascular and bolus/infusion			
Response	Drug Action	Baseline	Sigmoidicity
direct	E _{max}	with baseline	without sigmoidicity
effect compartment turnover	I _{max}	baseline = 0	with sigmoidicity

3.6.3 TMDD model library

3.6.3.1 Introduction to TMDD concepts

The concept of TMDD has been proposed as an explanation to the non-linear behavior (violation of the superposition principle and dose-dependent volume of distribution) displayed by some drugs such as bosentan. The concept was first formulated by Gerhard Levy in

Levy, G. (1994). *Pharmacologic target-mediated drug disposition. Clinical Pharmacology Therapeutics*, 56(3), 248–252.

Levy describes the TMDD in the following way: “a considerably larger fraction of the dose of these high-affinity compounds is bound to target sites, enough so that this interaction is reflected in the pharmacokinetic characteristics of the drug.”

Target-mediated drug disposition happens when the binding of the drug to the target influences the drugs distribution and elimination. This is in particular often the case for **biologics** (see section Examples of molecules), such as monoclonal antibodies for instance (for a review, see for instance Dostalek et al. (2013)), because they are designed to be highly specific and strongly bind to their target. In this case, the drug is eliminated both via usual linear clearance mechanisms, that dominate at high concentrations when the target is saturated, and non-linear target-mediated clearance (via binding and internalization of the drug-target complex), that is mainly visible at low concentrations.

The interplay of these mechanisms results in **complex concentration-time curves**. To describe the observed data, Mager and Jusko ((2001) JPP 28(6)) have introduced a set of equations that includes:

- the linear elimination of the ligand (elimination rate kel)
- the turnover of the receptor (synthesis rate $ksyn$, degradation rate $kdeg$, initial receptor concentration $R0=ksyn/kdeg$)

- the binding of the ligand to the receptor to form the complex (binding rate k_{on} , dissociation rate k_{off} , dissociation constant $KD=k_{off}/k_{on}$)
- the internalization of the complex (rate k_{int})
- (optional) the distribution of the ligand to a peripheral compartment (rates k_{12} and k_{21})

A key characteristic of TMDD systems is that the pharmacokinetic behavior depends on the dose. Let us focus on the free ligand concentration-time course with several doses of different magnitudes. In the figure below, we look at the concentration (on **log-scale**) with respect to time. In addition, we use a **bolus administration** and a **single compartment** for the ligand (the two compartment case will be studied later on).

As can be seen on the green curve, when **the initial concentration of ligand is larger than the initial receptor concentration (here $R_0=100$)**, the ligand concentration-time curve displays a complex shape (see also Peletier et al. (2012)) with:

- **Phase 1:** steep initial decrease, corresponding to the rapid binding of the ligand to the receptor.
- **Phase 2:** linear elimination phase, where the receptor is saturated with ligands (almost no more binding of ligand to receptor happens), and the ligand is eliminated via usual elimination processes (renal filtration, etc).
- **Phase 3:** transition phase, where the ligand binds to the no-longer saturated receptor.
- **Phase 4:** terminal elimination phase, where elimination of the free ligand happens mainly due to internalization (or degradation) of the target/receptor, which shifts the binding equilibrium out of balance leading to new binding of ligand.

Note that we focus on the concentration of the *free* ligand, such that binding of the ligand to the receptor constitutes an “elimination” mechanism in that it reduces the concentration of free ligand.

On the opposite, as can be seen on the red curve, if **the initial ligand concentration is of the same order of magnitude or lower than the receptor concentration (here $R_0=100$)**, the free ligand concentration time-curve displays two phases:

- **Phase 1:** steep initial decrease, corresponding to the rapid binding of the ligand to the receptor
- **Phase 4:** terminal elimination phase, where elimination of the free ligand happens mainly due to internalization (or degradation) of the target/receptor, which shifts the binding equilibrium out of balance leading to new binding of ligand

Note that in this case, the receptor is never saturated with ligand and target-mediated elimination usually dominates over the linear elimination. Thus, the curve goes directly from phase 1 to phase 4.

Below we show the **typical concentration-time curves for the other entities** in linear scale and log scale. The total ligand L_{tot} is the sum of free ligand L and bound ligand P (complex). The total receptor R_{tot} is the sum of free receptor R and bound receptor P (complex).

The original TMDD model and its approximations are useful to capture concentration data that display this kind of shapes, or part of them.

on linear y-scale:

on log y-scale:

3.6.3.2 TMDD library overview

The library contains a **large number of TMDD models corresponding to different approximations, different administration routes, different parameterizations, and different outputs**. In total 608 model files are available. The ordering and naming convention permits to easily browse through the list. The file names follow the pattern below:

3.6.3.2.1 Administration

Five different types of administrations are possible:

- **bolus**: iv bolus
- **infusion**: infusion with rate or infusion duration given in the data set (column RATE or TINF)
- **oral0**: zero-order absorption, with parameter Tk0 for the duration
- **oral1**: first-order absorption, with parameter ka
- **oral1+bolus**: first-order absorption or bolus depending on the dose. Bolus doses must be tagged with ADM=1 in the data set and first-order doses (oral or subcutaneous for instance) with ADM=2.

Note that repeated administrations are also allowed. If combinations other than oral1+bolus are necessary, the model file can be duplicated and modified to include a second administration type. In the model, the administration types are distinguished using the type or adm keyword. In the data set, an [ADM column](#) must be present.

3.6.3.2.2 Number of compartments

All models are available either with **1 compartment** or with **2 compartments** (central and peripheral). The impact on the model behavior will be detailed in the next section.

3.6.3.2.3 Models (approximations)

Beside the original full TMDD system of equations, **several approximations have been derived, corresponding to different limit cases**. The hierarchy of these approximations and their impact on the model behavior will be detailed in the next section.

3.6.3.2.4 Parameters

The list of parameters is mentioned in each file name. The naming convention follows Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). We use the parameters (ksyn, R0) instead of (ksyn, kdeg), and (kon, KD) instead of (kon, koff) because they allow an easier initialization of the parameters. For the elimination and peripheral compartment, two parametrizations are possible, either **using clearances or using rates**. In addition, a parameter Tlag is available to introduce a time lag for the administration.

3.6.3.2.5 Outputs

The model outputs will be matched to the observed data. If only **the free ligand L**, or **the total ligand Ltot** have been measured, the files ending with 'outputL' and 'outputLtot' can be used respectively. If one or several other entities have been measured, the model files must be adapted to output one or several variables in the `OUTPUT` section.

If several outputs are present, the outputs will be matched by order with the YTYPEs defined in the data set (first model output matched to observations with YTYPE=1, second model output matched to observations with YTYPE=2, etc). For all models except the Michaelis-Menten TMDD model, **the available outputs are the following:**

- **L:** free ligand
- **R:** free target/receptor
- **P:** free complex
- **Ltot:** total (free + bound) ligand
- **Rtot:** total (free + bound) target/receptor
- **TO:** receptor occupancy ($TO=R/R_{tot}$)
- **RR:** ratio of free receptor to baseline value ($RR=R/R_0$)

For the Michaelis-Menten TMDD model, only the free ligand L is available as output.

3.6.3.2.6 Adapting the models for multiple administration types

Except the oral1+bolus, the models from the library are written for only one administration type per data set. However, they can easily be modified to handle several types of administrations.

In the data set, the doses must be associated to an administration identifier in the ADM column. In the example below, the first dose is assigned to ADM=1 and the second to ADM=2. Often the CMT column of NONMEM data sets can simply be tagged as ADM column in Monolix.

ID	TIME	Y	AMT	ADM
1	0	.	500	1
1	7	55.2	.	.
1	14	44.3	.	.
1	28	35.5	.	.
1	32	23.9	.	.
1	60	.	100	2
1	67	61.1	.	.
1	74	47.3	.	.

Using the library model files as a template, the user can then create a new model file adapting the depot statements in the PK: block to its need. In the case of iv and sub-cutaneous administrations, one would write:

```
PK:
depot(adm=1, target=L, p=1/V) ; doses with ADM=1 in the data set, iv bolus
```

```
depot(adm=2, target=L, p=1/V, ka) ; doses with ADM=2 in the data set, first-order absorption with rate ka
```

For each dose, the depot macro will apply a bolus or first-order input rate to the target L, depending on the ADM identifier of the data set.

Do not forget to include the additional parameters into the `input` statement.

3.6.3.2.7 Overview of the model hierarchy

The figure below gives an overview of the different models, their parameter and the resulting typical concentration-time curve for the free ligand. The assumptions leading from one approximation to another one are also depicted.

The plots represent typical concentration-time curves in log-scale for the free ligand L. The arrows depict the degrees of flexibility: curved arrows denote that the angle can be changed, while straight arrows denote that the curve can be shifted.

A few comments to better understand the scheme:

- The QE and QSS models are shown together because their system of equations is the same. However the QSS model is derived from the full model using a quasi steady-state assumption. In this case, the name of the new parameter is $K_{SS} = \frac{k_{\text{int}} + k_{\text{off}}}{k_{\text{on}}}$.
- The parameters for the **second compartment** (k12 and k21) influence the non-linear concentration decrease in phase 2, but also the slopes of phase 3 and 4 (which is not depicted for clarity). In the models that lack flexibility in phase 4 (IB, Wagner, MM and const Rtot+IB), some flexibility is present due to k12 and k21 but it is tightly related to the shape of the non-linearity in phase 2.
- In the first and second rows of models, kint influences the slope of phase 4. On the opposite, in the third and fourth rows, kint influences the start time of phase 3, which was previously influenced by ksyn. Note that because $k_{\text{int}} = k_{\text{deg}}$ and $R_0 = \frac{k_{\text{syn}}}{k_{\text{deg}}}$, ksyn and kint are related via $k_{\text{syn}} = R_0 k_{\text{int}}$.
- The circled numbers represent the **number of parameters** for a two compartment model. In case of a one compartment model, the number of parameters would be reduced by two. With a single compartment, the phase 2 would be linear. In addition, phase 4 would be completely missing for the IB, MM and const. Rtot+IB models. These curves can be seen in the detailed description section.
- In the **IB model**, the kint parameter has no influence on the free ligand concentration L, but it has on the total ligand concentration Ltot. If only the free ligand concentration L is measured, the IB and the const. Rtot+IB models are equivalent.

3.6.3.2.8 Detailed description of the models

For clarity reasons, each model has its own dedicated page. All the links are below.

3.6.3.2.9 Typical parameters for TMDD

Following the PAGE talk by Leonid Gibiansky, the table below summarizes the typical TMDD parameters, their distribution, their usual range of values, their units, as well as possible covariates:

Parameter	Distribution	Typical value	Typical covariates
Dose	-	10-3000 nmol	-
Cl, Q	log-normal	0.24-1.4 L/day	weight, disease state, liver and kidney function, sex, anti-drug antibodies
V, V2	log-normal	3-6 L	weight
ka	log-normal	0.2-1.5 /day	age, formulation
kon	log-normal	1-100 /nM/day	-
koff	log-normal	0.1-100 /day	-
K _D	log-normal	1-100 nM	-
kint (soluble target)	log-normal	0.01-0.2 /day	-
kint (membrane target)	log-normal	5-100 /day	-
ksyn	log-normal	1-2 nM/day	-
kdeg	log-normal	1-150 /day	-
R ₀	log-normal	0.001-10 nM	-

Note that parameters related to the binding (such as Km, KD, kon, koff) depends on the molecule's chemical properties and are less likely to vary from individual to individual, compared to volumes or parameters that depend on enzyme levels such as kel for instance.

An extensive literature review of parameter values for monoclonal antibodies is also presented in Le Dirks (2010).

3.6.3.2.10 Examples of molecules

The table below presents a few examples of molecules displaying TMDD. Biologics are typical candidates for TMDD but small molecules can also display TMDD kinetics. The models used to describe the kinetics of these molecules range from simple MM TMDD models with one compartment to the full TMDD model with 2 compartments.

Drug	Type	Disease	Model	Ref
Tocilizumab	anti-IL6 mAB	rheumatoid arthritis	MM – 2cpt	Frey 2010
Omalizumab	anti-IgE mAB	asthma	QE – 1cpt	Hayashi 2006
HSP90 inhibitors	small molecule	cancer	QE – 1 and 2cpt	Yamazaki 2013
ABT-384	small molecule	diabetes	Const.Rtot – 2cpt	An 2014
recombinant VEGF	growth factor	cardiovascular	MM – 2 cpt	Eppler 2002
Thrombopoietin	cytokine	platelet	full – 2 cpt	Jin 2004

3.6.3.2.11 Extensions to more complex TMDD models

In this section, we propose links to resources to extend the proposed library of models to more complex TMDD models. The user who wishes to incorporate these extensions can use the library model files as a starting point.

3.6.3.2.11.1 PK/PD modeling

The mechanistic approach used in TMDD models makes it easy to extend the PK model to a PK/PD model and assume that the pharmacological effect is proportional to the concentration of the drug-receptor complex or to the target occupancy. PK/PD models for molecules displaying TMDD kinetics are for instance presented in Bauer et al. (1999), JPB 27(4), or in Mager et al. (2003), JPET 307(3).

3.6.3.2.11.2 Prediction of human PK from animal data

The prediction of the human PK of drugs is a key step for the accurate estimation of doses for first in human clinical trials. Two approaches are often used: allometric scaling and physiologically-based PK models.

Inter-species allometric scaling

To predict human pharmacokinetic parameters values from animal data, inter-species scaling is often used for small molecules. In the most common approach, the PK parameters are related to the body-weight using a power law. This approach is also often used for biologics, although possible species difference in the target must be kept in mind (Glassmann et al. (2016), JPP 43(4)). Successes and limitations are for instance presented in Kagan et al. (2010, Pharm Res 27), and Dong et al. (2011, Clin Pharm 50(2)).

Physiologically-based TMDD models

Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models extend typical PK models to more compartments that represent the different organs or tissues of the body, with interconnections corresponding to blood flows. The incorporation of the body's anatomy and physiology in a more detailed way makes it possible to predict human PK by adapting the volumes and flows of the animal body to those of the human body. A quite generic PBPK model for molecules displaying TMDD kinetics is presented in Glassman et al. (2016), JPP 43(3), and applied to four monoclonal antibodies. For three of them, the model could well predict the human PK.

3.6.3.2.11.3 Ligand facilitated target removal

To use ligand facilitated target removal (LFTR) model, presented in Peletier et al. (2021), a small change needs to be made to the full TMDD model available in the TMDD library. ODE line describing ligand behavior needs to be changed to $\text{ddt}_L = -k_{el} * L - k_{on} * L * R + (k_{off} + k_{int}) * P$.

3.6.3.2.11.4 More complex PK TMDD models

The full TMDD model presented here contains a number of implicit assumptions such as no binding in peripheral tissues, only one target, only one ligand, and no presence of endogenous drug amounts. Models have been proposed that alleviate these hypotheses. They are reviewed in Dua et al. (2015), CPT:PSP 4(6) and we here propose a short list of possible extensions:

- binding in the tissue compartment: Lowe et al. (2010), BCPT 106(3).
- multiple targets: Gibiansky et al. (2010), JPP 37(4).
- receptor recycling: Krippendorff et al. (2009), JPP 36.
- immune response: Perez-Ruixo et al. (2013), AAPS journal 15(1).
- drug-drug interactions: Yan et al. (2012), JPP 39(5), and Koch et al. (2017), JPP 44(1).
- endogenous drug present: Koch et al. (2017), JPP.

3.6.3.3 Detailed TMDD models

3.6.3.3.1 Full model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the original (full) TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.1.1 Equations

The first TMDD model has been proposed in Mager & Jusko (2001), JPP 28(6). The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - k_{\text{on}} L R + k_{\text{off}} P \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R - k_{\text{on}} L R + k_{\text{off}} P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{\text{on}} L R - k_{\text{off}} P - k_{\text{int}} P\end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma, R the *concentration* of the target/receptor, and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{off} the dissociation rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{\text{syn}}}{k_{\text{deg}}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters), and $K_D = \frac{k_{\text{off}}}{k_{\text{on}}}$ the dissociation constant (which replaces k_{off} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

If in addition the ligand can distribute to peripheral tissues, a **second compartment** can be added, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - k_{\text{on}} L R + k_{\text{off}} P - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R - k_{\text{on}} L R + k_{\text{off}} P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{\text{on}} L R - k_{\text{off}} P - k_{\text{int}} P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A\end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The main assumptions of this model are the following (Gibiansky et al. PAGE 2011 talk):

- the binding of the ligand to the target is simple, not cooperative
- binding occurs only in the central compartment
- target and complex do not diffuse to peripheral compartments
- internalized ligand-receptor complexes are not recycled

3.6.3.3.1.2 Model properties

To better understand the properties of such a model, we propose to **explore the typical concentration-time curves of this model and the influence of the parameter values**. We will focus

on the concentration-time curve of the **free ligand after a bolus dose**. The vignettes below explicit the impact of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time curve:

The effects are summarized below:

For every phase of the concentration-time curve, there exists a parameter to modify it. This is in contrast with the various approximations that lack flexibility for one or several phases of the curve.

3.6.3.3.1.3 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Full TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.6.3.3.2 Rapid binding (QE) and quasi steady-state (QSS) models

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the QE and QSS TMDD models, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.2.1 Rapid binding equations

The steep initial decrease (Phase 1) of the free ligand concentration in the full model usually occurs on a very short time-scale (minutes to hours) compared to the other phases (elimination over days or weeks). If the acquired data starts only after this initial phase, **the parameters associated with the binding (especially k_{on}) may not be identifiable**. This is why the rapid-binding (also called quasi-equilibrium) **approximation has been proposed**.

The first derivation has been detailed in Mager & Krzyzanski (2005), Pharm Res 22(10), while a more mathematically rigorous derivation can be found in Koch et al. (2016). JPP. In brief, **it is assumed that binding and dissociation of the ligand and target is much more rapid than the other processes**, such that the free ligand, free receptor and the complex are at quasi-equilibrium: $\frac{L \times R}{P} = K_D$ with $K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$ the dissociation constant. To derive a new set of equations, it is convenient to introduce the total ligand concentration $L_{tot} = L + P$ and the total receptor concentration $R_{tot} = R + P$. Below we present the equations using these quantities, which are the most common ones, but other equivalent formulations are also possible (see Koch et al. (2016). JPP).

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{int}} L_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{el}} - k_{\text{int}})L \\ \frac{dR_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{int}} - k_{\text{deg}})(L_{\text{tot}} - L) \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{\text{tot}}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

As before, V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, K_D the dissociation rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{\text{syn}}}{k_{\text{deg}}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

The complex concentration can be calculated via $P = L_{\text{tot}} - L$ and the free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_{\text{tot}} - (L_{\text{tot}} - L)$.

As for the full model, the system can be extended with a peripheral compartment, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{int}} L_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{el}} - k_{\text{int}})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{int}} - k_{\text{deg}})(L_{\text{tot}} - L) \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{\text{tot}}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

Note that the number of parameters has been reduced by one, as k_{on} and k_{off} have been replaced by K_D . The behavior of the rapid-binding approximation will be close to the full model behavior if indeed the binding and dissociation reactions are fast compared to the other reactions.

3.6.3.3.2.2 Quasi steady-state equations

The quasi steady-state approximation has been proposed by Gibiansky et al. (2008, JPP 35(5)) for the same reasons as the rapid-binding approximation: lack of identifiability of the full model for typical data sets.

In the QSS approximation, one assumes that the binding rate is balanced by the sum of the dissociation and internalization rates leading to $k_{\text{on}} L R - (k_{\text{int}} + k_{\text{off}})P = 0$, i.e. $K_{SS} = \frac{k_{\text{int}} + k_{\text{off}}}{k_{\text{on}}} = \frac{L R}{P}$.

The behavior of the QSS approximation is close to that of the full model if the binding, the dissociation and the elimination of the complex are fast compared to the other processes.

Again, it is more convenient to work with the total ligand concentration and the total receptor concentration, and the equations read:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{int}} L_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{el}} - k_{\text{int}})L \\ \frac{dR_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{int}} - k_{\text{deg}})(L_{\text{tot}} - L) \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_{SS}) + \sqrt{(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_{SS})^2 + 4K_{SS}L_{\text{tot}}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

The complex concentration can be calculated via $P = L_{\text{tot}} - L$ and the free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_{\text{tot}} - (L_{\text{tot}} - L)$.

And with a peripheral compartment, they read:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{int}} L_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{el}} - k_{\text{int}})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR_{\text{tot}}}{dt} &= k_{\text{syn}} - k_{\text{deg}} R_{\text{tot}} - (k_{\text{int}} - k_{\text{deg}})(L_{\text{tot}} - L) \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_{SS}) + \sqrt{(L_{\text{tot}} - R_{\text{tot}} - K_{SS})^2 + 4K_{SS}L_{\text{tot}}} \right]\end{aligned}$$

Notice that this system of equation is exactly the same as for the rapid binding approximation. The only difference is that the QSS approximation uses $K = K_{SS} = \frac{k_{\text{int}} + k_{\text{off}}}{k_{\text{on}}}$, while the rapid binding approximation uses $K = K_D = \frac{k_{\text{off}}}{k_{\text{on}}}$. The interpretation of the meaning of the parameter K differs, but the behavior of the QSS and rapid binding models are exactly the same.

3.6.3.3.2.3 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

Here is the summary figure:

The phase 1 is completely missing. Indeed, as the binding is assumed infinitely fast, part of the ligand binds immediately to the receptor. In addition, the slope of phase 3 is now fixed with none of the parameters having an influence on it.

Note also that both V and R_0 impact the initial concentration. However, whereas a change in V leads to the same shift of the initial concentration for all doses (on a linear scale), a change in R_0 shifts the initial concentration of low doses more. If the tested doses do not range over enough orders of magnitude, R_0 may be unidentifiable.

3.6.3.3.2.4 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way.

QE and QSS TMDD models with 2 compartments

3.6.3.3.3 Constant R_{tot} TMDD model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the constant R_{tot} TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.3.1 Equations

If the degradation rates of the free receptor and the complex are similar (i.e. the binding of the ligand to the receptor does not modify the receptor internalization rate), it may not be possible to identify both of them. If both rates are equal ($k_{int} = k_{deg}$), the total receptor concentration stays constant over time ($R_{tot}(t) = R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$) and the ODE system below can be derived, using the full model as starting point. This approximation is for instance analyzed in Peletier & Gabrielsson (2009). EJPS, 38(5). The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - (k_{el} + k_{on}R_0) L + (k_{off} + k_{on}L) P \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} R_0 L - (k_{off} + k_{int} + k_{on}L) P \end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{off} the dissociation rate, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$ the dissociation constant (which replaces k_{off} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

The free receptor concentration can be calculated via $R = R_0 - P$. Compared to the full model, the number of parameters is reduced by one, as k_{syn} and k_{deg} are replaced by R_0 .

With 2 compartments for the free ligand, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - (k_{el} + k_{on}R_0) L + (k_{off} + k_{on}L) P - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} R_0 L - (k_{off} + k_{int} + k_{on}L) P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

3.6.3.3.2 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

The summary figure is the following:

On opposite to the QE/QSS models, the constant R_{tot} model still captures all four phases of the free ligand concentration-time curve. However, note that because $k_{syn} = k_{int} \times R_0$, k_{int} now influences both the start time of phase 3 (as k_{syn} was doing in the full model), and height of phase 4 (and very slightly its slope at low doses). The flexibility on the slope of phase 4 is mostly missing.

3.6.3.3.3 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Constant R_{tot} TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.6.3.3.4 Irreversible binding TMDD model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the irreversible binding TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.4.1 Equations

If the binding of the ligand to the receptor is so strong that the dissociation of the ligand from the receptor is negligible, one can consider the binding reaction as irreversible, i.e. $k_{off} = 0$. This approximation has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. PAGE 2010 poster, as a simplification of the full model. In this case, the system of ODEs reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - k_{on} L R \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R - k_{on} L R \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} L R - k_{int} P \end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma, R the *concentration* of the target/receptor, and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, k_{syn} the synthesis rate for the target/receptor, k_{deg} its degradation rate, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $In(t)$ represents the input function,

corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

In the library model file, a slightly different parameterization is used using $R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$ the steady-state initial receptor concentration (which replaces k_{deg} in the list of parameters). This permits to better separate the effect of each parameter.

With a **second compartment**, one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - k_{on} L R - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R - k_{on} L R \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on} L R - k_{int} P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

This approximation has **one parameter less compared to the full model (koff is fixed to zero)**. In addition, if only the free ligand L and/or the free receptor R are observed, the equation for P can be removed, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - k_{on} L R \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= k_{syn} - k_{deg} R - k_{on} L R \end{aligned}$$

In this case, the system has two parameters less then the full system: k_{off} is fixed to zero and k_{int} doesn't influence the observed species L and R .

3.6.3.3.4.2 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts.

The summary picture is:

We observe that **the phase 4 is completely missing**. This approximation can make sense when the phase 4 is **below the lower limit of quantification** and no data point can be recorded in this zone. If this is the case, KD (or k_{off}) and k_{int} cannot be estimated. Note that if measurements about L_{tot} , R_{tot} or P would be available, then the k_{int} parameter might be identifiable.

3.6.3.3.4.3 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Irreversible binding TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.6.3.3.5 Wagner model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the Wagner TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.5.1 Equations

The constant R_{tot} , QSS/QE and irreversible binding approximations may still be overparametrized. A further simplification can be made and is called the Wagner model. It has initially been described in Biopharmaceutics and relevant pharmacokinetics by Wagner. The Wagner model can be derived from the QE/QSS approximation assuming in addition that the total receptor pool is constant (i.e.

$k_{int} = k_{deg}$ and $R_{tot} = R_0 = \frac{k_{syn}}{k_{deg}}$), as shown in Mager et al. (2005). It can also be derived from the

constant R_{tot} model by assuming in addition rapid binding (i.e. $\frac{L R}{P} = K_D = \frac{k_{off}}{k_{on}}$) or from the irreversible binding model by assuming in addition quasi-steady state of the free receptor ($k_{syn} - k_{deg}R - k_{on}L R = 0$, see Gibiansky et al. (2010) PAGE poster).

Adding these simplifications reduces the number of parameters by one more compared to the first

level of approximations, leading to 5 parameters for a 1 compartment model (or 7 for 2 compartments).

Two formulations are possible, either using the free ligand concentration L or using the total ligand concentration L_{tot} . To our knowledge, the formulation using L is always presented:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{\frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - \frac{R_0 k_{int} L}{K_D + L}}{1 + \frac{R_0 K_D}{(K_D + L)^2}}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, K_D the dissociation constant, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

If the system is derived from the QSS approximation, then K_D is replaced by K_{SS} . If it is derived from the irreversible model, then K_D is replaced by $K_W = \frac{k_{deg}}{k_{on}}$.

This formulation presents a disadvantage: in case of a bolus administration, the initial free ligand concentration cannot be assumed to be $L_0 = \frac{D}{V}$ with D the dose (amount of drug), because the dose will immediately split between the free and bound form due to the assumed infinitely fast binding. Thus a so-called dose correction is needed. For the first dose, the corrected initial concentration is relatively simple to calculate:

$$L(t=0) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{D}{V} - R_0 - K_D \right) + \sqrt{\left(\frac{D}{V} - R_0 - K_D \right)^2 + 4K_D \frac{D}{V}} \right]$$

however, the situation becomes more complicated for subsequent doses, where $R_{tot}(t)$ must be used instead of $R_{tot}(t=0)=R_0$.

We thus propose to use instead the formulation in L_{tot} (total ligand concentration):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

The number of parameters is the same, and the system complexity also. P , R and R_{tot} can easily be calculated using $P = L_{tot} - L$, $R_{tot} = R_0$ and $R = R_0 - (L_{tot} - L)$. Because the dose is applied to L_{tot} , no dose correction is needed: $L_{tot}(t=0) = \frac{D}{V} = P(t=0) + L(t=0)$, irrespective of the splitting of the dose between the free form L and the bound form P .

With a **second compartment**, the system becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dL_{tot}}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{int} L_{tot} - (k_{el} - k_{int})L - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A \\ L &= \frac{1}{2} \left[(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D) + \sqrt{(L_{tot} - R_0 - K_D)^2 + 4K_D L_{tot}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

3.6.3.3.2 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

The summary picture is:

The Wagner model combines the assumptions of the QE (or QSS) model and those of the constant R_{tot} model. **As for QE, the phase 1 is missing:** the free concentration of ligand directly starts at the equilibrium concentration. In addition, the lack of k_{on} passes on the lack of flexibility in the slope of phase 3. **As for the constant R_{tot} model, we also have a lack of flexibility on the slope of phase 4.**

3.6.3.3.3 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way.

Wagner TMDD model with 2 compartments

3.6.3.3.6 Irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the constant R_{tot} + irreversible binding TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.6.1 Equations

In the same way as the rapid binding + constant R_{tot} assumptions lead to the Wagner model, we can combine the irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} approximations to obtain a **new model**. To our knowledge, this approximation has not yet been presented in the literature. The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{el}L - k_{on}L(R_0 - P) \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on}R_0L - (k_{int} + k_{on}L)P\end{aligned}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma and P the *concentration* of the complex. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, k_{on} the binding rate, R_0 the initial receptor concentration, and k_{int} the degradation rate of the complex. $\text{In}(t)$ represents the input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

With **two compartments**, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{el}L - k_{on}L(R_0 - P) - k_{12}L + k_{21}A/V \\ \frac{dP}{dt} &= k_{on}R_0L - (k_{int} + k_{on}L)P \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12}LV - k_{21}A\end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The system has 5 parameters: same number of parameters as in the Wagner model, and one less compared to QE/QSS, irreversible binding and constant R_{tot} .

3.6.3.3.6.2 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

V (volume):
initial concentration

kon (binding rate):
slope of phase 1 and 3

kel (elimination rate):
slope of phase 2

kint (complex elimination rate):
start time of phase 3

R0 (initial target concentration):
depth of initial step decrease

Here is the summary picture:

If one looks only at the free ligand concentration, **this model is similar to the irreversible binding model. However it has one parameter less.** Note that the phase 4 is missing.

3.6.3.3.3 Model with 2 compartments

If a second compartment is added, the shape is modified in the following way. Note that k_{on} has been chosen large (very steep phase 1), to better focus on phase 2, where k_{12} and k_{21} have their main effect.

Const. R_{tot} + Irr. Bind. TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.6.3.3.7 Michaelis-Menten model

We here present the system of equation corresponding to the Michaelis-Menten (MM) TMDD model, as well as the model behavior.

3.6.3.3.7.1 Equations

The MM TMDD model has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). It is a further simplification of the Wagner model, assuming that $\frac{R_0 K_D}{(L + K_D)^2} \ll 1$. Introducing $K_m = K_D$ and $V_m = k_{int} R_0$ (which reduces by one the number of parameters), the equation for the free ligand reads:

$$\frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{In(t)}{V} - k_{el} L - \frac{V_m L}{K_D + L}$$

with L the *concentration* of the ligand in plasma. V is the volume of the central compartment for the ligand, k_{el} the linear elimination rate for the ligand, V_m the maximal velocity of the non-linear elimination and K_m the Michaelis-Menten constant of the non-linear elimination. $In(t)$ represents the

input function, corresponding to the input rate (amount per unit time) of the ligand into the central compartment due to the ligand administration.

With a **second compartment**, the model becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dL}{dt} &= \frac{\text{In}(t)}{V} - k_{\text{el}} L - \frac{V_m L}{K_D + L} - k_{12} L + k_{21} A/V \\ \frac{dA}{dt} &= k_{12} L V - k_{21} A\end{aligned}$$

with A the *amount* of ligand in peripheral tissues, k_{12} the rate of transfert from central to peripheral, and k_{21} the rate in the opposite direction.

The MM model can also be derived from the “irreversible + constant R_{tot} ” model, assuming a quasi state-steady on P (i.e. $k_{\text{on}}L(R_0 - P) - k_{\text{int}}P = 0$) and $\frac{R_0 K_I}{(L+K_I)^2} \ll 1$ with $K_I = \frac{k_{\text{int}}}{k_{\text{on}}}$.

In principle, a **dose correction must also be applied in case of bolus administration**, to split the incoming drug amount into free and bound ligand. However, the dose correction requires the use of one additional parameter, which would cancel out the advantages of the MM model compared to the Wagner or “constant R_{tot} + irreversible binding” models. Similarly, **the concentrations of P , R , R_{tot} and L_{tot} could be calculated from the concentration of L , but this would require to use of R_0 as additional parameter**. The MM model with 4 parameters (6 if 2 compartments) is thus applicable only if the only measured species is the free ligand.

3.6.3.3.7.2 Model properties

We investigate the influence of each parameter on the typical free ligand concentration-time shape for several dose amounts (bolus administration).

V (volume):
initial concentration

Km (MM constant):
slope of 3

kel (elimination rate):
slope of phase 2

Vm (MM reaction velocity):
start time of phase 3

The summary picture is:

The MM model with one compartment does not capture phase 1 and phase 4. In addition, the dose-dependent shift of the initial concentration is missing: the free ligand concentration starts at the concentration obtained by dividing the dose amount by the volume, as if the ligand would not bind to the receptor. If the amount of administrated ligand is large compared to the amount of free receptor, this assumption is reasonable.

3.6.3.3.7.3 Model with 2 compartments

The MM model is often used with a second compartment. In this case the shape is modified in the following way:

Michaelis-Menten (MM) TMDD model with 2 compartments

The introduction of a second compartment permits to recover a phase 4. Its flexibility is limited and linked to the effect of parameters k_{12} and k_{21} on phase 2.

3.6.3.4 Guidelines to choose a TMDD model

The choice of a model is often not trivial. Because the data may not be sufficient to identify all the parameters of the full model, the parameter estimation process using the full model may not only lead to parameter estimates with large uncertainty but also fail to converge. This page gives guidelines to help the modeler to choose an appropriate TMDD model for his data set.

The necessity of using simplified TMDD models is commonly the consequence of a limited data set and should not hide the fact that the reality may be more complex than the model.

In addition to using the TMDD approximation models (which are derived using assumptions on the parameter values), it is also possible to fix the unidentifiable parameter values, for instance using prior knowledge and typical values, while keeping the full TMDD model structure.

These guidelines are also conveniently summarized on this attached cheat sheet:

3.6.3.4.1 When to use a TMDD model

Several aspects can guide the choice of using a TMDD model.

First the **type of molecule**: biologics such as monoclonal anti-bodies, cytokines, growth factors, fusion proteins, antibody-small molecule drug conjugates or hormones are likely to display TMDD kinetics, at least in a certain concentration range. *Notice that even if the biologic is eliminated via a TMDD mechanism, the typical TMDD behavior may not be observable due to too high or too low doses.* In this case, a TMDD model will probably be over-parameterized. On the opposite, TMDD models should not be restricted to biologics as small molecules can also display TMDD kinetics (Guohua An (2017) J Clin Pharm 57(2)).

Second, the results of a **non-compartmental analysis (NCA)** can hint at TMDD kinetics if **the apparent volume of distribution or the total clearance vary between the first dose and subsequent doses or for different dose amounts** (Levy (1994), Clin Pharm Ther 56(3)).

Third, the **shapes of the concentration-time curves** is a key aspect. It will help to detect a TMDD behavior but also to choose the appropriate TMDD model among the several approximations possible.

3.6.3.4.2 How to choose a first model

3.6.3.4.2.1 Using prior information

The order of magnitude for some parameters might have been measured directly, for instance with in vitro experiments (e.g Biacore experiments, which usually provide k_{on} and k_{off}). This information can be used to choose an appropriate approximation:

- **evidence of fast binding to receptor** (high k_{on} and k_{off}) => QE, Wagner, MM
The influence of the k_{on} parameter on the concentration-time curve is depicted below using Mlxplora, for typical parameter values. When k_{on} is large, the initial drop of concentration due to the binding of the drug to the target is so fast that no data has been recorded in this part of the curve, therefore preventing a reliable estimation of k_{on} . In this case, as can be seen on the right, the QE

approximation gives the same concentration-time curve as the full model, except for the initial drop (phase 1).

- **evidence of irreversible binding to receptor** (very low dissociation constant K_D) => IB, "const. $R_{tot} + IB$ ", MMThe dissociation constant K_D controls the height of the last phase (phase 4). When the binding affinity is very strong and thus the K_D low, the last phase of the concentration-time curve is often below the LOQ and cannot be measured. In that case it is not possible to estimate K_D and one can assume that the binding is irreversible. As can be seen on the left panel, the full model and the IB approximation model will differ in a part of the curve in which anyway no data had been recorded.

- **evidence of similar rates for the elimination of free and bound receptor** (k_{deg} and k_{int}) => constant R_{tot} , Wagner, "const. $R_{tot} + IB$ ", MMIn the plot below (left), we show the total concentration of receptor. When k_{int} is larger than k_{deg} , the total receptor concentration will decrease after the ligand administration. Indeed, part of the receptor is then bound to the ligand and the complex is eliminated faster than the free receptor ($k_{int} > k_{deg}$). It is often the case in practice, as the binding of the ligand promotes the internalization of the receptor. On the opposite, when $k_{int} < k_{deg}$, the total receptor concentration increases. Finally, when the complex internalization rate k_{int} and the receptor degradation rate k_{deg} are very similar, the total receptor concentration is constant. The equation for the total receptor can then be dropped

leading to a system with less parameters to estimate. When truly $k_{int}=k_{deg}$, the constant R_{tot} model perfectly superimpose with the full model (right panel).

3.6.3.4.2.2 Entities measured

Usually, in the case of a soluble target, the total ligand concentration (L_{tot}) is available, and sometimes the free ligand concentration (L) and/or the total target concentration (R_{tot}). For membrane-bound targets, usually the free ligand concentration (L) is available, and sometimes the target occupancy (TO) (see Gibiansky et al. PAGE 2011 Talk).

The following outputs are available for all models except the MM model: free ligand L , total ligand L_{tot} , free receptor R , total receptor R_{tot} , complex P , target occupancy TO and ratio of free receptor to baseline RR . Here are the restrictions in the model choice depending on the measured entities:

- **only free ligand L measured** => all models
- **any other combination of measured entities** => all models except MM

3.6.3.4.2.3 Shape of measured concentrations

As can be seen in the overview figure, the different approximations lead to different typical concentration shapes. As a consequence, the shape of the measured concentrations is a key element to choose an appropriate model. Two situations are particularly common: first, if the binding of the drug to the target is fast, phase 1 will be very short (in time) and measurements may only start after phase 1. In this case, the parameters related to the binding (especially k_{on}) will not be identifiable and one can assume rapid-binding. Second, it may be that phase 4 appears at very low concentrations that are below the limit of quantification (LOQ). This may happen if the dissociation constant K_D is small, i.e if the binding is almost irreversible.

- **phase 1 not observable due to too rapid binding** => QE, Wagner, MM
- **phase 4 not observable because below LOQ** => IB, "const. R_{tot} + IB", MM

3.6.3.4.2.4 Range of doses

The initial receptor concentration R_0 and the volume of the central compartment V have a similar influence on the ligand concentration-time curve, except that the shift induced by a volume change is dose-independent (same shift for all doses), while that induced by a change in R_0 is dose-dependent (larger shift for small doses). **If the tested doses do not range over a sufficient range, R_0 may be difficult to identify.** In this case the MM model may be a good approximation. If the MM model is not possible or insufficient, it is also possible to fix the value of R_0 .

The plots below show the concentration-time profile for different initial receptor concentrations (related to the receptor production and degradation rates via \square).

- **$C_0 \gg R_0$:** When the initial drug concentration (calculated as Dose/V) is small compared to the initial receptor concentration, we recover the low dose case presented above, where only phase 1 and phase 4 can be seen.
- **$C_0 \approx R_0$:** When the initial ligand and receptor concentrations are of the same order of magnitude, the typical TMDD concentration-time curve shape is observed. The initial drop appears clearly and is dose-dependent. **If several doses are tested, R_0 (i.e. k_{deg}) is likely to be identifiable.**
- **$C_0 \ll R_0$:** When the initial drug concentration is much larger than the initial receptor concentration (which is often the case), the initial drop due to binding to the receptor is small on the scale of the ligand concentration and probably hard to quantify in the presence of measurement noise. In this case, **the parameter R_0 (or k_{deg} using the usual**

parameterization) which influences the height of the initial drop is usually not identifiable.

3.6.3.4.3 Improving the model

3.6.3.4.3.1 Bottom-up versus top-down approaches

A top-down approach to find an appropriate TMDD model has been proposed in Gibiansky et al. (2008), JPP 35(5). The procedure is the following: (i) fit the data with the full TMDD model, (ii) use the estimated parameters to simulate typical concentration-time curves with the full model and the approximations, (iii) if the simulations using an approximation are equivalent to the simulations with the full model, the approximation should be used. The strong disadvantage of this method is that the fitting of the full model may not converge, or give very uncertain estimates that are not informative and not reliable for simulations.

On the opposite, **in a bottom-up approach, simpler models are tested first and progressively complexified if mis-specifications are detected in the diagnostic plots.** Depending on the prior information, the first tested model can be any typical PK or TMDD model, and the diagnostic plots can help improving the model by removing one or several assumptions, in one or several steps. We recommend to use the bottom-up approach.

3.6.3.4.3.2 Examples of diagnostics

- **Residuals** (population weighted residuals, individual weighted residuals or normalized prediction distribution errors versus time or predictions): residuals plots help to detect if the model performs poorly for some specific times ranges or concentration ranges. Stratifying by dose group also permits to detect dose-dependent trends. An example is given below. **The trend in the residuals indicates a model mis-specification. In this case a more complex model (with more parameters and thus more flexibility) can be tried.**

- **Covariates:** plotting the distribution of parameter values (or of random effects) for the different dose groups (which needs to be considered as a categorical covariate) allows to detect dose-dependent trends that indicate a model mis-specification. In the figure below (left), the individual parameters distribution of V_m is stratified by dose and **shows a significant trend with increasing doses. This indicates that a more complex model is needed.**

- **Non-convergence of SAEM:** if the fixed effect estimates is unstable and/or the omega value representing the standard deviation of the random effects converges to a very high value (see example below), the model is probably over-parameterized. Several options are possible to reduce the model complexity: (i) remove the inter-individual variability on this parameter, (ii) fix the value of the parameter, (iii) choose a model with less parameters.

SAEM convergence

- High condition number:** the condition number is the ratio of the largest eigenvalue of the correlation matrix over the smallest value. High condition numbers hint at high correlations between parameters and thus model over-parameterizations. As a rule of thumb, condition numbers below 10 are ok, between 10 and 100 the model can be questionable, and above 100 the model is likely to be over-parameterized. In the example below, the high condition number probably reflects the high correlation between kdeg (kout) and KD. When the Monolix project is exported to Mlxplore using the last estimated parameters, one indeed clearly see that the influence of kdeg and KD on the concentration-time curve is the same. It will therefore not be possible to identify both. In this case, options are: (i) fix the value of one of the two parameters, or (ii) choose a model with less parameters.

```

correlation matrix of the estimates(linearization)
V_pop      1
kep_pop    0.07      1
KD_pop     -0.31    -0.17      1
kin_pop    -0.29     0.02     0.12      1
kout_pop   0.31     0.29    -0.97     -0.09      1
C11_pop    0.05     0.03    -0.15    -0.56     0.15      1
Q_pop      -0.29     0.05     0.01     0.37     0.03     0.02      1
V2_pop     -0.14     0.06    -0.29     0.48     0.28    -0.18     0.34

Eigenvalues (min, max, max/min): 0.019  2.4  1.3e+002
    
```

- High r.s.e values:** the r.s.e values indicate how uncertain the parameter estimate is. A high uncertainty may be the result of the parameter being unidentifiable because of lacking data. If a fixed parameter has a high r.s.e, one can try to either remove the IIV on this parameter, or fix this parameter value or try a model with less parameters. When an omega has a high r.s.e, one can try to remove the IIV on this parameter.

	parameter	s.e. (lin)	r.s.e. (%)
V_pop	: 2.51	0.093	4
kep_pop	: 2.8	27	958
kon_pop	: 17.1	12	73
koff_pop	: 0.00547	0.27	4.88e+003
kin_pop	: 1.6	0.089	6
kout_pop	: 0.672	0.52	78
C11_pop	: 0.126	0.0088	7
Q_pop	: 0.672	0.1	15
V2_pop	: 1.79	0.12	6

3.6.3.4.4 Conclusion

1. Visualize and explore the data before starting the modeling.

2. **Have in mind how the parameters influence the curves. It is possible to check the influence for specific parameter sets with Mlxplore.**
3. **Use the graphics to diagnose the model.**
4. **Try several models, the librairie makes it easy.**
5. **Consider several levels of flexibility:**
 - different model approximations, and 1 or 2 compartments
 - parameters estimated or fixed
 - parameters with or without inter-individual variability
6. **Keep in mind the ultimate modeling goal.**

3.6.4 Library of PK models with double absorption

Some drugs can display complex absorption kinetics. Common examples are mixed first-order and zero-order absorptions, either sequentially or simultaneously, and fast and slow parallel first-order absorptions. Multiple peaks in concentration-time curves can also be described with mixed absorptions, and can be explained by different physiological processes, such as enterohepatic recycling, delayed gastric emptying, or variability of absorption.

In most cases, a two mixed absorptions are sufficient to capture the main features of the absorption.

We have developed a library of double absorption models implemented in Monolix to take into account all the combinations of absorption types and delays. The absorptions can be specified as simultaneous or sequential, and with a pre-defined or independent order. This library simplifies the selection and testing of different types of absorptions and delays.

3.6.4.1 Modeling choices

In this documentation we detail the filtering options in the interface of Monolix, shown on the figure below, and the corresponding parameters and modelling choices.

First absorption		Second absorption				Global	
Type	Delay	Type	Delay	Order of absorption	Force longer delay	Distribution	Elimination
ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL	ALL
zero order	no delay	zero order	no delay	simultaneous	false	1 compartment	linear
first order	lag time	first order	lag time	sequential	true	2 compartments	Michaellis-Menten
	transit compartments		transit compartments			3 compartments	

In all cases, a fraction F1 of the dose is absorbed via the first absorption and the remaining 1-F1 fraction of the dose is absorbed via the second absorption. As the parameter F1 must stay within [0,1], a logit distribution is automatically chosen, and the default initial value is 0.5.

The choices for the **first absorption** are:

- **Type of absorption:**
 - zero order, modelled with the parameter Tk01
 - first order, modelled with the parameter ka1
- **Delay:**
 - no delay,
 - a lag time, modelled with the parameter Tlag1
 - transit compartments, modelled with the parameters Mtt1 (mean transit time) and Ktr1 (transfer rate)

The choices for the **second absorption** are:

- **Type of absorption:**
 - zero order, modelled with the parameter Tk02
 - first order, modelled with the parameter ka2
- **Delay:**
 - no delay,
 - a lag time, modelled with the parameter Tlag2
 - transit compartments, modelled with the parameters Mtt2 (mean transit time) and Ktr2 (transfer rate)
- **Order of absorption:** this option is available if the first absorption is a zero-order type, otherwise absorptions are always simultaneous.
 - Simultaneous: both absorptions are modelled with independent parameters. Depending on the values estimated for the parameters, the absorptions will be simultaneous or not.
 - Sequential: the second absorption starts at the end of or after the zero-order process corresponding to the first absorption. So the second absorption is necessarily modelled with a delay, with two possible parametrizations:
 - $Tlag2 = Tk01$ if “no delay” was chosen for both absorptions: the delay of the second absorption is equal to the duration of the first absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + Tk01$, if “lag time” was chosen for the first absorption and “no delay” was chosen for the second absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tk01 + diffTlag2$, if “no delay” was chosen for the first absorption and “lag time” was chosen for the second absorption. In that case $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$, but the value of $Tlag2$ will be available in the outputs of Monolix thanks to the table statement. This parametrization ensures that the delay for the second absorption is greater than the duration of the first absorption.
 - $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + Tk01 + diffTlag2$, if “lag time” was chosen for both absorptions. Similarly as before, $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$.
 - $Mtt2 = Tk01 + diffMtt2$, if “no delay” was chosen for the first absorption and “transit compartments” was chosen for the second absorption. Similarly as before, $diffMtt2$ is estimated instead of $Mtt2$.

- $Mtt2 = Tlag1 + Tk01 + diffMtt2$, if “lag time” was chosen for the first absorption and “transit compartments” was chosen for the second absorption. Similarly as before, $diffMtt2$ is estimated instead of $Mtt2$.
- **Force longer delay:** this option is available if both absorptions were selected with a delay (lag time or transit compartments), and if the absorptions are not sequential.
 - False: the parameters used to describe both delays are independent, so for the second absorption $Tlag2$ is estimated if “lag time” was chosen, and $Mtt2$ is estimated if “transit compartments” was chosen.
 - True: similarly as above, the parameter for the delay of the second absorption is forced to be larger than the delay of the first absorption. For example, if “lag time” was chosen for both absorptions, $Tlag2$ is written as $Tlag2 = Tlag1 + diffTlag2$, and $diffTlag2$ is estimated instead of $Tlag2$.

Finally, just like for the PK library, the remaining choices are:

- **Distribution:**
 - 1 compartment: the volume of the central compartment is V
 - 2 compartments: the two compartments are modelled with the parameters $V1$ (volume of central compartment), Q (inter-compartment clearance) and $V2$ (volume of peripheral compartment), or with V (volume of central compartment), $k12$ and $k21$ (transfer rates between the central and peripheral compartments).
 - 3 compartments: in the same way, the three compartments are modelled with $V1$, $Q2$, $V2$, $Q3$ and $V3$, or with V , $k12$, $k21$, $k13$ and $k31$.
- **Elimination:**
 - Linear: modelled with Cl (clearance) or k (elimination rate)
 - Michaelis-Menten: modelled with Vm and Km .

3.6.4.1.1 File names

The PK double absorption library contains many models, because of the many combinations of absorption types and delays for both absorptions, constraint on the time of the second absorption, distribution and parametrizations. In total 418 model files are available. The file names follow the pattern below:

In this pattern, *oral0* means zero-order absorption, *oral1* means first-order absorption, *seqAbs* corresponds to the filtering option “Order of absorptions = sequential” (the second absorptions starts at the end of the first absorption), and *seqDelay* corresponds to the filtering option “Force longer delay = true” (the delay for the second absorption is necessarily longer than the delay for the first absorption). If no keyword “*seqDelay*” or “*seqAbs*” are present in the file name, this is equivalent to the filtering option “Order of absorptions = sequential” and it means that the parameters for both absorptions are independent.

3.6.4.2 Examples

The models are written with PK macros.

For example, the model corresponding to a *zero-order* process with a *lag time* for the first absorption and a *simultaneous* (independent) *first-order* process with *transit compartments* for the second absorption, with a *longer delay* than the delay of the first absorption, a single compartment and parametrized with the clearance, is named *oral0_oral1_seqDelay_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1Tlag1diffMtt2Ktr2VCl.txt* and reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk01, ka2, F1, Tlag1, diffMtt2, Ktr2, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff

; Parameter transformations
k = Cl/V
Mtt2 = Tlag1 + diffMtt2

PK:
;PK model definition
compartment(cmt = 1, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0 = Tk01, Tlag = Tlag1, p = F1)
```

```
absorption(cmt = 1, ka = ka2, Mtt = Mtt2, Ktr = Ktr2, p = 1-F1)
elimination(cmt = 1, k)
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = Cc
table = Mtt2
```

3.6.4.3 Case study

A case study presenting a step-by-step modeling workflow for the PK of veralipride, using models from the double absorption library is available.

Veralipride plasma concentrations exhibit double peaks after oral absorption, due to site-specific absorption.

3.6.5 Library of parent-metabolite models

Drugs can undergo a transformation into metabolites – pharmacologically active and/or producing adverse effects. They can impact the pharmacokinetics of the parent and drive the efficacy. But, at the same time, can rise safety concerns. Joint parent – metabolite models account for the impact of the parent-metabolite interactions on the estimation.

Library of Parent – Metabolite models includes many characteristic mechanisms, such as first pass effect, uni and bidirectional transformation and up to three compartments for parent and metabolite, which makes it an excellent tool for exploration and modeling. Implementation with mlxtran macros uses analytical solutions for faster parameter estimation and makes a great basis for the development of more complex models.

Administration Select administration route, delay, absorption mechanism and first pass effect to correctly model drug input.	Transformation Check non-reversible and reversible metabolic systems to predict the impact of parent-metabolite interactions.
Distribution Explore different number of peripheral compartments independently for parent and metabolite.	Elimination Try linear or non-linear Michaelis-Menten elimination mechanism to get a better fit.

3.6.5.1 Parent-metabolite model filters

3.6.5.1.1 Administration

Parent-metabolite models can be combined with standard administration routes: bolus, infusion, oral/extravascular and oral with bolus. Intravenous doses are always administered to the central parent compartment. Oral doses can be in addition split between parent and metabolite – the first pass effect.

Intravenous doses (bolus, infusion) are always administered to the central parent compartment, can be with or without a time delay and does not include the first pass effect.

Oral doses can be with the following options:

- with or without the first pass effect
- zero ($Tk0$) or first order absorption process (ka for parent, kam for metabolite in case of the first pass effect)
- without or with a time delay ($Tlag$) or with the transit compartments (Mtt , Ktr)
- oral + bolus: bioavailability F (estimated as a separated parameter)

3.6.5.1.1.1 First pass effect

The first pass effect is a phenomenon in which a drug undergoes any biotransformation at a specific location in the body – for example transformation of parent to metabolite before reaching its site of action or the systemic circulation. The first-pass effect can be clinically relevant when the metabolized fraction is high or when it varies significantly from individual to individual or within the same individual over time, resulting in variable or erratic absorption. It also has an impact on peak drug concentrations, which may result in parent concentration peaks occurring much earlier.

In the Monolix library, models with the first pass effect include splitting a dose – with or without dose apportionment – and absorbing one fraction in the central parent compartment ($Tk0$ or ka) and the other fraction in the central metabolite compartment ($Tk0m$ or kam). The absorption process, zero or first order, is the same for parent and metabolite.

- **Dose apportionment** means that the splitting is independent of the absorption constants (Tk_0 , Tk_{0m} or ka , kam), with a fraction F_D of the dose leading to the parent and a fraction $1 - F_D$ leading to the metabolite prior to reach the plasma.
- In models **without dose apportionment**, dose splitting is implicit and results from different absorption rates ka , kam (or absorption times Tk_0 , Tk_{0m}).

3.6.5.1.2 Distribution

Parent		Metabolite	
Distribution	Elimination	Distribution	Elimination
1 compartment	Linear	1 compartment	Linear
2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
3 compartments		3 compartments	

In the library it is possible to select different number of compartments for parent and for metabolite. The central compartments have the same volume V – identifiability issue when only parent drug is administered.

3.6.5.1.2.1 Parametrization

Parent and metabolite have the same parametrization. As for the PK and PKPD libraries, there are two parametrizations available:

- **with exchange rates:** k_{12} , k_{21} for parent and k_{12m} , k_{21m} for metabolite for the second compartments, and k_{13} , k_{31} and k_{13m} , k_{31m} for the third compartments. Peripheral compartments are defined implicitly through the exchange rates, so volumes V_2 , V_3 , V_{2m} and V_{3m} are not estimated. The volume of central compartments is V (for both parent and metabolite)

- **with inter - compartment clearance:** Q_2, V_2, Q_3, V_3 for parent and $Q_{2m}, V_{2m}, Q_{3m}, V_{3m}$ for metabolite. The volume of central compartments is V_1 (for both parent and metabolite), to be compatible with the PK models in case of the sequential model development.

3.6.5.1.3 Transformation and elimination

Drug, after administration is eliminated from the system or transformed into metabolite, which subsequently is also eliminated. In addition, metabolite can be back-transformed into a parent – it is a common process for example for amines. Both, unidirectional and reversible, transformations can be selected from the “global” section of filters in the Monolix parent-metabolite library. Elimination, linear or non-linear (Michaelis-Menten), is specific for parent and for metabolite.

- Transformation:
 - K_{pm} – transformation rate from parent to metabolite
 - K_{mp} – transformation rate from metabolite to parent

Global				
Administration	First Pass Effect	Delay	Absorption	Transformation
Bolus	No first pass effect	No delay	Zero order	Uni-directional
Infusion	With dose apportionment	Lag time	First order	Bi-directional
Oral	Without dose apportionment	Transit compartments		
Oral + Bolus				

- Elimination: parent and metabolite can be eliminated with different process (linear or non-linear)
 - Cl, k, V_m, K_m – elimination parameters for parent
 - $Cl_m, k_m, V_{mm}, K_{mm}$ – elimination parameters for metabolite

Global			Parent	Metabolite		
Administration	Delay	Transformation	Distribution	Elimination	Distribution	Elimination
Bolus	No delay	Uni-directional	1 compartment	Linear	1 compartment	Linear
Infusion	Lag time	Bi-directional	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten	2 compartments	Michaelis-Menten
Oral			3 compartments		3 compartments	
Oral + Bolus						

Filter	Model Name
Cl, Cl_m, K_{pm}	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VClClmKpm</code>
$Cl, V_{mm}, K_{mm}, K_{pm}$	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VClVmmKmmKpm</code>
V_m, K_m, Cl_m, K_{pm}	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VmKmClmKpm</code>
$V_m, K_m, V_{mm}, K_{mm}, K_{pm}$	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VmKmVmmKmmKpm</code>
V_m, K_m, k_m, K_{pm}	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VmKmkmKpm</code>
$k, V_{mm}, K_{mm}, K_{pm}$	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VkVmmKmmKpm</code>
k, k_m, K_{pm}	<code>bolus_noFPE_1cptP1cptM_uni_VkkmKpm</code>

Examples:

3.6.5.2 Analytical solutions

Implementation in the Mlxtran

Example: a model with oral absorption (rate ka) of a dose D , one central compartment for parent ($cmt = 1$) and one for metabolite ($cmt = 2$), linear elimination (rates: k , km) and uni-directional transformation (rate Kpm), is the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC_p}{dt} &= \frac{ka \cdot D}{V} \cdot e^{-ka \cdot t} - k \cdot C_p - K_{pm} \cdot C_p \\ \frac{dC_m}{dt} &= K_{pm} \cdot C_p - k_m \cdot C_m \\ C_p(0) &= 0, C_m(0) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

where C_p and C_m are the concentrations in the central compartments of parent and metabolite respectively.

Models in the parent-metabolite Monolix library are build using mlxtran macros. For the above model:

```

;PK model definition for parent
compartment(cmt = 1, volume = V, concentration = Cp)
oral(cmt = 1, ka)
elimination(cmt = 1, k)

;PK model definition for metabolite
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cm)
elimination(cmt = 2, k = km)
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = Kpm)
    
```

Analytical solutions

Analytical solutions, which are more accurate than numerical solutions and are faster than ODE solvers, are implemented for parent – metabolite models satisfying the following conditions:

- administration (bolus, IV, oral 0 or 1st order) is to the central parent compartment only => *models from the library with first pass effect ("with dose apportionment" and "without dose apportionment") do not use analytical solutions*
- parameters are not time dependent (exception: dose coefficients such as Tlag, which are evaluated only once),
- elimination is linear and only from the central parent and/or metabolite compartments, => *models from the library with elimination = "Michaelis-Menten" do not use the analytical solutions*
- there are no transit compartments, => *models from the library with delay = "transit compartments" do not use the analytical solution*
- transfer between parent and metabolite is only between their central compartments,
- there are maximally two peripheral compartments for parent and maximally two for metabolite.

Comparison of the performance between analytical and numerical solutions

The following example compares the computational time (in seconds) of the parameter estimation task (SAEM) using analytical solutions (AS) and numerical solutions (ODE) for models with different number of compartments.

Dataset: simulated in Simulx N = 100 individuals, who received a single or multi oral doses. 5 or 20 measurements of both, parent and metabolite concentrations registered for each individual.

SAEM: (fixed number of iterations) 500 iterations for the exploratory phase, 200 iterations for the smoothing phase.

Number of cmt: Parent + metabolite	Single dose			Multidose		
	AS	ODE		AS	ODE	
1 + 1 (2dim)	27	100	3.7	27	130	4.8
2 + 1 (3dim)	48	150	3.1	44	180	4
2 + 2 (4dim)	71	210	3.0	66	230	3.5
3 + 2 (5dim)	96	260	2.7	91	290	3.2
3 + 3 (6dim)	140	310	2.2	130	340	2.6

Times are given in seconds, and values in bold give the speed up ratio when using an analytical solution.

3.6.6 Tumor growth inhibition (TGI) library

A wide range of ODEs models for tumour growth (TG) and tumour growth inhibition (TGI) is available in the literature and correspond to different hypotheses on the tumor or treatment dynamics. In the absence of detailed biological knowledge, selecting the most appropriate model is a challenge. In MonolixSuite2020, we provide a modular TG/TGI model library that combines sets of frequently used basic models and possible additional features. This library permits to easily test and combine different hypotheses for the tumor growth kinetics and effect of a treatment, allowing to fit a large variety of

tumor size data.

When available, analytical solutions are used.

3.6.6.1 Tumor growth models

3.6.6.1.1 Initial tumor size

The initial tumour size TS_0 can be either be:

- a parameter to estimate,
- a regressor to read from the dataset.

It has to be noted that the time corresponding to the initial tumour size is not necessarily 0. It is the case for models implemented with an analytical solution, but for models implemented with an ODE system it corresponds to the initial integration time. This time is not fixed for most models from this library, which means that it is by default the first dose or observation time in the data set, and can vary between individuals. If one wishes to fix the initial integration time for all individuals, one can uncomment the line “ $t_0=0$ ” in the model to fix the initial integration time at 0, and modify the line to choose another initial time, which must necessarily be before any dose or observation in the data set. Thus only models implemented with an analytical solution can capture observations at prior times than the time for TS_0 .

3.6.6.1.2 Kinetics of tumor growth

After a growing phase, tumors experience a saturation due to limits of nutrient supply. However, this saturation property is often never measured in patients in practice because the host dies in the majority of cases before this saturation phase begins. Also in preclinics, the experiments have to be canceled if a specific tumor size is reached due to ethical reasons. Thus, tumor growth models may be divided into two broad categories: those which are able to capture the saturation as the tumor grows (achieved by the introduction a carrying capacity or a spontaneous decay component) and those which do not.

No saturation

- Linear
- Quadratic
- Exponential
- Power law
- Simeoni / Exponential-linear
- Koch

Saturation

- Gompertz
- Gompertz-exponential
- Logistic
- Generalized logistic
- Simeoni-logistic
- Von Bertalanffy
- Generalized Von Bertalanffy

• **Models without saturation**

- **Linear**

The linear tumor growth assumes a constant zero-order growth rate.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = kgl$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	$T_S = kgl \times t + T_S0$	

- **Quadratic**

The quadratic tumor growth combines linear and quadratic growth rates. Because time is involved in this model, the initial time is fixed to 0 in corresponding library models.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{gl} + 2 \times k_{g2} \times t$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = k_{gl} \times t + k_{g2} \times t^2 + T_{S0}$	

- **Exponential**

The exponential growth assumes the growth rate of a tumor is proportional to tumor burden (first-order growth).

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = T_{S0} \times e^{k_{ge} \times t}$	

- **Power law**

If $0 < \gamma < 1$, the power law model (also named generalized exponential) provides a description in terms of a geometrical feature of the proliferative tissue: the growth rate is proportional to the number of proliferative cells as a fraction of the full tumor volume. The case $\gamma=1$ corresponds to proliferative cells uniformly distributed within the tumor and leads to exponential growth. The case $\gamma=2/3$ represents a proliferative rim limited to the surface of the tumor, where the tumor radius grows linearly in time.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S^\gamma$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = (k_{ge} \times (1 - \gamma) \times t + T_{S0}^{1-\gamma})^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$	

- **Exponential-linear**

Experimental data of tumor growth in untreated xenograft mice suggest that tumor growth dynamics follow two distinctively different phases of growth: an initial exponential growth, followed by a linear growth phase. Biologically, this is due to the fact that the growth of the tumor is almost unlimited at first, but that as the nutrients go scarce, its growth is then necessarily restricted.

The simple exponential-linear model captures this with a transition between an exponential (first-order) growth to a linear (zero-order) growth. The transition time is computed to ensure that the solution is continuously differentiable, but this is possible only if the model is not combined with any treatment effect or additional features. In that case, the transition time corresponds to $TS = k_{gl}/k_{ge}$.

In the library, the exponential-linear model is provided with its analytical solution and can not be combined to any treatment effect or additional features.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} \times T_S, t \leq \tau$ $\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{gl}, t \geq \tau$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$ $\tau = \frac{1}{k_{ge}} \ln\left(\frac{k_{gl}}{k_{ge} \times T_{S0}}\right)$	$T_S = T_{S0} \times e^{k_{ge} \times t}, t \leq \tau$ $T_S = k_{gl} \times (t - \tau) + T_{S0} * e^{k_{ge} \times \tau}, t \geq \tau$ $\tau = \frac{1}{k_{ge}} \ln\left(\frac{k_{gl}}{k_{ge} \times T_{S0}}\right)$	

- **Simeoni**

The Simeoni model approximates the exponential-linear model with a single differential equation. The power term is fixed to 20 to allow the system to pass from the first-order to the zero-order growth sharply enough, as in the original system. With this value, the growth rate is approximated by $k_{ge} \times T_S$ when T_S is smaller than k_{gl}/k_{ge} , and by k_{gl} when T_S is larger than k_{gl}/k_{ge} . The advantage of the Simeoni model over the exponential-linear model is that it is differentiable even when combined with any type of treatment effect.

When used in combination with the description of non-proliferating subpopulations of cells (transit compartments with cell distribution, or two populations model), with TS the size of the proliferating subpopulation, the growth function is slowed down by the factor $TS/TotalTS$ only when the tumor is in its linear growth phase, but not in the exponential growth phase.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dTS}{dt} = \frac{kge * TS}{(1 + (\frac{kge}{kgl} * TS)^\psi)^{\frac{1}{\psi}}}$ $TS(t_0) = TS0$	Simeoni et al. (2004).	

- **Koch**

Similarly to the exponential-linear and Simeoni models, the Koch tumor growth model is a nonlinear growth function that follows an initial exponential growth followed by a linear growth phase. Its particularity is a smooth transition between exponential and linear growth phase, rather than a rapid switch after a threshold reached for the time (exponential-linear) or tumor size (Simeoni).

When used in combination with the description of non-proliferating subpopulations of cells (transit compartments with cell distribution, or two populations model), with TS the size of the proliferating subpopulation, the growth function is slowed down by the factor $TS/TotalTS$.

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dTS}{dt} = \frac{2kge * kgl * TS}{kgl + 2kge * TS}$ $TS(t_0) = TS0$	$TS = TS0e^{2kge(t + \frac{1}{kgl}(TS0 - TS))}$	Koch et al. (2009)	

- **Models with saturation**

- **Logistic**

This model assumes an exponential growth rate which decelerates linearly with respect to the tumor size. This results in sigmoidal dynamics - with an initial exponential growth phase followed by a growth-saturated phase as the tumor reaches its carrying capacity (TSmax).

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dTS}{dt} = kge * TS(1 - \frac{TS}{TSmax})$ $TS(t_0) = TS0$	$TS = \frac{TSmax * TS0}{TS0 + (TSmax - TS0) * e^{-kge*t}}$	

- **Generalized logistic**

In this model, tumor growth depends on tumor size with a generalized logistic function. It reduces to the logistic model if $\gamma = 1$, or to the Gompertz model when γ is close to 0.

ODE system	Analytical solution	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = k_{ge} * T_S \left(1 - \left(\frac{T_S}{T_{Smax}}\right)^\gamma\right)$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \frac{T_{Smax} * T_{S0}}{\left(T_{S0}^\gamma + (T_{Smax}^\gamma - T_{S0}^\gamma) * e^{-k_{ge} * \gamma * t}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}}}$	

- **Simeoni-logistic**

In [Haddish-Berhane et al., 2013], a hybrid model derived from the Simeoni model is proposed, that combines exponential, linear and logistic growth.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \frac{k_{ge} * T_S * \left(1 - \frac{T_S}{T_{Smax}}\right)}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} * T_S\right)^\psi\right)^{\frac{1}{\psi}}}$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	Haddish-Berhane et al., 2013	

- **Gompertz**

The Gompertz model follows the observation of a deceleration of the growth rate over time, without any phase at which the growth rate remains constant. The volume converges asymptotically to

$$T_{Smax} = T_{S0} \cdot \exp(\alpha/\beta)$$

Several parametrizations can be used, and two are displayed on the table below. The first parametrization is the one implemented in the library, and the one for which the impacts of the parameters are the most separate and easiest to control. However, the carrying capacity T_{Smax} can be difficult to estimate and can lack biological meaning if no clear tumor size saturation is seen. With the second parametrization, alpha and beta have an impact on the carrying capacity and on the growth rate, while T_{S0} also has an impact on the carrying capacity.

ODE system	Analytical solution	

$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = T_S * \beta * \ln\left(\frac{T_Smax}{T_S}\right)$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	$T_S = T_Smax * e^{-\beta * t * \ln\left(\frac{T_S0}{T_Smax}\right)}$	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \alpha * e^{-\beta * t} * T_S$ <p>or, equivalently,</p> $\frac{dT_S}{dt} = (\alpha - \beta * \ln(T_S)) T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	$T_S = T_Smax * e^{-\beta * t * \ln\left(\frac{T_S0}{T_Smax}\right)}$	

• **Exponential-Gompertz**

An exponential-Gompertz model can also be considered, built upon the assumption that the tumor follows at first an exponential growth, and is then akin to a Gompertz model once the nutrients start to go scarce.

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = \min(k_{ge} * T_S, T_S * \beta * \ln\left(\frac{T_Smax}{T_S}\right))$ $T_S(t_0) = T_S0$	Wheldon (1988)	

• **Von Bertalanffy**

This model is based on balance equations of metabolic processes. The growth is limited with a loss term.

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = kg \cdot T_S^{2/3} - kd \cdot T_S$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \left[\frac{kg}{kd} + \left(T_{S0}^{1/3} - \frac{kg}{kd} \right) \cdot e^{-1/3 \cdot kd \cdot t} \right]^3$		

- **Generalized Von Bertalanffy**

This is the generalized version of the Von Bertalanffy model. The von Bertalanffy model corresponds to the case $\gamma = 2/3$, where the growth is proportional to the surface of the tumor.

The loss term induces for some parameter values a saturation of the tumor, with . When the loss term is neglected, the generalized von Bertalanffy model reduces to a power law

$$T_{S_{max}} = \left(\frac{kg e}{kd} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$$

When the Von Bertalanffy model (or generalized Von Bertalanffy model) is used in combination with a tumor inhibition model which makes use of the Norton Simon killing hypothesis, the treatment effect is only applied to the growth term of the model (and not to its decay term).

ODE system	Analytical solution	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = kg \cdot T_S^\gamma - kd \cdot T_S$ $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ $T_S(t_0) = T_{S0}$	$T_S = \left[\frac{kg}{kd} + \left(T_{S0}^{1-\gamma} - \frac{kg}{kd} \right) \cdot e^{-(1-\gamma) \cdot kd \cdot t} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}}$	Von Bertalanffy, 1957	

--

3.6.6.1.3 Additional features

Additional features can be included to consider more complex tumor growth models:

- Dynamic carrying capacity due to *angiogenesis*

The library includes, as an example, a module taken from Hahnfeldt et al,1999 that models the effect of angiogenesis as a dynamic carrying-capacity. When selecting the dynamic carrying-capacity module, T_{Smax} is defined as an ODE variable instead of a constant parameter, with the following ODE:

ODE	Reference	
$\frac{dT_{S_{max}}}{dt} = kp_v \cdot TS - \kappa \cdot T_{S_{max}} - kd_v \cdot TS \cdot TS^{2/3}$	Hahnfeldt et al,1999	

- *Immune dynamics* causing shrinkage or oscillations of tumor size

The library includes, as an example, a model of tumor-immune interactions with chemotherapy proposed by De Pillis et al. (2007), taking into account the control of the tumor growth by the immune system, and the weakening of the immune system as a side effect of chemotherapy. The model includes an additional ODE defining effector-immune cells:

ODE system	Reference	
$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth - k_i \cdot I \cdot T_S$ $\frac{dI}{dt} = kp_i - kd_i \cdot I + g \cdot \frac{T_S}{h + T_S} \cdot I - p \cdot I \cdot T_S$	De Pillis et al. (2007)	

More details on these additional features.

3.6.6.2 Treatment effect

3.6.6.2.1 Type of treatment

Flexible treatment definition is provided thanks to several possibilities:

- **No treatment**

This option corresponds to simple tumor growth models.

- **PK model**

Dosing information is encoded in the dataset, and the effect of the treatment is modeled via a simple PK model (one compartment, bolus administration, linear elimination) which can be easily adapted to a more complex model or to fix some parameters. The predicted concentration inhibits tumor size.

Note that in case of a high number of doses, it is preferable to approximate the exposure by a piecewise regressor or by a constant treatment, to reduce computation cost. Particularly when the dosing is daily and the disease lasts several years, modeling of the PK is not useful and very costly.

- **Exposure as regressor**

Values which describe the evolution of the treatment's exposure/concentration with respect to time are already stored within the data set and are used within the TGI model under the variable EXPOSURE.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The values describing the treatment's exposure with respect to time must be stored in a separate column of the data set labelled 'REGRESSOR'.

- **Treatment start at $t=0$**

The tumour growth inhibition component is applied with a constant effect after $t=0$.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The data must be formatted as to have the treatment being added at time $t=0$ for all individuals. Measurements before that can make use of negative values for time. Note that in that case, the initial integration time (corresponding to the initial tumour size TS0) is the first measurement time and can vary between individuals.

- **Treatment start time as regressor**

The time at which the treatment is added is a variable named T in the model, which may vary between individual, and whose value is read from a regressor column in the data set. When time $t < T$, a simple tumour growth model is being implemented. After, a tumour growth inhibition component to the model is added.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: The values for T must be stored within the data set in a separate column tagged as 'REGRESSOR'.

- **No treatment (0) vs treatment (1) regressor**

A simple tumour growth model is being implemented if the variable Trt = 0. If Trt = 1, a tumour growth inhibition component to the model is added. Trt is read from a regressor column in the dataset.

DATA FORMAT RESTRICTIONS: A 0 – if the measurement was taken before or after treatment – or 1 – if it was taken during treatment – must be matched and stored within a separate column under the header 'REGRESSOR' for each of the measurements of the data set.

3.6.6.2.2 Killing hypothesis

There are two different most commonly used hypothesis relevant to the method of killing of any given treatment within the literature:

- **Skipper-Schabel-Wilcox log-kill hypothesis**

$$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth - K \cdot T_S$$

This hypothesis states that exposure to a given amount of treatment kills a constant fraction of the total tumour cell population by increasing apoptosis. Consequently, the proportion of tumour cells removed every time a dose of treatment is administered remains constant regardless of the size of the tumor at the start of therapy. Tumor cell log-kill is typically induced by a standard cytotoxic or a targeted therapy. With this hypothesis, the Tumor Static Concentration (TSC) corresponds to $K \cdot T_S = growth$.

- **Norton-Simon killing hypothesis:**

$$\frac{dT_S}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K)$$

This hypothesis was based on the observation that faster-growing tumors respond better to chemotherapy than do slower-growing tumors, and states that the killing term is proportional to growth rate (tumor growth modulation). [R. Simon and R. Norton: The Norton-Simon hypothesis: designing more effective and less toxic chemotherapeutic regimens, Nature Clinical Practice Oncology 3(8) (2006), 406-407.] In the case of an anti-angiogenic drug for example, the cytostatic effect is assumed to be due to a direct inhibitory action on the unperturbed tumor growth rates. With this hypothesis, and if no decay or apoptosis term is considered, the Tumor Static Concentration (TSC) corresponds to $K=1$.

If the growth is exponential (λ), the log-kill and Norton-Simon hypotheses result in inhibition dynamics with equivalent shapes, but the inhibition from the Norton-Simon model depends on the growth rate while the log-kill inhibition does not: they are equivalent if K from the log-kill model is equal to K/k_{ge} in the Norton-Simon model.

On the figure below, the tumor size follows an exponential-linear growth, a constant treatment effect is applied either in the exponential phase (at $t=20$) or in the linear phase (at $t=60$). The treatment kinetics is linear. The parameters are adapted such that, thus the treatment effect is the same in the exponential phase. However, if the same treatment is applied later in the linear phase, a smaller proportion of tumor is removed with the Norton-Simon hypothesis, following a linear killing while the tumor remains in the linear phase. It enfolds that under the Norton-Simon hypothesis the optimal treatment should deliver the most effective dose level of drug over as short a time as possible (high dose density), since tumors given less time to grow between treatments are more likely to be eradicated.

$$growth = k_{ge} \cdot T_S$$

3.6.6.2.3 Dynamics of treatment effect

Five different exposure-dependent treatment kinetics which we found to be most common within the literature can be combined with both of these killing hypotheses. Below are plots showing the curves resulting from the addition of these TGI models to an exponential TG model, with a punctual drug exposure resulting from a single dose which is absorbed at time 0 and then eliminated. On the first figure, a linear range of different dose amounts has been applied in order to exhibit the linear and non-linear relationships between exposure and treatment effect.

When the treatment exposure is not given, the treatment effect is constant.

3.6.6.2.4 Delay of treatment effect

Chemotherapeutic effects often appear days or weeks following drug exposure. To account for a more progressive tumour regression, a delay in either the treatment effect (i.e. signal distribution model) or cell death (i.e. cell distribution model) may be added via transit compartments.

- **Signal distribution model**

Lobo and Balthasar (2002) applied to tumor growth the transit compartment model proposed by Sun & Jusko (1998) to characterize delayed drug effects that occur via a cascade or signal transduction. The operative rate function of tumor cells killing, K_3 , is related to K via a series of transit compartments (K_1 - K_3). τ refers to the mean transit time in each transit compartment. Although 4 transit compartments were used in Lobo and Balthasar (2002), the model implemented in our library has only 3 compartments for an easier comparison to the cell distribution model. It can be easily edited by the user to add more compartments if needed.

- **Cell distribution model**

The cell distribution model proposed in Simeoni et al., 2004 assumes that the anticancer treatment makes some cells non-proliferating. These cells pass through different stages (also called transit compartments), characterized by progressive degrees of damage, and, eventually, they die. Hence, the attacked tumor cells have a lifespan.

The number of stages of damage and the value of τ affect the shape of the distribution of the time-to-death of damaged tumor cells. The lifespan, or time-to-death, of the attacked tumor cells, is the mean transit time that it takes for the tumor cells, affected by the action of a drug, to go through the

cascade of damaging events to cell death. For n transit compartments, the average lifespan is computed by $Mtt = n \cdot \tau$. This library includes an implementation of the model with three transit compartments, as in Simeoni et al., 2004.

When the model considers two populations of cancer cells in the tumor (sensitive/resistant), the treatment induces the transfer or both types of cells into the first transit compartment, with different rates.

Below are plots showing the curves resulting from the addition of both of these delays to a model making use of exponential TG component and a log-kill constant TGI component depending on constant treatment starting at time 30.

3.6.6.2.5 Emergence of resistance

A common feature of tumours is the emergence of treatment-resistance. This phenomena can be modelled in a variety of ways. Decrease in treatment efficacy can be simply added in a phenomenological approach. More mechanistic models try to represent the cell population in its heterogeneity, splitting it into at least two subpopulations: the proliferating and the quiescent cells.

In this library, we included two common methods used within the literature to achieve this:

- **Claret exponential**

This simple phenomenological model accounts for the loss of drug-induced decay over time due to declining

efficacy of the drug, which can be due to the emergence of resistance. It uses a single resistance parameter, and it can be combined with any treatment effect.

Equation	Reference	
$K = K_0 \cdot e^{-\lambda \cdot t}$	Claret et al. (2009)	<p>Figure for an exponential growth function and constant treatment effect starting at time t=0.</p>

- **Resistant population**

There are many models in the literature that apply variations of the same approach based on two tumor cell populations with different sensitivities, for example Hahnfeldt et al., 2003, Desmée et al., 2017, Lobo & Balthasar, 2002, Jusko, (1973). We have integrated in the library simple versions inspired by this principle, combined with different treatment effects: these models assume that a fraction of the tumor is resistant to the treatment, thus being killed with a smaller rate than the sensitive part of the tumor. They use a parameter f as initial fraction of resistant tumour cells, and the number of parameters characterizing the treatment effect doubles to have population-specific effects.

Equation	
<p><i>Log-kill hypothesis:</i></p> $\frac{dT_{S_s}}{dt} = growth - TS_s \cdot K_{TS_s}$ $\frac{dT_{S_r}}{dt} = growth - TS_r \cdot K_{TS_r}$ <p><i>Norton-Simon hypothesis:</i></p> $\frac{dT_{S_s}}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K_{TS_s})$ $\frac{dT_{S_r}}{dt} = growth \cdot (1 - K_{TS_r})$ <p><i>Initial conditions:</i></p> $TS_s(t_0) = TS_0 \cdot (1 - f)$ $TS_r(t_0) = TS_0 \cdot f$	<p>Figure for an exponential growth function and constant treatment effect starting at time t=0.</p>

Below is a figure showing the curves resulting from the addition of these two resistance components to a model making use of exponential TG component and a log-kill linear TGI component, with a constant treatment effect starting at time 0.

3.6.6.2.6 Effect of treatment on angiogenesis or immune dynamics

If more complexity was added to the TG model by means of modelling immune dynamics or a dynamic carrying capacity, it can be decided that these should also be influenced by the addition of a treatment.

- **Combination therapy with active inhibition of angiogenesis**

Combination therapy is often used to maximise chances of tumour regression and minimise chances of treatment-resistant clones from emerging. As such, it may be wished to model the effect of an angiogenesis inhibitor, on top of the tumour inhibitor. This corresponds to an additional option named "Additional treatment effect" available in the library when both angiogenesis and a treatment effect are selected. In that case the ODE for TS_{max} becomes:

$$\frac{dTS_{max}}{dt} = kp_v \cdot TS - \kappa \cdot TS_{max} - kd_v \cdot TS \cdot TS^{2/3} - e \cdot TS_{max}$$

The treatment on angiogenesis is added as a second constant treatment (on top of the one selected earlier on). By choosing this additional option, it is assumed that no PK data is available for this second treatment and consequently, first-order kinetics are used to model the effect. Furthermore, the effect of the second treatment is assumed to follow a log-cell kill killing hypothesis.

- **Combination therapy with decay of immune cells**

If the treatment added does not only target tumour cells but a more general cell population (such as chemotherapy), it may be relevant to include a killing term on the immune cell dynamics as well. This feature is available in the library if modelling of immune dynamics was selected during selection of tumour growth model. It consists in adding an extra decay constant to take into consideration the effect chemotherapy will have on immune cells. The equations then become:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = kp_i - kd_i \cdot I + g \cdot \frac{TS}{h+TS} \cdot I - p \cdot I \cdot TS - K_i \cdot I$$

where the killing term $-K_i \cdot I$ actually follows the same pattern as the killing term on TS selected in the library.

3.6.6.3 Shortcut models

Lastly, we found that some typical models within the literature. In order to ease access to these models, we created a shortcut tab which automatically leads one to the appropriate selections when applicable, or loads the dedicated model otherwise. In each case, the initial tumor size TS_0 can be set as a parameter or as a regressor.

- **Claret exponential model**

This model from Claret et al., 2009 corresponds to the following choices in the library:

Shortcuts To Commonly Used Models						
Claret exponential	Simeoni	Stein	Wang	Bonazé	Ribba	TwoPopulation
Initial Tumor Size	Kinetics	Model	Additional Feature	Treatment		
As parameter	No saturation	Linear	None	None		
As regressor	Saturation	Quadratic	Immune Dynamics	PK model		
		Exponential		Exposure as regressor		
		Generalized Exponential		Treatment start at t=0		
		Exponential-linear		Treatment start time as regressor		
		Simeoni		No treatment (0) vs treatment (1) regressor		
		Koch				
Killing Hypothesis	Dynamics	Resistance	Delay			
Log-kill	Fair-order	Claret exponential	Signal distribution			
Norton-Simon	Michaelis-Menten	Resistant cells	Cell distribution			
	Michaelis-Menten Hill	None	None			
	Exponential Kill					

The treatment “PK model” is selected by default, but the Claret model is actually compatible with any type of treatment effect. The version with a constant treatment effect starting at $t=0$ (choice “Treatment start at $t=0$ ”), has an analytical solution implemented in the mode, and is therefore much faster to compute than other models implemented as ODEs

$$TS = TS_0 \cdot \exp\left(k_{ge} \cdot t - \frac{k_{kill}}{\lambda} \cdot (1 - \exp(-\lambda \cdot t))\right)$$

- **Simeoni model**

This model from Simeoni et al., 2004 corresponds to the following choices in the library:

Shortcuts To Commonly Used Models						
Claret exponential	Simeoni	Stein	Wang	Bonazé	Ribba	TwoPopulation
Initial Tumor Size	Kinetics	Model	Additional Feature	Treatment		
As parameter	No saturation	Linear	None	None		
As regressor	Saturation	Quadratic	Immune Dynamics	PK model		
		Exponential		Exposure as regressor		
		Generalized Exponential		Treatment start at t=0		
		Exponential-linear		Treatment start time as regressor		
		Simeoni		No treatment (0) vs treatment (1) regressor		
		Koch				
Killing Hypothesis	Dynamics	Resistance	Delay			
Log-kill	Fair-order	Claret exponential	Signal distribution			
Norton-Simon	Michaelis-Menten	Resistant cells	Cell distribution			
	Michaelis-Menten Hill	None	None			
	Exponential Kill					

Here again, the treatment “PK model” is selected by default, but the Simeoni model is actually compatible with any type of treatment effect.

The equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TS(t_0) &= TS_0 \\
 TS_1(t_0) &= 0 \\
 TS_2(t_0) &= 0 \\
 TS_3(t_0) &= 0 \\
 \frac{dTS}{dt} &= \frac{k_{ge} \cdot TS}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} \cdot TS\right)^\psi\right)^\psi} - K \cdot TS \\
 \frac{dTS_1}{dt} &= \frac{k_{ge} \cdot TS}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{k_{ge}}{k_{gl}} \cdot TS\right)^\psi\right)^\psi} - \frac{TS_1}{\tau} \\
 \frac{dTS_2}{dt} &= \frac{TS_1 - TS_2}{\tau} \\
 \frac{dTS_3}{dt} &= \frac{TS_2 - TS_3}{\tau} \\
 TS_{total} &= TS + TS_1 + TS_2 + TS_3
 \end{aligned}$$

- **Two-population model**

Also called evolutionary model, this simple model corresponds to an exponential growth, and a treatment effect based on log-cell kill hypothesis with first-order kinetics and no delay. The treatment can be set by the user as constant or exposure-dependent.

Shortcuts To Commonly Used Models	
Claret exponential	Simeoni
Initial Tumor Size	Treatment
As parameter	PK model
As regressor	Exposure as regressor
	Treatment start at t0
	Treatment start time as regressor

The equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 TS_0 &= TS_0 \cdot (1 - f) \\
 TSr_0 &= TS_0 \cdot f \\
 \frac{dTS}{dt} &= -k_{kill} \cdot EXPOSURE \cdot TS \\
 \frac{dTS_r}{dt} &= k_{ge} \cdot TSr \\
 TS_{total} &= TS + TSr
 \end{aligned}$$

TS represents the sensitive part of the tumor, and TSr the resistant part. TotalTS is the total tumor size. If the treatment is constant and starts at time 0, the model is encoded with its analytical solution:

$$TS = TS_0 \cdot (f \cdot \exp(k_{ge} \cdot t) + (1 - f) \cdot \exp(-k_{kill} \cdot t))$$

with kkill=0 before t=0.

- **Stein regression-growth model**

This model from Stein et al., 2011 is a simple phenomenological equation based on the assumption that the change of tumor size during therapy results from two independent component processes: an exponential decrease/regression and an exponential regrowth of the tumor:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot (\exp(-kkill \cdot t) + \exp(kge \cdot t) - 1)$$

with $kkill=0$ before $t=0$.

This model is only available with the treatment option "Treatment start at $t=0$ ".

In responding tumors, regression dominates from start of therapy until nadir, growth dominating after nadir. Theoretical curves depicting the separate components of the model and how these combine together to give the time dependence of the tumor size appear in the figure below.

• Wang model

This model from Wang et al., 2009 combines an exponential-decay (shrinkage) and a linear-growth (progression). In the original model, the linear growth component is considered as an approximation of tumor growth under a specific treatment, with a treatment-dependent slope. In the present library, the model is implemented with the same linear growth rate before and during treatment. It goes as follows:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot \exp(-kkill \cdot t) + kgl \cdot t$$

This model can only be used with the option "Treatment starting at time 0". The following figure shows a typical prediction:

• Bonate model

This model is based on Bonate & Suttle, 2013. It is a modification of the Wang model in which a quadratic growth term has been added to account for curvature of tumor growth following nadir.

The equation is:

$$TS = TS0 \cdot \exp(-kkill \cdot t) + kgl \cdot t + kg2 \cdot t^2$$

• **Ribba model**

This model has been proposed by Ribba et al., 2012. It is able to capture the growth kinetics of low-grade glioma after termination of chemotherapy, characterized by a frequent decrease in volume despite chemotherapy no longer being administered, by considering delayed action of chemotherapy on quiescent tumor cells. The tumor is represented as proliferative and quiescent tumor tissues that respond differently to treatment. The treatment concentration affects both proliferative and quiescent tissue. The tissue composed of cells in proliferation is directly eliminated because of lethal DNA damages induced by the treatment. Nonproliferative tissue is also subject to DNA damages due to the treatment. When re-entering the cell cycle, the DNA-damaged quiescent cells can either repair their DNA damages and return to a proliferative state or die because of unrepaired damages.

It is represented on this figure adapted from [Ribba et al., 2012]:

The following curves show the prediction of each variable of the model before and after a treatment dose at time 0, on the left, and the impact of the parameters on the prediction for TotalTS on the right. The treatment concentration causes an initial sharp drop in P and thus in TotalTS, as well as the transfer of cells from Q to Qp. While the treatment concentration decreases then rapidly to 0, TotalTS continues decreasing slowly, driven by the elimination of Qp. TotalTS increases again only once enough cells have been transferred from Qp to P. The growth function chosen in this model includes a saturation with a carrying capacity TSmax.

3.6.6.3.1 References

3.6.6.3.1.1 Reviews

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3.6.7 Time-to-event model library

This page presents the **TTE model library** included in Monolix. It includes an introduction on time-to-event data, the different ways to model this kind of data, and typical parametric models.

3.6.7.1 What is time-to-event data

In case of time-to-event data the recorded observations are the times at which events occur. We can for instance record the time (duration) from diagnosis of a disease until death, or the time between administration of a drug and the next epileptic seizures. In the first case, the event is one-off, while in the second it can be repeated.

In addition, the event can be:

- **exactly observed:** we know the event has happen exactly at time t_i ($T_i = t_i$)
- **interval censored:** we know the event has happen during a time interval, but not exactly when ($a_i \leq T_i \leq b_i$)
- **right censored:** the observation period ends before the event can be observed ($T_i > t_{end}$)

3.6.7.2 Formatting of time-to-event data in the MonolixSuite

In the data set, exactly observed events, interval censored events and right censoring are recorded for each individual. Contrary to other softwares for survival analysis, the MonolixSuite requires to specify the time at which the observation period starts. This allow to define the data set using absolute times, in addition to durations (if the start time is zero, the records represent durations between the start time and the event).

For instance for single events, exactly observed (with or without right censoring), **one must indicate the start time of the observation period (Y=0), and the time of event (Y=1) or the time of the end of the observation period if no event has occurred (Y=0)**. In the following example:

```
ID TIME Y
1 0 0
1 34 1
2 0 0
2 80 0
```

the observation period last from starting time $t=0$ to the final time $t=80$. For individual 1, the event is observed at $t=34$, and for individual 2, no event is observed during the period. Thus it is indicated that at the final time ($t=80$), no event had occurred. Using absolute times instead of durations, we could equivalently write:

```
ID TIME Y
1 20 0
1 54 1
2 33 0
2 113 0
```

The durations between start time and event (or end of the observation period) are the same as before, but this time we record the day at which the patients enter the study and the days at which they have events or leave the study. Different patients may enter the study at different times.

Examples for repeated events, and interval censored events are available [here](#).

3.6.7.3 Important concepts: hazard and survival

Two functions have a key role in time-to-event analysis: the survival function and the hazard function. **The survival function $S(t)$ is the probability that the event happens after time t .** A common way to estimate it non-parametrically is to calculate the Kaplan-Meier estimate. **The hazard function $h(t)$ is the instantaneous rate of an event, given that it has not already occurred.** Both are linked by the following equation:

$$S(t) = e^{-\int_0^t h(x)dx}$$

3.6.7.4 Different types of approaches

Depending on the goal of the time-to-event analysis, different modeling approaches can be used: non-parametric, semi-parametric (Cox models) and parametric.

- **Non-parametric models** do not require assumptions on the shape of the hazard or survival. Using the Kaplan-Meier estimate, statistical tests can be performed to check if the survival differs between sub-populations. The main limitations of this approach are that (i) only categorical covariates can be tested and (ii) the way the survival is affected by the covariate cannot be assessed.
- **Semi-parametric models (Cox models)** assume that the hazard can be written as a baseline hazard (that depends only on time), multiplied by a term that depends only on the covariates (and not time). Under this hypothesis of proportional covariate effect, one can analyze the effect of covariates (categorical and continuous) in a parametric way, leaving the baseline hazard undefined.
- **Parametric models** require to fully specify the hazard function. If a good model can be found, statistical tests are more powerful than for semi-parametric models. In addition, there is no restrictions on how the covariates affects the hazard. Parametric models can also be easily used for predictions.

The table below synthesizes the possibilities for the 3 approaches.

	Non-parametric approach	Semi-parametric approach (Cox models)	Parametric approach
Requires assumptions on baseline hazard	no	no	Yes, must be fully specified
Requires assumptions on covariates effect	no	Yes, effect of covariates must be proportional	Yes, no restrictions (accelerated failure time models possible)
Takes into account censoring	Partly, only right censoring	Partly, only right censoring	Yes, all types of censoring are easily taken into account
Uses all the available data	No, only the ranking of events	No, only the ranking of events	Yes
Statistical test for difference between subpopulations	Yes	Yes	Yes
Quantification of the effect of covariates	No	Yes	Yes
Power of statistical tests	Low to intermediate	Intermediate	Strong (if model is correct)
Can handle categorical covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes
Can handle continuous covariates	Only if transformed into categories	Yes	Yes
Can handle frailty models (to capture inhomogeneities between individuals, that are not recorded in covariates)	No	Feasible	Yes
Extrapolations/predictions possible	No	No	Yes

3.6.7.5 Focus on parametric modeling with the MonolixSuite

In the MonolixSuite, the only possible approach is the parametric approach. The model is defined via the hazard function, which in a population approach typically depends on individual parameters: $h(t, \psi_i)$. With the hazard function, the survival function can easily be computed, as well as the conditional distribution $p_{y_i|\psi_i}$ for various censoring situations (which is required for parameter estimation via SAEM, log-likelihood calculation, etc).

The typical syntax to define the output is the following:

DEFINITION:
 Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}

The output `Event` will be matched to the time-to-event data of the data set. The `hazard` function `h` is usually defined via an expression including the input individual parameters. For one-off events, the maximal number of events per individual is 1. It is important to indicate it in the `maxEventNumber` argument to speed up calculations. To use the model for simulations with Simulx, `rightCensoringTime` must be given as additional argument. Check here for details.

Note that the hazard can be a function of other variables such as drug concentration or tumor burden for instance (joint PK-TTE or PD-TTE models). An example of the syntax is given here.

3.6.7.6 Library of parametric models for time-to-event data

To describe the various shapes that the survival Kaplan-Meier estimate can take, several hazard functions have been proposed. Below we display the *survival curves*, for the most typical hazard functions:

A few comments:

- We have reparametrized T_e' as a function of T_e to better separate the effects of the scale parameter (characteristic time) and the shape parameter (shape of the curve).
- All parameters are positive. If we assume inter-individual variability, a log-normal distribution is usually appropriate.

The table below summarizes the number of parameters and typical parameter values:

Model	Number of parameters	Typical parameter values	Comments
Exponential	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ 	
Uniform	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S=0$ 	
Weibull	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ <u>shape</u> $p = 1 - 4$ 	If $p = 1$, simplifies to exponential
Log-logistic	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.5$ <u>shape</u> $s = 1 - 4$ 	
Gompertz	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.5$ <u>shape</u> $k = 0.01 - 1$ 	
Gamma	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ <u>shape</u> $\alpha = 1 - 10$ 	
Generalized gamma	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <u>scale</u> T_e = time at which $S \approx 0.4$ <u>shape</u> $\alpha = 1 - 10$ <u>shape</u> $p = 1 - 4$ 	If $p = 1$, simplifies to gamma If $p = \alpha$, simplifies to Weibull

For each model, we can in addition consider a delay `del` as additional parameter. The delay will simply shift the survival curve to the right (later times). For $t < del$, the survival is $S(t < del) = 1$.

3.6.7.6.1 Lognormal TTE model

The lognormal TTE model is quite standard but not yet included in the library. The mlxtran model for it is shown below:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={mu, sigma}

EQUATION:
if t<0.001
h = 0
else
a = (log(t)-mu)/sigma
h = (sigma*t*sqrt(3.14*2))-1 * exp(-1/2 * a2) / (1 - normcdf(a))
end

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}

OUTPUT:
output = {Event}
```

All models are available as Mlxtran model file in the TTE library. Each model can be with/without delay and for single/repeated events. For performance reasons, it is important to choose the file ending with '_singleEvent.txt' if you want to model one-off events (death, drop-out, etc).

3.6.8 Count data model library

3.6.8.1 What is count data

Count data come from counting something, e.g., the number of trials required for completing a given task. The task can for instance be repeated several times (longitudinal count data) and the individuals performance followed.

Count data can also represent the number of events happening in regularly spaced intervals, e.g the number of seizures every week. If the time intervals are not regular, the data may be considered as repeated time-to-event interval censored, see this example. Alternatively the interval length can be given as regressor or covariate to be used to define the probability distribution in the model, see this example.

3.6.8.2 Formatting of count data in the MonolixSuite

Count data can take only non-negative integer values. The counts for each individual are recorded in the OBSERVATION column-type. If the data is longitudinal (over time), the times at which the counts have been recorded are indicated in the TIME column-type. If the data is not longitudinal, the TIME column is still necessary and a time of 0 can be used for instance.

```
ID TIME Y
1 0 8
1 4 9
1 8 11
2 0 6
2 4 6
2 8 7
```

In the example above, the values in the time column can either indicate the time at which the counts have been counted, or the start or end time of the period over which the number of events are recorded.

In the Monolix GUI, the user must indicate that the data is of type Count/Categorical:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	Y
2	1	1	0
3	1	2	0
4	1	3	0
5	1	4	0
6	1	5	1
7	1	6	1

3.6.8.3 Important concept: the probability mass function

Count data are described by their probability mass function, which gives the probability that the discrete random variable is exactly equal to some value: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k)$ with y_{ij} the observed count number for individual i at time j and $k > 0$.

For instance the probability mass function for a Poisson distribution is:

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$$

If $\lambda=3$, then the probability of having a count of 0 is 4.9%, a count of 1 is 14.9%, a count of 2 is 22.4%, a count of 3 is 22.4%, etc.

3.6.8.4 Encoding of count models with the MonolixSuite

In Monolix, a model for count data is defined via the probability mass function, which in a population approach typically depends on individual parameters: $\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = k) = f(t_j, \psi_i)$.

The typical syntax to define the random variable representing the count number is the following:

DEFINITION:

```
CountNumber = {type=count, P(CountNumber=k) = ...}
```

`CountNumber` is the name of the random variable and can be replaced by another name. On the opposite, `k` is a mandatory name for the values. The random variable `CountNumber` is then listed in the outputs, to be matched to the observed data.

The probability mass functions often involve ratios of factorials. While the ratio is often a reasonable value, the numerator and denominator can be huge values that are difficult to handle numerically. **It is therefore better to work with the log of the factorials.** The function for log factorial in Mlxtran language is `factln()` (for integers). To extend the factorials to the continuous domain, the gamma function can be useful: $\Gamma(n) = (n - 1)!$. The log of the gamma function corresponds to the `gammaLn()` function in Mlxtran. It is possible to define directly the log of the probability mass function with:

```
DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count, log(P(CountNumber=k)) = ...}
```

For instance to define a binomial distribution, we can write:

```
DEFINITION:
Y = {type=count, log(P(Y=k)) = gammaLn(n+1) - factln(k) - gammaLn(n-k+1) + k*log(p) +
(n-k)*log(1-p)}
```

where `gammaLn()` is used for terms that can be non-integers and `factln()` for terms that are integers.

It is possible to use “if” statements related to `k` in the definition of the probability mass function by using the syntax below. This can be useful to define zero-inflated models for instance. The “if” statements relating to time, regressors, or parameters values can be put in a `EQUATION:` section before the `DEFINITION:` block.

```
DEFINITION:
CountNumber = {type=count,
if k==0
Pk = ...
else
Pk = ...
end
P(CountNumber=k) = Pk}
```

The parameters involved in the definition of the probability mass function (for instance λ for a Poisson distribution) can be identical for all individuals, or vary from individual to individual. This is defined in

the section “Individual model” of the graphical interface as usual. These parameters can also evolve over time or be a function of other variables such as drug concentration or tumor burden for instance. See the demo “PKcount_project.mlxtran” for instance in the Monolix demo folder, section 4.2.

3.6.8.5 Library of models for count data

To describe the various shapes that a count distribution can take, we have developed a library of models. The library includes the most typical distributions, their zero-inflated counterpart, and several options for the evolution of time of the main parameter:

<p><u>Distribution:</u> Poisson Binomial Negative binomial Beta binomial Generalized Poisson Geometric Hypergeometric Logarithmic Bernoulli Uniform</p>	<p><u>Zero-inflation:</u> not zero-inflated zero-inflated</p>	<p><u>Time evolution:</u> Constant Linear Exponential Emax Hill (sigmoidal)</p>
--	--	---

The probability mass functions and a description of the parameters is given below:

Model name	Probability mass function	Support	Parameters
Bernoulli	$P(Y = k) = p^k(1 - p)^k$	{0, 1}	p = probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Poisson	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	λ = average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0
Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{n!}{k!(n - k)!} p^k(1 - p)^{n-k}$	{0, 1, ..., n}	n = maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 p = probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Negative Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{(k + r - 1)!}{k!(r - 1)!} p^k(1 - p)^r$ or $P(Y = k) = \frac{\Gamma(k + \frac{1}{o})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{o})} \left(\frac{\lambda}{\frac{1}{o} + \lambda}\right)^k \left(\frac{1}{1 + o\lambda}\right)^{\frac{1}{o}}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	r = number of failures, > 0 p = probability of success, $\in [0,1]$ or λ = average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0 o = overdispersion, > 0
Generalized Poisson	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\lambda(1 - \delta)(\lambda(1 - \delta) + k\delta)^{k-1}}{k!} e^{-\lambda(1 - \delta) + k\delta}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	λ = average number of events (i.e event rate), > 0 δ = overdispersion, > 0
Beta Binomial	$P(Y = k) = \frac{\Gamma(n + 1)}{\Gamma(k + 1)\Gamma(n - k + 1)} \frac{\Gamma(k + \alpha)\Gamma(n - k + \beta)}{\Gamma(n + \alpha + \beta)} \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)}$	{0, 1, ..., n}	n = maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 α = first shape parameter, > 0 β = second shape parameter, > 0 or n = maximum count number (i.e number of trials), > 0 $p = \frac{\alpha - 1}{\alpha + \beta - 2}$ = most probable value for the probability, $\in [0,1]$ $\kappa = \alpha + \beta$ = concentration of the beta distribution, > 0
Geometric	$P(Y = k) = p(1 - p)^{k-1}$	{0, 1, ..., inf}	p = probability of success, $\in [0,1]$
Hypergeometric	$P(Y = k) = \frac{K!}{k!(K - k)!} \frac{(N - K)!}{(n - k)!(N - K - n + k)!} \frac{n!(N - n)!}{N!}$	{max(0, n+K-N), ..., min(n,K)}	N = size of the population > 0 $np = n/N$, number of draws divided by the population size, $\in [0,1]$ $p = K/N$, number of elements considered as success divided by the population size, $\in [0,1]$
Logarithmic	$P(Y = k) = \frac{-1}{\ln(1 - p)} \frac{p^k}{k}$	{1, 2, ..., inf}	p = probability, $\in [0,1]$
Uniform	$P(Y = k) = \frac{1}{N}$	{0, 1, ..., n-1}	n = maximum count number, > 0

3.7 Typical models

The following pages show how to write typical models for continuous or non-continuous outcomes.

3.7.1 Typical PK models

Different routes of administrations

- [Single route of administration](#)
- [Multiple administration routes](#)
- [Multiple doses and steady state](#)

Various absorption models

- Mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, or parallel first-order
- Saturation of the absorption rate
- Sigmoid absorption, transit compartments and Weibull absorption

Urine data

- [Models for urine data](#)

3.7.2 Models for non-continuous data

- [Time-to-event data models](#)
- [Count data models](#)
 - [Count models with offset](#)
- [Categorical data models](#)
- [Joint models for non-continuous outcomes](#)

3.7.3 Typical extensions of structural models

- [Joint model for continuous outcomes](#)
- [Mixture of structural models](#)
- [Using regressors](#)
- **Time varying parameters**
 - Time-varying clearance
 - Auto-induction model
 - Enterohepatic circulation model
- [Using a scale factor](#)
- [Delayed differential equations](#)
- **Additional model outputs**
 - [Outputs and tables](#)

- Computing additional model outputs such as Cmax or AUC
- [Calculating the half-life](#)

3.7.4 Advanced models

- [Lifespan models](#)
- [K-PD models](#)
- [Friberg model for myelosuppression](#)
- [ADC model](#)
- [Beta regression models](#)

3.7.5 Typical PK models

The following pages describe writing of typical PK models:

Different routes of administrations

- [Single route of administration](#)
- [Multiple administration routes](#)
- [Multiple doses and steady state](#)

Various absorption models

- Mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, or parallel first-order
- Saturation of the absorption rate
- Sigmoid absorption, transit compartments and Weibull absorption

Urine data

- [Models for urine data](#)

3.7.5.1 Single route of administration

Demos: [bolusLinear_project](#), [bolusMM_project](#), [bolusMixed_project](#), [infusion_project](#), [oral1_project](#), [oral0_project](#), [sequentialOral0Oral1_project](#), [simultaneousOral0Oral1_project](#), [oralAlpha_project](#), [oralTransitComp_project](#)

3.7.5.1.1 Introduction

Once a drug is administered, we usually describe subsequent processes within the organism by the pharmacokinetics (PK) process known as *ADME*: absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion. A PK model is a dynamical system mathematically represented by a system of *ordinary differential equations* (ODEs) which describes transfers between compartments and elimination from the central

compartment.

Mlxtran is remarkably efficient for implementing simple and complex PK models:

- The function `pkmodel` can be used for standard PK models. The model is defined according to the provided set of named arguments. The `pkmodel` function enables different parametrizations, different models of absorption, distribution and elimination, defined here and summarized in the following..
- Alternatively, PK macros can be used to define the different components of a compartmental model. Combining such PK components provide a high degree of flexibility for more complex PK models. They can also be combined with an ODE system.
- A system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) can also be implemented very easily.

Note that the dataset is completely independent from the model: the same dataset (with one dose line per actual dose) can be used to model a simple first-order absorption, transit compartments or a double absorption mechanism with two dose fractions going via different routes. In particular, we make a clear distinction between administration (related to the data) and absorption (related to the model).

We will first explain how the `pkmodel` macro works and then show examples of its usage.

3.7.5.1.1.1 The `pkmodel` function

The PK model is defined by the names of the input parameters of the `pkmodel` function. These names are **reserved keywords**.

Absorption

- `p` : Fraction of dose which is absorbed
- `ka` : absorption constant rate (first order absorption)
- or, `Tk0` : absorption duration (zero order absorption)
- `Tlag` : lag time before absorption
- or, `Mtt`, `Ktr` : mean transit time & transit rate constant

Distribution

- `V` : Volume of distribution of the central compartment
- `k12`, `k21` : Transfer rate constants between compartments 1 (central) & 2 (peripheral)
- or `V2`, `Q2` : Volume of compartment 2 (peripheral) & inter compartment clearance, between compartments 1 and 2,
- `k13`, `k31` : Transfer rate constants between compartments 1 (central) & 3 (peripheral)
- or `V3`, `Q3` : Volume of compartment 3 (peripheral) & inter compartment clearance, between compartments 1 and 3.

Elimination

- `k` : Elimination rate constant
- or `Cl` : Clearance

- `Vm, Km` : Michaelis Menten elimination parameters

Effect compartment

- `ke0` : Effect compartment transfer rate constant

In the background, the `pkmodel` macro is replaced by the analytical solution (when it exists) or by the correspondin ODE system (when using `Mtt,Ktr` and/or `Vm,Km`).

3.7.5.1.2 Intravenous bolus injection

3.7.5.1.2.1 Linear elimination

- **`bolusLinear_project`**

A single iv bolus is administered at time 0 to each patient. The data file `bolus1_data.txt` contains 4 columns: `id`, `time`, `amt` (the amount of drug in mg) and `y` (the measured concentration). After loading the dataset, the columns are automatically tagged by Monolix:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
id	time	amt	y	
1	0	40	.	
1	0.5	.	2.9761	
1	3	.	2.4224	
1	5	.	1.8996	
1	7	.	1.918	
1	9	.	1.0335	
1	12	.	0.6104	
1	15	.	0.4649	
1	18	.	0.2987	
1	24	.	0.0948	

In this example, a row contains either a dose record (in which case `y = "."`) or a observation record (in which case `amt = "."`). Dose lines and Observation lines are detected automatically based on the dots `"."`. We could equivalently use the data file `bolus2_data.txt` which contains 2 additional columns: `EVID` (in the green frame) and `IGNORED OBSERVATION` (in the blue frame) to mark dose and observation lines:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS	EVENT ID	IGNORED OBSERVATION
id	time	amt	y	evid	mdv
1	0	40	0	1	1
1	0.5	0	2.9761	0	0
1	3	0	2.4224	0	0
1	5	0	1.8996	0	0
1	7	0	1.918	0	0
1	9	0	1.0335	0	0
1	12	0	0.6104	0	0
1	15	0	0.4649	0	0
1	18	0	0.2987	0	0
1	24	0	0.0948	0	0

Here, the EVENT ID column allows the identification of an event: EVID=1 means that this record describes a dose while EVID=0 means that this record contains an observed value.

On the other hand, the IGNORED OBSERVATION column enables to tag lines for which the information in the OBSERVATION column-type is missing. MDV=1 means that the observed value of this record should be ignored while MDV=0 means that this record contains an observed value. The two data files bolus1_data.txt and bolus2_data.txt contain exactly the same information and provide exactly the same results.

To model this dataset, we want to use a one compartment model with linear elimination. The ODE system of this model is:

$$\frac{dA_c}{dt} = -k \times A_c(t)$$

$$A_c(0) = 0$$

Here, $A_c(t)$ and $C_c(t) = A_c(t)/V$ are, respectively, the amount and the concentration of drug in the central compartment at time t . When a dose D arrives in the central compartment at time τ an iv bolus administration assumes that the amount of drug in the central

$$A_c(\tau^+) = A_c(\tau^-) + D$$

where $A_c(\tau^-)$ (resp. $A_c(\tau^+)$) is the amount of drug in the central compartment just before (resp. after) τ . Parameters of this model are V and k . We therefore use the model `bolus_1cpt_Vk` from the Monolix PK library:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(V, k)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

We could equivalently use the model `bolusLinearMacro.txt` (click on the button Model and select the new PK model in the library `6.PK_models/model`)

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac)
iv(cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

These two implementations generate exactly the same C++ code and then provide exactly the same results. Here, the ODE system is linear and Monolix uses its analytical solution. Of course, it is also possible (but not recommended with this model) to use the ODE based PK model `bolusLinearODE.txt` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}

PK:
depot(target = Ac)

EQUATION:
ddt_Ac = - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Results obtained with this model are slightly different from the ones obtained with the previous implementations since a numeric scheme is used here for solving the ODE. Moreover, the computation time is longer (between 3 and 4 time longer in that case) when using the ODE compared to the analytical solution. Individual fits obtained with this model look nice:

but the VPC show some misspecification in the elimination process:

3.7.5.1.2.2 Michaelis Menten elimination

- **bolusMM_project**

A non linear elimination is used with this project:

$$\frac{dA_c}{dt} = -\frac{V_m A_c(t)}{V K_m + A_c(t)}$$

This model is available in the Monolix PK library as `bolus_1cpt_VVmKm` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Vm, Km}
```

```
PK:
Cc = pkmodel(V, Vm, Km)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Instead of this model, we could equivalently use PK macros with `bolusNonLinearMacro.txt` from the library `6.PK_models/model` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Vm, Km}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac, volume=V)
iv(cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, Vm, Km)
Cc = Ac/V
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

or an ODE with `bolusNonLinearODE` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Vm, Km}
```

```
PK:
depot(target = Ac)
```

```
EQUATION:
ddt_Ac = -Vm*Ac/(V*Km+Ac)
Cc=Ac/V
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Results obtained with these three implementations are identical since no analytical solution is available for this non linear ODE. We can then check that this PK model seems to describe much better the elimination process of the data:

3.7.5.1.2.3 Mixed elimination

- **bolusMixed_project**

The `Monolix` PK library contains “standard” PK models. More complex models should be implemented by the user in a model file. For instance, we assume in this project that the elimination process is a combination of linear and nonlinear elimination processes:

$$\frac{dA_c}{dt} = -\frac{V_m A_c(t)}{VK_m + A_c(t)} - kA_c(t)$$

This model is not available in the Monolix PK library. It is implemented in `bolusMixed.txt` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k, Vm, Km}
```

```
PK:
```

```
depot(target = Ac)
```

EQUATION:

$$ddt_Ac = -Vm*Ac/(V*Km+Ac) - k*Ac$$

$$Cc=Ac/V$$

OUTPUT:

```
output = Cc
```

This model, with a combined error model, seems to describe very well the data:

3.7.5.1.3 Intravenous infusion

- **infusion_project**

Intravenous infusion assumes that the drug is administrated intravenously with a constant rate (infusion rate), during a given time (infusion time). Since the amount is the product of infusion rate and infusion time, an additional column INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION is required in the data file: Monolix can use both indifferently. Data file infusion_rate_data.txt has an additional column rate:

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS	AMOUNT	INFUSION RATE
ID	TIME	DV	AMT	RATE
1	0	.	60000	60000
1	0.25	132.5	.	.
1	0.5	299.3	.	.
1	0.75	425.4	.	.
1	1	668.1	.	.
1	1.5	548.2	.	.
1	2	397.3	.	.
1	2.5	787.5	.	.
1	3	501.9	.	.
1	4	712.6	.	.

It can be replaced by infusion_tinf_data.txt which contains exactly the same information:

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS	AMOUNT	INFUSION DURATION
ID	TIME	DV	AMT	TINF
1	0	.	60000	1
1	0.25	132.5	.	.
1	0.5	299.3	.	.
1	0.75	425.4	.	.
1	1	668.1	.	.
1	1.5	548.2	.	.
1	2	397.3	.	.
1	2.5	787.5	.	.
1	3	501.9	.	.
1	4	712.6	.	.

We use with this project a 2 compartment model with non linear elimination and parameters V_1 , Q , V_2 , V_m , K_m :

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{12} &= Q/V_1 \\
 k_{21} &= Q/V_2 \\
 \frac{dA_c}{dt} &= k_{21}Ap(t) - k_{12}Ac(t) - \frac{V_m A_c(t)}{V_1 K_m + A_c(t)} \\
 \frac{dA_p}{dt} &= -k_{21}Ap(t) + k_{12}Ac(t) \\
 Cc(t) &= \frac{Ac(t)}{V_1}
 \end{aligned}$$

This model is available in the Monolix PK library as `infusion_2cpt_V1QV2VmKm` :

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V1, Q, V2, Vm, Km}

PK:
V = V1
k12 = Q/V1
k21 = Q/V2
Cc = pkmodel(V, k12, k21, Vm, Km)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
  
```

3.7.5.1.4 Oral administration

3.7.5.1.4.1 first-order absorption

- **oral1_project**

This project uses the data file `oral_data.txt` . For each patient, information about dosing is the time of administration and the amount. A one compartment model with first order absorption and linear elimination is used with this project. Parameters of the model are k_a , V and Cl . we will then use model `oral1_kaVCl.txt` from the `Monolix` PK library

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
  
```

Both the individual fits and the VPCs show that this model doesn't describe the absorption process properly.

Many options for implementing this PK model with Mlxtran exists:

- using PK macros: oralMacro.txt:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac)
oral(cmt=1, ka)
elimination(cmt=1, k=Cl/V)
Cc=Ac/V
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

- using a system of two ODEs as in oralODEb.txt :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:
k = Cl/V
ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

- combining PK macros and ODE as in `oralMacroODE.txt` (macros are used for the absorption and ODE for the elimination):

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac)
oral(cmt=1, ka)

EQUATION:
k = Cl/V
ddt_Ac = - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

- or equivalently, as in `oralODEa.txt` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, ka)

EQUATION:
k = Cl/V
ddt_Ac = - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

i Only models using the `pkmodel` function or PK macros use an analytical solution of the ODE system.

3.7.5.1.4.2 zero-order absorption

- **oral0_project**

A one compartment model with zero order absorption and linear elimination is used to fit the same PK data with this project. Parameters of the model are Tk_0 , V and Cl . We will then use model `oral0_1cpt_Tk0Vk.txt` from the Monolix PK library

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tk0, V, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```


i Implementing a zero-order absorption process using ODEs is not easy... on the other hand, it becomes extremely easy to implement using either the `pkmodel` function or the PK macro `oral(Tk0)`.

i The duration of a zero-order absorption has nothing to do with an infusion time: it is a parameter of the PK model (exactly as the absorption rate constant k_a for instance), it is not part of the data.

3.7.5.1.4.3 Sequential zero-order first-order absorption

- **sequentialOral0Oral1_project**

More complex PK models can be implemented using `Mlxtran`. A sequential zero-order first-order absorption process assumes that a fraction F_r of the dose is first absorbed during a time Tk_0 with a zero-order process, then, the remaining fraction is absorbed with a first-order process. This model is implemented in `sequentialOral0Oral1.txt` using PK macros:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Fr, Tk0, ka, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(amount=Ac)
absorption(Tk0, p=Fr)
absorption(ka, Tlag=Tk0, p=1-Fr)
elimination(k=Cl/V)
Cc=Ac/V
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Both the individual fits and the VPCs show that this PK model describes very well the whole ADME process for the same PK data:

3.7.5.1.4.4 Simultaneous zero-order first-order absorption

- **simultaneousOral0Oral1_project**

A simultaneous zero-order first-order absorption process assumes that a fraction Fr of the dose is absorbed with a zero-order process while the remaining fraction is absorbed simultaneously with a first-order process. This model is implemented in `simultaneousOral0Oral1.txt` using PK macros:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Fr, Tk0, ka, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(amount=Ac)
absorption(Tk0, p=Fr)
absorption(ka, p=1-Fr)
elimination(k=Cl/V)
Cc=Ac/V
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.1.4.5 alpha-order absorption

- **oralAlpha_project**

An α -order absorption process assumes that the rate of absorption is proportional to some power of the amount of drug in the depot compartment:

$$\frac{dA_d}{dt} = -r(A_d(t))^\alpha$$

This model is implemented in `oralAlpha.txt` using ODEs:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {r, alpha, V, Cl}

PK:
depot(target = Ad)

EQUATION:
dAd = Ad^alpha
ddt_Ad = -r*dAd
ddt_Ac = r*Ad - (Cl/V)*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.1.4.6 transit compartment model

- **oralTransitComp_project**

A PK model with a transit compartment of transit rate K_{tr} and mean transit time M_{tt} can be implemented using the PK macro `oral(ka, Mtt, Ktr)`, or using the `pkmodel` function, as in `oralTransitComp.txt`:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Mtt, Ktr, ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Mtt, Ktr, ka, V, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.1.5 Using different parametrizations

The PK macros and the function `pkmodel` use some preferred parametrizations and some reserved names as input arguments: `Tlag`, `ka`, `Tk0`, `V`, `Cl`, `k12`, `k21`. It is however possible to use another parametrization and/or other parameter names. As an example, consider a 2-compartment model for oral administration with a lag, a first order absorption and a linear elimination. We can use the `pkmodel` function with, for instance, parameters `ka`, `V`, `k`, `k12` and `k21`:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, k, k12, k21}

PK:
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, k, k12, k21)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Imagine now that we want i) to use the clearance `Cl` instead of the elimination rate constant `k`, ii) to use capital letters for the parameter names. We can still use the `pkmodel` function as follows:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {KA, V, CL, K12, K21}

PK:
Cc = pkmodel(ka=KA, V, k=CL/V, k12=K12, k21=K21)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.2 Multiple administration routes

Objectives: learn how to define and use a PK model for multiple routes of administration..

Demos: `ivOral1_project`, `ivOral2_project`

Some drugs can display complex absorption kinetics. Common examples are mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, either sequentially or simultaneously, and fast and slow parallel first-order absorption. A few examples of those kinds of absorption kinetics are proposed below. Various absorption models are proposed [here](#) as examples.

3.7.5.2.1 Combining iv and oral administrations – Example 1

- **ivOral1_project** (data = 'ivOral1_data.txt', model = 'ivOral1Macro_model.txt')

In this example, we combine oral and iv administrations of the same drug. The data file `ivOral1_data.txt` contains an additional column ADMINISTRATION ID which indicates the route of administration (1=iv, 2=oral).

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	ADMINISTRATION ID	INFUSION RATE	OBSERVATION CONTINUOUS
ID	TIME	AMT	ADM	RATE	Y
1	0	40	2	-	-
1	1	-	-	-	2.55815
1	5	-	-	-	2.50017
1	9	-	-	-	1.0702
1	12	40	2	-	-
1	13	-	-	-	3.57587
1	17	-	-	-	2.60105
1	18	20	1	5	-
1	21	-	-	-	2.23759
1	24	40	2	-	-

We assume here a one compartment model with first-order absorption process from the depot compartment (oral administration) and a linear elimination process from the central compartment. We further assume that only a fraction **F** (bioavailability) of the drug orally administered is absorbed. This model is implemented in `ivOral1Macro_model.txt` using PK macros:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {F, ka, V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=Ac)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
oral(adm=2, cmt=1, ka, p=F)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

A logit-normal distribution is used for bioavailability **F** that takes values in (0,1). The model properly fits the data as can be seen on the individual fits of the 6 first individuals:

The same PK model could be implemented using ODEs instead of PK macros.

Let A_d and A_c , respectively, the amounts in the depot compartment (gut) and the central compartment (bloodstream). Kinetics of A_d and A_c are described by the following system of ODEs:

$$\dot{A}_d(t) = -k_a A_d(t) \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{A}_c(t) = k_a A_d(t) - k A_c(t)$$

The target compartment is the depot compartment (A_d) for oral administrations and the central compartment (A_c) for iv administrations. This model is implemented in `ivOral1ODE_model.txt` using a system of ODEs:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {F, ka, V, k}

PK:
depot(type=1, target=Ad, p=F)
depot(type=2, target=Ac)

EQUATION:
ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Solving this ODEs system is less efficient than using the PK macros which uses the analytical solution of the linear system.

3.7.5.2.2 Combining iv and oral administrations – Example 2

- **ivOral2_project** (data = 'ivOral2_data.txt' , model = 'ivOral2Macro_model.txt')

In this example (based on simulated PK data), we combine intravenous injection with 3 different types of oral administrations of the same drug. The datafile `ivOral2_data.txt` contains column `ADM` which indicates the route of administration (1,2,3=oral, 4=iv). We assume that one type of oral dose (adm=1) is absorbed into a latent compartment following a zero-order absorption process. The 2 oral doses (adm=2,3) are absorbed into the central compartment following first-order absorption processes with different rates. Bioavailabilities are supposed to be different for the 3 oral doses. There is linear transfer from the latent to the central compartment. A peripheral compartment is linked to the central compartment. The drug is eliminated by a linear process from the central compartment:

This model is implemented in `ivOral2Macro_model.txt` using PK macros:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {F1, F2, F3, Tk01, ka2, ka3, kl, k23, k32, V, Cl}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=A1)
compartment(cmt=2, amount=Ac)
peripheral(k23,k32)
oral(type=1, cmt=1, Tk0= Tk01, p=F1)
oral(type=2, cmt=2, ka=ka2, p=F2)
oral(type=3, cmt=2, ka=ka3, p=F3)
iv(type=4, cmt=2)
transfer(from=1, to=2, kt=kl)
elimination(cmt=2, k=Cl/V)
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

Here, logit-normal distributions are used for bioavailabilities F_1 , F_2 and F_3 . The model fits the data properly:

The number and type of doses vary from one patient to another in this example.

3.7.5.3 Multiple doses and steady state

Objectives: learn how to define and use a PK model with multiple doses or assuming steady-state.

Demos: multidose_project, addl_project, ss1_project, ss2_project, ss3_project

3.7.5.3.1 Multiple doses

- **multidose_project** (data = 'multidose_data.txt' , model = 'lib:bolus_1cpt_Vk.txt')

In this project, each patient receives several iv bolus injections. Each dose is represented by a row in the data file multidose_data.txt:

ID ▾	TIME ▾	AMOUNT ▾	OBSERVATION ▾ CONTINUOUS ▾
id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	.
1	0.5	.	3.365
1	1	.	2.4718
1	3	.	2.5617
1	5	.	1.8819
1	7	.	2.1349
1	9	.	1.6741
1	11	.	2.0317
1	12	40	.
1	24	40	.

The PK model and the statistical model used in this project properly fit the observed data of each individual. Even if there is no observation between 12h and 72h, predicted concentrations computed on this time interval exhibit the multiple doses received by each patient:

VPCs, which is a diagnosis tool, are based on the design of the observations and therefore “ignore” what may happen between 12h and 72h:

On the other hand, the prediction distribution, which is not a diagnosis tool, computes the distribution of the predicted concentration at any time point:

3.7.5.3.2 Additional doses (ADDL)

- **addl_project** (data = 'addl_data.txt' , model = 'lib:bolus_1cpt_Vk.txt')

We can note in the previous project, that, for each patient, the interval time between two successive doses is the same (12 hours for each patient) and the amount of drug which is administrated is always the same as well (40mg for each patient). We can take advantage of this design in order to simplify the data file by defining, for each patient, a unique amount (AMT), the number of additional doses which are administrated after the first one (ADDITIONAL DOSES) and the time interval between successive doses (INTERDOSE INTERVAL):

ID ▾	TIME ▾	AMOUNT ▾	ADDITIONAL DOSES ▾	INTERDOSE INTERVAL ▾	OBSERVATION ▾ CONTINUOUS ▾
id	time	amt	addl	ii	y
1	0	40	6	12	.
1	0.5	.	.	.	3.9693
1	1	.	.	.	4.6038
1	3	.	.	.	3.3766
1	5	.	.	.	3.5052
1	7	.	.	.	3.221
1	9	.	.	.	2.3288
1	11	.	.	.	2.4186
1	72.5	.	.	.	10.361
1	73	.	.	.	9.0725

The keywords `ADDL` and `II` are automatically recognized by Monolix.

Remarks:

- Results obtained with this project, i.e. with this data file, are identical to the ones obtained with the previous project.
- It is possible to combine single doses (using `ADDL=0`) and repeated doses in a same data file.

3.7.5.3.3 Steady-state

- **ss1_project** (data = 'ss1_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral0_1cpt_TkOVCl.txt')

The dose, orally administrated at time 0 to each patient, is assumed to be a “steady-state dose” which means that a “large” number of doses before time 0 have been administrated, with a constant amount and a constant interval dosing, such that steady-state, i.e. equilibrium, is reached at time 0. The data file `ss1_data` contains a column `STEADY STATE` which indicates if the dose is a steady-state dose or not and a column `INTERDOSE INTERVAL` for the inter-dose interval:

ID ▾	TIME ▾	AMOUNT ▾	STEADY STATE ▾	INTERDOSE INTERVAL ▾	OBSERVATION ▾ CONTINUOUS ▾
id	time	amt	ss	ii	y
1	0	40	1	12	.
1	1	.	.	.	3.7423
1	2	.	.	.	5.2096
1	5	.	.	.	3.8594
1	9	.	.	.	3.15
1	13	.	.	.	2.135
1	17	.	.	.	1.571
1	21	.	.	.	0.9909
1	25	.	.	.	0.7124
1	29	.	.	.	0.6115

Click on Check the initial fixed effects to display the predicted concentration between the last dose administrated at time 0. One can see that the initial concentration is not 0 but the result of the steady state calculation.

We see on this plot that Monolix adds 5 doses before the last dose to reach steady-state. Individual fits display the predicted concentrations computed with these additional doses:

If the dynamics is slow, adding 5 doses before the last dose might not be sufficient. You can adapt the number of doses in the frame data and thus define it for all individuals as on the following figure.

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	STEADY STATE No doses 10	INTERDOSE INTERVAL	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
id	time	amt	ss	ii	y	
1	0	40	1	12	.	
1	1	.	.	.	3.7423	
1	2	.	.	.	5.2096	
1	5	.	.	.	3.8594	

leading to the following check initial fixed effects

- **ss2_project** (data = 'ss2_data.txt' , model = 'lib:oral0_1cpt_Tk0VCl.txt')

Steady-state and non steady-states doses are combined in this project:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	STEADY STATE	INTERDOSE INTERVAL	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
id	time	amt	ss	ii	y	
1	0	40	1	12	-	
1	1	-	-	-	3.9468	
1	2	-	-	-	5.9458	
1	5	-	-	-	4.9622	
1	9	-	-	-	3.4311	
1	13	-	-	-	1.8325	
1	17	-	-	-	1.5085	
1	21	-	-	-	1.1848	
1	24	60	0	-	-	
1	25	-	-	-	3.7182	

Individual fits display the predicted concentrations computed with this combination of doses:

3.7.5.4 Mixed first-order and zero-order absorption, or parallel first-order

Some drugs can display complex absorption kinetics. Common examples are mixed first-order and zero-order absorptions, where one fraction of the dose is absorbed via one route and the other fraction via another route, either simultaneously or with one of the route showing a delay. Another example is fast and slow first-order absorptions in parallel. Finally, sequential absorption with a zero-order process into a transit compartment followed by a first-order absorption in the central compartment is also possible.

A few examples of those kinds of absorption kinetics are listed below:

- **parallel first-order:** oral sustained-release Diltiazem (Murata et al. 1989) and sublingual doses with a rapid absorption from the bucal cavity followed by a delayed absorption from the gastrointestinal tract ("Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Data Analysis: Concepts and Applications" by Gabrielsson and Weiner)
- **first-order followed by zero-order:** oral sumatriptan (Cosson et al. 1999)
- **zero-order followed by first-order:** oral cefadroxil (Guarrigues et al. 1991)

More examples of complex absorptions are given in:

Zhou, H. (2003). *Pharmacokinetic Strategies in Deciphering Atypical Drug Absorption Profiles*. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 43(3), 211–227.

3.7.5.4.1 Mixtran models

For the examples below, we consider a single compartment and a linear elimination. The model is described using macros. When two absorption routes are considered, a fraction F of the dose is absorbed via the one process and the remaining $1-F$ fraction of the dose is absorbed via another process. **In the data set, the dose lines must *not* be duplicated.** A single dose line can be split into two processes using the keyword p in the absorption macros.

As the parameter F must stay within $[0,1]$, a logit distribution must be chosen in the Monolix GUI.

3.7.5.4.1.1 Sequential absorption

In this model, the drug is first absorbed via a zero-order process into a transit compartment and then transferred from the transit compartment into the central compartment using a first-order process. This model allows to capture a progressively faster increase of the concentration during the absorption phase with a simpler model than when taking into account an estimated number of transit compartments (absorption macro with M_{tt} and K_{tr} parameters). In addition, this model has the advantage of using an analytical solution, so it is faster to run than a model with estimated transit compartments that require the solve an ODE system. For the analytical solution to be used, a dummy elimination (equal to zero) from the transit compartment is necessary.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl}

PK:
compartment(cmt = 1, amount = Ad)
oral(cmt = 1, Tk0)
elimination(cmt = 1, Cl=0) ; dummy elimination term
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = ka)
elimination(cmt = 2, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is not yet available in the Monolix libraries.

3.7.5.4.1.2 Parallel first-order

Parallel first-order absorptions can have various causes, among other: absorption via water and lipid routes for dermal administrations, absorption in the bucal cavity and GI tract for sublingual administrations, progressive solubilisation along the GI tract and subsequent intestinal absorption for oral administrations or simply two different absorption sites.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka1, ka2, Tlag, F, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, ka=ka1, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, ka=ka2, Tlag, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral1_oral1_1cpt_ka1ka2F1Tlag2VCl.txt*, with Tlag named Tlag2 and F named F1.

3.7.5.4.1.3 Simultaneous zero-order and first-order

The drug is simultaneously absorbed via a first-order and a zero-order process, which both start at the administration time (no lag time).


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, V, Cl}
```

```

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
    
```

```

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
    
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral0_oral1_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1VCl.txt*, with Tk0 named Tk01, ka named ka2, and F named F1.

3.7.5.4.1.4 Sequential zero-order followed by first order

The drug is first absorbed via a zero-order process during a time Tk0. Once this is finished, the remaining fraction is absorbed via a first-order process, which starts with a lag time Tk0.


```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, V, Cl}
    
```

```

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F)
absorption(cmt=1, Tlag=Tk0, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
    
```

```

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
    
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral0_oral1_seqAbs_1cpt_Tk01ka2F1VCl.txt*, with Tk0 named Tk01, ka named ka2, and F named F1.

3.7.5.4.1.5 Sequential first-order followed by zero-order

Because a first-order absorption never ends (there is always a little bit of drug remaining in the depot compartment and being absorbed into the central compartment), the two absorption processes will not

be truly sequential. Yet **we can introduce a lag time for the zero-order process**, such that the zero-order process starts when the first-order process becomes negligible.


```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, Tlag, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(cmt=1, Tk0, p=F, Tlag)
absorption(cmt=1, ka, p=1-F)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model is available in the PK double absorption library, with the name *oral1_oral0_1cpt_ka1Tk02F1Tlag2VCl.txt*, with ka named ka1, Tk0 named Tk02, Tlag named Tlag2, and F named F1.

3.7.5.4.1.6 Two administration routes and mixed absorption

Below we present a model for an administration scheme with two different routes: some doses are administrated via iv and some orally. **The two routes are distinguished using an identifier**: in the data set the doses are tagged using the ADM column with either ADM=1 (iv for instance) or ADM=2 (oral). In the model, the adm keyword is used to associate a route to specific doses.

In addition, we introduce the total bioavailability for the oral route Foral.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Tk0, F, Foral, Tlag, V, Cl}
```

```
PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
absorption(adm=2, cmt=1, Tk0, p=F*Foral, Tlag)
absorption(adm=2, cmt=1, ka, p=(1-F)*Foral)
elimination(cmt=1, Cl)
```

```
OUTPUT:
```

```
output = {Cc}
```

3.7.5.5 Saturation of the absorption rate

In some cases, for instance in case of transporter-mediated uptake, the absorption from the depot compartment into the central compartment can saturate. To model this phenomenon, one can replace the first-order rate of absorption by a Michaelis-Menten term.

Examples of drugs displaying a saturating absorption include Phenylbutazone, Naproxen, Chlorothiazide, beta-lactam antibiotics and are reviewed in:

Wood, J. H., & Thakker, K. M. (1982). Michaelis-menten absorption kinetics in drugs: Examples and implications. European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology, 23(2), 183-188.

3.7.5.5.1 Mixtran model

To describe a saturable absorption, the depot compartment must be explicitly described and the model must be written as an ODE system. Below we present a one-compartment model with linear elimination and saturable absorption.

The depot macro permits to add the doses defined in the data set to the amount in the depot compartment. The Michaelis-Menten term is written using the amount of the depot compartment instead of the concentration as the volume needed to calculate the concentration is unidentifiable.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Vm, Km, V, CL}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ad = -Vm*Ad/(Ad+Km)
ddt_Ac = Vm*Ad/(Ad+Km) - CL/V*Ac

Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.7.5.6 Absorption delays via sigmoid absorption, transit compartments or Weibull absorption

Absorption delays are common after oral administrations. They reflect the time needed for drug dissolution and/or for transit to the absorption site (Savic et al., 2007). A simple option is to model this delay via a lag time (i.e the absorption starts after a delay). However, this may not properly capture the concentration-time profile and the progressive appearance of the drug to the absorption site. Several approaches have been used to model a progressive delay:

1. **sigmoid absorptions**, which assume a zero-order input into the depot compartment followed by a first-order absorption from the depot to the central compartment.
2. **transit compartment models**, which describes the absorption as a multiple step process with a chain of pre-systemic compartments
3. **Weibull absorptions**, which describe the change in the absorption rate k_a in a phenomenological way via a Weibull function.

3.7.5.6.1 Sigmoid absorption

The sigmoid model is also called “sequential zero order + first order absorption” where sequential is meant in terms of order of compartments. The absorption from the depot to the central compartment occurs via a usual first-order process with parameter k_a . To introduce the delay, the dose is put into the depot compartment progressively, via a zero-order process of duration T_{k0} (instead of a bolus). The model scheme is the following:

The sigmoid absorption model presents the advantage of introducing a **single additional delay parameter** and having an **analytical solution**. For the analytical solution to be used, it is necessary to add a dummy elimination with clearance equal zero from the depot macro.

Note that in comparison to Nonmem, it is **not necessary to add a RATE=-1 or RATE=-2 column** in the dataset.

The mlxtran code reads:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl, Q, Vp}

PK:
; depot compartment
compartment(cmt = 1, amount = Ad)
; zero order input in depot (cmt=1)
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0)
; elimination from depot is required for analytical solution but can be set to zero
elimination(cmt = 1, Cl=0)
; central compartment
compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
; first order absorption from depot to central
transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = ka)
; elimination from central compartment
elimination(cmt = 2, Cl)
; optional peripheral compartments (one or two peripheral compartments)
peripheral(k23=Q/V, k32=Q/Vp)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
    
```

If a bioavailability F needs to be considered, it can be added in the absorption() macro as:

```
absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0, p=F)
```

3.7.5.6.2 Transit compartments

Transit compartment can easily be implemented using the oral macro (when describing the model using macros) or the depot macro (when describing the model using ODEs), by adding the parameters Mtt and Ktr in addition to the usual absorption rate ka. Mtt represents the mean transit time and Ktr the transit rate between compartments. These two parameters are related via the number of compartments n:

i In case of multiple doses, the amounts in the depot, transit and absorption compartments are reset at each new doses. Thus the implementation is valid only if the dose is fully absorbed before the next dose administration. The amount in the central (and possibly other compartments) is not reset and can accumulate.

3.7.5.6.2.1 Example with model based on macros

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={ka, Mtt, Ktr, V, k}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
oral(cmt=1, Mtt, Ktr, ka)
elimination(cmt=1,k)

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.6.2.2 Example with model based on ODEs

The entire absorption process is handled by the depot macro, which reads the dose information in the data set and applies an input rate to the target A_c corresponding to an oral administration with transit compartments.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={ka, Mtt, Ktr, V, k}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, ka, Mtt, Ktr)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ac = - k * Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.6.3 Weibull absorptions

Despite the lack of physiological basis, the Weibull model is appreciated for its flexibility (Zhou et al, 2003). In practice, it is rarely used. We here demonstrate the implementation of one Weibull function models. The extension to two Weibull functions is straightforward. The time-varying absorption rate is:

$$k_a(t) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{t}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1}$$

The model requires to be written as an ODE system with a depot compartment and at last a central compartment. The transfer of matter from the depot compartment to the central compartment is described using a time-varying rate constant. To allow for multiple doses, the time is calculated with respect to the time of the last dose, using the tDose keyword. Note that only one type of administration (only oral or only iv for instance) is allowed per individual, as the tDose keyword doesn't distinguish between different administration types ADM.

The alpha parameter describes the delay, while the beta parameter influences the steepness of the absorption phase.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={beta, alpha, V, k}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ad = -Ad * (beta/alpha)*(max(0,t-tDose)/alpha)^(beta-1)
ddt_Ac = Ad * (beta/alpha)*(max(0,t-tDose)/alpha)^(beta-1) - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = Cc
```

3.7.5.7 Models for urine data

When collecting urine data, the urines are collected over several time intervals. For each time interval, the total urine volume and the drug concentration are recorded. The concentration is not relevant by itself, because it strongly depends on the urine volume that itself depend on how much the individual has drunk etc. We are rather interested in the amount of drug excreted in the urine, which is related to the urinary excretion rate.

3.7.5.7.1 Using the amount

The amount excreted in each interval can easily be computed by multiplying the concentration and the urine volume. When a new interval starts, the “urine compartment” must be emptied, i.e the variable representing the amount excreted in the urine must be reset to zero. To trigger this reset, pseudo-dose records must be added to the data set. They are distinguished from the true doses by a specific administration identifier (here adm=2) and have an amount of 0. To make sure the reset will happen after the observation, the time of the reset are slightly larger than the time of the observation.

Time	Amount	Adm	DV	
0	500	1	.	← True dose
2	.	.	155	
2.0001	0	2	.	← Pseudo-dose (amount 0) to trigger the reset (reset will be linked to adm=2 in the model)
4	.	.	132	
4.0001	0	2	.	
6	.	.	65	← amount excreted from the time 4.0001 (time of reset) until time 6
6.0001	0	2	.	
12	.	.	47	
12.0001	0	2	.	
24	.	.	5.6	

For the model, we will assume that the dose arrives in the central compartment and follows a linear elimination with a rate “k”. A fraction “pu” of the drug is eliminated with the kidney and arrives in the urine. The model is written with ODEs in order to be able to apply the resets. True doses (adm=1 in this example) are applied to the variable Aplasma representing the amount in the plasma (central compartment), while pseudo-doses (adm=2) are linked to the empty() macro which resets its target

Aurine (amount excreted in the urine) to zero at the time of the pseudo doses. The amount Aurine is outputted to be mapped to the observations of the data set.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {k, pu}

PK:
depot(adm=1, target=Aplasma)
empty(adm=2, target=Aurine)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Aplasma_0 = 0
Aurine_0 = 0

ddt_Aplasma = - k * Aplasma
ddt_Aurine = k * pu * Aplasma

OUTPUT:
output = Aurine
```

In the “check initial fixed effects” or “individual fits” plot, the resets are clearly visible:

3.7.5.7.2 Using the concentration and urine volume

It is also possible to directly use the measured urine volume and drug concentration. The drug concentration is considered as being the observation. To calculate in the predicted drug concentration in the model, the predicted amount excreted in the urine is divided by the urine volume. In order to be passed to the model, the urine volume column in the data set is tagged as regressor. For the parameter estimation in Monolix, only the regressor values on observation lines are important. However, to plot predictions on a regular time grid, Monolix interpolates the regressor values using “Last Observation Carried Forward” or “Linear interpolation” and it is necessary to provide a regressor value for the first record (dose or observation line). We thus recommend a provide the urine volume value on all lines.

As when working with the amount, the variable representing the amount excreted in the urine must be reset to zero when a new interval starts. To trigger this reset, pseudo-dose records must be added to the data set. They are distinguished from the true doses by a specific administration identifier (here adm=2) and have an amount of 0. To make sure the reset will happen after the observation, the time of the reset are slightly larger than the time of the observation.

Time	Amount	Adm	DV	UriVol
0	500	1	.	135
2	.	.	1150	135
2.0001	0	2	.	148
4	.	.	897	148
4.0001	0	2	.	121
6	.	.	540	121
6.0001	0	2	.	331
12	.	.	144	331
12.0001	0	2	.	1655
24	.	.	3.4	1655

← True dose
← Pseudo-dose (amount 0) to trigger the reset (reset will be linked to adm=2 in the model)
← Urine volume collected from the time 4.0001 (time of reset) until time 6
← Concentration measured in the urine collected from the time 4.0001 (time of reset) until time 6

For the model, we will assume that the dose arrives in the central compartment and follows a linear elimination with a rate “k”. A fraction “pu” of the drug is eliminated with the kidney and arrives in the urine. The model is written with ODEs in order to be able to apply the resets. True doses (adm=1 in this example) are applied to the variable Aplasma representing the amount in the plasma (central compartment), while pseudo-doses (adm=2) are linked to the empty() macro which resets its target Aurine (amount excreted in the urine) to zero at the time of the pseudo doses. Before being outputted, the concentration is calculated from the amount in plasma and the urine volume which is indicated as being a regressor and thus read from the data set. Note that the units of the dose, concentration and urine volume must be consistent, or a scaling factor can be added in the model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {k, pu, UriVol}
```

```
UriVol = {use=regressor}
```

PK:

```
depot(adm=1, target=Aplasma)
```

```
empty(adm=2, target=Aurine)
```

EQUATION:

```
t_0 = 0
```

```
Aplasma_0 = 0
```

```
Aurine_0 = 0
```

```
ddt_Aplasma = - k * Aplasma
```

```
ddt_Aurine = k*pu*Aplasma
```

```
Conc = Aurine/UriVol*1000
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = Conc
```

In the “check initial fixed effects” or “individual fits” plot, the resets are clearly visible:

3.7.5.7.3 Using the cumulative amount

The cumulative amount can easily be calculated as the sum of the amounts collected from the dose time until the time point of interest. This formatting presents the advantage that no emptying of the urine compartment is necessary. The format of the data set is thus straightforward:

Time	Amount	DV
0	500	.
2	.	155
4	.	287
6	.	352
12	.	399
24	.	404

total amount excreted from the dose time until time 4

Note that when working with cumulative amounts, if a concentration or urine volume observation is missing, then it is not possible to calculate the cumulative amount for all following time points. Missing information has thus larger consequences than when working with the two other formatting options.

In the model, the cumulative amount is calculated and outputted:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {k, pu}

PK:
depot(target = Aplasma)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Aplasma_0 = 0
Aurine_0 = 0

ddt_Aplasma = - k * Aplasma
ddt_Aurine = k*pu*Aplasma

OUTPUT:
output = Aurine
```

Note that for multiple doses, an emptying of the Aurine variable can be added in the model and in the data set such that the recorded observation represents the cumulative amount from the last dose to the current time.

In the “check initial fixed effects” or “individual fits” plot, the cumulative amount is always increasing (no reset):

3.7.6 Models for non-continuous data

The following pages describe structural model definition for non-continuous outcomes:

3.7.6.1 Time-to-event data models

Related resources on modeling time-to-event data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of time-to-event data in the MonolixSuite.
- [Time-to-event observation model](#): details on the different models for time-to-event data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax.
- [Time-to-event model library](#): detailed description of the library of time-to-event models integrated within Monolix.

On the current page, we show examples of time-to-event data models from the Monolix demos, and we then discuss how interval-censored repeated time-to-event data can also be considered as count data with examples in Monolix.

Demos: tte1_project, tte2_project, tte3_project, tte4_project, rtteWeibull_project, rtteWeibullCount_project

3.7.6.1.1 Single event

To begin with, we will consider a one-off event. Depending on the application, the length of time to this event may be called the *survival time* (until death, for instance), *failure time* (until hardware fails), and so on. In general, we simply say “time-to-event”. The random variable representing the time-to-event for subject i is typically written T_i .

3.7.6.1.1.1 Single event exactly observed or right censored

- **tte1_project** (data = tte1_data.txt , model=lib:exponential_model_singleEvent.txt)

The event time may be exactly observed at time t_i , but if we assume that the trial ends at time t_{stop} , the event may happen after the end. This is “right censoring”. Here, $Y=0$ at time t means that the event happened after t and $Y=1$ means that the event happened at time t . The rows with $t=0$ are included to show the trial start time $t_{start} = 0$:

By clicking on the button **Observed data**, it is possible to display the Kaplan-Meier plot (i.e. the empirical survival function) before fitting any model:

A very basic model with constant hazard is used for this data:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = Te

EQUATION:
h = 1/Te

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, hazard=h}

OUTPUT:
output = {Event}
    
```

Here, T_e is the expected time to event. Specification of the maximum number of events is required both for the estimation procedure and for the diagnosis plots based on simulation, such as the predicted interval for the Kaplan Meier plot which is obtained by Monte Carlo simulation:

3.7.6.1.1.2 Single event interval censored or right censored

- **tte2_project** (data = tte2_data.txt , model=exponentialIntervalCensored_model.txt)

We may know the event has happened in an interval I_i but not know the exact time t_i . This is *interval censoring*. Here, $Y=0$ at time t means that the event happened after t and $Y=1$ means that the event happened before time t .

Event for individual 1 happened between $t=10$ and $t=15$. No event was observed until the end of the experiment ($t=100$) for individual 5. We use the same basic model, but we now need to specify that the events are interval censored:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = Te

EQUATION:
h = 1/Te

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, maxEventNumber=1, eventType=intervalCensored, hazard = h
```

```

        intervalLength=5      ; used for the plots (not mandatory)
    }

    OUTPUT:
    output = Event
    
```

3.7.6.1.2 Repeated events

3.7.6.1.2.1 Repeated events exactly observed or right censored

- **tte3_project** (data = tte3_data.txt , model=lib:exponential_model_repeatedEvents.txt)

A sequence of n_i event times is precisely observed before $t_{stop} = 200$: We can then display the Kaplan Meier plot for the first event and the mean number of events per individual:

After fitting the model, prediction intervals for these two curves can also be displayed on the same graph as on the following:

3.7.6.1.2.2 Repeated events interval censored or right censored

- **tte4_project** (data = tte4_data.txt , model=exponentialIntervalCensored_repeated_model.txt)

We do not know the exact event times, but the number of events that occurred for each individual in each interval of time.

3.7.6.1.3 Considering the data as count or TTE data

Interval-censored repeated time-to-event data can also be considered as count data: we count the number of events during an interval.

3.7.6.1.3.1 Link between TTE models and count models

As in [Time-to-event observation model](#) , we note the hazard h and the cumulative hazard H .

The probability density function (pdf) for a single exactly observed event at time t_i is $p(y_i) = h(t_i) \times e^{-H_{t_0}^{t_i}}$. The pdf for a single event interval-censored between t_1 and t_2 , is $p(y_i) = e^{-H_{t_0}^{t_1}} \times (1 - e^{-H_{t_1}^{t_2}})$. The pdf for repeated interval censored events is slightly more complicated.

The probability density function (pdf) to observe k events within a time interval from t_1 to t_2 , given the hazard h , can be calculated as:

$$p(y_i) = \exp\left(-H_{t_1}^{t_2}\right) \frac{\left(H_{t_1}^{t_2}\right)^k}{k!} = \exp\left(-\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h\right) \frac{\left(\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h\right)^k}{k!}$$

with $\int_{t_1}^{t_2} h$ being the cumulative hazard between t_1 and t_2 .

If we have a model with a constant hazard $h = \alpha$, the cumulative hazard is equal to $H_{t_1}^{t_2} = \alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)$ and the probability density function is:

$$p(y_i) = \exp(-\alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)) \frac{(\alpha \times (t_2 - t_1))^k}{k!}$$

If, in addition, the intervals over which the events are counted are all of equal length, then we can define $\mu = \alpha \times (t_2 - t_1)$ and obtain:

$$p(y_i) = P(y = k) = \exp(-\mu) \frac{\mu^k}{k!}$$

We recognize the usual Poisson model for count data, which assume independent events and equal interval durations.

If we want to write a count model for data with non-equal interval durations, we can still use the Poisson model but make sure that the parameter μ takes into account the interval duration. This can be done by passing the *interval duration* as REGRESSOR, or by passing t_1 as REGRESSOR and obtaining the time t_2 , which is the current time, using the mlxtran keyword `t`.

The models for the data considered as TTE and the model for the data considered as count are equivalent. Note that when defining a TTE model, it is the hazard that must be defined. When defining the count model, we define the pdf. Thus, **considering the data as count can also be used to model TTE data but provide a custom likelihood (pdf) instead of providing the hazard function.**

Estimated model parameters should be consistent whether the data is considered as count or as TTE. However **the diagnostic plots provided by Monolix will be different**: Kaplan-Meier curve in case of TTE and probability over time to observed k events in case of count data.

Below we show an example with the more complex Weibull model.

3.7.6.1.3.2 Example with a Weibull model

The following dataset will be used with both approaches (TTE and count). As can be seen for individual 1, some intervals have 0 events, some 1 and some several (e.g 3). The number of observed events is indicated as an integer in the Y column tagged as OBSERVATIONS.

id	time	y
1	0	0
1	5	0
1	10	0
1	15	0
1	20	1
1	25	0
1	30	0
1	35	0
1	40	1
1	45	0
1	50	1
1	55	3
1	60	1

- **weibullRTTE** (data = weibull_data.txt , model=weibullRTTE_model.txt)

We first show an example where the data is considered as interval-censored repeated time-to-event. After loading the data, the data is indicated as being “EVENT”:

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. The top menu includes Project, Settings, Export, and Help. The main window is titled 'weibullRTTE.mlxtran [demo] * - Monolix estimation - 2024R1'. The 'Data' tab is active, showing 'Data file' information and a 'Data information' section where 'EVENT' is selected. Below this, a table displays the data with columns for LINE NUMBER, id, time, OBSERVATION (y), and IGNORE (te). The table shows 10 rows of data for individual 1, with the 'y' column containing values 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 3, and 1. The 'te' column contains values 0, 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, and 45. The interface also shows 'Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 1300' and 'Page 1 of 26'.

We use a Weibull model with the following hazard, with β the shape parameter and λ the scale parameter:

$$h = \left(\frac{\beta}{\lambda}\right) \left(\frac{t}{\lambda}\right)^{\beta-1}$$

Its implementation in mlxtran is the following. Note that the interval censoring is indicated using `eventType=intervalCensored`. The argument `intervalLength=5` is optional and is used only for simulations (e.g in the VPC).

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda, beta}

EQUATION:
h = (beta/lambda)*(t/lambda)^(beta-1)

DEFINITION:
Event = {type=event, hazard=h, eventType=intervalCensored,
        intervalLength=5}

OUTPUT:
output = Event
```

Regarding the statistical model, we keep random effects on both the location and shape parameter as we have several events per individuals which allow to distinguish the inter-individual variability from the randomness of the event time.

The estimated parameters are shown below. The estimated likelihood is 3552.

Population parameter estimates w

	VALUE	STOCH. APPROX.			
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5
Fixed Effects					
lambda_pop	10.49	0.56	5.35	9.45	11.65
beta_pop	1.55	0.051	3.32	1.45	1.65
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects					
	Value	C.V.(%)			
omega_lambda	0.22	21.76	0.049	22.8	0.14
omega_beta	0.16	15.6	0.024	15.6	0.11

In the diagnostic plots, we can see the Kaplan-Meier curve and corresponding VPC for the first event (left plot) and the mean number of events per subjects (right plot).

- **weibullCount** (data = weibull_data.txt , model=weibullCount_model.txt)

For the same dataset, instead of defining the data as events, it is possible to consider the data as *count data*: indeed, we *count* the number of events per interval. After loading the dataset, we indicate the data as being “COUNT/CATEGORICAL”.

LINE NUMBER	id	time	y	te
1	1			
2	1	0	0	0
3	1	5	0	0
4	1	10	0	5
5	1	15	0	10
6	1	20	1	15
7	1	25	0	20

To define the model, we start from the the hazard $h = \left(\frac{\beta}{\lambda}\right) \left(\frac{t}{\lambda}\right)^{\beta-1}$. We then need to obtain the cumulative hazard. For the Weibull model, the hazard integrates into the cumulative hazard as:

$$H = \int_{t_2}^{t_1} h = \frac{\beta}{\lambda} \left[\frac{t^\beta}{\beta} \right]_{t_1}^{t_2} = \left(\frac{t_2}{\lambda}\right)^\beta - \left(\frac{t_1}{\lambda}\right)^\beta$$

To calculate the cumulative hazard in the mlxtran model, we will by pass t_1 as REGRESSOR (called `tpe` in the example below) and obtain the time t_2 , which is the current time, using the mlxtran keyword `t`. Thus, an additional column with the start of the interval is added in the data file and defined as a REGRESSOR.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda, beta, tpe}
tpe = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
H = (t/lambda)^beta - (tpe/lambda)^beta
```

The probability to observe k events is then defined using the usual formula for Poisson models. We directly define the `log` of the probability, and use an `if/else` statement to distinguish the case $k = 0$ and $k > 0$.

```

DEFINITION:
nbEvents = {type=count,
if k>0
    lpk = - H + k*log(H) - factln(k)
else
    lpk = - H
end
log(P(Event=k)) = lpk
}
    
```

```

OUTPUT:
output = nbEvents
    
```

Note that the count model uses the same parameters as the TTE model: `lambda` and `beta`. As for the TTE case, we keep random effects on these two parameters.

The estimated parameters (shown below) are very similar to those estimated with the TTE model.

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface with the 'Results' tab selected. The main window displays 'Population parameter estimates' with a table of results. The table is organized into sections: 'Fixed Effects' and 'Standard Deviation of the Random Effects'. The 'Fixed Effects' section includes parameters `lambda_pop` and `beta_pop`. The 'Standard Deviation of the Random Effects' section includes parameters `omega_lambda` and `omega_beta`. The table columns are 'VALUE', 'S.E.', 'R.S.E.(%)', 'P2.5', and 'P97.5'.

	VALUE	STOCH. APPROX.			
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5
Fixed Effects					
<code>lambda_pop</code>	10.494	0.539	5.14	9.49	11.604
<code>beta_pop</code>	1.547	0.0496	3.21	1.453	1.647
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects					
	Value	C.V.(%)			
<code>omega_lambda</code>	0.218	22.023	0.0445	20.4	0.148
<code>omega_beta</code>	0.156	15.711	0.0228	14.6	0.118

The likelihood is identical (up to 4 digits): 3552.

In the diagnostic plots, the VPC shows several subplots corresponding to the probabilities to observe k events (e.g $P(\text{Event}=0)$), or between k_1 and k_2 events (e.g $P(6 \leq \text{Event} \leq 12)$). The number of subplots can be chosen in the settings "Y Bins".

3.7.6.2 Count data models

Related resources on modeling count data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of count data in the MonolixSuite
- [Count observation model](#): details on the different models for count data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax
- [Count data model library](#): detailed description of the library of count models integrated within Monolix

On the current page, we show examples of count data models from the Monolix demos.

Demos: count1a_project, count1b_project, count2_project

3.7.6.2.1 Count data with constant distribution over time

- **count1a_project** (data = 'count1_data.txt', model = 'count_library/poisson_mlxt.txt')

A Poisson model is used for fitting the data:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = lambda
```

DEFINITION:

$$Y = \{ \text{type} = \text{count}, \log(P(Y=k)) = -\lambda + k \cdot \log(\lambda) - \text{factln}(k) \}$$

OUTPUT:

```
output = Y
```

Residuals for noncontinuous data reduce to NPDEs. We can compare the empirical distribution of the NPDEs with the distribution of a standardized normal distribution either with the pdf (top) or the cdf (bottom):

VPCs for count data compare the observed and predicted frequencies of the categorized data over time:

- **count1b_project** (data = 'count1_data.txt', model = 'count_library/poissonMixture_mlxt.txt')

A mixture of two Poisson distributions is used to fit the same data. For that, we define the probability of k occurrences as the weighed sum of two Poisson distributions with two expected numbers of occurrences λ_1 and λ_2 . The structural model file writes

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda1, alpha, mp}

EQUATION:
lambda2 = (1+alpha)*lambda1

DEFINITION:
Y = { type = count,
      P(Y=k) = mp*exp(-lambda1 + k*log(lambda1) - factln(k)) + (1-mp)*exp(-lambda2 +
      k*log(lambda2) - factln(k))
}

OUTPUT:
output = Y
```

Thus, the parameter α has to be strictly positive to ensure different expected number of occurrences in the two poisson distributions and mp has to be in $[0, 1]$ to ensure the probability is

correctly defined. Thus those parameters should be defined with lognormal and probitnormal distribution respectively as shown on the following figure.

Individual model				
PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	
lbmbd1	LOGNORMAL	Select: All / None	#1	
sigma	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
rho	PROBITNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

We see on the VPC below that the data set is well modeled using this mixture of Poisson distributions.

3.7.6.2.2 Count data with time varying distribution

- **count2_project** (data = 'count2_data.txt', model = 'count_library/poissonTimeVarying_mlxt.txt')

The distribution of the data changes with time in this example:

We then use a Poisson distribution with a time varying intensity:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a,b}

EQUATION:
lambda= a*exp(-b*t)

DEFINITION:
y = {type=count, P(y=k)=exp(-lambda)*(lambda^k)/factorial(k)}

OUTPUT:
output = y
```

This model seems to fit the data very well:

3.7.6.3 Count models with offset

When the count data records the number of events happening within a time interval, one must ensure that all intervals have the same duration. If this is not the case, one option is to derive the probability to observe k events from the underlying hazard function. This is explained in the TTE documentation page. The second option is to consider an offset and this is shown here.

Let's assume that our data records the number of events during the follow-up period. The data is considered as count data (i.e an integer value) and we would like to model this data using a negative binomial distribution:

$$P(Y = k) = \frac{\Gamma(k + \frac{1}{o})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{o}) k!} \left(\frac{\lambda}{\frac{1}{o} + k} \right)^k \left(\frac{1}{1 + o\lambda} \right)^{\frac{1}{o}}$$

with λ the mean number of event and o the parameter that controls the over dispersion compared to the Poisson distribution. This model can be selected from the [library of Count models](#).

However, the number of events we observe tends to larger for individuals which have a long follow-up period. To take this into account, we can let λ depend on the duration of the follow-up observation called *DUR*. We expect that the number of events is proportional to the follow-up observation duration (often called offset), i.e that a doubling of the observation period leads to twice as much events on average. This would correspond to:

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 \times DUR$$

This equation is equivalent to:

$$\log(\lambda) = \log(\lambda_{pop}) + \beta \times \log(DUR)$$

with $\lambda_0 = \lambda_{pop}$ and $\beta = 1$.

We recognize in the equation above the typical formula for a lognormally distributed parameter.

Thus we set in Monolix:

- `lambda` with a lognormal distribution and no random-effects (unless there are several observations per individual, which would enable to estimate inter-individual variability on lambda)
- new covariate `tlogDUR = log(DUR)` added on `lambda`
- `beta_tlogDUR` fixed to 1
- `omicron` with a lognormal distribution and no random effects (same overdispersion for all individuals)

3.7.6.3.1 Equivalence with glm.nb in R

In R, one could fit a negative binomial model using the `glm.nb()` function. Considering an offset for the duration of the internal DUR and in addition the effect of the covariate WT on the mean number of events, one could write:

```
glm.nb(Count~ log(WT/70)+offset(log(DUR)), data=count_data, link=log)
```

The negative binomial model for count data can be selected from the count library, using the parametrization with lambda (mean number of events) and omicron (overdispersion).

The `link=log` indicates that the formula applies to the log of the mean number of events. The offset indicates that the variable DUR will enter the formula with a coefficient fixed to 1. On the opposite, the covariate `log(WT/70)` will enter the formula with a coefficient that will be estimated.

The equation for the mean number of events λ is thus:

$$\log(\lambda) = \lambda_0 + \beta_{WT} \times \log(WT/70) + \log(DUR)$$

In Monolix, this corresponds to:

- λ with a lognormal distribution and no random effects
- new covariate `tlogWT = log(WT/70)` added on λ
- new covariate `tlogDUR = log(DUR)` added on λ
- `beta_tlogDUR` fixed to 1
- σ with a lognormal distribution and no random effects

3.7.6.4 Categorical data models

Related resources on modeling categorical data in Monolix:

- [Columns used to define observations](#): formatting of categorical data in the MonolixSuite.
- [Categorical observation model](#): details on the different models for categorical data that can be used in Monolix and their syntax.

On the current page, we show examples of categorical data models from the Monolix demos.

Demos: `categorical1_project`, `categorical2_project`, `markov0_project`, `markov1a_project`, `markov1b_project`, `markov1c_project`, `markov2_project`, `markov3a_project`, `markov3b_project`

3.7.6.4.1 Ordered categorical data

- **`categorical1_project`** (data = 'categorical1_data.txt', model = 'categorical1_model.txt')

In this example, observations are ordinal data that take their values in {0, 1, 2, 3}:

- *Cumulative odds ratio* are used in this example to define the model

$$\text{logit}(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq k)) = \log\left(\frac{\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq k)}{1 - \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq k)}\right)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\text{logit}(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq 0)) &= \theta_{i,1} \\ \text{logit}(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq 1)) &= \theta_{i,1} + \theta_{i,2} \\ \text{logit}(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} \leq 2)) &= \theta_{i,1} + \theta_{i,2} + \theta_{i,3}\end{aligned}$$

This model is implemented in `categorical1_model.txt` :

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {th1, th2, th3}

DEFINITION:
level = { type = categorical, categories = {0, 1, 2, 3},
  logit(P(level<=0)) = th1
  logit(P(level<=1)) = th1 + th2
  logit(P(level<=2)) = th1 + th2 + th3
}
```

A normal distribution is used for θ_1 , while log-normal distributions for θ_2 and θ_3 ensure that these parameters are positive (even without variability). Residuals for noncontinuous data reduce to NPDEs. We can compare the empirical distribution of the NPDEs with the distribution of a standardized normal distribution:

VPC's for categorical data compare the observed and predicted frequencies of each category over time:

The prediction distribution can also be computed by Monte-Carlo:

3.7.6.4.2 Ordered categorical data with regression variables

- **categorical2_project** (data = 'categorical2_data.txt', model = 'categorical2_model.txt')

A proportional odds model is used in this example, where `PERIOD` and `DOSE` are used as regression variables (i.e. time-varying covariates).

3.7.6.4.3 Discrete-time Markov chain

If observation times are regularly spaced (constant length of time between successive observations), we can consider the observations $(y_{ij}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n_i)$ to be a discrete-time Markov chain.

- **markov0_project** (data = 'markov1a_data.txt', model = 'markov0_model.txt')

In this project, states are assumed to be independent and identically distributed:

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = 1) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(y_{ij} = 2) = p_{i,1}$$

Observations in `markov1a_data.txt` take their values in $\{1, 2\}$.

- **markov1a_project** (data = 'markov1a_data.txt', model = 'markov1a_model.txt')

Here,

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{i,j} = 1 | y_{i,j-1} = 1) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(y_{i,j} = 2 | y_{i,j-1} = 1) = p_{i,11}$$

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{i,j} = 1 | y_{i,j-1} = 2) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(y_{i,j} = 2 | y_{i,j-1} = 2) = p_{i,12}$$

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {p11, p21}
DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
  P(State=1|State_p=1) = p11
  P(State=1|State_p=2) = p21
}
```

The distribution of the initial state is not defined in the model, which means that, by default,

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 1) = \mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 2) = 0.5$$

- **markov1b_project** (data = 'markov1b_data.txt', model = 'markov1b_model.txt')

The distribution of the initial state, $p = \mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 1)$, is estimated in this example

```
DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
  P(State_1=1) = p
  P(State=1|State_p=1) = p11
  P(State=1|State_p=2) = p21
}
```

- **markov3a_project** (data = 'markov3a_data.txt', model = 'markov3a_model.txt')

Transition probabilities change with time in this example. We then define time varying transition probabilities in the model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a1, b1, a2, b2}
EQUATION:
lp11 = a1 + b1*t/100
lp21 = a2 + b2*t/100
DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
  logit(P(State=1|State_p=1)) = lp11
  logit(P(State=1|State_p=2)) = lp21
}
```

- **markov2_project** (data = 'markov2_data.txt', model = 'markov2_model.txt')

Observations in `markov2_data.txt` take their values in {1, 2, 3}. Then, 6 transition probabilities need to be defined in the model.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {a11, a12, a21, a22, a31, a32}

DEFINITION:
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2,3}, dependence = Markov
  logit(P(State<=1|State_p=1)) = a11
  logit(P(State<=2|State_p=1)) = a11+a12
  logit(P(State<=1|State_p=2)) = a21
  logit(P(State<=2|State_p=2)) = a21+a22
  logit(P(State<=1|State_p=3)) = a31
  logit(P(State<=2|State_p=3)) = a31+a32
}

OUTPUT:
output=State
```

3.7.6.4.4 Continuous-time Markov chain

The previous situation can be extended to the case where time intervals between observations are irregular by modeling the sequence of states as a *continuous-time Markov process*. The difference is that rather than transitioning to a new (or the same) state at each time step, the system remains in the current state for some random amount of time before transitioning. This process is now characterized by *transition rates* $\rho_{\ell k}(t)$ from the state ℓ to the state k .

- **markov1c_project** (data = 'markov1c_data.txt', model = 'markov1c_model.txt')

Observation times are irregular in this example. Then, a continuous time Markov chain should be used in order to take into account the Markovian dependence of the data:

```
DEFINITION:
State = { type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
  transitionRate(1,2) = q12
  transitionRate(2,1) = q21
}
```

- **markov3b_project** (data = 'markov3b_data.txt', model = 'markov3b_model.txt')

Time varying transition rates are used in this example.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {c1, d1, c2, d2}
```

EQUATION:

```
q12 = max(0.001, c1 + d1*t/100)
```

```
q21 = max(0.001, c2 + d2*t/100)
```

DEFINITION:

```
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
```

```
  transitionRate(1,2) = q12
```

```
  transitionRate(2,1) = q21
```

```
}
```

OUTPUT:

```
output=State
```

- **Initial state:** by default, the probabilities for the initial state (first observation) are equal for all categories. For instance in case of 3 categories,

$$\mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 1) = \mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 2) = \mathbb{P}(y_{i,1} = 3) = 0.333.$$

To define different initial probabilities (e.g all individuals in State 1), they can be defined using the following syntax. Note that it is only necessary to define the probabilities of N-1 categories (as the last one can be derived from the sum being equal to 1).

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```
input = {c1, d1, c2, d2}
```

EQUATION:

```
q12 = max(0.001, c1 + d1*t/100)
```

```
q21 = max(0.001, c2 + d2*t/100)
```

DEFINITION:

```
State = {type = categorical, categories = {1,2}, dependence = Markov
```

```
  P(State_1=1)= 1
```

```
  transitionRate(1,2) = q12
```

```
  transitionRate(2,1) = q21
```

```
}
```

OUTPUT:

```
output=State
```

3.7.6.5 Joint models for non-continuous outcomes

Details on the different types of models for non-continuous data in Monolix and their syntax are given on these pages:

- [Time-to-event observation model](#)
- [Count observation model](#)
- [Categorical observation model](#)

Detailed descriptions of the library of non-continuous data models integrated Monolix Simulx are given here:

- [Time-to-event model library](#)
- [Count data model library](#)

On the current page, we show examples of joint models combining continuous and non-continuous outcomes from the Monolix demos.

Demos: warfarin_cat_project, PKcount_project, PKrtte_project

3.7.6.5.1 Joint model for continuous PK and categorical PD data

- **warfarin_cat_project** (data = 'warfarin_cat_data.txt', model = 'PKcategorical1_model.txt')

In this example, the original PD data has been recorded as 1 (Low), 2 (Medium) and 3 (High).

More details about the data

International Normalized Ratio (INR) values are commonly used in clinical practice to target optimal warfarin therapy. Low INR values (<2) are associated with high blood clot risk and high ones (>3) with high risk of bleeding, so the targeted value of INR, corresponding to optimal therapy, is between 2 and 3.

Prothrombin complex activity is inversely proportional to the INR. We can therefore associate the three ordered categories for the INR to three ordered categories for PCA: Low PCA values if PCA is less than 33% (corresponding to INR>3), medium if PCA is between 33% and 50% (INR between 2 and 3) and high if PCA is more than 50% (INR<2).

The column `dv` contains both the PK and the new categorized PD measurements. Instead of modeling the original PD data, we can model the probabilities of each of these categories, which have direct clinical interpretations. The model is still a joint PKPD model since this probability distribution is expected to depend on exposure, i.e., the plasmatic concentration predicted by the PK model. We introduce an effect compartment to mimic the effect delay. Let $y_{ij}^{(2)}$ be the PCA level for patient i at time $t_{ij}^{(2)}$. We can then use a proportional odds model for modeling this categorical data:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 1 | \psi_i) \right) &= \alpha_i + \beta_i C_e(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)}) \\ \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 2 | \psi_i) \right) &= \alpha_i + \gamma_i + \beta_i C_e(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)}) \\ \text{logit} \left(\mathbb{P}(y_{ij}^{(2)} \leq 3 | \psi_i) \right) &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

where $C_e(t, \phi_i^{(1)})$ is the predicted concentration of warfarin in the effect compartment at time t for patient i with PK parameters $\phi_i^{(1)}$. This model defines a probability distribution for y_{ij} if $\gamma_i \geq 0$.

If $\beta_i > 0$, the probability of low PCA at time $t_{ij}^{(2)}$ ($y_{ij}^{(2)} = 1$) increases along with the predicted

concentration $Ce(t_{ij}^{(2)}, \phi_i^{(1)})$. The joint model is implemented in the model file `PKcategorical1_model.txt`

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, ke0, alpha, beta, gamma}

EQUATION:
{Cc,Ce} = pkmodel(Tlag,ka,V,Cl,ke0)
lp1 = alpha + beta*Cc
lp2 = lp1+ gamma          ; gamma >= 0

DEFINITION:
Level = {type=categorical, categories={1,2,3}
         logit(P(Level<=1)) = lp1
         logit(P(Level<=2)) = lp2
        }
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Level}
```

See Categorical data model for more details about categorical data models.

3.7.6.5.2 Joint model for continuous PK and count PD data

- **PKcount_project** (data = 'PKcount_data.txt', model = 'PKcount1_model.txt')

The data file used for this project is `PKcount_data.txt` where the PK and the count PD measurements are simulated. We use a Poisson distribution for the count data, assuming that the Poisson parameter is function of the predicted concentration. For any individual i , we have

$$\lambda_i(t) = \lambda_{0,i} \left(1 - \frac{Cc_i(t)}{Cc_i(t) + IC50_i} \right)$$

where $Cc_i(t)$ is the predicted concentration for individual i at time t and

$$\log\left(P(y_{ij}^{(2)} = k)\right) = -\lambda_i(t_{ij}) + k \log(\lambda_i(t_{ij})) - \log(k!)$$

The joint model is implemented in the model file `PKcount1_model.txt`

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, lambda0, IC50}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)
lambda=lambda0*(1 - Cc/(IC50+Cc))

DEFINITION:
```

```

Seizure = {type = count,
           log(P(Seizure=k)) = -lambda + k*log(lambda) - factln(k)
}

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Seizure}

```

See Count data model for more details about count data models.

3.7.6.5.3 Joint model for continuous PK and time-to-event data

- **PKrtte_project** (data = 'PKrtte_data.txt', model = 'PKrtteWeibull1_model.txt')

The data file used for this project is `PKrtte_data.txt` where the PK and the time-to-event data are simulated. We use a Weibull model for the events count data, assuming that the baseline is function of the predicted concentration. For any individual i , we define the hazard function as

$$h_i(t) = \gamma_i Cc_i(t) t^{\beta-1}$$

where $Cc_i(t)$ is the predicted concentration for individual i at time t . The joint model is implemented in the model file `PKrtteWeibull1_model.txt`

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, gamma, beta}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
if t<0.1
  haz = 0
else
  haz = gamma*Cc*(t^(beta-1))
end

DEFINITION:
Hemorrhaging = {type=event, hazard=haz}

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Hemorrhaging}

```

See Time-to-event data model for more details about time-to-event data models.

3.7.7 Typical extensions of structural models

The following pages describe typical extensions of structural model:

- [Joint model for continuous outcomes](#)
- [Mixture of structural models](#)

- [Using regressors](#)
- **Time varying parameters**
 - Time-varying clearance
 - Auto-induction model
 - Enterohepatic circulation model
- [Using a scale factor](#)
- [Delayed differential equations](#)
- **Additional model outputs**
 - [Outputs and tables](#)
 - Computing additional model outputs such as Cmax or AUC
 - [Calculating the half-life](#)

3.7.7.1 Joint model for continuous outcomes

Objectives: learn how to implement a joint model for continuous PKPD data.

Demos: warfarinPK_project, warfarin_PKPDimmediate_project, warfarin_PKPDeffect_project,
warfarin_PKPDturnover_project, warfarin_PKPDseq1_project, warfarin_PKPDseq2_project,
warfarinPD_project

3.7.7.1.1 Introduction

A “joint model” describes two or more types of observation that typically depend on each other. A PKPD model is a “joint model” because the PD depends on the PK. Here we demonstrate how several observations can be modeled simultaneously. We also discuss the special case of sequential PK and PD modelling, using either the population PK parameters or the individual PK parameters as an input for the PD model.

3.7.7.1.2 Fitting first a PK model to the PK data

- **warfarinPK_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

The column `DV` of the data file contains both the PK and the PD measurements: in Monolix this column is tagged as an `OBSERVATION` column. The column `DVID` is a flag defining the type of observation: `DVID=1` for PK data and `DVID=2` for PD data: the keyword `OBSERVATION ID` is then used for this column.

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION		CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE
			OBS ID: 1	CONTINUOUS			
id	time	amt	dv	dvid	wt	sex	age
1	0	100	.	1	66.7	1	50
1	0	.	100	2	66.7	1	50
1	24	.	9.2	1	66.7	1	50
1	24	.	49	2	66.7	1	50
1	36	.	8.5	1	66.7	1	50
1	36	.	32	2	66.7	1	50
1	48	.	6.4	1	66.7	1	50
1	48	.	26	2	66.7	1	50
1	72	.	4.8	1	66.7	1	50
1	72	.	22	2	66.7	1	50

We will use the model oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl from the Monolix PK library.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

Only the predicted concentration `Cc` is defined as an output of this model. Then, this prediction will be automatically associated to the outcome of type 1 (`DVID=1`) while the other observations (`DVID=2`) will be ignored.

i Any other ordered values could be used for `OBSERVATION ID` column: the smallest one will always be associated to the first prediction defined in the model.

3.7.7.1.3 Simultaneous PKPD modeling

- **warfarin_PKPDimmediate_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'immediateResponse_model.txt')

It is also possible for the user to write his own PKPD model. The same PK model used previously and an immediate response model are defined in the model file `immediateResponse_model.txt`

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, Imax, IC50, S0}
```

```
EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl)
E = S0 * (1 - Imax*Cc/(Cc+IC50))
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, E}
```

Two predictions are now defined in the model: `Cc` for the PK (`DVID=1`) and `E` for the PD (`DVID=2`).

- **warfarin_PKPDeffect_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'effectCompartment_model.txt')

An effect compartment is defined in the model file `effectCompartment_model.txt`

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, ke0, Imax, IC50, S0}
```

```
EQUATION:
{Cc, Ce} = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl, ke0)
E = S0 * (1 - Imax*Ce/(Ce+IC50))
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, E}
```

`Ce` is the concentration in the effect compartment

- **warfarin_PKPDturnover_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'turnover1_model.txt')

An indirect response (turnover) model is defined in the model file `turnover1_model.txt`

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, Imax, IC50, Rin, kout}
```

```
EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl)
E_0 = Rin/kout
ddt_E = Rin*(1-Imax*Cc/(Cc+IC50)) - kout*E
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, E}
```

3.7.7.1.4 Sequential PKPD modelling

In the sequential approach, a PK model is developed and parameters are estimated in the first step. For a given PD model, different strategies are then possible for the second step, i.e., for estimating the population PD parameters:

3.7.7.1.4.1 Using estimated population PK parameters

- **warfarin_PKPDseq1_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'turnover1_model.txt')

Population PK parameters are set to their estimated values but individual PK parameters are not assumed to be known and sampled from their conditional distributions at each SAEM iteration. In Monolix, this simply means changing the status of the population PK parameter values so that they are no longer used as initial estimates for SAEM but considered fixed as on the figure below.

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS		lw70
Tlag	Tlag _{pop}	0.828		ω _{Tlag}	0.5194	
ka	ka _{pop}	0.589		ω _{ka}	0.9538	
V	V _{pop}	8.341		ω _V	0.1368	β _{V, lw70} 0.8966
Cl	Cl _{pop}	0.139		ω _{Cl}	0.2641	β _{Cl, lw70} 0.6015
RO	RO _{pop}	100.1		ω _{RO}	1	
kout	kout _{pop}	0.0557		ω _{kout}	1	
lmax	lmax _{pop}	0.999		ω _{lmax}	1	
IC50	IC50 _{pop}	1.04		ω _{IC50}	1	

Residual error parameters ▾

y1	a1	0.2384		b1	0.05261	c1	1
y2	a2	1					

To fix parameters, click on the options button and choose the Fixed method as on the figure below:

The joint PKPD model defined in `turnover1_model.txt` is again used with this project.

3.7.7.1.4.2 Using estimated individual PK parameters

- **warfarin_PKPDseq2_project** (data = 'warfarinSeq_data.txt', model = 'turnoverSeq_model.txt')

In this case, individual PK parameters are set to their estimated values and used as constants in the PKPD model to fit the PD data. To do so, the individual PK parameters need to be added to the PD dataset (or PK/PD dataset) and tagged as regressors.

The PK project (that was executed before and through which the estimated PK parameters were obtained) contains in the result folder the individual parameter values `..\warfarin_PKPDseq1_project\IndividualParameters\estimatedIndividualParameters.txt`. These estimated PK parameters can be added to the PD dataset by using the data formatting tool integrated in Monolix version 2023R1. Depending which tasks have been run in the PK project, the individual parameters corresponding to the conditional mode (EBEs, with `"_mode"`), the conditional mean (mean of the samples from the conditional distributions, with `"_mean"`) and an approximation of the conditional mean obtained at the end of the SAEM step (with `"_SAEM"`) are available in the file. All columns are added to the PD dataset.

At the data tagging step, the user can choose which individual parameters to use. The most common is to use the EBEs so to tag the columns with “_mode” as regressor and leave the others as IGNORE (purple frame below). By activating the toggle button (green frame), the ignored columns flagged with the keyword IGNORE can be hidden.

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	OBSERVATION ID	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	REGLAG	KA	V	CL	AMOUNT	CENSORING
1				WT	Sex	Age	Tag_mode	ka_mode	V_mode	Cl_mode		
1	0			66.7	1	50	0.880987	1.29278	7.67925	0.111763	100	
1	0	100	2	66.7	1	50	0.880987	1.29278	7.67925	0.111763		notCensored
1	24	9.2	1	66.7	1	50	0.880987	1.29278	7.67925	0.111763		notCensored
1	24	49	2	66.7	1	50	0.880987	1.29278	7.67925	0.111763		notCensored

We use the same turnover model for the PD data. Here, the PK parameters are defined as regression variables (i.e. regressors).

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Imax, IC50, Rin, kout, Tlag, ka, V, Cl}
Tlag = {use = regressor}
ka = {use = regressor}
V = {use = regressor}
Cl = {use = regressor}
```

```
EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag,ka,V,Cl)
E_0 = Rin/kout
ddt_E= Rin*(1-Imax*Cc/(Cc+IC50)) - kout*E
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {E}
```

As you can see, the names of the regressors do not match the parameter names. **The regressors are matched by order (not by name) between the data set and the model input statement.**

If there are multiple observation types in the data as well as different response vectors in the output statement of the structural model, then these must be mapped accordingly in the mapping panel.

3.7.7.1.5 Fitting a PKPD model to the PD data only

- **warfarinPD_project** (data = 'warfarinPD_data.txt', model = 'turnoverPD_model.txt')

In this example, only PD data is available. Nevertheless, a PKPD model – where only the effect is defined as a prediction – can be used for fitting this data and thus defined in the OUTPUT section.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl, Imax, IC50, Rin, kout}

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl)
E_0 = Rin/kout
ddt_E = Rin*(1-Imax*Cc/(Cc+IC50)) - kout*E

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
```

3.7.7.1.6 Case studies

- **8.case_studies/PKVK_project** (data = 'PKVK_data.txt', model = 'PKVK_model.txt')

- **8.case_studies/hiv_project** (data = 'hiv_data.txt', model = 'hivLatent_model.txt')

3.7.7.2 Mixture of structural models

Objectives: learn how to implement between subject mixture models (BSMM) and within subject mixture models (WSMM).

Demos: bsmm1_project, bsmm2_project, wsmm_project

3.7.7.2.1 Introduction

There are two approaches to define a mixture of models:

- defining a **mixture of structural models** (via a regressor or via the bsmm function). This approach is detailed here.
- introducing a **categorical covariate** (known or latent). → click here to go to the page dedicated to this approach.

Several types of mixture models exist, they are useful in the context of mixed effects models. It may be necessary in some situations to introduce diversity into the structural models themselves:

- *Between-subject model mixtures (BSMM)* assume that there exists subpopulations of individuals. Different structural models describe the response of each subpopulation, and each subject belongs to one of these subpopulations. One can imagine for example different structural models for responders, nonresponders and partial responders to a given treatment.

The easiest way to model a finite mixture model is to introduce a label sequence $(z_i; 1 \leq i \leq N)$ that takes its values in $1, 2, \dots, M$ such that $z_i = m$ if subject i belongs to subpopulation m . $\mathbb{P}(z_i = m)$ is the probability for subject i to belong to subpopulation m . A BSMM assumes that the structural model is a mixture of M different structural models:

$$f(t_{ij}; \psi_i, z_i) = \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbf{1}_{z_i=m} f_m(t_{ij}; \psi_i)$$

In other word, each subpopulation has its own structural model: f_m is the structural model for subpopulation m .

- *Within-subject model mixtures (WSMM)* assume that there exist subpopulations (of cells, viruses, etc.) within each patient. In this case, different structural models can be used to describe the response of different subpopulations, but the proportion of each subpopulation depends on the patient.

Then, it makes sense to consider that the mixture of models happens *within* each individual. Such within-subject model mixtures require additional vectors of individual parameters $\pi_i = (\pi_{1,i}, \dots, \pi_{M,i})$ representing the proportions of the M models within each individual i :

$$f(t_{ij}; \psi_i, z_i) = \sum_{m=1}^M \pi_{m,i} f_m(t_{ij}; \psi_i)$$

The proportions ($\pi_{m,i}$) are now individual parameters in the model and the problem is transformed into a standard mixed effects model. These proportions are assumed to be positive and to sum to 1 for each patient.

3.7.7.2.2 Between subject mixture models

3.7.7.2.2.1 Supervised learning

- **bsmm1_project** (data = 'pdmixt1_data.txt', model = 'bsmm1_model.txt')

We consider a very simple example here with two subpopulations of individuals who receive a given treatment. The outcome of interest is the measured effect of the treatment (a viral load for instance). The two populations are non responders and responders. We assume here that the status of the patient is known. Then, the data file contains an additional column `GROUP`. This column is duplicated because Monolix uses it

1. as a regression variable (`REGRESSOR`): it is used in the model to distinguish responders and non responders,
2. as a categorical covariate (`CATEGORICAL COVARIATE`): it is used to stratify the diagnosis plots.

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS	AMOUNT	REGRESSOR	CATEGORICAL COV
ID	TIME	DV	AMT	GROUP_reg	GROUP_cat	
1	0	.	10000	2	2	
1	0.25	487.7125	.	2	2	
1	0.5	484.5521	.	2	2	
1	0.75	446.2827	.	2	2	
1	1	473.1457	.	2	2	
1	1.5	455.0252	.	2	2	
1	2	395.9784	.	2	2	
1	2.5	482.3503	.	2	2	
1	3	409.94	.	2	2	
1	4	345.0217	.	2	2	

We can then display the data

and use the categorical covariate GROUP_CAT to split the plot into responders and non responders:

We use different structural models for non responders and responders. The predicted effect for non responders is constant $f(t) = A1$ while the predicted effect for responders decreases exponentially $f(t) = A2 \cdot \exp(-kt)$.

The model is implemented in the model file `bsmm1_model.txt` (note that the names of the regression variable in the data file and in the model script do not need to match):

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {A1, A2, k, g}
g = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
if g==1
    f = A1
else
    f = A2*exp(-k*max(t,0))
end

OUTPUT:
```

```
output = f
```

The plot of individual fits exhibit the two different structural models:

VPCs should then be splitted according to the GROUP_CAT

as well as the prediction distribution for non responders and responders:

3.7.7.2.2 Unsupervised learning

- **bsmm2_project** (data = 'pdmixt2_data.txt', model = 'bsmm2_model.txt')

The status of the patient is unknown in this project (which means that the column `GROUP` is not available anymore). Let p be the proportion of non responders in the population. Then, the structural model for a given subject is $f1$ with probability p and $f2$ with probability $1-p$. The structural model is therefore a *BSMM*:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {A1, A2, k, p}

EQUATION:
f1 = A1
f2 = A2*exp(-k*max(t,0))
f = bsmm(f1, p, f2, 1-p)

OUTPUT:
output = f
    
```

 The bsmm function must be used on the last line of the structural model, just before “OUTPUT:”. It is not possible to reuse the variable returned by the bsmm function (here f) in another equation.

p is a population parameter of the model to estimate. There is no inter-patient variability on p: all the subjects have the same probability of being a non responder in this example. We use a logit-normal distribution for p in order to constrain it to be between 0 and 1, but without variability:

Individual model

FORMULA

```

log(A1) = log(A1_pop) + eta_A1
log(A2) = log(A2_pop) + eta_A2
log(k) = log(k_pop) + eta_k
logit(p) = logit(p_pop)
    
```

Correlations
ID : {A2, k}

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	- CORRELATION +
A1	LOGNORMAL ▾	Select: All None <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	#1 <input type="checkbox"/>
A2	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
k	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
p	LOGITNORMAL ▾	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

p is estimated with the other population parameters:

STOCH. APPROX.

	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
A1_pop	310	5.75	1.85
A2_pop	398	9.29	2.33
k_pop	0.0237	0.00245	10.3
p_pop	0.391	0.0645	16.5
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_A1	0.0876	0.0151	17.3
omega_A2	0.14	0.0182	13
omega_k	0.598	0.0897	15
Correlations			
corr_k_A2	0.75	0.0786	10.5
Error Model Parameters			
a	29.8	0.66	2.21

Then, the group to which a patient belongs is also estimated as the group of highest conditional probability:

$$\hat{z}_i = 1 \quad \text{if} \quad \mathbb{P}(z_i = 1 | (y_{ij}), \hat{\psi}_i, \hat{\theta}) > \mathbb{P}(z_i = 2 | (y_{ij}), \hat{\psi}_i, \hat{\theta}),$$

$$= 0 \quad \text{otherwise}$$

The estimated groups can be used as a stratifying variable to split some plots such as VPCs.

Bsmm function with ODEs

The bsmm function can also be used with models defined via ODE systems. The syntax in that case follows this example, with model M defined as a mixture of M1 and M2:

```

M1_0 = ... ; initial condition for M1
ddt_M1 = ... ; ODE for M1
M2_0 = ... ; initial condition for M2
ddt_M2 = ... ; ODE for M2

M = bsmm(M1,p1,M2,1-p1)
    
```

Unsupervised learning with latent covariates

If the models composing the mixture have a similar structure, it is sometimes possible and easier to implement the mixture with a latent categorical covariate instead of the `bsmm` function. It also has the advantage of allowing more than two mixture groups, while the `bsmm` function can only define two mixture groups.

3.7.7.2.3 Within subject mixture models

- **wsmm_project** (data = 'pdmixt2_data.txt', model = 'wsmm_model.txt')

It may be too simplistic to assume that each individual is represented by only one well-defined model from the mixture. We consider here that the mixture of models happens within each individual and use a *WSMM*: $f = p \cdot f_1 + (1-p) \cdot f_2$

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {A1, A2, k, p}

EQUATION:
f1 = A1
f2 = A2*exp(-k*max(t,0))
f = wsmm(f1, p, f2, 1-p)

OUTPUT:
output = f
```

Remark: Here, writing $f = \text{wsmm}(f_1, p, f_2, 1-p)$ is equivalent to writing $f = p \cdot f_1 + (1-p) \cdot f_2$

Important: Here, **p** is an individual parameter: the subjects have different proportions of non responder cells. We use a probit-normal distribution for **p** in order to constrain it to be between 0 and 1, with variability:

Individual model				MIXTURE
PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	
		Select All None		
A1	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	f1 <input type="checkbox"/>	
A2	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
k	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
p	PROBITNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

There is no latent covariate when using *WSMM*: mixtures are *continuous mixtures*. We therefore cannot split anymore the VPC and the prediction distribution anymore.

3.7.7.3 Using regressors

Objectives: learn how to define and use regression variables (time varying covariates).

Demos: reg1_project, reg2_project

3.7.7.3.1 Introduction

A regression variable is a variable x which is a given function of time, which is not defined in the model but which is used in the model. x is only defined at some time points t_1, t_2, \dots, t_m (possibly different from the observation time points), but x is a function of time that should be defined for any t (if is used in an ODE for instance, or if a prediction is computed on a fine grid). Then, Mlxtran defines the function x by interpolating the given values (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) . In the current version of Mlxtran, interpolation is performed by using the last given value:

$$x(t) = x_j \quad \text{for } t_j \leq t < t_{j+1}$$

Or linearly:

$$x(t) = x_j + (t - t_j) \frac{x_{j+1} - x_j}{t_{j+1} - t_j} \quad \text{for } t_j \leq t < t_{j+1}$$

3.7.7.3.2 Regressor definition in a data set

It is possible to have in a data set one or several columns with column-type **REGRESSOR**. Within a given subject-occasion, string "." will be interpolated (last value carried forward interpolation is used) for

observation and dose-lines. Lines with no observation and no dose but with regressor values are also taken into account by Monolix for regressor interpolation.

Several points have to be noticed:

- The name of the regressor in the data set and the name of the regressor used in the longitudinal model do not need to be identical.
- If there are several regressors, the mapping will be done by order of definition.
- Regressors can only be used in the longitudinal model.

3.7.7.3.3 Continuous regression variables

- **reg1_project** (data = reg1_data.txt , model=reg1_model.txt)

We consider a basic PD model in this example, where some concentration values are used as a regression variable. The data set is defined as follows

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS	REGRESSOR
id	time	y2		y1
1	0.5	42.8		3.22
1	1	42.96		5.15
1	2	54.96		6.52
1	3	47.65		6.85
1	5	39.29		5.5
1	7	40.25		4.75
1	9	39.64		3.94
1	12	24.43		2.73
1	15	28.36		2.08
1	18	32.29		1.49

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Emax, EC50, Cc}
Cc     = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
E = Emax*Cc/(EC50 + Cc)

OUTPUT:
output = E
```

As explained in the previous subsection, there is no name correspondance between the regressor in the data set and the regressor in the model file. Thus, in that case, the values of Cc with respect to time

will be taken from the y1 column.

In addition, in that case, the predicted effect is therefore piece wise constant because

- the regressor interpolation is performed by using the last given value, and then Cc is piece wise constant.
- The effect model is direct with respect to the concentration.

Thus, it changes at the time points where concentration values are provided:

3.7.7.3.4 Categorical regression variables

- **reg2_project** (data = reg2_data.txt , model=reg2_model.txt)

The variable z_{ij} takes its values in $\{1, 2\}$ in this example and represents the state of individual i at time t_{ij} . We then assume that the observed data y_{ij} has a Poisson distribution with parameter lambda1 if $z_{ij} = 1$ and parameter lambda2 if $z_{ij} = 2$. z is known in this example: it is then defined as a regression variable in the model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {lambda1, lambda2, z}
```

```
z = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
if z==0
  lambda=lambda1
else
  lambda=lambda2
end

DEFINITION:
y = {type=count,
     log(P(y=k)) = -lambda + k*log(lambda) - factln(k)
}

OUTPUT:
output = y
```

3.7.7.4 Time-varying clearance

Related resources:

- [Using the depot macro](#)
- [Writing a model with ODEs](#)

When treatments span over a long time with numerous repeated doses, the clearance can be observed to change over time, for instance due to a change in the disease status. One possible approach to handle this case is to define in a parametric way how the clearance changes over time. A common assumption is to use an I_{max} or E_{max} model. Below, we show how to implement such a model in the Mlxtran language.

Examples of time-varying clearances are for instance presented for PEGylated Asparaginase, and for mycophenolic acid [here](#)

Würthwein et al. Population Pharmacokinetics to Model the Time-Varying Clearance of the PEGylated Asparaginase Oncaspar® in Children with Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia. *Eur J Drug Metab Pharmacokinet* (2017). doi:10.1007/s13318-017-0410-5 .

van Hest et al. (2007). Time-dependent clearance of mycophenolic acid in renal transplant recipients. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. Volume 63, Issue 6, June 2007.

3.7.7.4.1 Mlxtran structural model

In the example below, we assume that the clearance is decreasing over time, with a sigmoidal shape. We consider a one-compartment model with first-order absorption. The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Clini, Imax, gamma, T50}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, ka)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

Clapp = Clini * (1 - Imax * t^gamma / (t^gamma + T50^gamma))
ddt_Ac = - Clapp/V * Ac
Cc = Ac/V

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

The `Clini` parameter described the initial clearance, `Imax` the maximal reduction of clearance, `T50` the time at which the clearance is reduced by half of the maximal reduction, and `gamma` characterizes the sigmoidal shape.

The apparent clearance `Clapp` is defined via an analytical formula depending on the time `t` and is then used in the ODE system. The first-order absorption is directly defined using the `depot` macro, which here indicates that the doses of the data set must be applied to the target `Ac` via a first-order absorption with rate `ka` (`ka` is a reserved keyword).

3.7.7.5 Auto-induction model

Auto-induction models have been proposed when **the drug stimulates its own metabolism, usually via induction of the metabolic enzyme expression**. Auto-induction models have for instance been used to describe the pharmacokinetics of Rifampin in Smythe et al. (2012), and of cyclophosphamide in Hassan et al. (1999).

The typical auto-induction model explicitly describes the enzyme level which is modeled using an turnover model with the drug inhibiting the enzyme degradation rate or increasing the enzyme production rate. The enzyme level is then taken into account in the apparent clearance for the drug.

The typical equations read:

$$\frac{dAc}{dt} = In(t) - Cl/V \times Enz \times Ac$$

$$\frac{dEnz}{dt} = K_{enz,in} - K_{enz,out} \left(1 - \frac{Cc}{Cc+IC50}\right) \times Enz$$

With $In(t)$ the drug input rate. To avoid unidentifiability issues (i.e the product $Cl \times Enz_0$ is identifiable, but not Cl and Enz_0 separately), the steady-state enzyme level is enforced to 1 which leads to $K_{enz,in} = K_{enz,out}$. It is usually not necessary to introduce an I_{max} parameter.

3.7.7.5.1 Mlxtran code

For a zero-order absorption, the model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Tk0, V, Cl, Kenz, IC50}

PK:
depot(target=Ac, Tk0)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
Enz_0 = 1

Cc = Ac/V

ddt_Ac = - Cl/V*Ac*Enz
ddt_Enz = Kenz - Kenz * (1- Cc/(Cc+IC50)) * Enz

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

3.7.7.6 Enterohepatic circulation model

Enterohepatic circulation (EHC) occurs when drugs circulate from the liver to the bile in the gallbladder, followed by entry into the gut when the bile is released from the gallbladder, and reabsorption from the gut back to the systemic circulation. The presence of EHC results in longer apparent drug half-lives and the appearance of multiple secondary peaks. Various pharmacokinetic models have been used in the literature to describe EHC concentration-time data.

The reference below provides a basic review of the EHC process and modeling strategies implemented to represent EHC.

Okour, M., & Brundage, R. C. (2017). Modeling Enterohepatic Circulation. *Current Pharmacology Reports*, 3(5), 301–313. doi: 10.1007/s40495-017-0096-z/

3.7.7.6.1 Mlxtran structural model

We present two examples of EHC models, based on a two-compartments model with iv bolus administration. Both models have been implemented with PK macros.

3.7.7.6.1.1 Example with switch function

In the first example, the gallbladder emptying is modeled with a switch function: the emptying rate constant follows a simple piece-wise function, implemented with if/else statements. Hence, gallbladder emptying occurs within time windows, where the rate constant outside these windows is assumed to be zero.

The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
```

```
input = {V, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, Tfirst, Tsecond}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2
duration=1
if t>Tfirst & t<Tfirst+duration
kemptying = kempt
elseif t>Tsecond & t<Tsecond+duration
kemptying = kempt
else
kemptying = 0
end

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
transfer(from=3, to=4, kt=kemptying)
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

The parameters `kbile`, `kempt` and `ka_gut` describe respectively the transfer rate between the central compartment and the bile, between the bile and the gut, and between the gut and the central compartment.

The parameter `kemptying` is the rate constant controlling the gallbladder emptying process, and its value changes with time as displayed below:

Here two windows of duration `duration=1` have been defined starting at times `Tfirst` and `Tsecond`. It is of course possible to extend this model with additional emptying windows, if more than two secondary peaks are noticeable in the data, and to change the value of the parameter `duration`.

3.7.7.6.1.2 Example with sine function

In the second example, gallbladder emptying is modeled with a sine function, assumed to equal zero outside the gallbladder emptying times. This model accounts for multiple cycles of gallbladder emptying.

The Mlxtran code for the structural model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, phase, period}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2

kemptying = max(0, kempt * (cos(2*3.14*(t+phase)/period)))

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
iv(adm=1, cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
transfer(from=3, to=1, kt=kemptying)
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)
```

```
OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

This model assumes fixed intervals between gallbladder release times, with the parameter `period` defining their frequency. The parameter `phase` represents the time of the beginning of the first gallbladder release. The value of the parameter `kemptying` over time is then:

Variation with oral administration

If the drug administration is oral instead of a bolus, the model can be adapted by replacing the macro `iv(adm=1, cmt=1)` with `absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)`, which defines a first-order absorption with a rate `ka`. While `ka` represents the absorption of the drug, `ka_gut` represents its reabsorption after storage in the gallbladder. These two physiological processes are not strictly equivalent, as the bile stored in the gallbladder is released into the duodenum. Depending on the drug, `ka` and `ka_gut` can be set as separate or identical rate constants.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, ka, Cl, Q, V2, kbile, kempt, ka_gut, phase, period}

PK:
k=Cl/V
k12=Q/V
k21=Q/V2

kemptying = max(0, kempt * (cos(2*3.14*(t+phase)/period)))

compartment(cmt=1, volume=V, concentration=Cc)
absorption(adm=1, cmt=1, ka)
elimination(cmt=1, k)
peripheral(k12, k21)
compartment(cmt=3)
compartment(cmt=4)
transfer(from=1, to=3, kt=kbile)
```

```
transfer(from=3, to=1, kt=kemptying)
transfer(from=4, to=1, kt=ka_gut)
```

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}

3.7.7.7 Using a scale factor

By default the models from the library do not include a scale factor. Units of the estimated parameters will depend on the units of the data set. For instance:

- Concentration in mg/L, amount in mg, time in hours => volumes are in L and clearances in L/h
- Concentration in ng/mL, amount in mg, time in minutes => volume are in 10^3 L and clearances in 10^3 L/min

The files from the library can easily be modified to include a scale factor:

Step 1: load a model from the library.

Step 2: in the “Structural model” tab, click “Edit model”.

Step 3: add a scaling of the concentration. If the dose is in mg and I want the volume in L, then the concentration Cc will be in mg/L. If my observations in the data set are in ng/mL (i.e. $\mu\text{g/L}$), I need to multiply Cc by 1000 (green highlight). Do not forget to output the scaled concentration instead of the original one (pink highlight).

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. On the left, the 'Model file' editor displays the following code:

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption (rate constant ka).
3 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear elimination (clearance Cl).
4
5 [LONGITUDINAL]
6 input = {ka, V, Cl}
7
8 PK:
9 ; PK model definition
10 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
11
12 Cc_scaled = Cc*1000
13
14 OUTPUT:
15 output = {Cc_scaled}
16
  
```

On the right, the 'Mapping' diagram shows a mapping between 'Data (Observation ID)' and 'Model'. A blue circle labeled 'CONC' is connected to a blue circle labeled 'CONC Cc'.

Step 4: save the file under a new name.

Be careful, in versions prior to 2023R1, it is possible to overwrite the library model files when saving edited model files.

Step 5: load the saved model file.

3.7.7.8 Delay differential equations

Objectives: learn how to implement a model with ordinary differential equations (ODE) and delay differential equations (DDE).

Demos: tgi_project, seir_project

3.7.7.8.1 Ordinary differential equations based model

- **tgi_project** (data = tgi_data.txt , model = tgi_model.txt)

Here, we consider the tumor growth inhibition (TGI) model proposed by Ribba *et al.* (Ribba, B., Kaloshi, G., Peyre, M., Ricard, D., Calvez, V., Tod, M., & Ducray, F., *A tumor growth inhibition model for low-grade glioma treated with chemotherapy or radiotherapy*. Clinical Cancer Research, 18(18), 5071-5080, 2012.). This model is defined by a set of ordinary differential equations

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dC}{dt} &= -k_{de}C(t) \\ \frac{dP_T}{dt} &= \lambda P_T(t)(1 - P^*(t)/K) + k_{QPP}Q_P(t) - k_{PQ}P_T(t) - \gamma k_{de}P_T(t)C(t) \\ \frac{dQ_T}{dt} &= k_{PK}P_T(t) - \gamma k_{de}Q_T(t)C(t) \\ \frac{dQ_P}{dt} &= \gamma k_{de}Q_T(t)C(t) - k_{QPP}Q_P(t) - \delta_{QP}Q_P(t)\end{aligned}$$

where $P^*(t) = P_T(t) + Q_T(t) + Q_P(t)$ is the total tumor size. This set of ODEs is valid for t greater than 0, while

$$\begin{aligned}C(0) &= 0 \\ P_T(0) &= P_{T0} \\ Q_T(0) &= Q_0 \\ Q_P(0) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

This model (derivatives and initial conditions) can easily be implemented with Mlxtran:

DESCRIPTION: Tumor Growth Inhibition (TGI) model proposed by Ribba et al
A tumor growth inhibition model **for** low-grade glioma treated with chemotherapy or radiotherapy.
Clinical Cancer Research, [18\(18\)](#), [5071-5080](#), [2012](#).

Variables

- PT: proliferative equiescent tissue
- QT: nonproliferative equiescent tissue
- QP: damaged quiescent cells
- C: concentration of a virtual drug encompassing the **3** chemotherapeutic components of the PCV regimen

Parameters

- K : maximal tumor size (should be fixed a priori)
- KDE : the rate constant **for** the decay of the PCV concentration in plasma
- kPQ : the rate constant **for** transition from proliferation to quiescence
- kQpP : the rate constant **for** transfer from damaged quiescent tissue to proliferative tissue
- lambdaP: the rate constant of growth **for** the proliferative tissue
- gamma : the rate of damages in proliferative and quiescent tissue
- deltaQP: the rate constant **for** elimination of the damaged quiescent tissue
- PT0 : initial proliferative equiescent tissue
- QT0 : initial nonproliferative equiescent tissue

[LONGITUDINAL]

input = {K, KDE, kPQ, kQpP, lambdaP, gamma, deltaQP, PT0, QT0}

PK:

depot(target=C)

```
EQUATION:
; Initial conditions
t0      = 0
C_0     = 0
PT_0    = PT0
QT_0    = QT0
QP_0    = 0

; Dynamical model
PSTAR   = PT + QT + QP
ddt_C   = -KDE*C
ddt_PT  = lambda*P*PT*(1-PSTAR/K) + kQpP*QP - kPQ*PT - gamma*KDE*PT*C
ddt_QT  = kPQ*PT - gamma*KDE*QT*C
ddt_QP  = gamma*KDE*QT*C - kQpP*QP - deltaQP*QP

OUTPUT:
output = PSTAR
```


`t0`, `PT_0` and `QT_0` are reserved keywords that define the initial conditions.

Then, the graphic of individual fits clearly shows that the tumor size is constant until $t=0$ and starts changing according to the model at $t=0$.

3.7.7.8.2 Don't forget the initial conditions!

- **tgiNoT0_project** (data = tgi_data.txt , model = tgiNoT0_model.txt)

The initial time t_0 is not specified in this example. Since t_0 is missing, Monolix uses the first time value encountered for each individual. If, for instance, the tumor size has not been computed before 5 for the individual fits, then $t_0=5$ will be used for defining the initial conditions for this individual, which introduces a shift in the plot:

As defined [here](#), the following rule applies

- When no starting time t_0 is defined in the Mlxtran model for Monolix then by default t_0 is selected to be equal to the first dose or the first observation, whatever comes first.
- **If t_0 is defined, a differential equation needs to be defined.**

Conclusion: don't forget to properly specify the initial conditions of a system of ODEs!

3.7.7.8.3 Delayed differential equations based model

A system of delay differential equations (DDEs) can be implemented in a block `EQUATION` of the section `[LONGITUDINAL]` of a script Mlxtran. Mlxtran provides the command `delay(x,T)` where x is a one-dimensional component and T is the explicit delay. Therefore, DDEs with a nonconstant past of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= f(x(t), x(t - T_1), x(t - T_2), \dots) \text{ for } t \geq 0 \\ x(t) &= x_0(t) \text{ for } \min(T_k) \leq t \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

can be solved. The syntax and rules are explained [here](#).

- **seir_project** (data = seir_data.txt , model = seir_model.txt)

The model is a system of 4 DDEs and defined with the following mode:

DESCRIPTION: SEIR model, using delayed differential equations.
 "An Epidemic Model with Recruitment-Death Demographics and Discrete Delays"♦, Genik & van den Driessche (1999)

Decomposition of the total population into four epidemiological classes
 S (susceptibles), E (exposed), I (infectious), and R (recovered)

The parameters corresponds to

- birthRate: the birth rate,
- deathRate: the natural death rate,
- infectionRate: the contact rate of infective individuals,
- recoveryRate: the rate of recovery,
- excessDeathRate: the excess death rate **for** infective individuals

There is a time delay in the model:

- tauImmunity: a temporary immunity delay

[LONGITUDINAL]

input = {birthRate, deathRate, infectionRate, recoveryRate, excessDeathRate, tauImmunity, tauLatency}

EQUATION:

; Initial conditions

t0 = 0

S_0 = 15

E_0 = 0

I_0 = 2

R_0 = 3

; Dynamical model

N = S + E + I + R

ddt_S = birthRate - deathRate*S - infectionRate*S*I/N +

recoveryRate*delay(I,tauImmunity)*exp(-deathRate*tauImmunity)

ddt_E = infectionRate*S*I/N - deathRate*E -

infectionRate*delay(S,tauLatency)*delay(I,tauLatency)*exp(-deathRate*tauLatency)/
 (delay(I,tauLatency)+delay(S,tauLatency)+delay(E,tauLatency)+delay(R,tauLatency))

ddt_I = -(recoveryRate+excessDeathRate+deathRate)*I +

infectionRate*delay(S,tauLatency)*delay(I,tauLatency)*exp(-deathRate*tauLatency)/
 (delay(I,tauLatency)+delay(S,tauLatency)+delay(E,tauLatency)+delay(R,tauLatency))

ddt_R = recoveryRate*I - deathRate*R - recoveryRate*delay(I,tauImmunity)*exp(-
 deathRate*tauImmunity)

OUTPUT:

output = {S, E, I, R}

Introducing these delays allows to obtain nice fits for the 4 outcomes, including (R_{ij}) (corresponding to the output y4):

3.7.7.8.4 Case studies

- **8.case_studies/arthritis_project**

3.7.7.9 Outputs and tables

Objectives: learn how to define outputs and create tables from the outputs of the model.

Demos: tgi_project, tgiWithTable_project

3.7.7.9.1 About the OUTPUT block

- **tgi_project** (data = 'tgi_data.txt' , model='tgi_model.txt')

We use the Tumor Growth Inhibition (TGI) model proposed by Ribba *et al.* in this example (Ribba, B., Kaloshi, G., Peyre, M., Ricard, D., Calvez, V., Tod, M., . & Ducray, F., *A tumor growth inhibition model for low-grade glioma treated with chemotherapy or radiotherapy*. Clinical Cancer Research, 18(18), 5071-5080, 2012.)

DESCRIPTION: Tumor Growth Inhibition (TGI) model proposed by Ribba et al
 A tumor growth inhibition model **for** low-grade glioma treated with chemotherapy or radiotherapy.
 Clinical Cancer Research, 18(18), 5071-5080, 2012.

Variables

- PT: proliferative equiescent tissue
- QT: nonproliferative equiescent tissue
- QP: damaged quiescent cells
- C: concentration of a virtual drug encompassing the 3 chemotherapeutic components of the PCV regimen

Parameters

- K : maximal tumor size (should be fixed a priori)
- KDE : the rate constant **for** the decay of the PCV concentration in plasma
- kPQ : the rate constant **for** transition from proliferation to quiescence
- kQpP : the rate constant **for** transfer from damaged quiescent tissue to proliferative tissue
- lambdaP: the rate constant of growth **for** the proliferative tissue
- gamma : the rate of damages in proliferative and quiescent tissue
- deltaQP: the rate constant **for** elimination of the damaged quiescent tissue
- PT0 : initial proliferative equiescent tissue
- QT0 : initial nonproliferative equiescent tissue

[LONGITUDINAL]

input = {K, KDE, kPQ, kQpP, lambdaP, gamma, deltaQP, PT0, QT0}

PK:

depot(target=C)

EQUATION:

; Initial conditions

t0 = 0
 C_0 = 0
 PT_0 = PT0
 QT_0 = QT0
 QP_0 = 0

; Dynamical model

PSTAR = PT + QT + QP
 ddt_C = -KDE*C
 ddt_PT = lambdaP*PT*(1-PSTAR/K) + kQpP*QP - kPQ*PT - gamma*KDE*PT*C
 ddt_QT = kPQ*PT - gamma*KDE*QT*C
 ddt_QP = gamma*KDE*QT*C - kQpP*QP - deltaQP*QP

OUTPUT:

output = PSTAR

PSTAR is the tumor size predicted by the model. It is therefore used as a prediction for the observations in the project.

At the end of the scenario or of SAEM, individual predictions of the tumor size `PSTAR` are computed using the individual parameters available. Thus, individual predictions of the tumor size `PSTAR` are computed using both the conditional modes (`indPred_mode`), the conditional mean (`indPred_mean`), and the conditional means estimated during the last iterations of SAEM (`indPred_SAEM`) and saved in the table `predictions.txt`.

Notice that the population prediction is also proposed.

```

predictions.txt - Bloc-notes
Fichier Edition Format Affichage ?
id,time,y,popPred_medianCOV,popPred,indivPred_SAEM,indivPred_mean,indivPred_mode,indivRes_SAEM,indivRes_mean,indivRes_mode
1,3.430000,51.122320,48.725695,48.725695,49.085670,49.306155,49.449744,0.788320,0.699834,0.642632
1,5.300000,49.548460,49.784364,49.784364,50.137291,50.351235,50.454281,-0.223136,-0.302918,-0.341103
1,42.130000,72.470750,69.839000,69.839000,74.388858,74.796007,74.748624,-0.489898,-0.590654,-0.578985
1,52.630000,84.962600,74.039384,74.039384,79.649049,80.090531,80.176622,1.267492,1.155774,1.134132
1,57.530000,75.042550,72.590892,72.590892,75.782580,75.865500,75.906487,-0.185533,-0.206096,-0.216244
1,63.300000,66.027410,69.263724,69.263724,70.113193,69.996769,69.881417,-1.107175,-1.077415,-1.047832
1,68.970000,67.761500,67.595943,67.595943,67.508441,67.321729,67.083365,0.071220,0.124112,0.192062
1,76.530000,68.742470,66.747311,66.747311,66.015143,65.745080,65.381584,0.784936,0.866205,0.976650
1,94.530000,66.639180,67.176863,67.176863,67.164648,66.899100,66.573207,-0.148644,-0.073818,0.018828
1,106.100000,65.711190,68.539866,68.539866,70.265168,70.234866,70.163833,-1.231379,-1.223713,-1.205717
1,116.230000,72.859610,70.138270,70.138270,73.753795,73.792882,73.985211,-0.230348,-0.240289,-0.289055
1,121.870000,82.225370,71.118847,71.118847,75.759907,76.010456,76.333726,1.621441,1.553469,1.466428
2,0.000000,49.123050,46.829058,46.829058,50.475375,50.751599,51.262269,-0.509029,-0.609666,-0.792863
2,11.070000,56.582700,53.118154,53.118154,55.831799,55.888731,57.068679,0.255530,0.235916,-0.161793
2,14.170000,57.636220,52.439983,52.439983,55.459009,55.593574,56.714543,0.745880,0.690806,0.308763
2,16.600000,51.822120,49.874785,49.874785,53.246111,53.514356,54.407701,-0.508113,-0.600802,-0.902898
2,19.330000,53.355120,47.139371,47.139371,50.600659,50.942745,51.623639,1.034240,0.899712,0.637250
2,25.130000,52.298970,43.072423,43.072423,45.918174,46.202210,46.655236,2.640165,2.507132,2.298301
2,29.270000,45.398260,41.630685,41.630685,43.778590,43.985217,44.405299,0.702919,0.610365,0.424853
2,33.400000,43.677270,40.734585,40.734585,42.289343,42.440432,42.857204,0.623557,0.553699,0.363551
2,37.430000,39.141120,40.234677,40.234677,41.413417,41.534492,41.962637,-1.042473,-1.094818,-1.277499
2,42.670000,40.675790,40.091872,40.091872,41.202391,41.323583,41.784144,-0.242829,-0.297838,-0.503974
2,48.830000,40.922430,40.646748,40.646748,42.470350,42.656541,43.177597,-0.692474,-0.772382,-0.992341
2,56.400000,48.510730,42.410907,42.410907,46.507480,46.866052,47.478819,0.818377,0.666750,0.412936
2,62.230000,56.657350,44.566857,44.566857,51.404747,51.939352,52.610986,1.941387,1.725846,1.461266
2,65.900000,52.233800,46.260372,46.260372,55.105589,55.745865,56.436641,-0.990391,-1.197236,-1.415132
2,71.370000,63.643690,49.191266,49.191266,61.102624,61.879989,62.566431,0.790127,0.541521,0.327129
3,0.000000,42.526460,46.829058,46.829058,43.479199,43.610223,44.242595,-0.416326,-0.472157,-0.736973
3,5.000000,46.051480,49.614850,49.614850,47.421771,47.415934,48.179637,-0.549004,-0.546733,-0.839230
3,10.800000,56.159840,52.960315,52.960315,51.929788,51.906878,52.704674,1.547640,1.556709,1.245548
3,17.430000,59.537890,56.838616,56.838616,56.841484,56.959959,57.654989,0.901282,0.859889,0.620485
3,23.100000,59.576360,60.108063,60.108063,60.733529,61.066671,61.586672,-0.362001,-0.463675,-0.620180
3,24.500000,64.760240,60.898211,60.898211,61.642879,62.037218,62.505970,0.960827,0.833949,0.685212
3,35.870000,69.413960,66.918753,66.918753,68.190800,69.113595,69.123576,0.338735,0.082571,0.079816
3,38.970000,62.092270,63.997889,63.997889,64.587999,64.823229,65.761000,-0.734153,-0.800434,-1.059957
3,44.830000,54.408800,56.985224,56.985224,56.675546,56.439877,57.977475,-0.759885,-0.683725,-1.169469
3,53.470000,53.160390,51.913393,51.913393,52.000027,51.882128,53.041476,0.420979,0.468104,0.042595
3,58.570000,57.047470,50.485403,50.485403,50.900267,50.823315,51.920983,2.261139,2.326796,1.875935
3,64.500000,55.272910,49.545453,49.545453,50.387580,50.238545,51.252261,1.842092,1.903919,1.490472
    
```


The same model file `tgi_model.txt` can be used with different tools, including PKanalix or Simulx.

3.7.7.9.2 Add additional outputs in tables

- `tgiWithTable_project` (`data = 'tgi_data.txt'`, `model='tgiWithTable_model.txt'`)

We can save in the tables additional variables defined in the model, such as `PT`, `Q` and `QP` for instance, by adding a block `OUTPUT:` in the model file:

```
OUTPUT:
output = PSTAR
table = {PT, QT, QP}
```

An additional file `tables.txt` now includes the predicted values of these variables for each individual (columns `PT_mean`, `QT_mean`, `QP_mean`, `PT_mode`, `QT_mode`, `QP_mode`, `PT_popPred`, `QT_popPred`, `QP_popPred`, `PT_popPred_medianCOV`, `QT_popPred_medianCOV`, `QP_popPred_medianCOV`, `PT_SAEM`, `QT_SAEM`, and `QP_SAEM`).

Notice that only continuous variable are possible for variable in table.

i It is not allowed to do calculations directly in the output or table statement. The following example is not possible:

```
; not allowed:
OUTPUT:
output = {Cser+Ccsf}
```

It has to be replaced by:

```
EQUATION:
Ctot = Cser+Ccsf
OUTPUT:
output = {Ctot}
```

3.7.7.10 Computing additional model outputs such as Cmax or AUC

Computing additional outputs such as AUC and Cmax in the structural model is possible but requires a particular syntax, because it is not possible to redefine a variable in Mlxtran. For example, it would not be possible to directly update the variable $C_{max} = C_c$ when $C_c > C_{max}$. But it is possible to compute Cmax via an ODE, where Cmax increases like Cc at each time where $C_c > C_{max}$. This page gives detailed examples for the AUC on full time interval or specific interval, Cmax, nadir, and other derived variables such as duration above a threshold.

Often the Area under the PK curve (AUC) is needed as an important PK metric to link with the pharmacodynamic effect. We show here how to:

- compute the AUC within the mlxtran model file
- output the AUC calculations for later analysis.

Calculation of the AUC can be done in the EQUATION section of the Mlxtran model. If a dataset contains the AUC observations, then the calculation in the EQUATION section can be used as an output in the `output={}` definition (matched to observations of the data set). Or it can be saved for post-treatment using `table={}`.

3.7.7.10.1 AUClast from t=0 to t=tlast

The following code is the basic implementation of the AUC for a 1-compartmental model with the absorption rate ka. It integrates the concentration profile from the start to the end of the observation period.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
Cc=pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
ddt_AUC = Cc

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {AUC}
```

3.7.7.10.2 AUC in a time interval

The following code computes the AUC between two time points t_1 and t_2 . The idea is to compute the AUC_{0,t_1} and AUC_{0,t_2} using if/else statements and then do the difference between the two.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}
PK:
depot(ka, target=Ac)

EQUATION:
odeType = stiff
useAnalyticalSolution=no

Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

t1=24
t2=48
AUCt1_0 = 0
if(t < t1)
  dAUCt1 = Cc
else
  dAUCt1 = 0
end
ddt_AUCt1 = dAUCt1

AUCt2_0 = 0
if(t < t2)
  dAUCt2 = Cc
else
  dAUCt2 = 0
end
ddt_AUCt2 = dAUCt2

AUC_t1_t2 = AUCt2 - AUCt1

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {AUC_t1_t2}
```


Note that the $t=tDose$ would not work because the integrator does not necessarily evaluate the time exactly at the times of doses. Thus the test $t=tDose$ might not be tested at all during the computation.

i Also note that, although partial AUC can be calculated by comparing time with the both boundaries in the if statement (e.g. if (t>20 and t<40)), this might not be the best practice when concentration is calculated using an analytical solution, because ODE solver used for calculating AUC could be deceived by AUC remaining 0 for a period of time and might increase the integration time step to a value larger than the difference between time boundaries.

3.7.7.10.3 Dose-interval AUC (AUCtau)

The following code compute the AUCtau for each dose interval. At each dose the AUC is reset to zero and the concentration is integrated until the next administration.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
Cc = pkmodel(ka,V,Cl)

; Reset the ODE variable AUCtau to zero each time there is a dose
empty(target=AUCtau)
```

```
EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
ddt_AUCtau = Cc

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {AUCtau}
```

Since AUCtau is equal to 0 at each dosing time as it has just been reset, the AUC in the last interdose interval should actually be read just before that time.

Here we provide a Simulx project with an example of a PK model where AUCtau is calculated as additional lines in the model and defined as an output of the simulations.

3.7.7.10.4 Computing the Cmax or nadir in the structural model

3.7.7.10.4.1 Cmax

Cmax can be calculated directly in the structural model by integrating the increase of the concentration. Alternatively, the Cmax can also be calculated in Simulx using the Outcomes and Endpoints tab.

Cmax for models with first-order absorption

The following example shows how to do it in case of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption and linear elimination. Absorption processes defined via the depot macro must be replaced by explicit ODEs, while the depot macro is used to add the dose as a bolus into the depot compartment.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cl, ka, V}

PK:
depot(target=Ad)

EQUATION:

; initial conditions
t_0 = 0
Ad_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Ad = -ka*Ad
ddt_Ac = ka*Ad - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

; Calculation of Cmax
slope = ka*Ad - k*Ac
Cmax_0 = 0
if slope > 0 && Cc > Cmax
  x = slope/V
else
  x = 0
end

ddt_Cmax = x

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Cmax}
```

Cmax for model with bolus administration or infusion

If the dose is administered as bolus, it is necessary to add in the model a very short infusion. This prevents from the instantaneous increase of the concentration. The following example shows this situations in case of a three-compartments model with linear elimination. The duration of the “short infusion” can be adapted with respect to the time scale by modifying $dT=0.1$.

If the doses are administered via iv infusion, then $dt=0.1$ can be replaced by $dt = \text{inftDose}$, which reads the infusion duration from the data.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cl, V1, Q2, V2, Q3, V3}

EQUATION:

; Parameter transformations
V  = V1
k   = Cl/V1
k12 = Q2/V1
k21 = Q2/V2
k13 = Q3/V1
k31 = Q3/V3

; initial conditions
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
A2_0 = 0
A3_0 = 0

;short pseudo-infusion duration
dT = 0.1 ; use dT=inftDose if the administration is infusion: inftDose is the
infusion duration from the last dose read from the data

; infusion input to Ac
if t < tDose+dT
  input = amtDose/dT ;amtDose is the last dose amount read from the data
else
  input = 0
end

dAc = input -k*Ac - k12*Ac - k13*Ac + k21*A2 + k31*A3
ddt_Ac = dAc
ddt_A2 = k12*Ac - k21*A2
ddt_A3 = k13*Ac - k31*A3
Cc = Ac/V

; Calculation of AUC
AUC_0 = 0
ddt_AUC = Cc

; Calculation of Cmax
Cmax_0 = 0
if dAc > 0 && Cc > Cmax
  x = dAc/V
else
  x = 0
end
```

```
ddt_Cmax = x
```

```
OUTPUT:
```

```
output = {Ac, Cc}
```

```
table = {Cmax, AUC}
```

Cmax for models with transit compartments

The transit compartments defined via the depot() macro must be replaced by explicit ODEs. The amount in the last (nth) transit compartment is described via an analytical solution using the keyword amtDose to get the dose amount and (t-tDose) to get the time elapsed since the last dose. The calculation of Cmax then follows the same logic as for a first-order absorption.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={F, Ktr, Mtt, ka, V, Cl}

EQUATION:
k = Cl/V
odeType=stiff

; transit model with explicit ODEs
n = max(0, Mtt*Ktr - 1)
An = F * amtDose * exp( n * log(Ktr*(t-tDose)) - factln(n) - Ktr * (t-tDose))

t_0 = 0
Aa_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0

ddt_Aa = Ktr*An - ka*Aa
ddt_Ac = ka*Aa - k*Ac
Cc = Ac/V

; Calculation of Cmax
slope = ka*Aa - k*Ac
Cmax_0 = 0
if slope > 0 && Cc > Cmax
  x = slope/V
else
  x = 0
end

ddt_Cmax = x

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Cmax}
```

Nadir

This example shows how to compute tumor size (variable TS) at time of nadir:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, Vl, Cl, TS0, kge, kkill, lambda}
EQUATION:

odeType=stiff
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

; ODE system for tumor growth dynamics
t_0 = 0
TS_0 = TS0
TSDynamics = (kge*TS)-kkill*TS*Cc*exp(-lambda*t)
ddt_TS = TSDynamics

; ===== computing TS at nadir
if TSDynamics < 0 && TS < TS_atNadir
  x = TSDynamics
else
  x = 0
end
TS_atNadir_0 = TS0
ddt_TS_atNadir = x

OUTPUT:
output = {TS}
table = {TS_atNadir}
```

Here is an example of simulation for TS and TS_atNadir with a multiple dose schedule:

3.7.7.10.5 Time above a threshold

Here we compute the time that a variable C spends above some threshold, which could be a toxicity threshold for example. This piece of code comes in the structural model, after the dynamics of the variable C has already been defined.

```

TimeAboveThreshold_0 = 0
if C > Cthreshold
  xTime = 1
else
  xTime = 0
end
ddt_TimeAboveThreshold = xTime
  
```

3.7.7.10.6 Time since disease progression

In this full structural model example, tumor size TS is described with an exponential growth, and a constant treatment effect since time=0 with a log-kill killing hypothesis and a Claret exponential resistance term. Several additional variables are computed:

- $TS_{atNadir}$: the tumor size at the time of nadir,
- $PC_{fromNadir}$: the percent change of TS between the time of nadir and the current time,
- DP : predicted disease progression status (1 if TS has increased more than >20% and >5-mm from last nadir, 0 otherwise),
- TDP : time since disease progression (duration since last time when DP is switched from 0 to 1)

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {TS0, kge, kkill, lambda}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff

;initial conditions:
;t_0 = 0 ;this should be uncommented if the initial time is 0 for all subjects
TS_0 = TS0

K = kkill*exp(-lambda*t)

;Saturation for TS at 1e12 to avoid infinite values
if TS>1e12
  TSDynamics = 0
else
  if t<0 ; before treatment
    TSDynamics = (kge*TS)
  else ; after treatment
    TSDynamics = (kge*TS)-K*TS
  end
end

ddt_TS = TSDynamics

; Computing time to nadir (TS decreases after treatment start at time=0, then
increases again because of resistance)
if TSDynamics<0
  x1=1
else
  x1=0
end
TimeToNadir_0=t0
ddt_TimeToNadir = x1 ; x1 is used as intermediate variable because it is not possible
to define an ODE inside an if/else statement

; Computing TS at time of nadir
if TSDynamics < 0 & TS < TS_atNadir
  x2 = TSDynamics
else
  x2 = 0
end
TS_atNadir_0 = TS0
ddt_TS_atNadir = x2 ;

; Computing DP: predicted disease progression status at the previous visit (1 if TS
has increased more than >20% and >5-mm from last nadir, 0 otherwise)
PC_from_Nadir = (TS/TS_atNadir-1)*100
if t>TimeToNadir & PC_from_Nadir > 20 & (TS-TS_atNadir) > 5
  DP = 1
else
  DP = 0
```

```

end

; Computing TDP = time since disease progression: duration since last time DP was
switched from 0 to 1
if DP==1
  x3 = 1
else
  x3 = 0
end
TDP_0 = 0
ddt_TDP = x3

OUTPUT:
output = {TS}
table = {TS_atNadir, PC_from_Nadir, DP, TDP}
  
```

Simulx can be conveniently used to simulate each intermediate variable with typical parameters (the example model and Simulx project can be downloaded [here](#)):

3.7.7.11 Calculating the half-life

The half-life is usually not part of the estimated parameters but it often needs to be reported. It presents the advantage of having units of time and being easy to understand. The terminal plasma half-life is the time required to divide the plasma concentration by two after reaching pseudo-equilibrium. It is especially relevant to multiple dosing regimens, because it controls the degree of drug accumulation and the time taken to reach equilibrium. For a more detailed overview, please refer to:

Toutain P.L, Bousquet-Melou A. Plasma terminal half-life, J. vet. Pharmacol. Therap. 27, 427-439, 2004

This documentation page explains the half-life formulas and how to modify the Monolix or Simulx models to calculate it.

3.7.7.11.1 Half-life formulas

3.7.7.11.1.1 One-compartmental model

For a drug captured by a model with one compartment and linear elimination, and without flip-flop kinetics, the half-life is calculated as:

$$T_{1/2} = \frac{\log(2)}{k} = \frac{\log(2) \times V}{Cl}$$

with k the elimination rate, Cl the clearance and V the volume of distribution. Note that $\log(2) \approx 0.632$ so you might also find the formula written with this value.

3.7.7.11.1.2 Two-compartmental model

For a drug captured by a model with one compartment and linear elimination, the half-life correspond to the slope of the second part of the curve on a log-concentration over time plot, once pseudo-equilibrium is achieved. The slope of the terminal (second) phase is usually called β , the first slope α and the intercepts A and B.

The parametrization of the 2-compartment model with (A, B, α , β) is an alternative parametrization compared to the parametrization with (k, V, k₁₂, k₂₁) or (Cl, V, Q, V₂).

It is possible to convert between these different parametrizations using the following formulas:

$$\alpha = \frac{k_{21}k}{\beta} = \frac{\frac{Q}{V_2} \frac{Cl}{V_1}}{\beta}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \left(k_{12} + k_{21} + k - \sqrt{(k_{12} + k_{21} + k)^2 - 4k_{21}k} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Q}{V_1} + \frac{Q}{V_2} + \frac{Cl}{V_1} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{Q}{V_1} + \frac{Q}{V_2} + \frac{Cl}{V_1} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{Q}{V_2} \frac{Cl}{V_1}} \right)$$

The half-life corresponds to the terminal phase and is defined as:

$$T_{1/2} = \frac{\log(2)}{\beta} = \frac{\log(2)}{0.5 (k_{12} + k_{21} + k - \sqrt{(k_{12} + k_{21} + k)^2 - 4k_{21}k})}$$

3.7.7.11.2 Implementation in Monolix

The calculation can be added to the structural model and outputted using the `table={}` statement.

Let's take the demo project theophylline as an example, which use a model from the PK library with parametrization (ka, V, Cl).

After loading the project, in the Structural model tab, click "EDIT MODEL" and add the following lines and save the file under a new name.

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl}

PK:
; PK model definition
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

Thalf = log(2)*V/Cl

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Thalf}
```

After running the project, the half-life values are displayed in the file tables.txt in the result folder.

id	time	Thalf_mean	Thalf_mode	Thalf_popPred	Thalf_popPred_medianCOV	Thalf_SAEM
1	0.25	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	0.57	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	1.12	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	2.02	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	3.82	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	5.1	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	7.03	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	9.05	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	12.12	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
1	24.37	12.2145	12.2474	7.82779	7.82779	12.0734
2	0.27	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	0.52	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	1	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	1.92	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	3.5	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	5.02	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342
2	7.03	6.9524	6.918	7.82779	7.82779	6.9342

The values will be identical on all lines corresponding to the same individuals (or occasion in case of IOV).

- Thalf_mode corresponds to the individual half-life value calculated using the EBEs.
- Thalf_popPred corresponds to the value calculated using the population parameters (and individual covariates values if covariates are used on V and Cl)

For a two-compartmental model from the PK library, the lines to add would be:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cl, V1, Q, V2}

PK:
; Parameter transformations
V = V1
k12 = Q/V1
k21 = Q/V2

; PK model definition
Cc = pkmodel(V, Cl, k12, k21)

k = Cl/V1
beta = 0.5*(k12+k21+k-sqrt((k12+k21+k)^2-4*k21*k))
Thalf = log(2)/beta

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
table = {Thalf}
```

3.7.8 Advanced models

The following pages show how to write advanced models:

3.7.8.1 Lifespan models

Lifespan based indirect response (LIDR) models have originally been proposed in the field of hematology. The population of cells are described by cell production and cell degradation. **The main assumption of LIDR models is that a cell dies when its lifespan expires.** This implies that the cell degradation rate is equal to the cell production rate delayed by the lifespan. This assumption differs from classical indirect response model where the cell (or response) degradation is proportional to the cell number (first-order process), independently of the production rate or the lifespan.

LIDR models have been reviewed in detail in:

Krzyzanski, W., & Perez Ruixo, J. J. (2012). Lifespan based indirect response models. Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics, 39(1), 109–123.

The implementation of LIDR model makes use of delayed differential equations, which can easily be solved in the MonolixSuite using the delay differential equation solver. In the following, we will consider a drug with simple exponential decay after a bolus administration and a response R, which can for instance be the number of blood cells.

3.7.8.1.1 Mlxtran code for LIDR models

3.7.8.1.1.1 LIDR model for drugs affecting the production rate of the response

In this model, **the drug affects the response via an I_{max} model on the production rate.** The equation for the response is:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t)}{IC_{50} + C(t)} \right) - k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t - T_R)}{IC_{50} + C(t - T_R)} \right)$$

where + would be used if the drug increases the production rate and - if it decreases it. Notice that the degradation rate is simply the production rate delayed by the lifespan T_R . If necessary, a sigmoidicity parameter gamma can be added to the formula. When implemented in mlxtran, $C(t - T_R)$ translates into delay(C,TR) which means that we use the value of the concentration C delayed by time T_R .

Note that the delay function makes use of the DDE solver, which is slower than the ODE solver. This video presents an alternative implementation using ODEs only, which leads to greatly shorter run times.

The mlxtran code reads (for the inhibition case):

[LONGITUDINAL]

```
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR}
```

PK:

```
depot(target=Ac)
```

EQUATION:

```
t_0 = 0
```

```
Ac_0 = 0
```

```
R_0 = kin * TR
```

```
Cc = Ac/V
```

```
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
```

```
ddt_R = kin*(1 - Imax *Cc/(Cc+IC50)) - kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TR)/(delay(Ac,TR)
+IC50*V))
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Cc, R}
```

As usual, the depot macro permits to link the doses defined in the data set to the DDEs system. In the model formulation above, it is assumed that both the drug concentration C_c and the response R are recorded in the data set. If only R is observed, the output line should be changed to `output= {R}`. Note that if the concentration C_c is not observed, it is not possible to identify both V and IC_{50} . The value of V can then be fixed. Alternatively, the K-PD model can be reformulated as in Jacqmin et al. (2007). In the delay macro, it is mandatory to use an ODE variable. We thus use Ac rather than C_c and divide by the volume V outside of the delay macro.

For a drug inhibiting the production rate, the typical response shape is the following (darker colors indicate larger drug amounts). The response start to change from baseline at time 0 and is maximal at time T_R :

If the drug would increase the production rate instead of decreasing it, the response would increase over time before recovering its basal level:

3.7.8.1.1.2 LIDR model for drugs affecting the cell lifespan distribution

This model assumes that initially the lifespan is T_R and that the drugs modifies the cell lifespan to a new value T_D . The drug effect is described by an I_{max} term, which represents the fraction of cells with lifespan T_D . The higher the drug concentration is, the more cells will switch from the baseline lifespan T_R to the new lifetime T_D .

The equation for the response is:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} - k_{in} \left(1 - I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_R)}{IC50+C(t-T_R)} \right) - k_{in} \left(I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_D)}{IC50+C(t-T_D)} \right)$$

The mlxtran code reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR, TD}

PK:
depot(target=Ac)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
R_0 = kin * TR

Cc = Ac/V
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
```

```

ddt_R = kin - kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TR)/(delay(Ac,TR)+IC50*V)) - kin*(Imax
*delay(Ac,TD)/(delay(Ac,TD)+IC50*V))
    
```

OUTPUT:

```

output = {Cc, R}
    
```

For a drug reducing the lifespan from $T_R = 30$ to $T_D = 10$ days, the typical response shape is the following (darker colors indicate larger drug amounts). The response is maximal at time $\max(T_R, T_D)$. Note that there is a delay before the response starts to change, which corresponds to $\min(T_R, T_D)$.

The possibility to have this delay requires one more parameter compared to the lifespan model for drugs affecting the production rate.

If the drug would increase the lifespan (i.e. $T_D > T_R$), the curves would be flipped over (increasing response):

3.7.8.1.1.3 LIDR model with a precursor pool

In this model we assume that **the drug effects a precursor pool, which matures into the main pool represented by the response R**. Interestingly, it is not necessary to solve the equation for the precursor, only the equation for the response R is needed:

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_P)}{IC50+C(t-T_P)} \right) - k_{in} \left(1 \pm I_{max} \frac{C(t-T_P-T_R)}{IC50+C(t-T_P-T_R)} \right)$$

where + is used if the drug increases the precursor production rate and - if it decreases it. T_R represents the lifespan of the main cells (response) and T_P the lifespan of the precursor.

The mlxtran code reads:

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input={V, k, kin, Imax, IC50, TR, TP}

PK:
depot(target=Ac)

EQUATION:
t_0 = 0
Ac_0 = 0
R_0 = kin * TR

Cc = Ac/V
ddt_Ac = -k*Ac
ddt_R = kin*(1 - Imax *delay(Ac,TP)/(delay(Ac,TP)+IC50*V)) - kin*(1 - Imax
*delay(Ac,TP+TR)/(delay(Ac,TP+TR)+IC50*V))

OUTPUT:
output= {Cc, R}
    
```

The typical response-time curve is displayed below for the case where the drug inhibits the precursor production. The response start to change at time T_P and the change is maximal at time $T_P + T_R$.

If the drug increases the precursor production, we obtain:

Exploration of indirect model and LIDR model differences with Mlxplore

We explore the differences between:

- the LIDR model
- the indirect response model

In both models, we assume that the drug inhibits the response production rate. Yet, in the LIDR model, the response degradation rate is equal to the production rate delayed by the lifespan. On the opposite, in the indirect response model, the response degradation rate is proportional to the response magnitude.

3.7.8.2 K-PD models

Usual PK-PD models describe the relationships between dose regimens, drug concentration and effect (or response). They are applied when both the drug concentration and the effect can be measured. However situations exist where the concentration PK data is not available. This may for instance be the case for phase III clinical trials or pediatric studies. **In this case K-PD models can be used: the drug concentration-effect relationship model is kept, but the (unobserved) PK profile is assumed to have a simple shape.** In comparison to dose-response studies which directly link the (constant) dose to the PD response, K-PD models permit to capture PD profile that varies over time as a consequence of the underlying time-varying PK profile.

Although not being the first published example of K-PD model, the usual reference is:

Jacqmin, P., Snoeck, E., Schaick, E. A. Van, Gieschke, R., Pillai, P., Steimer, J., & Girard, P. (2007). Modelling Response Time Profiles in the Absence of Drug Concentrations : Definition and Performance Evaluation of the K-PD Model. *Journal of Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics*, 34(1).

3.7.8.2.1 Mixtran code for K-PD models

The effect of the drug on the response can be as diverse as presented in the indirect response models and direct response models examples. **We here focus on the case of an indirect response where the drug decreases the response production rate.**

3.7.8.2.1.1 Formulation by Jacqmin et al.

The authors in Jacqmin et al. describe the model in the following way: "A virtual compartment representing the biophase in which the concentration is in equilibrium with the observed effect is used to extract the (pharmaco)kinetic component from the pharmacodynamic data alone. Parameters of this model are the elimination rate constant from the virtual compartment (KDE), which describes the equilibrium between the rate of dose administration and the observed effect, and the second parameter, named EDK50 which is the apparent in vivo potency of the drug at steady state.

The equations read:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ IR &= KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{IR}{EDK_{50} + IR} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

with A the drug amount, R the response, KDE the drug elimination rate, Ks the response synthesis rate, Kd the response disappearance rate constant. EDK50 represents the potency of the drug and also corresponds to EDK50 constant corresponds to the product of the EC50 and the clearance.

The corresponding Mixtran code is:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,EDK50}

PK:
depot(target=A)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
A_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_A = - KDE*A
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - (KDE*A)/(EDK50 + (KDE*A))) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}
```

Note that the only output is the response R , as only the response has been measured and recorded in the data set.

3.7.8.2.1.2 Alternative formulation

For some applications, the interpretation of the parameters of the Jacqmin model may be difficult. It is also unusual to consider that it is the rate at which the drug disappears (IR) that drives the effect on the response. **We thus propose an alternative formulation of the same model.**

We start by writing the model using the usual (and physiologically relevant) effect of the drug concentration on the response:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ C_A &= \frac{A}{V_A} \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{C_A}{IC_{50} + C_A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

This set of equations can be rewritten into:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{A}{IC_{50} \times V_A + A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

using the fact that $C_A = \frac{A}{V_A}$. When the drug concentration is observed, it is possible to identify both V_A and IC_{50} separately because V_A influences the observed drug concentration. However when the drug concentration is not measured, it is not possible to identify both V_A and IC_{50} , but only the product of the two. The unidentifiability of the volume of distribution is explored visually and interactively in the next section.

We thus introduce $A_{50} = IC_{50} \times V_A$ and write our final model as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dA}{dt} &= -KDE \times A \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= K_s \left(1 - \frac{A}{A_{50} + A} \right) - K_D R \end{aligned}$$

The parameter A_{50} can simply be interpreted as the product of the usual IC_{50} and the volume of distribution V_A of the drug.

The mlxtran model reads:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,A50}

PK:
depot(target=A)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
```

```

A_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_A = - KDE*A
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - A/(A50 + A) ) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}

```

The model can also be written using macros for the (P)K part. When macros are used, the PK part of the model will be calculated using the analytical solution while the PD part will be solved using the ODE solver.

```

[LONGITUDINAL]
input={Ks,Kd,KDE,A50}

PK:
compartment(cmt=1, amount=A)
iv(cmt=1)
elimination(cmt=1, k=KDE)

EQUATION:
; initialization
t_0 = 0
R_0 = Ks/Kd

; ODEs
ddt_R = Ks * (1 - A/(A50 + A) ) - Kd*R

OUTPUT:
output = {R}

```

3.7.8.2.1.3 Extensions

If data is sufficient to allow for the estimation of the additional parameters, the model can be extended, for instance in the following directions:

- more complex profile for the drug concentration, for example with a first-order input rate. In this case, the additional input arguments can be directly given in the depot macro;
- sigmoidal E_{max} or I_{max} model with a hill exponent;
- E_{max} or I_{max} value different from one.

The model can also be adapted to consider **K-PK models, where two drugs interact** and only one of the two is measured.

3.7.8.2.1.4 Simplifications

The use of an Emax or I_{max} model is only suited if the dose range is sufficiently large to cover both the linear and saturating part of the Michaelis-Menten curve. If concentrations are always smaller than the EC₅₀, the model simplifies to:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -KDE \times A$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_s (1 - K_e \times A) - K_D R$$

3.7.8.3 Friberg model for myelosuppression

The Friberg model is a semi-mechanistic pharmacodynamic model describing chemotherapy-induced myelosuppression. It has been originally developed to describe leukocyte and neutrophil data after administration of docetaxel, paclitaxel, etoposide, DMDC and irinotecan and vinflunine in Friberg et al. (2002), and has been reused in many other publications since.

Friberg et al. (2002). Model of chemotherapy-induced myelosuppression with parameter consistency across drugs. Journal of Clinical Oncology, 20(24), 4713–4721.

3.7.8.3.1 Model description

The model consists of a proliferating compartment that is sensitive to drugs, three transit compartments that represent maturation, and a compartment of circulating blood cells. The parameterization is parsimonious (initial circulating concentration, mean transit time and a feedback parameter), well suited for sparse data. The drug effect can be implemented as a linear function or with an Emax model, as shown below.

The PK part of the model is in this example a (ka,V,Cl) model but can be replaced by any other PK model. PK parameters can either be estimated (as below) or read from the data set (uncomment the three lines below the input line to consider the PK parameters as regressors).

3.7.8.3.2 Mixtran model code

```
DESCRIPTION:
PD = Friberg et al (2002) 'Model of Chemotherapy-Induced Myelosuppression with
Parameter Consistency Across Drugs', Journal of Clinical Oncology 20:4713-4721

[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {ka, V, Cl, Circ0, MTT, gam, Emax, EC50}
; ka = {use=regressor}
; V = {use=regressor}
; Cl = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
odeType=stiff
; PK model
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)

; parameter transformations
n = 3
ktr = (n+1)/MTT
kprol = ktr
kcirc = ktr

; drug effect
Edrug = Emax * Cc/(EC50 + Cc)

; initial values
t_0 = 0
Prol_0 = Circ0
T1_0 = Circ0
T2_0 = Circ0
T3_0 = Circ0
Circ_0 = Circ0

;ODEs for the response
ddt_Prol = kprol*Prol*(1-Edrug)*(Circ0/Circ)^gam - ktr*Prol
ddt_T1 = ktr*Prol - ktr*T1
ddt_T2= ktr*T1 - ktr*T2
ddt_T3 = ktr*T2 - ktr*T3
ddt_Circ = ktr*T3 - kcirc*Circ

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc, Circ}
```

In the Monolix GUI, a lognormal distribution can be chosen for Circ0, MTT, gam and EC50, and a **logit distribution for Emax** to ensure that (1-Edrug) stays always positive. It is common to remove the random effects on gam.

3.7.8.4 ADC model

Antibody-drug conjugates or **ADCs** are a class of drugs designed as a targeted therapy for treating cancer. They are complex molecules composed of an antibody that targets a specific tumor antigen, linked to a biologically active cytotoxic payload or drug.

On this page we show an example of population PK model for an ADC drug published in:

Li, H., Han, T.H., Hunder, N.N., Jang, G. and Zhao, B. (2017), *Population Pharmacokinetics of Brentuximab Vedotin in Patients With CD30-Expressing Hematologic Malignancies*. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 57: 1148-1158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcph.920>

In the publication the model is written for NONMEN, here we have translated it in Mlxtran for use with the MonolixSuite.

The model describes the PK of **brentuximab vedotin**, a CD30-directed antibody-drug conjugate (**ADC**), which is approved for treating certain patients with CD30-expressing hematologic malignancies. Its primary mechanism of action is the targeted delivery of a microtubule-disrupting agent, monomethyl auristatin E (**MMAE**), to CD30-expressing cells. In the model considers intravenous administration of **brentuximab vedotin** and characterizes also the PK of **unconjugated MMAE**.

The following figure from the publication describes the model:

Figure 1. ADC and MMAE PK model schema after an intravenous infusion of brentuximab vedotin. ADC, antibody-drug conjugate; DAR, drug-antibody ratio; CL, clearance of ADC by proteolytic degradation; Q_2 and Q_3 , ADC intercompartmental clearance; CL_M , MMAE apparent clearance; MMAE, monomethyl auristatin E; Q_5 , MMAE apparent intercompartmental clearance.

3.7.8.4.1 Mlxtran code for the ADC and MMAE population PK model

The full Mlxtran code is given below:

DESCRIPTION:

ADC-MMAE model describing ADC and MMAE concentrations following intravenous administration of brentuximab vedotin.

Published in:

Li, H., Han, T.H., Hunder, N.N., Jang, G. and Zhao, B. (2017), Population Pharmacokinetics of Brentuximab Vedotin in Patients With CD30-Expressing Hematologic Malignancies. *The Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 57: 1148-1158. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcph.920>

[LONGITUDINAL]

input={CL, V1, Q2, V2, Q3, V3, CLM, V4, Q5, V5, CYCLE, FM, DAR0, ALPHA, BETA}

CYCLE = {use = regressor}

PK:

MW_ADC = 153000 ; molecular weight of ADC [g/mol]

MW_MMAE = 718 ; molecular weight of MMAE [g/mol]

depot(target=A1, p=1e3/MW_ADC) ;from mg to nmol

EQUATION:

odeType=stiff

K10=CL/V1

K12=Q2/V1

K21=Q2/V2

K13=Q3/V1

K31=Q3/V3

K40=CLM/V4

K45=Q5/V4

K54=Q5/V5

FMC = CYCLE^FM ; FRACTION OF ADC CONVERTS TO MMAE BY CYCLE

DAR=DAR0*(ALPHA + (1-ALPHA)*exp(-BETA*(t-tDose)))

ddt_A1 = - (K10 + K12 + K13)*A1 + K21*A2+ K31*A3 ; ADC CENTRAL COMPT

ddt_A2 = K12*A1 - K21*A2 ; ADC PERI COMPT -1

ddt_A3 = K13*A1 - K31*A3 ; ADC PERI COMPT -2

ddt_A4 = K10*A1*DAR*FMC + A1*(DAR-DAR0*ALPHA)*BETA-K40*A4-K45*A4 + K54*A5 ; MMAE CENTRAL COMPT

ddt_A5 = K45*A4 - K54*A5 ;MMAE PERI COMPT

; Proteolytic pathway

ddt_A6 = K10*A1*DAR

; deconjugation pathway

ddt_A7 = A1*(DAR-DAR0*ALPHA)*BETA

ADCC_pmol_mL = A1/V1 ; in nmol/L

$$\text{MMAEc_pmol_mL} = A4/V4 \text{ ; in nmol/L}$$

$$\text{ADCc} = \text{ADCc_pmol_mL} * (\text{MW_ADC}/1\text{e}3) \text{ ; from nmol/L to ug/mL}$$

$$\text{MMAEc} = \text{MMAEc_pmol_mL} * (\text{MW_MMAE}/1) \text{ ; from nmol/L to ng/mL}$$
OUTPUT:

$$\text{output} = \{\text{ADCc}, \text{MMAEc}\}$$

The model has two outputs for ADC concentration and MMAE concentration.

The average drug load (or drug-antibody ratio DAR) was not measured but was assumed to decrease exponentially after each dose. In Mlxtran, the equation for DAR uses the keyword tDose that corresponds to the time of the last dose.

CYCLE is a time-varying regressor indicating the number of the last dose cycle. The fraction of ADC converted to MMAE by cycle varies with $\text{FMC} = \text{CYCLE}^{\text{FM}}$.

The model uses the molecular weights of ADC and MMAE to convert the dose amount from mg to nmol and the output concentrations from nmol/L to ug/mL or ng/mL.

3.7.8.4.2 Typical simulations of the model in Simulx

This Simulx project (Brentuximab Vedotin Simulation.zip) uses the brentuximal model and the population estimates from the paper to simulate a typical prediction:

(note that the link points to a zip file, so the download might be blocked by your browser, in that case you need to right-click > Save link as > Keep)

3.7.8.5 Beta regression model

Beta regression models have been recommended for bounded outcome scores that take values on a finite interval. Examples of bounded outcome data are the cognitive component of the Alzheimer's disease assessment scale (ADAS-cog), a key measure of cognition in Alzheimer's disease patients, which takes integer values from 0 to 70.

As the data is bounded within a certain range, the standard deviation of the error must approach zero as the model prediction approaches the boundary. If the data is considered as continuous, this can be achieved by considering a logitnormal distribution in the error model definition. However, this does not allow to use beta densities which are commonly used for scores.

To demonstrate the implementation of beta regression models in Monolix, we will use the dataset simulated in the following Nonmem tutorial:

Xu, X. S. et al. Mixed-effects beta regression for modeling continuous bounded outcome scores using NONMEM when data are not on the boundaries. *J. Pharmacokinet. Pharmacodyn.* 40, 537–544 (2013).

In order to handle data at the boundary, we will adapt the model to use an augmented beta distribution with inflation at boundaries, as described in the following presentation:

Rogers, Jim & French, Jonathan. *An Extension of Beta Regression to Handle Scores at Boundaries.*

3.7.8.5.1 Case study model

We are considering a model for the progression over time of Alzheimer's disease, measured by the ADAS-cog scale, which are integers from 0 to 70.

In Nonmem, the scores are normalized to obtain a response variable y_{ij} between 0 and 1. The probability to observe the value y_{ij} is described by a beta density:

$$p(y_{ij}) = \frac{\Gamma(\tau)}{\Gamma(\mu_{ij}\tau) \Gamma((1-\mu_{ij})\tau)} y_{ij}^{(\mu_{ij}\tau-1)} (1-y_{ij})^{(1-\mu_{ij})\tau-1}$$

with μ_{ij} the mean of the response process and τ the precision parameter (error parameter).

With the above probability density, the probability to have an observation on the boundary (being 0 or 1) is null, i.e. $p(y_{ij} = 0) = 0$ and $p(y_{ij} = 1) = 0$. In order to handle observations at the boundary, we will rather use an augmented beta distribution with an inflated probability for boundaries values:

$$p(y_{ij}) = \begin{cases} p_0 & \text{if } y_{ij} = 0 \\ p_1 & \text{if } y_{ij} = 1 \\ (1-p_0-p_1) \frac{\Gamma(\tau)}{\Gamma(\mu_{ij}\tau) \Gamma((1-\mu_{ij})\tau)} y_{ij}^{(\mu_{ij}\tau-1)} (1-y_{ij})^{(1-\mu_{ij})\tau-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The probability of observing zeros depends on the mean response μ_{ij} (as the probability to observe low non-zero counts does). The following choice for p_0 and p_1 achieves good properties:

$$\text{logit}(p_0) = -\gamma_0 - \gamma_1 \times \log\left(\frac{\mu_{ij}}{1 - \mu_{ij}}\right)$$

$$\text{logit}(p_1) = -\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \times \log\left(\frac{\mu_{ij}}{1 - \mu_{ij}}\right)$$

The mean of the response μ_{ij} must stay between 0 and 1 so it is convenient to use a logit link function to define it. In addition, the model should capture how μ_{ij} evolves over time, which corresponds to the disease progression. In this example we assume a simple linear evolution.

$$\text{logit}(\mu_{ij}) = \log\left(\frac{\mu_{ij}}{1 - \mu_{ij}}\right) = B_{0,i} + B_{1,i} \times t_{ij}$$

with $B_{0,i} = B_{0,pop} + \eta_{0,i}$ the intercept and $B_{1,i} = B_{1,pop} + \eta_{1,i}$ the slope of the evolution over time.

3.7.8.5.2 General idea

In opposition to Nonmem, the data will be considered as count/categorical in Monolix. This allows (1) to take into account that the scale can take only integer values and (2) to define the likelihood instead of the model prediction. The probability density function will be straightforward to write using the build-in `gammaLn()` function of the mlxtran language.

3.7.8.5.3 Dataset formatting

The OBSERVATION column of the dataset should contain the integer scores (and not a derived response variable between 0 and 1).

ID	TIME	DV
1	0	23
1	0.5	27
1	1	23
1	1.5	40
1	2	21
1	3	14
2	0	14
2	0.5	19
2	1	30
2	1.5	24
2	2	15
2	3	25

When loading the dataset, the observations must be indicated as being of type COUNT/CATEGORICAL:

LINE NUMBER	id	time	DV
2	1	0	23
3	1	0.5	27
4	1	1	23
5	1	1.5	40

3.7.8.5.4 Structural model

The DEFINITION block is used to define the model output to be a random variable following a beta probability density function. Note that in Monolix y_{ij} represents the scores from 0 to 70. An if/else statement is used to distinguish the case $y_{ij}=0$, $y_{ij}=70$ and otherwise. The normalized variable (between 0 and 1) is calculated directly in the equation using $y_{ij}/\text{maxValue}$ with $\text{maxValue}=70$.

We define the exponential of the log of the probability in order to transform the product into a sum and avoid divisions of large numbers. This also allows to use the $\text{gamma}\ln()$ function representing the log of the gamma function.

DEFINITION:

```

ADAScog = {type=count,
if yij==0
  pk = p0
elseif yij==maxValue
  pk = p1
else
  pk = (1-p0-p1) * exp(gammaLn(tau)-gammaLn(mu*tau)-gammaLn((1-mu)*tau) + (mu*tau-1)
*log(yij/maxValue) + ((1-mu)*tau-1)*log(1-yij/maxValue) - log(maxValue))
end
P(ADAScog=yij)= pk }
  
```

The time evolution of μ_{ij} and the definition of p_0 and p_1 are defined in the EQUATION block (above the DEFINITION block):

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input={tau, B0, B1, gamma0, gamma1}

EQUATION:
LINP = B0 + B1 * t
mu = exp(LINP)/(1+exp(LINP))

maxValue = 70

lp0 = -gamma0-gamma1*log(mu/(1-mu))
lp1 = -gamma0+gamma1*log(mu/(1-mu))
p0 = exp(lp0)/(1+exp(lp0))
p1 = exp(lp1)/(1+exp(lp1))
```

3.7.8.5.5 Statistical model

The distribution of the observations has already been defined in the structural model file, so there is nothing to do regarding the residual error model.

For the parameter distributions, we use a normal distribution with IIV for B0 (intercept) and B1 (slope). The other parameters (tau, gamma0 and gamma1) have no IIV. They are positive so we can keep a lognormal distribution.

beta_distribution_augmented.mlxtran* - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

POPULATION PARA... EBEs CONDITIONAL DIST... STANDARD ERRORS LIKELIHOOD PLOTS RUN

Use linearization method

Observation model ▾

Individual model ▾ f(x) Add covariate: LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION
		Select: All None	#1
tau	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B0	NORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B1	NORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
gamma0	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
gamma1	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.7.8.5.6 Diagnostic plots

The diagnostic plots will be those corresponding to count data. There is no individual fits and the VPC shows the probability of the score to be within a range (corresponding to the Y Bins settings):

beta_distribution_augmented.mlxtran* - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates Statistical model & Tasks Results **Plots**

Data

Observed data

Model for the observations

Scatter plot of the residuals

Distribution of the residuals

Model for the individual parameters

Distribution of the individual parameters

Distribution of the standardized random effects

Correlation between random effects

PLOT FORMATTING

APPLY... SAVE

RESET

DISPLAY

X BINS

Y BINS

Binning criteria

Equal width

Equal size

Least-squares

Number of Bins

Fixed

Number of bins

9

Number of data per bin

5

200

AXES

STRATIFY SETTINGS PREFERE...

3.7.8.5.7 Case study download

The entire case study using simulated data can be downloaded below. It must be open with version 2024 or above.

3.8 External model editor

mlxEditor is an application to write, edit and organise models written in the mlxtran language. It has mlxtran dedicated features, such as syntax coloring, autocompletion and verification, and is integrated with Monolix, Simulx and PKanalix for easier model development.


```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2
3 [LONGITUDINAL]
4 input={alpha_S, RF, RE, epsilon, PSAb, Nmax}
5
6 EQUATION:
7 odeType=stiff
8   stiff
9 p=20
10 delta=0.23
11 g=0.0000001
12
13 alpha_R=RF*alpha_S
14 d=RE*RF*alpha_S
15
16
17 PSA_0=PSAb
18 S_0=delta*PSAb/p
19 R_0=g/max(d-RF*(g+d),1e-9)*delta*PSAb/p
20
21
22 if t>0
23 alpha_S=alpha_S*(1-epsilon)
24 else
25 alpha_S=alpha_S
26 end
  
```

Main functions:

- Writing models in the mlxtran language.
- Editing user custom models and models from the Monolix library, which is integrated with the application.
- Editing models directly in the GUI: Monolix (tab: Structural model), Simulx (Tab: Definition/Model) and PKanalix (tab: Model, CA).
- Managing models in work sessions.

Main features:

- Mlxtran syntax coloring for different model elements, such as block definition, parameters, macros.
- Autocompletion for variables, mlxtran keywords, functions (tab-key accepts a selected item).
- Find and Find&Replace.
- Zoom in/out to increase/decrease the font size.
- Syntax check to verify if the mlxtran code is correct and a model can be loaded in Monolix or Simulx.

In the mlxEditor application:

- Access to the Monolix libraries,

- Monolix and Simulx syntax check,
- Save and export to Simulx,
- Sessions: collections of models that can be reloaded automatically.

In the GUI edit mode:

- Several saving options: Save & apply – saves the model under the same name (overwrites the previous model) and applies it to the current project, Save as & apply – saves the model under a different name and applies it to the current project, Save as – saves the model under a different name without applying to the current project.
- Zoom applied in the edition model remains in the “Tab: Structural model” after closing the edition mode.

4 Statistical model

The statistical model tab in Monolix enables to define the statistical model and run estimation tasks.

The statistical model includes

- the observation model, which combines the error model and the distribution of the observations.
- the individual model, combining
 - distributions for the individual parameters
 - which parameters have inter-individual variability (random effects)
 - correlations between the individual parameters
 - covariate effects on the individual parameters

The screenshot displays the 'Statistical model & Tasks' interface in Monolix. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Project, Settings, Export, and Help. Below these are sub-tabs: Data, Structural model, Initial estimates, **Statistical model & Tasks**, and Plots. The 'Tasks' bar contains buttons for POPULATION PARAMETERS, EBES, CONDITIONAL DISTRIBUTION, STANDARD ERRORS, LIKELIHOOD, and PLOTS, followed by a large green RUN button. A toggle for 'Use linearization method' is visible below the task bar.

The 'Observation model' section features a table with the following data:

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL
continuous	2	y2	R	CONSTANT	NORMAL

The 'Individual model' section includes a table for parameter configuration:

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	age	sex	wt
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	#1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.1 Observation model (residual error)

For continuous data, the observation model is the link between the prediction \mathbf{f} of the structural model and the observation. Thus, the observational model is an error model representing the noise and the uncertainty of the measurements. In Monolix, the observation model can be defined only in the interface.

4.1.1 Introduction

For continuous data, we are going to consider scalar outcomes ($y_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}$) and assume the following general model:

$$y_{ij} = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) + g(t_{ij}, \psi_i, \xi)\varepsilon_{ij}$$

for i from 1 to N , and j from 1 to n_i , where ψ_i is the parameter vector of the structural model \mathbf{f} for individual i . The residual error model is defined by the function \mathbf{g} which depends on some additional vector of parameters ξ . The residual errors ε_{ij} are standardized Gaussian random variables (mean 0 and standard deviation 1). In this case, $f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)$ and $g(t_{ij}, \psi_i, \xi)$ are the conditional mean and standard deviation of y_{ij} , i.e.,

$$\mathbb{E}(y_{ij}|\psi_i) = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) \text{ and } \text{sd}(y_{ij}|\psi_i) = g(t_{ij}, \psi_i, \xi)$$

4.1.2 Available observation models

4.1.2.1 Residual errors

In Monolix, we only consider the function \mathbf{g} to be a function of the structural model f , i.e. $g(t_{ij}, \psi_i, \xi) = g(f(t_{ij}, \psi_i), \xi)$ leading to an expression of the observation model of the form

$$y_{ij} = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) + g(f(t_{ij}, \psi_i), \xi)\varepsilon_{ij}$$

The following error models are available in the interface of Monolix and as model keywords in Simulx:

- **constant** : $y = f + a\varepsilon$. The function \mathbf{g} is constant, and the additional parameter is $\xi = a$.
- **proportional** : $y = f + bf^c\varepsilon$. The function \mathbf{g} is proportional to the structural model f , and the additional parameters are $\xi = (b, c)$. By default, the parameter c is fixed at 1 and the additional parameter is $\xi = b$.
- **combined1** : $y = f + (a + bf^c)\varepsilon$. The function \mathbf{g} is a linear combination of a constant term and a term proportional to the structural model f , and the additional parameters are $\xi = (a, b)$ (by default, the parameter c is fixed at 1).
- **combined2** : $y = f + \sqrt{a^2 + b^2(f^c)^2}\varepsilon$. The function \mathbf{g} is a combination of a constant term and a term proportional to the structural model f ($g = bf^c$), and the additional parameters are $\xi = (a, b)$ (by default, the parameter c is fixed at 1). It is equivalent to $y = f + ae_1 + bfe_2$ where e_1 and e_2 are sequences of independent random variables normally distributed with mean 0 and variance 1.

Notice that the parameter c is fixed to 1 by default. However, it can be unfixed and estimated.

It is also possible to assume that the residual errors are correlated.

Positive gain on the error model

The second parameter b in the observational models `comb1` and `comb1c` can be forced to be always positive by selecting $b > 0$.

4.1.2.2 Distributions

The assumption that the distribution of any observation y_{ij} is symmetrical around its predicted value is a very strong one. If this assumption does not hold, we may want to transform the data to make it more symmetric around its (transformed) predicted value. In other cases, constraints on the values that observations can take may also lead us to transform the data.

The model extended model with a transformation of the data is then :

$$u(y_{ij}) = u(f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)) + g(u(f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)), \xi)$$

As we can see, both the data y_{ij} and the structural model f are transformed by the function u so that $f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)$ remains the prediction of y_{ij} . Classical distributions are proposed as transformation:

- **normal** : $u(y) = y$. This is equivalent to no transformation.
- **lognormal** : $u(y) = \log(y)$. Thus, for a combined error model for example, the corresponding observation model writes $\log(y) = \log(f) + (a + b \log(f))\varepsilon$. It assumes that all observations are strictly positive. Otherwise, an error message is thrown. In case of censored data with a limit, the limit has to be strictly positive too. *[Note: if your observations are already log-transformed in your dataset, then you should not use that distribution as y in the formula would correspond to log-transformed measurements. Instead use the normal distribution.]*
- **logitnormal** : $u(y) = \log(y/(1-y))$. Thus, for a combined error model for example, corresponding observation model writes $\log(y/(1-y)) = \log(f/(1-f)) + (a + b \log(f/(1-f)))\varepsilon$. It assumes that all observations are strictly between 0 and 1. However, we can modify these bounds to define the logit function between a minimum and a maximum, and the function u becomes $u(y) = \log((y-y_{min})/(y_{max}-y))$. Again, in case of censored data with a limit, the limits has to be strictly in the proposed interval too.

4.1.2.3 Combinations of distribution and residual error model

Hence, the following observation models can be defined with a combination of distribution and residual error model:

- **exponential error model**: $u(y) = \log(y)$ and $y = fe^{ae}$ → constant error model and a lognormal distribution.
- **logit error model** $u(y) = \log(\frac{y}{1-y})$ → constant error model and a logitnormal distribution.

- **band(0,10):** $u(y) = \log\left(\frac{y}{10-y}\right)$ → constant error model and a logitnormal distribution with min and max at 0 and 10 respectively.
- **band(0,100):** $u(y) = \log\left(\frac{y}{100-y}\right)$ → constant error model and a logitnormal distribution with min and max at 0 and 10 respectively.

4.1.3 Defining the residual error model from the Monolix GUI

A menu in the frame Statistical model & Tasks of the main GUI allows one to select both the error model and the distribution as on the following figure (in blue and green respectively)

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	CONC	CONC	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

with the available options:

- Error model: combined1, combined2, constant, proportional.
- Distribution: normal, lognormal, logitnormal. For logitnormal, min and max values can be defined.

Any questions on what is the formula behind your observation model? There is a button $f(x)$ in the interface as on the figure below where the observation model is described linking the observation (named CONC in that case) and the prediction (named Cc in that case). Note that ϵ is noted e here.

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	CONC	CONC	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

Observation model ×
 $CONC = Cc + (a + b \cdot Cc) \cdot e$

4.1.4 Some basic residual error models

- **warfarinPK_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

The residual error model used with this project for fitting the PK of warfarin is a combined error model, i.e. $y_{ij} = f(t_{ij}, \psi_i) + (a + bf(t_{ij}, \psi_i))\varepsilon_{ij}$.

Observation model f(x)					
TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1 ▾	NORMAL ▾

Several diagnosis plots can then be used for evaluating the error model. The observation versus prediction figure below seems ok.

Remarks:

- Figures showing the shape of the prediction interval for each observation model available in Monolix are displayed here.
- When the residual error model is defined in the GUI, a bloc **DEFINITION:** is then automatically added to the project file in the section `[LONGITUDINAL]` of `<MODEL>` when the project is saved:

```
DEFINITION:
y1 = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=combined1(a,b)}
```

4.1.5 Residual error models for bounded data

- **bandModel_project** (data = 'bandModel_data.txt', model = 'lib:immed_Emax_null.txt')

In this example, data are known to take their values between 0 and 100. We can use a constant error model and a logitnormal for the transformation with bounds (0,100) if we want to take this constraint into account.

Observation model f(x)						
TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION	LIMITS
continuous	Effect	Effect	E	CONSTANT	LOGITNORMAL	0 <input type="text"/> 100

In the Observation versus prediction plot, one can see that the error is smaller when the observations are close to 0 and 100 which is normal. To see the relevance of the predictions, one can look at the 90% prediction interval. Using a logitnormal distribution, we have a very different shape of this prediction interval to take that specificity into account.

VPCs obtained with this error model do not show any misspecification:

This residual error model is implemented in Mlxtran as follows:

```
DEFINITION:
effect = {distribution=logitnormal, min=0, max=100, prediction=E,
errorModel=constant(a)}
```

Autocorrelated residuals

- Starting from version 2023R1, autocorrelation is not available in the interface when creating new projects. However, projects created with older versions that contain autocorrelation can still be opened. To use autocorrelation with new projects, the user should either use the connectors, or write it directly in the Mlxtran file:

- add "autoCorrCoef=r" in definition "DV = {distribution=normal, prediction=Cc, errorModel=proportional(b), autoCorrCoef=r}", for example
- add "r" as an input parameter.

For any subject i , the residual errors $(\varepsilon_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ are usually assumed to be independent random variables. The extension to autocorrelated errors is possible by assuming, that ε_{ij} is a stationary autoregressive process of order 1, AR(1), which autocorrelation decreases exponentially:

$$\text{corr}(\varepsilon_{ij}, \varepsilon_{i,j+1}) = r_i^{(t_{i,j+1} - t_{ij})}$$

where $0 \leq r_i \leq 1$ for each individual i . If $t_{ij} = j$ for any (i,j) , then $t_{i,j+1} - t_{i,j} = 1$ and the autocorrelation function γ_i for individual i is given by

$$\gamma_i(\tau) = \text{corr}(\varepsilon_{ij}, \varepsilon_{i,j+\tau}) = r_i^\tau$$

The residual errors are uncorrelated when $r_i = 0$.

- **autocorrelation_project** (data = 'autocorrelation_data.txt', model = 'lib:infusion_1cpt_Vk.txt')

Autocorrelation is estimated since the checkbox r is ticked in this project:

Observation model

FORMULA

log(concentration) = log(Cc) + a * e, e = AR(r)

NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION	AUTOCORRELATION
concentration	Cc	CONSTANT	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Estimated population parameters now include the autocorrelation r:

LINEARIZATION			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
V_pop	98.7	2.59	2.63
k_pop	0.194	0.00444	2.28
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_V	0.226	0.0216	9.57
omega_k	0.218	0.0167	7.66
Error Model Parameters			
b	0.203	0.00578	2.85
r	0.497	0.0282	5.67

Important remarks:

- Monolix accepts both regular and irregular time grids.
- **For a proper estimation of the autocorrelation structure of the residual errors, rich data is required** (i.e. a large number of time points per individual) .

4.1.6 Using different error models per group/study

- **errorGroup_project** (data = 'errorGroup_data.txt', model = 'errorGroup_model.txt')

Data comes from 3 different studies in this example. We want to have the same structural model but use

different error models for the 3 studies. A solution consists in defining the column STUDY with the reserved keyword OBSERVATION ID. It will then be possible to define one error model per outcome:

STUDY	ID	TIME	AMT	OBSERVATION	
				OBS ID: 1	CONTINUOUS
1	1	0	40	.	.
1	1	1	.	.	3.76806
1	1	5	.	.	3.12646
1	1	9	.	.	2.20348
1	1	13	.	.	1.66139
1	1	17	.	.	1.69985
1	1	21	.	.	1.27998
1	1	25	.	.	0.90664
1	1	29	.	.	0.651657
1	1	33	.	.	0.753478

Here, we use the same PK model for the 3 studies:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {V, k}
```

PK:

```
Cc1 = pkmodel(V, k)
```

```
Cc2 = Cc1
```

```
Cc3 = Cc1
```

OUTPUT:

```
output = {Cc1, Cc2, Cc3}
```

Since 3 outputs are defined in the structural model, one can now define 3 error models in the GUI:

Observation model f(x)

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc1	PROPORTIONAL	NORMAL
continuous	2	y2	Cc2	PROPORTIONAL	NORMAL
continuous	3	y3	Cc3	COMBINED1	NORMAL

Observation model f(x)

```
y1 = Cc1 + b1*Cc1 * e
y2 = Cc2 + b2*Cc2 * e
y3 = Cc3 + (a3 + b3*Cc3) * e
```

Different residual error parameters are estimated for the 3 studies. One can remark that, even if 2 proportional error models are used for the 2 first studies, different parameters b_1 and b_2 are estimated:

	VALUES
Fixed Effects	
V_pop	10.2
k_pop	0.0499
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects	
omega_V	0.154
omega_k	0.16
Error Model Parameters	
b1	0.109
b2	0.144
a3	0.126
b3	0.0696

4.2 Individual model

The population approach considers that parameters of the structural model can have a different value for each individual, and the way these values are distributed over individuals and impacted by covariate values is defined in the *individual model*. The individual model is defined in the lower part of the statistical model tab. This model includes

- distributions for the individual parameters,
- which parameters have inter-individual variability (random effects),
- correlation structure of the random effects,
- covariate effects on the individual parameters.

4.2.1 Theory for the individual model

A model for observations depends on a vector of individual parameters ψ_i . As we want to work with a population approach, we now suppose that ψ_i comes from some probability distribution \mathcal{P}_{ψ_i} .

In this section, we are interested in the implementation of individual parameter distributions $(\mathcal{P}_{\psi_i}, 1 \leq i \leq N)$. Generally speaking, we assume that individuals are independent. This means that in the following analysis, it is sufficient to take a closer look at the distribution \mathcal{P}_{ψ_i} of a unique individual i . The distribution \mathcal{P}_{ψ_i} plays a fundamental role since it describes the *inter-individual variability* of the individual parameter ψ_i . In Monolix, we consider that some transformation of the individual parameters is normally distributed and is a linear function of the covariates:

$$h(\psi_i) = h(\psi_{pop}) + \beta \cdot (c_i - c_{pop}) + \eta_i, \quad \eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Omega)$$

This model gives a clear and easily interpreted decomposition of the variability of $h(\psi_i)$ around $h(\psi_{pop})$, i.e., of ψ_i around ψ_{pop} :

The component $\beta \cdot (c_i - c_{pop})$ describes part of this variability by way of covariates c_i that fluctuate around a typical value c_{pop} .

The random component η_i describes the remaining variability, i.e., variability between subjects that have the same covariate values. By definition, a mixed effects model combines these two components: fixed and random effects. In linear covariate models, these two effects combine. In the present context, the vector of population parameters to estimate is $\theta = (\psi_{pop}, \beta, \Omega)$. Several extensions of this basic model are possible:

- We can suppose for instance that the individual parameters of a given individual can fluctuate over time. Assuming that the parameter values remain constant over some periods of time called *occasions*, the model needs to be able to describe the inter-occasion variability (IOV) of the individual parameters.
- If we assume that the population consists of several homogeneous subpopulations, a straightforward extension of mixed effects models is a finite mixture of mixed effects models, assuming for instance that the distribution p_{ψ_i} is a mixture of distributions.

4.2.2 Distribution of individual parameters

Objectives: learn how to define the probability distribution and the correlation structure of the individual parameters.

Projects: warfarin_distribution1_project, warfarin_distribution2_project, warfarin_distribution3_project, warfarin_distribution4_project

4.2.2.1 Introduction

One way to extend the use of Gaussian distributions is to consider that some transformation of the parameters in which we are interested is Gaussian, i.e., assume the existence of a monotonic function h such that $h(\psi)$ is normally distributed. Then, there exists some ω such that, for each individual i :

$$h(\psi_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(h(\bar{\psi}_i), \omega^2)$$

where $\bar{\psi}_i$ is the predicted value of ψ_i . In this section, we consider models for the individual parameters without any covariate. Then, the predicted value of ψ_i is the $\bar{\psi}_i = \psi_{pop}$ and

$$h(\psi_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(h(\psi_{pop}), \omega^2)$$

The transformation h defines the distribution of ψ_i . Some predefined distributions/transformations are available in Monolix:

- **Normal distribution in (-inf,+inf):**

In that case, $h(\psi_i) = \psi_i$.

Note: the two mathematical representations for normal distributions are equivalent:

$$\psi_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{\psi}_i, \omega^2) \Leftrightarrow \psi_i = \bar{\psi}_i + \eta_i, \text{ where } \eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \omega^2)$$

- **Log-normal distribution in (0,+inf):**

In that case, $h(\psi_i) = \log(\psi_i)$. A log-normally distributed random variable takes positive values only. A log-normal distribution looks like a normal distribution for a small variance ω^2 . On the other hand, the asymmetry of the distribution increases when ω^2 increases.

Note: the two mathematical representations for log-normal distributions are equivalent:

$$\log(\psi_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(\bar{\psi}_i), \omega^2) \Leftrightarrow \log(\psi_i) = \log(\bar{\psi}_i) + \eta_i \Leftrightarrow \psi_i = \bar{\psi}_i e^{\eta_i}, \text{ where } \eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \omega^2)$$

$\bar{\psi}_i$ represents the typical value (fixed effect) and ω the standard deviation of the random effects, which is interpreted as the inter-individual variability. Note that $\bar{\psi}_i$ is the median of the distribution (neither the mean, nor the mode).

- **Logit-normal distribution in (0,1):**

In that case, $h(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i}{1-\psi_i}\right)$. A random variable ψ_i with a logit-normal distribution takes its values in (0,1). The logit of ψ_i is normally distributed, i.e.,

$$\text{logit}(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i}{1-\psi_i}\right) \sim \mathcal{N}(\text{logit}(\bar{\psi}_i), \omega^2) \Leftrightarrow \text{logit}(\psi_i) = \text{logit}(\bar{\psi}_i) + \eta_i, \text{ where } \eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \omega^2)$$

Note that:

$$m = \text{logit}(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i}{1-\psi_i}\right) \Leftrightarrow \psi_i = \frac{\exp(m)}{1 + \exp(m)}$$

- **Generalized logit-normal distribution in (a,b):**

In that case, $h(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i - a}{b - \psi_i}\right)$. A random variable ψ_i with a logit-normal distribution takes its values in (a,b). The logit of ψ_i is normally distributed, i.e.,

$$\text{logit}_{(a,b)}(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i - a}{b - \psi_i}\right) \sim \mathcal{N}(\text{logit}_{(a,b)}(\bar{\psi}_i), \omega^2) \Leftrightarrow \text{logit}_{(a,b)}(\psi_i) = \text{logit}_{(a,b)}(\bar{\psi}_i) + \eta_i, \text{ where } \eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \omega^2)$$

Note that:

$$m = \text{logit}_{(a,b)}(\psi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\psi_i - a}{b - \psi_i}\right) \Leftrightarrow \psi_i = \frac{b \exp(m) + a}{1 + \exp(m)}$$

- **Probit-normal distribution:**

The probit function is the inverse cumulative distribution function (quantile function) Φ^{-1} associated with the standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. A random variable ψ_i with a probit-normal distribution also takes its values in (0,1).

$$\text{probit}(\psi_i) = \Phi^{-1}(\psi_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\Phi^{-1}(\bar{\psi}_i), \omega^2)$$

To chose one of these distribution in the GUI, click on the distribution corresponding to the parameter you want to change in the individual model part and choose the corresponding distribution.

Individual model f(x)

Add covariate: CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	- CORRELATION +	SEX	WEIGHT
		Select: All None	#1		
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Remarks:

1. If you change your distribution and your population parameter is not valid, then an error message is thrown. Typically, when you want to change your distribution to a log normal distribution, make sure the associated population parameter is strictly positive.
2. When creating a project, the default proposed distribution is lognormal.
3. Logit transformations can be generalized to any interval (a,b) by setting $\psi_{(a,b)} = a + (b - a)\psi_{(0,1)}$ where $\psi_{(0,1)}$ is a random variable that takes values in (0,1) with a logit-normal distribution. Thus, if you need to have bounds between a and b, you need to modify your structural model to reshape a parameter between 0 and 1 and use a logit or a probit distribution. Examples are shown on this page.

- **“Adapted” Logit-normal distribution:**

Another interesting possibility is to “extend” the logit distribution to be bounded in (a, b) rather than in (0, 1). It is possible starting from the 2019 version. For that, set your parameter in a logit normal distribution. The setting button appear next to the distribution.

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	- CORRELATION +	AGE	SEX	WT	logWT
		Select: All None	#1				
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
V1	LOGITNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
V2	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Clicking on it will allow to define your bounds as in the following figure.

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface. A 'Distribution limits' dialog box is open, showing a range from 0 to 13.28. The background shows the 'Observation model' section with a table of parameters and their distributions, and the 'Individual model' section with a table of parameters and their distributions.

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	AGE	SEX	WT	logfWT
CI	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
V1	LOGITNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Q	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				
V2	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Notice that if your parameter initial value is not in (0, 1), the bounds are automatically adapted and the following warning message is given "The initial value of XX is greater than 1: the logit limit is adjusted".

4.2.2.2 Marginal distributions of the individual parameters

- **warfarin_distribution1_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

We use the warfarin PK example here. The four PK parameters Tlag, ka, V and CI are log-normally distributed. LOGNORMAL distribution is then used for these four log-normal distributions in the main Monolix graphical user interface:

Individual model f(x)

Add covariate: CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	age	sex	wt
		Select: All None	#1			
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The distribution of the 4 PK parameters defined in the Monolix GUI is automatically translated into Mlxtran in the project file:

```
[INDIVIDUAL]
input = {Tlag_pop, omega_Tlag, ka_pop, omega_ka, V_pop, omega_V, Cl_pop, omega_Cl}
DEFINITION:
Tlag = {distribution=lognormal, typical=Tlag_pop, sd=omega_Tlag}
ka = {distribution=lognormal, typical=ka_pop, sd=omega_ka}
V = {distribution=lognormal, typical=V_pop, sd=omega_V}
Cl = {distribution=lognormal, typical=Cl_pop, sd=omega_Cl}
```

Estimated parameters are the parameters of the 4 log-normal distributions and the parameters of the residual error model:

	VALUE	LINEARIZATION				
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	
Fixed Effects						
Tlag_pop	0.796	0.202	25.3	0.495	1.28	
ka_pop	1.404	0.443	31.5	0.787	2.505	
V_pop	7.922	0.326	4.12	7.308	8.586	
Cl_pop	0.132	0.00689	5.22	0.119	0.146	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects						
	Value	C.V.(%)				
omega_Tlag	0.582	63.505	0.181	31.1	0.329	1.031
omega_ka	0.814	97.015	0.234	28.7	0.478	1.388
omega_V	0.221	22.404	0.0305	13.8	0.17	0.289
omega_Cl	0.29	29.621	0.0373	12.9	0.226	0.372
Error Model Parameters						
a	0.24	0.0429	17.9	0.17	0.338	
b	0.0522	0.00875	16.8	0.0378	0.072	

Here, $V_{pop} = 7.922$ and $\omega_V = 0.221$ means that the estimated population distribution for the volume is: $\log(V_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(7.922), 0.221^2)$ or, equivalently, $V_i = 7.922e^{\eta_i}$ where $\eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.221^2)$.

Remarks:

- $V_{pop} = 7.922$ **is not** the population mean of the distribution of V_i , but the median of this distribution (in that case, the mean value is 8.848). The four probability distribution functions are displayed figure

Parameter distributions:

- V_{pop} **is not** the population mean of the distribution of V_i , but the median of this distribution. The same property holds for the 3 other distributions which are not Gaussian.
- Here, standard deviations ω_{Tlag} , ω_{ka} , ω_V and ω_{Cl} are approximately the coefficients of variation (CV) of Tlag, ka, V and Cl since these 4 parameters are log-normally distributed with variances < 1.

- **warfarin_distribution2_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

Other distributions for the PK parameters are used in this project:

- NORMAL for Tlag, we fix the population value $Tlag_{pop}$ to 1.5 and the standard deviation ω_{Tlag} to 1,
- NORMAL for ka,
- NORMAL for V,
- and LOGNORMAL for Cl.

Estimated parameters are the parameters of the 4 transformed normal distributions and the parameters of the residual error model:

LINEARIZATION			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
Tlag_pop	1.5		
ka_pop	1.85	0.404	21.9
V_pop	8.18	0.33	4.03
Cl_pop	0.133	0.00694	5.22
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_Tlag	1		
omega_ka	0.781	0.364	46.6
omega_V	1.75	0.248	14.1
omega_Cl	0.29	0.0376	13
Error Model Parameters			
a	0.299	0.048	16.1
b	0.0514	0.00926	18

Here, $Tlag_{pop} = 1.5$ and $\omega_{Tlag} = 1$ means that $Tlag_i \sim \mathcal{N}(1.5, 1^2)$ while $Cl_{pop} = 0.133$ and $\omega_{Cl} = 0.29$ means that $\log(Cl_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(0.133), 0.29^2)$. The four probability distribution functions are displayed Figure Parameter distributions:

4.2.2.3 Correlation structure of the random effects

Dependency can be introduced between individual parameters by supposing that the random effects η_i are not independent. This means considering them to be linearly correlated.

- **warfarin_distribution3_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

4.2.2.3.1 Defining correlation between random effects in the interface

To introduce correlations between random effects in Monolix, one can define correlation groups. For example, two correlation groups are defined on the interface below, between $\eta_{V,i}$ and $\eta_{Cl,i}$ (#1 in that case) and between $\eta_{Tlag,i}$ and $\eta_{ka,i}$ in an other group (#2 in that case):

Individual model

FORMULA

```

log(Tlag) = log(Tlag_pop) + eta_Tlag
log(ka) = log(ka_pop) + eta_ka
log(V) = log(V_pop) + eta_V
log(Cl) = log(Cl_pop) + eta_Cl
  
```

Correlations
id : [V, Cl] [ka, Tlag]

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	
		Select All None	#1	#2
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

To define a correlation between the random effects of V and Cl, you just have to click on the check boxes of the correlation for those two parameters. If you want to define a correlation between the random effects ka and Tlag independently of the first correlation group, click on the + next to CORRELATION to define a second group and click on the check boxes corresponding to the parameters ka and Tlag under the correlation group #2. Notice, that as the random effects of Cl and V are already in the correlation group #1, these random effects can not be used in another correlation group. When three or more parameters are included in a correlation groups, all pairwise correlations will be estimated. It is not instance not possible to estimate the correlation between $\eta_{ka,i}$ and $\eta_{V,i}$ and between $\eta_{Cl,i}$ and $\eta_{V,i}$ but not between $\eta_{Cl,i}$ and $\eta_{ka,i}$.

It is important to mention that the estimated correlations are not the correlation between the individual parameters (between $Tlag_i$ and ka_i , and between V_i and Cl_i) but the (linear) correlation between the random effects (between $\eta_{Tlag,i}$ and $\eta_{ka,i}$, and between $\eta_{V,i}$ and $\eta_{Cl,i}$ respectively).

Remarks

- If the box is greyed, it means that the associated random effects can not be used in a correlation group, as in the following cases
 - when the parameter has no random effects
 - when the random effect of the parameter is already used in another correlation group
- There are no limitation in terms of number of parameters in a correlation group
- You can have a look in the FORMULA to have a recap of all correlations
- In case of inter-occasion variability, you can define the correlation group for each level of variability independently.
- The initial value for the correlations is zero and cannot be changed.
- The correlation value cannot be fixed.

Estimated population parameters now include these 2 correlations:

LINEARIZATION			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
Tlag_pop	0.929	0.21	22.6
ka_pop	1.75	0.623	35.5
V_pop	7.98	0.327	4.1
Cl_pop	0.132	0.00695	5.25
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_Tlag	0.538	0.174	32.4
omega_ka	0.902	0.307	34
omega_V	0.219	0.0306	13.9
omega_Cl	0.292	0.0377	12.9
Correlations			
corr_V_Cl	0.421	0.159	37.7
corr_ka_Tlag	0.412	0.444	108
Error Model Parameters			
a	0.274	0.0458	16.7
b	0.0544	0.00907	16.7

Notice that the high uncertainty on corr_ka_Tlag suggests that the correlation between $\eta_{Tlag,i}$ and $\eta_{ka,i}$ is not reliable.

4.2.2.3.2 How to decide to include correlations between random effects?

The scatterplots of the random effects can hint at correlations to include in the model. This plot represents the joint empirical distributions of each pair of random effects. The regression line (in pink below) and the correlation coefficient ("information" toggle in the settings) permits to visually detect tendencies. If "conditional distribution" (default) is chosen in the display settings, the displayed random effects are calculated using individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution, which permits to avoid spurious correlations (see the page on shrinkage for more details). If a large

correlation is present between a pair of random effects, this correlation can be added to the model in order to be estimated as a population parameter.

Depending on a number of random effects values used to calculate the correlation coefficient, a same correlation value can be more or less significant. To help the user identify significant correlations, Pearson's correlation tests are performed in the "Result" tab, "Tests" section. If no significant correlation is found, like for the pair η_{Tlag} and η_{Cl} below, the distributions can be assumed to be independent. However, if a significant correlation appears, like for the pair η_V and η_{Cl} below, it can be hypothesized that the distributions are not independent and that the correlation must be included in the model and estimated. Once the correlation is included in the model, the random effects for V and Cl are drawn from the joint distribution rather than from two independent distributions.

4.2.2.3.3 How do the correlations between random effects affect the individual model?

In this example the model has four parameters $Tlag$, ka , V and Cl . Without correlation, the individual model is:

$$\log(Tlag) = \log(Tlag_{pop}) + \eta_{Tlag}$$

$$\log(ka) = \log(ka_{pop}) + \eta_{ka}$$

$$\log(V) = \log(V_{pop}) + \eta_V$$

$$\log(Cl) = \log(Cl_{pop}) + \eta_{Cl}$$

The random effects follow normal distributions: $(\eta_{Tlag,i}, \eta_{ka,i}, \eta_{V,i}, \eta_{Cl,i}) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Omega)$.

Ω is the variance-covariance matrix defining the distributions of the vectors of random effects, here:

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_{Tlag}^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_{ka}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \omega_V^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \omega_{Cl}^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

In this example, two correlations between η_{Tlag} and η_{ka} and between η_V and η_{Cl} are added to the model. They are defined with two population parameters called `corr_Tlag_ka` and `corr_V_Cl` that appear in the variance-covariance matrix. So the only difference in the individual model is in Ω , that is now:

$$\Omega = \begin{pmatrix} \omega_{Tlag}^2 & \omega_{Tlag}\omega_{ka}\text{corr_Tlag_ka} & 0 & 0 \\ \omega_{Tlag}\omega_{ka}\text{corr_Tlag_ka} & \omega_{ka}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \omega_V^2 & \omega_V\omega_{Cl}\text{corr_V_Cl} \\ 0 & 0 & \omega_V\omega_{Cl}\text{corr_V_Cl} & \omega_{Cl}^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

So the correlation matrix is related to the variance-covariance matrix Ω as:

$$\text{corr}(\theta_i, \theta_j) = \frac{\text{covar}(\theta_i, \theta_j)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_i)}\sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_j)}}$$

4.2.2.3.4 Why should the correlation be estimated as part of the population parameters?

The effect of correlations is especially important when simulating parameters from the model. This is the case in the VPC or when simulating new individuals in Simulx to assess the outcome of a different dosing scenario for instance. If in reality individuals with a large distribution volume also have a large clearance (i.e there is a positive correlation between the random effects of the volume and the clearance), but this correlation has not been included in the model, then the concentrations predicted by the model for a new cohort of individuals will display a larger variability than they would in reality.

4.2.2.3.5 How do the EBEs change after having included correlation in the model?

Before adding correlation in the model, the EBEs or the individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution may already be correlated, as can be seen in the “correlation between random effects” plot. This is because the individual parameters (EBEs or sampled) are based on the individual conditional distributions, which takes into account the information given by the data. Especially when the data is rich, the data can indicate that individuals with a large volume of distribution also have a large clearance, even if this correlation is not yet included in the model.

Including the correlation in the model as a population parameter to estimate allows to precisely estimate its value. Usually, one can see a stronger correlation for the corresponding pair of random effects when the correlation is included in the model compared to when it is not. In this example, after

including the correlations in the individual model, the joint distribution of η_V and η_{Cl} displays a higher correlation coefficient (0.439 compared to 0.375 previously):

- **warfarin_distribution4_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

In this example, $Tlag_i$ does not vary in the population, which means that $\eta_{Tlag,i} = 0$ for all subjects i , while the three other random effects are correlated:

Individual model

FORMULA

```
log(Tlag) = log(Tlag_pop)
log(ka) = log(ka_pop) + eta_ka
log(V) = log(V_pop) + eta_V
log(Cl) = log(Cl_pop) + eta_Cl
Correlations
id : {V, ka, Cl}
```

MIXTURE

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS Select All None	CORRELATION #1
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Estimated population parameters now include the 3 correlations between $\eta_{ka,i}$, $\eta_{V,i}$ and $\eta_{Cl,i}$:

LINEARIZATION			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
Tlag_pop	0.902	0.187	20.8
ka_pop	1.49	0.372	25
V_pop	7.95	0.328	4.12
Cl_pop	0.132	0.00689	5.22
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_Tlag	0.507	0.153	30.2
omega_ka	0.632	0.213	33.6
omega_V	0.22	0.0307	13.9
omega_Cl	0.29	0.0375	12.9
Correlations			
corr_V_Cl	0.423	0.159	37.5
corr_ka_Cl	-0.318	0.354	111
corr_ka_V	-0.151	0.383	253
Error Model Parameters			
a	0.29	0.0471	16.2
b	0.0511	0.00915	17.9

4.2.2.4 Parameters without random effects

4.2.2.4.1 Adding/removing inter-individual variability

By default, all parameters have inter-individual variability. To remove it, click on the checkbox of the random effect column:

Individual model

FORMULA

Add covariate
CONTINUOUS DISCRETE MIXTURE

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS Select: All None	- CORRELATION + #1	SEX	WEIGHT	icat ▾
ka	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How the parameters with no variability are estimated is explained here.

4.2.2.5 Custom parameter distributions

Some datasets may require more complex parameter distributions than those pre-implemented in the Monolix GUI. This video shows how to implement a lognormal distribution with Box-Cox transformation and how to bound a parameter between two values using a transformed logit distribution (this latter case can be handled automatically from Monolix2019R1):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aOFm0xpYF9E>

4.2.2.6 Understanding shrinkage

4.2.2.6.1 Introduction

Shrinkage is a phenomenon that appears when the data is insufficient to precisely estimate the individual parameters (EBEs). In that case, the EBEs “shrink” towards the center of the population distribution and do not properly represent the inter-individual variability. This leads to diagnostic plots that may be misleading, either hiding true relationships or inducing wrong ones.

In the diagnostic plots, Monolix uses samples from the conditional distribution as individual parameters, which lead to reliable plots even when shrinkage is present in the model [1]. This method is based on the calculation of the conditional distribution.

4.2.2.6.2 Conditional distribution

The conditional distribution is defined for each individual. **It represents the uncertainty of the individual's parameter value, taking the information at hand for this individual into account:**

- the observed data for that individual,
- the covariate values for that individual,
- the fact that the individual belongs to the population for which we have already estimated the typical parameter value (fixed effects) and the inter-individual variability (standard deviation of the random effects).

In a mathematical formalism, the conditional distribution is written $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ with ψ_i the individual parameters for individual i , $\hat{\theta}$ the estimated population parameters, and y_i the data (observations) for individual i .

It is not possible to directly calculate the probability for a given ψ_i (no closed form), but **it is possible to obtain samples from the distribution using a Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo procedure (MCMC)**. This is what is done in the Conditional distribution task.

With the following conditional distribution for the volume V of individual i , we see that the most probable value is around 25 L but there is quite some uncertainty: the value could also be 15 or 40 for instance. For visual purpose, we have drawn the distribution as a smooth curve, but remember that the conditional distribution has no explicit expression. One can only obtain samples from this distribution using MCMC.

4.2.2.6.3 Conditional mode (EBEs) and conditional mean

It is often convenient to work with a single value for the individual parameters (called an estimator), instead of a probability distribution. **Several “summary” values can be used, such as the mode or the mean of the conditional distribution.**

The mode is also called **maximum a posteriori or EBE** (for empirical bayes estimate). It is often preferred over the mean, because the mode represents the most likely value, i.e the value which has the highest probability.

In Monolix, the mode is calculated via the EBEs task, while the mean is calculated via the Conditional distribution task, as the average of all samples drawn from the conditional distribution.

Once the value of the individual estimator (conditional mode or conditional mean) is known for each individual, **one can easily calculate the individual random effects for each individual**. For instance for the volume V, that depends on the covariate weight WT:

$$V_i = V_{pop} \left(\frac{WT_i}{70} \right)^\beta e^{\eta_i}$$

$$\Rightarrow \eta_i = \log(V_i) - \log(V_{pop}) - \beta \log\left(\frac{WT_i}{70}\right)$$

The individual parameters and individual random effects are used in diagnostic plots. They are used either directly, such as in the Correlation between random effects or Individual parameter versus covariate plots, or indirectly to generate individual predictions, such as in Individual Fits, Observations versus Predictions or Scatter plot of the residuals. **But these diagnostic plots can be biased in presence of shrinkage.**

4.2.2.6.4 Shrinkage

When the individual data brings only few information about the individual parameter value, the conditional distribution is large, reflecting the uncertainty of the individual parameter value. In that case, **the mode of the conditional distribution is close to (or “shrinks” to) the mode of the population distribution**. If this is the case for all or most of the individuals, all individual parameters end up concentrated around the mode of the population distribution and do not correctly represent the inter-individual variability which has been estimated via the standard deviation parameters (omega parameters in Monolix). This is the shrinkage phenomenon. Shrinkage typically occurs when the data is sparse.

Below we present the example of a parameter V which has a lot of shrinkage and a parameter k with almost no shrinkage. We consider a data set with 10 individuals. In the upper plots, the conditional distributions of each of the 10 individuals are shown. For the volume V, the individual parameter values are uncertain and their conditional distributions are large. When reporting the mode (closed circles) of the conditional distributions on the population distribution (black curve, bottom plots), **the modes appear shrunk compared to the population distribution**. On the opposite, for k, the conditional distributions are narrow and the modes are well spread over the population distribution. There is shrinkage for V, but not for k.

Volume of distribution V
V has high shrinkage

Elimination rate k
k has very low shrinkage

Pulling the individual parameters of all individuals together, one can overlay the population distribution (black line) with the histogram of individual parameters (i.e conditional modes) (blue bars). This is displayed in the Distribution of the individual parameters plot in Monolix:

The shrinkage phenomenon can be quantified via a shrinkage value for each parameter. In Monolix, the formula for shrinkage has been updated in version 2024 to use the standard deviation instead of the variance in accordance with industry standards.

Starting with **Monolix version 2024**, shrinkage is calculated from the empirical standard deviation of the random effects $sd(\eta_i)$ and the estimated standard deviation (the omega population parameter ω). The random effects $sd(\eta_i)$ can be calculated from the EBEs, conditional mean or samples from the conditional distribution. Typically, the shrinkage is reported using the EBEs.

$$\eta\text{-sh} = 1 - \frac{sd(\eta_i)}{\omega}$$

In the case of inter occasion variability, shrinkage includes both inter individual and inter occasion variability (the gamma population parameter γ)

$$\eta\text{-sh} = 1 - \frac{sd(\eta_i)}{\sqrt{\omega^2 + \gamma^2}}$$

In **Monolix versions 2023 and earlier**, shrinkage is calculated using the ratio of the empirical variance and the estimated variance as:

$$\eta\text{-sh} = 1 - \frac{\text{var}(\eta_i)}{\omega^2}$$

4.2.2.6.5 Results

In **Monolix versions 2023** and earlier, the shrinkage can be displayed in the Distribution of the individual parameters plot, by selecting the “information” toggle.

Starting in **Monolix version 2024**, shrinkage information is available in several ways:

- Results / Indiv. Results / Cond. Mean [summary] – shrinkage is reported if the Conditional Distribution task has been run
- Results / Indiv. Results / Cond. Mode [summary] – shrinkage is reported if the EBEs task has been run
- In the IndividualParameters folder inside the results folder, there is a file **shrinkage.txt**
- In reports, using the metric SHRINKAGE in the population or individual parameters table placeholder
- In the plot Distribution of the individual parameters by switching on “information”
- In the plot Distribution of the standardized random effects by switching on “information”

Calculating the shrinkage in R

Starting with Monolix version 2024, there is a method available to directly return the shrinkage information: **getEtaShrinkage()**.

In Monolix version 2023 and earlier, there is no function from the lixoftConnectors to directly get the shrinkage, but you can easily calculate it from the estimated parameters like this for example for parameter V:

```

population_params <- read.csv("monolix_project/populationParameters.txt")
eta_estimated <- read.csv("monolix_project/IndividualParameters/
estimatedRandomEffects.txt")
omega_V <- population_params$value[population_params$parameter=="V"]
eta_V_estimated_mode <- eta_estimated$eta_V_mode
shrinkage_eta_V_estimated_mode <- (1-var(eta_V_estimated_mode)/omega_V^2)*100
  
```

4.2.2.6.6 Comparison to Nonmem

The Nonmem definition of shrinkage is based on a **ratio of standard deviations**. **This is also the case in Monolix 2024 and above**. However, Monolix 2023 and below uses a **ratio of variances** (which is more common in statistics). Below we provide a “conversion table” which should be read in the following way: a situation that would in Nonmem and Monolix 2024 lead to a shrinkage calculation of 30%, would in Monolix 2023 lead to a calculation of shrinkage of around 50%. The Nonmem and Monolix 2024 version of the shrinkage can be calculated from the Monolix 2023 shrinkage using the following formula:

$$\eta\text{-shNM} = \eta\text{-shMLX24} = 1 - \sqrt{1 - \eta\text{-shMLX23}}$$

		Shrinkage value			
Nonmem & Monolix 2024 (and above)	$\eta\text{-sh} = 1 - \frac{\text{sd}(\eta_i)}{\omega}$	10%	30%	50%	70%
Monolix 2023 (and below)	$\eta\text{-sh} = 1 - \frac{\text{var}(\eta_i)}{\omega^2}$	19%	51%	75%	91%

Is it OK to get a negative shrinkage? Yes. In case of no shrinkage, $\text{var}(\eta_i) = \omega^2$ when $\text{var}(\eta_i)$ is calculated on an infinitely large sample. In practice, $\text{var}(\eta_i)$ is calculated on a limited sample related to the number of individuals. Its value can be by chance a little bigger than ω^2 , leading to a slightly negative shrinkage.

4.2.2.6.6.1 Consequences of shrinkage

In case of shrinkage the individual parameters (conditional mode/EBEs or conditional mean) are biased because they do not correctly reflect the population distribution.

As these individual parameters are used in diagnostic plots (in particular the Correlation between random effects and the Individual parameters versus covariates plots) **the diagnostic plots can become misleading in presence of shrinkage, either hiding relations or suggesting wrong ones**. This complicates the identification of misspecifications and burdens the modeling process.

Note that the shrinkage of the EBEs has no consequences on the population parameter estimation via SAEM (which doesn't use EBEs, contrary to FOCE for instance). However the lack of informative data may lead to large standard errors for the population parameters and a slower convergence.

4.2.2.6.7 How to circumvent shrinkage

Monolix provides a very efficient solution to circumvent the shrinkage problem, i.e the bias in the diagnostic plots induced by the use of shrunk individual parameters. **Instead of using the shrunk conditional mode/EBEs or conditional mean, Monolix uses parameter values randomly sampled from the conditional distribution:**

The fact of pooling the random samples of the conditional distribution of all individuals allows us to look at them as if they were sampled from the population distribution. And this is exactly what we want: to have individual parameter values (i.e the samples) that correctly reflect the population distribution.

From a mathematical point of view, one can show that the random samples are an unbiased estimator:

$$p(\psi_i) = \int p(\psi_i | y_i) p(y_i) dy_i = \mathbb{E}_{y_i}(p(\psi_i | y_i))$$

The improvement brought by the random samples from the conditional distributions can be visualized in the following way: while the mode (closed circles) are shrunk, the random samples (stars) spread over the entire population distribution (in black). **One can even draw several random sample per individual to increase the informativeness of the diagnostic plots.** This is what is done in the MonolixSuite2018R1 version (while MonolixSuite2016R1 uses one sample per individual).

Using the mode of the conditional distribution

Using one sample from the conditional distribution

Using several samples from the conditional distribution

In [1], the authors warrant the use of sampled individual parameters. They demonstrate their usefulness in diagnostic plots via numerical experiments with simulated data. They also show that statistical tests based on these sampled individual parameters are unbiased, the type I error rate is the desired significance level of the test and the probability to detect a misspecification in the model increases with the magnitude of this misspecification.

4.2.2.6.8 Example

Fitting the sparse [Tobramycin data](#) with a (V,k) model leads to a high shrinkage (75%) of the volume V when using the EBEs. On the opposite, when using samples from the conditional distributions of each individual, there is no shrinkage anymore.

Using the EBEs
(conditional mode)

Using samples from the
conditional distribution

The usefulness of using the samples from the conditional distribution can be seen in the **Correlation between the random effects plot**. Using the EBEs, the plot suggests a positive correlation of about 30% between the volume and the elimination rate. Using the random samples, the plot does not suggest this correlation any more. If the correlation is added to the model, it is estimated small and not significant.

Using the EBEs
(conditional mode)

Using samples from the
conditional distribution

Another example of shrinkage can be seen for the parameter k_a in the [warfarin data set](#). In this example, the data is sparse during the absorption phase leading to a large uncertainty of the individual parameter values.

4.2.2.6.9 Conclusion

The use of samples from the conditional distribution is a powerful way to avoid the bias due to the shrinkage in the diagnostic plots. This method has been validated mathematically and with numerical experiments.

In Monolix, the random samples are used by default in all diagnostic plots, if the Conditional distribution task has been run. The choice of the estimator for the individual parameters can be changed in the Settings tab:

4.2.3 Covariate model

Objectives: learn how to implement a model for continuous and/or categorical covariates.

Projects: warfarin_covariate1_project, warfarin_covariate2_project, warfarin_covariate3_project, phenobarbital_project

4.2.3.1 Model with continuous covariates

- **warfarin_covariate1_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

The warfarin data contains 2 individual covariates: `weight` which is a continuous covariate and `sex` which is a categorical covariate with 2 categories (1=Male, 0=Female). We can ignore these columns if are sure not to use them, or declare them using respectively the reserved keywords `CONTINUOUS COVARIATE` and `CATEGORICAL COVARIATE` to define continuous and categorical covariate.

Even if these 2 covariates are now available, we can choose to define a model without any covariate by not clicking on any check box in the covariate model.

Individual model

FORMULA MODEL BUILDING

Add covariate CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS Select All None	- CORRELATION + #1	sex	wt
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Here, an unchecked box in the line of the parameter V and the column of the covariate wt means that there is no relationship between weight and volume in the model. A diagnosis plot **Individual parameters vs covariates** is generated which displays possible relationships between covariates and individual parameters (even if these covariates are not used in the model):

On the figure, we can see a strong correlation between the volume V and both the weight wt and the sex. One can also see a correlation between the clearance and the weight wt . Therefore, the next step is to add some covariate to our model.

- **warfarin_covariate2_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

We decide to use the weight in this project in order to explain part of the variability of V_i and Cl_i . We will implement the following model for these two parameters:

$$\log(V_i) = \log(V_{pop}) + \beta_V \log(w_i/70) + \eta_{V,i} \quad \text{and} \quad \log(Cl_i) = \log(Cl_{pop}) + \beta_{Cl} \log(w_i/70) + \eta_{Cl,i}$$

which means that population parameters of the PK parameters are defined for a typical individual of the population with weight = 70kg.

More details about the model

The model for V_i and Cl_i can be equivalently written as follows:

$$V_i = V_{pop}(w_i/70)^{\beta_V} e^{\eta_{V,i}} \quad \text{and} \quad Cl_i = Cl_{pop}(w_i/70)^{\beta_{Cl}} e^{\eta_{Cl,i}}$$

The individual predicted values for V_i and Cl_i are therefore

$$\bar{V}_i = V_{pop}(w_i/70)^{\beta_V} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{Cl}_i = Cl_{pop}(w_i/70)^{\beta_{Cl}}$$

and the statistical model describes how V_i and Cl_i are distributed around these predicted values:

$$\log(V_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(\bar{V}_i), \omega_V^2) \quad \text{and} \quad \log(Cl_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\log(\bar{Cl}_i), \omega_{Cl}^2)$$

Here, $\log(V_i)$ and $\log(Cl_i)$ are linear functions of $\log(w_i/70)$: we then need to transform first the original covariate w_i into $\log(w_i/70)$ by clicking on the button CONTINUOUS next to ADD COVARIATE (blue button). Then, the following pop up arises

Define a new continuous covariate

Available covariates

wt	min: 40
	mean: 70.0031
	median: 71.65
	max: 102
	weighted mean: 67.9436

Name

Formula

You have to

- define the name of the covariate you want to add (the blue frame),
- define the associated equation (the green frame),
- click on the ACCEPT button.

Remarks

- You can define any formula for your covariate as long as you use mathematical functions available in the Mlxtran language.
- You can use any covariate available in the list of covariates proposed in the window. Thus, if you have a Height and Weight as covariates, you can directly compute the Body Mass Index.
- If you go over a covariate with your mouse, all the information (min, mean, median, max and weighted mean) are displayed as a tooltip. The weighted mean is defined as

$$\text{weighted mean}(cov) = \exp \left(\sum_i \frac{\text{nbObs}_i}{\text{nbObs}} \log(cov_i) \right)$$

where nbObs_i is the number of observation for the i -th individual and nbObs is the total number of observations.

- If you click on the covariate name, it will be written in the formula.
- You can use this formula box to replace missing continuous covariate values by an imputed value. For example, if your continuous covariate takes only positive values, you can use a negative value for the missing values in your dataset, for example -99, and enter the following formula: $\max(\text{COV}, 0) + \min(\text{COV}, 0) / \text{COV} * \text{ImputedValue}$ with the desired ImputedValue (COV is the name of your covariate).

We then define a new covariate model, where $\log(V_i)$ and $\log(Cl_i)$ are linear functions of the transformed weight $lw70_i$ as shown on the following figure:

Individual model

FORMULA

log(Tlag) = log(Tlag_pop) + eta_Tlag
 log(ka) = log(ka_pop) + eta_ka
 log(V) = log(V_pop) + beta_V_lw70*lw70 + eta_V
 log(Cl) = log(Cl_pop) + beta_Cl_lw70*lw70 + eta_Cl

ADD COVARIATE: CONTINUOUS DISCRETE MIXTURE

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	#1	sex	wt
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Notice that by clicking on the button FORMULA, you have the display of all the individual model equations. Coefficients β_V and β_{Cl} are now estimated with their s.e. and the p-values of the Wald tests are derived to test if these coefficients are different from 0.

Again, a diagnosis plot Individual parameters vs covariates is generated which displays possible relationships between covariates and individual parameters (even if these covariates are not used in the model) as one can see on the figure below on the left. However, as there are covariates on

the model, what is interesting is to see if there still are correlation between the random effects and the covariates as one can see on the figure below on the right.

Note: To make it automatic, starting from the 2019 version, there is an arrow next (in purple in the next figure) to the continuous covariate from the data set and propose to add a log transformed covariate centered by the weighted mean.

Individual model

FORMULA MODEL BUILDING

Add covariate
CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	SEX	wt
		Select: All None	#1		
Tlag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.2.3.2 Model with categorical covariates

- **warfarin_covariate3_project** (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

We use `sex` instead of `weight` in this project, assuming different population values of volume and clearance for males and females. More precisely, we consider the following model for V_i and Cl_i :

$$\log(V_i) = \log(V_{pop}) + \beta_V \mathbf{1}_{sex_i=F} + \eta_{V,i} \quad \text{and} \quad \log(Cl_i) = \log(Cl_{pop}) + \beta_{Cl} \mathbf{1}_{sex_i=F} + \eta_{Cl,i}$$

where $\mathbf{1}_{sex_i=F} = 1$ if individual i is a female and 0 otherwise. Then, V_{pop} and Cl_{pop} are the population volume and clearance for males while V_{pop}, e^{β_V} and $Cl_{pop}, e^{\beta_{Cl}}$ are the population volume and clearance for females. By clicking on the purple button **DISCRETE**, the following window pops up

Define a new categorical covariate

Function of: **SEX** ▾

Name
tSex

RESET **ALLOCATE**

0 1

CANCEL ACCEPT

You have to

- define the name of the covariate you want to add (the blue frame),
- define the associated categories (the green frame),
- click on the **ALLOCATE** button to define all the categories.

Then, you can

- define the name of the categories (the blue frame),
- define the reference category (the green frame),
- click on **ACCEPT**.

Then, define the covariate model in the main GUI:

Individual model

FORMULA

ADD COVARIATE: CONTINUOUS **DISCRETE** MIXTURE

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	lw70	sex	tsex	wt
		Select: All None	#1				
Tlag	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Estimated population parameters, including the coefficients β_V and β_{Cl} are displayed with the results:

	STOCH. APPROX.			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P-VALUE
Fixed Effects				
Tlag_pop	0.936	0.314	33.5	
ka_pop	1.64	1.64	100	
V_pop	8.53	0.302	3.54	
beta_V_tSex_F	-0.375	0.0837	22.3	7.34e-06
Cl_pop	0.134	0.00766	5.7	
beta_Cl_tSex_F	-0.096	0.143	149	0.501
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects				
omega_Tlag	0.527	0.21	39.8	
omega_ka	0.961	1.23	128	
omega_V	0.163	0.0254	15.5	
omega_Cl	0.288	0.0378	13.1	
Error Model Parameters				
a	0.261	0.0632	24.2	
b	0.0574	0.0112	19.6	

We can display the probability distribution functions of the 4 PK parameters using the Individual parameter graphic:

Notice that for the volume and the clearance, the theoretical curve is not the PDF of a lognormal distribution, due to the impact of the covariate sex.

4.2.3.2.1 Calculating the typical value for each category

Cl_{pop} represents the typical value for the reference category (in the example above $SEX=0$). The typical value for the other categories can be calculated based on the estimated beta parameters:

- normal distribution: $Cl_{SEX=1} = Cl_{pop} + beta_Cl_SEX_1$
- lognormal distribution: $Cl_{SEX=1} = Cl_{pop} \times e^{beta_Cl_SEX_1}$
- logit distribution:
$$F_{SEX=1} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\left(\log\left(\frac{F_{pop}}{1-F_{pop}}\right) + beta_F_SEX_1\right)}}$$

4.2.3.3 Transforming categorical covariates

- **phenobarbital_project** (data = 'phenobarbital_data.txt', model = 'lib:bolus_1cpt_Vk.txt')

The phenobarbital data contains 2 covariates: the weight and the APGAR score which is considered as a categorical covariate. Instead of using the 10 original levels of the APGAR score, we will transform this categorical covariate and create 3 categories: Low = {1,2,3}, Medium = {4, 5, 6, 7} and High={8,9,10}.

Edit tAPGAR

RESET ALLOCATE

High

Ref.

10

8

9

Low

Ref.

1

2

3

Med

Ref.

4

5

6

7

CANCEL
ACCEPT

If we assume, for instance that the volume is related to the APGAR score, then $\beta_{V,Low}$ and $\beta_{V,High}$ are estimated (assuming that Medium is the reference level).

	STOCH. APPROX.			
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P-VALUE
Fixed Effects				
V_pop	1.26	0.0946	7.51	
beta_V_tAPGAR_High	0.253	0.115	45.5	0.028
beta_V_tAPGAR_Low	0.113	0.171	151	0.508
k_pop	0.0047	0.000227	4.82	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects				
omega_V	0.4	0.0388	9.71	
omega_k	0.165	0.0447	27	
Error Model Parameters				
b	0.114	0.00938	8.24	

In that case, one can see that both p-values concerning the transformed APGAR covariate are over .05.

4.2.3.4 The same covariate effect for several parameters

Adding a covariate effect on a parameter in the Individual Model section of the Statistical Model and Tasks tab, creates automatically a corresponding beta parameter (population parameter) that describes the strength of the effect. For example, adding weight WT on a parameter volume V1 creates beta_V1_WT. If you add the same covariate effect on two different parameters, eg. V1 and V2, then Monolix will create two corresponding parameters: beta_V1_WT and beta_V2_WT.

If you need to add the same covariate effect for several parameters, eg. have only one parameter `betaWT` for both `V1` and `V2` in the example above, then this covariate effect has to be implemented in the structural model directly. It requires:

- Reading weight `WT` from the dataset, so the column `WT` in the dataset has to be tagged as a regressor (not covariate)
- Defining in the model new volumes with the covariate effect (sample code below, based on a two-compartment model from the PK library)

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {WT, betaWT, ka, Cl, V1, Q2, V2}
WT = {use=regressor}

PK:
; Effect of WT on V1, V2
V1_withWT = V1*exp(betaWT*WT)
V2_withWT = V2*exp(betaWT*WT)

; Parameter transformations
V = V1_withWT
k12 = Q2/V1_withWT
k21 = Q2/V2_withWT

; PK model definition
Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl, k12, k21)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

- In the Individual model in the GUI, set normal distribution for “`betaWT`” – to allow positive and negative values, and remove random effects from it – they are already included in the parameters `V1`, `V2`.

This method gives more flexibility for more complex parameter-covariate relationships, also to include time-varying covariates in the model. However, remember that when you add covariate effects in the structural model – the statistical tests are not available for these relationships. Also, Monolix is more efficient when covariate effects are added in the GUI, as the algorithm “see” that `V` and `beta_V_WT` are related, and it improves the stability.

4.2.3.5 Complex covariate-parameter relationships

Note that starting from version 2024 on, analytical solutions are used even if a time-varying regressor is used in the model.

4.2.3.5.1 Complex parameter-covariate relationships and time-dependent continuous covariates

Covariate-parameter relationships are usually defined via the Monolix GUI, leading for instance to exponential and power law relationships. However **more complex parameter-covariate relationships** such as Michaelis-Menten or Hill dependencies cannot be defined via the GUI because they cannot be put into the format where the (possibly transformed) covariate is added linearly on the transformed parameter. Similarly, when **the covariate value is changing over time** and thus not constant for each subject (or each occasion in each subject in case of occasions), the covariate cannot be added to the model via the GUI. In both cases, **the effect of the covariate must be tagged as a regressor and the relationship must be defined directly in the model file.**

In the following, we will use **as an example a Hill relationship** between the clearance parameter Cl and the **time-varying** post-conception age (PCA) covariate, which is a typical way to scale clearance in paediatric pharmacokinetics:

$$Cl_i = Cl_{pop} \frac{PCA^n}{PCA^n + A50^n} e^{\eta_i}$$

where Cl_i is the parameter value for individual i , Cl_{pop} the typical clearance for an adult, $A50$ the PCA for the clearance to reach 50% mature, n the shape parameter and η_i the random effect for individual i .

Step 1: To make the PCA covariate available as a variable in the model file, the first step is to **tag it as a regressor column-type REGRESSOR** when loading the data set (instead of using the CONTINUOUS COVARIATE column-type).

The screenshot shows the Monolix GUI interface. At the top, there is a 'Data' tab and a 'Data file' section with a file path: C:\Users\celena\Workspace\Casa_studies\2017_08_covariates_doc\dummy_data_PCA_WT.csv. Below this is a table with 11 rows and 7 columns. The columns are: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, AMT, Y, PCA, and WT. The PCA column is highlighted with a red box and labeled 'REGRESSOR' in a dropdown menu. The table contains the following data:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMT	Y	PCA	WT
2	1	0	10	-	20	34
3	1	1	-	9.6	20	34
4	1	2	-	7.1	20	34
5	1	3	-	5.5	20	34
6	1	4	-	4.8	20	34
7	1	5	-	3.5	20	34
8	1	6	-	2.9	20	34
9	1	7	-	2	20	34
10	2	0	10	-	56	45
11	2	1	-	8	56	45

At the bottom of the table, there is a 'Showing 1 to 10 of 16 entries' indicator and a 'Next' button. An 'ACCEPT' button is located at the bottom right of the window.

Step 2: In the model file, the **PCA covariate is passed as input argument and designated as being a regressor**. The clearance Cl, the hill shape parameter n, and the A50 are passed as usual input parameters:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {..., Cl, n, A50, PCA, ...}
PCA = {use=regressor}
```

If several regressors are used, be careful that the regressors are matched by order with the data set columns tagged as REGRESSOR (not by name).

The relationship between the clearance Cl and the post-conception age PCA is defined in the EQUATION: block, before ClwithPCA is used (for instance in a simple (V,Cl) model):

```
EQUATION:
ClwithPCA = Cl * PCA^n / (PCA^n + A50^n)

Cc = pkmodel(Cl=ClwithPCA, V)
```

Note that the input parameter `Cl` includes the random effect ($Cl = Cl_{pop}e^{\eta_i}$), such that only the covariate term must be added. Because the parameter including the covariate effect `ClwithPCA` is not a standard keyword for macros, one must write `Cl=ClwithPCA`.

Step 3: The definition of the parameters in the GUI deserves special attention. Indeed the parameters n and A50 characterize the covariate effect and are the same for all individuals: their inter-individual variability must be removed by unselecting the random effects. On the opposite, the parameter Cl keeps its inter-individual variability, corresponding to the e^{η_i} term.

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	WT
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
n	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A50	LOGNORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Step 4: When covariates relationships are not defined via the GUI, **the p-value corresponding to the Wald test is not automatically outputted. It is however possible to calculate it externally.**

Assuming that we would like to test if the shape parameter n is significantly different from 1:

$$H_0 : "n = 1" \quad \text{versus} \quad H_1 : "n \neq 1"$$

Using the parameter estimate and the s.e outputted by Monolix, we can calculate the Wald statistic:

$$W = \frac{\hat{n} - n_{ref}}{\text{s.e.}(\hat{n})}$$

with \hat{n} the estimated value for parameter n , n_{ref} the reference value for n (here 1) and $\text{s.e.}(\hat{n})$ the standard error for the n estimate.

The test statistic W can then be compared to a standard normal distribution. Below we propose a simple R script to calculate the p-value:

```
n_estimated = 1.32
n_ref = 1
se_n = 0.12

W = abs(n_estimated - n_ref)/se_n

pvalue = 2 * pnorm(W, mean = 0, sd = 1, lower.tail = FALSE)
```

Note that the factor 2 is added to do a two-sided test.

4.2.3.5.2 Categorical time-varying covariates

Categorical covariates may also be time-varying, for instance when the covariate represents concomitant medications over the course of the clinical trial or a fed/fasting state at the time of the dose.

In the following, we will use **as an example a concomitant medication categorical covariate with 3 categories:** no concomitant drug, concomitant drug 1, and concomitant drug 2. We would like to investigate the effect of the concomitant drug covariate on the clearance Cl .

$$Cl_i = \begin{cases} Cl_{pop} e^{\eta_i} & \text{if no concomitant drug} \\ Cl_{pop} (1 + \beta_1) e^{\eta_i} & \text{if concomitant drug 1} \\ Cl_{pop} (1 + \beta_2) e^{\eta_i} & \text{if concomitant drug 2} \end{cases}$$

where Cl_i is the parameter value for individual i , Cl_{pop} the typical clearance if no concomitant drug, β_1 the fractional change in case of concomitant drug 1, β_2 the fractional change in case of concomitant drug 2 and η_i the random effect for individual i .

Step 1: Encode the categorical covariate as integers. Indeed, while strings are accepted for the CATEGORICAL COVARIATE column-type, only numbers are accepted for the REGRESSOR column-type. Here we will use 0 = no concomitant medication, 1 = concomitant drug 1 and 2 = concomitant drug 2.

Step 2: To make the COMED covariate available as a variable in the model file, **tag it as a column-type REGRESSOR** when loading the data set (instead of using the CATEGORICAL COVARIATE column-type).

Untitled* - Monolix - 2018R1

Project Help

Welcome Data Structural model

Data file
C:/Users/cellere/Workspace/documentation/monolix/complex_cov_param/data_COMED.csv

BROWSE...

Records per page: 10 25 50 100

	ID ▾	TIME ▾	AMOUNT ▾	OBSERVATION ▾ CONTINUOUS ▾	REGRESSOR ▾
LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMT	Y	COMED
2	1	0	10		0
3	1	1	.	10.6	0
4	1	2	.	8.4	0
5	1	4	.	6.3	0
6	1	6	.	5.2	0
7	1	8	.	4.9	0
8	1	11.9	.	4	0
9	1	12	10		1
10	1	13	.	11.1	1
11	1	14	.	8.5	1

Showing 1 to 10 of 13 entries

Previous 1 2 Next

ACCEPT

Step 3: In the model file, the **COMED covariate is passed as input argument and designated as being a regressor**. The clearance Cl, and the two beta parameters are passed as usual input parameters:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {..., Cl, beta1, beta2, COMED, ...}
COMED = {use=regressor}
```

If several regressors are used, be careful that the regressors are matched by order with the data set columns tagged as REGRESSOR (not by name).

To define the COMED covariate impact, **we use a if/else statement** in the EQUATION: block. The parameter value taking into account the COMED effect (called `ClwithCOMED` in this example) can then be used in an ODE system or within macros.

```
EQUATION:
if COMED==0
ClwithCOMED = Cl
elseif COMED==1
ClwithCOMED = Cl * (1+beta1)
else
ClwithCOMED = Cl * (1+beta2)
end

Cc = pkmodel(Cl=ClwithCOMED, V)
```

Note that the input parameter `Cl` includes the random effect ($Cl = Cl_{pop}e^{\eta_i}$), such that only the covariate term must be added. Because the parameter including the covariate effect `ClwithCOMED` is not a standard keyword for macros, one must write `Cl=ClwithCOMED`.

If the categorical covariate has only two categories encoded as 0 and 1 (for instance `COMED=0` for no concomitant medication and `COMED=1` for concomitant medication), it is also possible to write the model in a more compact form:

```
ClwithCOMED = Cl * (1 + beta * COMED)
```

Step 4: The definition of the parameters in the GUI deserves special attention. Indeed the parameters `beta1` and `beta2` characterize the covariate effect and are the same for all individuals: their inter-individual variability must be removed by unselecting the random effects. On the opposite, the parameter `Cl` keeps its inter-individual variability, corresponding to the e^{η_i} term. In addition, we choose a normal distribution for `beta1` and `beta2` (with a standard deviation of zero as we have removed the random effects) in order to allow both positive and negative values.

The screenshot shows the Monolix 2018R1 interface. The 'Statistical model & Tasks' tab is active. In the 'Individual model' section, there is a table with the following data:

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION
Ci	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	#1
beta1	NORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	
beta2	NORMAL	<input type="checkbox"/>	
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

4.2.3.5.3 Covariate-dependent parameter

When adding a categorical covariate on a parameter via the GUI, different typical values will be estimated for each group. However, all groups will have the same standard deviation. It can sometimes be useful to consider that the standard deviations also differ between groups. For example, healthy volunteers may have a smaller inter-individual variability than patients.

From the 2018R1 version on, categorical covariates affecting both the typical value and the standard deviation have to be defined directly in the structural model, by using the covariate as a regressor and different parameters depending on the value of the regressor. Using a different parameter for each group permits to estimate a typical value and a standard deviation per group. Note that a regressor can contain only numbers, so the categorical covariate should be encoded with integers rather than strings.

We show below an example, where the fixed effect and standard deviation of the volume V both depend on the covariate SEX . This requires the definition of two different parameters VM (for male) and VF (for female).

Step 1: To make the covariate SEX available as a variable in the model file, it has to be **tagged as a regressor with column-type REGRESSOR** when loading the data set (instead of using the CONTINUOUS COVARIATE and CATEGORICAL COVARIATE column-types).

Untitled* - Monolix - 2018R2

Project Help

Welcome Data Structural model

Data file
C:/Users/paul/Desktop/data.csv
BROWSE...

Records per page: 10 25 50 100

	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	REGRESSOR
LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMT	DV	AGE	SEX
2	1	0	1439.8	.	30.58	1
3	1	1.5	.	9.51	30.58	1
4	1	2	.	11.5	30.58	1
5	1	2.52	.	14.1	30.58	1
6	1	3.02	.	16.7	30.58	1
7	1	3.63	.	17.1	30.58	1
8	1	4.05	.	16.8	30.58	1
9	1	5.02	.	18.7	30.58	1
10	1	6.02	.	14.2	30.58	1
11	1	7.03	.	15.8	30.58	1

Showing 1 to 10 of 1,000 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 100 Next

ACCEPT

Step 2: In the model file shown below, the **covariate SEX is passed as input argument and designated as being a regressor. Two parameters VM (for male) and VF (for female) are given as input**, to be used as the volume V depending on the SEX. The use of VM or VF depending on the SEX value is defined in the EQUATION: block, before V is used (for instance in a simple (V,C1) model):

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {Cl, VM, VF, SEX}
SEX = {use=regressor}

EQUATION:
if SEX==0
V = VM
else
V = VF
end

Cc = pkmodel(Cl, V)

OUTPUT:
output = {Cc}
```

Step 3: The distribution of the parameters VM and VF is set as usual in the GUI. A different typical population value and a different standard deviation of the random effects will be estimated for males and females.

Note: As SEX has been tagged as a regressor, it is not available as a covariate in the GUI. If a covariate effect of SEX on another parameter is needed, the column SEX can be duplicated in the dataset so that the duplicate can be tagged as a covariate.

4.2.3.5.4 Transforming a continuous covariate into a categorical covariate

The Monolix GUI allows to discretize a continuous covariate in order to handle it as a categorical covariate in the model, using binary 0/1 values.

4.2.4 Inter-occasion variability

Objectives: learn how to take into account inter occasion variability (IOV).

Projects: iov1_project, iov1_Evid_project, iov2_project, iov3_project, iov4_project

4.2.4.1 Introduction

A simple model consists of splitting the study into K time periods or *occasions* and assuming that individual parameters can vary from occasion to occasion but remain constant within occasions. Then, we can try to explain part of the *intra-individual* variability of the individual parameters by piecewise-constant covariates, i.e., *occasion-dependent* or *occasion-varying* (varying from occasion to occasion and constant within an occasion) ones. The remaining part must then be described by random effects. We will need some additional notation to describe this new statistical model. Let

- ψ_{ik} be the vector of individual parameters of individual i for occasion k , where $1 \leq i \leq N$ and $1 \leq k \leq K$.
- c_{ik} be the vector of covariates of individual i for occasion k . Some of these covariates remain constant (gender, group treatment, ethnicity, etc.) and others can vary (weight, treatment, etc.).

Let $\psi_i = (\psi_{i1}, \psi_{i2}, \dots, \psi_{iK})$ be the sequence of K individual parameters for individual i . We also need to define:

- $\eta_i^{(0)}$, the vector of random effects which describes the random *inter-individual variability* of the individual parameters,
- $\eta_{ik}^{(1)}$, the vector of random effects which describes the random *intra-individual variability* of the individual parameters in occasion k , for each $1 \leq k \leq K$.

Here and in the following, the superscript (0) is used to represent *inter-individual variability*, i.e., variability at the individual level, while superscript (1) represents *inter-occasion variability*, i.e., variability at the occasion level for each individual. The model now combines these two sequences of random effects:

$$h(\psi_{ik}) = h(\psi_{pop}) + \beta(c_{ik} - c_{pop}) + \eta_i^{(0)} + \eta_{ik}^{(1)}$$

i Individuals do not need to share the same sequence of occasions: the number of occasions and the times defining the occasions can differ from one individual to another.

4.2.4.2 Occasion definition in a data set

There are two ways to define occasions in a data set:

- Explicitly using an OCCASION column. It is possible to have, in a data set, one or several columns with the column-type OCCASION. It corresponds to the same subject (ID should remain the same) but under different circumstances, occasions. For example, if the same subject has two successive different treatments, it should be considered as the same subject with two occasions. The OCC columns can contain only integers.
- Implicitly using EVID column. If there is an EVID column with a value 4 then Monolix defines a washout and creates an occasion. Thus, if there are several times where EVID equals 4 for a subject, it will create the same number of occasions. Notice that if EVID equals 4 happens only once at the beginning, only one occasion will be defined and no inter occasion variability would be possible.

There are three kinds of occasions

- **Cross over study:** In that case, data is collected for each patient during two independent treatment periods of time, there is an overlap on the time definition of the periods. A column OCCASION can be used to identify the period. An alternative way is to define an EVID column starting for all occasions with EVID equals 4. Both types of definition will be presented in the iov1 example.
- **Occasions with washout:** In that case, data is collected for each patient during one period and there is no overlap between the periods. The time is increasing but the dynamical system (i.e. the compartments) is reset when the second period starts. In particular, EVID=4 indicates that the system is reset (washout) for example, when a new dose is administrated.
- **Occasions without washout:** In that case, data is collected for each patient during one period and there is no overlap between the periods. The time is increasing and we want to differentiate periods in terms of occasions without any reset of the dynamical system. Multiple doses are administrated to each patient. each period of time between successive doses is defined as a statistical occasion. A column OCCASION is therefore necessary in the data file to define it.

4.2.4.3 Cross over study

- **iov1_project** (data = 'iov1_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVk.txt')

In this example, PK data is collected for each patient during two independent treatment periods of time (each one starting at time 0). A column OCCASION is used to identify the study:

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS	AMOUNT	OCCASION	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	Time	Y		DOSE	OCC	TREAT	SEX
1	0	.		4	1	A	M
1	0.25	2.1243964		.	1	A	M
1	0.5	4.308573		.	1	A	M
1	1	7.6059305		.	1	A	M
1	2	6.9678311		.	1	A	M
1	3.5	7.7741686		.	1	A	M
1	5	7.2018224		.	1	A	M
1	7	6.5708042		.	1	A	M
1	9	5.0258613		.	1	A	M
1	12	5.0740874		.	1	A	M
1	24	1.5194051		.	1	A	M
1	0	.		4	2	B	M
1	0.25	4.2049182		.	2	B	M

This column is defined using the reserved keyword OCCASION. Then, the model associated to the individual parameter is as presented below

PARAMETERS		DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS		ID	CORRELATION	SEX	RANDOM EFFECTS		OCC	CORRELATION	TREAT
			Select: All None			#1		Select: All None			#1	
k _a	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
C _i	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

First, to define the variability of each parameter on each level, you just have to go on the good level, and you'll see the associated random effects on each level. On the figure above, we see that all parameters have variability on the ID level, which means that all parameters have inter-individual variability. On the figure below, we see the OCC level. In the presented case, only the volume V has inter-study variability and thus inter occasion variability. Thus, this is the only one having variability on the occasion level.

In terms of covariates, we then see two parts as displayed below. We see the covariates

- associated to the level ID (in green). It corresponds to all the covariates that are constant for each subject.
- associated to the level OCC (in blue). It corresponds to all the covariates that are constant for each occasion but not on each subject.

In the presented case, the treatment TRT varies for each individual. It contains inter-occasion information and is thus displayed with the occasion level. On the other hand, the SEX is constant for each subject. It contains then inter-individual information but no inter-occasion information. It is then displayed with the ID level.

Individual model

FORMULA

Add covariate DISCRETE

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS		CORRELATION +	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION +	TREAT
		Select: All None	#1				
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Covariates can be associated to the parameter if and only if their level of variability is coherent with the level of variability of the parameter.

In the presented case,

- TRT has inter-occasion variability. It can only be used with the parameter V that has inter-occasion variability. The two other parameters have only inter-individual variability and can therefore not use this TRT information. The interface is greyed and the user can not add this covariate to the parameters ka and Cl.
- SEX has only inter-individual variability. It can therefore be associated to any parameter that has inter-individual variability.

The population parameters now include the standard deviations of the random effects for the 2 levels of variability (ω is used for IIV and γ for IOV):

Two important features are proposed in the plots. Firstly, in the individual fits, you can split or merge the occasions. When split is done, the name of the subject-occasion is the name of the subject, #, and the name of the occasion.

Secondly, you can use the occasion to split the plots

- **iov1_Evid_project** (data = 'iov1_Evid_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kavk.txt')

Another way to describe this cross over study is to use `EVID=4` as explained in the data set definition. In that example, the EVID creates a washout and another occasion.

ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS	AMOUNT	EVENT ID	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	Time	Y		DOSE	EVID	TREAT	SEX
1	0	.		4	1	A	M
1	0.25	2.1243964		.	0	A	M
1	0.5	4.308573		.	0	A	M
1	1	7.6059305		.	0	A	M
1	2	6.9678311		.	0	A	M
1	3.5	7.7741686		.	0	A	M
1	5	7.2018224		.	0	A	M
1	7	6.5708042		.	0	A	M
1	9	5.0258613		.	0	A	M
1	12	5.0740874		.	0	A	M
1	24	1.5194051		.	0	A	M
1	0	.		4	4	B	M
1	0.25	4.2049182		.	0	B	M

4.2.4.4 Occasions with washout

- **iov2_project** (data = 'iov2_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVk.txt')

The time is increasing in this example, but the dynamical system (i.e. the compartments) is reset when the second period starts. Column **EVID** provides some information about events concerning dose administration. In particular, **EVID=4** indicates that the system is reset (washout) when a new dose is administrated

Monolix automatically proposes to define the treatment periods (between successive resetting) as statistical occasions and introduce IOV, as we did in the previous example. We can display the individual fit by splitting each occasion for each individual

Or by merging the different occasions in a unique plot for each individual:

Remark: If you are modeling a PK as in this example, the washout implies that the occasions are independent. Thus, the CPU time is much faster as we do not have to compute predictions between occasions.

4.2.4.5 Occasions without washout

- **iov3_project** (data = 'iov3_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kavk.txt')

Multiple doses are administrated to each patient. We consider each period of time between successive doses as a statistical occasion. A column `OCCASION` is therefore necessary in the data file.

We can color the observed data by their occasion to have a better representation:

The model for IIV and IOV can then be defined as usual. The plot of individual fits allows us to check that the predicted concentration is now continuous over the different occasions for each individual:

4.2.4.6 Multiple levels of occasions

- **iov4_project** (data = 'iov4_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVk.txt')

We can easily extend such an approach to multiple levels of variability. In this example, columns P1 and P2 define embedded occasions. They are both defined as occasions:

ID	OCCASION	OCCASION	IGNORE	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
ID	P1	P2	PER	TIME	AMT	Y	
1	2	1	4	0.0	5	.	
1	2	1	4	0.5	.	3.3549	
1	2	1	4	2.0	.	7.1957	
1	2	1	4	6.0	.	5.1769	
1	2	1	4	10.0	.	4.7589	
1	2	1	4	15.0	.	2.0915	
1	2	1	4	21.0	.	1.1401	
1	2	3	6	0.0	6	.	
1	2	3	6	0.5	.	4.4001	
1	2	3	6	2.0	.	7.8282	

We then define a statistical model for each level of variability.

Individual model

FORMULA

```
log(ka) = log(ka_pop) + eta_ID_ka + eta_P1_ka + eta_P2_ka
log(V) = log(V_pop) + eta_ID_V + eta_P1_V + eta_P2_V
log(Cl) = log(Cl_pop) + eta_ID_Cl + eta_P1_Cl + eta_P2_Cl
```

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	ID		P1		P2	
		RANDOM EFFECTS Select: All None	- CORRELATION + #1	RANDOM EFFECTS Select: All None	- CORRELATION + #1	RANDOM EFFECTS Select: All None	- CORRELATION + #1
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.2.5 Mixture of distributions

Objectives: learn how to implement a mixture of distributions for the individual parameters.

Projects: PKgroup_project, PKmixt_project

4.2.5.1 Introduction

Mixed effects models allow us to take into account between-subject variability.

One complicating factor arises when data is obtained from a population with some underlying heterogeneity. If we assume that the population consists of several homogeneous subpopulations, a straightforward extension of mixed effects models is a finite mixture of mixed effects models.

There are two approaches to define a mixture of models:

- defining a **mixture of structural models** (via a regressor or via the bsmm function),
- introducing a **categorical covariate** (known or latent). This approach is detailed here.

The second approach assumes that the probability distribution of some individual parameters vary from one subpopulation to another one. The introduction of a categorical covariate (e.g., sex, phenotype, treatment, status, etc.) into such a model already supposes that the whole population can be decomposed into subpopulations. The covariate then serves as a *label* for assigning each individual to a subpopulation.

In practice, the covariate can either be known or not. If it is unknown, the covariate is called a latent covariate and is defined as a random variable with a user-defined number of modalities in the statistical model. Differences in estimation and diagnosis methods appear to deal with this additional random variable: this difference represents a task of unsupervised classification.

Mixture models usually refer to models for which the categorical covariate is unknown and unsupervised classification is needed.

For the sake of simplicity, we will consider a basic model that involves individual parameters $(\psi_i, 1 \leq i \leq N)$ and observations $(y_{ij}, i \leq N, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$. Then, the easiest way to model a finite mixture model is to introduce a label sequence $(z_i, 1 \leq i \leq N)$ that takes its values in $\{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ such that $z_i = m$ if subject i belongs to subpopulation m .

In some situations, the label sequence $(z_i, 1 \leq i \leq N)$ is known and can be used as a categorical covariate in the model. If (z_i) is unknown, it can be modeled as a set of independent random

variables taking their values in $\{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ where for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, $P(z_i = m)$ is the probability that individual i belongs to group m . We will assume furthermore that the (z_i) are identically distributed, i.e., $P(z_i = m)$ does not depend on i for $m = 1, \dots, M$.

4.2.5.2 Mixture of distributions based on a categorical covariate

- **PKgroup_project** (data = 'PKmixt_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt')

The sequence of labels is known as **GROUP** in this project and comes from the dataset. It is therefore defined as a categorical covariate that classifies. We can then assume, for instance different population values for the volume in the two groups and estimate the population parameters using this covariate model.

STOCH. APPROX.				
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P-VALUE
Fixed Effects				
ka_pop	1.01	0.0259	2.57	
V_pop	68.5	1.7	2.48	
beta_V_GROUP_1	-0.514	0.0386	7.51	<2.2e-16
Cl_pop	4	0.0698	1.75	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects				
omega_ka	0.202	0.0222	11	
omega_V	0.179	0.0135	7.56	
omega_Cl	0.167	0.0129	7.74	
Error Model Parameters				
b	0.199	0.00358	1.8	

Then, this covariate **GROUP** can be used as a stratification variable and is very important in the modeling.

4.2.5.3 Mixture of distributions based on unsupervised classification with a latent covariate

A latent covariate is defined as a random variable, and the probability of each modality is part of the statistical model and is estimated as well. Methods for estimation and diagnosis are different. After the estimation, for each individual the categorical covariate is not perfectly known, only the probabilities of each modality are estimated.

Note also that latent covariates can be useful to model statistical mixtures of populations, but they provide no biological interpretation for the cause of the heterogeneity in the population since they do not come from the dataset.

Latent covariates can not be handled with IOV.

- **PKmixt_project** (data = 'PKmixt_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt')

We will use the same data with this project but ignoring the column `GROUP` (which is equivalent to assuming that the label is unknown). If we suspect some heterogeneity in the population, we can introduce a "latent covariate" by clicking on the grey button LATENT.

Define a new latent covariate

Name

lcat

Number of modalities

2

CANCEL

ACCEPT

It is possible to change the name and the number of modalities of this latent covariate.

Several latent covariates can be introduced in the model, with different number of categories.

We can then use this latent covariate `lcat` as any observed categorical covariate. Again, we can assume again different population values for the volume in the two groups by applying it on the volume random effect and estimating the population parameters using this covariate model. Proportions of each group are also estimated, `plcat_1` which is the probability to have modality 1:

STOCH. APPROX.				
	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P-VALUE
Fixed Effects				
ka_pop	1.01	0.0262	2.6	
V_pop	40.1	2.02	5.03	
beta_V_Icat_2	0.503	0.0478	9.5	<2.2e-16
Cl_pop	4	0.0707	1.77	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects				
omega_ka	0.205	0.0227	11.1	
omega_V	0.182	0.0197	10.8	
omega_Cl	0.169	0.0128	7.57	
Error Model Parameters				
b	0.199	0.0036	1.8	
Latent Probabilities				
pIcat_1	0.343	0.0715	20.9	
pIcat_2	0.657	0.0715	10.9	

Once the population parameters are estimated, the sequence of latent covariates, i.e. the group to which belongs each subject, can be estimated together with the individual parameters, as the modes of the conditional distributions.

The sequence of estimated latent covariates Icat can be used as a stratification variable. We can for example display the VPC in the 2 groups:

By plotting the distribution of the individual parameters, we see that V has a bimodal distribution:

5 Tasks and results

5.1 Overview

5.1.1 Monolix tasks

Monolix allows a workflow with several tasks.

On the interface, one can see six different tasks

- POP. PARAM.: it corresponds to the estimation of the population parameters,
- EBEs: it corresponds to the estimation of the individual parameters using the conditional mode, i.e. the most probable individual parameters.
- CONDITIONAL DISTRIBUTION: It corresponds to the draws individual parameters based on the conditional distribution. It allows to compute the mean value of the conditional distribution.
- STD. ERRORS.: it corresponds to the calculation of the Fisher information matrix and standard errors. Two methods are proposed for it. Either using the linearization method or using the stochastic approximation. The choice between those methods is done with the “Use linearization method” toggle under the tasks.
- LIKELIHOOD: it corresponds to the explicit calculation of the log-likelihood. A specificity of the SAEM algorithm is that it does not explicitly compute the objective function. Thus, a dedicated task is proposed. Two methods are proposed for it. Either using the linearization method or using the importance sampling. The choice between those methods is done with the “Use linearization method” toggle under the tasks. This toggle is for both STD ERRORS and LIKELIHOOD tasks to be more relevant.
- PLOTS: it corresponds to the generation of the plots.

Also, different types of results are available in the form of plots and tables. The tasks can be run individually by clicking on the associated button, or you can define a workflow by clicking on the tasks to run (on the small light blue checks) and click on the play button (in green) as proposed on the figure below.

Notice that you can initialize all the parameters and the associated methods in the “Initial Estimates” frame as described here.

Moreover, Monolix includes a convergence assessment tool. It is possible to execute a workflow as defined above but for different, randomly generated, initial values of fixed effects.

5.1.2 Monolix results

All the output files are detailed here.

5.1.3 Monolix-R functions

Monolix has an API leading to the possibility to have access to the project exactly by the same way as you would do with the interface. All the functions are described here.

5.2 Estimation tasks

The following pages describe the Estimation perspective tasks in Monolix in more detail:

5.2.1 Initialization

5.2.1.1 Initial estimates

5.2.1.1.1 Parameter initial estimates and associated methods

Initial values are specified for the fixed effects, for the standard deviations of the random effects and for the residual error parameters. These initial values are available through the frame “Initial estimates” of the interface as can be seen on the following figure. It is recommended to initialize the estimation to have faster convergence.

Initial estimates

Check initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	$k_{a_{pop}}$	1		ω_{ka} 1
v	V_{pop}	0.5		ω_v 1
cl	Cl_{pop}	0.1		ω_{cl} 1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

5.2.1.1.2 Initialization of the estimates

5.2.1.1.2.1 Initialization of the "Fixed effects"

The user can modify all the initial values of the fixed effects. When initializing the project, the values are set by default to 1. To change it, the user can click on the parameter and change the value

Initial estimates

Check initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	$k_{a_{pop}}$	0.2		ω_{ka} 1
v	V_{pop}	0.5		ω_v 1
cl	Cl_{pop}	0.1		ω_{cl} 1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

Notice that when you click on the parameter, an information is provided to tell what value is possible. The constraint depends on the distribution chosen for the parameter. For example, if the volume parameter V is defined as lognormal, its initial value should be strictly greater than 0. In that case, if you set a negative value, an error will be thrown and the previous parameter will be displayed.

When a parameter depends on a covariate, initial values for the dependency (named with β prefix, for instance $\beta_{V_SEX_M}$ to add the dependency of SEX, on parameter V) are displayed. The default initial value is 0. In case of a continuous covariate, the covariate is added linearly to the transformed parameter, with a coefficient β . For categorical covariates, the initial value for the reference category will be the one of the fixed effect, while for all other categories it will be the initial value for the fixed effect plus the initial value of the β , in the transformed parameter space. It is possible to define different initial values for the non-reference categories. The equations for the parameters can be visualized by clicking on button formula in the “Statistical model & Tasks” frame.

5.2.1.1.2.2 Initialization of the “Standard deviation of the random effects”

The user can modify all the initial values of the standard deviations of the random effects. The default value is set to 1. We recommend to keep these values high in order for SAEM to have the possibility to explore the domain.

5.2.1.1.2.3 Initialization of the “Residual error parameters”

The user can modify all the initial values of the residual error parameters. There are as many lines as continuous outputs of the model. The default value depends on the parameter (1 for “a”, 0.3 for “b” and 1 for “c”).

5.2.1.1.2.4 What method can I use for the parameters estimations?

For all the parameters, there are several methods for the estimation

- “Fixed”: the parameter is kept to its initial value and so, it will not be estimated. In that case, the parameter name is set to orange.
- “Maximum Likelihood Estimation”: The parameter is estimated using maximum likelihood. In that case, the parameter name remains grey. This is the default option
- “Maximum A Posteriori Estimation”: The parameter is estimated using maximum a posteriori estimation. In that case, the user has to define both a typical value and a standard deviation. For more about this, see here. In that case, the parameter name is colored in purple.

To change the method, click on the right of the parameter as on the following.

Initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	ka _{pop}	0.2		ω _{ka} 1
v	V _{pop}	0.5		ω _v 1
cl	Cl _{pop}	0.1		ω _{cl} 1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

A window pops up to choose the method as on the following figure:

Initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population dist

PARAMETERS

				STD. DEVIATIONS
ka				1
v				1
cl	Cl _{pop}	0.1		1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

Select method

- Fixed
- Maximum Likelihood Estimation
- Maximum A Posteriori Estimation

CLOSE

Notice that there are buttons to fix all the parameters or estimate all on the top right of the window as can be seen on the following figure:

Initial estimates

Check initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	$k_{a_{pop}}$	0.2		ω_{ka} 1
v	V_{pop}	0.5		ω_v 1
cl	Cl_{pop}	0.1		ω_{cl} 1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

5.2.1.1.3 How to initialize your parameters?

5.2.1.1.3.1 On the use of last estimates

If you have already estimated the population parameters for this project, then you can use the “Use the last estimates” buttons to use the previous estimates as initial values. The user has the possibility to use all the last estimates or only the fixed effects. The interest of using only the fixed effects is not to have too low initial standard effects and thus let SAEM explore a larger domain for the next run.

Initial estimates

Check initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS		POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS		SEX
ka	ka _{pop}	0.2		ω _{ka}	1	
v	V _{pop}	0.5		ω _v	1	β _{v,SEX,M} 0
cl	Cl _{pop}	0.1		ω _{cl}	1	

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

Check initial fixed effects

When clicking on the “Check the initial fixed effects”, the simulations obtained with the initial population fixed effects values are displayed for each individual together with the data points, in case of continuous observations. It allows also an automatic initialization in case of a model of the PK library as described here.

5.2.1.2 Check initial estimates and auto-init

5.2.1.2.1 Check initial fixed effects

The subtab “Check initial estimates” is part of the tab “Initial estimates”.

When clicking on the “Check the initial estimates”, the simulations obtained with the initial population fixed effects values and the individual designs (doses and regressors) are displayed for each individual together with the data points, in case of continuous observations. This feature is very useful to find some “good” initial values. Although Monolix is quite robust with respect to initial parameter values, good initial estimates speed up the estimation. You can change the values of the parameters on the bottom of the screen and see how the agreement with the data change. In addition, you can change the axis to log-scale and choose the same limit on all axes to have a better comparison of the individuals. When you are confident with the initial values, you should click on the “SET AS INITIAL VALUES” button on the top of the frame to validate the selection.

In addition, if you think that there are not enough points for the prediction (if there are a lot of doses for example), you can change the discretization and increase the number of points as displayed in the blue box of the figure.

If several observation ids have been mapped to model outputs (for example a parent and a metabolite, or a PK and a PD observation), you can select which output to look at under the output section on the right:

5.2.1.2.2 Using the reference in the “check initial estimates”

Starting from the 2019 version, it is possible to add a reference and thus change a parameter to see the impact of the variation of this parameter. In this example, we click on reference to use the current fit as reference and change k_{12} from 1 to 2 as can be seen on the following figure.

The solid red curve corresponds to the current curve and the dashed one corresponds to the reference. At any time, you can change the reference to use the current fit, and restore and delete the reference or delete all references by clicking on the icons at the top right of the frame.

5.2.1.2.3 Automatic initialization of the parameters

Starting from the 2021 version, an auto-init section appears on the right side of the frame:

By clicking on RUN, Monolix will compute initial population parameters that best fit the data points, starting from parameter values currently used in the initial estimates panel, and using the data from the 12 first individuals by default, and from all observations mapped to a model output. It is possible to change the set of individuals used in the Ids selection panel just below the RUN button.

The computation is done with a custom optimization method, on the pooled data, without inter-individual variability. The purpose is not to find a perfect match but rather to have all the parameters in the good range for starting the population modeling approach. While auto-init is running, we show the evolution of the cost of the optimization algorithm over the iterations. It is possible to stop the algorithm at any time if you find the cost has decreased sufficiently and you want to have a look at the parameter values. Note that the more individuals are selected, the longer the run will take. Moreover, it may be easier for the auto-init algorithm to find a point in the parameter space that is sensitive to specific model features (eg a third compartment, a complex absorption) if you select only a few individuals (1-3 for instance) for which this feature can be observed.

After clicking on the button, the population parameters are updated and the corresponding fit is displayed. To use these parameters as initial estimates, you need to click on the button "SET AS INITIAL VALUES". A new reference appears with previous parameter values so that you can come back to previous values if you are not satisfied with the fit.

Note that the auto-init procedure takes into account the current initial values. Therefore, in the few cases where the auto-init might give poor results, it is possible to improve the results by changing manually the parameter values before running the auto-init again.

5.2.2 Population parameters

5.2.2.1 SAEM

5.2.2.1.1 Purpose

The estimation of the population parameters is the key task in non-linear mixed effect modeling. In Monolix, it is performed using the **Stochastic Approximation Expectation-Maximization (SAEM) algorithm** [1]. SAEM has been shown to be extremely efficient for both simple and a wide variety of complex models: categorical data [2], count data [3], time-to-event data [4], mixture models [5–6], differential equation based models, censored data [7], ... The convergence of SAEM has been rigorously

proven [1] and its implementation in Monolix is particularly efficient. No other algorithms are available in Monolix.

5.2.2.1.2 Calculations: the SAEM algorithm

5.2.2.1.3 Running the population parameter estimation task

5.2.2.1.3.1 Overview

The pop-up window which permits to follow the progress of the task is shown below. The algorithm starts with a small number (5 by default) of burn-in iterations for initialization which are displayed in the following way: (note that **this step can be so fast that it is not visible by the user**).

Afterwards, the evolution of the value for each population parameter over the iterations of the algorithm is displayed. The **red line** marks the switch from the exploratory phase to the smoothing phase. The exact value at each iterations can be followed by hovering over the curve (as for Cl_{pop} below). The **convergence indicator** (in purple) helps to detect that convergence has been reached (see below for more details).

5.2.2.1.3.2 Dependencies between tasks

The “Population parameter” estimation task must be launched before running any other task. To skip this task, the user can fix all population parameters. If all population parameters have been set to “fixed”, the estimation will stop after a single iteration and allow the user to continue with the other tasks.

5.2.2.1.3.3 The convergence indicator

The **convergence indicator** (also sometimes called complete likelihood) is defined as the joint probability distribution of the data and the individual parameters and can be decomposed using Bayes law:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{ind}}} \log(p(y_i, \phi_i; \theta)) = p(y_i | \psi_i; \theta) p(\psi_i; \theta)$$

Those two terms have an analytical expression and are easy to calculate, using as ϕ_i the individual parameters drawn by MCMC for the current iteration of SAEM. This quantity is calculated at each SAEM step and is useful to assess the convergence of the SAEM algorithm.

The convergence indicator aggregates the information from all parameters and can serve to detect if the SAEM algorithm has already converged or not. When the indicator is stable, that is it oscillates around the same value without drifting, then we can be pretty confident that the maximum likelihood has been achieved. The convergence indicator is used, among other measures, in the auto-stop criteria to switch from the exploratory phase to the smoothing phase.

Note that the likelihood (i.e the objective function) $\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{ind}}} \log(p(y_i; \theta))$ cannot be computed in closed form because the individual parameters ϕ_i are unobserved. It requires to integrate over all possible values of the individual parameters. Thus, to estimate the log-likelihood an importance sampling Monte Carlo method is used in a separate task (or an approximation is calculated via linearization of the model).

5.2.2.1.3.4 The simulated annealing

The simulated annealing option (setting enabled by default) permits to keep the explored parameter space large for a longer time (compared to without simulated annealing). This allows to escape local maximums and improve the convergence towards the global maximum.

In practice, the simulated annealing option constrains the variance of the random effects and the residual error parameters to decrease by maximum 5% (by default – the setting “Decreasing rate” can be changed) from one iteration to the next one. As a consequence, the variances decrease more slowly:

The size of the parameter space explored by the SAEM algorithm depends on individual parameters sampled from their conditional distribution via Markov Chain Monte Carlo. If the standard deviation of the conditional distributions is large, the individual parameters sampled at iteration k can be quite far away from those at iteration $(k-1)$, meaning a large exploration of the parameter space. The standard deviation of the conditional distribution depends on the standard deviation of the random effects (population parameters ‘omega’). Indeed, the conditional distribution is $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ with ψ_i the individual parameters for individual i , $\hat{\theta}$ the estimated population parameters, and y_i the data (observations) for individual i . The conditional distribution thus depends on the population parameters,

and the larger the population parameters 'omega', the larger the standard deviation of the conditional distribution. That's why we want to keep large 'omega' values during the first iterations.

5.2.2.1.3.5 Methods for the parameters without variability

Parameters without variability are not estimated in the same way as parameters with variability. Indeed, the SAEM algorithm requires to draw parameter values from their marginal distribution, which exists only for parameters with variability.

Several methods can be used to estimate the parameters without variability. By default, these parameters are optimized using the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm (Matlab's `fminsearch` method). Other options are also available in the SAEM settings:

- **No variability** (default): optimization via Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm
- **Add decreasing variability**: an artificial variability (i.e random effects) is added for these parameters, allowing estimation via SAEM. The variability starts at $\omega=1$ and is progressively decreased such that at the end of the estimation process, the parameter has a variability of $1e-5$. The decrease in variability is exponential with a rate based on the maximum number of iterations for both the exploratory and smoothing phases. Note that if the autostop is triggered, the resulting variability might be higher.
- **Variability at the first stage**: during the exploratory phase of SAEM, an artificial variability is added and progressively forced to $1e-5$ (same as above). In the smoothing phase, the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm is used.

Depending on the specific project, one or the other method may lead to a better convergence. If the default method does not provide satisfying results, it is worth trying the other methods. In terms of computing time, if all parameters are without variability, the first option will be faster because only the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm will be used to estimate all the fixed effects. If some parameters have random effects, the first option will be slower because the Nelder-Mead and the SAEM algorithm are computed at each step. In that case the second or third option will be faster because only the SAEM algorithm will be required when the artificial variability is added.

Alternatively, the standard deviation of the random effects can be fixed to a small value, for instance 5% for log-normally distributed parameters. (See next section on how to enforce a fixed value). With this method, the SAEM algorithm can be used, and the variability is kept small.

5.2.2.1.3.6 Other estimation methods: fixing population parameters or Bayesian estimation

Instead of the default estimation method with SAEM, it is possible to fix a population parameter, or set a prior on the estimate and use Bayesian estimation. This page gives details on these methods and how to use them.

5.2.2.1.4 Outputs

5.2.2.1.4.1 In the graphical user interface

The estimated population parameters are displayed in the POP.PARAM section of the RESULTS tab. Fixed effects names are "**_pop*", the standard deviation of the random effects "*omega_**", parameters of the error model "*a*", "*b*", "*c*", the correlation between random effects "*corr_*_**" and parameters associated to covariates "*beta_*_**". The standard deviation of the random effects is also expressed as coefficient of variation (CV) – a feature present in versions Monolix 2023 or above. The CV calculation depends on the parameter distribution:

- lognormal: $CV = 100 * \sqrt{\exp(\omega_p^2) - 1}$
- normal: $CV = 100 \times \frac{\omega_p}{p_{pop}}$
- logitnormal and probitnormal: the CV is computed by Monte-Carlo. 100000 samples *X* are drawn from the distribution (defined by ω_p and p_{pop}) and the CV is calculated as the ratio of the sample standard deviation over the sample mean: $CV = 100 \times \frac{sd(X)}{mean(X)}$

When you run the "Standard errors" task, then the population parameter table contains also the standard error (s.e) and relative standard error (r.s.e). Note that the CV% represents the inter-individual variability, while the RSE% represents the uncertainty on the estimated parameters.

theophylline_project.mlxtran [demo] * - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

SAEM ESTIMATION

POP.PARAM

INDIV.PARAM

STD.ERRORS

TESTS

PROPOSAL

Population parameter estimates

	VALUE	LINEARIZATION				
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	
Fixed Effects						
ka_pop	1.5258	0.3163	20.7	1.0287	2.2629	
V_pop	0.4546	0.02044	4.50	0.4163	0.4964	
Cl_pop	0.04025	0.003289	8.17	0.03432	0.04721	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects						
	Value	C.V.(%)				
omega_ka	0.6595	73.8112	0.1472	22.3	0.4323	1.0061
omega_V	0.1253	12.5768	0.03829	30.6	0.07134	0.22
omega_Cl	0.2609	26.5424	0.06143	23.5	0.1674	0.4068
Error Model Parameters						
a	0.4442	0.1254	28.2	0.2629	0.7504	
b	0.05382	0.02396	44.5	0.02479	0.1169	

Elapsed time (seconds): 1.19
 Exploratory phase iterations: 220 (auto-stop)
 Smoothing phase iterations: 148 (auto-stop)

Starting from version 2024, alongside the standard errors, the upper and lower percentiles, here P2.5 and P97.5 of the **confidence interval** with level $1-\alpha$ are computed for population parameters. This calculation depends on the execution of the “Standard errors” task, as it relies on the standard error of the respective parameter. In order to take into account the boundaries of the parameters (e.g omega or V_pop cannot be negative), the SE is transformed into the gaussian domain, the CI in gaussian domain is calculated assuming a normal distribution and finally the CI is backtransformed. Its transformation is determined by the type of parameter and its distribution assumption:

- **Normally** distributed parameters:
 $CI_{1-\alpha}(\theta_{pop}) = [\theta_{pop} + q_{\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\theta_{pop}), \theta_{pop} + q_{1-\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\theta_{pop})]$. This applies for typical values (fixed effects) of normally distributed parameters and covariate effects (betas).
- **Lognormally** distributed parameters:
 $CI_{1-\alpha}(\theta_{pop}) = [\exp(\mu_{pop} + q_{\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\mu_{pop})), \exp(\mu_{pop} + q_{1-\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\mu_{pop}))]$,
 where $\mu_{pop} = \ln(\theta_{pop})$. This applies to typical values (fixed effects) of lognormally distributed parameters, standard deviations of the random effects (omegas), and error model parameters.

- **Logitnormally** distributed parameters:

$$CI_{1-\alpha}(\theta_{pop}) = [\text{logit}^{-1}(\mu_{pop} + q_{\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\mu_{pop})), \text{logit}^{-1}(\mu_{pop} + q_{1-\alpha/2} \times s.e.(\mu_{pop}))]$$

, where $\mu_{pop} = \text{logit}(\theta_{pop})$. This applies to typical values (fixed effects) of logitnormally distributed parameters and correlation parameters.

where $q_{\alpha/2}$ is the quantile of order $\alpha/2$ for a standard normal distribution. The confidence interval level α can be modified in the settings of the “Standard errors” task within the Statistical Model & Tasks tab by clicking on the wrench icon.

Information about the SAEM task performance are below the table (orange frame):

- The total elapsed time for this task
- The number of iterations in the exploratory and smoothing phases, along with a message that indicates whether the convergence has been reached (“auto-stop”), or if the algorithm arrived at the maximum number of iterations (“stopped at the maximum number of iterations/auto-stop criteria have not been reached”) or if it was stopped by the user (“manual stop”). (for Monolix versions 2021 or above)

A “Copy table” icon on the top of the table allows to copy it in Excel, Word, etc. The table format and display is kept.

Starting from version 2024R1, if categorical covariate effects are included in the statistical model, a “Display fixed effects by category” toggle allows to add a section named “Fixed effects by category” in the table, with the values of the typical population parameters in each category of the categorical covariates and their SEs, RSEs and confidence intervals.

Population parameter estimates

VALUE	LINEARIZATION				
	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	
Fixed Effects					
ka_pop	1.01	0.027	2.67	0.96	1.07
V_pop	68.4	1.73	2.53	65.09	71.88
beta_V_GROUP_1	-0.51	0.039	7.79	-0.58	-0.43
Cl_pop	4	0.071	1.78	3.86	4.14
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects					
	Value	C.V.(%)			
omega_ka	0.21	20.83	0.024	11.5	0.16
omega_V	0.18	18.28	0.015	8.05	0.15
omega_Cl	0.17	17.07	0.013	7.69	0.15
Error Model Parameters					
b	0.2	0.0035	1.77	0.19	0.21

Population parameter estimates

VALUE	LINEARIZATION				
	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	
Fixed Effects					
ka_pop	1.01	0.027	2.67	0.96	1.07
V_pop	68.4	1.73	2.53	65.09	71.88
beta_V_GROUP_1	-0.51	0.039	7.79	-0.58	-0.43
Cl_pop	4	0.071	1.78	3.86	4.14
Fixed Effects by Category					
V_GROUP_0	68.4	1.73	2.53	65.09	71.88
V_GROUP_1	41.22	1.27	3.07	38.81	43.77
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects					
	Value	C.V.(%)			
omega_ka	0.21	20.83	0.024	11.5	0.16
omega_V	0.18	18.28	0.015	8.05	0.15
omega_Cl	0.17	17.07	0.013	7.69	0.15
Error Model Parameters					
b	0.2	0.0035	1.77	0.19	0.21

5.2.2.1.4.2 In the output folder

After having run the estimation of the population parameters, the following files are available:

- **summary.txt**: contains the estimated population parameters (and the number of iterations in Monolix2021R1), in a format easily readable by a human (but not easy to parse for a computer)
- **populationParameters.txt**: contains the estimated population parameters (by default in csv format), including the CV.
- **populationParametersByGroups.txt**: contains the estimated population parameters by categories of categorical covariates included in the statistical model. This file is not generated if there are no categorical covariate effects.
- **predictions.txt**: contains for each individual and each observation time, the observed data (y), the prediction using the population parameters and population median covariates value from the data set (popPred_medianCOV), the prediction using the population parameters and individual covariates value (popPred), the prediction using the individual approximate conditional mean calculated from the last iterations of SAEM (indivPred_SAEM) and the corresponding weighted residual (indWRes_SAEM).
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedIndividualParameters.txt**: individual parameters corresponding to the approximate conditional mean, calculated as the average of the individual parameters sampled by MCMC during all iterations of the smoothing phase. When several chains are used (see project settings), the average is also done over all chains. Values are indicated as *_SAEM in the file.

Parameters without variability:

- method “no variability” or “variability at the first stage”: *_SAEM represents the value at the last SAEM iteration, so the estimated population parameter plus the covariate effects. In absence of covariate, all individuals have the same value.
- method “add decreasing variability”: *_SAEM represents the average of all iterations of the smoothing phase. This value can be slightly different from individual to individual, even in the absence of covariates.
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedRandomEffects.txt**: individual random effects corresponding to the approximate conditional mean, calculated using the last estimations of SAEM (*_SAEM).
For parameters without variability, see above.

More details about the content of the output files can be found [here](#).

5.2.2.1.5 Settings

The settings are accessible through the interface via the button next to the parameter estimation task.

Burn-in phase:

The burn-in phase corresponds to an initialization of SAEM: individual parameters are sampled from their conditional distribution using MCMC using the initial values for the population parameters (no update of the population parameter estimates).

Note: the meaning of the burn-in phase in Monolix is different to what is called burn-in in Nonmem algorithms.

- **Number of iterations** (default: 5): number of iterations of the burn-in phase

Exploratory phase:

- **Auto-stop criteria** (default: yes): if ticked, auto-stop criteria are used to automatically detect convergence during the exploratory phase. If convergence is detected, the algorithm switches to the smoothing phase before the maximum number of iterations. The criteria take into account the stability of the convergence indicator, omega parameters and error model parameters.
- **Maximum number of iterations** (default: 500, if auto-stop ticked): maximum number of iterations for the exploratory phase. Even if the auto-stop criteria are not fulfilled, the algorithm switches to the smoothing phase after this maximum number of iterations. A warning message will be displayed in the GUI if the maximum number of iterations is reached while the auto-stop criteria are not fulfilled.
- **Minimum number of iterations** (default: 150, if auto-stop ticked): minimum number of iterations for the exploratory phase. This value also corresponds to the interval length over which the auto-stop criteria are tested. A larger minimum number of iterations means that the auto-stop criteria are harder to reach.

- **Number of iterations** (default: 500, if auto-stop unticked): fixed number of iterations for the exploratory phase.
- **Step-size exponent** (default: 0): The value, comprised between 0 and 1, represents memory of the stochastic process, i.e how much weight is given at iteration k to the value of the previous iteration compared to the new information collected. A value 0 means no memory, i.e the parameter value at iteration k is built based on the information collected at that iteration only, and does not take into account the value of the parameter at the previous iteration.
- **Simulated annealing** (default: enabled): the Simulated Annealing version of SAEM permits to better explore the parameter space by constraining the standard deviation of the random effects to decrease slowly.
- **Decreasing rate for the variance of the residual errors** (default: 0.95, if simulated annealing enabled): the residual error variance (parameter "a" for a constant error model for instance) at iteration k is constrained to be larger than the decreasing rate times the variance at the previous iteration.
- **Decreasing rate for the variance of the individual parameters** (default: 0.95, if simulated annealing enabled): the variance of the random effects at iteration k is constrained to be larger than the decreasing rate times the variance at the previous iteration.

Smoothing phase:

- **Auto-stop criteria** (default: yes): if ticked, auto-stop criteria are used to automatically detect convergence during the smoothing phase. If convergence is detected, the algorithm stops before the maximum number of iterations.
- **Maximum number of iterations** (default: 200, if auto-stop ticked): maximum number of iterations for the smoothing phase. Even if the auto-stop criteria are not fulfilled, the algorithm stops after this maximum number of iterations.
- **Minimum number of iterations** (default: 50, if auto-stop ticked): minimum number of iterations for the smoothing phase. This value also corresponds to the interval length over which the auto-stop criteria is tested. A larger minimum number of iterations means that the auto-stop criteria is harder to reach.
- **Number of iterations** (default: 200, if auto-stop unticked): fixed number of iterations for the smoothing phase.
- **Step-size exponent** (default: 0.7): The value, comprised between 0 and 1, represents memory of the stochastic process, i.e how much weight is given at iteration k to the value of the previous iteration compared to the new information collected. The value must be strictly larger than 0.5 for the smoothing phase to converge. Large values (close to 1) will result in a smoother parameter trajectory during the smoothing phase, but may take longer to converge to the maximum likelihood estimate.

Methodology for parameters without variability (if parameters without variability are present in the model):

The SAEM algorithm requires to draw parameter values from their marginal distribution, which does not exist for parameters without variability. These parameters are thus estimated via another method, which can be chosen among:

- **No variability (default choice):** After each SAEM iteration, the parameter without variability are optimized using the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm. The absolute tolerance (stopping criteria) is $1e-4$ and the maximum number of iterations 20 times the number of parameters to calculate via this algorithm.
- **Add decreasing variability:** an artificial variability is added for these parameters, allowing estimation via SAEM. The variability is progressively decreased such that at the end of the estimation process, the parameter has a variability of $1e-5$.
- **Variability in the first stage:** during the exploratory phase, an artificial variability is added and progressively forced to $1e-5$ (same as above). In the smoothing phase, the Nelder-Mead simplex optimization algorithm is used.

Handling parameters without variability is also discussed here.

Set all SAEM iterations to zero in one click

The icon on the bottom left provides a shortcut to set all SAEM iterations to zero (in all three phases). This is convenient if the user wish to skip the estimation of the population parameters and keep the initial estimates as population estimates to run the other tasks, since running SAEM first is mandatory. It is not equivalent to fixing all population parameters, since standard errors are not estimated for fixed parameters, while they will be estimated for the initial estimates in this case. The action can be easily reversed with the second shortcut to reset default SAEM iterations.

5.2.2.1.6 Good practice, troubleshooting and tips

5.2.2.1.6.1 Choosing to enable or disable the simulated annealing

As the simulated annealing option permits to more surely find the global maximum, it should be used during the first runs, when the initial values may be quite far from the final estimates.

On the other side, the simulated annealing option may keep the omega values artificially high, even after a large number of SAEM iterations. This may prevent the identification of parameters for which the variability is in fact zero and lead to NaN in the standard errors. So once good initial values have been found and there is no risk to fall in a local maximum, the simulated annealing option can be disabled. Below we show an example where removing the simulated annealing permits to identify parameters for which the inter-individual variability can be removed.

Example: The dataset used in the [tobramycin case study](#) is quite sparse. In these conditions, we expect that estimating the inter-individual variability for all parameters will be difficult. In this case, the estimation can be done in two steps, as shown below for a two-compartment model on this dataset:

- First, we run SAEM with the simulated annealing option (default setting), which facilitates the convergence towards the global maximum. All four parameters V, k, k12 and k21 have random effects. The estimated parameters are shown below:

	VALUES	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
V_pop	19.7	1.43	7.28
k_pop	0.181	0.0123	6.79
k12_pop	0.0293	0.0585	200
k21_pop	0.0611	0.0304	49.8
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_V	0.145	0.0566	38.9
omega_k	0.559	0.0499	8.92
omega_k12	1.09	1.43	131
omega_k21	1.07	1.22	114
Error Model Parameters			
b	0.188	0.0124	6.57

The parameters omega_k12 and omega_k21 have high standard errors, suggesting that the variability is difficult to estimate. The omega_k12 and omega_k21 values themselves are also high (100% inter-individual variability), suggesting that they may have been kept too high due to the simulated annealing.

- As a second step, we use the last estimates as new initial values (as shown here), and run SAEM again after disabling the simulated annealing option. On the plot showing the convergence of SAEM, we can see omega_V, omega_k12 and omega_k21 decreasing to very low values. The data is too sparse to correctly identify the inter-individual variability for V, k12 and k21. Thus, their random effects can be removed, but the random effect of k can be kept.

Note that because the ω_V , ω_{k12} and ω_{k21} parameters decrease without stabilizing, the convergence indicator does the same.

5.2.2.1.7 The convergence indicator

When you launch the estimation of the population parameters, you can see the evolution of the population parameter estimates over the iterations of the SAEM algorithm but also the convergence indicator in purple.

The convergence indicator is the complete log-likelihood. It can help to follow convergence.

Note that the complete likelihood is not the same as the log-likelihood computed as separate task.

5.2.2.1.7.1 Log-likelihood

The likelihood is the probability density of the data given the population parameter, so the log-likelihood is defined as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{ind}}} \log(p(y_i; \theta))$$

The likelihood is the objective function, therefore it is the relevant quantity to compare model, but unfortunately it cannot be computed in closed form because the individual parameters ϕ_i are unobserved. It requires to integrate over all possible values of the individual parameters. Thus, to estimate the log-likelihood an importance sampling Monte Carlo method is used in a separate task (or an approximation is calculated via linearization of the model).

5.2.2.1.7.2 Complete log-likelihood

On the contrary, the complete likelihood refers to the joint probability distribution of the data and the individual parameters. The convergence indicator (complete log-likelihood) is then defined as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{ind}}} \log(p(y_i, \phi_i; \theta))$$

The joint probability distribution can be decomposed using Bayes law as:

$$p(y_i, \psi_i; \theta) = p(y_i | \psi_i; \theta) p(\psi_i; \theta)$$

Those two terms have an analytical expression and are easy to calculate, using as ϕ_i the individual parameters drawn by MCMC for the current iteration of SAEM. This quantity is calculated at each SAEM step and is useful to assess the convergence of the SAEM algorithm.

5.2.2.1.7.3 Typical shape of the convergence indicator

Typically, the convergence indicator decreases progressively and then stabilizes. The convergence indicator aggregates the information from all parameters and can serve to detect if the SAEM algorithm has already converged or not. When the indicator is stable, that is it oscillates around the same value without drifting, then we can be pretty confident that the maximum likelihood has been achieved.

5.2.2.2 Bayesian estimation or fixed population parameters

In the tab “Initial estimates”, clicking on the wheel icon next to a population parameters opens a window to choose among three estimation methods (see image below). “Maximum Likelihood Estimation” corresponds to the default method using SAEM, detailed on this page. “Maximum A Posteriori Estimation” corresponds to Bayesian estimation, and “Fixed” to a fixed parameter.

5.2.2.2.1 Bayesian estimation

5.2.2.2.1.1 Purpose

Bayesian estimation allows to take into account prior information in the estimation of parameters. It is called in Monolix Maximum A Posteriori estimation, and it corresponds to a penalized maximum likelihood estimation, based on a prior distribution defined for a parameter. The weight of the prior in the estimation is given by the standard deviation of the prior distribution.

Objectives: learn how to combine maximum likelihood estimation and Bayesian estimation of the population parameters.

Demos: theobayes1_project, theobayes2_project,

5.2.2.2.1.2 Introduction

The *Bayesian approach* considers the vector of population parameters θ as a random vector with a *prior distribution* π_{θ} . We can then define the **posterior distribution** of θ :

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\theta|y) &= \frac{\pi_{\theta}(\theta)p(y|\theta)}{p(y)} \\
 &= \frac{\pi_{\theta}(\theta) \int p(y, \psi|\theta)d\psi}{p(y)}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can estimate this conditional distribution and derive statistics (posterior mean, standard deviation, quantiles, etc.) and the so-called *maximum a posteriori* (MAP) estimate of θ :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \hat{\theta}^{\text{MAP}} &= \arg\text{-max}_{\theta} p(\theta|y) \\
 &= \arg\text{-max}_{\theta} \{ \mathcal{LL}_y(\theta) + \log(\pi_{\theta}(\theta)) \}
 \end{aligned}$$

The MAP estimate maximizes a penalized version of the observed likelihood. In other words, MAP estimation is the same as penalized maximum likelihood estimation. Suppose for instance that θ is a scalar parameter and the prior is a normal distribution with mean θ_0 and variance γ^2 . Then, the MAP estimate is the solution of the following minimization problem:

$$\hat{\theta}^{\text{MAP}} = \arg\text{-min}_{\theta} \left\{ -2\mathcal{LL}_y(\theta) + \frac{1}{\gamma^2} (\theta - \theta_0)^2 \right\}$$

This is a trade-off between the MLE which minimizes the deviance, $-2\mathcal{LL}$, and θ_0 which minimizes $(\theta - \theta_0)^2$. The weight given to the prior directly depends on the variance of the prior distribution: the smaller γ^2 is, the closer to θ_0 the MAP is. In the limiting case, $\gamma^2 = 0$; this means that θ is fixed at θ_0 and no longer needs to be estimated. Both the Bayesian and frequentist approaches have their supporters and detractors. But rather than being dogmatic and following the same rule-book every time, we need to be pragmatic and ask the right methodological questions when confronted with a new problem.

All things considered, the problem comes down to knowing whether the data contains sufficient information to answer a given question, and whether some other information may be available to help answer it. This is the essence of the art of modeling: find the right compromise between the confidence we have in the data and our prior knowledge of the problem. Each problem is different and requires a specific approach. For instance, if all the patients in a clinical trial have essentially the same weight, it is pointless to estimate a relationship between weight and the model's PK parameters using the trial data. A modeler would be better served trying to use prior information based on physiological knowledge rather than just some statistical criterion.

Generally speaking, if prior information is available it should be used, on the condition of course that it is relevant. For continuous data for example, what does putting a prior on the residual error model's parameters mean in reality? A reasoned statistical approach consists of including prior information only for certain parameters (those for which we have real prior information) and having confidence in the data for the others. Monolix allows this hybrid approach which reconciles the Bayesian and frequentist approaches. A given parameter can be

- a fixed constant if we have absolute confidence in its value or the data does not allow it to be estimated, essentially due to lack of identifiability.
- estimated by maximum likelihood, either because we have great confidence in the data or no information on the parameter.

- estimated by introducing a prior and calculating the MAP estimate or estimating the posterior distribution.

5.2.2.2.1.3 Computing the Maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate

- demo project: **theobayes1_project** (data = 'theophylline_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt')

We want to introduce a prior distribution for ka_{pop} in this example. Click on the option button

theophylline_project.mltran [demo] - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates Statistical model & Tasks Results Plots

Initial estimates

Check initial estimates

Use last estimates: All | Fixed effects
Fix parameters values: All | None

Population distribution parameters ▾

PARAMETERS	POPULATION	STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	ka_{pop} 1	
V	V_{pop} 0.5	ω_V 1
Cl	Cl_{pop} 0.1	ω_{Cl} 1

Residual error parameters ▾

CONC	a	b	c
	1	0.3	1

and select **Maximum A Posteriori Estimation**

We propose a typical value, here 2 and standard deviation 0.1 for ka_{pop} and to compute the MAP estimate for ka_{pop} . The parameter is then colored in purple.

Population distribution parameters			
PARAMETERS	POPULATION		STD. DEVIATIONS
ka	ka_{pop}	1	
V	V_{pop}	0.5	ω_V 1
Cl	Cl_{pop}	0.1	ω_{Cl} 1

Starting from the 2021 version, it is possible to select maximum *a posteriori* estimation also for the omega parameters (standard deviations of the random effects). In this case, an inverse Wishart is set as a prior distribution for the omega matrix.

The following distributions for the priors are used:

- **typical value (*_pop):** the distribution of the prior is the same as the distribution of the parameter. For instance, if ka has been set with a lognormal distribution in the “Statistical model & Tasks” tab, a lognormal distribution is also used for the prior on ka_pop. When a lognormal

distribution is used, setting $sd=0.1$ roughly corresponds to 10% uncertainty in the provided prior value for ka_{pop} .

- **covariate effects (beta_*)**: a normal distribution is used, to allow betas to be either positive or negative.
- **standard deviations (omega_*)** [starting version 2021]: an inverse Wishart distribution is used. Inverse Wisharts are common prior distributions for variance-covariance matrices as they allow to fulfill the positive-definite matrix requirement. The weight of the prior in the estimation is based on the number of degrees of freedom (df) of the inverse Wishart, instead of a standard deviation. More degrees of freedom correspond to a higher constrain of the prior in the omega estimation. In Monolix, each omega parameter is handled as a 1×1 matrix with its own degree of freedom, independently from the other omegas. The univariate inverse Wishart $W^{-1}(df, (df + 2)\omega_{typ})$ simplifies to an inverse gamma distribution with shape parameter $\alpha = df/2$ and scale parameter $\beta = \omega_{typ} \times (df + 2)/2$. The coefficient of variation is thus $CV = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{df}{2} - 2}}$. To obtain a 20% uncertainty on omega (CV=0.2), the user can set df=50.
- **correlations**: it is currently not possible to set a prior on the correlation parameters

It is common to set the initial value of the parameter to be the same as the typical value of the prior. Note that the default value for the typical value of the prior is set to the initial value of the parameter. However, if the initial value of the parameter is modified afterwards, the typical value of the prior is not updated automatically.

5.2.2.2 Fixing the value of a parameter

Population parameters can be fixed to their initial values, in this case they are not estimated. It is possible to fix one, several or all population parameters, among the fixed effects, standard deviations of random effects, and error model parameters. In Monolix2021, it is also possible to fix correlation parameters.

To fix a population parameter, click on the wheel next to the parameter in the tab "Initial estimates" and select "Fixed", like on the image below:

Fixed parameters appear on this tab in red. Starting from the 2021 version of Monolix, they are also colored in red in the subtab “Check initial estimates”.

- **theobayes2_project** (data = ‘theophylline_data.txt’, model = ‘lib:oral1_1cpt_kaVCl.txt’)

We can combine different strategies for the population parameters: Bayesian estimation for ka_{pop} , fixed value for V_{pop} and maximum likelihood estimation for Cl_{pop} , for instance.

Population distribution parameters

PARAMETERS	POPULATION	STANDARD DEVIATIONS
ka	ka_pop 2	omega_ka 1
V	V_pop 32	omega_V 1
Cl	Cl_pop 3	omega_Cl 1

Remark:

- The parameter V_{pop} is fixed and then colored in red.
- V_{pop} is not estimated (it's s.e. is not computed) but the standard deviation ω_V is estimated as usual.

5.2.3 EBEs

5.2.3.1 Purpose

EBEs stands for **Empirical Bayes Estimates**. The EBEs are **the most probable value of the individual parameters** (parameters for each individual), given the estimated population parameters and the data of each individual. In a more mathematical language, they are the **mode of the conditional parameter distribution** for each individual.

These values are useful to compute the most probable prediction for each individual, for comparison with the data (for instance in the Individual Fits plot).

5.2.3.2 Calculation of the EBEs (conditional mode)

When launching the “EBEs” task, the **mode of the conditional parameter distribution** is calculated.

5.2.3.2.1 Conditional distribution

The conditional distribution is $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ with ψ_i the individual parameters for individual i , $\hat{\theta}$ the estimated population parameters, and y_i the data (observations) for individual i . The conditional distribution represents the uncertainty of the individual's parameter value, taking into account the

information at hand for this individual: the observed data for that individual, the covariate values for that individual and the fact that the individual belongs to the population for which we have already estimated the typical parameter value (fixed effects) and the variability (standard deviation of the random effects). It is not possible to directly calculate the probability for a given ψ_i (no closed form), but is possible to obtain samples from the distribution using a Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo procedure (MCMC). This is detailed more on the Conditional Distribution page.

5.2.3.2.2 Mode of the conditional distribution

The mode is the parameter value with the highest probability:

$$\hat{\psi}_i^{mode} = \arg \max_{\psi_i} p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$$

To find the mode, we thus need to maximize the conditional probability with respect to the individual parameter value ψ_i .

5.2.3.2.3 Individual random effects

Once the individual parameters values ψ_i are known, the corresponding individual random effects can be calculated using the population parameters and covariates. Taking the example of a parameter ψ having a normal distribution within the population and that depends on the covariate c , we can write for individual i :

$$\psi_i = \psi_{pop} + \beta \times c_i + \eta_i$$

As ψ_i (estimated conditional mode), ψ_{pop} and β (population parameters) and c_i (individual covariate value) are known, the individual random effect η_i can easily be calculated.

5.2.3.2.4 Algorithm

For each individual, to find the ψ_i values that maximizes the conditional distribution, we use the Nelder-Mead Simplex algorithm.

As the conditional distribution does not have a closed form solution (i.e. $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$) cannot be directly or easily calculated for a given ψ_i), we use the Bayes' theorem to rewrite it in the following way (leaving the population parameters $\hat{\theta}$ out for clarity):

$$p(\psi_i | y_i) = \frac{p(y_i | \psi_i) p(\psi_i)}{p(y_i)}$$

The conditional density function of the data when knowing the individual parameter values (i.e. $p(y_i | \psi_i)$) is easy to calculate, as well as the density function for the individual parameters (i.e. $p(\psi_i)$), because they have closed form solutions. On the opposite, the likelihood $p(y_i)$ has no closed form

solution. But as it does not depend on ψ_i , we can leave it out of the optimization procedure and only optimize $p(y_i|\psi_i)p(\psi_i)$.

The initial value used for the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm is the conditional mean (estimated during the conditional distribution task) if available (typical case of a full scenario), or the approximate conditional mean calculated at the end of SAEM otherwise.

Parameters without variability are not estimated, they are set to $\psi_i = \psi_{pop} + \beta \times c_i$.

5.2.3.3 Running the EBEs task

When running the EBEs task, the progress is displayed in the pop-up window:

5.2.3.3.1 Dependencies between tasks:

- The "Population parameters" task must be run before launching the EBEs task.
- The EBEs task is recommended before calculating the Standard errors task and the Log-likelihood task using the linearization method.

5.2.3.4 Outputs

5.2.3.4.1 In the graphical user interface

In the `Indiv.Param` section of the `Results` tab, a summary of the individual parameters is proposed (min, max, median, quartiles, and shrinkage [in Monolix 2024 and later]) as shown in the figure below. The elapsed time for this task is also shown.

Summary

Statistics on conditional mode results

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	SHRINKAGE (%)
ka	0.66	0.97	1.34	2.07	6.27	2.95
V	0.38	0.43	0.46	0.5	0.54	12.55
Cl	0.021	0.036	0.042	0.048	0.057	0.85

Elapsed time (seconds): 0.003

To see the estimated parameter value for each individual, the user can click on the `[INDIV. ESTIM.]` section. Notice that the user can also see them in the output files, which can be accessed via the folder icon at the bottom left. Notice that there is a “Copy table” icon on the top of each table to copy them in Excel, Word, ... The table format and display will be kept.

theophylline_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

COND. MEAN [SUMMARY] COND. MEAN [INDIV. ESTIM.] COND. MODE [SUMMARY] COND. MODE [INDIV. ESTIM.]

POP.PARAM

INDIV.PARAM

TESTS

PROPOSAL

Individual estimates

Conditional mode results per individual

id	ka	V	Cl	WEIGHT	SEX
1	1.72	0.38	0.021	79.6	M
2	1.91	0.44	0.044	72.4	M
3	2.23	0.47	0.041	70.5	M
4	1.15	0.43	0.038	72.7	M
5	1.34	0.48	0.044	54.6	F
6	1.07	0.5	0.05	80	M
7	0.66	0.5	0.05	64.6	F
8	1.34	0.49	0.046	70.5	M
9	6.27	0.38	0.033	86.4	M
10	0.74	0.45	0.033	58.2	F

Records per page: 10 12

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Showing 1 to 10 of 12 entries

5.2.3.4.2 In the output folder

After having run the EBEs task, the following files are available:

- **summary.txt**: contains the summary statistics (as displayed in the GUI).
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedIndividualParameters.txt**: the individual parameters for each subject-occasion are displayed. In addition to the already present approximation conditional mean from SAEM (*_SAEM), the conditional mode (*_mode) is added to the file.
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedRandomEffects.txt**: the individual random effects for each subject-occasion are displayed (*_mode), in addition to the already present value based on the approximate conditional mean from SAEM (*_SAEM).
- **IndividualParameters/shrinkage.txt**: starting with Monolix 2024, the shrinkage for each parameter for the conditional mode as shrinkage_mode.

More details about the content of the output files can be found here.

5.2.3.5 Settings

The settings are accessible through the interface via the button next to the EBEs task.

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface with a toolbar at the top containing buttons for 'POPULATION P...', 'EBEs', 'CONDITIONAL ...', 'STANDARD ...', 'LIKELIHOOD', and 'PLOTS'. The 'EBEs' button is highlighted with a red box. A dialog box titled 'Conditional Mode - Settings' is open, displaying the following settings:

- Conditional mode**
- Optimization options**
- Maximum number of iterations: 200
- Tolerance: 0.000001
- Buttons: SET DEFAULTS, CLOSE

- **Maximum number of iterations** (default: 200): maximum number of iterations for the Nelder-Mead Simplex algorithm, for each individual. Even if the tolerance criteria is not met, the algorithm stops after that number of iterations.
- **Tolerance** (default: 1e-6): absolute tolerance criteria. The algorithm stops when the change of the conditional probability value between two iterations is less than the tolerance.

5.2.3.6 Calculate EBEs for a new data set using an existing model

5.2.4 Conditional distribution

5.2.4.1 Conditional distribution task

5.2.4.1.1 Purpose

The conditional distribution represents the uncertainty of the individual parameter values. The conditional distribution estimation task permits to sample from this distribution. The samples are used to calculate the condition mean, or directly as estimators of the individual parameters in the plots to improve their informativeness [1]. They are also used to compute the statistical tests.

5.2.4.1.2 Calculation of the conditional distribution

5.2.4.1.2.1 Conditional distribution

The conditional distribution is $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ with ψ_i the individual parameters for individual i , $\hat{\theta}$ the estimated population parameters, and y_i the data (observations) for individual i . The conditional distribution represents the uncertainty of the individual's parameter value, taking into account the information at hand for this individual:

- the observed data for that individual,
- the covariate values for that individual,
- and the fact that the individual belongs to the population for which we have already estimated the typical parameter value (fixed effects) and the variability (standard deviation of the random effects).

It is not possible to directly calculate the probability for a given ψ_i (no closed form), but is possible to obtain samples from the distribution using a Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo procedure (MCMC).

5.2.4.1.2.2 MCMC algorithm

MCMC methods are a class of algorithms for sampling from probability distributions for which direct sampling is difficult. They consist of constructing a stochastic procedure which, in its stationary state, yields draws from the probability distribution of interest. Among the MCMC class, we use the Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm, which has the property of being able to sample probability distributions which can be computed up to a constant. This is the case for our conditional distribution, which can be rewritten as:

$$p(\psi_i | y_i) = \frac{p(y_i | \psi_i)p(\psi_i)}{p(y_i)}$$

$p(y_i | \psi_i)$ is the conditional density function of the data when knowing the individual parameter values and can be computed (closed form solution). $p(\psi_i)$ is the density function for the individual parameters and can also be computed. The likelihood $p(y_i)$ has no closed form solution but it is constant.

In brief, the MH algorithm works in the following way: at each iteration k , a new individual parameter value is drawn from a proposal distribution for each individual. The new value is accepted with a probability that depends on $p(\psi_i)$ and $p(y_i | \psi_i)$. After a transition period, the algorithm reaches a stationary state where the accepted values follow the conditional distribution probability $p(\psi_i | y_i)$. For the proposal distribution, three different distributions are used in turn with a (2,2,2) pattern (setting "Number of iterations of kernel 1/2/3" in Settings > Project Settings): the population distribution, a unidimensional Gaussian random walk, or a multidimensional Gaussian random walk. For the random walks, the variance of the Gaussian is automatically adapted to reach an optimal acceptance ratio ("target acceptance ratio" setting in Settings > Project Settings).

5.2.4.1.2.3 Conditional mean

The draws from the conditional distribution generated by the MCMC algorithm can be used to estimate any summary statistics of the distribution (mean, standard deviation, quantiles, etc). In particular we calculate the conditional mean by averaging over all draws:

$$\hat{\psi}_i^{mean} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \psi_i^k$$

The standard deviation of the conditional distribution is also calculated. The number of samples used to calculate the mean and standard deviation corresponds to the number of chains times the total number of iterations of the conditional distribution task (not only during the convergence interval length). In version 2021 the mean is calculated over the transformed individual parameters (in the gaussian space), and back-transformed to the non-gaussian space. Whereby in version 2023 the mean and standard deviation, are based on the untransformed samples.

5.2.4.1.2.4 Samples from the conditional distribution

Among all samples from the conditional distribution, a small number (between 1 and 10, see "Simulated parameters per individual" setting) is kept to be used in the plots. These samples are unbiased estimators and they present the advantage of not being affected by shrinkage, as shown for example on the documentation of the plot "distribution of the individual parameters".

Shrinkage and the use of random samples from the conditional distribution are explained in more details here.

5.2.4.1.2.5 Stopping criteria

At iteration k , the conditional mean is calculated for each individual by averaging over all k previous iterations. The average conditional means over all individuals (noted $E(X|y)$), and the standard deviation of the conditional means over all individuals (noted $sd(X|y)$) are calculated and displayed in the pop-up window. The algorithm stops when, for all parameters, the average conditional means and standard deviations of the last 50 iterations (“Interval length” setting) do not deviate by more than 5% (2.5% in each direction, “relative interval” setting) from the average and standard deviation values at iteration k .

In some very specific cases (for example with a parameter with a normal distribution and a value very close to 1), it can take many iterations to reach the convergence criteria because the criteria is defined as a percentage. In that case, the toggle “enable maximum number of iterations” can be used to limit the number iterations of this task. If the limit is reached, a warning message will be displayed in the interface.

5.2.4.1.3 Running the conditional distribution estimation task

During the evaluation of the conditional distribution, the following plot pop-ups, displaying the average conditional means over all individuals (noted $E(X|y)$), and the standard deviation of the conditional means over all individuals (noted $sd(X|y)$) for each iteration of the MCMC algorithm.

The convergence criteria described above means that the blue line, which represents the average over all individuals of the conditional mean, must be within the tube. The tube is centered around the last value of the blue line and spans over 5% of that last value. The algorithm stops when all blue lines are in their tube.

5.2.4.1.3.1 Dependencies between tasks:

- The “Population parameters” task must be run before launching the conditional distribution task.
- The conditional distribution task is recommended before calculating the log-likelihood task without the linearization method (i.e log-likelihood via importance sampling).
- The conditional distribution task is necessary for the statistical tests.
- The samples generated during the conditional distribution task will be reused for the Standard errors task (without linearization).

5.2.4.1.4 Outputs

5.2.4.1.4.1 In the graphical user interface

In the **Indiv.Param** section of the **Results** tab, a summary of the estimated conditional mean is given (min, max, quartiles, and shrinkage [in Monolix 2024 and later]), as shown in the figure below. Starting from Monolix2021R1, the number of iterations is also displayed, along with a message indicating whether convergence has been reached (“auto-stop”) or if the task was stopped by the user or reached the maximum number of iterations.

theophyliline_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

COND. MEAN [SUMMARY] COND. MEAN [INDIV. ESTIM.] COND. MODE [SUMMARY] COND. MODE [INDIV. ESTIM.]

POP.PARAM

INDIV.PARAM

TESTS

PROPOSAL

Summary

Statistics on conditional mean results

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	SHRINKAGE (%)
ka	0.67	0.99	1.37	2.17	7.03	0.13
V	0.38	0.43	0.46	0.5	0.55	12.21
Cl	0.021	0.035	0.042	0.048	0.056	1.8

Elapsed time (seconds): 0.25
Iterations: 85 (auto-stop)

To see the estimated parameter value for each individual, the user can click on the [INDIV. ESTIM.] section. Notice that the user can also see them in the output files, which can be accessed via the folder icon at the bottom left. Notice that there is a “Copy table” icon on the top of each table to copy them in Excel, Word, ... The table format and display will be kept.

theophylline_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

COND. MEAN [SUMMARY] **COND. MEAN [INDIV. ESTIM.]** COND. MODE [SUMMARY] COND. MODE [INDIV. ESTIM.]

POP.PARAM

INDIV.PARAM

TESTS

PROPOSAL

Individual estimates

Conditional mean results per individual

id	ka	V	Cl	WEIGHT	SEX
1	1.77	0.38	0.021	79.6	M
2	1.98	0.44	0.044	72.4	M
3	2.36	0.48	0.041	70.5	M
4	1.16	0.44	0.037	72.7	M
5	1.37	0.48	0.043	54.6	F
6	1.1	0.5	0.05	80	M
7	0.67	0.5	0.05	64.6	F
8	1.38	0.5	0.046	70.5	M
9	7.03	0.38	0.033	86.4	M
10	0.75	0.45	0.033	58.2	F

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Showing 1 to 10 of 12 entries

5.2.4.1.4.2 In the output folder

After having run the conditional distribution task, the following files are available:

- **summary.txt**: contains the summary statistics (as displayed in the GUI)
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedIndividualParameters.txt**: the individual parameters for each subject-occasion are displayed. The conditional mean (*_mean) and the standard deviation (*_sd) of the conditional distribution are added to the file. The number of samples used to calculate the mean and standard deviation corresponds to the number of chains times the total number of iterations of the conditional distribution task (not only during the convergence interval length).
- **IndividualParameters/estimatedRandomEffects.txt**: the individual random effects for each subject-occasion are displayed. Those corresponding to the conditional mean (*_mean) are added to the file, together with the standard deviation (*_sd).

- **IndividualParameters/simulatedIndividualParameters.txt:** several simulated individual parameters (draws from the conditional distribution) are recorded for each individual. The rep column permits to distinguish the several simulated parameters for each individual.
- **IndividualParameters/simulatedRandomEffects.txt:** the random effects corresponding to the simulated individual parameters are recorded.
- **IndividualParameters/shrinkage.txt:** starting with Monolix 2024, the shrinkage for each parameter for the conditional mean as shrinkage_mean and for the conditional distribution as shrinkage_condDist.

More details about the content of the output files can be found here.

5.2.4.1.5 Settings

To change the settings, you can click on the settings button next the conditional distribution task.

- **Interval length** (default: 50): number of iterations over which the convergence criteria is checked.

- **Relative interval** (default: 0.05): size of the interval (relative to the current average or standard deviation) in which the last “interval length” iterations must be for the stopping criteria to be met. A value at 0.05 means that over the last “interval length” iterations, the value should not vary by more than 5% (2.5% in each direction).
- **Simulated parameters per individual** (default: via calculation): number of draws from the conditional distribution that will be used in the plots. The number is calculated as $\min(10, \text{idealNb})$ with $\text{idealNb} = \max(500 / \text{number of subject}, 5000 / \text{number of observations})$. This means that the maximum number is 10 (which is usually the case for small data sets). For large data sets, the number may be reduced, but the number of individual times the number of simulated parameters should be at least 500, and the number of observations times the number of simulated parameters should be at least 5000. This ensures to have a sufficiently large but not unnecessarily large number of dots in the plots such as Observations versus predictions or Correlation between random effects.
If the user sets the number of simulated parameters to a value larger than the number of chains (project settings) times the total number of iterations of the conditional distribution task (maximum number of iterations or when convergence criteria are reached), the number will be restricted to the number of available samples.
If the user sets the number of simulated parameters to a value smaller than interval length times number of chains, the simulated parameters are picked evenly from the interval length and the chains. If the requested number of simulated parameters is larger, the last n ($n = \text{number of requested simulated parameters}$) samples are picked.
- **Enable maximum iterations limit** (default: toggle off) [from version 2020 on]: When the toggle in “on”, a maximum number of iterations can be defined.
- **Maximum number of iterations** (default: 500, needs to be larger than the interval length, available if “enable maximum iterations limit” is on): maximum number of iterations for the conditional distribution task. Even if the convergence criteria are not fulfilled, the algorithm stops after this maximum number of iterations. If the maximum number of iterations is reached, a warning message will be displayed in the interface.

Conditional Distribution - Settings

Conditional distribution (mean and sd)

MCMC convergence assessment

Interval length
50

Enable maximum iterations limit

Relative interval width
0.05

Simulated parameters per individual
10

SET DEFAULTS CLOSE

Conditional Distribution - Settings

Conditional distribution (mean and sd)

MCMC convergence assessment

Interval length
50

Enable maximum iterations limit

Maximum number of iterations
500

Relative interval width
0.05

Simulated parameters per individual
10

SET DEFAULTS CLOSE

5.2.4.2 Statistical tests

Several statistical tests may be automatically performed to test the different components of the model. These tests use individual parameters drawn from the conditional distribution, which means that you need to run the task “Conditional distribution” in order to get these results. In addition, the tests for the residuals require to have first generated the residuals diagnostic plots (scatter plot or distribution). The tests are all performed using the individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution (or the random effects and residuals derived thereof). They are thus not subject to bias in case of shrinkage. For each individual, several samples from the conditional distribution may be used. The used tests include a correction to take into account that these samples are correlated among each other.

Results of the tests are available in the tab “Results” and selecting “Tests” in the left menu

5.2.4.2.1 The model for the individual parameters

Consider a PK example (warfarin data set from the demos) with the following model for the individual PK parameters (k_a , V , Cl):

Individual model ▾ f(x)

Add covariate: CONTINUOUS DISCRETE LATENT Q ▾

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	- CORRELATION +	age ▾	lw70 ▾	sex	wt ▾
		Select: All None	#1				
ka	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
V	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cl	LOGNORMAL ▾	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

In this example, the different assumptions we make about the model are:

- The 3 parameters are lognormally distributed.
- ka is function of sex.
- V is function of sex and wt. More precisely, the log-volume $\log(V)$ is a linear function of the log-weight $lw70 = \log(wt/70)$.
- Cl is not function of any of the covariates.
- The random effects η_V and η_{Cl} are linearly correlated.
- η_{ka} is not correlated with η_V and η_{Cl} .

Let's see how each of these assumptions are tested:

5.2.4.2.1.1 Covariate model

Individual parameters vs covariates – Test whether covariates should be removed from the model

If an individual parameter is function of a continuous covariate, the linear correlation between the transformed parameter and the covariate is not 0 and the associated β coefficient is not 0 either. To detect covariates bringing redundant information, we check if these beta coefficients are different from 0. For this, we perform two different tests: a correlation test based on betas coefficients estimated with a linear regression, and a Wald test relying on the estimated population parameters and their standard error.

In both cases, a small p-value indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected and thus that the estimated beta parameter is significantly different from zero. If this is the case, the covariate should be kept in the model. On the opposite, if the p-value is large, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected and this suggests to remove the covariate from the model. Note that if beta is equal to zero, then the covariate has no impact on the parameter. High p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.01-0.05]), orange (p-value in [0.05-0.10]) or red (p-value in [0.10-1]) to draw attention on parameter-covariate relationships that can be removed from the model from a statistical point of view.

Correlation test

Briefly, we perform a linear regression between the covariates and the transformed parameters and test if the resulting beta coefficient are different from 0.

More precisely: for each individual i , let z_i^l be the transformed individual parameters (e.g $\log(V)$ for log-normally distributed parameters or $\logit(F)$ for logit-distributed parameters) sampled from the conditional distribution (called replicates, index l). Here we will call covariates all continuous covariates and all non-referent categories of categorical covariates $cov^{(c)}$, $c = 1..n_C$. For each individual i , $cov_i^{(c)}$ is the value of the c^{th} covariate, equal to 0 or 1 if the covariate is a category.

The transformed individual parameters are first averaged over replicates for each individual:

$$z_i^{(L)} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L z_i^l$$

We then perform the following linear regression:

$$z_i^{(L)} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{c=1}^{n_c} \beta_c cov_i^{(c)} + e_i$$

If two covariates $cov^{(1)}$ and $cov^{(2)}$ (for example WT and BMI) are strongly correlated with a parameter $z^{(L)}$ (for example the volume), only one of them is needed in the model because they are redundant. In the linear regression, only one of the estimated $\hat{\beta}_1$ and $\hat{\beta}_2$ will be significantly different from zero.

For each covariate c we conduct a t-test on the $\hat{\beta}_c$ with the null hypothesis:

$$\mathbf{H0: } \beta_c = 0$$

The test statistic is

$$T_0 = \frac{\hat{\beta}_c}{se(\hat{\beta}_c)}$$

where $se(\hat{\beta}_c)$ is the estimated standard error of $\hat{\beta}_c$ (obtained by least squares estimation during the regression). If the null hypothesis is true, T_0 follows a t distribution with $N - n_C - 1$ degrees of freedom (where N is the number of individuals).

In our example, the correlation test suggests to remove sex from ka:

Correlation test

ka			V		
	STATISTICS	P-VALUE		STATISTICS	P-VALUE
beta_ka_sex_1	0.035	9.72e-1	beta_V_lw70	5.36	9.27e-6
			beta_V_sex_1	3.81	6.68e-4

Wald test

The Wald test relies on the standard errors. Thus the task “Standard errors” must have been calculated to see the test results. The test can be performed using the standard errors calculated using either the “linearization method” (indicated as “linearization”) or not (indicated as “stochastic approximation” in the tests).

The Wald test tests the following null hypothesis:

H0: the beta parameter estimated by SAEM is equal to zero.

The math behind: Let’s note $\hat{\beta}$ the estimated beta value (which is a population parameter) and $se(\hat{\beta})$ the associated standard error calculated during the task “Standard errors”. The Wald test statistic is:

$$W = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{se(\hat{\beta})}$$

The test statistic is compared to a normal distribution (z distribution).

In our example, the Wald test suggests to remove sex from ka and V:

Wald test (stochastic approximation)

ka				V			
	VALUE	STATISTICS	P-VALUE		VALUE	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
beta_ka_sex_1	-0.026	0.056	9.55e-1	beta_V_lw70	0.51	2.16	3.06e-2
				beta_V_sex_1	0.2	1.91	5.65e-2

 The Wald test and the correlation test may suggest different covariates to keep or remove. Note that the null hypothesis tested is not the same.

Random effects vs covariates – Test whether covariates should be added to the model

Pearson's correlation tests and ANOVA are performed to check if some relationships between random effects and covariates not yet included in the model should be added to the model.

For continuous covariates, the Pearson's correlation test tests the following null hypothesis:

H₀: the person correlation coefficient between the random effects (calculated from the individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution) and the covariate values is zero

For categorical covariates, the one-way ANOVA tests the following null-hypothesis:

H₀: the mean of the random effects (calculated from the individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution) is the same for each category of the categorical covariate

A small p-value indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected and thus that the correlation between the random effects and the covariate values is significant. If this is the case, it is probably worth considering to add the covariate in the model. Note that the decision of adding a covariate in the model should not only be driven by statistical considerations but also biological relevance. Note also that for parameter-covariate relationships already included in the model, the correlation between the random effects and covariates is not significant (while the correlation between the parameter and the covariate can be – see above). Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]) to draw attention on parameter-covariate relationships that can be considered for addition in the model from a statistical point of view.

In our example, we already have sex on k_a and V , and $lw70$ on V in the model. The only remaining relationship that could possibly be worth investigating is between weight (or the log-transformed weight "lw70") and clearance.

Pearson's correlation test and/or ANOVA

eta_ka				eta_V			
	COEFF	STATISTICS	P-VALUE		COEFF	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
sex		0.022	8.83e-1	sex		0.00099	9.75e-1
age	-0.098	-0.54	5.93e-1	age	0.1	0.55	5.85e-1
lw70	0.27	1.53	1.37e-1	lw70	0.035	0.19	8.48e-1
wt	0.31	1.81	8.06e-2	wt	0.04	0.22	8.27e-1

eta_Cl			
	COEFF	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
sex		0.29	5.91e-1
age	0.34	1.95	6.09e-2
lw70	0.38	2.28	2.99e-2
wt	0.37	2.2	3.58e-2

The math behind:

Continuous covariate: Let η_i^l the random effects corresponding to the L individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution (called replicates) for individual i , and cov_i the covariate value for individual i . The random effects are first averaged over replicates for each individual:

$$\eta_i^{(L)} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \eta_i^l$$

We note $\overline{cov} = \sum_{i=1}^N cov_i$ the average covariate value over the N subjects and $\bar{\eta} = \sum_{i=1}^N \eta_i^{(L)}$ the average random effect. The Pearson correlation coefficient is calculated as:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (cov_i - \overline{cov})(\eta_i^{(L)} - \bar{\eta})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (cov_i - \overline{cov})^2 \sum_{i=1}^N (\eta_i^{(L)} - \bar{\eta})^2}}$$

The test statistic is:

$$t = \frac{r}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \sqrt{N-2}$$

and it is compared to a t-distribution with $N - 2$ degrees of freedom with N the number of individuals.

Categorical covariates: The random effects are first averaged over replicates for each individual and a one-way analysis of variance is performed (simplified to a t-test when the covariate has only two categories).

5.2.4.2.1.2 The model for the random effects

Distribution of the random effects – Test if the random effects are normally distributed

In the individual model, the distributions for the parameters assume that the random effects follow a normal distribution. Shapiro-Wilk tests are performed to test this hypothesis. The null hypothesis is:

H0: the random effects are normally distributed

If the p-value is small, there is evidence that the random effects are not normally distributed and this calls the choice of the individual model (parameter distribution and covariates) into question. Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]).

In our example, there is no reason to reject the null-hypothesis and no reason to question the chosen log-normal distributions for the parameters.

Shapiro Wilk test

	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
eta_ka	0.97	6.6e-1
eta_V	0.96	3.29e-1
eta_Cl	0.97	6.22e-1

The math behind: Let η_i^l the random effects corresponding to the L individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution (called replicates) for individual i . The Shapiro-Wilk test statistic is calculated for each replicate l (i.e the first sample from all individuals, then the second sample from all individuals, etc):

$$W^l = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N a_i \eta_i^l\right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (\eta_i^l - \bar{\eta}^l)^2}$$

with a_i tabulated coefficient and $\bar{\eta}^l = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \eta_i^l$ the average over all individuals, for each replicate.

The statistic displayed in Monolix corresponds to the average statistic over all replicates $W = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L W^l$. For the p-values, one p-value is calculated for each replicate, using the Shapiro-Wild table with N (number of individuals) degrees of freedom. The Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure is then applied: the p-values are ranked by ascending order and the BH critical value is calculated for each as $\frac{\text{rank}}{L} Q$ with **rank** the individual p-value's rank, L the total number of p-values (equal to the number of replicates) and $Q = 0.05$ the false discovery rate. The largest p-value that is smaller than the corresponding critical value is selected.

Joint distribution of the random effects – Test if the random effects are correlated

Correlation tests are performed to test if the random effects (calculated from the individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution) are correlated. The null-hypothesis is:

H0: the expectation of the product of the random effects of the first and second parameter is zero

The null-hypothesis is assessed using a t-test.

Remark: In the 2018 version, a Pearson correlation test was used.

For correlations not yet included in the model, a small p-value indicates that there is a significant correlation between the random effects of two parameters and that this correlation should be estimated as part of the model (otherwise simulations from the model will assume that the random effects of the two parameters are not correlated, which is not what is observed for the random effects estimated using the data). Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]).

For correlations already included in the model, a large p-value indicates that one cannot reject the hypothesis that the correlation between the random effects is zero. If the correlation is not significantly different from zero, it may not be worth estimating it in the model. High p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.01-0.05]), orange (p-value in [0.05-0.10]) or red (p-value in [0.10-1]).

In our example, we have assumed in the model that η_V and η_{Cl} are correlated. The high p-value (0.033, above the 0.01 threshold, see above) indicates that the correlation between the random effects of V and Cl is not significantly different from zero and suggests to remove this correlation from the model.

Correlation test (t-test)

		STATISTICS	P-VALUE
eta_ka	eta_V	-0.26	7.94e-1
eta_ka	eta_Cl	-0.21	8.38e-1
eta_V	eta_Cl	1.52	1.39e-1

Remark: as correlations can only be estimated by groups (i.e if a correlation is estimated between (ka, V) and between (V, Cl), then one must also estimate the correlation between (ka, Cl)), it may happen that it is not possible to remove a non-significant correlation without removing also a significant one.

The math behind: Let $\eta_{\psi_1,i}^l$ and $\eta_{\psi_2,i}^l$ the random effects corresponding to the L individual parameters ψ_1 and ψ_2 sampled from the conditional distribution (called replicates) for individual i . First we calculate the product of the random effects averaged over the replicates:

$$p_i^{(L)} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \eta_{\psi_1,i}^l \eta_{\psi_2,i}^l$$

We note $\bar{p} = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i^{(L)}$ the average of the product over the individuals and s their standard deviation. The test statistic is:

$$T = \frac{\bar{p}}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{N}}}$$

and it is compared to a t-distribution with $N - 1$ degrees of freedom with N the number of individuals.

5.2.4.2.1.3 The distribution of the individual parameters

Distribution of the individual parameters not dependent on covariates - Test if transformed individual parameters are normally distributed

When an individual parameter doesn't depend on covariates, its distribution (normal, lognormal, logit or probit) can be transformed into the normal distribution. Then, a Shapiro-Wilk test can be used to test the normality of the transformed parameter. The null hypothesis is:

H0: the transformed individual parameter values (sampled from the conditional distribution) is normally distributed

If the p-value is small, there is evidence that the transformed individual parameter values are not normally distributed and this calls the choice of the parameter distribution into question. Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]).

In our example, there is no reason to reject the null hypothesis of lognormality for Cl.

Shapiro Wilk test

	DISTRIBUTION	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
Cl	lognormal	0.97	6.22e-1

Remark: testing the normality of a transformed individual parameter that does not depend on covariates is equivalent to testing the normality of the associated random effect. We can check in our example that the Shapiro-Wilk tests for $\log(Cl)$ and η_{Cl} are equivalent.

The math behind: Let z_i^l the transformed individual parameters (e.g $\log(V)$ for log-normally distributed parameters and $\text{logit}(F)$ for logit-distributed parameters) sampled from the conditional distribution (called replicates, index l) for individual i . The Shapiro-Wilk test statistic is calculated for each replicate l (i.e the first sample from all individuals, then the second sample from all individuals, etc):

$$W^l = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N a_i z_i^l\right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (z_i^l - \bar{z}^l)^2}$$

with a_i tabulated coefficient and $\bar{z}^l = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N z_i^l$ the average over all individuals, for each replicate.

The statistic displayed in Monolix corresponds to the average statistic over all replicates $W = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L W^l$

. For the p-values, one p-value is calculated for each replicate, using the Shapiro-Wild table with N (number of individuals) degrees of freedom. The Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure is then applied: the p-values are ranked by ascending order and the BH critical value is calculated for each as $\frac{\text{rank}}{L} Q$ with rank the individual p-value's rank, L the total number of p-values (equal to the number of replicates) and $Q = 0.05$ the false discovery rate. The largest p-value that is smaller than the corresponding critical value is selected.

Distribution of the individual parameters dependent on covariates - test the marginal distribution of each individual parameter

Individual parameters that depend on covariates are not anymore identically distributed. Each transformed individual parameter is normally distributed, with its own mean that depends on the value of the individual covariate. In other words, the distribution of an individual parameter is a mixture of (transformed) normal distributions. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for testing the distributional adequacy of these individual parameters. The null-hypothesis is:

H0: the individual parameters are samples from the mixture of transformed normal distributions (defined by the population parameters and the covariate values)

A small p-value indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected. Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]).

With our example, we obtain:

Kolmogorov Smirnov adequacy test

	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
ka	0.1	2.5e-2
v	0.12	1.06e-1

5.2.4.2.2 The model for the observations

A combined1 error model with a normal distribution is assumed in our example:

Observation model f(x)					
TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

5.2.4.2.2.1 Distribution of the residuals

Several tests are performed for the individual residuals (IWRES), the NPDE and for the population residuals (PWRES).

Test if the distribution of the residuals is symmetrical around 0

A Miao, Gel and Gastwirth (2006) test (or Van Der Waerden test in the 2018 release) is used to test the symmetry of the residuals. Indeed, symmetry of the residuals around 0 is an important property that deserves to be tested, in order to decide, for instance, if some transformation of the observations should be done. The null hypothesis tested is:

H0: the median of the residuals is equal to its mean

A small p-value indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected. Small p-values are colored in yellow (p-value in [0.05-0.10]), orange (p-value in [0.01-0.05]) or red (p-value in [0.00-0.01]).

With our example, we obtain:

Symmetry test

	y1	
	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
IWRES	-1.11	2.68e-1
PWRES	-1.94	5.21e-2
NPDE	-3.14	1.66e-3

The math behind: Let R_i the residuals (NPDE, PWRES or IWRES) for each individual i , \bar{R} the mean of the residuals, and M_R their median. The MGG test statistic is:

$$T = \frac{\sqrt{n}}{0.9468922} \frac{\bar{R} - M_R}{\sum_{i=1}^n |R_i - M|}$$

with n the number of residuals. The test statistic is compared to a standard normal distribution.

The formula above is valid for i.i.d (independent and identically distributed) residuals. For the IWRES, the residuals corresponding to a given time and given id are not independent (they resemble each other). To solve the problem, we estimate an effective number of residuals. The number of residuals n can be split into the number of replicates L times the number of observations m . We look for the effective number of replicates \tilde{L} such that:

$$\frac{\tilde{L}}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L (R_i^l)^2 \approx \chi^2(\tilde{L})$$

using a maximum likelihood estimation. The number of residuals is then calculated as $n = \tilde{L} \times m$.

Test if the residuals are normally distributed

A Shapiro Wilk test is used for testing the normality of the residuals. The null hypothesis is:

H0: the residuals are normally distributed

If the p-value is small, there is evidence that the residuals are not normally distributed. The Shapiro Wilk test is known to be very powerful. Then, a small deviation of the empirical distribution from the normal distribution may lead to a very significant test (i.e. a very small p-value), which does not necessarily means that the model should be rejected. Thus, no color highlight is made for this test.

In our example, we obtain:

Shapiro Wilk test

	y1	
	STATISTICS	P-VALUE
IWRES	0.94	2.24e-9
PWRES	0.99	2.68e-1
NPDE	0.98	3.6e-4

The math behind: Let R_i^l the residuals (NPDE, PWRES or IWRES) for individual i . NPDE and PWRES have one values per time points and per individual. IWRES have one value per time point, per individual and per replicate (corresponding to the L individual parameters sampled from the conditional distribution). The Shapiro-Wilk test statistic is calculated for each replicate l (i.e the first sample from all individuals, then the second sample from all individuals, etc):

$$W^l = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N a_i R_i^l\right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (R_i^l - \bar{R}^l)^2}$$

with a_i tabulated coefficient and $\bar{R}^l = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i^l$ the average over all individuals, for each replicate.

The statistic displayed in Monolix corresponds to the average statistic over all replicates $W = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L W^l$. For the p-values, one p-value is calculated for each replicate, using the Shapiro-Wilk table with N (number of individuals) degrees of freedom. The Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure is then applied: the p-values are ranked by ascending order and the BH critical value is calculated for each as $\frac{\text{rank}}{L} Q$ with rank the individual p-value's rank, L the total number of p-values (equal to the number of replicates) and $Q = 0.05$ the false discovery rate. The largest p-value that is smaller than the corresponding critical value is selected.

5.2.4.3 Proposal

Starting from the 2019 version, the section Proposal in the tab Results includes automatic proposals of improvements for the statistical model, based on comparisons of many correlation, covariate and error models.

Model selections are performed by using a BIC criteria (called Criteria in the interface), based on the current simulated individual parameters. This is why the proposal is computed by the task Conditional distribution.

Note that the BIC criteria is not the same as the BIC computed for the Monolix project with the task log-likelihood: it does not characterize the whole model but only each part of the statistical model evaluated in the proposal, and thus yields different values for each type of model. Each criteria is given by the formula:

$$BIC = -2 \log(\mathcal{L}') / nRep + \log(N) \times k$$

where:

- \mathcal{L}' = likelihood of the linear regression
- N = number of individuals
- k = number of estimates betas
- $nRep$ = number of replicates (samples per individual)

The number of estimated parameters k characterizes the part of the statistical model that is evaluated. The likelihood \mathcal{L}' is not the same as the one computed by the log-likelihood task, it is based on the joint distribution:

$$p(y_i, \phi_i; \theta) = p(y_i | \phi_i; \theta) p(\phi_i; \theta)$$

where all the parameters are fixed to the values estimated by Monolix except the parameters characterizing the model that is evaluated: error parameters (in θ) for the error models, individual parameters or random effects (in ϕ_i) for the covariate models or the correlation models.

5.2.4.3.1 Proposed model

The section Proposal is organized in 4 tabs. The first tab summarizes the best proposal for the statistical model, that is the combination of best proposals for the error, covariate and correlation models.

The screenshot displays the Monolix software interface for model estimation. The main window is titled 'PK3_mlxtran - Monolix estimation - 2021R1'. The 'Results' tab is active, showing a comparison between a 'Proposed model' and a 'Current model'.

Proposed model [Apply]

Error model: Y1 COMBINED2

	CORRELATIONS	COVARIATES		
	#1	AGE	LBM	SEX
C1	✓	✓	✓	
V1		✓	✓	
Q2		✓		
V2		✓		
Q3	✓	✓		
V3	✓	✓		✓

Current model

Error model: Y1 COMBINED1

	CORRELATIONS	COVARIATES		
	#1	AGE	LBM	SEX
C1	✓	✓		✓
V1	✓		✓	
Q2		✓		
V2				
Q3		✓		
V3				

The current statistical model is displayed below the proposed model, and the differences are highlighted in light blue.

The proposed model can be applied automatically with the button "Apply". This modifies the current project to include all elements of the proposed statistical model. It is then recommended to save the project under a new name to avoid overwriting previous results.

5.2.4.3.2 Error model

The error model selection is done by computing the criterion for each possible residual error model (constant, proportional, combined1, combined2), where the error parameters are optimized based on the data and the current predictions, for each observation model.

The evaluated models are displayed for each observation mode in increasing order of criterion. The current error model is highlighted in blue.

The screenshot displays the 'Results' tab in the Monolix software interface. It shows two tables of evaluated models for observation modes y1 and y2. The current error model is highlighted in blue.

y1

CRITERIA	PARAMETERS		APPLY
	CONSTANT	PROPORTIONAL	
PROPORTIONAL	5856.56	0.11	APPLY
COMBINED2	5862.01	0.0076	APPLY
COMBINED1	5862.92	0.0015	APPLY
CONSTANT	11766.38	4.63	APPLY

y2

CRITERIA	PARAMETERS		APPLY
	CONSTANT	PROPORTIONAL	
COMBINED1	16014.42	0.87	0.074
COMBINED2	16079.46	1.18	0.1
CONSTANT	16287.41	1.86	APPLY
PROPORTIONAL	16418.21	0.16	APPLY

5.2.4.3.3 Covariate model

The covariate model selection is based on the evaluation of the criterion for each individual parameter independently.

For each individual parameter, all covariate models obtained by adding or removing one covariate are evaluated: beta parameters are estimated with linear regression, and the criterion is computed. The model with the best criterion is retained to continue the same procedure.

All evaluated models are displayed for each parameter, in increasing order of criterion. The current covariate model is highlighted in blue.

Since possibly many covariate models can be evaluated for each parameter, the maximum number of displayed models per parameter is 4 by default and can be changed with a slider, as below. Additional evaluated models can still be displayed by clicking on "more entries" below each table.

The screenshot shows the Monolix software interface for a PK3_mlxtran project. The 'Results' tab is active, displaying the 'COVARIATE MODEL' section. A green box highlights the 'Maximum number of models displayed per parameter' set to 4. Below this, a toggle for 'Display betas' is shown. Two tables are displayed: one for 'CI' and one for 'V1'. Each table shows four models with their respective criteria values and covariate application status (AGE, LBM, SEX).

CI

MODEL	CRITERIA	COVARIATES			APPLY
		AGE	LBM	SEX	
MODEL 1	-57.33	✓	✓		APPLY
MODEL 2	-54.02	✓	✓	✓	APPLY
MODEL 3	-47.6	✓		✓	APPLY
MODEL 4	-44.59	✓			APPLY

V1

MODEL	CRITERIA	COVARIATES			APPLY
		AGE	LBM	SEX	
MODEL 1	17.05	✓	✓		APPLY
MODEL 2	17.08		✓		APPLY
MODEL 3	21.22	✓	✓	✓	APPLY
MODEL 4	21.25		✓	✓	APPLY

Beta parameters are computed for each evaluated model by linear regression. They are not displayed by default, but can be displayed with a toggle as shown below. For categorical covariates, the categories corresponding to the beta parameters are also displayed.

PK3_mlxtran - Monolix estimation - 2021R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Structural model Initial estimates **Statistical model & Tasks** Results Plots

PROPOSED MODEL ERROR MODEL COVARIATE MODEL **CORRELATION MODEL**

POP.PARAM

INDIV.PARAM

STD.ERRORS

LIKELIHOOD

TESTS

PROPOSAL

Maximum number of models displayed per parameter: 4

Display betas

Cl

CRITERIA	CL_POP	COVARIATES			APPLY
		AGE	LBM	SEX	
MODEL 1	-57.33	2.24	-0.007	0.0076	APPLY
MODEL 2	-54.02	2.06	-0.007	0.0097 M	-0.057 APPLY
MODEL 3	-47.6	3.25	-0.0078	M	0.11 APPLY
MODEL 4	-44.59	3.56	-0.0079		APPLY

3 more entries...

V1

CRITERIA	V1_POP	COVARIATES			APPLY
		AGE	LBM	SEX	
MODEL 1	17.05	1.67	-0.0032	0.021	APPLY
MODEL 2	17.08	1.32		0.023	APPLY
MODEL 3	21.22	1.66	-0.0032	0.021 M	-0.0037 APPLY
MODEL 4	21.25	1.33		0.023 M	0.006 APPLY

2 more entries...

5.2.4.3.4 Correlation model

The correlation model selection is done by computing the criterion for each possible correlation block at each dimension, starting with the best solution from the previous dimension. The correlation models are displayed by increasing value of criterion. The current correlation model is highlighted in blue.

In Monolix2021, the correlation model includes also random effects at the inter-occasion level, like in the example below, while they were excluded from the proposal in previous versions.

Proposed model [\[Apply\]](#)

Error model

Y COMBINED1

	CORRELATIONS	COVARIATES	
	ID #1	SEX	TREAT
ka	✓		
v	✓		✓
cl			✓

Current model

Error model

Y COMBINED1

	CORRELATIONS	COVARIATES	
	OCCEVID #1	SEX	TREAT
ka	✓		
v			✓
cl	✓		

5.2.5 Standard errors

5.2.5.1 Purpose

The standard errors represent the uncertainty of the estimated population parameters. In Monolix, they are calculated via the estimation of the Fisher Information Matrix. They can for instance be used to calculate confidence intervals or detect model overparametrization.

5.2.5.2 Calculation of the standard errors

Several methods have been proposed to estimate the standard errors, such as bootstrapping or via the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM). In the Monolix GUI, the standard errors are estimated via the FIM. Bootstrapping can be accessed either through the Rsmix R package or is now incorporated directly into the Monolix interface starting from version 2024R1.

5.2.5.2.1 The Fisher Information Matrix (FIM)

The observed Fisher information matrix (FIM) I is minus the second derivatives of the observed log-likelihood:

$$I(\hat{\theta}) = -\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \log(\mathcal{L}_y(\hat{\theta}))$$

The log-likelihood cannot be calculated in closed form and the same applies to the Fisher Information Matrix. Two different methods are available in Monolix for the calculation of the Fisher Information Matrix: by linearization or by stochastic approximation.

5.2.5.2.1.1 Via stochastic approximation

A stochastic approximation algorithm using a Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm is implemented in Monolix for estimating the FIM. This method is extremely general and can be used for many data and model types (continuous, categorical, time-to-event, mixtures, etc.).

5.2.5.2.1.2 Via linearization

This method can be applied for continuous data only. A continuous model can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{ij} &= f(t_{ij}, z_i) + g(t_{ij}, z_i)\epsilon_{ij} \\ z_i &= z_{pop} + \eta_i \end{aligned}$$

with y_{ij} the observations, \mathbf{f} the prediction, \mathbf{g} the error model, z_i the individual parameter value for individual i , z_{pop} the typical parameter value within the population and η_i the random effect.

Linearizing the model means using a Taylor expansion in order to approximate the observations y_{ij} by a normal distribution. In the formulation above, the appearance of the random variable η_i in the prediction \mathbf{f} in a nonlinear way leads to a complex (non-normal) distribution for the observations y_{ij} . The Taylor expansion is done around the EBEs value, that we note z_i^{mode} .

5.2.5.2.2 Standard errors

Once the Fisher Information Matrix has been obtained, the standard errors can be calculated as the square root of the diagonal elements of the inverse of the Fisher Information Matrix. The inverse of the FIM $I(\hat{\theta})$ is the variance-covariance matrix $C(\hat{\theta})$:

$$C(\hat{\theta}) = I(\hat{\theta})^{-1}$$

The standard error for parameter $\hat{\theta}_k$ can be calculated as:

$$\text{s.e.}(\hat{\theta}_k) = \sqrt{\tilde{C}_{kk}(\hat{\theta})}$$

Note that in Monolix, the Fisher Information Matrix and variance-covariance matrix are calculated on the transformed normally distributed parameters. MonolixSuite version 2024R1 incorporates a change in the calculation of the variance covariance matrix \tilde{C} . **In version 2023 and before**, \tilde{C} was obtained

for untransformed parameters using the Jacobian matrix J . The Jacobian matrix is a first-order approximation.

$$\tilde{C} = J^T C J$$

Starting from version 2024R1 and later, the Jacobian matrix has been replaced by exact formulas to compute the variance, dependent on the distribution of the parameters. Parameters are distinguished into those with normal distribution, lognormal distribution, as well as logit and probitnormal distribution:

- **Normal** distributed parameters: No transformation is required.
- **Lognormal** distributed parameters: The variance in the Gaussian domain (e.g variance of $\log(V_{\text{pop}})$) are obtained via the FIM. To obtain the variance of the untransformed parameters (e.g variance of V_{pop}), the following formula is applied:

$$\text{Var}(\hat{\theta}_k) = (\exp(\sigma^2) - 1) \exp(2\mu + \sigma^2), \text{ with } \mu = \ln(\hat{\theta}_k) \text{ and } \sigma^2 = \text{Var}(\ln(\hat{\theta}_k)).$$
- **Logitnormal and probitnormal** distributed parameters: There are no explicit formula to obtain the variance of the untransformed parameters (e.g bioavailability F) from the transformed parameter (e.g $\text{logit}(F)$). Therefore, a Monte Carlo sampling approach is used. 100000 samples are drawn from the covariance matrix in gaussian domain. Then the samples are transformed from gaussian to non-gaussian domain. For instance in the case of a logitnormal distributed parameter within bounds a and b , the i -th sample of parameter $\theta_{k,i} : \mu_{k,i} = \text{logit}(\theta_{k,i})$ is transformed into non-gaussian space by the inverse logit, i.e. $\theta_{k,i} = \frac{b \times \exp(\mu_{k,i}) + a}{(1 + \exp(\mu_{k,i}))}$. Then the empirical variance σ^2 over all transformed samples θ_k is calculated.

This transformation applies only to the typical values (fixed effects) “pop”. For the other parameters (standard deviation of the random effects “omega”, error model parameters, covariate effects “beta” and correlation parameters “corr”), we obtain directly the variance of these parameters from the FIM.

5.2.5.2.3 Correlation matrix

The correlation matrix is calculated from the variance-covariance matrix as:

$$\text{corr}(\theta_i, \theta_j) = \frac{\tilde{C}_{ij}}{\text{s.e.}(\theta_i)\text{s.e.}(\theta_j)}$$

5.2.5.2.4 Wald test

For the beta parameters characterizing the influence of the covariates, the relative standard error can be used to perform a Wald test, testing if the estimated beta value is significantly different from zero.

5.2.5.3 Running the standard errors task

When running the standard error task, the progress is displayed in the pop-up window. At the end of the task, the correlation matrix is also shown, along with the elapsed time and number of iterations.


```

Monolix scenario
[FISHER] Stochastic Approximation: DONE (iterations: 50)
ESTIMATION OF THE FISHER INFORMATION MATRIX
[FISHER] Stochastic Approximation: DONE (iterations: 50)
Estimation of the Fisher information matrix by Stochastic Approximation -----
Correlation Matrix :
ka_pop      1
V_pop      0.11646      1
cl_pop     -0.040462 -0.097692      1
omega_k     0.052261 -0.016585 0.0046131      1
omega_v     0.024937  0.11377 -0.014448 -0.0040456      1
omega_cl    -0.0024427 -0.016732 -0.055661 0.0060385 -0.12209      1
a           0.045172 -0.030905 0.0081934 -0.024384 0.059117 0.023002      1
b          -0.051996 0.029012 -7.3167e-05 0.010838 -0.077276 -0.023263 -0.93811      1
Eigen values      :      min      max      max/min
                   :      0.062      2      32
Elapsed time (seconds): 0.084
Iterations:      50 (Autostop)
    
```

5.2.5.3.1 Dependencies between tasks:

The “Population parameters” task must be run before launching the Standard errors task. If the Conditional distribution task has already been run, the first iterations of the Standard errors (without linearization) will be very fast, as they will reuse the same draws as those obtained in the Conditional distribution task.

5.2.5.4 Output

5.2.5.4.1 In the graphical user interface

In the **Pop.Param** section of the **Results** tab, three additional columns appear in addition to the estimated population parameters:

- **S.E.:** the estimated standard errors
- **R.S.E.:** the relative standard error (standard error divided by the estimated parameter value)

To help the user in the interpretation, a color code is used for the p-value and the RSE:

- For the p-value: **between .01 and .05**, **between .001 and .01**, and **less than .001**.
- For the RSE: **between 50% and 100%**, **between 100% and 200%**, and **more than 200%**.

When the standard errors were estimated both with and without linearization, the S.E. and R.S.E. are displayed for both methods.

 To estimate standard errors for both methods, the task needs to be run twice, once with and once without the linearization toggle turned on.

	VALUE	STOCH. APPROX.				LINEARIZATION				
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	
Fixed Effects										
ka_pop	1.53	0.31	20.1	1.04	2.24	0.31	20.1	1.04	2.24	
V_pop	0.8	0.22	28.0	0.48	1.35	0.23	28.3	0.47	1.35	
beta_V_WEIGHT	-0.0081	0.0038	46.7	-0.016	-0.00069	0.0038	46.8	-0.016	-0.00068	
Cl_pop	0.04	0.0035	8.62	0.034	0.047	0.0035	8.61	0.034	0.047	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects										
	Value	C.V.(%)								
omega_ka	0.64	70.97	0.15	24.2	0.41	1.01	0.14	22.3	0.42	0.97
omega_V	0.088	8.83	0.035	40.2	0.043	0.18	0.036	40.5	0.043	0.18
omega_Cl	0.28	28.21	0.067	24.3	0.18	0.44	0.064	23.1	0.18	0.43
Error Model Parameters										
a	0.45	0.16	35.8	0.23	0.85	0.12	27.7	0.27	0.75	
b	0.055	0.032	58.7	0.021	0.14	0.024	43.3	0.026	0.12	

In the **STD.ERRORS** section of the **Results** tab, we display:

- **R.S.E:** the relative standard errors
- **Correlation matrix:** the correlation matrix of the population parameters
- **Eigen values:** the smallest and largest eigen values, as well as the condition number (max/min)

- The elapsed time and, starting from Monolix2021R1, the number of iterations for stochastic approximation, as well as a message indicating whether convergence has been reached (“auto-stop”) or if the task was stopped by the user or reached the maximum number of iterations.

To help the user in the interpretation, a color code is used:

- For the correlation: between .5 and .8, between .8 and .9, and higher than .9.
- For the RSE: between 50% and 100%, between 100% and 200%, and more than 200%.

When the standard errors were estimated both with and without linearization, both results appear in different subtabs.

If you hover on a specific value with the mouse, both parameters are highlighted to know easily which parameter you are looking at:

5.2.5.4.2 In the output folder

After having run the Standard errors task, the following files are available:

- **summary.txt:** contains the s.e., r.s.e., p-values, correlation matrix and eigenvalues in an easily readable format, as well as elapsed time and number of iterations for stochastic approximation (starting from Monolix2021R1).
- **populationParameters.txt:** contains the s.e., r.s.e. and p-values in csv format, for the method with (*_lin) or without (*_sa) linearization
- **FisherInformation/correlationEstimatesSA.txt:** correlation matrix of the population parameter estimates, method without linearization (stochastic approximation)
- **FisherInformation/correlationEstimatesLin.txt:** correlation matrix of the population parameter estimates, method with linearization
- **FisherInformation/covarianceEstimatesSA.txt:** variance-covariance matrix of the transformed normally distributed population parameter, method without linearization (stochastic approximation)
- **FisherInformation/covarianceEstimatesLin.txt:** variance-covariance matrix of the transformed normally distributed population parameter, method with linearization

5.2.5.5 Interpreting the correlation matrix of the estimates

The color code of Monolix's results allows to quickly identify population parameter estimates that are strongly correlated. This often reflects model overparameterization and can be further investigated using Mlxlore and the convergence assessment. This is explained in details in this video:

5.2.5.6 Settings

The settings are accessible through the interface via the button next to the Standard errors task:

- **Level of the confidence intervals:** level of confidence intervals to calculate and display in the Population parameters section of the Results.
- **Minimum number of iterations:** minimum number of iterations of the stochastic approximation algorithm to calculate the Fisher Information Matrix.

- **Maximum number of iterations:** maximum number of iterations of the stochastic approximation algorithm to calculate the Fisher Information Matrix. The algorithm stops even if the stopping criteria are not met.

5.2.5.7 Good practices and tips

5.2.5.7.1 When to use “use linearization method”?

Firstly, it is only possible to use the linearization method for continuous data. For the linearization is available, this method is generally much faster than without linearization (i.e stochastic approximation) but less precise. The Fisher Information Matrix by model linearization will generally be able to identify the main features of the model. More precise- and time-consuming - estimation procedures such as stochastic approximation will have very limited impact in terms of decisions for these most obvious features. Precise results are required for the final runs where it becomes more important to rigorously defend decisions made to choose the final model and provide precise estimates and diagnosis plots.

5.2.5.7.2 I have NaNs as results for standard errors for parameter estimates. What should I do? Does it impact the likelihood?

NaNs as standard errors often appear when the model is too complex and some parameters are unidentifiable. They can be seen as an infinitely large standard error.

The likelihood is not affected by NaNs in the standard errors. The estimated population parameters having a NaN as standard error are only very uncertain (infinitely large standard error and thus infinitely large confidence intervals).

5.2.6 Likelihood

5.2.6.1 Purpose

The log-likelihood is the objective function and a key information. The log-likelihood cannot be computed in closed form for nonlinear mixed effects models. It can however be estimated.

5.2.6.2 Log-likelihood estimation

Performing likelihood ratio tests and computing information criteria for a given model requires computation of the log-likelihood

$$\mathcal{LL}_y(\hat{\theta}) = \log(\mathcal{L}_y(\hat{\theta})) \triangleq \log(p(y; \hat{\theta}))$$

where $\hat{\theta}$ is the vector of population parameter estimates for the model being considered, and $p(y; \hat{\theta})$ is the probability distribution function of the observed data given the population parameter estimates. The log-likelihood cannot be computed in closed form for nonlinear mixed effects models. It can

however be estimated in a general framework for all kinds of data and models using the importance sampling Monte Carlo method. This method has the advantage of providing an unbiased estimate of the log-likelihood – even for nonlinear models – whose variance can be controlled by the Monte Carlo size.

Two different algorithms are proposed to estimate the log-likelihood:

- by linearization,
- by Importance sampling.

5.2.6.2.1 Log-likelihood by importance sampling

The observed log-likelihood $\mathcal{LL}(\theta; y) = \log(\mathcal{L}(\theta; y))$ can be estimated without requiring approximation of the model, using a Monte Carlo approach. Since

$$\mathcal{LL}(\theta; y) = \log(p(y; \theta)) = \sum_{i=1}^N \log(p(y_i; \theta))$$

we can estimate $\log(p(y_i; \theta))$ for each individual and derive an estimate of the log-likelihood as the sum of these individual log-likelihoods. We will now explain how to estimate $\log(p(y_i; \theta))$ for any individual i . Using the ϕ -representation of the model (the individual parameters are transformed to be Gaussian), notice first that $p(y_i; \theta)$ can be decomposed as follows:

$$p(y_i; \theta) = \int p(y_i, \phi_i; \theta) d\phi_i = \int p(y_i | \phi_i; \theta) p(\phi_i; \theta) d\phi_i = \mathbb{E}_{p_{\phi_i}} (p(y_i | \phi_i; \theta))$$

Thus, $p(y_i; \theta)$ is expressed as a mean. It can therefore be approximated by an empirical mean using a Monte Carlo procedure:

1. Draw \mathbf{M} independent values $\phi_i^{(1)}, \phi_i^{(2)}, \dots, \phi_i^{(M)}$ from the marginal distribution $p_{\phi_i}(\cdot; \theta)$.
2. Estimate $\log(p(y_i; \theta))$ with $\hat{p}_{i,M} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M p(y_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)$.

By construction, this estimator is unbiased, and consistent since its variance decreases as $1/\mathbf{M}$:

$$\mathbb{E}(\hat{p}_{i,M}) = \mathbb{E}_{p_{\phi_i}} (p(y_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)) = p(y_i; \theta) \quad \text{Var}(\hat{p}_{i,M}) = \frac{1}{M} \text{Var}_{p_{\phi_i}} (p(y_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta))$$

We could consider ourselves satisfied with this estimator since we “only” have to select \mathbf{M} large enough to get an estimator with a small variance. Nevertheless, it is possible to improve the statistical properties of this estimator.

For any distribution \tilde{p}_{ϕ_i} that is absolutely continuous with respect to the marginal distribution p_{ϕ_i} , we can write

$$p(y_i; \theta) = \int p(y_i | \phi_i; \theta) \frac{p(\phi_i; \theta)}{\tilde{p}(\phi_i; \theta)} \tilde{p}(\phi_i; \theta) d\phi_i = \mathbb{E}_{\tilde{p}_{\phi_i}} \left(p(y_i | \phi_i; \theta) \frac{p(\phi_i; \theta)}{\tilde{p}(\phi_i; \theta)} \right)$$

We can now approximate $p(\mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$ using an *importance sampling* integration method with \tilde{p}_{ϕ_i} as the proposal distribution:

1. Draw \mathbf{M} independent values $\phi_i^{(1)}, \phi_i^{(2)}, \dots, \phi_i^{(M)}$ from the marginal distribution $p_{\phi_i}(\cdot; \theta)$.
2. Estimate $\log(p(\mathbf{y}_i; \theta))$ with $\hat{p}_{i,M} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M p(\mathbf{y}_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta) \frac{p(\phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)}{\tilde{p}(\phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)}$.

By construction, this estimator is unbiased, and its variance also decreases as $1/\mathbf{M}$:

$$\text{Var}(\hat{p}_{i,M}) = \frac{1}{M} \text{Var}_{\tilde{p}_{\phi_i}} \left(p(\mathbf{y}_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta) \frac{p(\phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)}{\tilde{p}(\phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)} \right)$$

There exist an infinite number of possible proposal distributions \tilde{p} which all provide the same rate of convergence $1/\mathbf{M}$. The trick is to reduce the variance of the estimator by selecting a proposal distribution so that the numerator is as small as possible.

For this purpose, an optimal proposal distribution would be the conditional distribution $p_{\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i}$. Indeed, for any $m = 1, 2, \dots, M$,

$$p(\mathbf{y}_i | \phi_i^{(m)}; \theta) \frac{p(\phi_i^{(m)}; \theta)}{p(\phi_i^{(m)} | \mathbf{y}_i; \theta)} = p(\mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$$

which has a zero variance, so that only one draw from $p_{\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i}$ is required to exactly compute the likelihood $p(\mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$.

The problem is that it is not possible to generate the $\phi_i^{(m)}$ with this exact conditional distribution, since that would require computing a normalizing constant, which here is precisely $p(\mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$.

Nevertheless, this conditional distribution can be estimated using the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm and a practical proposal “close” to the optimal proposal $p_{\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i}$ can be derived. We can then expect to get a very accurate estimate with a relatively small Monte Carlo size \mathbf{M} .

The mean and variance of the conditional distribution $p_{\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i}$ are estimated by Metropolis-Hastings for each individual i . Then, the $\phi_i^{(m)}$ are drawn with a non-central student t -distribution:

$$\phi_i^{(m)} = \mu_i + \sigma_i \times T_{i,m}$$

where μ_i and σ_i^2 are estimates of $\mathbb{E}(\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$ and $\text{Var}(\phi_i | \mathbf{y}_i; \theta)$, and $(T_{i,m})$ is a sequence of i.i.d. random variables distributed with a Student’s t -distribution with ν degrees of freedom (see section Advanced settings for the log-likelihood for the number of degrees of freedom).

i The standard error of the LL on all the draws is proposed. It represents the impact of the variability of the draws on the LL uncertainty, given the estimated population parameters, but it does not take into account the uncertainty of the model that comes from the uncertainty on the population parameters.

i Even if $\hat{\mathcal{L}}_y(\theta) = \prod_{i=1}^N \hat{p}_{i,M}$ is an unbiased estimator of $\mathcal{L}_y(\theta)$, $\hat{\mathcal{L}}_y(\theta)$ is a biased estimator of $\mathcal{L}_y(\theta)$.
Indeed, by Jensen's inequality, we have $\mathbb{E}(\log(\hat{\mathcal{L}}_y(\theta))) \leq \log(\mathbb{E}(\hat{\mathcal{L}}_y(\theta))) = \log(\mathcal{L}_y(\theta))$.

✓ Best practice: the bias decreases as M increases and also if $\hat{\mathcal{L}}_y(\theta)$ is close to $\mathcal{L}_y(\theta)$. It is therefore highly recommended to use a proposal as close as possible to the conditional distribution $p_{\phi_i|y_i}$, which means having to estimate this **conditional distribution** before estimating the log-likelihood (i.e. run task "Conditional distribution" before).

5.2.6.2.2 Log-likelihood by linearization

The likelihood of the nonlinear mixed effects model cannot be computed in a closed-form. An alternative is to approximate this likelihood by the likelihood of the Gaussian model deduced from the nonlinear mixed effects model after linearization of the function \mathbf{f} (defining the structural model) around the predictions of the individual parameters $(\phi_i; 1 \leq i \leq N)$.

Notice that the log-likelihood **can not be computed** by linearization **for discrete outputs (categorical, count, etc.) nor for mixture models**.

✓ Best practice: We **strongly** recommend to compute the conditional mode before computing the log-likelihood by linearization. Indeed, the linearization should be made around the most probable values as they are the same for both the linear and the nonlinear model.

5.2.6.2.3 Best practices: When should I use the linearization and when should I use the importance sampling?

Firstly, it is only possible to use the linearization algorithm for the continuous data. In that case, this method is generally much faster than importance sampling method and also gives good estimates of the LL. The LL calculation by model linearization will generally be able to identify the main features of the model. More precise- and time-consuming - estimation procedures such as stochastic

approximation and importance sampling will have very limited impact in terms of decisions for these most obvious features. Selection of the final model should instead use the unbiased estimator obtained by Monte Carlo.

5.2.6.3 Display and outputs

In case of estimation using the importance sampling method, a graphical representation is proposed to see the valuation of the mean value over the Monte Carlo iterations as on the following:

The final estimations are displayed in the result frame as below. Notice that there is a “Copy table” icon on the top of each table to copy them in Excel, Word, ... The table format and display will be kept.

The log-likelihood is given in Monolix together with the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC):

$$AIC = -2\mathcal{L}\mathcal{L}_y(\hat{\theta}) + 2P$$

$$BIC = -2\mathcal{L}\mathcal{L}_y(\hat{\theta}) + \log(N)P$$

where P is the total number of parameters to be estimated and N the number of subjects.

The new BIC criterion penalizes the size of θ_R (which represents random effects and fixed covariate effects involved in a random model for individual parameters) with the log of the number of subjects (N) and the size of θ_F (which represents all other fixed effects, so typical values for parameters in the population, beta parameters involved in a non-random model for individual parameters, as well as error parameters) with the log of the total number of observations (n_{tot}), as follows:

$$BIC_c = -2\mathcal{L}\mathcal{L}_y(\hat{\theta}) + \dim(\theta_R) \log N + \dim(\theta_F) \log n_{tot}$$

$\dim(\theta_R)$ counts the number of estimated population parameters corresponding to ω_{*} (standard deviation of IIV), γ_{*} (standard deviation of IOV), corr_{**} (correlation between random effects) and β_{*} (covariate effects) if the covariate is added on a parameter with random effects. $\dim(\theta_F)$ counts the number of population parameters corresponding to $_{*}\text{pop}$ (typical value), a/b (error model), and β_{*} if the covariate is added on a parameter without random effects.

If the log-likelihood has been computed by importance sampling, the number of degrees of freedom used for the proposal t-distribution (5 by default) is also displayed, together with the standard error of the LL on the individual parameters drawn from the t-distribution.

In terms of output, a folder called `LogLikelihood` is created in the result folder where the following files are created

- `logLikelihood.txt`: containing for each computed method, the $-2 \times$ log-likelihood, the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC), the Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC), and the corrected Bayesian Information Criteria (BICc).
- `individualLL.txt`: containing the $-2 \times$ log-likelihood for each individual for each computed method.

5.2.6.4 Advanced settings for the log-likelihood

Monolix uses a t-distribution as proposal. By default, the number of degrees of freedom of this distribution is fixed to 5. In the settings of the task, it is also possible to optimize the number of degrees of freedom. In such a case, the default possible values are 1, 2, 5, 10 and 20 degrees of freedom. A distribution with a small number of degree of freedom (i.e. heavy tails) should be avoided in case of stiff ODE's defined models.

Estimation of the log-likelihood - Settings

Monte Carlo Importance Sampling

Monte Carlo size
10000

Degrees of freedom of the t-distribution
 Fixed Optimized

5

SET DEFAULTS CLOSE

Estimation of the log-likelihood - Settings

Monte Carlo Importance Sampling

Monte Carlo size
10000

Degrees of freedom of the t-distribution
 Fixed Optimized

Degrees of freedom to test

SET DEFAULTS CLOSE

5.3 Convergence assessment

Monolix includes a convergence assessment tool. It allows to execute a workflow of estimation tasks several times, with different, randomly generated, initial values of fixed effects, as well as different seeds. The goal is to assess the robustness of the convergence.

5.3.1 Running the convergence assessment

For that, click on the shortcut button in the “Tasks” part.

A dedicated panel opens as in the figure below. The first shortcut button next to Run can be used to go back to the estimation.

The user can define

- the number of runs, or replicates

- the type of assessment:
 - Estimation of the standard errors and log-likelihood
 - Use the linearization method if the previous option is selected.
- the initial parameters. By default, initial values are uniformly drawn from intervals defined around the estimated values if population parameters have been estimated, the initial estimates otherwise. Notice that it is possible to set one initial parameter constant while generating the others. The minimum and maximum of the generated parameters can be modified by the user.

All settings used are saved and reloaded with the run containing the convergence assessment results.

Notice that

- In the case of estimation of the standard errors and log-likelihood by linearization, the individual parameters with the conditional mode method are computed as well to have more relevant linearization.
- In the case of estimation of the standard errors and log-likelihood without the linearization, the conditional distribution method is computed too to have more relevant estimation.
- **The workflow is the same between the runs and is not the one defined in the interface.**

Click on Run to execute the tool. Thus you are able to estimate the population parameters using several initial seeds and/or several initial conditions.

5.3.2 Display and outputs

Several kinds of plots are given as a summary of the results.

First of all, the SAEM convergence assessment is proposed. The convergence of each parameter on each run is proposed. It allows to see if the convergence for each run is ok.

Then, a plot showing the estimated values for each replicate is proposed. If the estimation of the standard errors was included in the scenario, the estimated standard errors are also displayed as horizontal bars. It allows to see if all parameters converge statistically to the same values.

Starting from the 2019 version, it is possible to export manually all the plots in the `Assessment` folder in your result folder by clicking on the “export” icon (purple box on the previous figure). Finally, if log-likelihood without linearization is used, the curves for convergence of importance sampling are proposed.

In addition, a Monolix project and its result folder is generated for each set of initial parameters. They are located in the `Assessment` subfolder of the main project’s result folder (located by default next to the `.mlxtran` project file). Along with all the runs, there is a summary of all the runs “`assessment.txt`” providing all the individual parameter estimates along with the `-2LL`, as in the following:

```
Parameters,Run_1,Run_2,Run_3,Run_4,Run_5
Cl_pop,0.03994527,0.04017999,0.04016216,0.04012077,0.0400175
V_pop,0.4575748,0.4556463,0.4560732,0.4557009,0.4569431
a,0.4239969,0.42482,0.4227559,0.4294611,0.435585
b,0.05653124,0.05684357,0.05700663,0.054965,0.05450724
ka_pop,1.527947,1.521184,1.5226,1.519333,1.519678
omega_Cl,0.2653109,0.2643172,0.268475,0.266199,0.2693083
omega_V,0.1293328,0.1274441,0.122951,0.1301242,0.1261098
omega_ka,0.6530206,0.6655251,0.643456,0.6425528,0.6424614
-2LL,339.387,339.417,339.429,339.444,339.462
```

Notice that, starting from the 2019 version, it is possible to reload all the results of a previous convergence if nothing has changed in the project. Starting from version 2021, the settings of the convergence assessment are also reloaded.

5.3.3 Best practices: what is the use the convergence assessment tool?

We cannot claim that SAEM always converges (i.e., with probability 1) to the global maximum of the likelihood. We can only say that it converges under quite general hypotheses to a maximum – global or perhaps local – of the likelihood. A large number of simulation studies have shown that SAEM converges with high probability to a “good” solution – hopefully the global maximum – after a small number of iterations. The purpose of this tool is to evaluate the SAEM algorithm with initial conditions and see if the estimated parameters are the “global” minimum.

The trajectory of the outputs of SAEM depends on the sequence of random numbers used by the algorithm. This sequence is entirely determined by the “seed.” In this way, two runs of SAEM using the same seed will produce exactly the same results. If different seeds are used, the trajectories will be different but convergence occurs to the same solution under quite general hypotheses. However, if the trajectories converge to different solutions, that does not mean that any of these results are “false”. It just means that the model is sensitive to the seed or to the initial conditions. The purpose of this tool is to evaluate the SAEM algorithm with several seeds to see the robustness of the convergence.

5.4 Model building

Starting from the 2019 version, a panel Model building provides automatic model building tools:

- Automatic covariate model building
- Automatic statistical model building

This panel is accessible via the button Model building next to Run in the interface of Monolix, or from the section Perspective in the tab Home.

5.4.1 Automatic covariate model building

Starting from the 2019 version, automatic covariate model building algorithms are implemented in Monolix. The feature is available by clicking on the icon next to the Run button in the Statistical model & Tasks tab:

Or by clicking on the Home tab and then the Perspective subtab:

Three different methods for automatic covariate model building can be chosen in the “Initialization” tab of the Model building panel:

Model building initialization

AUTOMATIC COVARIATE MODEL BUILDING
 AUTOMATIC STATISTICAL MODEL BUILDING

Strategy

COSSAC
 At each step, the covariate to test is chosen based on correlations between covariates and parameters (fast)

SAMBA
 At each step, the covariates model is updated based on statistical tests (very fast)

SCM
 At each step, all covariates are tested (slow)

RUN

5.4.1.1 SCM

This is the classic stepwise covariate modeling method. A set of iterations of forward selection is followed by a set of iterations of backward selection.

In the forward selection, at each step, each of the remaining (i.e not yet included) parameter-covariate relationships are added to the model in an univariate model (one model per relationship), and run. Among all models, the model that improves some criteria (LRT, or BICc) most is selected and taken forward to the next step. During backward elimination, parameter-covariate relationships are removed in an univariate manner.

This method is effective but expensive in terms of number of runs, because it requires to estimate the population parameters with SAEM and simulate individual parameters from Conditional distributions for each evaluated model.

5.4.1.2 COSSAC

COSSAC (COnditional Sampling use for Stepwise Approach based on Correlation tests) is a fast, innovative covariate search strategy that Lixoft validated and published here:

Ayral G, Si Abdallah JF, Magnard C, Chauvin J. A novel method based on unbiased correlations tests for covariate selection in nonlinear mixed effects models: The COSSAC approach. *CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol.* 2021 Apr;10(4):318-329. doi: 10.1002/psp4.12612. PMID: 33755345; PMCID: PMC8099437.

COSSAC makes use of the information contained in the base model run to choose which covariate to try first (instead of trying all covariates “blindly” as in SCM). Indeed, the correlation between the individual parameters (or random effects) and the covariates hints at possibly relevant parameter-covariate relationships. If the EBEs (empirical Bayes estimates) are used, shrinkage may bias the result. COSSAC instead uses samples from the a posteriori conditional distribution (available as “conditional distribution” task in Monolix) to calculate the correlation between the random effects and covariates. A p-value can be derived using the Pearson’s correlation test for continuous covariate and ANOVA for categorical covariate. The p-values are used to sort all the random effect-covariate relationships, whether they are included in the model or not.

The iterations of COSSAC alternate between a forward selection and a backward selection, depending on the results of the correlation tests:

- Initialization:

- Run the base model (population parameter estimation, conditional distribution sampling, and log-likelihood estimation).
- Calculate the p-values of all the parameter-covariate relationships using Pearson's correlation tests and ANOVA (automatically done in Monolix)
- Start with a backward selection.
- Forward selection:
 - a. Add the covariate with the smallest correlation p-value (among the remaining parameter-covariate relationships) to the model, or the next smallest if the smallest has already been tried, and so until no correlation p-values below a threshold remain
 - b. Run the model with the same initial values as the base model (initial estimates for the new beta parameters are 0)
 - c. Accept/reject the relationship based on the likelihood ratio test or BICc: the model is not retained if the criteria does not improve (with a threshold for the likelihood ratio test)
 - d. Calculate all parameter-covariate correlation p-values
 - e. Try a backward selection
- Backward selection:
 - a. Among the covariates present in the model, remove the covariate with the highest (less significant) correlation p-value, or the next highest if the highest has already been tried, and so until no correlation p-values above a threshold remain
 - b. Run the model with the same initial values as the base model (initial estimates for the new beta parameters are 0)
 - c. Accept/reject the relationship removal based on the likelihood ratio test or BICc: the model is not retained if the criteria does not improve (with a threshold for the likelihood ratio test)
 - d. Calculate all parameter-covariate relationship correlation p-value
 - e. Try a forward selection
- The algorithm continues until no forward or backward selection is possible, or after testing 10 new relationships on the same model.
- Relationships between covariates and parameters without variability can not be explored with COSSAC, therefore parameters without variability are handled with SCM at the end of COSSAC.

Example

The major difference between SCM and COSSAC is that very few iterations are usually needed with COSSAC before deciding to add or remove a parameter-covariate relationship: between 1 and 10, depending on the number of significant correlations and the improvement brought by each new relationship.

The schema below illustrates this difference on an example with 4 parameters (k_a , V , Cl , $Tlag$) and 3 covariates (Age, Sex, WT). Purple arrows represent forward selections while orange arrows represent backward selections. Starting from a model with no relationship between parameters and covariates, each model run in a new iteration is represented with a rectangle, colored in blue if the model is kept as a starting point for the next iteration, or in grey if the model does not bring improvement. Final models are colored in green. In the case of COSSAC, 1 iteration is sufficient to update the model except at the second step, because the first relationship tried (Sex on η_{Tlag}) does not improve the criteria. At the last step only 3 relationships with a remaining p-value below the threshold have to be tested

before finishing. In the case of SCM, all models run are not displayed but the number of iterations at each step is written. In total, 45 models are run during the SCM procedure, while COSSAC needs only 8 models.

5.4.1.3 SAMBA

Starting from the 2021 version, with “SAMBA” in the covariate model building panel, it is possible to run SAMBA algorithm applied only to the covariate effects. At each iteration, the model is run, the Proposal is calculated and applied (taking into account only the covariates and not the error model or correlations) and this new model is then run in the next iteration. The algorithm stops when the Proposal does not suggest any change any more (or if an already tested model is suggested by the proposal).

At each iteration, several covariates can be added or removed, thus SAMBA is very fast.

5.4.1.4 Settings

The linearization method is selected by default to compute the log-likelihood of the estimated model at each iteration. It can be unselected to use importance sampling.

The improvement can be evaluated with two different criteria based on the log-likelihood, that can be selected using the Advanced settings button:

- BICc (by default)
- LRT (likelihood ratio threshold): by default the forward threshold is 0.01 for COSSAC and 0.05 for SCM, and the backward threshold is 0.01. These values can be changed in the settings.

By default, the correlation thresholds to add new covariate effects in COSSAC (forward) is 0.5 and the correlation threshold to remove some covariate effects in COSSAC (backward) is 0.01. These values can be changed in the settings.

Starting from the 2021 version, all settings used are saved and reloaded with the run containing the model building results.

The estimation tasks for all runs are set automatically to “population parameter”, “EBEs”, “conditional distribution” and “likelihood”, independently of the tasks selected in the base (parent) run.

5.4.1.5 Selecting covariates and parameters

It is possible to select part of the covariates and individual parameters to be used in the algorithm:

Moreover, a panel “Locked relationships” can be opened to lock in or lock out some covariate-parameter relationships among the ones that are available:

Covariates age, wt Parameters 4 items selected

Select: All | None

- ✓ age
- sex
- ✓ wt

Locked relationships

🔓 Unlocked
🔒 Locked in
🔴 Locked out
Unlock all

	age	sex	wt
Tlag	🔒	🔒	🔒
ka	🔒	🔒	🔴
V	🔒	🔒	🔴
cl	🔒	🔒	🔒

Starting from the 2021 version, all relationships considered in model building are part of the settings which are saved and reloaded with the run containing the model building results.

5.4.1.6 Results

The results of the model building are displayed in a tab Results, with the list of model run at each iteration (see for example the figure below). All resulting runs are also located in the ModelBuilding subfolder of the project's result folder (located by default next to the .mlxtran project file).

In the Results tab, by default runs are displayed by order of iteration, except the best model which is displayed in first position, highlighted in green. Differences with the previous iteration are highlighted in yellow. Parameters or covariates that have been excluded from the covariate search appear in grey. Locked in or locked out relationships are also indicated with a blue or red icon.

	age	sex	wt
Iteration: 1 ^ BICc: 703.34 -2LL: 652.95 Export and load			
Tlag	✓	🔒	
ka			🔒
V			🔒
cl			
Iteration: 2 BICc: 702.69 -2LL: 648.84 Export and load			
Tlag	✓	🔒	
ka			🔒
V			🔒
cl			✓
Iteration: 3 BICc: 704.48 -2LL: 650.63 Export and load			
Tlag	✓	🔒	
ka			🔒
V			🔒
cl	✓		

Note that the table of iterations can be sorted by iteration number or criteria (see green marks below). Buttons “export and load” (see blue mark below) can also be used to export the model estimated at this iteration as a new Monolix project with a new name.

	age	sex	wt
Iteration: 1 ^ BICc: 703.34 -2LL: 652.95 Export and load			
Tlag	✓	🔒	
ka			🔒
V			🔒
cl			

5.4.2 Statistical model building with SAMBA

Starting from the 2019 version, an automatic statistical model building algorithm is implemented in Monolix: SAMBA (Stochastic Approximation for Model Building Algorithm)

SAMBA is an iterative procedure to accelerate and optimize the process of model building by identifying at each step how best to improve some of the model components (residual error model, covariate effects, correlations between random effects). This method allows to find the optimal statistical model which minimizes some information criterion in very few steps. It is described in more details in the following publication:

Prague, M, Lavielle, M. SAMBA: A novel method for fast automatic model building in nonlinear mixed-effects models. CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol. 2022; 00: 1- 12. doi:10.1002/psp4.12742

At each iteration, the best statistical model is selected with the same method as the Proposal. This step is very quick as it does not require to estimate new parameters with SAEM for all evaluated models. Initial estimates are set to the estimated values from the Proposal.

The population parameters of the selected model are then estimated with SAEM, individual parameters are simulated from the conditional distributions, and the log-likelihood is computed to evaluate the improvement of the model. The algorithm stops when no improvement is brought by the selected model or if it has already been tested.

5.4.2.1 Initialization

Model building initialization

AUTOMATIC COVARIATE MODEL BUILDING | **AUTOMATIC STATISTICAL MODEL BUILDING**

Strategy: SAMBA
 At each step, the error, covariates and correlations models are updated based on statistical tests (very fast)

RUN

SET DEFAULT SETTINGS | ADVANCED SETTINGS

Use linearization method

Covariates: 3 items selected | Parameters: 4 items selected

Locked relationships

🔓 Unlocked | 🔒 Locked in | 🔒 Locked out | 🔓 Unlock all

	age	sex	wt
Tlag	🔒	🔒	🔒
ka	🔒	🔒	🔒
v	🔒	🔒	🔒
cl	🔒	🔒	🔒

5.4.2.1.1 Settings

The linearization method is selected by default to compute the log-likelihood of the estimated model at each iteration. It can be unselected to use importance sampling.

The improvement can be evaluated with two different criteria based on the log-likelihood, that can be selected in the settings (available via the icon next to Run):

- BICc (by default)
- LRT (likelihood ratio threshold): by default the forward threshold is 0.01 and the backward threshold is 0.01. These values can be changed in the settings.

Starting from the 2021 version, all settings used are saved and reloaded with the run containing the model building results.

5.4.2.1.2 Selecting covariates and parameters

It is possible to select part of the covariates and individual parameters to be used in the algorithm:

Moreover, a panel “Locked relationships” can be opened to lock in or lock out some covariate-parameter relationships among the ones that are available:

Starting from the 2021 version, all relationships considered in model building are part of the settings which are saved and reloaded with the run containing the model building results.

5.4.2.2 Results

The results of the model building are displayed in a tab Results, with the list of model run at each iteration (see for example the figure below) and the corresponding $-2LL$ and BICc values.

All resulting runs are also located in the ModelBuilding subfolder of the project’s result folder (located by default next to the .mlxtran project file).

In the Results tab, by default runs are displayed by order of iteration, except the best model which is displayed in first position, highlighted in blue.

The screenshot shows the Monolix model building results interface. The window title is "warfarinPK_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix model building - 2021...". The interface has a menu bar with "Project", "Settings", "Export", and "Help". Below the menu bar are tabs for "Initialization" and "Results".

The main content area is titled "Model building results" and displays two iterations:

- Iteration 2:** BICc: 695.42, -2LL: 638.1. The error model is Y1 COMBINED2. The covariate table shows Tlag (checked), ka (locked), V (locked), and Cl (checked).
- Iteration 1:** BICc: 703.34, -2LL: 652.95. The error model is Y1 COMBINED1. The covariate table shows Tlag (checked), ka (locked), V (locked), and Cl (checked).

Each iteration section includes an "Error model" and a "COVARIATES" table. The "Error model" section shows the model name (Y1 COMBINED2 for iteration 2, Y1 COMBINED1 for iteration 1). The "COVARIATES" table has columns for AGE and WT. The parameters Tlag, ka, V, and Cl are listed in a separate column. Green checkmarks indicate that the parameter is checked, and red padlocks indicate that the parameter is locked.

Note that the table of iterations can be sorted by iteration number or criteria (see green marks below). Buttons "export and load" (see blue mark below) can also be used to export the model estimated at this iteration as a new Monolix project with a new name and open it in the current Monolix session.

While the algorithm is running, the progress of the estimation tasks at each iteration is displayed on a white pop-up window, and temporary green messages confirm each successful task.

5.5 Bootstrap

i Bootstrap is not available in versions prior to 2024R1

5.5.1 Introduction

The Bootstrap module in Monolix provides a robust method to assess parameter uncertainty, offering an alternative to calculating standard errors via inversion of the Fisher Information Matrix. This approach becomes particularly valuable when facing issues such as NaNs in standard errors due to numerical errors in matrix inversion or biases in results caused by incorrect assumptions of asymptotic

normality for parameter estimates. Bootstrap overcomes these challenges by sampling many replicate datasets and re-estimating parameters on each replicate.

While powerful, bootstrap comes with certain drawbacks:

- Running many replicates for population parameter estimation can be time-consuming. Bootstrap in Monolix can be used from command line and with distributed calculation (parallelization on a grid via MPI).
- Saving a large number of new datasets and results may raise storage issues. You can choose in the settings whether to save sampled datasets and results.

5.5.2 Accessing the bootstrap module

Bootstrap can be accessed under the “Perspective” menu or with a shortcut next to “Run” in the “Statistical model & Tasks” tab:

5.5.3 Available bootstrap settings

Users can customize the following settings:

- **Number of runs:** Number of bootstrap replicates
- **Estimation tasks:** Estimation tasks to run among population parameters, Standard Errors, and Log-Likelihood
- **Initial values:** Whether bootstrap runs should start their estimation from the same initial values as the initial run, or from the final estimated values from the initial run.
- **Sampling method:** Type of bootstrap:
 - **Nonparametric Bootstrap** (case resampling): New datasets are sampled from the initial dataset for each replicate. Each individual of the new dataset is sampled randomly with replacement from the initial dataset. This means that some individuals from the original dataset will appear several times in the resampled dataset, while some individuals will not appear at all. The generated datasets are thus similar but different compared to the original dataset. This method makes no assumption on the model.
 - **Parametric Bootstrap** (SSE): This method is also called SSE for stochastic simulation and estimation. New datasets are simulated from the model for each replicate. Individual parameters are sampled from the population distribution and individuals are simulated using the same design as in the original dataset (same treatments, covariates, regressors, and

observation times). Residual error is added on top of the model predictions to obtain a realistic dataset. If the initial dataset has censored data, censoring limits to apply to the simulated datasets can be specified by the user. This method assumes that the model correctly captures the original data.

- **Sample size:** Number of individuals in the bootstrap datasets. By default it is set equal to the number of individuals of the original dataset but can be modified if required.
- **Stratified resampling:** Selection of categorical covariates which distribution should be preserved when re-sampling individuals to create datasets for non-parametric bootstrap. When the original dataset contains few individuals, or when a categorical covariate distribution is highly imbalanced with only few individuals belonging to one of the categories, resampled bootstrap datasets can result in quite different distributions (e.g. only one individual left in one of the categories) and this can lead to a bias, in particular on the covariate effects (beta) parameters. To avoid this situation, the sampling can be done such that the number of individuals in each category of the covariates selected in “stratified resampling” remains the same as in the initial dataset.
- **Confidence interval level:** Level of the confidence interval bounds displayed in the results to summarize the uncertainty on the population parameters.
- **Save bootstrap runs:** Option to save or not save bootstrap datasets and results folder of each bootstrap run. Both options need to be selected if you want to be able to reload each bootstrap run including the results.
- **Replace runs with failed convergence:** Option to replace or not bootstrap replicates that have a failed convergence. This option allows to replace runs for which the “auto-stop” criteria of the exploratory phase of the population parameter estimation have not been reached. You can also set a maximal number of runs to replace, so that bootstrap will not go on forever if many runs do not converge. Bootstrap will stop once the maximal number is reached.

5.5.4 Running bootstrap

After clicking on “Run”, bootstrap is launched and the population parameters estimates from all runs already done are shown as a table and as a plot of their medians and their confidence intervals with respect to the bootstrap iterations. The table and plot updates as soon as new bootstrap run finishes. An estimation of the remaining time to complete all bootstrap runs is available at the top.

If you have stopped bootstrap before the last run, or you want to add more runs to your bootstrap results, you can resume bootstrap so that the runs already done will be reused instead of being rerun:

5.5.5 Results

Bootstrap results reported in the interface and the output files include the following. Depending on the choice of estimation tasks in the bootstrap settings, results for population parameters, RSE (if Standard error task was selected), and LL (if log-likelihood task was selected) are available.

- **Results > [Estimates]:** Estimates from each bootstrap run displayed in tables.

RUN	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load	Load
Fixed Effects															
ka_pop	1.4012	1.0241	1.4076	1.4324	1.274	1.9782	1.7039	1.565	1.7805	1.5778	1.2017	1.5507	2.0223	1.6283	1.8276
V_pop	0.4601	0.4335	0.4747	0.47	0.4609	0.4405	0.4572	0.4625	0.4996	0.4616	0.4628	0.4606	0.44	0.4544	0.4859
Cl_pop	0.04263	0.03895	0.04178	0.04157	0.04292	0.03635	0.03799	0.04218	0.0442	0.04175	0.0426	0.0416	0.03715	0.03762	0.04426
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects															
omega_ka	0.3997	0.3898	0.6214	0.4439	0.2673	0.768	0.6745	0.7398	0.77	0.619	0.3978	0.5813	0.7548	0.594	0.8138
omega_V	0.1153	0.0791	0.1258	0.1191	0.04357	0.1436	0.1208	0.1289	0.1153	0.09866	0.03737	0.1071	0.1149	0.08825	0.1448
omega_Cl	0.2626	0.2613	0.2956	0.2753	0.134	0.3266	0.2678	0.1527	0.2056	0.1046	0.1355	0.04599	0.2197	0.2382	0.1761
Error Model Parameters															
a	0.5469	0.7037	0.5371	0.5932	0.4561	0.3777	0.4947	0.4988	0.1758	0.3821	0.3955	0.4784	0.4225	0.2876	0.1716
b	0.05355	0.000002873	0.005217	0.0008658	0.06623	0.06084	0.02551	0.00005355	0.07792	0.05204	0.05432	0.05672	0.03384	0.09324	0.1075

When the options to save both the results folder and the datasets have been selected, it is possible to load each bootstrap run via the “load” button in the “Pop [Estimates]” tab:

- **Plots:** Estimates from each bootstrap run displayed as distribution plots. Distribution plots can be displayed as boxplots or as histograms (pdf).

- **Results > [Summary]:** Summary table of bootstrap estimates including value of the initial run (reference), mean and median over bootstrap runs, standard error (SE) over bootstrap runs, relative standard error (RSE) over bootstrap runs, confidence intervals (according to chosen

confidence level). For population parameter, the bias of the mean over bootstrap runs compared to the reference value is calculated as $\text{bias} = (\text{mean} - \text{reference})/\text{reference} * 100$. If some runs have not reached convergences, a toggle appears to filter the summary table and keep only runs which have converged.

theophyliline_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix bootstrap - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Initialization Results Plots

Pop [Estimates] Pop [Summary] RSE [Estimates] RSE [Summary] LL [Estimates] LL [Summary]

Pop [Summary]

	REFERENCE	MEAN	SE	RSE (%)	P2.5	MEDIAN	P97.5	BIAS (%)
Fixed Effects								
ka_pop	1.53	1.63	0.37	22.87	1.08	1.58	2.47	6.7
V_pop	0.45	0.46	0.02	4.34	0.42	0.46	0.5	1.14
CL_pop	0.04	0.04	0.003	7.3	0.034	0.041	0.045	0.3
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects								
omega_ka	0.66	0.63	0.2	31.62	0.29	0.63	1.05	-4.87
omega_V	0.12	0.12	0.029	24.82	0.037	0.12	0.16	-4.57
omega_CL	0.26	0.23	0.087	37.82	0.063	0.24	0.38	-12.1
Error Model Parameters								
a	0.45	0.43	0.17	38.9	0.12	0.41	0.74	-4.72
b	0.053	0.055	0.037	67.82	0.0001	0.054	0.13	3.21

Elapsed time: 00:18:55
Number of runs: 200

theophyliline_project.mlxtran [demo] - Monolix bootstrap - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Initialization Results Plots

Pop [Estimates] Pop [Summary] RSE [Estimates] RSE [Summary] LL [Estimates] LL [Summary]

LL (lin) [Summary]

	MEAN	SE	RSE (%)	P2.5	MEDIAN	P97.5
-2LL	326.33	24.15	7.4	274.97	327.93	371.56
AIC	342.33	24.15	7.05	290.97	343.93	387.56
BIC	346.21	24.15	6.97	294.84	347.81	391.44
BICc	357.72	24.15	6.75	306.36	359.33	402.96

- **Main window (Estimation) > Results > Pop Param:** The bootstrap results also appear in the table of population parameter estimates of the parent run. This is convenient to compare the estimated values and their confidence intervals estimated via the Fisher Information Matrix, to the median and confidence intervals estimated via bootstrap. Bootstrap results can be included in the pop param table when generating reports from Monolix.

theophylline_project.mlxtran [demo] * - Monolix estimation - 2024R1

		LINEARIZATION		BOOTSTRAP (N=1000)					
VALUE		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)	P2.5	P97.5	P2.5	MEDIAN	P97.5	
Fixed Effects									
ka_pop	1.53	0.32	20.7	1.03	2.26	1.07	1.55	2.34	
V_pop	0.45	0.02	4.50	0.42	0.5	0.42	0.46	0.5	
Cl_pop	0.04	0.0033	8.17	0.034	0.047	0.034	0.04	0.046	
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects									
	Value	C.V.(%)							
omega_ka	0.66	73.81	0.15	22.3	0.43	1.01	0.29	0.63	1.05
omega_V	0.13	12.58	0.038	30.6	0.071	0.22	0.037	0.12	0.16
omega_Cl	0.26	26.54	0.061	23.5	0.17	0.41	0.065	0.25	0.39
Error Model Parameters									
a	0.44	0.13	28.2	0.26	0.75	0.12	0.41	0.74	
b	0.054	0.024	44.5	0.025	0.12	0.00014	0.054	0.14	

- Saved datasets:** In the case of non-parametric bootstrap, resampled datasets used in bootstrap runs have new subject identifiers defined as integers in the column tagged as ID, and include an additional column named "original_id" with the corresponding subject identifiers from the initial dataset.

ID	AMT	TIME	CONC	WEIGHT	SEX	original_id
1	4.4	0	.	72.4	M	2
1	.	0.27	1.72	72.4	M	2
1	.	0.52	7.91	72.4	M	2
1	.	1	8.31	72.4	M	2
1	.	1.92	8.33	72.4	M	2
1	.	3.5	6.85	72.4	M	2
1	.	5.02	6.08	72.4	M	2
1	.	7.03	5.4	72.4	M	2
1	.	9	4.55	72.4	M	2
1	.	12	3.01	72.4	M	2
1	.	24.3	0.9	72.4	M	2
2	4.92	0	.	65	F	11
2	.	0.25	4.86	65	F	11
2	.	0.5	7.24	65	F	11
2	.	0.98	8	65	F	11
2	.	1.98	6.81	65	F	11
2	.	3.6	5.87	65	F	11
2	.	5.02	5.22	65	F	11
2	.	7.03	4.45	65	F	11
2	.	9.03	3.62	65	F	11
2	.	12.12	2.69	65	F	11
2	.	24.08	0.86	65	F	11

5.6 Output files

Monolix generates a lot of different output files depending on the tasks done by the user.

5.6.1 Settings

By default, the results folder storing all run outputs is created next to the project .mlxtran file and has the same name as the project. It can however be changed via the Monolix menu: Settings > Project settings > Result folder:

When clicking on the path, a pop-up file browser window allows to manually choose another folder. All results will be put in that folder (without creation of folder with the same name as the project).

Note that the given path will be overwritten by the default location when doing a “save as” (but not when doing a “save”).

5.6.2 Listing

Here is a complete listing of the files, along with the condition for their creation and their content.

5.6.2.1 Population parameter estimation

5.6.2.1.1 summary.txt

Description: summary file.

Outputs:

- **Header:** project file name, date and time of run, Monolix version
- **Estimation of the population parameters:** Estimated population parameters & computation time

5.6.2.1.2 populationParameters.txt

Description: estimated population parameters (with SAEM).

Outputs:

- **First column (no name):** contains the parameter names (e.g 'V_pop' and 'omega_V').
- **value:** contains the estimated parameter values.

5.6.2.2 Individual parameters estimation

All the files are in the IndividualParameters folder of the result folder

5.6.2.2.1 estimatedIndividualParameters.txt

Description: Individual parameters (from SAEM, mode, and mean of the conditional distribution)

Outputs:

- **ID:** subject name and occasion (if applicable). If there is one type of occasion, there will be an additional(s) column(s) defining the occasions.
- **parameterName_SAEM:** individual parameter estimated by SAEM, it corresponds to the average of the individual parameters sampled by MCMC during all iterations of the smoothing phase. When several chains are used (see project settings), the average is also done over all chains. This value is an approximation of the conditional mean.
- **parameterName_mode (if conditional mode was computed):** individual parameter estimated by the conditional mode task, i.e mode of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$.
- **parameterName_mean (if conditional distribution was computed) :** individual parameter estimated by the conditional distribution task, i.e mean of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$. The average of samples from all chains and all iterations is computed in the gaussian space (e.g., mean of the log values in case of a lognormal distribution), and back-transformed.
- **parameterName_sd (if conditional distribution was computed):** standard deviation of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ calculated during the conditional distribution task.
- **COVname:** continuous covariates values corresponding to all data set columns tagged as "Continuous covariate" and all the associated transformed covariates.
- **CATname:** modalities associated to the categorical covariates (including latent covariates and the bsmm covariates) and all the associated transformed covariates.

5.6.2.2.2 estimatedRandomEffects.txt

Description: individual random effect, calculated using the population parameters, the covariates and the conditional mode or conditional mean. For instance if we have a parameter defined as $k_i = k_{pop} + \beta_{k,WT} WT_i + \eta_i$, we calculate $\eta_i = k_i - k_{pop} - \beta_{k,WT} WT_i$ with k_i the estimated individual parameter (mode or mean of the conditional distribution), WT_i the individual's covariate, and k_{pop} and $\beta_{k,WT}$ the estimated population parameters.

Outputs:

- **ID:** subject name and occasion (if applicable). If there is one type of occasion, there will be an additional(s) column(s) defining the occasions.

- **eta_parameterName_SAEM**: individual random effect estimated by SAEM, it corresponds to the last iteration of SAEM.
- **eta_parameterName_mode (if conditional mode was computed)**: individual random effect estimated by the conditional mode task, i.e mode of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$.
- **eta_parameterName_mean (if conditional distribution was computed)** : individual random effect estimated by the conditional distribution task, i.e mean of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$. The average of random effect samples from all chains and all iterations is computed.
- **eta_parameterName_sd (if conditional distribution was computed)**: standard deviation of the conditional distribution $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ calculated during the conditional distribution task.
- **COVname**: continuous covariates values corresponding to all data set columns tagged as "Continuous covariate" and all the associated transformed covariates.
- **CATname**: modalities associated to the categorical covariates (including latent covariates and the bsmm covariates) and all the associated transformed covariates.

5.6.2.2.3 simulatedIndividualParameters.txt

Description: Simulated individual parameter (by the conditional distribution)

Outputs:

- **rep**: replicate of the simulation
- **ID**: subject name and occasion (if applicable). If there is one type of occasion, there will be an additional(s) column(s) defining the occasions.
- **parameterName**: simulated individual parameter corresponding to the draw rep.
- **COVname**: continuous covariates values corresponding to all data set columns tagged as "Continuous covariate" and all the associated transformed covariates.
- **CATname**: modalities associated to the categorical covariates (including latent covariates and the bsmm covariates) and all the associated transformed covariates.

5.6.2.2.4 simulatedRandomEffects.txt

Description: Simulated individual random effect (by the conditional distribution)

Outputs:

- **rep**: replicate of the simulation
- **ID**: subject name and occasion (if applicable). If there is one type of occasion, there will be an additional(s) column(s) defining the occasions.
- **eta_parameterName**: simulated individual random effect corresponding to the draw rep.
- **COVname**: continuous covariates values corresponding to all data set columns tagged as "Continuous covariate" and all the associated transformed covariates.
- **CATname**: modalities associated to the categorical covariates (including latent covariates and the bsmm covariates) and all the associated transformed covariates.

5.6.2.3 Fisher Information Matrix calculation

5.6.2.3.1 summary.txt

Description: summary file.

Outputs:

- **Header:** project file name, date and time of run, Monolix version (outputted population parameter estimation task)
- **Estimation of the population parameters:** Estimated population parameters & computation time (outputted population parameter estimation task). Standard errors and relative standard errors are added.
- **Correlation matrix of the estimates:** correlation matrix by block, eigenvalues and computation time

5.6.2.3.2 populationParameters.txt

Description: estimated population parameters, associated standard errors and p-value.

Outputs:

- **First column (no name):** contains the parameter names (outputted population parameter estimation task)
- **Column 'parameter':** contains the estimated parameter values (outputted population parameter estimation task)
- **se_lin / se_sa:** contains the standard errors (s.e.) for the (untransformed) parameter, obtained by linearization of the system (lin) or stochastic approximation (sa).
- **rse_lin / rse_sa:** contains the parameter relative standard errors (r.s.e.) in % ($\text{param_r.s.e.} = 100 * \text{param_s.e.} / \text{param}$), obtained by linearization of the system (lin) or stochastic approximation (sa).
- **pvalues_lin / pvalues_sa:** for *beta* parameters associated to covariates, the line contains the p-value obtained from a Wald test of whether $\beta=0$. If the parameter is not a *beta* parameter, 'NaN' is displayed.

Notice that if the Fisher Information Matrix is difficult to invert, some parameter's standard error can maybe not be computed leading to NaN in the corresponding columns.

All the more detailed files are in the FisherInformation folder of the result folder.

5.6.2.3.3 covarianceEstimatesSA.txt and/or covarianceEstimatesLin.txt

Description: variance-covariance matrix of the estimates for the (untransformed) parameters or transformed normally distributed parameters depending on the MonolixSuite version (see below)

Outputs: matrix with the project parameters as lines and columns. First column contains the parameter names.

The Fisher information matrix (FIM) is calculated for the transformed normally distributed parameters (i.e. $\log(V_{\text{pop}})$ if V has a lognormal distribution). By inverting the FIM, we obtain the variance-covariance matrix Γ for the transformed normally distributed parameters ζ . This matrix is then multiplied by the jacobian J (which elements are defined by $J_{ij} = \frac{\partial \theta_i}{\partial \zeta_j}$) to obtain the variance-covariance matrix $\tilde{\Gamma}$ for the untransformed parameters θ :

$$\tilde{\Gamma} = J^T \Gamma J$$

The diagonal elements of the variance-covariance matrix $\tilde{\Gamma}$ for the untransformed parameters are finally used to calculate the standard errors.

Version	2018	2019	2020	2021
Monolix output SA	Non-transformed parameters	Non-transformed parameters	transformed normally distributed parameters	transformed normally distributed parameters
Monolix output LIN	Non-transformed parameters	Non-transformed parameters	Non-transformed parameters	transformed normally distributed parameters

5.6.2.3.4 **correlationEstimatesSA.txt and/or correlationEstimatesLin.txt**

Description: correlation matrix for the (untransformed) parameters

Outputs: matrix with the project parameters as lines and columns. First column contains the parameter names.

The correlation matrix is calculated as:

$$\text{corr}(\theta_i, \theta_j) = \frac{\text{covar}(\theta_i, \theta_j)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_i)} \sqrt{\text{var}(\theta_j)}}$$

This implies that the diagonal is unitary. The variance-covariance matrix for the untransformed parameters θ is obtained from the inverse of the Fisher Information Matrix and the jacobian. See above for the formula.

5.6.2.4 Log-Likelihood calculation

5.6.2.4.1 **summary.txt**

Description: summary file.

Outputs:

- **Header:** project file name, date and time of run, Monolix version (outputted population parameter estimation task)

- **Estimation of the population parameters:** Estimated population parameters & computation time (outputted population parameter estimation task). Standard errors and relative standard errors are added.
- **Correlation matrix of the estimates:** correlation matrix by block, eigenvalues and computation time
- **Log-likelihood Estimation:** $-2 \times \log$ -likelihood, AIC and BIC values, together with the computation time

All the more detailed files are in the LogLikelihood folder of the result folder

5.6.2.4.2 logLikelihood.txt

Description: Summary of the log-likelihood calculation with the two methods.

Outputs:

- **criteria:** OFV (Objective Function Value), AIC (Akaike Information Criteria), and BIC (Bayesian Information Criteria)
- **method:** ImportanceSampling and/or linearization

5.6.2.4.3 individualLL.txt

Description: $-2LL$ for each individual. Notice that we only have one by individual even if there are occasions.

Outputs:

- **ID:** subject name
- **method:** ImportanceSampling and/or linearization

5.6.2.5 Tests

5.6.2.6 Tables

5.6.2.6.1 *predictions.txt*

Description: predictions at the observation times

Outputs:

- **ID:** subject name. If there are occasions, additional columns will be added to describe the occasions.
- **time:** Time from the data set.
- **MeasurementName:** Measurement from the data set.
- **RegressorName:** Regressor value.
- **popPred_medianCOV:** prediction using the population parameters and the median covariates.

- **popPred**: prediction using the population parameters and the covariates, e.g.,

$$V_i = V_{pop} \left(\frac{WT_i}{70} \right)^\beta$$
 (without random effects).
- **indivPred_SAEM**: prediction using the mean of the conditional distribution, calculated using the last iterations of the SAEM algorithm.
- **indPred_mean (if conditional distribution was computed)**: prediction using the mean of the conditional distribution, calculated in the Conditional distribution task.
- **indPred_mode (if conditional mode was computed)**: prediction using the mode of the conditional distribution, calculated in the EBEs task.
- **indWRes_SAEM**: weighted residuals $IWRES_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij} - f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}{g(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}$ with ψ_i the mean of the conditional distribution, calculated using the last iterations of the SAEM algorithm.
- **indWRes_mean (if conditional distribution was computed)**: weighted residuals

$$IWRES_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij} - f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}{g(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}$$
 with ψ_i the mean of the conditional distribution, calculated in the Conditional distribution task.
- **indWRes_mode (if conditional mode was computed)**: weighted residuals

$$IWRES_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij} - f(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}{g(t_{ij}, \psi_i)}$$
 with ψ_i the mode of the conditional distribution, calculated in the EBEs task.

Notice that in case of several outputs, Monolix generates predictions1.txt, predictions2.txt, ...

Below is a correspondence of the terms used for predictions in Nonmem versus Monolix:

Nonmem	Monolix	Definition	Output files and plots
IPRED	indivPred_mode	$f(\psi_i^{EBEs}, t_{ij})$ predictions using individual parameters (EBEs)	- File: predictions.txt - Plot: Observations vs individual prediction
PRED	popPred	$f(\psi_{pop}, t_{ij})$ prediction for typical individual (using population parameter and covariate effects but random effects set to 0)	- File: predictions.txt - Plot: Observations vs population prediction
CPRED	<i>Not applicable</i>	conditional population predictions using FOCE approximation	<i>Not applicable</i>
EPRED	Not outputted by Monolix but used in residuals calculations	$\frac{1}{k} \sum y_{sim}^k = \frac{1}{k} \sum (f(\psi_i^k, t_{ij}) + g \times \varepsilon_{ij})$ average of the simulated observations (including residual error) using the individual design and several sets of individual parameters sampled from the population distribution	

5.6.2.7 Charts data

All plots generated by Monolix can be exported as a figure or as text files in order to be able to plot it in another way or with other software for more flexibility. The description of all generated text files is described here.

5.7 Comments

Starting from the 2019 version, it is possible to add comments to the project with a dedicated part in the interface in the frame "Comments" as in the following figure.

The screenshot shows the 'Statistical model & Tasks' tab in the Monolix software. The interface is divided into several sections:

- Comments:** A large text area containing markdown-formatted text:


```
### Structural model
* Two compartment model
* Linear elimination

### Statistical model
No correlation/No covariate used

---

### Diagnostic plots
**Misspecification** → third compartment needed
```

 Below the text area is a toggle switch labeled 'Preview markdown' which is currently turned on.
- Structural model:** A section displaying a bulleted list:
 - Two compartment model
 - Linear elimination
- Statistical model:** A section displaying the text: 'No correlation/No covariate used'.
- Diagnostic plots:** A section displaying the text: '**Misspecification** → third compartment needed'.

It allows to put information on the project and save it within the project. Notice that you can put information before running the project and/or after running the project and the plots to comment the VPC for example. The text can be formatted with HTML markup or markdown syntax. A preview window is also proposed in order to see the formatted text.

The comments are displayed in Sycomore.

5.8 Export a Monolix project

5.8.1 Export a Monolix project to PKanalix, Simulx and Sycomore

MonolixSuite applications are interconnected and projects can be exported/imported between different applications. This interconnection is guaranteed by using the same model syntax (mlxtran language) and the same dataset format. You can export a Monolix project to PKanalix or Simulx in one click directly from the interface.

To export a project click EXPORT PROJECT TO in the top menu "Export":

The screenshot shows the MonolixSuite interface for a project named 'warfarinPK_project.mlxtran (demo) - Monolix estimation - 2023R1'. The 'Export' menu is open, and the 'Export project to...' option is highlighted with a red box. The interface also shows the 'Tasks' section with buttons for 'POPULATION PAR...', 'CONDITIONAL DI...', 'STANDARD ER...', 'LIKELIHOOD', 'PLOTS', and 'RUN'. Below the tasks, there is an 'Observation model' table and an 'Individual model' section.

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

The export pop-up window will appear where you can choose:

- to which application you want to export your current project: PKanalix, Simulx or Sycomore (starting from the 2024 version),
- which dataset you want to use in the export (PKanalix and Simulx only): original dataset, VPC dataset (if VPC plot has been generated), individual fits dataset (if individual fits plot has been generated).

By default, Monolix will copy all files, e.g. dataset and model, next to the new PKanalix/Simulx project. To keep current location of these files, switch the toggle “Generated files next to project” off.

It is now feasible to export additional covariates to Simulx that were not initially included in the individual model (starting from version 2024R1). In the export configurations window a dedicated “Covariates” section appears. This section lists the covariates that are already incorporated in the model, and underneath, additional covariates can be selected from an available drop-down menu titled “Other exported covariates”.

To export a Monolix project click the “EXPORT” button at the bottom. PKanalix/Simulx/Sycomore will open automatically with a predefined project called “untitled”. You can save this project, edit and run. For more information about exported elements, see:

- [Import from Monolix to Simulx documentation page](#)
- [Import from Monolix to PKanalix documentation page](#)

When exporting to Sycomore, a new Sycomore project will be created that contains only the current Monolix project. To add additional Monolix projects to the Sycomore project, the following instructions can be followed.

5.8.2 Share a Monolix project

The 2024 version of MonolixSuite introduces a highly convenient method for sharing projects. Simply click on “Share Project” in the export menu, and a zip folder is generated containing all the required files to re-open the project (dataset, model if not from library, mxtran file, result folder). By default, the suggested location for the zipped shared project matches that of the original, but this can be easily modified to any other location on the computer.

The screenshot shows the MonolixSuite interface for a project named 'warfarinPK_project.mlxtran - Monolix estimation - 2024R1'. The 'Export' menu is open, and the 'Share Project' option is highlighted with a red box. The main workspace displays six plots (labeled 1 through 6) showing the relationship between 'y1' and 'time'. The plots show observed data points (blue dots) and a fitted model curve (purple line). The y-axis ranges from 0 to 15, and the x-axis ranges from 0 to 100. The right-hand side of the interface shows a settings panel with various options like 'Legend', 'Grid', 'Information', 'Dosing times', and 'Zoom constraint'.

The functionality of this feature remains consistent across all software within the MonolixSuite.

6 Project comparison in Sycomore

Sycomore is an application for the visual and interactive exploration of your models. It enables to keep an overview of the Monolix runs and compare them side by side.

6.1 Interface

The interface of Sycomore is separated in two main tabs:

- **Hierarchy tab.** The hierarchy tab provides an overview of the Monolix runs. It is composed of three panels:
 - Projects selection: the panel on the left allows to select Monolix projects in a list of folders chosen by the user.
 - Table of projects: the panel on top shows a quick overview of selected Monolix projects as a table, with information on each project's definition and results.
 - Tree representation: the panel on the bottom provides a schematic representation of the modeling workflow as a tree of projects.

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)-	-2*LL (IS)-	BICc (Lin)-	BICc (IS)-	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_2cmt			☆☆☆	8044.43		8106.71		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2.txt	y1: comb1	C1, V1, Q1, V2		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt			☆☆☆	7185.46		7271.28		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: comb1	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3		
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_AGEonCI			☆☆☆	7143.57		7233.56		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: comb1	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3	logAGE	
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_PROP			☆☆☆	7249.98		7328.21		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3		
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_PROP_AGEonCI			☆☆☆	7175.15		7257.55		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3	logAGE	
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_PROP_cossac_run16			☆☆☆	7004.09		7115.71		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3	AGE, SEX, logAGE	
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_PROP_cossac_run16_corr			☆☆☆	6905.06		7029.2		lib:infusion_3cpt_CI V1QV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	C1, V1, Q1, V2, Q3, V3	AGE, SEX, logAGE	

- **Comparison tab.** To compare the results of several runs side-by-side.

Project Name	pk_3cmt	pk_3cmt	pk_3cmt_prop
Select for reference	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rating	☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆☆
Comments			
SAEM	✓	✓	✓
Likelihood results			
-2*LL (Linearization)	▶	▶	▶
BICc (Linearization)			
-2*LL (Importance sampling)	8044.43	7185.46	7249.98
BICc (Importance sampling)	8106.71	7271.28	7328.21
Fisher tasks			
Linearization	▶	▶	▶
Stochastic approximation	✓	✓	✓
Fixed effects			
	S.A.		S.A.
Cl_pop	2.49	2.85%	2.46
V1_pop	5.16	5.91%	4.51
Q_pop	1.54	6.39%	
V2_pop	9.33	5.02%	8.62
Q2_pop			5.14%
Q3_pop			1.78
V3_pop			6.83%
			1.7
			0.09
			9.45%
			4.31
			12.86%
			5.02
			13.12%

Follow the links to read detailed descriptions of each part of the interface.

6.2 File

Sycamore projects are saved as text files with the extension **.syc**. A sycamore project contains relative paths to the Monolix runs described in the overview.

6.3 Hierarchy

Following pages describe the different elements of the Hierarchy tab in Sycamore:

6.3.1 Table of projects

The panel on top shows a table overview of the Monolix runs selected in the Selection panel, that has the following functions, detailed on this page:

- **Displaying key information on each Monolix run**
 - Elements from the projects: project name, structural model, error model, covariates, correlation groups, comments

- Objective function and BICc from the results
- **Performing actions on each run**
 - Running one or several projects in Monolix
 - Opening a project in Monolix or opening its result folder
 - Cloning a project
 - Updating the elements and results of a run
- **Modifying elements of the Sycomore overview**
 - Including projects as nodes in the tree view
 - Changes from parent nodes
 - Selecting projects for side-by-side comparison
 - Removing a run from the table
 - Rating

An example is shown below:

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lk)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lk)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates	Comments	Changes from parent
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_2cmt		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	8044.43	8106.71			lib:infusion_2cpt_CIV IQV2.txt	y1: comb1	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	7185.46	7271.28			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: comb1	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>			
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_AGEonCI		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	7143.57	7233.56			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: comb1	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>	logtAGE		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	7249.99	7328.21			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>			
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_AGEonCI		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	7175.15	7257.55			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>	logtAGE		
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	7004.09	7115.71			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>	AGE, SEX, logtAGE		
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16_corr		X [Icons]	☆☆☆	6905.06	7029.2			lib:infusion_3cpt_CIV IQV2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	<u>C</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u> <u>Q</u> <u>V</u>	AGE, SEX, logtAGE		

6.3.1.1 Displaying key information on each Monolix run

6.3.1.1.1 Project settings

The name of the projects displayed in the table are the file names without the .mlxtran extension. If several projects from different folders have the same name, the name of the folders are also added to distinguish them. It is possible to sort the table rows by project name.

The main elements of the structural and statistical models from each Monolix projects are displayed in the columns:

- Structural model: the path to the structural model
- Observation model: the error model chosen for each observation id (const=constant, prop=proportional, comb1=combined1, comb2=combined2)
- Individual model: the names of the parameters are displayed. They are underlined if they are involved in covariate effects, in italic if they have no variability, and colored if they are part of correlation groups.

- Used covariates: covariates that are used in the statistical model.

An example is shown below, where the structural model is the file `infusion_3cpt_SigmoidEffectCompartmentImax_ClV1Q2V2Q3V3ke0E0ImaxIC50gamma.txt` from the PKPD models library, the error model is proportional (PK) and combined 1 (PD), the individual parameters Cl, V1, Q2, V2, Q3, V3, ke0, gamma, E0, Imax and IC50 all have random effects and all have some covariate effect, among the covariates AGE, SEX, logtAGE. There are also two correlation groups: {Cl, Q2, V2} and {ke0, IC50}.

Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates
lib: infusion_3cpt_SigmoidEffectCompartmentImax_ClV1Q2V2Q3V3ke0E0ImaxIC50gamma.txt mma.txt	y1: prop y2: comb1		AGE, SEX, logtAGE

The column Comments displays all comments saved in the Monolix projects. Note that markup or markdown formatting is not applied.

6.3.1.1.2 Objective function and BIC

The log-likelihood and corrected BIC are displayed in the columns:

- -2*LL (Lin): -2*log-likelihood computed by linearization,
- -2*LL (IS): -2*log-likelihood computed by importance sampling,
- BICc (Lin): corrected BIC based on the log-likelihood computed by linearization,
- BICc (IS): corrected BIC based on the log-likelihood computed by importance sampling.

Table rows can be sorted in increasing or decreasing order according to each of these columns with the sorting icon, as seen here:

-2*LL (Lin) ↕	-2*LL (IS) ↕	BICc (Lin) ↕	BICc (IS) ↕
---------------	--------------	--------------	-------------

6.3.1.2 Performing actions on each run

6.3.1.2.1 Running one or several projects in Monolix

The table can be used to select projects in a run list that can be run together in a row. This is done by clicking on each project name, as can be seen below. A button “Run” appears, it runs the scenario defined in each project. The results are then automatically updated in the table.

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lit)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lit)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates	Comments	Changes from parent
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_2cmt													
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt													
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_AGEonCI			logtAGE										
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop													
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_AGEonCI			logtAGE										
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16			AGE, SEX, logtAGE										
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16_corr			AGE, SEX, logtAGE										

6.3.1.2.2 Action buttons

The column named Actions contains a set of buttons, seen above, to perform useful actions. Their functions are:

- Remove the project from the table. This does not remove the project from the Selection panel.
- Clone a project: this action asks for a new name, a copy of the project is saved under this name.
- Update the elements and results displayed for the project
- Open the project in Monolix
- Open the result folder of the project

6.3.1.3 Modifying elements of the Sycomore overview

Several elements of the table can be modified and saved in the Sycomore project.

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lin)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates	Comments	Changes from parent
<input type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_AGEonCI		X [Icons]	★☆☆	7175.15	7257.55			lib: infusion_3cpt_CV1 Q2V2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	[Icons]	logTAGE		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16		X [Icons]	★★★☆☆	7004.09	7115.71			lib: infusion_3cpt_CV1 Q2V2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	[Icons]	AGE, SEX, logTAGE	Performed COSSAC run	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	pk_3cmt_prop_cossac_run16_corr		X [Icons]	★★★★☆	6905.06	7029.2			lib: infusion_3cpt_CV1 Q2V2Q3V3.txt	y1: prop	[Icons]	AGE, SEX, logTAGE		

- Selecting projects for side-by-side comparison (see green mark above): this is done by checking boxes in the column named "Compare". The selected projects are then displayed in the Comparison tab.
- Including projects as nodes in the tree view (see blue mark above): with buttons in the column named "Hierarchy".
- Rating (see orange mark above): by clicking on the stars in the column Rating. The ratings then appear as a color code in the tree view (*: red, **: orange, ***: red).
- Changes from parent nodes (see purple mark above): text fields for projects that have a parent in the tree diagram can be filled directly in the column named "Changes from parent", or in the tree diagram.

6.3.2 Selection panel

The panel on the left of the Hierarchy tab allows to select Monolix projects in a list of folders chosen by the user. Selected projects appear in the Table part of the interface, and can then be added in the Tree representation and/or in the Comparison tab.

Hovering on a project in the list displays its absolute path at the bottom. It also highlights the project in orange in the Table and Tree representation in the interface. Moreover, if the project is included in the tree representation, its parent is highlighted in green and its child(ren) is(are) highlighted in blue.

6.3.2.1 Adding a project in the list

A new project can be added in the selection list by clicking on “Add project” in the Project menu, and selecting a Monolix project (.mlxtran file) in the browser.

It is also possible to click “Add directory” and select a folder in the browser. In that case all Monolix projects contained in the folder are displayed in the selection list, and are by default unselected.

If several projects appear in the list, the hierarchy of folders up to the closest common root is displayed as well.

6.3.2.2 Selecting projects

Projects can be selected one-by-one, or all the projects in a folder can be selected together by selecting their folder.

The list of projects in a folder can be updated with the button “Rescan directory” as below:

Next to the button “Rescan directory”, the cross icon permits to remove a directory from the list.

6.3.3 Tree view

The panel on the bottom of the Hierarchy tab provides a schematic representation of the modeling workflow as a tree of projects. This graph diagram is built by the user and contains:

- the name of the Monolix projects
- changes from the parent project
- the rating of the projects is displayed with a color code

As seen on the figure below, hovering on a node of the diagram highlights its parent in green and its child(ren) in blue, on the diagram but also in the Selection panel and the Table of runs. The path to the root node is also displayed in dashed blue line.

6.3.3.1 Building the tree representation

To build the tree representation of your workflow, use the buttons “Add node to diagram” (shown below) in the table of projects to add relevant projects in the tree view.

The projects are first added in the tree view as free nodes. They can be linked to a parent node via drag-and-drop. Available nodes are then highlighted in red, and the selected parent is highlighted in green, as on the following figure.

Cloning a project allows to create a copy of the Monolix project with a different name, that can then be opened in Monolix and modified. A clone is automatically added in the tree view as the child of the cloned project.

6.3.3.2 Defining parent-child relationships

Changes from the parent project can be saved and displayed on the graph edges and in the table of projects.

Two ways to define a parent-child relationship	Display on hover

6.3.3.3 Display of rating

The rating of runs set manually in the table of project is displayed with a color code on the tree view: red for one star, orange for two stars, green for three stars.

Compare All None	Project name All None	Hierarchy Add all Clean	Actions	Rating
<input type="checkbox"/>	pkpd_effectCmt	—		★☆☆
<input type="checkbox"/>	pkpd_effectCmt_AGEonke0IC50	—		★★★☆☆
<input type="checkbox"/>	pkpd_effectCmt_AGEonke0IC50_corrke0IC50	—		★★★★★

6.3.3.4 Export

Starting from the version 2024, it is now possible to export the tree as an SVG file by clicking on the export button next to the tree. The exported tree will be the same as the tree in the interface, however it will not contain the information icons.

6.4 Comparison

The comparison tab allows to compare side-by-side the main results of a set of Monolix projects selected in Sycomore.

Monolix projects are selected for comparison in the Table overview of the Hierarchy tab.

The results include:

- Project information:
 - Project name
 - Rating: the rating given to the projects in Sycomore. They can be changed on this table or in the Hierarchy tab.
 - Comments: the comments saved in each Monolix project
 - SAEM: this row indicates for each project whether the population parameters have been estimated.
- Likelihood results: the values of $-2*LL$ and BICc based on the log-likelihood computed by linearization or by importance sampling
- Fisher tasks: these rows indicate for each project whether the Fisher information matrix by linearization or by stochastic approximation has been computed.
- Fixed effects: estimates and standard errors for the fixed effects (omega parameters)
- Standard deviation: estimates and standard errors for the standard deviations of the random effects (omega parameters)
- Residual error parameters: estimates and standard errors for the parameters of the residual error model
- Figures: diagnostic plots exported as png images

Here is an example of the table Comparison with 4 projects:

Project Name	pk_2cmt	pk_3cmt	pk_3cmt_AGEonCl	pk_3cmt_prop
Select for reference	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rating	★★★	★★★	★☆☆	★★★
Comments				
SAEM	✓	✓	✓	✓
Likelihood results				
$-2*LL$ (Linearization)				
BICc (Linearization)				
$-2*LL$ (Importance sampling)	8044.43	7185.46	7143.57	7249.98
BICc (Importance sampling)	8106.71	7271.28	7233.56	7826.21

The table can be copied with the button , to be pasted in any other software.

6.4.1 Actions

Actions icons are available in the headers of the table, to perform useful actions.

Their functions are:

- Remove the project from the comparison table. This does not remove the project from the Selection panel nor the Table overview in the Hierarchy tab.
- Update the elements and results displayed for the project
- Open the project in Monolix
- Open the result folder of the project

6.4.2 Sorting projects

Columns of the table can be sorted in increasing or decreasing order according to the values of some row of the table, by clicking on the arrows next to the row names. Moreover, clicking on a row name colors the row in yellow to facilitate the comparison.

Hierarchy	Comparison	pk_2cmt	pk_3cmt	pk_3cmt_AGEonCl	pk_3cmt_prop
Project Name					
Select for reference		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rating		☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆☆
Comments					
SAEM		✓	✓	✓	✓
Likelihood results					
-2*LL (Linearization)					
BICc (Linearization)					
-2*LL (Importance sampling)		8044.43	7185.46	7143.57	7249.98
BICc (Importance sampling)		8106.71	7271.28	7233.56	7338.31

6.4.3 Running a task to get missing results

Some Monolix estimation tasks that have not run yet can be launched from the Comparison tab with the “Run” buttons (green arrow) to provide missing results:

- population parameters estimation with SAEM
- computing the log-likelihood by linearization or by importance sampling
- computing the standard errors with the Fisher information matrix by linearization or by stochastic approximation.

Project Name	pk_2cmt	pk_3cmt	pk_3cmt_AGEonCI	pk_3cmt_prop
Select for reference	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rating	☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆☆
Comments				
SAEM	✓	✓	✓	✓
Likelihood results				
-2*LL (Linearization)	8018.5	▶	▶	▶
BICc (Linearization)	8080.78			
-2*LL (Importance sampling)	8044.43	7185.46	7143.57	7249.98
BICc (Importance sampling)	8106.71	7271.28	7233.56	7328.21
Fisher tasks				
Linearization	▶	▶	▶	▶ COPY TABLE

6.4.4 Comparing plots

For each project, diagnostic plots that have been exported as png images (this requires to generate the plots in the interface of Monolix and export them) are listed in the Figures section. Hovering on a file name colors the same diagnostic plots available for other projects, and displays a preview of the image.

Project Name	pk_2cmt		pk_3cmt		pk_3cmt_AGEonCl		pk_3cmt_prop	
omega_V3			0.81	11.12%	0.82	12.81%	0.82	10.82%
Residual error parameters	S.A.		S.A.		S.A.		S.A.	
a1	0.093	5.45%	0.00047	275.03%	0.0018	83.23%		
b1	0.12	2.06%	0.11	1.88%	0.11	1.88%	0.11	1.76%
Figures								
PNG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 vpc_y1_0_0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 saemresults__0_1 vpc_y1_0_0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 saemresults__0_1 vpc_y1_0_0 					

Clicking on a file name opens a window where the corresponding plot from each project of the table is displayed with the name of the project.

Project Name	pk_2cmt		pk_3cmt		pk_3cmt_AGEonCI		pk_3cmt_prop	
omega_V3			0.81	11.12%	0.82	12.81%	0.82	10.82%
Residual error parameters	S.A.		S.A.		S.A.		S.A.	
a1	0.093	5.45%	0.00047	275.03%	0.0018	83.23%		
b1	0.12	2.06%	0.11	1.88%	0.11	1.88%	0.11	1.76%
Figures								
PNG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualsscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 vpc_y1_0_0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualsscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 saemresults__0_1 vpc_y1_0_0 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bivariatedataviewer__0_0 covariancemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariatemodeldiagnosis__0_0 covariateviewer__0_0 indfits_y1_0_0 indfits_y1_0_1 indfits_y1_0_2 indfits_y1_0_3 indfits_y1_0_4 indfits_y1_0_5 obspred_y1_0_0 outputplot_2_0_0 outputplot_y1_0_0 parameterdistribution__0_0 randomeffects__0_0 residualsdistribution_y1_0_0 residualsscatter_y1_0_0 saemresults__0_0 saemresults__0_1 vpc_y1_0_0 					

6.5 Example

In the proposed example, we use Sycomore to guide the modelling of the PKPD of remifentanil in Monolix, by providing an overview of the modelling workflow, and allowing to easily add a new step of the workflow by cloning a project to modify it.

We choose to perform a quick modelling workflow with the help of automatic model building tools, to find a good model in only a few steps.

All modelling decisions are only summarized.

6.5.1 Insights from data exploration

A detailed presentation and exploration of the remifentanil PKPD dataset that we wish to model is available [here](#).

In summary, it contains:

- administration information for IV infusion,
- PK measurements of remifentanil: these observations are named y1 in Datxplora and Monolix,
- EEG measurements as PD: these observations are named y2 in Datxplora and Monolix,

- continuous covariates (age and lean body mass LBM), as well as categorical covariates (sex and tinfcats which is a dose group).

Data exploration with the data viewer in Monolix gives relevant insights to guide the modelling, mainly:

- The elimination shows different phases, as can be seen on the left figure below, where the PK measurements over times have been split by dose group. This means that several compartments will be needed in the PK model to capture them.
- The PD is inhibited by the PK with a delay, visible for example on the right figure below, which shows the PD over PK for id 15.

6.5.2 First PK model

Since the data exploration in Monolix shows that a model with several compartments seems necessary to describe this dataset, we start by setting up a first PK model with two compartments in Monolix, with the following steps:

- Load the structural model `infusion_2cpt_CIV1QV2.txt` from the PK library. This is a 2 compartments model with infusion administration and linear elimination.
- Choose automatically good initial estimates for the population parameters with the “Auto-init” button in the tab “Initial estimates”.
- Keep the default statistical model.

We save this first project as `PK_1.mlxtran` in a folder “PK”. Then, all estimation and diagnosis tasks are run to evaluate the model. In particular, the plots “Individual fits” and “Observations vs predictions” displayed below show a mis-specification of the structural model: a third compartment is needed in order to avoid under-predictions of the end of the elimination phase.

Since these plots are important to diagnose the model, we export these plots in the result folder with the button “Export as png”.

Finally, we note in the tab Comments the conclusion for this project: “Misspecification in diagnostic plots: 3rd cpt needed”.

6.5.3 Second PK model

Next, we change the structural model to add a third compartment to the PK model. This is done by loading the structural model `infusion_2cpt_CIV1Q2V2Q3V2.txt`. Good initial estimates are again chosen with the button “Auto-init”.

We then save the modified project as `PK_2.mlxtran` in the PK folder, before running all estimation and diagnosis tasks.

The plots “Individual fits” and “Observations vs predictions” displayed below no longer show any misspecification of the structural model.

These plots are also exported in the Results folder. Moreover, we note in Comments: “No misspecification in structural model”.

We can also check in the plots for individual parameters that the distributions of the individual parameters are not misspecified.

6.5.4 Comparing two PK projects in Sycomore

To compare further these two projects, we create a new overview with Sycomore: after opening Sycomore and clicking on “New project”, we select the PK folder containing the two Monolix projects.

The two projects with their common folder then appear in the Selection panel on the left of the Hierarchy tab in Sycomore. After selecting them both, they also appear with their characteristics in the overview table on the top:

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lin)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Comments	Changes from parent
<input type="checkbox"/>	PK_1	+	✕ 🔄 📄 🗑️	★ ★ ★		7945.98		8008.26	<i>lib: infusio n_2cptLCl V1QV2.txt</i>	y1: comb1	Cl V1 Q V2	Mis-specification in diagnostic plots: 3rd cpt needed	
<input type="checkbox"/>	PK_2	+	✕ 🔄 📄 🗑️	★ ★ ★		7150.89		7236.72	<i>lib: infusio n_3cptLCl V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt</i>	y1: comb1	Cl V1 Q2 V2 Q3 V3	No mis-specification in structural model	

Since both projects contain the BICc computed by importance sampling, we can already see in the table that the second project PK_2 has a lower value for BICc (IS), which confirms that the fit is better. A rating can be added for each project. Here we note a rating ★ for PK_1 and a rating ★★ for PK_2.

To keep track of the workflow, add these two projects in the tree view by clicking on the + icons in the column "Hierarchy". The rating appears as a color code, with PK_1 in red and PK_2 in orange. We then drag the node PK_2 close to PK_1 to create a parent-child relationship.

It is now possible to comment the parent-child relationship to record the changes from the parent. We write "added 3rd cpt" in the corresponding cell in the table.

We have now recorded all elements of the current workflow, thus we save the Sycomore overview as a file PKPD_remifentani.sys. The project now looks like this:

Project Help

Home Hierarchy Comparison

PK

- PK_1.mlxtran
- PK_2.mlxtran

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lin)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Comments	Changes from parent
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_1	[-]	[x] [copy] [refresh] [paste]	★ ★ ★		7945.98		8008.26	lib: infusio n-2cpt_CI V1QV2.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q V1 V2	Mis-specification in diagnostic plots: 3rd cpt needed	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_2	[-]	[x] [copy] [refresh] [paste]	★ ★ ★		7150.89		7236.72	lib: infusio n-3cpt_CI V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q2 V1 Q3 V2 V3	No mis-specification in structural model	added 3rd cpt

Comparing PK_1 and PK_2 in more details is also possible by selecting them both in the column Compare. The tab Comparison is then generated and allows a side-by-side comparison of the results of the projects.

Project		Help	
Home Hierarchy Comparison			
Project Name	PK_1	PK_2	
Rating	★ ★ ★	★ ★ ★	
Comments	Mis-specification in diagnostic plots: 3rd cpt needed	No mis-specification in structural model	
SAEM	✓	✓	
Likelihood results			
-2*LL (Linearization)	▶	▶	
BICc (Linearization)			
-2*LL (Importance sampling)	7945.98	7150.89	
BICc (Importance sampling)	8008.26	7236.72	
Fisher tasks			
Linearization	▶	▶	
Stochastic approximation	✓	✓	
Fixed effects			
		S.A.	S.A.
Cl_pop	2.49	2.83%	2.46 2.87%
V1_pop	5.24	5.43%	4.46 5.08%
Q_pop	1.55	6.39%	
V2_pop	9.35	5%	7.83 5.86%
Q2_pop			1.65 8.65%
Q3_pop			0.137 15.93%
V3_pop			4.53 11.11%

COPY TABLE

The estimates for Cl, V1 and V2 are quite close between the two projects.

The columns can be sorted according to the values of each row, and missing tasks can also be launched from there with the “run” buttons, for example if the log-likelihood has not been yet computed.

The exported plots in the section Figures can also be compared, for example as below by clicking on obspred_y1_0_0.png, which is the file name for the plot “Observation vs predictions”:

Note that we only mention a few diagnostic plots in this short case study to keep a simple workflow, however it is important to check all diagnostic plots to get a complete model diagnostic.

6.5.5 Adjusting the statistical model with Proposal

The structural model in PK_2 has been validated by the diagnostic plots and parameter estimation. We can now try to improve the statistical model with a different error model, covariate effects or correlations between random effects.

In a complete and detailed modelling workflow, it would be important to look at the diagnostic plots for correlations between covariates and individual parameters as well as between pairs of random effects, to detect possible effects of outliers or to identify relevant transformations for covariates before adding covariate effects. This step is neglected in this simple workflow.

For a quick improvement of the statistical model, we can look at the proposal section in the tab Results of PK_2, seen below. The aim of the Proposal is to estimate the best statistical model for the dataset, taking into account the residual error model, covariate effects and correlations between random effects.

Proposed model [Apply](#)

Error model	CORRELATIONS		COVARIATES			
	#1	AGE	LBM	SEX	TINFCAT	
Y1	COMBINED2					
CI		✓	✓	✓		
V1			✓	✓		
Q2		✓	✓			
V2		✓	✓			
Q3		✓	✓			
V3			✓			

Current model

Error model	COVARIATES			
	AGE	LBM	SEX	TINFCAT
Y1	COMBINED1			
CI				
V1				
Q2				
V2				
Q3				
V3				

A model different than the current model is available in the tab Proposal. This proposed model includes a combined2 residual error model, covariate effects of Age on all parameters and LBM on CI and V1, and a correlation group with the random effects of CI, Q2, V2 and Q3. It is estimated that this model will be more performant than the current model, thus it is an interesting information that we can add in the Comments for PK_2.mlxtran with: "Statistical model can be improved". We save PK_2.mlxtran to update its comments, and we can also update the Comments visible in Sycamore by clicking on the "refresh" button for PK_2 in the column Actions:

PK_2	7150.89	7236.72	lib: infusion_3cpt_C IV1Q2V2Q3V3.txt	y1: comb1	CI V1 Q2 V2 Q3 V2	No mis-specification in structural model Statistical model can be improved	added 3rd cpt

However the performance of the proposed model should be verified by applying the model and estimating its parameters.

To do this, we choose the proposed model in Monolix by clicking on "Apply", and save the modified project as PK_3.mlxtran. We run the scenario of tasks for this project, and check that the convergence of the estimates is good and that all parameters are estimated with a good confidence:

	VALUE	STOCH. APPROX.	
		S.E.	R.S.E.(%)
Fixed Effects			
Cl_pop	2.56	0.23	8.98
beta_Cl_AGE	-0.00729	0.000906	12.4
beta_Cl_LBM	0.00547	0.00125	22.9
V1_pop	1.65	0.419	25.3
beta_V1_AGE	-0.00351	0.00178	50.5
beta_V1_LBM	0.0211	0.00371	17.6
Q2_pop	3.36	0.706	21
beta_Q2_AGE	-0.0174	0.00412	23.6
V2_pop	14.6	1.82	12.4
beta_V2_AGE	-0.0133	0.00244	18.4
Q3_pop	0.332	0.122	36.7
beta_Q3_AGE	-0.017	0.00743	43.8
V3_pop	8.33	1.62	19.4
beta_V3_AGE	-0.0186	0.00381	20.5
Standard Deviation of the Random Effects			
omega_Cl	0.146	0.0133	9.11
omega_V1	0.244	0.0289	11.8
omega_Q2	0.666	0.0692	10.4
omega_V2	0.393	0.0389	9.9
omega_Q3	1.13	0.115	10.2
omega_V3	0.484	0.0613	12.7
Correlations			
corr_Q2_Cl	0.473	0.112	23.6
corr_Q3_Cl	0.295	0.129	43.7
corr_V2_Cl	0.55	0.0948	17.3
corr_Q3_Q2	-0.533	0.0947	17.8
corr_V2_Q2	0.734	0.0774	10.5
corr_V2_Q3	-0.255	0.125	48.8
Error Model Parameters			
a	0.019	0.00256	13.4
b	0.109	0.002	1.84

Next, we add PK_3 in the workflow overview to compare it to the previous projects, by clicking on the icon "Rescan directory" next to the PK folder in the Selection panel, like this:

This adds the project PK_3.mlxtran in the list of selected projects of the overview. It can now be added in the tree view as a child of PK_2, with the comment "Applied best proposal".

As we can see on the table below, the BICc indeed indicates that PK_3 is more performant than PK_2, thus we choose the rating ★★★★★ for PK_3. Note that BICc values can be easily compared in this table by sorting the column BICc with the button marked on the figure.

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lin)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_1	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		7945.98		8008.26	lib: infusio n_2cpt_Cf V1QV2.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q V1 V2	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_2	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		7150.89		7236.72	lib: infusio n_3cpt_Cf V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q2 Q3 V1 V2 V3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	PK_3	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		6869.56		7013.82	lib: infusio n_3cpt_Cf V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb2	CI Q2 Q3 V1 V2 V3	AGE, LBM

In the tab Results of Monolix for PK_3, we see that PK_3 also has a proposed model available, where a covariate effect of Sex is also included on V3, therefore, we finalize PK_3 with a comment “Proposed model available” and save.

If the proposal at the previous step has been efficient, we should not expect a large improvement of the objective function value with this new covariate effect. To check this, we apply again the best proposed model and save the modifications in a project PK_4.mlxtran. As before, it is important to not only run the scenario, but also check the convergence of the estimates and their standard errors.

Once this is done, we add PK_4 to the overview in Sycomore. Since the table is still sorted by BICc, it is quickly visible that PK_4 actually has a higher BICc than PK_3. Therefore, we choose a rating ★★ for PK_4 and we consider PK_3 as more performant.

Compare	Project name	Hierarchy	Actions	Rating	-2*LL (Lin)	-2*LL (IS)	BICc (Lin)	BICc (IS)	Structural model	Observation model	Individual model	Used covariates	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_1	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		7945.98		8008.26	lib: infusio n_2cpt_Cf V1QV2.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q V1 V2		Mis-specification in diagnostic plots: 3rd cpt needed
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PK_2	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		7150.89		7236.72	lib: infusio n_3cpt_Cf V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb1	CI Q2 Q3 V1 V2 V3		No mis-specification in structural model Statistical model can be improved
<input type="checkbox"/>	PK_3	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★★		6869.56		7013.82	lib: infusio n_3cpt_Cf V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb2	CI Q2 Q3 V1 V2 V3	AGE, LBM	Statistical model can be improved
<input type="checkbox"/>	PK_4	⊖	✕ 📄 ↺ ↻ 🗑️	★★		6946.9		7095.34	lib: infusio n_3cpt_Cf V1Q2V2Q 3V3.txt	y1: comb2	CI Q2 Q3 V1 V2 V3	AGE, LBM, SEX	Statistical model can be improved

We can now consider PK_3 as the final PK model. To save this decision in the comments of the project, it is possible to open again the project in Monolix directly from Sycomore, by clicking on the “Monolix” icon in the row for PK_3:

After completing the comments and saving the project, the comments displayed in Sycomore can be updated with the “refresh” button.

6.5.6 Joint PK-PD model

We next would like to develop a joint model for the PK and the PD. We choose to try two different PD models that could take into account the delay between remifentanil concentration and decrease of EEG, revealed by the data exploration:

- Model 1: a direct inhibition model with an effect compartment.
- Model 2: a turnover model with PD production inhibition by the PK.

Here are the equations for EEG (PD observations) for both models:

<p>Model 1</p> $EEG = EEG_0 \left(1 - I_{max} \frac{C e^{\gamma}}{C e^{\gamma} + IC50^{\gamma}} \right)$	<p>Model 2</p> $\frac{dEEG}{dt} = k_{syn} \left(1 - I_{max} \frac{C e^{\gamma}}{C e^{\gamma} + IC50^{\gamma}} \right) - k_{deg} EEG$
--	--

We will now define two projects with these two models, available in the libraries of Monolix, and we will then run the two projects in a row from Sycomore.

Since both PKPD models will be based on the final PK model, we start by creating two clones of PK_3 in Sycomore with the button “Clone project” (note that the action “Clone project” is also available by clicking on the node for PK_3 in the tree view):

We save each cloned project in a new folder named PKPD, under the names PKPD_1.mlxtran and PKPD_2.mlxtran. The cloned project are automatically included in the panel selection and the tree view as children nodes of PK_3:

Let's now open PKPD_1.mlxtran in Monolix to add the first PD model.

The project has been saved with the comments of PK_3, that we can delete, and the results of PK_3, which means that the PK parameters estimated with PK_3 are available. We start by defining these estimated parameters as new initial values, by clicking on "Use last estimates: all" in the tab "Initial estimates". Then, we choose to fix all the PK population parameters: the goal is to perform a quick estimation of only the PD population parameters that will be added later in the model. To fix all population parameters, we click on "Fix parameters values: All" in the tab "Initial estimates":

Note that this method is easy to implement in the interface of Monolix and allows to estimate only the PD population parameters, however all individual parameters will be estimated, including the PK parameters. Therefore, it will take longer than a fully sequential approach where individual PK parameters from the PK analysis are included in the dataset to be used for predictions.

We can now complete the structural model with a PD model. In the tab “Structural model”, we load a model from the PKPD models library, corresponding to the same PK model as before, with a partial inhibition PD model with effect compartment and with sigmoidicity.

We choose good initial values for the PD parameters in the panel “Check initial estimates” of the tab “Initial estimates”. The auto-init is only available for models from the PK library, therefore we have to choose manually some values that give a reasonable fit to the data, for example $ke0_pop=1$, $\gamma_pop=2$, $E0_pop=20$, $lmax_pop=0.9$, $IC50_pop=10$. We can then save the modified project. Since the project will be run from Sycomore, we make sure that all the tasks of the scenario are selected and saved.

We follow the same steps as for PKPD_1.mlxtran to define the second PD model in PKPD_2.mlxtran. Here we choose a PKPD model where the PD model is a turnover model with partial inhibition of the production and with sigmoidicity. We can take for initial values $kout_pop=1$, $\gamma_pop=2$, $R0_pop=20$, $lmax_pop=0.9$, $IC50_pop=10$.

Once both projects have been defined and refreshed in Sycomore, we can launch their scenarios directly from Sycomore, by clicking in the table on the two names PKPD_1 and PKPD_2. The projects are then colored in green. The list of selected projects can then be run in a row with the button “Run”. A pop-up window opens to display the progress of the runs:

After the two runs have finished, we finally select the two PKPD projects for side-by-side comparison, to check their results, in particular the estimated values and standard errors. In both cases, the parameters have been estimated with a good confidence.

To compare the diagnostic plots, it is necessary to open the projects in the interface of Monolix to generate the plots and export them as png images. The comparison of the VPC for example shows that both models have a good predictive power:

Finally, the comparison of the BICc values indicate that the model 1 is slightly more performant than model 2.

Project Name	PKPD_1	PKPD_2
-2*LL (Importance sampling)	23892.17	24264.05
BICc (Importance sampling)	23998.97	24370.84

To visualize this difference on the tree view, we choose a rating ★★★ for PKPD_1 and ★★ for PKPD_2.

6.5.7 Conclusion

We built a quick joint PKPD model for remifentanyl in Monolix, with the help of structural model libraries and automatic statistical model building tools implemented in Monolix.

This example illustrates how Sycomore can be used to:

- track the steps of the modelling workflow and see at a glance the main elements of each step,
- easily add a new step of the workflow by cloning a Monolix project,
- save the changes between successive runs,
- compare side-by-side the results of similar models,
- run sets of Monolix projects.

All the material of this case study (data, Monolix projects and Sycomore overview) can be downloaded here: [PKPD_remifentanil_workflow_sycomore.zip](#)

7 Plots

7.1 General plot features

7.1.1 Generating and exporting plots

7.1.1.1 Generating plots

Diagnostic plots can be generated by clicking on the **task “Plots”** or as part of the scenario when clicking on Run. By default, when reloading a project which has already run, only the plots Observed data and Covariate viewer are displayed. To generate the other diagnostic plots, click on the Plot task. Generating plots automatically at project load can be enabled via a Preference.

The set of plots to compute can be selected by clicking on the button next to the task as shown below, prior to running the task.

By default, only a subset of plots are selected (see below), with one occurrence for each plot. The number of occurrences can be selected via the **number selection box**. Having several occurrences of the same plot allows to choose different settings for each occurrence, for instance one on linear scale and one on log scale. The plot selection and number of occurrences is saved as part of the mlxtran file upon save, and reapplied at project reload.

The **green arrow** can be used to generate only one plot type with the given number of occurrences without re-generating all other plots. The **“+” button** allows to add one additional occurrence. If the information necessary to generate a plot is not available, these buttons are hidden.

Selected plots

Data	Model for the observations
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observed data # 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Individual fits # 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bivariate data viewer # 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Observations vs predictions # 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Covariate viewer # 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scatter plot of the residuals # 1
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution of the residuals # 1
Select: All None	
Model for the individual parameters	Predictive checks and predictions
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution of the individual parameters # 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Visual predictive check # 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Distribution of the standardized random effects # 1	<input type="checkbox"/> Numerical predictive check # 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Correlation between random effects # 1	<input type="checkbox"/> Prediction distribution # 1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Individual parameters vs covariates # 1	
Select: All None	
Tasks results	Convergence diagnosis
<input type="checkbox"/> Likelihood contribution # 1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SAEM # 1
<input type="checkbox"/> Standard errors of the estimates # 1	<input type="checkbox"/> MCMC # 1
	<input type="checkbox"/> Importance sampling # 1

7.1.1.2 List of available plots

7.1.1.2.1 Data

- Observed data: This plot displays the original data w.r.t. time as a spaghetti plot, along with some additional information.

7.1.1.2.2 Model for the observations

- Individual fits: This plot displays the individual fits: individual predictions using the individual parameters and the individual covariates w.r.t. time on a continuous grid, with the observed data overlaid.
- Observations vs predictions: This plot displays observations w.r.t. the predictions computed using the population parameters or the individual parameters.
- Scatter plot of the residuals: This plot displays the PWRES (population weighted residuals), the IWRES (individual weighted residuals), and the NPDE (Normalized Prediction Distribution Errors) w.r.t. the time and the prediction.
- Distribution of the residuals: This plot displays the distributions of PWRES, IWRES and NPDE as histograms for the probability density function (PDF) or as cumulative distribution functions (CDF).

7.1.1.2.3 Diagnosis plots based on individual parameters

- Distribution of the individual parameters: This plot displays the estimated population distributions overlaid with a histogram of the individual parameters
- Distribution of the random effects: This plot displays the estimated populated distribution of the random effects overlaid with a histogram of the random effects derived from the individual parameters.
- Correlation between random effects: This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of random effects.
- Individual parameters vs covariates: This plot displays the individual parameters or random effects w.r.t. the covariates.

7.1.1.2.4 Predictive checks and predictions

- Visual predictive checks: This plot displays the Visual Predictive Check.
- Numerical predictive checks: This plot displays the numerical predictive check.
- BLQ predictive checks: This plot displays the predicted and observed proportion of censored data w.r.t. time.
- Prediction distribution: This plot displays the prediction distribution.

7.1.1.2.5 Convergence diagnosis

- SAEM: This plot displays the convergence trajectories of the population parameters estimated with SAEM with respect to the iteration number.
- MCMC: This plot displays the convergence of the Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm for the estimation of the individual conditional distributions.
- Importance sampling: This plot displays the convergence of log-likelihood estimation by importance sampling.

7.1.1.2.6 Tasks results

- Likelihood contribution: This plot displays the contribution of each individual to the log-likelihood.
- Standard errors for the estimates: This plot displays the relative standard errors (in %) for the population parameters.

7.1.1.3 Exporting plots and setting plot-related preferences

Several features can be used to export plots or plot data or create plots automatically:

- Saving a single plot as image (icon button)
- Create plots at project load (Preference)

- Save charts data as binary file (Preference)
- Export VPC simulations (Preference and Export menu)
- Export charts datasets (Preference and Export menu)
- Export plots (Preference and Export menu)
- Export charts data (Preference and Export menu)

Each feature is detailed below in this section.

Most of them are located:

- in the **Export menu**: to export the plots as image file or a text files for a single project.

- in the **Preferences**: to export the plots as image file or a text files automatically at the end of each plot generation task. Preferences are user-specific and apply to all projects. The preferences are saved in C:\Users\\lixoft\monolix\monolixXXXXRX\config\config.ini.

7.1.1.3.1 Saving a single plot as image (icon button)

The user can choose to export each plot as an image with an icon on top of the plot, choosing between png and svg format. The files are saved in <result folder>/ChartsFigures with the name of the plot, the observation name (e.g y1 or y2) and a postfix indicating the plot occurrence, and page number. Note that information frames are not exported. The icon becomes available only when a structural model has been selected.

7.1.1.3.2 Create plots at project load (Preference)

By default, when a project which has already run is re-opened, only the plots “Observed data” and “Covariate viewer” are displayed. To generate the other diagnostic plots, it is necessary to click on the “Plots” task. Note that it is not necessary to rerun the entire scenario of all tasks.

Starting with version 2024, it is possible to choose whether plots should be created automatically at project load. This option is available in **Settings > Preferences > Create plots at project load**. When this option is “on”, plots are generated when opening a project with results. Note that this increases the load time, in particular if the charts data have not been saved as binary (see below). By default, the option is “off”.

7.1.1.3.3 Save charts data as binary file (Preference)

Generating the plots can take several minutes depending on the model and dataset, because it requires to redo the simulations used in the VPC for instance. Starting with version 2024, it is possible to save the charts data (in particular the simulations) as a binary file, which is re-used when the plots are re-generated. This greatly speeds up the time necessary to generate the diagnostic plots. This option is available in **Settings > Preferences > Save charts data as binary file**. When this option is “on” (default), the charts data are saved in a non-human-readable format in <result folder>/ChartsData/.Internals/chartsData.dat each time the plots are generated. At project reload, if the file chartsData.dat exists and is valid, it is used to generate the plots faster.

7.1.1.3.4 Export VPC simulations (Preference and Export menu)

Simulations used to generate the VPC plot can be exported as txt file. This allows to replot the VPC with an external software for instance. If this export is required for a single project, the user can click **Export > Export VPC simulations**. The simulations are saved in <result folder>\ChartsData\VisualPredictiveCheck\XXX_simulations.txt. If the user wishes to do this export each time the VPC plot is generated, the option **Settings > Preferences > Export VPC simulations** can be set to “on”.

7.1.1.3.5 Export charts datasets (Preference and Export menu)

Simulations used for the VPC and the Individual fits (prediction on a fine time grid) can be exported as MonolixSuite-formatted datasets (including dose records, regressors, etc). This is useful if these simulations need to be loaded in another MonolixSuite application such as PKAnalix for instance. To export these formatted simulations once use **Export > Export Charts Datasets > VPC or Individual fits**. A pop-up window will let you choose the name and location of the saved files.

To export the simulations as formatted dataset systematically each time the plots are generated, the option **Settings > Preferences > Export charts datasets** can be set to “on”. The files are saved in <result folder>/DataFile/ChartsData/indfits_data.csv and vpc_data.csv.

7.1.1.3.6 Export plots (Preference and Export menu)

Plots can be saved as image files. To save a single plot, use the icon on the top of the plot (see section above). To save all plots for a single project, use **Export > Export plots**. To systematically save all generated plots as image file, set the the option **Settings > Preferences > Export plots** to “on”. The files are saved in <result folder>/ChartsFigures with the name of the plot, the observation name (e.g y1 or y2) and a postfix indicating the plot occurrence, and page number. The files are saved at the end of the plot generation task. The file format (png or svg) can be chosen in the Preferences. Note that information frames are not exported.

7.1.1.3.7 Export charts data (Preference and Export menu)

The values used to draw the plots can be saved as txt files. This can be useful to regenerate the plots using an external tool. To export the charts data for a single project, use **Export > Export charts data**. To systematically export the charts data at the end of the plot generation, set the the option **Settings > Preferences > Export charts data** to “on”. The files are saved in <result folder>/ChartsData with one subfolder per plot. The content of each file is described on the dedicated page. The file separator can be chosen in the Preferences.

7.1.1.4 Plot settings

A few plot settings impact the simulations required for the plots. They can be chosen in the Settings panel for the Plots task.

- **Number of simulations:** number of replicates simulated for the VPC, NPC and Prediction distribution plot (default: 500)
- **Grid:** number of points of the fine time grid used for the individuals fits (default: 250). See the video below for more details.

7.1.2 Interacting with the plots

7.1.2.1 Interactive diagnostic plots

In the Plots tab, the right panel has several sub – tabs (at the bottom) to interact with the plots:

- The tab “Settings” provides options specific to each plot, such as hiding or displaying elements of the plot, modifying some elements, or changing axes scales, ticks and limits.

- The tab “Stratify” can be used to select one or several covariates for splitting, filtering or coloring the points of the plot. See [below](#) for more details.
- The tab “Preferences” allows to customize graphical aspects such as colors, font size, dot radius, line width, ...

These tabs are marked in purple on the figure below, which is the panel that is showed for observed data.

7.1.2.2 Highlight: tooltips and ID

In all the plots, when you hover a point or a curve with your mouse, some informations are provided as tooltips. For example, the ID is displayed when hovering a point or the curve of an individual in the observed data plot, the ID, the time and/or the prediction is displayed in the scatter plot of the residuals.

In addition, starting from the 2019 version, when hovering one point/ID in a plot, the same ID will be highlighted in all the plots with the same color.

7.1.2.3 Stratification: split, color, filter

The stratification panel allows to create and use covariates for stratification purposes. It is possible to select one or several covariates for splitting, filtering or coloring the data set or the diagnosis plots as exposed on the following video.

The following figure shows a plot of the observed data from the warfarin dataset, stratified by coloring individuals according to the continuous covariate wt: the observed data is divided into three groups, which were set to equal size with the button “rescale” . It is also possible to set groups of equal width, or to personalize dividing values.

In addition, the bounds of the continuous covariate groups can be changed manually.

Moreover, clicking on a group highlights only the individuals belonging to this group, as can be seen below:

Values of categorical covariates can also be assigned to new groups, which can then be used for stratification.

In addition, the number of subjects in each categorical covariate groups is displayed.

Starting from the 2021R1 version, the list of subplots obtained by split is displayed below the split selection. It is possible to reorder the items in this list with drag-and-drop, which also reorders the subplot layout. Moreover, an “edit” icon next to each subplot name in the list allows to change the subplot titles.

7.1.2.4 Preferences: customizing the plot appearance

In the “preferences” tab, the user can modify the different aspects of the plot: colors, line style and width, fonts and label position offsets, ...

The following figures show on the warfarin demo the choices for the plot content and the choices for the labels and titles (in the “Plotting region” section). The sizes of all elements of the plots can also be changed with the single “zoom” preference in “Plotting region”.

7.1.2.5 Layout

The layout can be modified with buttons on top of each plot.

The first button can be used to select a set of subplots to display in the page. For example, as shown below, it is possible to display 9 individual fits per page instead of 12 (default number). The layout is then automatically adapted to balance the number of rows and columns.

The second button can be used to choose a custom layout (number of rows and columns). On the example figures below, the default layout with 3 subplots (left) is modified to arrange them on a single column (right).

7.1.3 Transferring plot formatting

The features described on this page are not available in MonolixSuite versions prior to 2024R1.

MonolixSuite offers the ability to transfer plot formatting from one plot to another within the same project or across projects. This can save you time and effort when you want to apply the same formatting options, such as stratification, preferences, or settings, to multiple plots, or when you want to use the same plot formatting for different analyses or datasets.

7.1.3.1 Transferring plot formatting within one project

To transfer plot formatting within one project, you need to use the “Apply...” button on the bottom left of the Plots tab and select “From plot” in the window that opens:

7.1.3.1.1 Selecting the source and target plots

The window allows you to select the source plot, which is the plot that has the formatting you want to transfer, and the target plots, which are the plots that you want to apply the formatting to. You can select all plots by clicking on the Select all button, or select all plots specific to some observation id with the “Fast selection”.

7.1.3.1.2 Choosing the sections to transfer

You can also choose which sections of the configuration you want to transfer: Stratify, Settings, or Preferences.

Plot formatting: STRATIFY SETTINGS PREFERENCES

By default, Stratify and Preferences are selected.

- The Stratify section includes the options to stratify the plots by covariates or occasions.
- The Settings section includes the options to customize the content of the plots: elements displayed or not on the plots, such as the legend, the grid, the observed data points, etc, and calculation settings such as the axes, bins etc.
- The Preferences section includes the options to change the colors, fonts, sizes, etc.

Once you have selected the source plot, the target plots, and the sections to transfer, you can click on the Apply button to transfer the plot configurations.

7.1.3.2 Transferring plot formatting across projects with plot presets

To transfer plot formatting across different projects, you need to use the **plot presets** feature, which allows you to define and apply presets for plot configurations.

7.1.3.2.1 Defining a plot preset

To define a plot preset, you need to first set up your plot configuration as you would like by choosing the stratification, preferences, and settings options for each plot (you can use the transfer or plot formatting between plots within the same project, described in the first section, to help you). Then, you can save this configuration as a preset by clicking on the Save icon in the Apply from the Plot Formatting panel:

You will be asked to give a name and a description to your preset, and to select which sections of the formatting you want to include in the preset among Stratify, Settings and Preferences. If the project has several types of observations, only the plots corresponding to one of them can be used to define the preset so it is necessary to select the observation id. You can also choose to set this preset as your default, which means that when you click on Reset, the plot formatting from this preset will be applied instead of the system default.

New custom preset from current plots

Name: From Obs ID:

STRATIFY

SETTINGS

PREFERENCES

Description:
Add description

Use this preset as default to generate plots in all MonolixSuite apps

CANCEL
CREATE

7.1.3.2.2 Applying a plot preset

After saving your preset, it will be available in the list of presets that you can choose from when you click on "From preset" in the window that opens with "Apply..." in the Plot Formatting panel.

Apply formatting...

From plot Observed data | Obs ID: 1_Cp ▼

From preset MyPlotPreset ▼

Plot formatting: PREFER

...to the following

- Greyscale_Preferences
- Typical_Reporting_Settings
- CompanySettings
- GreyScaleMargins_Monolix
- GreyScaleMargins_PKanalix
- MyPlotPreset

Observed data

Observed data

You can apply your preset to a list of plots in another project, by opening this project, clicking on “Apply...” and “From preset” and by selecting the preset and the target plots, and finally clicking on Apply. This will transfer the plot configurations from the preset to the target plots.

The target plots must be the same type of plots that were used to define the preset: for example if no CA plot had been generated in the project used to define the preset, then the plot preset cannot be applied to a CA plot in a new project, as there is no CA formatting option to apply.

Note that axis limits values and bins settings are not saved as part of the preset because they are considered too project-specific.

Note this major difference between “Apply formatting from plot” and “Apply formatting from preset”:

- “Apply formatting from plot”: applies **selected options from the source plot only** to **all selected target plots**.
 - Example: if you select:
 - the NCA data plot stratified by STUDY as source plot
 - and the Observed data plot as target plot,
 - and “Stratify” section in plot formatting to be transferred,
 - after applying the formatting, you will obtain the Observed data plot stratified by STUDY.
- “Apply formatting from preset”: applies **selected options from each plot** saved in the preset **to the corresponding plot only** in your project.
 - Example: if you saved a preset:
 - from a project where the NCA data plot is stratified by STUDY but not the Observed data plot,
 - including the “Stratify” section,
 - after applying that preset to another project, you will obtain the NCA data plot stratified by STUDY, but not the Observed data plot.

7.1.3.2.3 Managing plot presets

You can also manage your presets by going to Settings > Manage presets > Plot formatting.

This will open a window where you can see all presets, modify, update or remove your custom presets, and export or import them as separate files with a lixpst extension. That way you can easily share your presets with your colleagues or collaborators to standardize your plot formatting.

7.1.3.3 Applying predefined plot formatting

In addition to your custom presets, MonolixSuite also provides two predefined presets that you can use to apply plot formatting. These presets are:

- **Greyscale_Preferences:** This preset affects only the Preferences section of the plot configurations, and produces publication-ready greyscale plots with optimized size and spacing of the texts to improve readability of the plots (example shown below for the NCA Individual fits).

- **Typical_Reporting_Settings:** This preset affects only the Settings section of the plot configuration, and corresponds to plot settings typically chosen to report the analysis results. It has additional settings for Monolix plots, but in PKanalix it only removes the grid in the background for all plots:

You can apply these presets to any plot in your project by selecting them from the list of presets and clicking on Apply. You can also combine these presets with your own presets or with the Apply from plot feature, to create the plot configuration that suits your needs.

7.1.3.4 Restoring default plot configuration

7.1.3.4.1 Using the Reset button

If you want to restore the default plot configuration, you can click on the Reset icon in the Apply from plot panel. This will reset all plots to the system default, or to your custom default if you have defined one.

Note that resetting the plot configuration will not affect the plot presets that you have defined or imported. You can still apply them to any plot after resetting.

7.1.3.4.2 Defining a custom default

To define a custom default, you need to create a preset and select the option “Use this preset as default” when saving it. This will make this preset the default configuration for all plots. You can also unset a preset as default by going to Settings > Manage presets > Plot formatting, and unchecking the option “Use this preset as default” for the preset.

7.1.4 Export charts data

7.1.4.1 All plots generated by Monolix can be exported

All plots generated by Monolix can be exported as figures or as text files in order to be able to plot them in another way or with other softwares for more flexibility.

Exporting the charts data can be made through the Export menu or through the preferences as described here.

The list of files in the next sections corresponds to all the charts data that Monolix can generate. They are computed with the task “Plots”, and the list of plots to compute in that task can be selected by clicking on the button next to the task prior to running it.

All the files can then be exported in R, for example using the following command:

```
read.table("/path/to/file.txt", sep = ",", comment.char = "#", header = T)
```

Remarks

- The separator is the one defined in the user preferences. We set “,” in this example as it is the one by default.
- The command `comment.char = "#"` is needed for some files because to define groups or color, we use the character # that can be interpreted as a comment character by R.

7.1.4.2 Charts concerning the Data

7.1.4.2.1 Observed data (continuous, categorical, and count)

7.1.4.2.1.1 *xxx_observations.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Comment
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation time	-
y	Observation value (log)	The name of the column is the observation name
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-
split	Name of the split the subject belongs to	-
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	-
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.2.2 Observed data (event)

7.1.4.2.2.1 *xxx_curves.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Observation times	-
survivalFunction	Survival of first event	-

averageEventNumber	Average number of event at that time	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	-

7.1.4.2.2.2 *xxx_censored.txt*

Description: censored values

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Observation times	-
values	Survival of first event	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	-

7.1.4.3 Model for the observations

7.1.4.3.1 Individual Fits

7.1.4.3.1.1 *xxx_observations.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Comment
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation time	-
y	Observation value (log)	-
median	Prediction interval median	-
piLower	Lower percentile of the individual prediction interval	-

piUpper	Upper percentile of the individual prediction interval	-
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.3.1.2 *xxx_fits.txt*

Description: individual fits based on population parameters and individual parameters

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Continuous time grid used to compute fits	-
pop	Prediction using population parameter values and average covariate value from the population (continuous) or reference covariate value (categorical).	-
popPred	Prediction using population parameter values and individual covariates.	-
indivPredMean	Prediction based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mean	Conditional distribution need to be computed
indivPredMode	Prediction based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mode	EBEs need to be computed

7.1.4.3.2 Observation vs Prediction

7.1.4.3.2.1 *xxx_obsVsPred.txt*

Description: observation and prediction (pop & indiv) values

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-

OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	time of the observation	
y	Observation value (log)	-
y_simBlq	Observation value (simulated blq)	
popPred	Predictions based on population parameter values	
indivPredMean	Predictions based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mean	Conditional distribution need to be computed
indivPredMode	Predictions based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mode	EBEs need to be computed
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.3.2.2 *xxx_obsVsSimulatedPred.txt*

Description: observation and simulated prediction values

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	Replicate id	
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	time of the observation	
y	Observation value (log)	-

y_simBlq	Observation value (simulated blq)	
indivPredSimulated	Predictions based on the simulated individual parameter values estimated by conditional distribution	Conditional distribution need to be computed
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	

7.1.4.3.2.3 *xxx_visualGuides.txt*

Description: splines and confidence intervals for predictions

Column	Description	Needed Task
popPred	Continuous grid over population prediction values	-
popPred_spline	Spline ordinates for population predictions	-
popPred_piLower	Lower percentile of prediction interval for population predictions	-
popPred_piUpper	Upper percentile of prediction interval for population predictions	-
indivPred	Continuous grid over individual prediction values	-
indivPred_spline	Spline ordinates for individual predictions	-
indivPred_piLower	Lower percentile of prediction interval for individual predictions	-
indivPred_piUpper	Upper percentile of prediction interval for individual predictions	-
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	

7.1.4.3.3 Distribution of the residuals

7.1.4.3.3.1 *xxx_pdf.txt*

Description: probability density function of each residual type (pwres, iwres, npde)

Column	Description	Needed Task
pwRes_abcissa	Abscissa for pwres pdf	-
pwRes_pdf	Pdf of pwres	-
iwRes_abcissa	Abscissa for iwres pdf	-
iwRes_pdf	Pdf of the iwres	-
npde_abcissa	Abscissa for npde pdf	-
npde_pdf	Pdf of the npde	-
split	-	

7.1.4.3.3.2 *xxx_cdf.txt*

Description: cumulative distribution function of each residual type (pwres, iwres, npde)

Column	Description	Needed Task
pwRes_abcissa	Abscissa for pwres cdf	-
pwRes_cdf	Cdf of pwres	-
iwRes_abcissa	Abscissa for iwres cdf	-
iwRes_cdf	Cdf of the iwres	-
npde_abcissa	Abscissa for npde cdf	-
npde_cdf	Cdf of the npde	-
split	-	

7.1.4.3.3 *theoreticalGuides.txt*

Description: theoretical guides for the pdf and the cdf

Column	Description	Needed Task
abscissa,pdf,cdf	Abscissa for the theoretical curves	-
pdf	Theoretical value of the pdf	-
cdf	Theoretical value of the cdf	-

7.1.4.3.4 Scatter plot of the residuals

7.1.4.3.4.1 *xxx_prediction_percentiles_iwRes.txt*

Description: prediction percentiles of the iwREs to plot iwRes w.r.t. the prediction. The same files exists with the pwres and the npde.

Column	Description	Needed Task
prediction	Value of the prediction	-
empirical_median	Empirical median of the iwRes	-
empirical_lower	Empirical lower percentile of the iwRes	
empirical_upper	Empirical upper percentile of the iwRes	
theoretical_median	Theoretical median of the iwRes	
theoretical_lower	Theoretical lower of the iwRes	
theoretical_upper	Theoretical upper of the iwRes	
theoretical_median_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical median prediction interval	
theoretical_median_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical median prediction interval	

theoretical_lower_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical lower prediction interval	
theoretical_lower_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical lower prediction interval	
theoretical_upper_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical upper prediction interval	
theoretical_upper_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical upper prediction interval	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.3.4.2 *xxx_time_percentiles_iwRes.txt*

Description: time percentiles of the iwREs to plot iwRes w.r.t. the time. The same files exists with the pwres and the npde.

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Value of the time	-
empirical_median	Empirical median of the iwRes	-
empirical_lower	Empirical lower percentile of the iwRes	
empirical_upper	Empirical upper percentile of the iwRes	
theoretical_median	Theoretical median of the iwRes	
theoretical_lower	Theoretical lower of the iwRes	
theoretical_upper	Theoretical upper of the iwRes	
theoretical_median_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical median prediction interval	
theoretical_median_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical median prediction interval	
theoretical_lower_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical lower prediction interval	

theoretical_lower_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical lower prediction interval	
theoretical_upper_piLower	Lower bound of the theoretical upper prediction interval	
theoretical_upper_piUpper	Upper bound of the theoretical upper prediction interval	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.3.4.3 *xxx_residuals.txt*

Description: residuals values (pwres, iwres, npde)

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation times	-
prediction_pwRes	Predictions based on population parameter values	SAEM
pwRes	PwRes (computed with observations)	SAEM
pwRes_blq	PwRes (computed with simulated blq)	
prediction_iwRes_mean	Predictions based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mean (INDIVESTIM) if available, SAEM either	
iwRes_mean	IwRes (computed with observations and individual parameter values estimated by conditional mean (INDIVESTIM) if available, SAEM either)	
iwRes_mean_simBlq	IwRes (computed with simulated blq and individual parameter values estimated by conditional mean (INDIVESTIM) if available, SAEM either)	

prediction_iwRes_mode	Predictions based on the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mode (INDIVESTIM)	
iwRes_mode	IwRes (computed with observations and the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mode (INDIVESTIM))	
iwRes_mean_simBlq	IwRes (computed with simulated blq and the individual parameter values estimated by conditional mode (INDIVESTIM))	
prediction_npde	Predictions based on population parameter values	
npde	Npde (computed with observations)	
npde_simBlq	Npde (computed with simulated blq)	SAEM – If there are some censored data in the data set
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	–

7.1.4.3.4.4 *xxx_simulatedResiduals.txt*

Description: simulated residuals values

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	replicate	–
id	Subject identifier	–
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation times	–

prediction_iwRes	Predictions based on the simulated individual parameter values based on the conditional distribution	
iwRes_simulated	IwRes (computed with observations and the simulated individual parameter values)	
iwRes_simulated_simBlq	IwRes (computed with simulated blq and the simulated individual parameter values)	
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.3.4.5 *xxx_spline.txt*

Description: splines (residuals values against time and prediction)

Column	Description	Needed Task
time_pwRes	Time grid for pwRes spline	SAEM
time_pwRes_spline	pwRes against time spline	SAEM
time_iwRes	Time grid for iwRes spline	At least SAEM
time_iwRes_spline	iwRes against time spline	At least SAEM
time_npde	Time grid for npde spline	SAEM
time_npde_spline	npde against time spline	SAEM
prediction_pwRes	Prediction grid for pwRes spline	SAEM
prediction_pwRes_spline	pwRes against population prediction spline	SAEM
prediction_iwRes	Prediction grid for iwRes spline	At least SAEM

prediction_iwRes_spline	iwRes against individual prediction spline	At least SAEM
prediction_npde	Prediction grid for npde spline	SAEM
prediction_npde_npde	npde against population prediction spline	SAEM
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.3.4.6 *xxx_{time,population,individual}Bins.txt*

Description: bins values for the corresponding axis.

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsValues	Abscissa bins values	-
split	Name of the split the bins refer to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.4 Model for the individual parameters

7.1.4.4.1 Distribution of the individual parameters

7.1.4.4.1.1 *cdf.txt*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_abcissa	Abscissa of the cdf of the individual parameter param	-
param_cdf	Empirical cdf of the individual parameter param	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.4.1.2 *pdf.txt*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_abcissa	Abscissa of the pdf of the individual parameter param	-
param_pdf	Empirical pdf of the individual parameter param	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.4.1.3 *visualGuides.txt*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_abcissa	Abscissa of the pdf and the pdf of the individual parameter param	-
param_pdf	Theoretical pdf of the individual parameter param	-
param_cdf	Theoretical cdf of the individual parameter param	

7.1.4.4.2 Distribution of the random effects

7.1.4.4.2.1 *cdf.txt*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_abcissa	Abscissa of the cdf of the standardized random effect of param	-
param_cdf	Empirical cdf of the standardized random effect of param	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.4.2.2 *pdf.txt*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_abcissa	Abscissa of the pdf of the standardized random effect of param	-
param_pdf	Empirical pdf of the standardized random effect of param	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	

7.1.4.4.2.3 *StandardizedEta.txt*

Description: standardized random effects of the individual parameters

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
standEta_X_method	Standardized random effects values on each individual parameter with variability. It can be StandEta_SAEM, StandEta_Mean, StandEta_Mode	-
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.4.2.4 *SimulatedStandardizedEta.txt*

Description: simulated standardized random effects of the individual parameters

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	Replicate id	-
id	Subject identifier	-

OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
standEta_X_simulated	Standardized random effects values on each individual parameter with variability.	-
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.4.3 Correlation between Random Effects

7.1.4.4.3.1 *eta.txt*

Description: standard error on individual parameter predictions

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
eta_X_method	Random effects values on each individual parameter with variability. It can be eta_SAEM, eta_Mean, or eta_Mode	-
color	Name of the color the ID is colored with	-
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.4.3.2 *simulatedEta.txt*

Description: standard error on individual parameter predictions

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	Replicate number	
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set

eta_X_simulated	Simulated random effects values on each individual parameter	-
color	Name of the color the ID is colored with	-
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.4.3.3 *visualGuides.txt*

Description: spline and linear regression for each couple of individual parameters plotted one against the other

This is done for each combination of parameter p1 and p2 to have p1 w.r.t. p2

Column	Description	Needed Task
p1_vs_p2_abscissa	Abscissa	-
p1_vs_p2_spline	Spline ordinates	-
p1_vs_p2_regression	Linear regression ordinates	-

7.1.4.4.4 Individual Parameters Vs Covariates

7.1.4.4.4.1 *covariates.txt*

Description: individual parameters and random effects and covariate value for each subject

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
trans_X_method	Individual parameter value in the transformed space. It can be X_SAEM, X_mean, or X_mode	-
eta_X_method	Random effects values. It can be eta_X_SAEM, eta_Mean, or eta_Mode	-

covariate	Covariates values	
split		
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	

7.1.4.4.2 *simulatedCovariates.txt*

Description: simulated individual parameters and random effects and covariate value for each subject

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	Replicate of the simulation	
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
trans_X_simulated	Simulated transformed individual parameter value.	-
eta_X_simulated	Simulated random effects values.	-
covariate	Covariates values	
split		
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.4.3 *visualGuides.txt*

Description: spline and linear regression for each couple of individual parameters plotted against a covariate

This is done for each combination of parameter *param* and covariate *cov* to have *param* w.r.t. *cov*

Column	Description	Needed Task
param_vs_cov_abscissa	Abscissa	-
param_vs_cov_spline	Spline ordinates	-
param_vs_cov_regression	Linear regression ordinates	-

7.1.4.5 Predictive checks and prediction

7.1.4.5.1 Visual Predictive Checks (continuous)

7.1.4.5.1.1 *xxx_observations.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Needed Task
ID	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation times	-
timeAfterLastDose	Observation times after the last dose	-
y	Observation values (loq)	-
y_simBlq	Observation values (simulated blq)	
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.5.1.2 *xxx_bins.txt*

Description: bins values for the corresponding axis.

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsValues	Abscissa bins values	-
split	Name of the split the bins refer to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.5.1.3 *xxx_percentiles.txt*

Description: empirical and theoretical percentiles values (lower, median & upper) + confidence interval on theoretical percentiles (lower & upper)

Column	Description	Needed Task
bins_middles	Abscissa bin middles	-
empirical_median	Empirical median	-
empirical_lowerPercentile	Empirical lower percentile	-
empirical_upperPercentile	Empirical upper percentile	-
theoretical_median	Theoretical median	-
theoretical_median_piLower	Lower percentile of prediction interval of theoretical median	-
theoretical_median_piUpper	Upper percentile of prediction interval of theoretical median	-
theoretical_lowerPercentile	Median of the prediction interval for the lower percentile	-
theoretical_lower_piLower	Lower percentile of the prediction interval for the lower percentile	-
theoretical_lower_piUpper	Upper percentile of the prediction interval for the lower percentile	-
theoretical_upperPercentile	median of the prediction interval for the upper percentile	-

theoretical_upper_piLower	Lower percentile of the prediction interval for the upper percentile	-
theoretical_upper_piUpper	Upper percentile of the prediction interval for the upper percentile	-
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.5.1.4 **xxx_simulations.txt**

Description: simulated values. This file is not exported by default with the charts data, but it can be exported by clicking on “Export > Export VPC simulations” in the application menu. Moreover, if the option “Export VPC simulations” is enabled in the Preferences, it is exported each time the VPC is generated.

Column	Description	Needed Task
rep	Simulation replicate	-
ID	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time / timeAfterLastDose	Observation times or times after last dose	timeAfterLastDose if the corresponding option is used in the VPC
sim_y	Simulated observation values (loq)	-
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
	color	Name of the color the observation is colored with
filter	1 if the subject is filtered, 0 otherwise	-

7.1.4.5.2 Visual Predictive Checks (discrete)

7.1.4.5.2.1 *xxx_distribution.txt*

Description: discrete observation modalities theoretical distribution (among continuous time grid)

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsTimeBefore	Abscissa bins time value before this time	-
binsTimeAfter	Abscissa bins time value after this time	
propCategory_empirical	Empirical proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_median	Median of the prediction interval for the proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_piLower	Lower percentile of the prediction interval for proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_piUpper	Upper percentile of the prediction interval for proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
category	Label for modality sets	
split	Name of the split the distributions refer to	-

7.1.4.5.2.2 *xxx_xBins.txt*

Description: bins values for the x-axis.

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsValues	Abscissa bins values	-
split	Name of the split the bins refer to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.5.3 Visual Predictive Checks (event)

7.1.4.5.3.1 *xxx_curves.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Observation times	-
survivalFunction_empirical	Empirical survival of first event	-
survivalFunction_median	Survival median	
survivalFunction_pXX	Survival percentile XX	
averageEventNumber_empirical	Empirical mean number of events	-
averageEventNumber_median	Median mean number of events	
averageEventNumber_pXX	Percentile XX mean number of events	
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.5.3.2 *xxx_censored.txt*

Description: censored values

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Observation times	-
values	Survival of first event	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	-

7.1.4.5.4 BLQ Predictive Checks

7.1.4.5.4.1 *xxx_cumulatedBLQfrequencies.txt*

Description: censored simulated observations cumulated frequency

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Time	-
empiricalCumulatedFrequencies	Empirical fraction of data that is BLQ between time 0 and time t	-
median	Prediction interval median	-
piLower	Lower bound of prediction interval	-
piUpper	Upper bound of prediction interval	-
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	

7.1.4.5.5 Numerical Predictive Check

7.1.4.5.5.1 *xxx_cdf.txt*

Description: empirical and theoretical cumulative distribution function of observations

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Cdf continuous grid time	-
empiricalCdf	Empirical cdf based on observations	-
theoreticalCdf	Median of prediction interval for cdf	-
piLower	Lower percentile of prediction interval for cdf	-
piUpper	Upper percentile of prediction interval for cdf	-
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	

7.1.4.5.6 Prediction distribution (continuous)

7.1.4.5.6.1 *xxx_observations.txt*

Description: observation values

Column	Description	Needed Task
id	Subject identifier	-
OCC	Occasion value	(optional) if there is IOV in the data set
time	Observation times	-
y	Observation values (loq)	-
censored	1 if the observation is censored, 0 otherwise	-
split	Name of the split the subject occasion belongs to	
color	Name of the color the observation is colored with	
filter	1 if the subject occasion is filtered, 0 otherwise	

7.1.4.5.6.2 *xxx_percentiles.txt*

Description: theoretical percentiles computed on continuous grid

Column	Description	Needed Task
time	Continuous time grid used for simulation	-
median	Median	-
pPercentile	Percentile	-
split	Name of the split the visual guides belong to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.5.7 Prediction distribution (discrete)

7.1.4.5.7.1 *xxx_distribution.txt*

Description: discrete observation modalities theoretical distribution (among continuous time grid)

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsTimeBefore	Abscissa bins time value before this time	-
binsTimeAfter	Abscissa bins time value after this time	
propCategory_empirical	Empirical proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_median	Median of the prediction interval for the proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_piLower	Lower percentile of the prediction interval for proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
propCategory_piUpper	Upper percentile of the prediction interval for proportion of the modality set represented by the subchart	-
category	Label for modality sets	
split	Name of the split the distributions refer to	-

7.1.4.5.7.2 *xxx_xBins.txt*

Description: bins values for the x-axis.

Column	Description	Needed Task
binsValues	Abscissa bins values	-
split	Name of the split the bins refer to	If the chart is splitted

7.1.4.6 Convergence diagnosis

7.1.4.6.1 SAEM

7.1.4.6.1.1 *CvParam.txt*

Description: evolution of the parameters during SAEM iterations

Column	Description	Needed Task
iteration	Iteration number	-
convergenceIndicator	Convergence Indicator	-
phase	1 for exploratory and 2 for smoothing	
X	Parameter X	-

7.1.4.6.2 MCMC

7.1.4.6.2.1 *convergences.txt*

Description: evolution of the convergence with respect to the MCMC iterations

Column	Description	Needed Task
iteration	Iteration number	-
E_X	Conditional expectation of the parameter X	-
sd_X	Conditional standard error of the parameter X	

7.1.4.6.2.2 *bounds.txt*

Description: bounds for each parameter corresponding to the bounds on the graph. The first line corresponds to the minimum and the second one corresponds to the maximum.

Column	Description	Needed Task
--------	-------------	-------------

E_X	Conditional expectation of the parameter X	-
sd_X	Conditional standard error of the parameter X	

7.1.4.6.3 Standard errors of the estimates

7.1.4.6.3.1 *rse.txt*

Description: Standards errors for each parameter

Column	Description	Needed Task
X	parameter	-
rse_lin	Relative standard error with linearization method	-
rse_sa	Relative standard error with linearization method	

7.2 Data plots

The following pages describe plots related to the observed data:

7.2.1 Observed data

It is always good to have a look first at the observed data before running the parameter estimation. Indeed, it is very convenient to see if all the data is consistent, or if some outliers appear.

The purpose of this plot, also called a spaghetti plot, is to display the original data w.r.t. time.

In the example below, the concentration of warfarin from the warfarin data set is displayed. A subject is highlighted in yellow by hovering on the line.

One can plot the output in a log-scale to have a better evaluation of the elimination part for example as in the figure below.

The data can be displayed as dots and lines (by default), or only as dots or only as lines, as in the figure below. In addition, a trend line can be overlaid on the plot, based on mean values of the observed data pooled in bins. The user can choose arithmetic or geometric mean, and can add error bars representing either the standard deviations or standard errors. The mean and error values can be displayed as fixed labels next to the bars, or as tooltips when hovering on a bar.

Bin limits can be displayed as vertical lines, and the user can change the number of bins as well as binning criteria.

An interesting feature is the possibility to display the dosing time as on the figure below. The individual dosing time of the individual can be displayed when the user hovers an individual or always visible. Starting in version 2021R1 on, dosing times corresponding to doses with null amounts are not displayed.

The units (only in PKanalix) as well as additional descriptive statistics of the observations (both PKanalix and Monolix) can be displayed. We propose

- The total number of subjects
- The average number of doses per subject
- The total, average, minimum and maximum number of observations per individual.

In addition, if we split the graphic with a covariate, these numbers are recomputed to display the information of the group as in the following plot.

From the version 2023R1 it is now possible to display the mean curves, split by covariate, in a single plot. By switching on the "Merged splits" option, the mean curves of the two wiehgt groups, which appeared in previous versions in separate plots, are merged into a single plot.

7.2.2 Covariate viewer

7.2.2.1 Covariate viewer

It is possible to show the matrix of all the covariates as on the following figure:

It is possible to display one covariate vs another one, selecting in the display panel which covariate to look at.

Here we display the weight versus the height and show the correlation coefficient as an information:

Categorical covariates w.r.t. other categorical covariates are displayed as a histogram (stacked or grouped),

and continuous covariates w.r.t. categorical covariates are displayed as a boxplot as below ("+" are outlier points below $Q1-1.5IQR$ (interquartile range) or above $Q3+1.5IQR$):

7.2.2.2 Covariate statistics

Starting from the 2021 version, it is also possible to get the covariate statistics in a dedicated frame of the interface:

Continuous covariates

Statistics on continuous covariates distribution

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	SD
AGE	21	22	25	28	39	5
HT	176	179	181	183	191	4.26
WT	65	68	70	77	83	5.27

Categorical covariates

Categorical covariates distribution across modalities

	ref	test	RT	TR
FORM	18	18		
SEQ			18	18

All the covariates (if any) are displayed and a summary of the statistics is proposed. For continuous covariates, minimum, median and maximum values are proposed along with the first and third quartile, and the standard deviation. For categorical covariates, all the modalities are displayed along with the number of each. Note the “Copy table” button that allows to copy the table in Word and Excel. The format and the display of the table will be preserved.

7.2.3 Bivariate data viewer

In case of several continuous outputs, one can plot one type of observation w.r.t. another one as on the following figure for the warfarin data set. The direction of time is indicated by the red arrow. Linear interpolation is used for observations of different types that are not at the same time.

Labels for x and y axes correspond to the observation names in the model for data types that are mapped to an output of the model, or observation ids used in the dataset for data types not captured by the model. It is possible to choose which observation id to display on the X or Y axis in the settings panel on the right.

7.3 Plots for structural model diagnosis

List of plots to diagnose the structural and observation model:

7.3.1 Individual fits

7.3.1.1 Purpose

The figure displays the observed data for each subject, as well as two curves from simulations using the design and the covariates of each subject:

- the predicted profile given by the estimated population model (Population fits),
- the predicted profile given by the estimated individual model (Individual fits). If the EBEs and/or the conditional distribution tasks were performed, the user can choose either the conditional means or the conditional modes, estimated by MCMC, as estimators. Otherwise, approximations of the conditional means from SAEM are used.

This is a good way to see on each subject the validity of the model, and the actual fit proposed, as well as the inter-individual variability in the kinetics. It is possible to show the computed individual parameters on the figure. Moreover, it is also possible to display an individual predictive check: the median and a confidence interval for (y_{ij}) estimated with a Monte Carlo procedure.

7.3.1.2 Examples

- Individual fits and population fits

In the example below, the concentration for the theophylline data set is shown with simulations of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption and linear elimination. For each subject, the data are displayed with blue points along with the individual fit and population fit (the prediction using the estimated individual and population parameters respectively).

- Individual parameters

Information on individual parameters can be used in two ways, as shown below. By clicking on Information (marked in green on the figure) in the General panel, individual parameter values can be displayed on each individual plot. Moreover, the plots can be sorted according to the values for a given parameter, in ascending or descending order (Sorting panel marked in orange). By default, the individual plots are sorted by subject id, with the same order as in the data set.

- Individual predictive check

Individual predictive checks can be added to the plots: for each individual a prediction interval is computed based on multiple simulations with the population parameters and the design structure of this individual. The median line of the interval is also drawn. The interval allows to check whether the observed data are compatible with the population prediction, taking into account the inter-individual variability. The example below shows that the first subject in the theophylline data set show too much variability from the rest of the population to be correctly described by the population model.

- Dosing times

Dosing times can also be overlaid, which is useful to visualize the effect of doses on the prediction. As an example, the following figure shows the observations of an individual from the tobramycin data set along with the corresponding individual fit and multiple dosing times. Starting in version 2021R1 on, dosing times corresponding to doses with null amounts are not displayed.

- Special zoom

User-defined constraints for the zoom are available. They allow to zoom in according to one axis only instead of both axes. Moreover, a link between plots can be set in order to perform a linked zoom on all individual plots at once. This is shown on the figure below with observations from the theophylline example, and individual fits from a two-compartment model. It is thus possible to focus on the same time range or observation values for all individuals. In this example it is used to zoom on time on the elimination phase for all individuals, while keeping the Y axis in log scale unchanged for each plot.

- Censored data

When a data is censored, this data is different to a “classical” observation and has thus a different representation. We represent it as a bar from the censored value specified in the data set and the associated limit.

7.3.1.2.1 Settings

- *Grid arrange*. The user can define the number of subjects that are displayed, as well as the number of rows and the number of columns. Moreover, a slider is present to be able to change the subjects under consideration.
- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Information: hide/show the individual parameter values for each subject (conditional mode or conditional mean depending on the “Individual estimates” choice is the setting section “Display”).
 - Dosing times: hide/show dosing times as vertical lines for each subject.
 - Link between plots: activate the linked zoom for all subplots. The same zooming region can be applied on all individuals only on the x-axis, only on the Y-axis or on both (option “none”).
- *Display*
 - Observed data: hide/show the observed data.
 - Censored intervals [if censored data present]: hide/show the data marked as censored (BLQ), shown as a rectangle representing the censoring interval (for instance [0, LOQ]).
 - Split occasions [if IOV present]: Split the individual subplots by occasions in case of IOV.
 - Individual fits: Model prediction for each individual using the subject’s design and the individual parameters. The individual parameters can be the conditional mode or the conditional mean depending on the choice in the “Individual estimates” section.
 - Population fits [if no covariates in the model]: Model prediction for each individual using the subject’s design and the population parameters.

- Population fits (individual covariates) [if covariates present in the model]: Model prediction for each individual using the subject's design, the population parameters and the individual covariates values.
- Population fits (population covariates) [if covariates present in the model]: Model prediction for each individual using the subject's design, the population parameters and the median covariates values (median from all individuals of the data set).
- Individual estimates [if EBEs task has run]: depending on the tasks that have been calculated, choice between conditional mode (given by EBEs task), conditional mean (approximation given by the population parameter estimated task) or conditional mean (given by the conditional distribution task).
- Individual predictive check: For each individual, 500 (see "number of simulations" in the PLOTS task settings) data sets are simulated using the individual's design (dose and regressor values). The parameter values used for the simulation include the population parameter values, the individual covariate values and random effects sampled from the population distribution. The simulated data sets include residual errors. The *prediction interval* represents the interval containing 90% (see "level" setting) of the simulated data points. The *predicted median* is the median of all simulated data points. The individual predictive check allows to visualize the inter-individual variability (unexplained by covariates) and compare the population prediction to the individual observations.
- *Sorting*: Sort the subjects by ID or individual parameter values in ascending or descending order.

By default, only the observed data and the individual fits are displayed.

7.3.2 Observations vs predictions

7.3.2.1 Purpose

This figure displays observations (y_{ij}) versus the corresponding predictions (\hat{y}_{ij}) computed using either the population parameters and covariate effects but random effects set to 0, or with the individual parameters. This figure is useful to detect misspecifications in the structural model. The 90% prediction interval, which depends on the residual error model, can be overlaid. Predictions that are outside of the interval are denoted as outliers. A high proportion of outliers suggest misspecifications in the model. Moreover, the distribution of the observations should be symmetrical around the corresponding predicted values.

7.3.2.2 Population and individual predictions vs observations

The following example corresponds to the observations and predicted concentrations for the PK of [warfarin](#), modeled by a one-compartment model with a first-order absorption and a linear elimination. On the left, predictions are made using the *population* parameters while on the right they correspond

to the *individual* parameters. More points appear with the individual predictions: for each observation point, ten predictions are displayed, corresponding to ten simulated individual parameters.

7.3.2.3 Visual guides

In addition to the line $y = x$, it is possible to display the 90% prediction interval, as well as a spline interpolation.

The 90% prediction interval represents the uncertainty of predictions due to the residual error model defined in the observation model. In the figure below, the shape of this interval can be seen for the four existing residual error models (constant, proportional, combined1, combined2) when the observation model is defined with a normal distribution:

Normal distribution - $a=1, b=0.3$

The next figure corresponds to data that follow a log-normal distribution. The combination of constant error model and log-normal distribution corresponds to an exponential error model. Error models with a proportional term can cause numerical issues with the log-normal distribution for small observations because the error becomes very small as well.

Log-normal distribution - $a=1, b=0.3$

Choosing an observation model with a logit-normal distribution for the data is useful to take into account bounded data. The figure below shows the shape of the prediction intervals for the different error models associated with data that follow a logit-normal distribution in [0.1-10]:

The prediction interval for the same example as above on the PK of [warfarin](#) characterizes a residual error model that combines a constant and a proportional term:

On the figure above it can be noted that several zero observations measured at low times correspond to nonzero predictions that fall outside the 90% prediction interval, and thus cannot be explained by the residual error. This could be explained by a delay between the administration and absorption of warfarin, therefore a model with a delayed absorption might fit better the data.

7.3.2.4 Outliers proportion

The outliers proportion can be displayed: it is the proportion of residuals outside the 90% prediction interval.

7.3.2.5 Individual estimates

As for all diagnosis plots based on individual parameters, it is possible to choose the individual estimates that are used to compute the plot of observations vs individual predictions, among the different estimates computed during the individual parameter estimation: conditional modes (EBEs) or means of the conditional distributions, or simulated individual parameters drawn from the conditional distributions (by default). In the latter case, each observation is associated with a set of individual predictions derived from a set of individual parameters simulated from the same individual conditional distribution. On the two figures below, one can compare the plot based on simulated parameters from the conditional distribution (top) and the same plot based on conditional modes (bottom).

7.3.2.6 Highlight

As shown on the figures below, hovering on a point of observed data reveals the subject id and time corresponding to this point. All the points corresponding to this subject are highlighted in yellow. On the left, there are several predictions per observation, and the ten points corresponding to the hovered observation are indicated with a bigger diameter. On the right, there is only one prediction per observation, and all points corresponding to the same individual are linked with segments to visualize the time chronology.

7.3.2.7 Log scale

A log scale is useful to focus on low observation values. It can be set for each axis separately or both together.

A second example below displays the predicted concentrations of [remifentanyl](#), modeled by a two-compartment model with a linear elimination. In this example, the log-log scale reveals a clear misspecification of the model: the small observations are under-predicted. These observations correspond to high times: this means that the elimination is not properly captured by the two-compartment model. A three-compartment model might give better results.

that here 10 predictions are displayed for each observation, corresponding to different simulated parameters drawn from the conditional distribution during the individual parameter estimation task.

7.3.2.8 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for both plots.
 - Outliers proportion: display/hide the proportion of points outside the 90% prediction interval.
- *Subplots*
 - Population prediction: add/remove the figure with the comparison between the population predictions and the observations.
 - Individual prediction: add/remove the figure with the comparison between the individual predictions and the observations.
- *Display*
 - Observed data: Add/remove the points corresponding to pairs of observations and predictions.
 - BLQ data : show and put in a different color the data that are BLQ (Below the Limit of Quantification)
 - Individual estimates: select the estimates condition mean or mode, or simulated estimates from the conditional distribution (by default).
 - Visual cues: add/remove visual guidelines such as the line $y = x$, a spline interpolation, and the 90% prediction interval indicated with dotted lines.

By default, only the individual predictions are displayed.

7.3.3 Scatter plot of residuals

7.3.3.1 Purpose

These plots display the PWRES (population weighted residuals), the IWRES (individual weighted residuals), and the NPDEs (normalized prediction distribution errors) as scatter plots with respect to the time or the prediction.

The PWRES and NPDEs are computed using the population parameters and the IWRES are computed using the individual parameters. For discrete outputs, only NPDEs are used.

These plots are useful to detect misspecifications in the structural and residual error models: if the model is true, residuals should be randomly scattered around the horizontal zero-line.

7.3.3.2 Definition

7.3.3.2.1 Population Weighted Residuals PWRES_{ij}

PWRES_{ij} are defined as the normalized difference between the observations and their expected mean. Let $\mathbf{y}_i = (y_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ be the vector of observations for subject i . The mean of \mathbf{y}_i is the vector $\mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}_i) = (\mathbb{E}(f(t_{ij}; \psi_i)), 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$. Let \mathbf{V}_i be the $n_j \times n_j$ variance-covariance matrix of \mathbf{y}_i . Then, the i -th vector of the population weighed residuals $\text{PWRES}_i = \{\text{PWRES}_{ij}, 1 \leq j \leq n_i\}$ is defined by

$$\text{PWRES}_i = \mathbf{V}_i^{-1/2}(\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}_i))$$

The population residuals $(\mathbf{y}_i - \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}_i))$ are correlated within each individual. The population weighted residuals PWRES standardize and decorrelate the population residuals using the model-predicted variance-covariance matrix of observations \mathbf{V}_i .

$\mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}_i)$ and \mathbf{V}_i are not known in practice but are estimated empirically by Monte-Carlo simulation without any approximation of the model. In the formula above, \mathbf{y}_i represents the observations from the dataset. $\mathbb{E}(\mathbf{y}_i)$ is calculated as the mean of simulated observations using individual parameters sampled from the population distribution to obtain the model prediction plus a sample from the residual error model. The number of simulated observations depends on the Plot task setting "Number of simulations". \mathbf{V}_i is calculated on the same simulated observations.

When the PWRES are plotted w.r.t the model prediction, the population prediction popPred (i.e with random effects eta equal to zero but keeping the covariate effects) are used on the x-axis.

7.3.3.2.2 Individual weighted residuals IWRES_{ij}

IWRES_{ij} are estimates of the standardized residual (ϵ_{ij}) based on individual predictions, with g the function defining the residual error model:

$$\text{IWRES}_{ij} = \frac{y_{ij} - f(t_{ij}; \hat{\psi}_i)}{g(t_{ij}; \hat{\psi}_i)}$$

If the residual errors are assumed to be correlated, the individual weighted residuals can be decorrelated by multiplying each individual vector $\text{IWRES}_i = (\text{IWRES}_{ij}; 1 \leq j \leq n_i)$ by $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i^{-1/2}$, where $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_i$ is the estimated correlation matrix of the vector of residuals ($\epsilon_{ij}; 1 \leq j \leq n_i$).

When the IWRES are plotted w.r.t the model prediction, the individual prediction using the conditional mode (EBEs), conditional mean or samples from the conditional distribution is used, depending on the choice of the “Individual estimates” in the settings panel on the right.

7.3.3.2.3 Normalized prediction distribution errors NPDE_{ij}

NPDE_{ij} are a nonparametric version of PWRES_{ij} based on a rank statistic. For any (i,j), let $\mathbf{F}_{ij} = \mathbf{F}_{\text{PWRES}_{ij}}(\text{PWRES}_{ij})$ where $\mathbf{F}_{\text{PWRES}_{ij}}$ is the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of PWRES_{ij}. NPDEs are then obtained from \mathbf{F}_{ij} by applying the inverse of the standard normal cdf Φ .

In practice, one simulates a large number K of simulated data set $y^{(k)}$ using the model, and estimate \mathbf{F}_{ij} as the fraction of simulated data below the original data, i.e:

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{ij} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{1}_{y_{ij}^{(k)} \leq y_{ij}^{\text{obs}}}$$

By definition, the distribution of \mathbf{F}_{ij} is uniform on [0,1], we thus rather use $\Phi^{-1}(\mathbf{F}_{ij})$, which follows a standard normal distribution (with Φ the cdf of the standard normal distribution). NPDEs are defined as an empirical estimation of $\Phi^{-1}(\mathbf{F}_{ij})$, i.e. $\text{NPDE}_{ij} = \Phi^{-1}(\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{ij})$.

When the NPDE are plotted w.r.t the model prediction, the population prediction popPred (i.e with random effects eta equal to zero but keeping the covariate effects) are used on the x-axis.

Below is a correspondence table of the Nonmem and Monolix terms used for residuals:

Nonmem	Monolix	Definition	Output files and plots
IWRES	indWRes	$\frac{y_{ij} - f(\psi_i^{EBEs}, t_{ij})}{g}$ with y_{ij} the observations, $f(\psi_i^{EBEs}, t_{ij})$ the individual prediction using the EBEs and g the residual error function	- File: predictions.txt - Plot: Scatter and distribution of the residuals (individual prediction)
WRES and CWRES	<i>Not applicable</i>	$\frac{y_{ij} - f(\psi_{pop}, t_{ij})}{\sqrt{\text{var}(y_{ij})}}$ with y_{ij} the observations, $f(\psi_{pop}, t_{ij})$ the population predictions (random effects set to 0) and $\text{var}(y_{ij})$ model-predicted var-covariance matrix of observations obtained from FO (WRES) or FOCE (CWRES) approximation	<i>Not applicable</i>
EPRED	pwRes	$\frac{y_{ij} - \frac{1}{k} \sum y_{sim}^k}{\sqrt{\text{var}(y_{ij})}}$ with y_{ij} the observations, $\frac{1}{k} \sum y_{sim}^k$ the average of simulated observations (including residual error) using sampled individual parameters, and $\text{var}(y_{ij})$ model-predicted var-covariance matrix calculated on the simulations	- File: charts data - Plot: Scatter and distribution of the residuals (population prediction)

7.3.3.2.4 Count and categorical data

For each data point y_{ij} :

- the model is used to simulate m simulated data points $y_{sim_ij_m}$
- the values of the true observation y_{ij} and of the simulated data $y_{sim_ij_m}$ are slightly perturbed (using a uniform distribution) to avoid that y_{ij} has exactly the same value as the simulated values $y_{sim_ij_m}$
- the rank of y_{ij} among the m simulated values $y_{sim_ij_m}$ is calculated

The ranks of all data points are expected to be uniformly distributed in $[0, m]$. To obtain a gaussian distribution, we divide the ranks by m and then use the quantile function of a gaussian.

Are CWRES available in Monolix? No, PWRES are given instead. They are defined with the same formula but are obtained with simulations rather than FOCE approximation, so without any approximation of the model. The PWRES in Monolix are equivalent to the EWRES in Nonmem.

:question_mark:

7.3.3.3 Examples

In the following example, the parameters of a two-compartment model with iv unfusion and linear elimination are estimated on the [remifentanil data set](#). One can see the PWRES, the IWRES and the NPDE w.r.t. the time (on top), and the prediction (at the bottom).

Since the points are clearly scattered unevenly around the horizontal zero-line, these plots suggest a misspecification of the structural model.

The corresponding distributions can be seen on this [page](#).

It is possible to select some of the subplots to focus on, with the panel Subplots in Settings:

7.3.3.4 Predefined displays

A number of element can be overlaid or hidden from the plots in the panel Display. Only the horizontal zero-line, representing the theoretical mean, is always displayed. Two predefined displays with selections of displayed elements are available: the first one called "Scatter" hides all elements except the points for residuals, while the second called "VPC" displays instead empirical and predicted percentiles for the residuals as lines, as well as prediction intervals as colored areas. This figure is detailed below.

DISPLAY

SCATTER VPC

Residuals

Empirical percentiles

Predicted percentiles

Prediction interval

Level

90

Higher percentile

90

Outliers

Dots

Areas

Individual estimates

Conditional distribution

Conditional mode (EBEs)

Conditional mean

Calculations

Linear interpolation

Visual cues

Spline

DISPLAY

SCATTER VPC

Residuals

Empirical percentiles

Predicted percentiles

Prediction interval

Level

90

Higher percentile

90

Outliers

Dots

Areas

Individual estimates

Conditional distribution

Conditional mode (EBEs)

Conditional mean

Calculations

Linear interpolation

Visual cues

Spline

7.3.3.5 Predictive checks

The predefined display “VPC” displays prediction intervals for the median, 10th and 90th percentiles, obtained with simulations of the residuals, as well as the empirical percentiles to compare the behavior of the model to the data. Residual points are hidden, but the trend is represented with a spline interpolation.

Misspecification in the structural model, the error model, and the covariate model can be detected by discrepancies between the observed percentiles and their prediction intervals, as can be seen for example on the plots of IWRES vs time and NPDE vs time below, with log-scale on the x-axis. Population residuals greatly depart from the data at all time points, while individual residuals show better predictions for low times only.

Outliers (empirical percentiles outside the prediction intervals) can be marked with red points or red areas:

7.3.3.6 Comparing PWRES and NPDEs

NPDEs are quite similar to PWRES, but are simulation-based, and therefore account for the heterogeneity in study design by comparing the observations with their own distribution. NPDEs are thus displayed by default rather than PWRES.

7.3.3.7 Comparing IWRES and NPDEs

The IWRES are based on individual predictions, therefore the values on the X axis with respect to predictions are not the same as for NPDEs and PWRES, as can be seen on the plots below. If the tasks EBEs and Conditional distribution have been run, several different individual estimates are available to be used for the individual predictions. The next section shows how to choose the estimates.

7.3.3.8 Preventing shrinkage in IWRES

The individual estimates used to compute the IWRES can be chosen in the Display panel:

- Individual estimates
- Conditional distribution
 - Conditional mode (EBEs)
 - Conditional mean

By default, the individual estimates are drawn from the conditional distributions rather than coming from usual estimators such as conditional modes (EBEs) or conditional means. This choice is recommended in order to prevent shrinkage, a phenomenon that occurs when the individual data are not sufficiently informative with respect to one or more parameters. If overfitting occurs, IWRES computed from biased estimators might thus shrink toward 0.

7.3.3.9 Highlight

Hovering on a point highlights all the points from the same individual in yellow on all plots, and reveals the corresponding subject id and time. If the individual estimates selected in Display are the simulated condition distribution, each observation corresponds to a set of IWRES computed from a set of simulated individual parameters. When the observation is hovered, the points from this set are indicated with a bigger diameter.

If the individual estimates selected in Display are condition modes (EBEs) or conditional means, there is only one residual per observation, and all points corresponding to the same individual are linked with segments to visualize the time chronology.

7.3.3.10 Binning

As for VPC, data binning used to compute percentiles can be changed. Several strategies exist to segment the data: equal-width binning, equal-size binning, and a least-squares criterion. The number of bins can also be either set by the user, or automatically selected to obtain a good trade off.

On the three figures below where NPDEs are displayed with respect to log-scaled time, 5 bins are selected with equal width on the left, equal size in the center, and the least-squares criteria on the right. Observations are overlaid in light purple to visualize the data density in each bin. Equal width in particular shows low density for some bins, and result in a less informative plot for low times where data density is high.

On the figure below, the number of bins for least-squares criteria is automatically set, allowing a more precise display.

7.3.3.11 Censored data

The residuals for [censored data](#) appear in a different color. They are by default based on simulated observations that take into account the censoring interval.

An option available in the panel “Display” can be used to select the method of calculation for the residuals corresponding to censored data: either based on simulated observations (by default), or based on LOQ (values from the observation column in the dataset).

- Use censored data
- Simulated observations
- LOQ

7.3.3.12 Discrete data

For categorical or count data, only NPDEs are used. Here again, NPDEs correspond to the rank of each observation among a set of simulations based on the model. However, to prevent problems with discrete values, both observations and simulations are slightly perturbed with a uniform distribution before computing the ranks.

7.3.3.13 Settings

- *Subplots*
 - *Residuals*
 - Population residuals: Add/remove scatterplots for PWRES. Hidden by default.
 - Individual residuals: Add/remove scatterplots for IWRES, using the individual parameter estimated using the conditional mode or the conditional mean. By default, individual parameters come from the conditional mode estimation.
 - NPDE: Add/remove scatterplots for NPDE.
 - *X-axis*
 - time: Add/remove the scatterplots w.r.t. the time.
 - prediction: Add/remove the scatterplots w.r.t. the prediction.
- *Display*
 - *Presets*: apply the preselections of elements for scatter plots or VPC
 - *Residuals*: Add/remove observed data.
 - *Censored data*: Add/remove BLQ data (with a different color) if present.
 - *Empirical percentiles*: Add/remove empirical percentiles for the 10%, 50% and 90% quantiles.
 - *Predicted percentiles*: Add/remove theoretical percentiles for the 10% and 90% quantiles.
 - *Prediction interval*: Add/remove prediction intervals given by the model for the 10% and 90% quantiles (in blue) and the 50% quantile (in pink), with user-defined level (by default, 90).
 - *Outliers*: Add/remove dots or areas to mark outliers.
 - *Individual estimates*: Choose the individual estimates among conditional modes (EBEs), conditional means (computed with SAEM), or simulated parameters from the conditional distributions.
 - *Calculations – linear interpolation*: Choose the display for prediction intervals: by default linear interpolation is used, otherwise the display is piecewise.
 - *Calculations – Use censored data*: Choose the display for censored data: by default simulated BLQ observations are used, otherwise the LOQ from the observation column in the data set can be used.
 - *Visual cues*: Add/remove spline interpolation.
 - *Bins*
 - Bin values: Add/remove vertical lines on the scatterplots to indicate the bins.

- Binning criteria: Choose the binning criteria among equal width (default), equal size or least-squares.
- Number of bins: Choose a fixed number of bins or a range, with the range for the number of data points per bin.

7.3.4 Distribution of residuals

7.3.4.1 Purpose

These plots display the empirical distributions of the residuals: the PWRES (population weighted residuals), the IWRES (individual weighted residuals), and the NPDEs (normalized prediction distribution errors) for continuous outputs, together with the standard Gaussian probability density function and cumulative distribution function.

If the model is true, the PWRES, IWRES and NPDEs should behave as independent standardized normal random variables. These plots are thus useful to detect misspecifications in the structural and residual error models.

7.3.4.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a two-compartment model with iv unfusion and linear elimination are estimated on the [remifentanyl data set](#).

Below, one can see on top the comparison between the empirical and theoretical probability density function (PDF) of the PWRES, IWRES and NPDE, and at the bottom the comparison between the empirical and theoretical cumulative distribution function (CDF). The theoretical distribution follows a standard normal distribution.

The corresponding scatter plots can be seen on this page.

7.3.4.3 Settings

By default, all the residuals and all the plots are displayed.

- *Subplots*
 - *Residuals*: choose the plots to display according to residuals
 - Population residuals: PWRES
 - Individual residuals: IWRES, using the individual parameter estimated using the conditional distribution, the conditional mode, or the conditional mean.
 - NPDE
 - *X-axis*
 - PDF: Probability density function of residuals (standard normal distribution) and empirical distribution as histograms.
 - CDF: Theoretical and empirical cumulative distribution functions.
- *Display*
 - Individual estimates: choose the estimator for individual parameters as parameters drawn from the conditional distributions. or the modes or means of the conditional posterior distributions.

7.4 Plots for individual model diagnosis

The following pages contain documentation for plots related to the individual model:

7.4.1 Distribution of individual parameters

7.4.1.1 Purpose

This figure can be used to compare:

- the empirical distribution of the individual parameters, estimated with the conditional means, the conditional modes, or simulated from the conditional distributions,
- the theoretical distribution defined in the statistical model, with the estimated population parameter.

Further analysis such as stratification by covariate or shrinkage assessment can be performed and will be detailed below.

7.4.1.2 PDF and CDF

In the `warfarinPK_project`, several parameters are estimated. It is possible to display the theoretical distribution and the histogram of the empirical distribution as proposed below.

The distributions are represented as histograms for the probability density function (PDF). Hovering on the histogram also reveals the density value of each bin as shown on the figure below

Notice that the theoretical pdf is a pure log-normal distribution. However, in case of covariate use with the parameters, it is not a pure log-normal but rather a combinaison of log-normal distribution. If for

example, on set the SEX covariate on the parameter V, a parameter beta_V_SEX_1 is created and the individual parameter distribution becomes as the following.

Cumulative distribution functions (CDF) is proposed too.

Again, overlaying the plots display the information concerning the parameter value and its empirical and theoretical cdf.

7.4.1.3 Getting away with shrinkage using simulated individual parameters

If the data does not contain enough information to correctly estimate some individual parameters, the individual estimates coming from the means or the modes of the individual conditional distributions shrink towards the same population value (respectively the mean or the mode of the population distribution of the parameter), a phenomenon known as shrinkage. For a parameter ψ_i that is a function of a random effect η_i , this phenomenon can be quantified by defining the η -shrinkage as:

$$\eta\text{-shrinkage} = 1 - \frac{sd(\hat{\eta}_i)}{\hat{\omega}}$$

where $sd(\hat{\eta}_i)$ is the empirical standard deviation of the estimated random effects $\hat{\eta}_i$. The $\hat{\eta}_i$ can be calculated from the EBEs, the conditional mean or the samples from the conditional distribution. Typically, the shrinkage is reported using the EBEs.

i In Monolix version 2023 and earlier, shrinkage was defined based on the variance as

$$\eta\text{-shrinkage} = 1 - \frac{Var(\hat{\eta}_i)}{\hat{\omega}^2}.$$

It is possible to display the shrinkage value on top of the histograms, as seen below for the conditional mode (EBEs):

Selecting the “Conditional distribution” option instead for the individual estimates uses individual parameters drawn from the conditional distribution, simulated using MCMC sampling. This method is recommended as it results in unbiased estimators that are not affected by possible shrinkage, and leads to more reliable results. For more details see the page [Understanding shrinkage and how to circumvent it](#).

In the same example, using the conditional distribution instead of the conditional mode reduces shrinkage, as can be seen below.

The following table shows the shrinkage calculation (in %) for all methods. The shrinkage is large for Tlag and ka when using the EBEs, which means that the individual data is not reach enough to reliable estimate the EBEs for Tlag and ka. The close to zero shrinkage value when using the samples from the conditional distribution shows that the samples from the conditional distribution are well spread over the population distribution, as expected.

Method\Parameters	Tlag	ka	V	CI
Conditional mean	43.45	42.3	3.18	0.15
Conditional mode (EBEs)	46.07	47.11	4.14	0.065
Conditional distribution	-0.317	1.57	-0.26	162

7.4.1.4 Example of stratification

It is possible to stratify the population by some covariate values and obtain the distributions of the individual parameters in each group. This can be useful to check covariate effect, in particular when the distribution of a parameter exhibits two or more peaks for the whole population. On the following example, the distribution of the parameter k from the same example as above has been split for two

groups of individuals according to the value of the continuous covariate AGE, allowing to visualize two clearly different distributions.

7.4.1.5 Settings

- *General*: add/remove the legend, the grid, and the shrinkage in %.
- *Display*
 - Empirical: add/remove histogram of empirical distribution.
 - Theoretical: add/remove curve of theoretical distribution.
 - Distribution function: The user can choose to display either the probability density function (PDF) as histogram or the cumulative distribution function (CDF).
 - Individual estimates: The user can define which estimator is used for the definition of the individual parameters.

Simulated individual parameters are used by default, otherwise the conditional mode is the default estimation if it has been computed with the "Individual parameters estimation" task.

7.4.2 Distribution of standardized random effects

7.4.2.1 Purpose

This plot displays the distribution of the standardized random effects with boxplots or with histograms. Since random effects should follow normal probability laws, it is useful to compare the distributions to standard Gaussian distributions.

7.4.2.2 Example

In the following example, one can see the distributions of two parameters of a two-compartment bolus model with linear elimination, estimated on the [tobramycin example](#). On the left, the distributions are represented as boxplots, in the middle as histograms for the probability density function (PDF), and on the right as cumulative distribution functions (CDF). In each case, marks to compare the results to standard Gaussian distributions are overlaid: dotted horizontal lines indicate the interquartile interval of a standard Gaussian distribution for the boxplots, and black curves represent the PDF and CDF of a standard Gaussian distribution.

In boxplots, the dashed line represents the median, the blue box represents the 25th and 75th percentiles (Q1 and Q3), and the whiskers extend to the most extreme data points, outliers excluded. Outliers are the points larger than $Q1 + w(Q3 - Q1)$ or smaller than $Q1 - w(Q3 - Q1)$ with $w=1.5$. Outliers are shown with red crosses.

On the figure below, the individuals have been split into two groups according to the value of the continuous covariate CLCR. One can notice differences on the boxplots for the distributions of random effects between both groups, in particular for the parameter k.

7.4.2.3 Shrinkage

When there is not enough data to well-estimate individual parameters, individual estimates based on the conditional mean or mode (rather than the entire conditional distribution) have a tendency to

shrink towards the population parameter estimate. For the distribution of the standardized random effects, shrinkage leads to bias showing less than the true variation if the individual estimates are shown using the conditional mean or conditional mode rather than the conditional distribution in this case. The shrinkage can be displayed in the plot by toggling “information” in general settings. For more details see the page Understanding shrinkage and how to circumvent it.

7.4.2.4 Settings

- *General*: add/remove the grid and the shrinkage in %.
- *Display*
 - *Distribution function*. The user can choose which type of plot is used to represent the distributions of the random effects: boxplots, pdf (probability density function) or cdf (cumulative distribution function).
 - *Individual estimates*. The user can define which estimator is used for the definition of the individual parameters and thus for the random effects (conditional mean, conditional mode, or conditional distribution)
 - *Visual cues*: If boxplot has been selected, the user can choose to add or hide dotted lines to mark the median or quartiles of a standard Gaussian distribution.

By default, the distributions of simulated random effects are displayed as boxplots.

7.4.2.5 Standardized random effects in case of IOV

Starting from the 2019 version, in case of IOV and if the conditional distribution is computed, we propose to display the standardized random effect by level of variability. In the presented example, we put IOV on both k_a and V parameters. Thus, in the plot, we proposed to display the several levels of variability for all the parameters. We can then display the standardized random effects for

- the ID level,
- the OCC level (where only the parameters with variability on this level are displayed),
- the ID+OCC level corresponding to the addition of the levels.

7.4.3 Correlation of random effects

7.4.3.1 Purpose

This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of random effects. It allows to identify correlations between random effects, which can then be introduced in the models for the probability distributions for the individual parameters.

7.4.3.2 Example

In the following example, one can see pairs of random effects estimated for all parameters of a one-compartment model with delayed first-order absorption and linear elimination estimated on the PK of [warfarin data set](#). The estimators for random effects have been simulated from conditional distributions of individual random effects.

7.4.3.2.1 Visual guidelines

In addition to regression lines, Pearson correlation coefficients can be added to see the correlation between random effects, as well as spline interpolations.

7.4.3.2.2 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of random effects, whose pairs of correlations are then displayed, as shown below.

7.4.3.2.3 Highlight

Similarly to other plots, hovering on a point provides information on the corresponding subject id, and highlights other points corresponding to the same individual, if multiple individual parameters have been simulated by sampling the conditional distribution.

On the figure below, we can see the same plot with only one parameter value per individual (left) or multiple values (right). Notice that the correlation coefficient is more reliable when multiple parameters are available, as they take into account the uncertainty of individual parameters.

7.4.3.2.4 Stratification: coloring and filtering

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be colored (left) or filtered (right), allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the filtering.

7.4.3.3 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - Correlation: display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
- *Display*

- *Selection.* The user can select some of the parameters to display only the corresponding scatter plots. A simple click selects one parameter, whereas multiple clicks while holding the Ctrl key selects a set of parameters.
- *Individual estimates.* The user can define which estimates are used for the definition of the individual parameters and thus for the random effects (conditional mean, conditional mode, simulated parameters)
- *Visual cues.* Add/remove the regression line or the spline interpolation.

By default, all scatter plots are proposed with simulated individual parameters.

7.4.3.3.1 Display in case of correlation in the statistical model

Starting from the 2019 version, when there is correlation in the statistical model, we propose to see the decorrelated random effects in order to see if some correlation remains. In that case, there is an option in the display to switch between the random effects and the decorrelated random effects as can be seen on the following figure. The methodology behind the calculation can be found here. The formula to calculate the decorrelated random effects $\hat{\eta}_i$ from the random effects η_i and the estimated variance-covariance of the random effects Ω is:

$$\hat{\eta}_i = \Omega^{-1/2} \times \eta_i$$

7.4.3.3.2 Display in case of IOV

Starting from the 2019 version, in case of IOV and if the conditional distribution is computed, we propose to display the by level of variability as can be seen in the following figure.

We can then display the correlation of the random effects for

- the ID level,
- the OCC level (where only the parameters with variability on this level are displayed)
- the ID+OCC level corresponding to the addition of the levels

Notice that at least 2 parameters should have variability on the occasion level to have the correlation on the several level displayed.

7.4.4 Individual parameters vs covariates

7.4.4.1 Purpose

The figure displays the estimators of the individual parameters, and those for random effects, as a function of the covariates. It allows to identify correlation effects between the individual parameters and the covariates.

The estimators can be:

- simulated parameters: individual parameters and individual random effects are sampled from the distributions $p(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ and $p(\eta_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$. These estimators lead to more reliable results, especially when individual data are sparse and the distributions of conditional modes and means of individual parameters are affected by shrinkage.
- the conditional means $E(\psi_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ for parameters ψ_i and $E(\eta_i | y_i; \hat{\theta})$ for random effects η_i ,
- the conditional modes of the same distributions.

On the boxplots for categorical covariates, red "+" are outlier points below $Q1-1.5*IQR$ (interquartile range) or above $Q3+1.5*IQR$.

7.4.4.2 Identifying correlation effects

In the example below, we can see the parameters of a one-compartment PK model with delayed first-order absorption and linear elimination estimated on the [warfarin data set](#). The simulated individual parameters of the 4 parameters of the PK model are displayed with respect to the covariates: the weight wt, a transformed version of the weight ($\ln70 = \log(wt/70)$) and the sex category.

7.4.4.2.1 Visual guidelines

In order to help identifying correlations, regression lines, spline interpolations and Pearson correlation coefficients can be overlaid on the plots for continuous covariates. Here we can see a strong correlation between the parameter V and the covariate $lw70$.

7.4.4.2.2 Highlight

Hovering on a point reveals the corresponding individual and, if multiple individual parameters have been simulated from the conditional distribution for each individual, highlights all the points from the same individual. This is useful to identify possible outliers and subsequently check their behavior in the observed data.

7.4.4.2.3 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of covariates or parameters, as shown below. This is useful when there are many parameters or covariates. In particular, it is frequent to introduce transformed covariates, the selection allows to focus on the transformed versions rather than the original.

7.4.4.3 Comparing individual parameters and random effects

By default, the values on the Y-axis are computed with the individual parameters. One can choose to display the random effects instead. If some individual parameters are already modelled with covariates, this is taken into account by the random effects values, thus allowing to focus on remaining correlations.

The figures below show the diagnosis plots with individual parameters or random effects when the models for parameters V includes the covariate lw70. On the top, one can identify the correlations between individual parameters and covariates: the log-volume ($\log(V)$) clearly increases with the log-transformed weight, as well with sex. On the other hand, the random effects on the bottom allow to focus on correlations that are not yet taken into account in the covariate model. Because the model already includes a linear relationship between the log-volume and the log-transformed weight, shows no correlation with lw70. There is no correlation either between η_V and sex, because of an existing correlation between lw70 and sex.

7.4.4.3.1 Stratification

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be split, colored or filtered, allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the split or filtering.

7.4.4.4 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - Correlation: display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
- *Display*
 - *Y-axis*. The user can choose to see either the individual parameters or the random effects.
 - *Selection*. The user can select some of the parameters or covariates to display only the corresponding plots. A simple click selects one parameter (or covariate), whereas multiple clicks while holding the Ctrl key selects a set of parameters.
 - *Individual estimates*. The user can define which estimators are used for the definition of the individual parameters and thus for the random effects (conditional mean, conditional mode, simulated parameters)
 - *Visual cues*. Add/remove a regression line or a spline interpolation.

By default, all plots are proposed with simulated individual parameters.

7.5 Predictive checks

List of predictive checks available in Monolix:

7.5.1 Visual predictive check

7.5.1.1 Purpose

The VPC (Visual Predictive Check) offers an intuitive assessment of misspecification in structural, variability, and covariate models. The principle is to assess graphically whether simulations from a model of interest are able to reproduce both the central trend and variability in the observed data, when plotted *versus* an independent variable (typically time). It summarizes in the same graphic the structural and statistical models by computing several quantiles of the empirical distribution of the data after having regrouped them into bins over successive intervals.

More precisely, the goal is to compare the two following elements:

- Empirical percentiles: percentiles of the observed data, calculated either for each unique value of time, or pooled by adjacent time intervals (bins). By default, the 10th, 50th and 90th percentiles are displayed as green lines. These quantiles summarize the distribution of the observations.
- Theoretical percentiles: percentiles of simulated data are computed from multiple Monte Carlo simulations with the model of interest and the design structure of the original dataset (i.e., dosing, timing, and number of samples). By default 500 simulations are performed. For each simulation, the same percentiles are computed across the same bins as for empirical percentiles.

Prediction intervals for each percentile are then estimated across all simulated data and displayed as colored areas (pink for the 50th percentile, blue for the 10th and 90th percentiles). By default, prediction intervals are computed with a level of 90%.

If the model is correct, the observed percentiles should be close to the predicted percentiles and remain within the corresponding prediction intervals.

7.5.1.2 Examples

VPCs vary slightly for different types of data. For joint models for multivariate outcomes, VPCs are available for each outcome.

7.5.1.2.1 Continuous outcomes

warfarinPK_project (data = 'warfarin_data.txt', model = 'lib:oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl.txt')

In the following example, the parameters of a one-compartment model with delayed first-order absorption and linear elimination are estimated on the [warfarin dataset](#). A constant residual error model was used. The figure presents the VPC with the prediction intervals for the 10th, 50th and 90th percentiles. Outliers are highlighted with red dots and areas. Here the three quantiles appear closer together than the model would suggest, therefore the VPC suggests that a proportional component should be added to the error model.

Since version 2024, there are options for displaying the x-axis using either nominal time, time after the last dose or regressors, if they are available in the dataset and appropriately tagged. You can choose these options within the x-axis settings of the plot settings.

For joint models for continuous PK and time-to-event data, VPCs are available for each type of data. However it is important to note that dropout events are not taken into account in the VPC corresponding to the continuous data. Therefore, in the case of non-random dropout events in the dataset, this can result in discrepancies between observed and simulated data and thus hamper the diagnosis value of the VPC. Correcting this bias would require to include the simulated dropout in VPC, as well as adapt the design structure to compensate observed dropouts, an approach that is problematic when the design structure is complex. More details on this approach are given here.

7.5.1.2.2 Non-continuous outcomes: count data and categorical data

VPCs for count data and categorical data compare the observed and predicted frequencies of the categorized data over time. The predicted frequency is associated with a blue prediction interval.

The following figure shows the VPC for a project with a continuous time Markov chain model and time varying transition rates.

- **markov3b_project** (data = 'markov3b_data.txt', model = 'markov3b_model.txt')

In addition to the categorization over time (binning on X), count data are also binned into groups of count values on the VPC (binning on Y). The number of bins and binning method can be set in Settings under “Y Bins”.

As an example, the VPC below corresponds to a project where a Poisson model is used for fitting the data. Observations are binned in 3 groups on the Y axis and 20 bins on the X axis.

- **count1a_project** (data = 'count1_data.txt', model = 'count_library/poisson_mlxt.txt')

7.5.1.2.3 Time-to-event data

In case of time-to-event data, two visual predictive checks are available, survival function based on the Kaplan-Meier plot for exactly observed events and the Turnbull estimator for the interval censored data, and the mean number of events per individual using Turnbull estimation (see here and here for reference papers).

Details on the VPC for TTE generation in Monolix are presented [here](#).

The example below shows these two figures, computed with a model for the survival of patients with advanced lung cancer from the Veterans' Administration Lung Cancer study. Censored data has been selected and displayed on the Kaplan-Meier plot. Note that censored data also cause an over prediction bias in the VPC based on the mean number of events per individual, because censored individuals contribute to the prediction interval but not to the empirical curve.

Sometimes numerical errors can appear in the simulations used for the TTE VPC. For example, when simulating a joint model with tumor growth and survival over a long time scale, the simulated hazard for death can become too high for some individuals at high times. In Monolix2021R1, the appearance of NaNs in the VPC simulations does not stop the generation of the VPC. The simulated individuals with NaNs in their simulations are not used in the prediction interval, and the percentage of simulated individuals with NaNs is then displayed in the Warnings.

7.5.1.3 Details

7.5.1.3.1 Binning criteria

Correctly defining the intervals (or bins) into which the data are grouped is crucial to construct a VPC that avoids distortion between the original and approximated distributions. Several strategies exist to segment the data: equal-width binning, equal-size binning, and a least-squares criterion. The number of bins can also be either set by the user, or automatically selected to obtain a good tradeoff. Indeed, a small number of bins leads to a poor approximation but a good estimation of the data's distribution, while a large number of bins leads to a good approximation but poor estimation.

As an example, the VPCs below are computed on the PK model built for [remifentanyl](#) pharmacokinetics, a dataset that involves a large variability in doses. The bins are delimited with vertical lines. The first VPC on the left is computed with 5 bins, the number automatically selected for this dataset. On the other hand, the second VPC on the right is computed with 15 bins. We notice that in this case the heterogeneity of the data results in a poor estimation of the data's distribution. To keep a good estimation, a small number of bins is required, but the approximation then prevents from visualizing the kinetics in details. The absorption phase is for example not visible.

7.5.1.3.2 Corrected predictions

As shown above, VPCs can be misleading if applied to data that include a large variability in dose and/or influential covariates, or that follow adaptive designs such as dose adjustments. The prediction-corrected VPC (pcVPC), with prediction correction, was developed to maintain the diagnosis value of a VPC in these cases. In each bin, the observed and simulated data are normalized based on the typical population prediction for the median time in the bin. Formulae are applied as in the publication from Bergstrand et al. In the simple case of normally distributed observations and a zero lower bound for observations, we get:

$$pcY_{ij} = Y_{ij} \frac{\tilde{PRED}_{bin}}{PRED_{ij}}$$

where

- Y_{ij} : observation or prediction for the i th individual and j th time point,
- pcY_{ij} : prediction-corrected observation or prediction,
- $PRED_{ij}$: typical population prediction for the i th individual and j th time point
- \tilde{PRED}_{bin} : median of typical population predictions for the specific bin of independent variables.

This removes the variability coming from binning across independent variables.

The example below shows the pcVPC computed on the PK model built for [remifentanyl](#) pharmacokinetics with 15 bins: the figure now gives a good estimation of the data's distribution, including the absorption phase.

7.5.1.3.3 Stratification

When possible, another useful approach to deal with heterogeneous data can be to split the VPC into groups of subjects that are more homogeneous. As an example, the VPCs below are computed again on the PK model built for [remifentanyl](#) pharmacokinetics, with 15 bins, but the data was first split by a categorical covariate that characterizes groups of similar doses.

7.5.1.3.4 VPC based on time after last dose (continuous data only)

Option in the display panel “Time after last dose” displays the VPC with data for times (the X-axis) after last dose (for Monolix versions 2021 and above). Below is an example with result for the demo project multidose_project.mlxtran (Monolix demo folder 6.3). Observed data overlaid the VPC. On the left image the X-axis is “Time”, and on the right the X-axis is “Time after last dose”. The exported charts data for the VPC include two columns for time and time after last dose – independently of the option selected in the interface. Doses with amount=0 are handled as the others. For observations before the first dose (or if no doses at all), time remains unchanged (i.e time after last dose = time). Finally, all administration ids are handled together (it is not possible to define time after dose for adm id = 2 only for instance).

7.5.1.3.5 Axis limits

From the 2023 version on, the user can choose the axis limits manually. This is particularly convenient when the prediction intervals go into negative values and log-scale is used on the y-axis. In that case, the VPC is shown by default from $1e-16$ to the maximum value, which leads to an unreadable plot. After toggling the setting “custom limits” on, the axis limits can be selected by the user. As the other plot settings, the axis limits are copied to the placeholders when preparing a report.

Default y-axis limits

Custom y-axis limits

7.5.1.3.6 Settings

- *Number of simulations* (default: 500): the number of simulated datasets used to generate the VPC can be modified before generating the plots in the settings of the Plots task:

- *General*: Add/remove legend or grid
- *Subplots (for TTE data)*
 - Add/remove plot for survival function (Kapan-Meier plot) or plot for mean number of events per individual
- *Display*
 - *Observed data*
 - Observed data: Add/remove observed data.
 - BLQ: Add/remove BLQ data if present.
 - Use BLQ: Choose to use BLQ data or to ignore it to compute the VPC. BLQ data can be simulated, or can be equal to the limit of quantification (LOQ). The latter case induces strong bias .
 - Empirical percentiles: Add/remove empirical percentiles for the 10%, 50% and 90% quantiles.
 - Predicted percentiles: Add/remove theoretical percentiles for the 10% and 90% quantiles.
 - Prediction interval: Add/remove prediction intervals given by the model for the 10% and 90% quantiles (in blue) and the 50% quantile (in pink).
 - Set interpercentile level and higher percentile for prediction intervals (for continuous data by default the level is 90 and the higher percentile is 90%), or number of bands for TTE data
- *Outliers*
 - Dots: Add/remove red dots indicating empirical percentiles that are outside prediction intervals
 - Areas: Add/remove red areas indicating empirical percentiles that are outside prediction intervals
- *Calculations*
 - Corrected predictions: compute the pcVPC using Uppsala prediction correction (see details above)

- Linear interpolation: Set piece wise display for prediction intervals (by default the display is linear)
- Time after last dose: Use time after last dose instead of time on the X-axis.
- *Bins – for categorical data, X Bins and DV Bins (for Y axis) can be specified*
 - Bin limits: Add/remove vertical lines on the scatter plots to indicate the bins.
 - Binning criteria: Choose the binning criteria among equal width (default), equal size or least-squares
 - Number of bins: Choose a fixed number of bins or a range for automatic selection, and a range for the number of data points per bin.
- *Axes*
 - Label: note that “prediction corrected” and “after last dose” are added automatically when choosing these settings and cannot be removed
 - Log-scale
 - Variable for x-axis: time, time after last dose (time relative to the previous dose), or regressor from the dataset
 - Axis limits

All colors, points and lines can be modified by the user.

7.5.1.3.7 Generating predictive checks on an external data set

This video shows how to generate an external VPC in Monolix: a VPC that compares the simulations based on a population model estimated on a first data set to a second data set, for example to check whether a population model estimated on a single dose study is also valid on a new multiple dose study for the same molecule.

7.5.1.3.8 Exporting VPC simulations

When exporting the charts data, by default the charts data for the VPC include the observed data and predicted percentiles, but not the detailed simulations, which are usually quite large. Starting from the 2020 version, the user can nonetheless choose to include the VPC simulations by clicking on “Export > Export VPC simulations” in the application menu:

The simulated values are saved in <result folder>/ChartsData/VisualPredictiveCheck/XXX_simulations.txt. They can be used to replot the VPC in R for instance.

In Monolix2021 it is also possible to include systematically the VPC simulations in the exported charts data with an option in the Preferences:

7.5.1.4 Correcting the VPC for missing observations

Missing observations can cause a bias in the VPC and hamper its diagnosis value. This page discusses why missing censored data or censored data replaced by the LOQ can cause a bias in the VPC, and how Monolix handles censored data to prevent this bias. It also explains the bias resulting from non-random dropout, and how this can be corrected with Simulx.

7.5.1.5 Troubleshooting

If the VPC plot is empty or with non-appropriate axis limits, follow the procedure below.

The problem appears after having clicked “Export > Export charts settings as default” (versions 2023R1 and before) on a previous project where the y-axis limits were different and this is now applied as default. It is possible to delete the default setting corresponding to the axis limits in the following way:

- Open the file C:/Users/<username>/lixoft/monolix/monolix2023R1/config/settings.default in a text editor
 - Delete the following lines:

```
VPCContinuous\yInterval= ...
outputPlot\yInterval= ...
```

- Save the file
- Reopen your project

7.5.1.6 Correcting the VPC for missing observations

Missing observations can cause a bias in the VPC and hamper its diagnosis value. This mini case-study shows why missing censored data or censored data replaced by the LOQ can cause a bias in the VPC, and how Monolix handles censored data to prevent this bias. It also explains the bias resulting from non-random dropout, and how this can be corrected with Simulx.

7.5.1.6.1 Censored data and VPC

This section explains the different cases that can occur when some data are censored. If the censored data are marked in the dataset, they are handled by Monolix in a way that prevents bias in the diagnostic plots such as the VPC. The bias remains however if the censored data are missing.

7.5.1.6.1.1 Censored data missing from the dataset

The figures below show what happens if censored data are missing from the dataset. The figures on the left and middle focus on two individuals in a PK dataset, with their observed concentrations (on the left) or predicted concentrations (in the middle) over time as blue dots, and with similar measurement times. We assume that a good model has been estimated on this data. Three simulated replicates are represented on the same plot in the middle, although percentiles are calculated on each replicate separately in order to generate the prediction intervals on the VPC.

In case of missing censored data, the empirical percentiles represented by the blue lines on the VPC do not decrease much at high times, because only the individuals with high enough observations (like the orange individual, and not like the green individual) contribute to the percentiles.

The simulations for the VPC follow the same measurement times as the initial dataset, however if the variability is unexplained the predictions for all the individuals have the same prediction distributions, so the number of predicted observations that contribute to the prediction intervals are the same for each percentile. This results in a discrepancy between observed and simulated data, that can be seen in red.

Explained inter-individual variability

This bias is reduced if most of the variability in the predictions is explained by some covariate effects in the model. In that case the variability of the predicted concentrations at high times will match the variability in the measurement times, and the discrepancy is reduced and can disappear. The diagnosis value of the VPC is improved, although the shape of the percentiles in the VPC is still affected by missing observations.

7.5.1.6.1.2 Censored data in dataset and “Use censored data” is OFF

If there is censored data in the dataset and the toggle “use censored data” in VPC plot display settings is off, the VPC is simulated for all times including censored times, and all values below the maximum LLOQ value and above the minimum ULOQ in dataset are dropped to calculate the percentiles.

The empirical percentiles are calculated using the non-censored times only.

7.5.1.6.1.3 “Use censored data” is ON and LOQ is used for calculations

In this case, the VPC is simulated for all times including censored times, and all simulated values are used to calculate the simulated percentiles.

For the empirical percentiles, the LOQ value in the dataset is used to replace the censored observations in the percentile calculation.

A strong bias appears in the VPC. The bias affects the empirical percentiles, as seen below, because the censored observations should actually be lower than the LOQ.

7.5.1.6.1.4 “Use censored data” is ON and simulated observations are used for calculations

In this case, the VPC is simulated for all times including censored times, and all simulated values are used to calculate the simulated percentiles.

For the empirical percentiles, the bias shown above is prevented by replacing the censored observations in the diagnostic plots by samples from the conditional distribution $p(y^{BLQ} | y^{nonBLQ}, \hat{\psi}, \hat{\theta})$, where $\hat{\theta}$ and $\hat{\psi}$ are the estimated population and individual parameters. This corrects the shape of the empirical percentiles in the VPC, as seen on the figure below. More information on handling censored data in Monolix is available [here](#).

7.5.1.6.2 Dropout and VPC

The same kind of bias can also occur when the dataset is affected by non-random dropout events. In this section we take an example of tumor growth data. We assume that the data have been fitted with a good model, and is affected by non-random dropout, because individuals with a high tumor size quit the study or die. This means that no more observation for the tumor size is available after the time of dropout, represented with the dashed vertical lines.

A bias appears in the VPC, caused by the missing censored observations. This is because there are more missing observations in the dataset for high tumor sizes, which is not the case in simulated predictions from the model, unless the inter-individual variability is well explained by some covariate effects.

7.5.1.6.2.1 Correcting the bias from dropout

Correcting this bias requires to provide additional measurement times after the dropouts, which cannot be done automatically in Monolix without making strong assumptions on the design of the dataset. However, it can be attempted with simulations in Simulx, with additional measurement times chosen by the user in adequation with the dataset, and some post-processing in R.

The correction also requires to model the dropout with a time-to-event model, that should depend on the tumour size. After estimating the joint tumor growth and time-to-event model in Monolix, it becomes possible to predict the time of dropout for each individual. The predictions for dropout times we will use for post-processing in R.

The figure below shows the main steps for correcting the bias from dropout in a VPC. The VPC (on the bottom of the figure) can be regenerated with new simulations in Simulx (shown on the top of the figure) and with some plotting functions of ggplot to display the empirical percentiles and prediction intervals. Two simulations that can be corrected are colored in light orange and in light green.

First, the light green simulation comes from an individual that had a late dropout in the initial dataset, so it has late prediction times. However, in this case the predicted tumor size is high, and the predicted dropout, visible in light green dashed line, occurs before the last prediction time. If this individual was real, it would not have been possible to measure this observation. (Note that for Monolix or Simulx the dropout is just an event, it cannot have any effect on the predictions of the size model)

Second, the light orange simulation comes from the orange individual, so it has missing predictions at high times. However in this case the predicted tumor size is small and the predicted dropout time is quite high, higher than the missing predictions. So if this individual was real, it would have been possible to measure an additional observation here.

- Step 1 (left): the VPC is displayed without post-processing: it has the same bias as in Monolix.
- Step 2 (middle): To get predictions that are more representative of the dataset, the prediction marked in red from the light green simulation is removed before plotting the VPC, along with all the individual predictions that occur after the corresponding predicted dropout. This first correction is seen in the middle and reduces strongly the bias of the VPC.
- Step 3 (right): With Simulx it is possible to change the design structure for the prediction times defined in the outputs of the simulations. The time marked in red for the light orange simulation is added in the output before performing the simulations for the VPC, and the same is done for all individuals that have missing observations in the dataset.

Combining the pre-processing of the outputs before the simulations from Step 3 and the post-processing of the simulations from Step 2 to remove the predictions occurring after a dropout gives a VPC that is not biased by a spurious discrepancy (VPC3). The shape of the percentiles in the VPC is still affected by the dropouts, but the diagnosis value of the VPC is retained.

The difficulty of the approach in Step 3 is to extrapolate the design of the dataset in a way that makes sense. This can not be done in Monolix, but it has to be done in R by the user because it requires to make assumptions on the design, and it might be problematic when the design structure is complex.

For example, in the case of repeated doses, doses that are missing from the dataset because they would occur after a dropout will also have to be included in the new design. Furthermore, the user has to extrapolate the measurement times from the dataset, that are not necessarily the same for all individuals, while keeping the same measurement density for the new observations as for the rest of the observations, to avoid introducing other bias in the VPC.

7.5.1.6.2.2 Example

The example shown on this page along with the R script to correct the VPC can be downloaded here:

- example for Monolix2018 and Monolix2019: [example_correction_VPC_dropout.zip](#)
- example for Monolix2020R1: [example_correction_VPC_dropout_2020R1.zip](#)

This example is based on simulated data from the PDTTE model developed in “Desmée, S, Mentré, F, Veyrat-Follet, C, Sébastien, B, Guedj, J (2017). Using the SAEM algorithm for mechanistic joint models characterizing the relationship between nonlinear PSA kinetics and survival in prostate cancer patients. *Biometrics*, 73, 1:305-312.” We assume for the sake of the example that the level of PSA is a marker of the tumour size.

7.5.1.7 How Monolix generates the VPC for Time-To-Event data

The construction of a VPC plot for time-to-event data by Monolix requires several steps in the background:

1. **Simulation of datasets.** First, Monolix simulates datasets using the population model, which contains the structural and statistical models and the estimated population parameters.
2. **Survival function estimators.** Then, for the original dataset and each simulated dataset, it estimates the survival function with either the Kaplan-Meier estimator for exactly observed events or the Turnbull estimator for interval censored events.
3. **Prediction interval.** Finally, Monolix calculates lower and upper percentiles of the simulated survival function estimates, which give a prediction interval.

7.5.1.7.1 Simulation of TTE data sets using a population model

Simulations of time-to-event datasets give, for each individual, times when an event occurs. The simulations are based on the same design as in the original data set, the same number of individuals as in the original data set and individual parameters are sampled using the covariates from this original data set and the population parameters estimated in Monolix.

To simulate a time when an event occurs, (u) is defined as a probability that an event (X) occurs before a certain time (T). This probability is computed using the cumulative hazard function ($H(t)$)

$$u = P(X \leq T) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_0^T h(t, \psi_i) dt\right) = 1 - \exp(-H(T)),$$

where H is a solution to the ODE system $dH/dt = h$. A value of the probability u is sampled from the uniform $[0,1]$ distribution, thus in the above equation the time T becomes the unknown variable. A root finding method from an ODE solver finds its value.

The time T is not a given independent variable, but it is a simulated observation. Moreover, simulations are only until the time T_{max} , which corresponds to the last time found in the data set. This value is the final integration time of the ODEs for each individual and it also defines a unique right censoring time for all individuals in the simulated data sets. It is independent of the individual times of events or right censoring in the original data set.

If the simulation fails because of a numerical error (e. g. because of a too high hazard), the simulated individuals with NaNs in their simulations are not used in the prediction interval, and the proportion of simulated individuals involved is then displayed in the interface.

The appearance of NaNs in the VPC simulations stops the generation of the VPC in Monolix versions prior to 2021R1. In Monolix versions starting at 2021R1, NaNs are ignored and the percentage of simulations giving NaNs is indicated in a warning message.

7.5.1.7.1.1 Example

In this example, the individual 3 in the original data set (table on the left) experienced an event at time 4. In the simulations (tables on the right), an event for this individual can occur before or after that time, or may occur after $T_{max}=5$ (last table). Similarly, while the individual 5 left the study at time 3 without experiencing an event in the original data set, in the simulations for this individual an event can occur before or after time 3. If an event has not occurred at $T_{max}=5$, then it is right censored.

ORIGINAL DATA SET		
ID	TIME	DV
1	0	0
1	3	1
2	0	0
2	1	1
3	0	0
3	4	1
4	0	0
4	5	0
5	0	0
5	3	0

Tmax=5

POSSIBLE SIMULATED DATA SETS

simulated DATA SET 1		
ID	TIME	DV
1	0	0
1	5	0
2	0	0
2	2.3	1
3	0	0
3	1.6	1
4	0	0
4	4.5	1
5	0	0
5	5	0

simulated DATA SET 2		
ID	TIME	DV
1	0	0
1	3.3	1
2	0	0
2	5	0
3	0	0
3	4.8	1
4	0	0
4	3.9	1
5	0	0
5	3.5	1

simulated DATA SET 3		
ID	TIME	DV
1	0	0
1	2.8	1
2	0	0
2	5	0
3	0	0
3	5	0
4	0	0
4	3.6	1
5	0	0
5	1.1	1

7.5.1.7.1.2 Possible sources of bias in the simulations

Censoring (dropout)

In the original dataset (input Monolix dataset), censoring can be at any time: because the patient drops out or because the study is stopped for instance. In contrast, simulated datasets have no dropout until the global T_{max} over all individuals, which means that there are on average more events in the simulated datasets than in the original dataset. However, if censoring in the original dataset is truly random, simulating until the global T_{max} over all individuals should not produce a bias because the “additional” simulated events are evenly distributed over time. But if censoring in the dataset is not truly random, the empirical Kaplan-Meier curve is biased while the VPC predictions are not, so it may appear as a misfit. If we would instead censor the simulated datasets at the same censoring times as in the original dataset ($T_{max}=5$ for id 4 and $T_{max}=3$ for ID 5 on the above example), this could introduce other bias.

Regressor

If the TTE model depends on a regressor, the regressor is interpolated using last value carried forward.

Doses

If the TTE model depends on a PK model with doses present in the dataset, it is important to also include the planned (but not given because of event or dropout) doses in the dataset such that the doses span the same time range for all individuals. Otherwise this will create a bias in the VPC.

7.5.1.7.2 Survival function estimators

Given some survival data that includes censoring (right-censoring or interval-censoring), a survival function can be estimated as a non-parametric maximum likelihood estimator (NPMLE).

Thus Monolix estimates an NPMLE for each simulated dataset, depending on the event type:

1. **Kaplan-Meier estimator** for **exactly observed events**.
2. **Turnbull estimator** for **interval censored data**.

The calculation of these estimators is detailed in the next sections.

Note: for interval censored data, the Turnbull estimator is used only in the VPC:

- **In the plot of Observed data**, Monolix assumes that all events are exactly observed and displays the data using the **Kaplan-Meier estimator** explained in the previous section. This is because that plot is generated right after accepting the dataset, before a model has been selected. However, just looking at the dataset, the case of exact and interval censored events are indistinguishable. For example: assume that an observation period started at $t=0$ and at $t=1$ an event is marked by 1 in the column for the observation. Without any other information, the event could have occurred at $t=1$ or before.
- **In the VPC**, Monolix uses the event type information specified in the structural model. If “event type = intervalCensored” is specified in the structural model, Monolix uses the **Turnbull estimator** for empirical and simulated survival curves in the VPC, in order to avoid bias in the survival function estimate. If event type is not specified in the structural model, Monolix considers all interval-censored events as exactly observed at the end of a censored interval, and uses **the Kaplan-Meier estimator**.

DEFINITION:

```
Event = {type = event, eventType = intervalCensored, intervalLength = L,  
        maxEventNumber = 1, hazard = h}
```

7.5.1.7.2.1 Exact events: Kaplan-Meier estimator

The Kaplan-Meier estimator, or product limit estimator, is a type of non-parametric maximum likelihood estimator and a standard method to approximate the survival function $S(t)$

in the case of exact events. It describes the probability that an individual survives until time t , knowing that it survived at any earlier time. For single events, it is given by the following formula:

$$\hat{S}(t) = \prod_{i:t_i < t} \left(1 - \frac{d_i}{n_i}\right),$$

where

- t_i - times before t , when at least one event occurred,
- d_i - number of events at the time t_i ,
- n_i - number of individuals at risk, that is who did not experience an event until t_i .

The probability (p_e) of an event is the ratio between the number of occurred events (d_i) and the number of individuals at risk (n_i). The complement of it, $(1 - p_e)$, gives an estimation of the survival. For each time t , the total number of individuals at risk, who survived, may change. Thus, the current survival probability is the product of all probabilities at previous times t_i , when at least one event occurred.

This formula can be better understood by calculating for example the probability that a patient survives 2 days: it is a product of two probabilities: the probability that the patient survives the first day and a conditional probability that they survive the second day, knowing that they survived the first one.

Example

On the left of the figure below, a typical example of a time-to-event data set contains information about exact times when individuals experienced an event ($T=1$) or when they left the study (drop-out: $T=0$). Five individuals have two observations each: the time at which the observation starts ($T=0$ for everyone) and the time of an event. If a patient leaves the study, then the dataset contains a drop-out time with $T=0$, instead of $T=1$, in the column for the observations. This means that the patient experienced no event but survived until the drop-out time. The Kaplan-Meier estimator takes into account such situations, because these individuals are not counted as individuals at risk (they are not counted in the denominator n_i) at later times.

The study starts at time t_1 . There are no events, so $d_1=0$ and the value of the Kaplan-Meier estimator is 1. Until the next event time at $t_2=1$, the estimator remains constant. At that time, one individual

experienced an event, hence $d_2=1$, and all individuals survived until that time so $n_2=5$. As a result, the probability to survive decreases by 0.2. It is the height of the jump at $t=1$ in the plot. The Kaplan-Meier estimator remains constant until the next event. At time $t=3$ there are two events. The number n_3 counts now only 4 individuals – it has decreased by 1 due to the previous event. The final probability at time 3 is a product of all earlier probabilities. At $t=4$ there is a drop-out: patient 5 left the study without experiencing an event. The survival curve remains constant and a red dot marks the drop-out. The Kaplan-Meier estimator takes into account this situations, because at the next event time $t=5$, this individual is not counted as an individual at risk – thus the denominator n will be smaller. Finally, at time $t=5$, there is only one individual left, and one event, so the survival becomes 0.

Remarks

- The Kaplan-Meier estimator handles correctly the information about individuals who left the study (right-censoring), but there is a bias when the exact times of events are unknown (interval-censoring).
- In the TTE VPC, Monolix estimates a linear approximation of the Kaplan-Meier estimate.

7.5.1.7.2.2 Interval censored events: Turnbull estimator

The Turnbull estimator is a generalization of the Kaplan-Meier estimator that allows for interval censoring. In the TTE VPC, Monolix uses this estimator to plot both the empirical and simulated survival curves.

Interval censored events do not occur at exact times t_i , $i = (1, \dots, n)$, but within some time intervals between times L_i and U_i , $L_i < t_i \leq U_i$. In case of right censored data (dropout), L_i is the time when the individual leaves the study, and $U_i = +\infty$: an event will occur within the interval $(L_i, +\infty)$.

In the TTE VPC, the intervals $(L_i, U_i]$ are:

- **For the empirical survival curve**, they correspond to the censoring intervals of the original data set.
- **For simulated survival curves**, the definition of these intervals depends on whether the structural model contains the option “intervalLength” or not:
 - If “intervalLength=L” is given, then the intervals are $[0, L], (L, 2 \cdot L], \dots, (m \cdot L, T_{max}]$
- If “intervalLength” is missing, then the whole period of observation defined with the minimal and maximal times in the data is split in 10 regular intervals.

Simulations of interval censored datasets give, as in the case of exactly observed events, exact times of events for each individual. In order to compare the simulated survival to the empirical survival without bias, simulated events are counted in regular intervals to be transformed into interval censored events, and they are then represented in the VPC with the Turnbull estimator just like for the empirical survival.

Turnbull intervals

The Turnbull estimator is computed on time intervals $(\tau_{j-1}, \tau_j]$ that are called Turnbull intervals:

$$0 = \tau_0 \leq \tau_1 \leq \dots \leq \tau_m \leq \tau_{m+1} = \infty$$

This grid of times is constructed from all points L_i, U_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$ in increasing order.

Turnbull algorithm

Notations

- The probability that an event occurs in a j -th Turnbull interval is

$$p_j = P(\tau_{j-1} \leq T \leq \tau_j) = S(\tau_{j-1}) - S(\tau_j)$$

- For each individual i : α_i denotes a weight such that

$$\alpha_i = 1 \cdot (\tau_{j-1}, \tau_j] \subset (L_i, U_i].$$

- The Weight a_{ij} is an event indicator - it indicates whether an event from the interval $(L_i, U_i]$ occurred at τ_j .
- d_j is the number of events until τ_j and n_j is the number of individuals at risk at τ_j
- The likelihood function for $p = (p_1, \dots, p_{m+1})$ is:

$$L_S(p) = \prod_{i=1}^n [S(L_i) - S(R_i)] = \prod_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{m+1} \alpha_{ij} p_j$$

Main idea of the Turnbull algorithm

Finding the NPMLE of S , denoted by \hat{S} , means maximizing $L_S(p)$ under the constraint that p_j are positive and $\sum_{j=1}^{m+1} p_j = 1$. The original Turnbull algorithm (1976) is the first and the simplest method to maximize $L_S(p)$ with respect to p . It is an application of the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm.

Remark: L_S depends only on values of S at points τ_j , and the behaviour of S within the Turnbull intervals is unknown. The convention applied here is: $\hat{S}(t) = \hat{S}(\tau_j)$ when $\tau_{j-1} \leq t \leq \tau_j$.

Procedure

The algorithm is the following:

- Step 0:** Initialization - choose an initial guess for $S^{old}(\tau_j)$. This initial guess for S is the estimate obtained from the Kaplan-Meier estimator under the assumption that events occur at U_i , interpolated on the τ -grid.
- Step 1:** Compute the probability of an event at time τ_j as

$$p_j = S^{old}(\tau_{j-1}) - S^{old}(\tau_j), j = 1, \dots, m$$

- **Step 2:** Estimate the number of events at τ_j as

$$\tilde{d}_j = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\alpha_{ij} p_j}{\sum_{k=1}^m \alpha_{ik} p_k}, j = 1, \dots, m$$

- **Step 3:** Compute the estimated number of individuals at risk at time τ_j

$$\tilde{n}_j = \sum_{k=j}^m \tilde{d}_k, j = 1, \dots, m$$

- **Step 4:** Compute S^{new} using the Kaplan-Meier estimator using \tilde{d} and \tilde{n} to update the survival function
- **Stopping criterion:** If the updated solution S^{new} is close to the old solution S^{old} (in Monolix, $\|S^{new} - S^{old}\| < 0.001$), stop, otherwise set $S^{old} = S^{new}$ and repeat steps 1 - 4

Linear approximation

In the TTE VPC, just like for the the Kaplan-Meier estimate, Monolix calculates a linear approximation of the Turnbull estimate.

Example

Below we show a small dataset with interval censored events. The individuals are in increasing order of the times at which censored intervals end. The figure on the rights shows two curves:

- The upper bound curve is the Kaplan-Meier estimate assuming that events occur exactly at the upper interval limit $t_i = U_i$.
- The lower bound curve is the Kaplan-Meier estimate assuming that events occur exactly at the lower interval limit $t_i = L_i$.

ID	time	Yobs
1	0	0
1	L1	0
1	U1	1
2	0	0
2	L2	0
2	U2	1
3	0	0
3	L3	0
4	0	0
4	L4	0
4	U4	1

For comparison, we show now a similar dataset corresponding to exactly observed events at the upper interval limit. The figure on the right shows again the Kaplan-Meier estimator, and in addition its linear approximation.

ID	time	Yobs
1	0	0
1	t1	1
2	0	0
2	t2	1
3	0	0
3	t3	0
4	0	0
4	t4	1

Kaplan-Meier estimator	
t0	$S_0 = 1$
t1	$S_1 = \frac{3}{4}$
t2	$S_2 = \frac{1}{2}$
t3	$S_3 = \frac{1}{2}$
t4	$S_4 = 0$

Procedure

The time points of the lower and upper interval limits for all individuals are ordered in increasing sequence. In this example, the assumption is

$$0 < L_1 < U_1 < L_2 < U_2 < L_3 < U_4$$

$$0 < \tau_1 < \tau_2 < \tau_3 < \tau_4 < \tau_5 < \tau_6 < \tau_7$$

The Turnbull intervals are the intervals $(\tau_{j-1}, \tau_j]$, where $j = 1, \dots, m$, with $\tau_0 = 0$ and $\tau_8 = \infty$.

The weights α_{ij} are elements of the following matrix:

	$(0, L_1]$	$(L_1, U_1]$	$(U_1, L_2]$	$(L_2, U_2]$	$(U_2, L_3]$	$(L_3, U_4]$	$(U_4, \infty]$
$(L_1, U_1]: \alpha_1$	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
$(L_2, U_2]: \alpha_2$	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
$(L_3, \infty]: \alpha_3$	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
$(L_4, U_4]: \alpha_4$	0	0	0	1	1	1	0

First iteration of the algorithm

Step 0: The initial guess is the upper bound curve, that is the Kaplan-Meier estimator under the assumption that events occur at U_i , interpolated on the τ -grid.

$$S^{old}(\tau_0) = 1, \quad S^{old}(\tau_1) = 1, \quad S^{old}(\tau_2) = S_1, \quad S^{old}(\tau_3) = S_1, \quad S^{old}(\tau_4) = S_1$$

$$S^{old}(\tau_5) = S_2, \quad S^{old}(\tau_6) = S_2, \quad S^{old}(\tau_7) = S_4, \quad S^{old}(\tau_8) = S_4$$

Step 1: The probabilities that events occur in the Turnbull intervals are

$$p_1 = 0, \quad p_2 = 1 - S_1, \quad p_3 = 0, \quad p_4 = 0$$

$$p_5 = S_1 - S_2, \quad p_6 = 0, \quad p_7 = S_2 - S_4, \quad p_8 = 0$$

Step 2: Modified number of events

$$\tilde{d}_1 = 0$$

$$\tilde{d}_2 = \frac{\alpha_{12}p_2}{\alpha_{12}p_2} = 1$$

$$\tilde{d}_3 = 0$$

$$\tilde{d}_4 = 0$$

$$\tilde{d}_5 = \frac{\alpha_{25}p_5}{\alpha_{25}p_5} + \frac{\alpha_{45}p_5}{\alpha_{45}p_5 + \alpha_{47}p_7} = 1 + \frac{S_1 - S_2}{S_1 - S_4}$$

$$\tilde{d}_6 = 0$$

$$\tilde{d}_7 = \frac{\alpha_{37}p_7}{\alpha_{37}p_7} + \frac{\alpha_{47}p_7}{\alpha_{45}p_5 + \alpha_{47}p_7} = 1 + \frac{S_2 - S_4}{S_1 - S_4}$$

$$\tilde{d}_8 = 0$$

Step 3: Modified number of individuals at risk

$$\tilde{n}_1 = 4$$

$$\tilde{n}_2 = 4$$

$$\tilde{n}_3 = 3$$

$$\tilde{n}_4 = 3$$

$$\tilde{n}_5 = 3$$

$$\tilde{n}_6 = 1 + \frac{S_2 - S_4}{S_1 - S_4}$$

$$\tilde{n}_7 = 1 + \frac{S_2 - S_4}{S_1 - S_4}$$

$$\tilde{n}_8 = 0$$

Step 4: Kaplan-Meier estimator for the modified values of d and n :

$$\begin{aligned}
 S^{new}(\tau_0) &= 1 \\
 S^{new}(\tau_1) &= 1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{0}{4}\right) = 1 \\
 S^{new}(\tau_2) &= 1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{4}\right) = \frac{3}{4} \\
 S^{new}(\tau_3) &= \frac{3}{4} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{0}{3}\right) = \frac{3}{4} \\
 S^{new}(\tau_4) &= \frac{3}{4} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{0}{3}\right) = \frac{3}{4} \\
 S^{new}(\tau_5) &= \frac{3}{4} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1 + \frac{1}{3}}{3}\right) = \frac{5}{12} \\
 S^{new}(\tau_6) &= \frac{5}{12} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{0}{1 + \frac{2}{3}}\right) = \frac{5}{12} \\
 S^{new}(\tau_7) &= \frac{5}{12} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1 + \frac{2}{3}}{1 + \frac{2}{3}}\right) = 0 \\
 S^{new}(\tau_8) &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

The figure below compares the linear approximations of Turnbull estimate at the start of the first iteration (S^{old}) and at the end (S^{new}), as well as the linear approximation of the Kaplan-Meier estimate in case of exact events.

- The difference between the blue curve and S^{old} comes from the fact that S^{old} is interpolated on a grid including the L_i time points while they are not included in the grid considered in the case of exact events.
- The first iteration of the Turnbull algorithm has the effect of lowering S^{new} compared to S^{old} after τ_4 , which is due to the fact that the event in $(L_4, U_4]$ may have already occurred after that point.

7.5.1.7.2.3 Prediction interval

To generate the prediction interval in the VPC plot, Monolix performs by default 500 simulations with N individuals as in the original data set. As a result, it produces 500 time series that form 500 survival curves (based on Kaplan-Meier or Turnbull estimators). Since simulated event times are random numbers, all estimated survival functions have different time grids. *This is shown on Fig.(a) with two different simulated datasets.*

The interpolation of these curves on a fixed time grid allows to calculate the prediction interval. In Monolix the default time grid consists of a uniform grid with 100 points. For exactly observed events, the grid includes in addition all time points from the original data set to provide all possible information. Exact event times are unknown for interval censored events, so dataset time points have no additional information. *This is shown on Fig.(b) with the Kaplan-Meier plot from the simulated dataset 1 from Fig.(a), interpolated on a different time grid than its events, combining regularly spaced points at times 0, 10, 20, ..., 100, and additional time points indicated in green that come from the original dataset.)*

The interpolation on the new grid gives at each time point of the grid a set of probabilities corresponding to different simulated survival curves. It allows to calculate lower and upper percentiles (the 5th and 95th percentiles are the default choice) and draw the prediction interval. *This is shown on Fig. (c) with the survival estimators from multiple simulations on the same time grid as on Fig. (b).*

Example: exactly observed events

The dataset contains times of exactly observed single events of 30 individuals. The survival model has a constant hazard function and the Kaplan-Meier estimator approximates the survival function. The VPC plot uses a linear approximation of the Kaplan-Meier curve (Fig. on the left). By default, the fixed grid has 100 uniformly distributed points together with all time points from the date set. The figure on the left presents the VPC plot with the default settings. The approximation of the empirical and simulated

Kaplan-Meier curves is sufficient on the default grid. In contrast, the VPC on the Figure on the right uses a grid with only time points from the original dataset. The accuracy of the prediction interval is decreased.

Example: interval censored events

In this dataset, the times of events from the previous example are the ends of time intervals within which events occurred. The length of the censored intervals in the dataset is non constant among individuals, and oscillates around 5. The structural model includes this information in eventTime and intervalLength options.

7.5.2 Numerical predictive check

7.5.2.1 Purpose

This plot displays the numerical predictive check (NPC). The NPC is a model diagnosis tool for continuous data which is closely related to the VPC procedure: the principle is similar, with a different way to visualize the resulting information. While the VPC maintains the time dimension and can be used to point out at which time points the model overpredicts or underpredicts the data, the NPC allows to compare the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the observations, computed on the original data set, with the theoretical cumulative distribution, computed from data simulated with the model of interest and the design structure of the original data set.

Note that since the NPC compares each observation with its own simulated distribution, there is no concern of data binning like for the VPC.

7.5.2.2 Examples

In the following example, the parameters of a two-compartment model with iv infusion and linear elimination are estimated on the [remifentanil data set](#).

One can see the empirical CDF of remifentanil concentration in blue, compared to the theoretical CDF based on simulated data in black. The 90% prediction interval corresponding to the theoretical CDF is visualized as a light blue area. Discrepancies between the empirical CDF and this area are marked in red. The log-scale on the x-axis allows to focus on small observations. The plot shows that the model underpredicts small observations, and tends to overpredict some observations between 20 and 40 units.

7.5.2.2.1 Settings

- *General:* Add/remove legend or grid.
- *Display*
 - Empirical distribution: Add/remove empirical CDF.
 - Predicted median: Add/remove theoretical CDF.
 - Prediction interval: Add/remove the prediction interval for the theoretical CDF, and set the interpercentile level for the prediction interval (by default the level is 90) and its associated level.
 - Outliers (area): Add/remove red areas indicating where the empirical CDF is outside the prediction interval.
- Calculations:
 - Set the number of evaluation points in the NPC.

- Use BLQ: Choose to use BLQ data or to ignore it to compute the VPC. BLQ data can be simulated, or can be equal to the limit of quantification (LOQ). The latter case induces strong bias.

7.5.3 BLQ predictive check

7.5.3.1 Purpose

This plot displays the proportion of censored data w.r.t. time. It is possible to choose the censoring interval. This plot is only available for projects with censored data.

7.5.3.2 Examples

The figure presents the simulated and empirical BLQ frequencies w.r.t. time (example taken from the censored1_project of the demos).

7.5.3.2.1 Censored interval

The censored interval can be modified in Display. By default, the limit and the censored values are used. However, one can look at a smaller censored interval for example. This is the case with the example below: on the left, the BLQ predictive check uses the default censored interval wher Min=-Infinity because there is no LIMIT column in the dataset. Since the observations are PK concentrations, Min=0 has been specified on the right, and no more outlier area is visible. This suggests that the outlier areas seen on the left are due to predicted negative values for censored observations, which means that it would be important in this case to specify a null lower limit for the censored observations by adding a column LIMIT to the dataset.

7.5.3.2.2 Settings

- *General*: Add/remove legend or grid
- *Display*
 - Empirical proportion: Add/remove the blue line for empirical proportion of censored observations in cumulative observations.
 - Predicted median : Add/remove the median proportion of censored observations in cumulative observations calculated by simulation.
 - Prediction interval: Add/remove the prediction interval given by the model for the 90% quantile. The level (quantile) can be modified.
 - Outliers (area): Add/remove red areas indicating time points for which the empirical proportion is outside the prediction interval.
 - *Calculations*
 - Number of point for the discretization

- Censored interval: min and max for censored data. By default, the limit and the censored values are used. However, one can look at a smaller censored interval for example.

By default, the censored area corresponds to the data set description and the BLQ frequency observation, the prediction interval, and the outliers are displayed.

7.5.4 Prediction distribution

7.5.4.1 Purpose

This plot displays the prediction distribution. It allows to compare the observations with the theoretical distribution of the predictions. It is based on multiple simulations of all individuals from the dataset, without the residual error. The simulations use the estimated population parameters, without considering their uncertainty.

7.5.4.2 Example

Prediction distribution plots vary slightly for different types of data. For joint models for multivariate outcomes, a separate plot is available for each type of data.

7.5.4.2.1 Continuous outcomes

In the following example, the parameters of a one compartmental model with first order absorption and linear elimination are estimated on the theophylline data set. One can see the prediction distribution of the concentration overlaid with the data set.

7.5.4.2.2 Non-continuous outcomes: count data and categorical data

count2_project (data = 'count2_data.txt', model = 'count_library/poissonTimeVarying_mlxt.txt')

Prediction distribution plots for count data and categorical data show the predicted frequencies of the categorized data over time, computed by Monte-Carlo. In the following example, predictions come from a Poisson distribution with a time varying intensit. Note that hovering on a band reveals the corresponding modality.

7.5.4.3 Settings

- *General:* Add/remove legend or grid
- *Display (for continuous data)*
 - Observed data
 - BLQ: Add/remove BLQ data if present.
 - Median: Add/remove the median of predictions.
 - Level: set the level (90 by default). The distribution corresponds to $[50 - \frac{level}{2}, 50 + \frac{level}{2}]$.
 - Number of bands: set the number of bands (9 by default) and the associated percentile in case of a discrete representation
- *X Bins (for discrete data)*
 - Bin values: Add/remove vertical lines on the plot to indicate the bins.
 - Bining criteria: Choose the binning criteria among equal width (default), equal size or least-squares
 - Number of bins: Choose a fixed number of bins or a range for automatic selection, and a range for the number of data points per bin.

By default, only the prediction distribution and the median are displayed (for continuous data).

7.6 Convergence diagnosis

The following pages describe the plots related to the convergence diagnosis:

7.6.1 Convergence of SAEM

7.6.1.1 Purpose

This plot displays the sequence of estimates for population parameters computed after each iteration of the SAEM algorithm. The purpose is to check the convergence of the algorithm. In addition, a convergence indicator gives the estimation for $-2 \times \log\text{-likelihood}$ along the iterations.

7.6.1.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption and linear elimination are estimated on the [theophylline data set](#). The vertical line indicates where the algorithm switches from the first phase to the second. Notice also that the convergence indicator is displayed. More details on the convergence indicator can be found [here](#).

7.6.1.3 Settings

- *Select plots and arrange layout.* It is convenient when there are many parameters and the user wants to focus on some particular parameter convergence for example.

By default, 12 parameters are displayed.

7.6.2 Convergence of MCMC

7.6.2.1 Purpose

This plot displays the sequence of estimates for the conditional means and the conditional standard deviations along the iterations of the MH algorithm during individual parameters estimation by MCMC. The purpose is to check the convergence of the algorithm. The algorithm stops when these sequences remain in an interval of a given amplitude for a certain number of iterations: this interval is visualized on the figure with horizontal lines. The plot is shown and interactively updated while the task is running, and can be found after the end of the task in the Plots frame.

7.6.2.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption and linear elimination are estimated on the [theophylline data set](#).

7.6.2.3 Settings

- *Select plots and arrange layout.* It is convenient when there are many parameters and the user wants to focus on some particular parameter convergence for example.

By default, 12 parameters are displayed.

7.6.3 Convergence of importance sampling

7.6.3.1 Purpose

This plot displays the sequence of estimates for observed log-likelihood computed by Monte Carlo approach. The purpose is to check the convergence of the algorithm.

7.6.3.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a three-compartments infusion model with linear elimination are estimated on the [remifentanyl data set](#). As explained on this page, the bias of the log-likelihood estimator decreases with the number of iterations, before the estimation value stabilizes. The number of points in the plot is usually smaller than the number of iterations, and depends on the total number of observations.

7.6.3.3 Settings

- Add/remove grid.

7.7 Task results

The following pages describe the plots related to the task results:

7.7.1 Likelihood contribution

7.7.1.1 Purpose

This plot displays the contribution of each individual to the log-likelihood. It is only available if the log-likelihood was previously computed. It can be sorted by index or by log-likelihood value (either via linearization of importance sampling, depending on which has been computed).

7.7.1.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption, linear elimination and a delay are estimated on the [warfarin data set](#). The figure shows the top ten contributions from individuals to the log-likelihood, computed via linearization or importance sampling methods. All the contributions appear in small size on the mini-plot on top, as well as a window indicating the selection of individuals for the main histogram.

Here we notice that the subject with id 8 has a much higher contribution to the log-likelihood than all other subjects, meaning that its response is less well captured by the model than others. It is worth checking this individual in the plots of individual fits, and remove it from the data set if its observations look abnormal.

7.7.1.2.1 Settings

- *General.* Add/remove the legend, grid, or a mini-plot that allows to select a range of ranks to display.
- *Methods.* Add/remove histograms bins for values computed by linearization or importance sampling, if they have been computed.
- *Sorting.* The user can choose to sort the histogram by index, or by contribution value computed with linearization or importance sampling, if they have been computed.
- *Label.* The user can choose to display labels on top of the bins to indicate subject indices or names (ids).

7.7.2 Standard errors of estimates

7.7.2.1 Purpose

This plot displays a histogram with the relative standard error of each parameter estimate, computed with the Fisher Information Matrix. It is only available if the standard errors were previously computed, and it provides a graphical representation of the information already available in the column “R.S.E (%)” in the Pop.Param tab of the Results frame.

7.7.2.2 Example

In the following example, the parameters of a one-compartment model with first-order absorption, linear elimination and a delay are estimated on the [warfarin data set](#). The figure shows the relative standard errors of all population estimates, computed via linearization and importance sampling methods, with the exact values written in front of each bin.

This figure allows here to highlight `beta_CI_tsex_F` as an estimate associated with a high standard error. This suggests to check the relevance of this covariate effect, by looking at the estimate for this parameter and the result of the Wald test in the statistical tests.

7.7.2.3 Settings

- *General.* Add/remove the legend or grid.
- *Methods.* Add/remove histograms bins for values computed by linearization or stochastic approximation, if they have been computed.

8 Reporting

8.1 Overview

Starting from the 2023R1 version of the MonolixSuite, Monolix includes a feature of automated report generation. This feature is available in Monolix through Export > Generate report. After defining settings in the window that pops up and clicking on the Generate report button, a report in the form of a Microsoft Word (docx) document will be generated in the specified directory. Note that reports generated using command line and lixoftConnectors will contain tables but no plots. Reporting module is not available on the CentOS 7 version of MonolixSuite 2023R1.

8.1.1 Report generation strategies

When selecting Export > Generate report..., there are two different strategies available for report generation:

1. **Using a default template file** – choosing this option will generate the report containing tables of estimated population parameters (with standard errors) and log-likelihood and information criteria, as well as all plots available in the interface using their current settings. This option allow to obtain a basic report with all results in one click.
2. **Using a custom template file** – if users choose this option, they will be required to provide a path to the template word file which contains placeholders that will be replaced by tables, plots and keywords when generating the report.

Several other options are available in the pop-up window after the Generate report option is clicked on:

1. **Document watermark** – users can specify a custom text that will appear as a watermark in the report. Font family, font size, color, layout and transparency can be specified, if text is entered into the Text input widget.
2. **Generated report file** – users can choose if the generated report will be saved next to the project file (in that case only the name of the generated report file needs to be given to Monolix) or in a custom directory (absolute path that includes the generated report file name needs to be given).
3. **Table styles** (only when the custom template file option is selected) – users can choose a style for tables from the list of styles available by default in Microsoft Word. This setting can be overridden by specifying the style directly in the table placeholder. This way custom user-created or company-specific styles can be used.

8.1.2 Default template file

Selecting the option to use the default template file to generate a report gives users a possibility to quickly generate a document containing results of an analysis.

Such a report will consist of:

1. name of the Monolix project
2. data set file name,
3. a date of report generation,
4. a table of estimated population parameters (with standard errors, if calculation of SE was performed),
5. a table of log-likelihood and information criteria (if calculation of likelihood was performed),
6. all plots displayed in the GUI with settings currently defined in the interface.

By clicking on View default template, a Word document containing placeholders for all the elements that will be present in the generated report can be downloaded. This document can then be used as a basis for the creation of a custom template file.

8.1.3 Custom template file

The option to use the custom template file can be selected if a user has previously created a Word document (a template) that typically contains placeholders to be replaced by project-specific information, such as tables of results, plots or settings used in a project. Placeholders are strings with a specific syntax that define the settings and layout with which tables and plots will be generated during the report generation process.

For example, in the picture below, a template file on the right contains a placeholder for the observed data plot. So, after report generation, the report file on the right contains a plot for the observed data instead of this placeholder.

8.1.3.1 Using placeholders

There are three types of placeholders that can be used:

1. placeholders for project settings,
2. placeholders for plots,
3. placeholders for tables.

Placeholders for project settings are of format `%keyword%` and, during the report generation step, they will be replaced by project or global Monolix settings. For example, if a custom template file contains the placeholder `%SAEM_nbBurningIterations%`, this placeholder will be replaced by the number of SAEM burning iterations used by a Monolix project for which the report is being generated. The list of all project settings placeholders can be found [here](#).

Placeholders for plots are of format `<lixoftPLH>settings</lixoftPLH>` and, during the report generation step, they will be replaced by plots that are available in the Monolix user interface. Placeholders for plots contain settings that describe how the generated plots should look like. All settings that are available for plots in the interface are available in reporting as well, with addition of several others that describe plot dimensions and display of captions. The list of the main plot settings placeholders can be found [here](#).

Placeholders for tables are also of format `<lixoftPLH>settings</lixoftPLH>`. Placeholders for tables contain settings that describe how the generated table should look like and they allow more flexibility in the layout compared to the display of tables in the GUI. Indeed, table placeholders can contain settings that result in generated tables being different from the ones available in the Results tab of the Monolix interface, such as an option to choose which rows or columns to include in the table, or to split tables in a different direction than the one present in interface. Here is the list of all settings that can be used for table placeholders.

Placeholders do not need to be written by the users. They can be generated through the interface, using the Copy reporting placeholder () button which can be found next to every plot and results table. Clicking on this button will display the corresponding placeholder in a pop-up window. The displayed placeholder can then be copied to a template file and will be replaced by the table or plot, exactly as they are shown in the interface, with all stratification options and display settings applied.

Let's take a look at how "Copy reporting placeholder" buttons work on a specific example. If we load the demo project `project_censoring.pkx`, go to the Observed data plot and click on the Copy reporting placeholder button above the plot, a pop-up window will appear containing the placeholder for the plot, which can then be used in a report template to generate the plot that looks exactly like the plot currently shown in the interface. As you can see on the screenshot below, the placeholder contains information about plot type, plot size, caption and axes labels.

If we now close the pop-up, enable legend and open the pop-up again, the placeholder will contain the enabled legend setting and, if we put the placeholder in a report template, the generated plot will have a legend present in its corner, as shown in the screenshot on the right.

Figure 1: Observed data

If we would like our report to have the Observed data plot stratified by a categorical covariate, SEX, we can stratify the plot in the interface and click on the Copy reporting placeholder button again to generate a placeholder for this plot, as shown on the images below. You can notice that the generated placeholder now contains settings stratification and layout, which control stratification and plot layout.

Figure 1: Observed data

There are several options present inside the “Placeholder for Report Template” pop-up:

1. **indent** – determines number of spaces used for indentation of settings in the placeholder,
2. **flow level** – determines the compactness of placeholders, i.e how often we start a new line (lower the number, more compact the placeholder will be),
3. **dimensions units** – gives the ability to choose if width and height will be in cm or inches,
4. **lock aspect ratio** – if on, changing width or height will change the other dimension to keep the aspect ratio present on the screen.

It is possible to edit placeholders directly inside the pop-up. Clicking on the **Preview** button will generate and open a Word document containing a plot or a table described with the placeholder. This option is especially useful when a user manually modifies placeholders, to check if the syntax and the behavior are correct.

Copy to clipboard button will copy the placeholder with the <lixoftPLH> tag, ready to be pasted to the custom Word template.

8.1.3.2 Using areTaskResultsAvailable

Besides placeholders, templates can include the `areTaskResultsAvailable` tag, which can be used to display part of the template conditionally in the report.

For example, if a template contains the text:

```
<? areTaskResultsAvailable(likelihood) ?>  
Show this if likelihood estimation has been run  
</?>
```

The text “Show this if likelihood estimation has been run” will be present in the generated report, only if results of the likelihood task are available, otherwise the tags and the text will not be present in the generated report. Besides text, it is possible to include placeholders inside the `areTaskResultsAvailable` tag. The syntax of `areTaskResultsAvailable` tag is `areTaskResultsAvailable(task, method)`, with the method argument being optional. Tasks that can be used inside the parentheses are:

- `populationParameters`,
- `individualParameters` (methods: `mode` and `mean`),
- `correlationMatrix` (methods: `stochasticApproximation` and `linearization`),
- `likelihood` (methods: `importanceSampling` and `linearization`).

It is also possible to show content when task results are not available by writing `!areTaskResultsAvailable`.

8.1.3.3 Example use of a custom template

Download custom template for Warfarin case study

Here is an example custom template to use with the warfarin project available in demo projects (Monolix Demos > 1.1.libraries of models > warfarinPK_project.mlxtran). This dataset is also the topic of a video explaining the typical workflow in Monolix here. The custom template includes table of contents for tables and figures, which get updated when generating the report.

8.1.4 Renamings

A section Reporting placeholder entry renamings in Preferences can be used to change words and phrases that will appear in generated reports by default. For example, if we give alias “Thetas” to the placeholder entry “fixedeffects”, the word “fixedeffects” in the population parameter table generated by the reporting feature will be replaced by the word “Thetas”.

In addition, it is possible to rename words found in generated tables, by specifying an argument renamings inside the placeholder. This allows users to change words present in the data set as well. For example, if an imported data set contains a column “Formulation” with values T (for the test drug) and R (for the reference drug), specifying the following inside a placeholder will replace all occurrences of word “T” inside the table with “test” and “R” with “reference”:

```
renamings:  
  T: test  
  R: reference
```

For categorical covariates, it is possible to specify both the covariate name and the covariate modality to be replaced, in order to avoid ambiguities if, for example, category “0” appears in several covariates. In addition, quotes can be used if spaces are needed within the springs:

```
renamings:  
  SEX#0: Male  
  SEX#1: Female  
  RACE#0: Caucasian  
  RACE#1: "African american"  
  RACE#2: Hispanic
```


Respecting the indentation before the modalities to replace and the space after the “:” is crucial to have the placeholder properly recognized.

8.1.5 Generating reports from the command line

It is possible to generate a report directly from R with the connector generateReport() or through the command line, without using the Monolix interface. This can be useful when running Monolix on a server.

 Note that reports generated via command line will not contain plots. This is a known limitation of the current implementation of the reporting feature.

To generate a report via command line, the executable **reportGenerator** can be called from the lib folder (typically \$HOME/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2023R1/lib/):

```
reportGenerator -p monolix_project_path
```

Multiple options can be provided to reportGenerator:

-?, -h, -help	Displays the help.
-p, -project <path>	Project file to load
-tpl, -template <path>	Template .docx file used as reporting base (if not provided a default report file is generated)
-onxt, -output-next-project <[true], false>	Generate report next to project
-op, -output-path <path>	Generated report file name (if output-next-project is true) or complete path (if output-next-project is false)
-tab, -tables-style <style>	Table style sheet applied on generated tables
-wt, -watermark-text <text>	Watermark text
-wff, -watermark-font-family <[Arial], ...>	Watermark font family
-wfs, -watermark-font-size <integer>	Watermark font size
-wc, -watermark-color <[255:0:0]>	Watermark color (RGB)
-wl, -watermark-layout <[horizontal], diagonal>	Watermark layout
-wst, -watermark-semi-transparent <[true], false>	Watermark semi-transparent

8.2 List of reporting keywords

This page provides a list of placeholders for project settings that can be used in report templates for Monolix projects.

Keyword	Description	Possible values
%SAEM_nbBurningIterations%	Number of iterations in the burn-in phase.	a number
%SAEM_nbExploratoryIterations%	If "exploratoryAutoStop" is set to FALSE, it is the number of iterations in the exploratory phase. Else, if "exploratoryAutoStop" is set to TRUE, it is the maximum of iterations in the exploratory phase.	a number
%SAEM_exploratoryAutoStop%	Whether exploratory autostop was used.	used / not used
%SAEM_exploratoryInterval%	Minimum number of iteration in the exploratory phase.	a number
%SAEM_nbSmoothingIterations%	If "smoothingAutoStop" is set to FALSE, it is the number of iterations in the smoothing phase. Else, if "smoothingAutoStop" is set to TRUE, it is the maximum of iterations in the smoothing phase.	a number
%SAEM_smoothingAutoStop%	Whether smoothing autostop was used.	used / not used
%SAEM_smoothingInterval%	Minimum number of iteration in the smoothing phase. Used only if "smoothingAutoStop" is TRUE.	a number
%SAEM_simulatedAnnealing%	Whether simulated annealing was used.	used / not used
%SAEM_decreasingRateResError%	Simulated annealing decreasing rate for the variance of the residual errors.	a number
%SAEM_decreasingRateIndividualParam%	Simulated annealing decreasing rate for the variance of the individual parameters.	a number

%SAEM_withoutVariabilityMethod%	Method for parameters without variability.	variability at first stage / decreasing variability / no variability
%CondDist_nbMaxIterations%	Maximum number of iterations for conditional distribution sampling.	a number
%CondDist_nbSimulatedParameters%	Number of samples from the conditional distribution per individual.	a number
%CondDist_intervalLength%	Interval length for MCMC convergence assessment.	a number
%CondDist_relIntervalWidth%	Relative interval width for MCMC convergence assessment.	a number
%EBEs_nbMaxIterations%	Maximum number of optimization iterations for EBEs task.	a number
%EBEs_optimizationTolerance%	Optimization tolerance for EBEs task.	a number
%SE_nbMaxIterations%	Maximum number of optimization iterations for Standard Errors task.	a number
%SE_nbMinIterations%	Minimum number of optimization iterations for Standard Errors task.	a number
%LL_nbFixedIterations%	Monte Carlo size for the LL task.	a number
%LL_degreesFreedom%	Degrees of freedom of the t-distribution.	5 (fixed) or 1, 2, 5, 10 (optimized)
%Global_seed%	Seed used in the project.	a number
%MCMC_transitionKernels%	Number of calls for each one of the three MCMC kernels.	number-number-number (e.g., 2-2-2)
%MCMC_acceptanceRatio%	Target acceptance ratio for MCMC.	a number
%MCMC_nbChains%	Computed number of chains if not automatically set.	a number
%MCMC_minIndivForChains%	Minimum number of individuals for chains if automatically set.	a number
%TotalNbSubjects%	Total number of subjects in the data set (all observation ids together).	a number

%TotalNbSubjectsOcc%	Total number of subjects-occasions in the dataset (all observation ids together).	a number
%AvgNbDosesPerSubject%	Average number of doses per subject (any administration id, any occasion, all observation ids).	a number
%TotalNbObservations%	Total number of observations in the data set.	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%AvgNbObservationsPerID%	Average number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%MinNbObservationsPerID%	Minimum number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%MaxNbObservationsPerID%	Maximum number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%PercentCensoredObservations%	Percentage of censored observations.	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%StructModelCode%	Mlxtran code for the structural model.	whole structural model file content, as shown in the Structural model tab
%reportGenerationDateTime(yyyy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss)%	Report generation date and time. Part of yyyy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss can be removed or reordered.	yyyy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss
%system%	Operating system on which report was generated.	Linux, macOS, Windows
%version%	Version of Monolix with which report was generated.	2023R1
%project_fileName%	File name of the project (without path).	Example: NCA_run.pkx
%project_filePath%	File path of the project.	Example: C:/Users/user/lixoft/monolix/monolix2024R1/demos/1.creating_and_using_models/1.1.libraries_of_models/theophylline_project.mlxtran
%data_fileName%	File name of the data set (without path).	Example: data.csv

8.3 List of plot settings

This page describes all the settings that can be used in plot placeholders and are not editable by changing settings in the interface. All of them are optional (default values are described in the Default column).

Setting	Group	Default	Possible values	Description	Example
widthCm	-	16	positive numbers	Width of the plot in the report document in centimetres.	widthCm: 16
widthInches	-	6.3	positive numbers	Width of the plot in the report document in inches.	widthInches: 6.3
heightCm	-	11.1	positive numbers	Height of the plot in the report document in centimetres.	heightCm: 11.09
heightInches	-	4.37	positive numbers	Height of the plot in the report document in inches.	heightInches: 4.37
zoom	-	100	positive numbers	Larger values will increase the label font sizes and margins.	zoom: 80
caption	-	no caption	a phrase	Caption that will appear next to the plot.	caption: Individual fits
captionAbove	-	false	true, false	If true, caption will be positioned above the plot. If false, caption will be positioned below the plot.	captionAbove: true
legendPosition	settings	ne	n, ne, e, se, s, sw, w, nw	Position of the legend, based on abbreviations of compass points.	legendPosition: sw

For all other settings, select the settings of your plot in the GUI and then click the “copy placeholder” button to see the corresponding placeholder.

8.4 List of table settings

The following page describes all the settings that can be used in table placeholders in reporting templates. Placeholders for tables can include four different groups of settings. These are:

- “**data**” (required) – containing settings about table content, such as type of the table, and rows and columns that the table will contain,
- “**display**” (optional) – containing information about table display (e.g., number of significant digits to which the values in the table should be rounded, table direction, style, ...),
- “**renamings**” (optional) – containing various words present in the data set or Monolix that should be reworded in the table.

Settings inside these groups of settings need to be indented or put inside curly brackets. It is crucial to respect the indentation rules and the space after the “:” for the placeholder to be properly interpreted.

8.4.1 Data

Data settings define the type of the table that will be generated, as well as rows and columns that the table will contain. Here is the list of all settings of the data group of settings, along with their descriptions:

Setting	Table	Required	Possible values	Description
task	All	yes	populationParameters, individualParameters, correlationMatrix, likelihood	Task of which the table represents the results.
table	Likelihood and SE tables	no	Likelihood: criteria/ samplingInformation SE: matrix/eigenvalues	Table type. If empty, criteria or matrix table will be generated, depending on the task.
methods	Population parameters and likelihood	no (default: all)	Population parameters: linearization, stochasticApproximation, all Likelihood: linearization, importanceSampling, all	Value for population parameters is used for the SE part of the table.
method	Individual parameters and SE	yes	Individual parameters: mode, mean SE: linearization, stochasticApproximation	Method for reported values.

metrics	Population parameters table	no	SE, RSE, CV, SHRINKAGE, all	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Individual parameters table	no	ID, MIN, Q1, MEDIAN, Q3, MAX, SHRINKAGE, all	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	SE tables	no	Matrix table: RSE Eigenvalues table: MIN, MAX, Ratio, all	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Likelihood tables	no	Criteria table: OFV, AIC, BIC, BICc, all	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
excludedMetrics	All	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for metrics (except "all").	Metrics that will be excluded from the table. Handy when a user wants to specify metrics: "all" and exclude a few with excludedMetrics.
parameters	All except SE tables	no (default: all)	Model parameter names, or all.	Parameters that will be included in the table.
excludedParameters	All except SE tables	no (default: none)	Model parameter names, or all.	Parameters that will be excluded from the table.
ids	Individual parameters	no (default: all)	One or several of IDs present in the dataset, or "all".	IDs of subjects whose parameters should be shown in the table. The summary statistics will be calculated on all individuals, not just ones shown in the table. If not present, default is "all".

excludedIds	Individual parameters	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for ids, excluding "all".	IDs of subjects whose parameters should be excluded from the table. The summary statistics will be calculated on all individuals, not just ones shown in the table.
nbOccDisplayed	Individual parameters	no (default: -1 meaning all)	-1 or an integer	-1 means all occasion levels are displayed. 0 mean none of the occasion levels are displayed. 1 means only the first occasion level is displayed, etc.
covariates	Individual parameters	no (default: all)	One or more of covariates present in the data set, or "all".	Which covariates to include in the table.
covariatesAfterParameters	Individual parameters	no (default: true)	true, false	If covariates should be shown after parameters in the table.
types	Population parameters table	no (default: all)	One or more of: fixedEffects, stDev, correlations, error, all	Which types of parameters should be included in the table (fixed effects, standard deviations of random effects, correlations, error model parameters).

8.4.2 Display

Display group of settings defines how the information in the tables will be displayed. Here is the list of all settings for the display group of settings:

Setting	Table	Required	Possible values	Description	Example(s)
style	All	no (default: selected in Generate report pop-up)	Name of table styles present in the template document.	Microsoft Word document template style to apply to the table. This setting overrides the setting in the Generate report pop-up.	style: "Medium Grid 1 – Accent 1"
metricsDirection	All	no (default: vertical)	vertical, horizontal	Direction of metrics.	metricsDirection: horizontal

significantDigits	All	no (default: taken from Preferences)	positive integers	Number of significant digits values in the table will be rounded to.	significantDigits: 3
trailingZeros	All	no (default: taken from Preferences)	true, false	If trailing zeros should be shown in the tables.	trailingZeros: true
fitToContent	All	no (default: true)	true, false	If true, width of the table will be equal to the width of content, otherwise width of the table will be equal to the width of the page.	fitToContent: false
caption	All	no (default: no caption)	a phrase inside quotation marks	Caption that will appear next to the table.	caption: "EBEs"
captionAbove	All	no (default: false)	true, false	If true, caption will be positioned above the table. If false, caption will be positioned below the table.	captionAbove: true
fontSize	All	no (default: 12)	a number	Font size of the table content (will not be applied to the caption).	fontSize: 10
colored	SE matrix table	no (default: true)	true, false	If values should be color-coded.	colored: false

8.4.3 Renamings

Renamings setting can be provided to the placeholder to replace certain words or expressions that will appear in the table with a user-defined word or expression. We will explain the usage of renamings setting on a concrete example.

Let's take a look at the demo project `iov1_project.mlxtran`. Let's say we want to put a table of EBEs in the report, with renaming of the occasion column header.

A generated placeholder for the EBEs table, with its default settings, is shown below, including the table it generates.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: individualParameters
  method: mode
  metrics: [ID]
  parameters: all
  covariates: all
  covariatesAfterParameters: true
display:
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
</lixoftPLH>

```

ID	OCC	ka	V	CI	SEX	TREAT
1	1	1.6102	0.443	0.03353	M	A
1	2	1.6102	0.3498	0.03353	M	B
2	1	1.4346	0.4941	0.02389	M	A
2	2	1.4346	0.4018	0.02389	M	B
3	1	1.8029	0.5139	0.03806	M	A
3	2	1.8029	0.4048	0.03806	M	B
4	1	0.9828	0.4857	0.03621	M	A
4	2	0.9828	0.3875	0.03621	M	B
5	1	1.8905	0.5514	0.03684	M	A
5	2	1.8905	0.4388	0.03684	M	B
6	1	1.3289	0.4653	0.03175	M	A
6	2	1.3289	0.3623	0.03175	M	B
7	1	1.9682	0.3904	0.04016	M	B
7	2	1.9682	0.509	0.04016	M	A

Let's say we would like to hide some of the columns (SEX) and rename some of the expressions in the table. For example, it would be convenient to rename "OCC" to "Period". We can then modify the placeholder to look like the one on the left and it will generate the table on the right.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: individualParameters
  method: mode
  metrics: [ID]
  parameters: all
  excludedCovariates: SEX
  covariatesAfterParameters: true
display:
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
renamings:
  OCC: "Period"
</lixoftPLH>

```

ID	Period	ka	V	CI	TREAT
1	1	1.6102	0.443	0.03353	A
1	2	1.6102	0.3498	0.03353	B
2	1	1.4346	0.4941	0.02389	A
2	2	1.4346	0.4018	0.02389	B
3	1	1.8029	0.5139	0.03806	A
3	2	1.8029	0.4048	0.03806	B
4	1	0.9828	0.4857	0.03621	A
4	2	0.9828	0.3875	0.03621	B
5	1	1.8905	0.5514	0.03684	A
5	2	1.8905	0.4388	0.03684	B
6	1	1.3289	0.4653	0.03175	A
6	2	1.3289	0.3623	0.03175	B
7	1	1.9682	0.3904	0.04016	B
7	2	1.9682	0.509	0.04016	A

9 Submissions and Reproducibility

Monolix is used for regulatory submissions (including the FDA and the EMA) of population PK and PK/PD analyses. The summary of elements needed for submission can be found in [Submission of Monolix analysis to regulatory agencies](#).

MonolixSuite applications ensure full reproducibility and consistency of analysis results.

9.1 Submission of Monolix analysis to regulatory agencies

Monolix is used for **regulatory submissions (including the FDA and the EMA)** of population PK and PK/PD analyses. Monolix analyses for first in human dose estimation, dose-finding studies and registration studies have been routinely and successfully submitted to the FDA, EMA and other agencies. The FDA and the EMA do have access to Monolix and the modelling experts to understand, review and run Monolix. In addition, regulators are also taking part in publishing research articles with Monolix.

9.1.1 Files to include for submissions

Regulatory guidelines provide only little information on the required electronic files for submission. Based on exchanges with regulatory agencies and confirmed through past regulatory submissions using Monolix, the following listed files in Table 1 and 2 are required for a Monolix analysis submission package.

Table 1 lists all files needed to run Monolix and reproduce the results and diagnostic plots. Attention must be paid to use relative file path definitions (Settings > Preferences > Use relative path) to facilitate the project transfer from one computer system to another. It is also possible to create a .zip containing all requires input files, as well as all results with Export > Share project. **Table 2** lists the files containing the run results. **Table 3** lists the files that are needed to reload project results in Monolix.

A Monolix run will automatically produce a large number of additional files. However, the files listed in Table 1 and Table 2 are sufficient to entirely reproduce the results and share the main findings. Note that all files are in a human readable format. Thus, the information contained in these files can also be included into the appendices of the report creating one single document that contains everything to reproduce the results.

All MonolixSuite file types are accepted by the FDA and are listed in the "Specifications for File Format Types Using eCTD Specifications".

Table 1 Monolix files required for reproducibility of results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
Dataset file	Always	Input dataset	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat or .xpt
Additional columns file	If "additional columns" in data formatting module was used	Additional columns appended to the dataset	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat or .xpt
Monolix project file (.mlxtran)	Always	Path to dataset, dataset settings (column tagging, filters, etc), path to structural model, statistical model, algorithm settings, estimation tasks	.mlxtran
Structural model file	If not using a model from the libraries	Structural model in mlxtran syntax	.txt
Plot properties (.mlxproperties)	Always (except if file not present because only default settings)	Plot stratify, settings and preferences	.mlxproperties
Model building configuration file	If model building (covariate search) has been run via the command line	Covariate search method, settings and relationships to test	.txt
Conv. assessment configuration file	If convergence assessment has been run via the command line	Convergence assessment settings and estimation tasks to run	.txt
Bootstrap configuration file	If bootstrap has been run via the command line	Bootstrap settings	.txt

Table 2 Monolix files containing the key results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
summary.txt	Always	Results of population parameter, EBEs, conditional distribution, standard errors and likelihood tasks. Number of iterations and dataset recap (number of individuals, observations and doses).	.txt
populationParameters.txt	Always	Population parameters and standard errors with 15 digits	.txt

ModelBuilding/ modelBuilding.txt	If model building (covariate search) has been run	Overview of all tested models, their likelihood and BICc	.txt
Bootstrap/ populationSummary.txt	If bootstrap has been run	Summary statistics of bootstrap estimates	.txt
Assessment/ assessment.txt	If convergence assessment has been run	Parameter estimate of each assessment run	.txt

Table 3 Minimal set of Monolix files required to reload the results without rerunning the project (if model building, bootstrap, CA were not run)

File	When is it needed	File extension
Dataset file	Always	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat or .xpt
Structural model file	If not using a model from the libraries	.txt
Monolix project file (.mlxtran)	Always	.mlxtran
<result folder>/Internals/ <project>.mlxtran	Always	.mlxtran
<result folder>/Internals/ individualParameters.dat	Always	.dat
<result folder>/Internals/ individualPhiValues.dat	Always	.dat
<result folder>/Internals/ populationParameters.dat	Always	.dat
<result folder>/Internals/results.dat	Always	.dat
<result folder>/Internals/version.dat	Always	.dat
<result folder>/IndividualParameters/ simulatedIndividualParameters.txt	Always	.txt
<result folder>/IndividualParameters/ simulatedRandomEffects.txt	Always	.txt

9.1.2 Examples of submissions

This section lists examples of Clinical pharmacology reviews (FDA) and Assessment reports (EMA) explicitly mentioning the use of Monolix.

9.1.2.1 Submissions to the FDA using Monolix

- ZALTRAP (Aflibercept) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- CORLANOR (Ivabradine) - Amgen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- JEVTANA (Cabazitaxel) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- PONVORY (Ponesimod) - Janssen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- RYZNEUTA (Efbemalenograstim) - Evive Biotechnology Singapore - Integrated review ([link](#))
- EXBLIFEP (Cefepime and enmetazobactam) - Allecra Therapeutics - Integrated review ([link](#))

9.1.2.2 Submission to the EMA using Monolix

- OSELTAMIVIR (Tamiflu) - Roche - Assesment report ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000402/II/0110/G – EMA/CHMP/186699/2015)
- BOSENTAN (Tracleer) - Actelion - Assessment report ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000401/II/0066 – EMA/168487/2015)
- ISATUXIMAB (Sarclisa) - Sanofi - Assesment report ([link](#)) and Statistical analysis plan ([link](#))
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004977/II/0003 – EMA/CHMP/186236/2021)

9.1.3 Publications by the FDA using MonolixSuite

This section lists a few (non-exhaustive) publications by the FDA using MonolixSuite.

- “Plasma pharmacokinetics of ceftiofur metabolite desfurroylceftiofur cysteine disulfide in holstein steers: application of nonlinear mixed-effects modeling.”, *J Vet Pharmacol Ther* 2016 Apr;39(2):149-56, DOI: 10.1111/jvp.12245. *O. A. Chiesa, S. Feng, P. Kijak, E. A. Smith, H. Li and J. Qiu.*
- “Quantification of disease progression and dropout for Alzheimer’s disease.”, *Int. Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, Volume 51 – February (120 – 131),(Doi: 10.5414/CP201787). *D. William-Faltaos, Y. Chen, Y. Wang, J. Gobburu,, and H. Zhu.*
- “Estimation of Population Pharmacokinetic Parameters Using MLXTRAN Interpreter in MONOLIX 2.4”, *D. William Faltaos, Acop* 2009.

9.1.4 Regulatory guidelines

- EMA “Guideline on reporting the results of population pharmacokinetic analyses” (CHMP/EWP/185990/06): details what should be contained in a PK or PK/PD analysis report.
- FDA “Population pharmacokinetics – Guidance for industry” (2022): guidance on how to present the results of a population pharmacokinetic analysis and the information to be included. It also addresses “Electronic Files”.

- FDA “Exposure-Response Relationships – Study Design, Data Analysis, and Regulatory Applications – Guidance for Industry”. (2003)

9.2 Reproducibility of MonolixSuite results

9.2.1 Consistent reload of MonolixSuite projects and results

MonolixSuite applications ensure full reproducibility and consistency of analysis results. Here is how it works:

- **MonolixSuite applications save in each project all the elements necessary to run the analysis and replicate results from submitted analyses.** In practice, the path to the dataset file, the path to the model file (if custom model not from library), and all settings chosen in the Monolix GUI (tagging of the data set columns, initial parameter values, statistical model definition, task settings, seed of the random number generator, etc) are saved in the .mlxtran file. When an existing Monolix project is loaded and re-run, the results will be exactly the same as for the first run.
- In addition, **the results of the analysis are loaded in the interface from the results folder as valid results only if nothing has changed in the project since the time of the run.** In practice, when launching a run, the content of the mlxtran file is saved in the result folder. When a Monolix project is reloaded, the content of the loaded mlxtran file and the information in the result folder is compared. If they are the same, it means that the results present in the result folder are consistent with the loaded mlxtran and that therefore they are valid. If anything that could affect the results has changed (e.g initial values indicated in the loaded mlxtran file are different from the initial values used to generate the results), the results are not loaded and the warning message “Results have not been loaded due to an old inconsistent project” appears.
- Starting with the 2021R1 version, in Monolix and PKanalix a **fingerprint of the dataset** is also generated and checked when the project is loaded to ensure that not only the path to the data set file but also the content of the dataset has not been modified.
- Plot settings are saved in a different file (not the .mlxtran file) and do not impact the reloading of the results.

Rerunning a project with the same MonolixSuite version and the same OS (because random number generators are different in Windows, Linux and Mac) yields the exact same results if nothing has changed in the project. The software version used to generate the results is displayed in the file summary.txt in the results folder.

9.2.2 History of runs

In addition, in Monolix and PKanalix there is a timestamping option in the Preferences of the software called “Save History”. When it is enabled, the project and its results is saved in the results folder after each run, in a subfolder named “History”, thus making sure that previous runs are not lost even if they have been overwritten by a new run.

Below is an example of “History” subfolder in which 3 runs have been saved. Each subfolder named with the time of the run contains the project and its results as they were at the time of the run.

10 FAQ

10.1 Frequently asked questions

We list here the questions regarding the use of Monolix when everything runs fine. If you have an issue with download, installation, run and display, please check Frequent installation issues.

If you think there is a bug in one of the MonolixSuite apps, please check if it is already in our List of known bugs, and otherwise write us at support@lixoft.com.

10.1.1 Regulatory

- **What is needed for a regulatory submission using Monolix?** Monolix is used for regulatory submissions (including the FDA and the EMA) of population PK and PK/PD analyses. The summary of elements needed for submission can be found [here](#).
- **How to cite Monolix, Simulx or PKanalix?** Please reference each application as here (adjusting to the version you used):

```
Monolix 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11401936  
Simulx 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11402004  
PKanalix 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11401684
```

10.1.2 Running Monolix

- **On what operating systems does Monolix run?** MonolixSuite runs on Windows, Linux and MacOS platform. The requirements for each platform can be found on our [download page](#).
- **Is it possible to run Monolix using a simple command line?** Yes, see [here](#). In addition, there is a complete R API providing the full flexibility on running and modifying a Monolix project.
- **When trying to re-open a project, I get an error "Parse error in (file location), line XX: Expected STRING, but the actual syntax is a TREE_LIST."** This happens when trying to open with version 2023 a Monolix project saved with version 2024. The mlxtran file saved in version 2024 contains syntax elements that are new and not known by the 2023 version.

10.1.3 Initialization

- **How to initialize my parameters?** There are several ways to initialize your parameters and visualize the impact. See [here](#) the different possibilities.

10.1.4 Results

- **Can I define myself the result folder?** By default, the result folder corresponds to the project name. However, you can define it by yourself. See here to see how to define it on the user interface.
- **What result files are generated by Monolix?** Monolix proposes a lot of different output files depending on the tasks done by the user. Here is a complete listing of the files along with the condition for creation. See here for more information.
- **Can I replot the plots using another plotting software?** Yes, if you go to the menu Export and click on "Export charts data", all the data needed to reproduce the plots are stored in text files. See here for the description of all the files generated along with the plots.
- **When I open a project, my results are not loaded (message "Results have not been loaded due to an old inconsistent project"). Why?** When loading a project, Monolix checks that the project (i.e all the information saved in the .mlxtran file) being loaded and the project that has been used to generate the results are the same. If not, the error message is shown. For instance if one runs a project, then do "use last estimates", save and try to reload the project, the saved project has the "last estimates" as initial values which are different from the initial values used to run and generate the results. In that case the results will not be loaded because they are inconsistent with the loaded project. This is also explained with some examples in this video. It is possible to check what is preventing the load of the results by comparing the content of the .mlxtran file to load and the .mlxtran file located in the hidden .Internals folder in the result folder. To see the .Internals folder, the "show the hidden files/folders" must be activated on the machine.
- **Are the results of Monolix reproducible if I rerun the same analysis?** Yes, see here for more information.
- **The Observed data plot or VPC plot is empty or with non-appropriate axis limits**

The problem appears after having clicked "Export > Export charts settings as default" on a previous project where the y-axis limits were different and this is now applied as default. It is possible to delete the default setting corresponding to the axis limits in the following way:

 - Open the file C:/Users/<username>/lixoft/monolix/monolix2023R1/config/settings.default in a text editor
 - Delete the following lines:

```
VPCContinuous\yInterval= ...  
outputPlot\yInterval= ...
```

 - Save the file
 - Reopen your project
- **Where can I find the epsilon-shrinkage?** The epsilon shrinkage (for the residual error) is not calculated by Monolix. However, it is possible to calculate it using the result file predictions.txt with the following R code:

```
pred <- read.csv("predictions.txt")  
epsilon_shrinkage = 1 - sd(pred$indWRes_mode)
```

10.1.5 Tasks

- **How are the censored data handled?** The handling of censored data is described here.
- **How are the parameters without variability handled?** The different methods for parameters without variability are explained here.
- **What is the convergence indicator, displayed during SAEM?** Its meaning and function is explained here.
- **When estimating the log-likelihood via importance sampling, the log-likelihood does not seem to stabilize. What can I do?** The log-likelihood estimator obtained by importance sampling is biased by construction (see here for details). To reduce the bias, the conditional distribution $p\phi_i | y_i$
- should be known as well as possible. For this, run the “conditional distribution” task before estimating the log-likelihood.

10.1.6 Model definition

- **Is it possible to use time-varying covariates?** Yes, however the covariates relationship must be defined in the model instead of the GUI. See here how to do that.
- **Is it possible to define complex covariate-parameter relationships such as Michaelis-Menten for instance?** Yes, this can be done directly in the model file. See here how to do it.
- **Is it possible to define a categorical covariate effect on the standard deviation of a parameter?** Yes, this can be done directly in the model file. See here how to do it.
- **Is it possible to define mixture of structural models?** Yes, it may be necessary in some situations to introduce diversity into the structural models themselves using between-subject model mixtures (BSMM) or within-subject model mixtures (WSMM). The handling of mixture of structural models is defined here. Notice that in the case of a BSMM, the proportion \mathbf{p} between groups is a population parameter of the model to estimate. There is no inter-patient variability on \mathbf{p} : all the subjects have the same probability and a logit-normal distribution for \mathbf{p} must be used to constrain it to be between 0 and 1 without any variability.
- **Is it possible to define mixture of distributions?** Yes, the handling of mixture of structural models is defined here.
- **Can I set bounds on the population parameters for example between a and b?** It is not possible to set bounds for the estimated population parameters. However it is possible to define bounded parameter distributions, which as a consequence also bound the estimated fixed effect parameter. See here how to do it.
- **Can I put any distribution on the population parameters? Not directly through the interface.** Using the interface, you can only put normal, lognormal, logitnormal and probitnormal. However, you can set any transformation of your parameter in the EQUATION: part of the structural model and apply any transformation on it. See here how to do it.
- **Can I set a custom error model?** No, this is not possible. It may however be possible to transform the data such that the error model can be picked from the list. For an example with a model-based meta-analysis project, see here.

- **What are the units of estimated parameters? Can I define a scale factor?** The units of the estimated parameters depend on the units of the data set and are implicit. Check here to learn how to include a scale factor.

10.1.7 Tricks

- **How to compute AUC, time interval AUC, ... using Mlxtran in a Monolix project?** See here.

10.1.8 Export

- How to export to Datxplore, Mlxpore and Simulx?
- **I exported the chart settings as default, how can I come back to the default Monolix settings for all plots?** Delete the file <home>/lixoft/monolix/monolix2020R1/config/settings.default . In windows, the path to the <home> folder is C:\Users\

10.1.9 Reporting

- **How can I include plots and table from different Monolix projects into the same Word document?** It is currently not possible to include plots and tables coming from different Monolix runs into the same Word document in one step. You can add placeholders to an already generated report and use it as a template for another project, however we are aware that this is not a very convenient solution. If generating a single report for several projects is important for you, please let us know so that we take it into account for future versions.
- **The report I generated via command line or via R do not contain plots.** This is a known limitation of the current implementation of the reporting feature.

10.1.10 Legacy Documentation

- **Can I still access the documentation for versions prior to 2016?**

Please check Legacy Documentation.

11 Running through command line

11.1 Running different tasks through command line

11.1.1 Command and arguments

```
monolixSuiteInstallationFolder/bin/Monolix.sh --no-gui -p fullPathProjectName
```

(replace .sh into .bat for windows operating system)

Notice that the project name should be defined using a full path and not a relative path. The program options are:

- `--no-gui` : run without opening a window, mandatory in no-desktop environments.
- `-p, --project` : path to the project to run. It should be the absolute (not relative) path name of the project.
- `--thread, --number-of-threads` : number of threads to use for the run (integer)
- `--mode, --console-mode` : select the verbosity of the run information that will be log in console. It can be "none", "basic" (default value), or "complete".
- `--nosplash` : no splash screen. Only used when opening with GUI. When the option `-no-gui` is used, `nosplash` option is not read.
- `-o, --output-dir` : output directory
- `-t, --tool` : tool to launch. It can be "monolix" (default value), "modelBuilding", "convergenceAssessment" or "bootstrap"
- `--config` : config file with additional settings for model building, convergence assessment or bootstrap

Notes for Windows:

- The maximum number of arguments is 10. If more are needed, you can use the `monolix.exe` file in the `/lib` directory.
- The native terminals command prompt and PowerShell will not show an output while the project runs, whereas terminals for Windows with a bash shell will. A workaround to still get an output is to write the output to a text file (use `|tee console_output.txt` at the end of your command).

11.1.1.1 Example

```
monolix.bat --no-gui --mode none --thread 4 -p "C:\Users\celliere\lixoft\monolix\monolix2021R1\demos\1.creating_and_using_models\1.1.libraries_of_models\theophylline_project.mlxtran"
```

11.1.2 Exporting charts data

If the plots task is selected in the Monolix scenario, and if “Export charts data” is selected in Monolix preferences, the charts data are saved in the result folder. Generating the interactive plots requires to open the project in the GUI.

From the 2021 version on, the plots can also be generated as ggplot object using R functions from the `lixoftConnectors` R package.

11.1.3 Outputting to the console

With versions prior to 2023R1, the output is displayed in the console.

With versions 2023R1 and 2024R1, the output is not displayed in the console by default which may give the impression that nothing happens. In order to see the progress in the system console, it is possible to add `2>>&1 | findstr /r "/c:.*"` at the end of the call, for instance:

```
monolix.bat --no-gui --mode complete --thread 4 -p "C:\Users\celliere\lixoft\monolix\monolix2021R1\demos\1.creating_and_using_models\1.1.libraries_of_models\theophylline_project.mlxtran" 2>>&1 | findstr /r "/c:.*"
```

11.1.4 Running the covariate search (model building), convergence assessment or bootstrap

Notes:

- In Monolix versions prior to 2024R1, convergence assessment and bootstrap are not available from commandline.
- See [here for running the covariate search \(model building\) with MonolixSuite2023R1 and prior](#)

Users can choose the tool to run with `--tool` (see section above) and can provide all settings for the selected tool using `--config` followed by a configuration text file (for example saved as `.txt` or `.config`).

Settings for different tools can be included in a single config file, as they are separated in different blocks: `[modelBuilding]`, `[assessment]` and `[bootstrap]`. Below we show the config file template for the different tools.

If a setting is not specified, the default setting as in the GUI is used, unless the tool has already run in the project with custom settings: in that case the previous settings have been saved with the project and are reused.

11.1.4.1 Model building

Documentation for model building in Monolix

Template for model building settings:

```
[modelBuilding]
strategy=<COSSAC, SAMBA, covSAMBA, SCM>
lin=<true, false>
copyData=<true, false>
stoppingCriterion=<bicc, LRT>
LRTThreshold=<forward threshold>, <backward threshold>
correlationThreshold=<forward threshold>, <backward threshold>
locked\<parameter>\<covariate>=<out, in>
selectedParameters=<parameter>, <parameter>, ...
selectedCovariates=<covariate>, <covariate>, ...
```

The default settings correspond to:

```
[modelBuilding]
strategy=COSSAC
lin=true
copyData=false
stoppingCriterion=LRT
LRTThreshold=0.01, 0.01
correlationThreshold=0.3, 0.01
```

11.1.4.1.1 Example

- Covariate search on warfarinPK_project.mlxtran using SAMBA considering only the parameters V, Cl and Tlag and the covariates sex and wt, with a locked covariate effect of sex on Cl and no possible covariate effect of sex on V, without linearization, and using the BICc as the stopping criterion to add or remove a covariate effect. The correlation p-value thresholds for forward and backward selection is 0.001.

```
monolix.exe --no-gui -t modelBuilding -p warfarinPK_project.mlxtran --config  
warfarinPK_project_config.txt
```

With warfarinPK_project_config.txt containing:

```
[modelBuilding]  
strategy=covSAMBA  
lin=false  
copyData=true  
stoppingCriterion=bicc  
correlationThreshold=0.001, 0.001  
locked\V\sex=out  
locked\Cl\sex=in  
selectedParameters=V, Cl, Tlag  
selectedCovariates=sex, wt
```

11.1.4.2 Convergence assessment

Documentation for convergence assessment in Monolix

Template for convergence assessment settings:

```
[assessment]  
nbruns=<number of runs>  
SEandLL=<true, false>  
linearization=<true, false>  
parameter\<population parameter>\interval=<lower bound>, <upper bound>
```

The default settings correspond to:

```
[assessment]  
nbruns=5  
SEandLL=false  
linearization=false
```

11.1.4.2.1 Example

- Running convergence assessment on warfarinPK_project.mlxtran with 10 runs where standard errors and log-likelihood are also estimated using linearization, and where the initial values of V_{pop} are randomly chosen in the [3,4] interval while other parameters keep the same initial values as the original run.

```
monolix.exe --no-gui -t assessment -p warfarinPK_project.mlxtran --config  
warfarinPK_project_config.txt
```

With warfarinPK_project_config.txt containing:

```
[assessment]  
nbruns=10  
SEandLL=true  
linearization=true  
parameter\V_pop\interval=3, 4
```

11.1.4.3 Bootstrap

Documentation for bootstrap in Monolix

Template for bootstrap settings:

```
[bootstrap]  
nbruns=<number of runs>  
runLikelihood=<true, false>  
runSE=<true, false>  
lin=<true, false>  
initialValues=<initial, final>  
sampling=<parametric, nonparametric>  
sampleSize=<number of subjects in sampled dataset>  
stratifiedResampling=<covariate>, <covariate>, ...  
confidenceInterval=<percentage level for confidence interval>  
saveBootResults=<true, false>  
saveBootData=<true, false>  
replaceFailedConv=<true, false>  
maxNbFailedRuns=<maximum number of runs with failed convergence that can be replaced>  
cens\<Observation name>\<left, right>=<limit of quantification for parametric  
sampling>  
cens\<Observation name>\<interval>=<first limit of quantification for parametric  
sampling>, <second limit of quantification for parametric sampling>
```

The default settings correspond to:

```
[bootstrap]  
nbruns=200  
runLikelihood=false  
runSE=false  
lin=false  
initialValues=initial
```

```
sampling=nonparametric
sampleSize=<same number of subjects as original dataset>
confidenceInterval=95
saveBootResults=false
saveBootData=false
replaceFailedConv=false
maxNbFailedRuns=20
```

11.1.4.3.1 Examples

- Running non-parametric bootstrap on warfarinPK_project.mlxtran with 500 runs, with stratified resampling by sex (ie all sampled datasets have the same proportions of subjects in sex categories as in the original dataset). Each run uses the final estimates from the original run as initial estimates for SAEM, and standard errors and log-likelihood are also estimated using linearization.

```
monolix.exe --no-gui -t bootstrap -p warfarinPK_project.mlxtran --config
warfarinPK_project_config.txt
```

With warfarinPK_project_config.txt containing:

```
[bootstrap]
nbruns=500
sampling=parametric
runLikelihood=true
runSE=true
lin=true
initialValues=final
stratifiedResampling=sex
saveBootData=true
```

- Running parametric bootstrap on censoring1_project.mlxtran with 1000 runs, where all simulated Y observations below 4 in the sampled datasets are set as censored with LLOQ=4, and each sampled dataset is saved with the bootstrap run.

```
monolix.exe --no-gui -t bootstrap-p censoring1_project.mlxtran --config
censoring1_project_config.txt
```

With censoring1_project_config.txt containing:

```
[bootstrap]
```

```
nbruns=1000  
sampling=parametric  
cens\CONC\left=4  
saveBootData=true
```

11.1.5 Running covariate search (model building) with MonolixSuite2023R1 and prior

In versions of Monolix prior to 2023R1, there is no `-config` option to give a config file with model building settings. Instead, the following options can be used:

- `-s, --strategy` : select the model building algorithm. It can be "cossac" (default value), "samba", "covSamba" or "scm".
- `-c, --stoppingCriterion` : Select the stopping criterion of model building. It can be "bic" or "lrt" (default value).
- `-a, --LRTThresholdUp` : p-value threshold for the LRT in backward (default 0.01)
- `-r, --LRTThresholdLower` : p-value threshold for the LRT in forward (default 0.01 for cossac and 0.05 for scm)
- `--lin, --useLinearization` : use linearization if possible. "true" (default value) or "false".

11.1.5.1 Examples

```
monolix.bat --no-gui -t modelBuilding -s cossac -a 0.06 -r 0.001 --lin false -p "C:  
\Users\celliere\lixoft\monolix\monolix2021R1\demos\1.creating_and_using_models\1.1.li  
braries_of_models\theophylline_project.mlxtran"
```

```
monolix.bat --no-gui -t modelBuilding -s scm -c bic -p "C:  
\Users\celliere\lixoft\monolix\monolix2021R1\demos\1.creating_and_using_models\1.1.li  
braries_of_models\theophylline_project.mlxtran"
```

```
monolix.bat --no-gui -t modelBuilding -s covSamba -p "C:  
\Users\celliere\lixoft\monolix\monolix2021R1\demos\1.creating_and_using_models\1.1.li  
braries_of_models\theophylline_project.mlxtran"
```

From the 2021 version on, the settings of the model building are saved and reloaded. It is thus possible to do the following to run the model building (covariate search) with more custom settings than provided with the command line arguments, for instance regarding which parameter-covariate relationship to test:

- with the GUI, setup the model building settings you need

- launch the model building run and click on the “stop” button immediately. The model building setting are saved in the monolix result folder.
- launch the model building in command line using:

```
monolix.bat --no-gui -t modelBuilding -p yourProject
```

Note that:

- the results folder of the monolix run needs to be present for the model building setting to load and be used by the run in command line.
- this method does not work with distributed calculation using openMPI.

11.2 Parallelization over multiple nodes of a cluster

11.2.1 Running distributed Monolix on a cluster

To distribute calculations over multiple nodes, a special Monolix executable needs to be used. This executable, named **distMonolix**, comes with the installation of the Linux version of MonolixSuite. A separate **cluster license** is available and needs to be obtained in order to use distMonolix. All settings on [this](#) page can also be used with distMonolix on a cluster.

11.2.1.1 Monolix installation

To run MonolixSuite on a cluster, each cluster node must have access to the MonolixSuite directory and to the user home directory. Thus, there are two possibilities.

1. MonolixSuite is installed on each node.
2. MonolixSuite installation is shared. MonolixSuite is installed on a master server. Each cluster node accesses to MonolixSuite through a shared directory (via CIFS, Network drive, NFS, ...).

11.2.1.2 License management

On a cluster, we are managing the usage of our applications with the license management system described here.

The license management server is on a physical machine and manage the application through its license file. The associated license file has to be put in the folder {MonolixSuite install path}/config/system/access (and also {MonolixSuite install path}/bin/Monolix_mcr/runtime/config/system/access for MonolixSuite2016R1). So either on all nodes in the installation case 1, or only on the master server in the configuration 2.

11.2.1.3 Running Monolix on a single node

If a Monolix run is performed on a single node, it is possible to run Monolix using its executable in the lib folder (typically `$HOME/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1/lib/`):

```
monolix --no-gui -p mlxtran_project_path
```

where `mlxtran_project_path` is a Monolix project with a `.mlxtran` extension.

11.2.1.4 Running Monolix on multiple nodes using MPI

To run Monolix on multiple nodes, OpenMPI needs to be installed on all nodes. To run using MPI directly using the `distMonolix` executable in the lib folder (typically `$HOME/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1/lib/`), you can use this command (this command will distribute Monolix over 4 nodes listed in `hostfile.txt`):

```
mpirun -n 4 -hostfile hostfile.txt distMonolix -p mlxtran_project_path
```

Arguments that can be provided to `distMonolix` are the same ones as with Monolix. This includes `--tool` to select a multi-run task (model building, convergence assessment, bootstrap) and `--config` to provide settings for this task.

11.2.1.4.1 MPI troubleshooting

Different versions of distributed Monolix were built using different versions of Open MPI. If a more recent version was installed on the cluster, the following error may appear when trying to run distributed Monolix:

```
distMonolix: error while loading shared libraries: libmpi_cxx.so.YY: cannot open shared object file: No such file or directory
```

To resolve the error, you have to create a symbolic link from your installation:

- from your installation of `libmpi.so` (usually in `/usr/lib64/openmpi/lib/libmpi.so.XX`) to `libmpi.so.YY` (in the MonolixSuite lib folder):

```
sudo ln -s your_installation_of_openmpi/lib/libmpi.so.XX  
installation_of_MonolixSuiteXXXX/lib/libmpi.so.YY
```

- from your installation of `libmpi_cxx.so` (usually in `/usr/lib64/openmpi/lib/libmpi_cxx.so.XX`) to `libmpi_cxx.so.YY` (in the MonolixSuite lib folder):

```
sudo ln -s your_installation_of_openmpi/lib/libmpi_cxx.so.XX
installation_of_MonolixSuiteXXXX/lib/libmpi_cxx.so.YY
```

11.2.1.5 Distributed calculation

How the distribution is done differs between different tasks:

- in MCMC (SAEM, Fisher by Stochastic Approximation, Conditional Distribution): pools of ids are created and distributed by process,
- in Importance Sampling: the same is done with simulation pools,
- in multi-run tasks (bootstrap, convergence assessment): each run is distributed over all processes.

11.2.1.6 Using distributed Monolix with a scheduler

Usually, runs on clusters are scheduled using a job scheduling application (e.g., Torque, PBS, GridEngine, Slurm, LSF, ...). After submitting a Monolix run with the job scheduling application, the run will wait in a queue until enough of the resources become available. When the resources become available, the run will be performed.

Generally, a task is submitted to the cluster using a specific command, e.g. `qsub` in the case of Torque, PBS or GridEngine (former SGE). This command runs a script, provided as parameter, on a cluster node chosen by the cluster scheduler.

11.2.1.6.1 Scheduling Monolix runs with Slurm Workload Manager

When using Slurm Workload Manager on a cluster, the runs are submitted using the `sbatch` command. With the command, a path to a batch script needs to be provided. A simple example of a batch script that can be used to run Monolix is shown here (note that there is no need to provide the number of nodes directly to the `mpirun` command in the script, since Slurm will automatically pass that information to Open MPI):

```
#!/bin/bash
mpirun ~/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1/lib/distMonolix -p $1
```

If the script is saved as `run.sh`, we can schedule a Monolix project to run with the following command (the command will distribute the run across 16 tasks on 4 nodes):

```
$ sbatch -n 16 --nodes 4 run.sh mlxtran_project_path
```

Additional arguments, such as time limit or job name, can be provided to the `sbatch` command either through the command line or through the batch script. All the available options are listed on this page.

Here is how the `run.sh` file should look like if we want to assign a job name through the file:

```
#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --job-name=monolixRun

mpirun ~/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1/lib/distMonolix -p $1
```

After submitting the job using the `sbatch` command, we can use the command `squeue` check the status of a run:

```
$ sbatch -n 16 --nodes 4 run.sh mlxtran_project_path
$ squeue
```

JOBID	PARTITION	NAME	USER	ST	TIME	NODES	NODELIST(REASON)
86	debug	monolixR	lixoft	R	0:02	4	slave[1-4]

We can cancel the run using `scancel` and specifying the job ID:

```
$ scancel 86
```

For further assistance, contact us.

12 Legacy Documentation

This page groups the legacy documentation of Lixoft products prior to release 2016R1.

12.1 Monolix methodology

- Monolix methodology: this document describes the main algorithms for the tasks performed by Monolix.

12.2 Mlxtran syntax (for version prior to 2016R1)

For software prior 2016R1, all the software do not share the same model coding language, i.e. the same Mlxtran language reference. Here are the several links to see the model coding language for

- Model coding language for Monolix: for Monolix until Monolix 4.3.3
- Model coding language for Mlxplore: for Mlxplore until Mlxplore 1.1.1
- Model coding language for Simulx: for Simulx version until Simulx 1.1.0

12.3 Tutorial and libraries

- Mlxtran tutorial for Monolix 4.3: The following slidedeck provides a tutorial on how to easily describe simple and complex pharmacometric models, including PK, PK-PD and discrete data models, using the MLXTRAN language included in MONOLIX 4.3.
- Lixoft is providing model libraries to simplify the use of its software. The mathematical expressions of the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic models implemented in MonolixSuite can be found here: PKPDlibrary.

12.4 Legacy user guides

To get the associated user guide, please click on the associated link

Datxplore

- Datxplore v1.0.1: Datxplore user guide

Mlxplore

- Mlxplore v1.1.1: Mlxplore user guide

Monolix

- Monolix v4.3.3 user guide: Monolix433-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.3.2 user guide: Monolix432-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.3.1 user guide: Monolix431-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.3.0 user guide: Monolix430-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.2.2 user guide: Monolix422-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.2.1 user guide: Monolix421-doc.zip
- Monolix v4.2.0 user guide: Monolix420-doc.zip

12.5 Legacy video for Monolix 433

https://lixoft.com/filesToWebsite/Videos/demoV4f_1.avi